

IASTA National Aerosol Conference 2024

***December 17-20, 2024
Doon University, Dehradun***

**Conference
Proceedings of IASTA - 2024**

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PREFACE

Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital and Doon University, Dehradun, is hosting the National Aerosol Conference 2024, from 17-20 December 2024, under the flagship of the Indian Aerosol Science and Technology Association (IASTA). IASTA-2024 focuses on broad topics covering aerosol/air pollution climate effects, indoor air quality and human health impact, cloud-aerosol interactions, aerosol/air quality modeling, nuclear and radioactive aerosols, aerosols for medical applications, bioaerosols, air quality control, clean energy, and sustainability development, aerosol instruments. The aim of IASTA-2024 is to provide an excellent platform for young researchers, technocrats, and policymakers to exchange their knowledge/ideas. IASTA-2024 will allow participants to interact, collaborate, and contribute toward the growth of aerosol science and technology. The conference will also provide an opportunity for the industries to showcase their technologies, different products, and innovations in the field of aerosol and air pollution. The scientific and technical program of the IASTA-2024 conference includes keynote addresses, Plenary Lectures, Invited Talks, contributed papers, and posters (108 platforms, 48 lightning, and 150 posters), along with a technical exhibition of different products and systems related to aerosol research and technology and allied areas. The conference also includes panel discussions on the topic “Air Quality in Uttarakhand” and popular lectures.

On behalf of the IASTA, the technical program committee thanks all the invited speakers, panelists, authors of the contributed papers, and sponsors who have supported in finalising the scientific and technical programmes. The committee thank all the persons involved in bringing out the proceedings, well in time for IASTA 2024. We take this opportunity to wish all the delegates interactive and fruitful discussions during the conference.

(Technical Programme Committee)
IASTA 2024

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KEYNOTE TALK

AEROSOL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY: FROM A BRIEF HISTORY TO OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE FUTURE

PRATIM BISWAS

Dean, Engineering, Professor Chemical, Env and Materials Engr. & Atmospheric Science
University of Miami, Miami, FL 33146, USA

E-mail: pbiswas@miami.edu

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Science and Technology, historical perspective, enabling discipline, future directions for research

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol science and technology is a fascinating field of study, often referred to as an “enabling discipline” due to its own fundamentals that are applied to a variety of fields. The talk will provide a historical perspective of the field, starting from the modern era (~ 1600) to the current period. The emphasis will be on current developments in the field and the exciting areas in future education and research. I will try to focus on developments in the field of aerosol science and technology in India and end with my perspectives on potential impact areas for work in this field specific to India.

METHODS

The approach in this paper to review the history of aerosol science and technology and provide a perspective of some of the newer areas of application. A key highlight will be illustrating how the fundamental aspects have resulted in an enabling discipline with many application areas. The historical aspects are based on a review of the literature and a class taught in Aerosol Science and Engineering for the last 35 years (Biswas, 2015). The current and future perspectives are based on research supported by a number of federal agencies and industry (AAQRL, 2024).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The early modern era with the advent of Isaac Newton (circa late 1600s/early 1700) resulted in a formula to estimate the drag force. It was only ~ 200 years later with the development of fields such as fluid mechanics (Stokes et al), that a more robust estimation of the drag force could be estimated. Other developments focused on other transport mechanisms such as diffusion (~ 1827) followed by Einstein’s elegant with intuition derivation of the inter-molecular forces that resulted in robust formula for calculating diffusion coefficients. The latter part of the modern era (till today) can thus be divided into three major categories: a) the quantum age, b) the information age and c) the genetic age. All these three periods influence aerosol science and technology, and are influenced by this enabling field; that will be highlighted in the paper.

A simple description of particle formation and growth is illustrated in Figure 1, And, it is this fundamental understanding that allows us to not only understand phenomena, but design processes to control particle formation and growth that opens up a vista of different applications. While the physical aspects are illustrated, the rates of the various processes are impacted by the chemistry (composition) of the system, which itself maybe undergoing dynamic changes due to chemical reactions. It also must be stated that aerosols can be biological in nature (bacteria, viruses, protein fragments) and have innumerable applications when in the airborne states

Figure 1. Mechanistic understanding of particle formation and growth and its innumerable applications.

A brief review of the status of aerosol science and technology in the Indian context (Mishra, 2000) will also be discussed. While extensive work has been underway in aerosol science in India and by scientists of Indian origin, there is no compiled record of the same. From this brief review, suggestions for enhancement of the Indian Aerosol scientific community will be discussed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This presentation was undertaken with the support of the College of Engineering, the University of Miami start-up funds, and the Center for Aerosol Science and Technology (CAST).

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PLENARY TALKS

HEALTH IMPACT OF FINE AEROSOLS: A MULTIPARAMETRIC APPROACH

D. PARASKEVOPOULOU^{1,2}, I. TSIODRA¹, K. TAVERNARAKI¹, G. GRIVAS¹, I. M. VRETTOU², M. TSAGKARAKI¹, C. PARINOS³, E. LIAKAKOU¹, A. BOUGIATIOTI² AND N. MIHALOPOULOS^{1,2}

¹ECPL, Department of Chemistry, University of Crete, Heraklion, Greece

²Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, Palaia Penteli

³Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Oceanography, 19013 Anavyssos, Attiki, Greece

E-mail: [-nmihalo@noa.gr](mailto:nmihalo@noa.gr)

KEYWORDS: PAHs, ROS, OP, Fine Aerosols, Health

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) constitutes a mixture of various chemical components depending on the existing sources and ageing processes in the atmospheric environment. PM-induced oxidative stress is considered as a primal mechanism in the inception of adverse health effects. Furthermore, particulate Polycyclic aromatic compounds (PACs) have been reported for their potential carcinogenic and mutagenic properties. Thus, the association of Oxygenated – Polycyclic Aromatic hydrocarbons (OPAHs) with oxidative potential (OP) and oxidative stress-induced health outcomes is receiving increasing attention. The main objective of the work is to assess the potential health impact of aerosols over Greece, as a case study for other areas of the world, by characterizing their ROS activity, using a combination of field and laboratory measurements.

METHODS

The measurements were performed at several sites across Greece ranging from the capital (Athens, 3.6M inhabitants) and the second most important city of Greece (Thessaloniki, 1M), to small to medium size cities (Xanthi, Volos, Ioannina, Heraklion, Piraeus) as well as a regional background location (Finokalia, Crete, Greece). Ambient PM 2.5 particle samples were collected on quartz-fiber filters (Flex Tissuquartz, Pall Corporation, Port Washington, NY, USA) using high-volume samplers, during winter (December and January) and summer (June to August) months. The sampling duration at all sites was 24h. Filters were analyzed for all the main compounds (ions, OC/EC, trace metals, levoglucosan, BrC, WSOC) as well as for PAHs, OPAHs and reactive oxygen species (ROS) to assess their oxidative potential (OP).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The aims of this work were to report: i) measurements, for the first time - to our knowledge and on an annual basis of the activity of ROS of the fine fraction of aerosols in Athens, a well-characterized urban location, as well as in 3 other urban areas of Greece with different population, meteorology and sources with specific emphasis on traffic and biomass burning. ii) characterization of both water-soluble (DTT activity) and total activity of ROS using advanced analytical techniques. iii) combination of ROS measurements with corresponding aerosol chemical composition with emphasis on classes of compounds known from the literature to contribute to ROS activity, namely secondary inorganic ions, carbonaceous aerosols (OC, EC and BC), metals and brown carbon. Emphasis was given on PAHs and their oxo compounds such as kinones. iv) source attribution techniques to quantify the contribution of various sources to the measured oxidizing potential (OP).

Highest levels for both PM and DTT activity are found at sites which are highly impacted by biomass burning during winter. When correlating the aerosol fine levels (PM_{2.5}) with the DTT activity it can be seen that there is a correlation between these two only during winter. On the other hand during summer when regionally sources prevail no relation between PM and DTT activity occurs. Thus, the underlying hypothesis of linearity between endogenous variables (PM concentration of the sources) and exogenous variables (OP's) remains to be investigated and may be invalid. Figure 2 compares the sum of the 16 EPA and 6 PAHs proposed by the EU with BaP levels. It can be observed that the average concentration difference when considering the 16 EPA and the 6 EU proposed PAHs is almost 2-fold. Furthermore, the excellent correlation seen between the $\Sigma 16\text{PAHs}$ ($R^2=0.97$) and $\Sigma 6\text{EU}$ ($R^2 = 0.95$) PAHs with BaP demonstrates that by determining the levels of BaP a fair estimation of PAH sums can be provided across Greece but this is valid only during winter.

Figure 1. Correlation between DTT activity and particulate matter at all measurement sites.

Figure 2. Relation between the 16 EPA (high slope) and the 6 EU- proposed (low slope) PAHs with BaP.

CONCLUSIONS

Our results concerning ROS levels are the first not only in Greece but also in the southeastern Europe and can serve as reference for future studies. With our measurements, the role of biomass burning was highlighted both as a source of aerosols as well as a source of aerosol toxicity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge support by the Action “National Network on Climate Change and its Impacts (CLIMPACT)” implemented under the project “Infrastructure of national research networks in the fields of Precision Medicine, Quantum Technology and Climate Change”, funded by the Public Investment Program of Greece, Greek General Secretary of Research and Technology/Ministry of Development and Investments.

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AEROSOL RESEARCH IN SOUTH ASIA: QUESTIONS FOR THE NEXT DECADE

ARNICO K PANDAY
Former Member, National Planning Commission
Government of Nepal

E-mail: arnicopanday@gmail.com

Arnico Panday's plenary lecture will consist of three parts. The first part will provide a broad review of aerosol research in South Asia over the past decade, attempting to assess the current state of knowledge on a range of topics, including spatial and temporal patterns, health impacts, source apportionment, as well as connections to global and regional climate, winter fog, cryosphere and monsoon. The second part of the lecture will suggest priorities and research questions for the coming decade related to aerosols in the atmosphere over South Asia. The third part will discuss the broad changes that will be needed to successfully address these priorities. These include changes in the roles of institutions and scientists, changes in the education of science students, changes in funding and collaboration, as well as changes in politics and policy in a South Asia where aerosols don't recognize political borders.

INVITED TALKS

THE IMPACT OF AEROSOL PARTICLE-BORNE CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS AND THEIR INTERNAL/EXTERNAL MIXING STATE ON CLIMATE AND HEALTH AND HOW TO MEASURE THESE PARAMETERS

R. ZIMMERMANN^{1*}, J. PASSIG¹, E. ROSEWIG¹, M. IHALAINEN², L. ANDERS¹, A. HARTIKAINEN², O. SIPPULA², S. PELTOKORPI², A. BUCHHOLZ, L. HAO, A. VIRTANEN⁶, H. HAKIM¹, R. IRSIG³, S. EHLERT³, A. WALTE³, V. VAKKARI⁴, J. SCHADE⁵, T. ADAM⁵, H. HAKIM¹, H. CZECH¹

¹Joint Mass Spectrometry Centre, University of Rostock and Helmholtz Munich, Germany.

²University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland.

³Photonion GmbH, Schwerin, Germany.

⁴North-West University, Potchefstroom, South Africa.

⁵Universität der Bundeswehr, Germany.

(E-mail: ralf.zimmermann@uni-rostock.de)

INTRODUCTION

By emitting large amounts of CO₂, reactive trace gases and particulate matter (aerosols), wildfires and anthropogenic combustion emissions strongly affect air quality, human health and climate. Atmospheric aging and particle-gas phase distribution of these emissions are extremely complex and variable. Moreover, the photochemical changes are highly relevant to climate and health by determining the particle's optical- and radiative-effects, cloud condensation-activity and biological/toxic effects. To better understand the impact of wildfire emissions and of other pollution-sources like ship emissions it's very important to analyze the internal and external mixing-state of relevant components in the aerosol particle distribution (1).

METHOD

In classical on-line single particle mass spectrometry (SPMS), aerosol particles from ambient air are introduced directly by an aerodynamic-lens into the SPMS. Individual particle sizes and ion source-arrival times are determined laser-velocimetrically and intense UV-laser pulses are triggered to hit selected individual particles for laser desorption/ionization (LDI). Formed anions and cations from individual aerosol particles are detected in a bipolar time-of-flight MS setup. Beyond this, we recently introduced a multi-step laser ionization scheme in SPMS, exploiting on-the-fly IR-laser desorption and resonance ionization of transition metals (using 248 nm atomic iron transition) as well as of the toxic Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH, using Resonance Enhanced Multiphoton Ionization). This allows to detect efficiently the most important air trace-toxicants (PAH, transition metals) together with more abundant species (soot, minerals, ammonium sulphate etc.) on single particle-basis. Using this new resonant-ionization SPMS-method, metals and PAHs can be detected in real-time (2,4) at much lower quantities and less dependent from the matrix (e.g., sea salt, organics etc.) on particles, opening the avenue to detect the carcinogenic PAHs on single-particle basis. The new technology of field-deployable resonance-enhanced single particle mass spectrometry (2,3,4) thus is giving unsurpassed access to single particle chemical distribution-information.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The new approach has been applied e.g., to ambient air, ship or wildfire emissions, generating intriguing results. For example, we investigated ambient air (remote measurement site at Baltic Sea), revealing sources and carriers of PAHs. The results suggest to use the PAHs as molecular

markers to retrieve pollution sources and aerosol transformation-processes in complex environments. In addition to the contribution of local ship emissions also biomass burning- and industrial combustion-related particles were detected. Indeed, we also observed aerosol aging-processes via individual particle PAH-signatures. The mixing state analysis, however, depicts that the PAH burden is concentrated solely on a rather small fraction of particles (~1-2 %, external mixture). The impact of this finding on potential PM health effects is discussed. In a further larger study, smoke particles from wildfire simulation burns were investigated. Typical vegetation from e.g., the boreal forest and African savannah was used as model fuel and fresh and photochemically aged wildfire emissions were investigated. For climate- and health-relevant PAH we found high concentrations of the softwood combustion-marker retene in boreal forest burnings as well as its rapid degradation during aging. The toxic, larger unsubstituted PAHs show higher stability against photooxidation. Particles with the highest PAH-loads are observed in the long-range transported size mode even after prolonged aging, in accordance with the ambient air study (3). For the water-soluble components, we could show the time-resolved glyoxal/methylglyoxal-formation during photochemical chamber-aging. Interestingly, a non-uniform mixing of water-soluble glyoxal/methylglyoxal and non-polar PAH was observed (i.e., 2 classes with different chemical composition). Counterintuitively, atmospheric aging reduced cloud condensation nucleation-activity (CCN) of wildfire aerosol-particles. This is explainable by the observed sulphuration of KCl to the less hygroscopic K₂SO₄ during aging. The CCN-activity of the aerosols, however, has a large impact on the climate impact of wildfire emissions. A final application focuses on the particle emission from large diesel engines (ship engines). Ship emissions are highly relevant for climate (i.e., light absorbing and cloud formation activity) health. The impact of fuels and Sulphur abatement technology on particle concentration and composition is revealed and discussed.

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EXTREME AEROSOL PHENOMENA IN THE ERA OF CLIMATE CRISIS: DUST STORMS AND SEVERE WILDFIRES

D.G. KASKAOUTIS

Chemical Engineering Department, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani 50100, Greece

E-mail: dkaskaoutis@uowm.gr

INTRODUCTION

Dust-storms are considered natural hazards with deleterious effects on climate, human health, and marine and terrestrial ecosystems. Therefore, investigation of dust storms is very important in countries located in the global dust belt or directly affected by transported dust plumes. On the other hand, severe wildfires in areas close to large cities are an important challenge nowadays, with devastating consequences for ecosystems, infrastructure, and human health. This lecture focuses on the analysis of meteorological dynamics, ground measurements, and model simulations for an extreme dust event impacting NW India in June 2018 that had the characteristics of a density current. Strong near-surface winds in the monsoon-flow area caused dust emissions when advancing northward into the Thar desert, as they behave like a density current due to the difference in density between the cold and wet monsoon flow and the dry and warm air over the desert. Such dust storms exhibit a certain transportation pattern, on which the Himalayan Range and the northwesterly play an important role. Convective mixing during daytime favors the vertical uplift of dust to higher altitudes above the monsoon flow, but the towering Himalayas and the associated return northerly flow aloft play a blocking role, leading to dust accumulation at heights between 1 and 3 km. The prevailing northwesterly in the middle troposphere favors the eastward transport of the dust plumes along the Ganges valley. In addition, this lecture presents some results related to carbonaceous aerosols, atmospheric chemistry, and modulations in atmospheric composition over Athens caused by dense smoke plumes from nearby peri-urban forest fires that lasted for several days, following an intense Mediterranean heatwave in August 2021. Such phenomena are deleterious for human health due to very high concentrations of black carbon and several toxic organic compounds related to the combustion of infrastructure, rubbers, waste material, and industrial chemicals.

MODELLING AIR POLLUTION EXPOSURE USING GEOSPATIAL TECHNIQUES AND ITS APPLICATIONS IN INDIA

SAGNIK DEY

Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi, 110016.

Email: sagnik@cas.iitd.ac.in

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has been identified as the leading environmental health risk in India. Assessing exposure is the first step in air pollution epidemiology. The best way to estimate exposure is by measuring at a personal level using portable sensors. However, this is not feasible at the population scale, and hence, innovative methods are required to estimate population-scale exposure. In India, the most populous nation in the world, the ground-based monitoring network has expanded in more recent years, yet it is disproportionately distributed with a focus on urban centers. Most of the continuous air quality monitoring stations became operational after 2017-2018, limiting exposure analysis for a longer period. Manual stations sample twice a week and therefore, may not represent annual exposure.

We developed methods to derive air pollution exposure at a population scale using geospatial data. For exposure to particulate pollution, we used to satellite-derive columnar aerosol optical depth (AOD) data, while for gaseous pollutants, we used to satellite-derive columnar concentrations. Such retrievals are affected by the presence of clouds and other retrieval challenges. We first filled in missing AOD data using a support vector machine relying on predictor variables that vary spatially and temporally (e.g., meteorological predictors) and only spatially (e.g., other sociodemographic variables). We then converted AOD to surface PM_{2.5} at a 1-km² spatial scale using random forest and further scaled the instantaneous PM_{2.5} values to a 24-hour average based on a reanalysis-derived scaling factor. Machine learning methods have been finalized by undertaking sensitivity analysis. We found robust performance (R^2 of 0.92 and error less than 10%) of this product against ground-based measurements. We used a land use regression model to estimate surface NO₂ concentration.

RESULTS AND APPLICATIONS

Overlaying the PM_{2.5} and NO₂ concentrations with population distribution, we finally extracted ambient PM_{2.5} and NO₂ exposure statistics for India for more than two decades. We found that PM_{2.5} exposure would have been overestimated by 19.1% if the AOD sampling gaps were not filled in. The rising trend in PM_{2.5} exposure, reaching a peak around 2016-2017,

was found to show a sign of stabilization in more recent years. In the NCAP era, a reduction in overall exposure partially compensated the effect of the rising population and its aging to maintain the attributable mortality and morbidity burden at par.

Satellite-derived exposure data has been used in health impact assessment for both acute and chronic exposure, utilizing health data from the National Family Survey and the death registry. Disparity in exposure across demographic subgroups was assessed. Further, exposure to PM_{2.5} species and to multiple pollutants was assessed by merging satellite-derived information with chemical transport model simulations, and relative risks of a range of child and adult health outcomes were assessed. Analysis revealed that health risk would be underestimated if PM_{2.5} mass was used as an exposure metric, disregarding the composition.

CONCLUSION

Advancement in exposure modelling using geospatial techniques propelled epidemiology research in India and allowed the generation of scientific evidence, enabling health to be an integral part of the air quality management ecosystem.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank Clean Air Fund and Central Pollution Control Board, Govt. of India for financial support

BIOAEROSOL RESEARCH OVER INDIA: PAST, PRESENT, AND

MISSING LINK

SACHIN S. GUNTHE

CACS and IIT Madras

(E-mail: s.gunthe@civil.iitm.ac.in; s.gunthe@iitm.ac.in)

In India, bioaerosol research has garnered significant attention due to its implications for public health, agriculture, and climate. Past studies in the Indian context have focused on the identification, quantification, and characterization of bioaerosols, providing insights into their seasonal variations, distribution, and sources. These studies also highlighted the influence of bioaerosols on respiratory diseases, allergic reactions, and the potential dissemination of infectious agents. The status of bioaerosol research in India involves the integration of advanced analytical techniques and interdisciplinary approaches to gain a deeper understanding of the biological component of atmospheric aerosols. Real-time monitoring systems and molecular biology techniques are now employed to elucidate the complex interactions between bioaerosols and environmental factors. The future scope of bioaerosol research in India encompasses the development of predictive models for the effective management of air quality and public health. There is a growing need to establish nationwide bioaerosol monitoring networks like those for chemical pollutants. Cross-disciplinary partnerships are necessary to tackle the challenges posed by bioaerosols, addressing gaps in standardization, and integrating findings into policies for better environmental and health outcomes. Furthermore, the implications of climate change on bioaerosol dynamics present an additional area for future investigation. I will present the historical perspective of bioaerosol studies over India, studies my group is carrying out, and the potential future direction and need for collaborations for bioaerosol studies over India

NUCLEAR AEROSOL STUDIES FOR A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY FUTURE

B. K. SAPRA

Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

(E-mail: bsapra@barc.gov.in)

In recent years, there has been a global resurgence in the pursuit of nuclear energy as a key component for meeting future electricity demands. India's ambitious goal of achieving net-zero carbon emissions by 2070 presents a challenging prospect to the nuclear sector, particularly in expanding its power generation capacity. To address this, a wide range of academic, industrial, and policy initiatives are currently underway. Nuclear aerosol studies play a critical role in these efforts, ensuring the safety of nuclear reactors during operational and non-operational phases. This talk highlights the significant research in this field conducted in India over the past decade while also looking ahead to the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead. Accurate prediction of 'Source Term' has been a central focus of nuclear aerosol studies. Source term, which defines the amount and nature of radioactive material released from a nuclear reactor during a severe accident, depends on a deep understanding of various phenomenological factors. A key area in this pursuit is the behavior of single and mixed cesium and iodine compounds under both sub-saturation and super-saturation conditions. Any alteration in aerosol properties affects the residence time, ultimately influencing dry and wet deposition rates. To bridge laboratory research with field applications, the National Aerosol Facility (NAF) at IIT Kanpur and the High Temperature Aerosol Facility (HTAF) at IIT BHU have been established. These facilities have been instrumental in conducting numerous studies aimed at quantifying deposition fractions and characterizing aerosol properties. By refining the prediction of the source term and its impact on aerosol dynamics, these efforts contribute directly to enhancing the safety and reliability of India's nuclear energy sector. As we look to the future, these studies will play a vital role in ensuring that nuclear energy can meet growing demand while balancing the concerns of the environment and the industry.

ATTAINING CLOSURE BETWEEN EMISSIONS AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL POLLUTANTS FOR EFFECTIVE MITIGATION: INTEGRATING OBSERVATIONS AND SOURCE- RECEPTOR MODELLING APPROACHES

SHUBHA VERMA

Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur 721302,
West Bengal, India

Email: shubha@iitkgp.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Constrained Emissions, Anthropogenic Aerosol Pollutants, Desert Dust, Mitigation, Source-Receptor Modelling

The spatial and temporal distributions of combustion-derived anthropogenic aerosol species concentration over the Indian region are very heterogeneous in comparison to undifferentiated PM mass. While the heterogeneity in anthropogenic aerosol species distribution is influenced by the prevalence of region- and season-specific local combustion activities, PM also includes other species such as desert dust, which comes, in part, from long-range transport over most of the Indian subcontinent during the summer season and western India during the winter season. This heterogeneity leads to a contrast in population exposure to combustion-derived anthropogenic aerosol species compared to total PM mass. Also, the spatial heterogeneity in aerosol species (anthropogenic and dust) distribution induces heterogeneous aerosol induced radiative perturbations over the Indian region thereby potentially exerting regionally distinct climatic impacts, including the spatial modulations in the monsoon rainfall. Due to heterogeneous distribution of aerosol species concentration region-wide or area-wide strategic mitigation plan of anthropogenic aerosol pollutants needs to be continuously evolved through attaining closure between emissions and source apportionment of atmospheric aerosol pollutants. To attain the above-mentioned closure over the Indian subcontinent, constraining approaches have recently been developed integrating ambient observations of aerosol physical- chemical properties and source-receptor modelling systems. The developed constraining approaches included information about well-mixed layer and nearly steady-state conditions from temporal evaluation of observational data of black carbon (BC) aerosols. Furthermore, taking into account the transboundary transport from receptor modelling approach, the source fields of emissions were configured corresponding to the strategically selected receptor locations with the measured BC concentrations. Constraining the modelled BC burden from forward modelling in the atmospheric chemical transport model (CTM) relative to observations, the spatially- and temporally resolved BC emissions were thus

derived. The derivation for emission fields of Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and organic matter (OM) emissions was further obtained by constraining the scattering to absorbing aerosols with the simulated fields of aerosol single scattering albedo (SSA) in the forward CTM.

While aerosol emissions data from the traditional bottom-up approach provide useful information about prevalent sources and the combustion activity, including their relative contribution to emissions of aerosol species, the magnitude of emission rate formed from the bottom-up approach is thus found to be often lower than the actual emissions. As compared to bottom-up emission inventory which in general lack the desired spatial and temporal variability for representing the atmospheric burden of aerosol species. The spatially and temporally resolved emission fields of aerosol species so obtained from constrained approaches thus aid to fulfil the identified gaps in the prevailing bottom-up emission inventory while utilizing their adhered useful information on sources. The spatially and temporally resolved so-called constrained emission fields of aerosol species further implemented in the state-of-the-art CTM at a fine grid resolution and driven by adequate meteorological forcing have been found providing the successful simulation (close to the observed) of aerosol species distribution over the Indian subcontinent, including the wintertime and inter-seasonal BC distribution. Thus, identifying the combustion-derived pollutant hotspots, population exposures, and assessing their climatic impacts over the Indian subcontinent and thereby suggesting region-wide desired control measures for mitigating their adverse impacts.

LOW-COST SENSORS, SATELLITE IMAGERY, AND DEEP LEARNING: THE FUTURE OF IMPROVING ENVIRONMENTAL AND HUMAN HEALTH

MIKE BERGIN

Duke University, Durham, NC, USA

E-mail: -michael.bergin@duke.edu

The past several years has seen explosive growth in the development of environmental sensors, in particular those that measure air pollutants such as fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). A similar revolution has taken place in the development of data analytics techniques, that hold great promise in analyzing sophisticated existing and emerging data sets related to environmental and human health. Emerging data sets include environmental sensor data, satellite imagery, fitness device data, and a wealth of information from social media and web browsing. At present, there is a critical need to develop broader collaborations amongst disciplines (i.e. environmental science and computer science) and to further develop the field of Environmental and Human Health Data Analytics (EHHDA). With this in mind, I will discuss several recent studies conducted by my research group and our collaborators, including the application of low-cost air quality sensors to determine personal exposure and the influence of indoor air filtration on children's health. I will also discuss the application of machine learning to managing low-cost sensor networks. In addition, I will discuss the use of satellite imagery to determine highly spatially resolved neighborhood-level PM_{2.5} concentrations, air pollution hot spots, and plumes. Lastly, I will describe a deep-learning approach to image analyses for facial recognition that holds great promise in linking human sentiment with environmental contaminants. Overall, the theme of this talk will highlight the exciting future of EHHDA and will emphasize the need to further develop key collaborations across disciplines.

AEROSOL-CLOUD-PRECIPIATION INTERACTIONS: A MAJOR UNCERTAINTY IN THE CLIMATE SYSTEM

G. PANDITHURAI

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune

E-mail: pandit@tropmet.res.in

The effect of aerosols on cloud and precipitation continue to remain one of the major uncertainties in the climate system. The ability of an aerosol particle to act as Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN) or Ice Nucleating Particles (INP) for the generation of cloud droplets depends on the local supersaturation conditions, followed by its size and chemical composition. In the Western Ghats, warm orographic clouds float close to the ground and is a natural laboratory for aerosol-cloud-precipitation interactions. IITM Pune set up a High-Altitude Cloud Physics Laboratory (HACPL) to better understand orographic clouds, aerosol- cloud interactions, and precipitation formation processes. State-of-the-art observing systems relevant to clouds, aerosol, radiation, precipitation, and other meteorological parameters were implemented. Observations from the above lab were utilized to better understand the processes involved in CCN and INP activation. Using measurements from the lab, INP parameterization is developed as representative of the Indian region. Aerosol hygroscopicity derived from its aerosol growth factor measurements and its role in CCN activation processes are investigated. The recent results from IITM's HACPL on CCN, INP, and aerosol-cloud interactions will be presented.

**THEME 1: INDOOR AIR QUALITY AND HEALTH RISK
IMPACT ASSESSMENT**

IS INDOOR AIR POLLUTION MORE HAZARDOUS THAN OUTDOOR AIR POLLUTION? HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT AND INFILTRATION OF PM_{2.5} BOUND METALS

K. SINGH¹, K. M. KUMARI¹, AND A. SATSANGI¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh, Agra, UP

KEYWORDS: Heavy Metals, Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Indoor and Outdoor PM_{2.5}, Infiltration

INTRODUCTION

World health organization statistics are estimated to cause 7 million death every year due to air pollution (WHO, 2023). Further, ambient air pollution has received much attention from the scientific community than indoors. The majority of people spend more than 90% of their time indoors, thus it becomes important to assess simultaneously both indoor and outdoor air quality. Several studies have demonstrated that metals bound to PM_{2.5} can penetrate deeply into the lungs and enter the blood circulation, thereby compromising human health. Although these pollutants are often present in low concentrations in buildings, long-term exposure can cause significant risks to human health (Abbatt and Wang, 2020; Tran et al., 2020). In this regard, the objective of this study is to estimate the extent to which outdoor-originating particles and indoor-emitted particles contribute to the residential indoor PM_{2.5} metallic composition thereby affecting human health.

METHOD

The study was conducted at urban residential buildings (near Kendriya Hindi Sansthan) in the city of Agra (27°10' N, 78°05' E), Uttar Pradesh, India from May 2023 to April 2024. The city generally experiences a high atmospheric pollution load of which 60% is mainly due to vehicular and nearby industrial pollution (Pipal et al., 2022). Simultaneous indoor (living room) and outdoor (rooftop) PM_{2.5} were collected at 5 residential homes on alternate days for 24 h using Envirotech APM 821 on a quartz fibre filter with a flow rate of 3L/min. The collected PM_{2.5} was then subjected to metal analysis using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES). The infiltration of particles as a result of ventilation was then studied using I/O ratios and the infiltration factor model. Further, health risk assessment was done by calculating the hazard quotient (HQ) and Incremental lifetime cancer risk (ILCR) (Sah et al., 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The annual mean 24 h indoor and outdoor PM_{2.5} concentrations were $83.2 \pm 15.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $73.5 \pm 12.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively, exceeding the National Ambient Air-Quality Standards of India ($60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Meteorological parameters (temperature and RH), and infiltration of particles play a significant role in the seasonal variability of indoor and outdoor PM_{2.5}. Winter season with low-temperature and high relative humidity conditions showed the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations for both indoors and outdoors followed by post-monsoon, summer and the monsoon season. Out of the total PM_{2.5} concentrations, metals contributed 3.4% indoors and 2.4% outdoors. Indoor PM_{2.5} showed higher concentrations of Ba, Na, Zn, Ni, Cu and Cr as compared to their corresponding outdoor concentrations. Contrarily, Ca, Al, Mg, K, Fe and Pb showed higher outdoor concentrations, attributed to have emitted from

the re-suspension of soil dust in-filtered indoors (Toffulet al., 2021). High indoor concentrations of Zn, Na and K were attributed to be emitted from the combustion of cooking fuels (Yang et al., 2018), while that of Ba, Cr, Cu and Ni indoors were attributed to have emitted from a combination of indoor emission sources (building materials and cleansing agents) and infiltration of outdoor emission sources (Hu et al., 2023). Similar results were shown by the infiltration factor analysis (Figure 1). Health risk assessment of individual metals showed Hq higher than the acceptable limit ($Hq < 1$) for Zn. Hazard Index (HI) was also >1 indicating that they are likely to cause non-carcinogenic effects in adults and children. Similarly, ILCR of Cr, Ni and Pb for adults and children showed carcinogenic effects of Ni indoors for both adults and children, Cr showed carcinogenic effects for children only at the indoor site, while Pb showed no carcinogenic effects both indoors and outdoors (acceptable ILCR by USEPA is 10^{-6} to 10^{-4})

Figure 1: Average mean 24-hour indoor-outdoor PM_{2.5} concentrations, metallic composition, infiltration analysis, and health risk assessment.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study showed higher indoor PM_{2.5} concentration than outdoors (I/O=1.13). Ca was found to be the dominant element at both sites. The results suggested the dominance of Zn, Na, Cr, Cu, Ba and Ni indoors with I/O > 1 while Ca, Al, Mg, Fe, K and Pb were dominant outdoors with an I/O < 1 . Both Cr and Ni showed carcinogenic effects indoors, while at the outdoor site, only Cr showed the carcinogenic effect.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Director, Dayal bagh Educational Institute (DEI) and Head, Department of Chemistry for providing the necessary facilities.

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MORTALITY RISK ASSOCIATED WITH PARTICULATE MATTER OVER THE ENTIRE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN (IGP)

A. PRAKASH¹, P. RAJEEV¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh, Agra, UP

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Mortality Risk, Exposure Assessment, Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP)

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution due to fine particulate matter (particulate matter less than 2.5 μm ; PM_{2.5}) is a major health concern worldwide, especially in India (Balakrishnan et al., 2019). In the post-monsoon and winter seasons, meteorological conditions favor the confinement of aerosols, leading to higher concentrations of PM_{2.5} in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) (Nair et al., 2007). Scientific research has associated PM_{2.5} exposure with various causes of premature mortality, including ischemic heart disease (IHD), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung cancer (LC) (Bowe et al., 2019). This study investigates transport of particulate matter and associated mortality risk over six states in the IGP to gain insights into their origin and transport, during the most polluted (post-monsoon and winter) seasons. A comparative analysis of PM levels and the mortality risk associated with the PM concentration over the six states (two sites in each state) in IGP has been reported in this study, which will help policymakers to make suitable remedial actions

METHODS

PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations reported by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) at twelve (12) stations in six states of IGP for post-monsoon (Oct–Nov) and winter season (Dec–Feb) in the year 2022-23 have been utilized in this study. Further, air mass back trajectory analysis (AMBTs) was performed to visualize the trajectory patterns of aerosols at twelve (12) sites over the entire Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP). Across the 12 cities, the total mortality per million exposed population for each city in IGP due to six months of exposure to PM_{2.5} concentrations has been estimated. For estimating mortality, the Integrated Exposure Response (IER) function is used (Burnett et al., 2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The back trajectory analysis suggests that the majority of air masses are of Type 1 (long-range air mass traversing from Middle Eastern countries) and Type 4 (local air masses) for all states (see Figure 4). Different patterns of air mass back trajectories were recorded for other states in the IGP.

Due to exposure to high PM_{2.5} concentrations, premature mortality was calculated using the IER model from October 2022 - March 2023 for 6 polluted states over the IGP. The study was performed for three diseases namely IHD, COPD and LC. Anand Vihar, site at Delhi documented the highest mortality 2380 for IHD, 1487 for COPD, and 557 for LC according to WHO's limit (Fig 2) followed by Dwarka and Patna. Using the Integrated Exposure-Response (IER) model, it has been found that PM_{2.5} exposure could result in more than 3000 total mortalities per million exposed population in each city per year, according to WHO limit.

Figure 1: Five-day air mass back trajectories for Punjab (Type 1: Long-range air mass traversing from Middle Eastern countries; Type 2: Long-range air mass coming from the southwest through the Arabian Sea; Type 3: Long-range air mass traversing through the Bay of Bengal; and Type 4: local air masses).

Figure 2: Mortality per million exposed population for LC, COPD, and IHD as per WHO's limit (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

CONCLUSIONS

The back trajectory analysis suggests that the majority of air masses are long-range air masses traversing from Middle Eastern countries and the local air masses. The IER model projected more than 3000 premature deaths due to IHD, COPD, and LC for each city in IGP as per WHO's limit. Delhi faces the highest mortality risk (4425 total mortality per million)

followed by Bihar > Uttar Pradesh > Haryana > Punjab > West Bengal. IHD (54.3 %) was the primary cause of premature mortality, followed by COPD (33.2 %), and LC (12.5 %). The following study suggests an immediate and collective need to implement mitigation strategies to reduce emissions and protect human health, particularly in most polluted cities of IGP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We acknowledge the support from IIT Patna in completing this study.

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INDOOR AIR - BIOAEROSOL MONITORING AND ITS POTENTIAL RISKS IN AIR-CONDITIONED GYMS

P. AMRUTHA¹, E. V. ASWATHY¹

¹Department of Civil Engineering, National Institute of Technology Calicut Kerala

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality, Bioaerosol, Viable Bacteria, Gyms.

INTRODUCTION

Gyms are unique indoor environments where high physical activity can exacerbate the generation and dispersion of fine particles, potentially affecting both air quality and human health (Mohd Hashim et al., 2019; Bragoszewska et al., 2020). Indoor air quality (IAQ) in airconditioned gyms is a critical factor influencing the health and performance of occupants. Bioaerosols consist of all airborne particles of biological origin such as bacteria, fungi, fungal spores, viruses, etc. (Kalogerakis et al., 2005). The fact that bioaerosols can be pathogenic or result in an allergic reaction when inhaled makes them a major contributor to indoor air pollution (Fröhlich-Nowoisky et al., 2016). In this study, we investigate the concentration and size distribution of viable bacteria in air-conditioned gyms and the various factors influencing it.

METHODS

The present study to investigate the concentration and variation of bioaerosols was carried out in two air-conditioned gyms located in Kerala. The sampling was carried out during both working hours (morning and evening) and non-working hours of the gyms under varying occupancy levels and across diverse workout intensities. The sampling of viable bacterial aerosols was carried out using a viable six-stage Andersen sampler cascade impactor (TISCH make) operating at a flow rate of 28.3 L min⁻¹. Each stage of the Andersen sampler collects bioaerosols at different sizes ranging from 0.65 to 1.1 µm in stage 6 to 7 to 10 µm in stage 1. All the samples were collected in duplicates on nutrient agar plates with a sampling time of 3 min. After sampling, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours and the number of colonies were counted. The concentration of airborne bacteria measured in each stage is expressed in CFU/m³, which is obtained using the following equation:

$$\text{Airborne bacterial concentration (CFU/m}^3\text{)} = \{[\text{Number of colonies} / (28.3 \times 3)] \times 1000\}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The total concentration of viable bacterial aerosols measured in the working (morning and evening) and non-working hours of both gyms are shown in Table 1.

Gym name	Time of the day	Viable Bacterial concentration (CFU/m ³)	Average number of users during sampling
Gym A	Morning	8803	32
	Non-working	648	0
	Evening	11567	55
Gym B	Morning	5588	24

Non-working	1255	0
Evening	8128	29

Table 1: Measured bacterial aerosol concentrations and corresponding average occupancy in two AC gyms at different times of the day.

Figure 1: Enter Caption

In both the gyms, relatively higher concentration of bacterial aerosols was observed in the evening samples, when the average number of persons working out was higher. A comparison of the total bacterial concentrations obtained during workout sessions in the morning and evening with the non-working concentration clearly shows that human beings contribute significantly to the gym’s bacterial aerosol concentration. Gym A, which has a larger area per user, has the highest concentration of bacterial aerosols during working hours as compared to Gym B, indicating that irrespective of the area, as the number of users increases, the bacterial aerosol concentration also increases. However, during non-working hours, there is a sudden drop in the bacterial aerosol concentration in Gym A as compared to Gym B. This relatively higher concentration of bacterial aerosols during non-working hours in Gym B might be due to the daily cleaning activity which takes place during this time. It was also observed that the bioaerosol concentrations are exceeding the ACGIH limits (500 CFU/m³) even in the non-working period of the gyms.

The highest concentration of bacterial aerosols in both the gyms was observed in stages 4 and 5, which corresponds to the size range of 2.2 to 3.3 μm and 1.1 to 2.2 μm , respectively. The lowest concentration of bacterial aerosols was found in stage 6, corresponding to the size range of 0.65 μm to 1.1 μm . In Gym A, an increased concentration of bacterial aerosols was observed in stage 1, corresponding to a size range of 7 to 10 μm . This high concentration of bacterial aerosols in larger size fractions might be the result of bacterial aerosols sticking to the larger dust particles. In Gym A, which has a lower cleaning frequency and a greater number of gym users, the chances of dust resuspension are also high during working hours. This would have resulted in a higher concentration of bacterial aerosols in the larger size fraction.

CONCLUSIONS

Air-conditioned gyms, which everyone believes to be cleaner and safer with respect to pollution, are observed to have increased bacterial aerosol concentration which significantly affect the indoor air quality of the gyms. The major contributor to the bioaerosol concentration in gyms is observed to be human beings and it is evident from the obtained concentrations during various times of the day. The regular exposure to such elevated

concentrations of bioaerosol inside gyms can pose more serious health risks to the gym-goers than those related to outdoor concentration exposures, as the breathing rate and metabolism rate are comparatively higher in gyms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to those who cooperated in the sampling and monitoring inside the gyms.

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TRACE ELEMENTS IN PM_{2.5} OVER A SEMI-URBAN REGION AT IGP: TEMPORAL VARIATIONS AND RISK ASSESSMENT

S. MUKHERJEE¹, A.M QADRI², T. GUPTA² AND A. CHATTERJEE¹

Department of Chemical Sciences, Bose Institute, Block-EN, Sector-V, Salt Lake, Kolkata

Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Kanpur

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, IGP, Heavy Metals, Risk Assessment

INTRODUCTION

The major components of fine-mode aerosols have adverse health and climatic effects. Acceleration of urbanization, industrialization, emissions from the energy-related sectors, and growing usage of petrol-driven vehicles are among the prime sources of PM_{2.5} leading to high mortality rates as per the Global Energy Organization reports, 2016. There are trace elements (TEs) that remain bound to the particulate matter (PMs) which serve as important components contributing significantly to health hazards related to the lungs due to their bio-reactive and toxic nature with prolonged environmental exposure (Han et al., 2015). Heavy metals present in PM_{2.5} like Pb and Ni are group 2A carcinogenic contaminants that have been listed in the 2009 National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). Pb exposure to humans in long-terms can lead to abortion, stunted foetal growth and lessened development of offspring neural behaviour. TEs like Ni, Cr, V, Fe, Zn and Cu potentially generate and catalyze redox-active oxygen (RoS) species in tissues of biological organisms because of their variable oxidation state (Alias et al., 2020). Although, exposure to PM is a well-recognized risk factor for human health the risk factors based on its constituents in India are not quite established. These potential effects urge the need for undertaking a quantitative health risk analysis of carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health risks of PM_{2.5} bound trace elements.

METHODS

This year-long study (Jan-Dec 2019) has been conducted over a semi-urban atmosphere called Shyamnagar (22°50'N, 88°23'E, 8 m asl) in the eastern part of IGP. 24-hour samples of PM_{2.5} were collected using a 5-channel aerosol sampler (SASS, Met-One, USA) on every alternate day covering all the seasons. Teflon filters were used for the collection of aerosols. The Teflon filters underwent ED-XRF analysis (Epsilon 4, Panalytical) to analyze a comprehensive set of elements, encompassing both metals and nonmetals. Further, risk assessments were done for some selected toxic metals (Zn, Ni, Pb, Cr, Cd, Cu) using a four-step human health risk assessment framework consisting of hazard identification, exposure assessment, dose–response assessment and risk characterization steps, developed as per the USEPA methodology similar to Das et al., (2020). While Hazard Quotients (HQ) is calculated for all the mentioned metals, Excess Cancer Risk (ECR) were estimated for the carcinogenic metals (Ni, Pb, Cr and Cd).

Figure 2: Figure 1: Box plots showing the seasonal variation of a) the excess cancer risks for Pb for adults and kids (children) and b) Hazard Quotients for Pb in adults and kids (children)

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A total of 38 elements were analyzed using ED-XRF out of the presence of 32 elements that have been observed here. 12 elements have been observed majorly throughout the year. The presence of other important trace elements like Ni, Cd, Cr and V were also observed in the PM_{2.5} over the study area but their occurrence was quite irregular. Annually the highest mean concentration was observed for S ($3.40 \pm 1.71 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), followed by Cl ($1.75 \pm 2.59 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), K ($1.58 \pm 1.25 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Si ($0.84 \pm 0.66 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Fe ($0.57 \pm 0.49 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Na ($0.49 \pm 0.38 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Zn ($0.40 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Pb ($0.35 \pm 0.47 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Al ($0.34 \pm 0.56 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$), Ca ($0.19 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) and Ba ($0.06 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$). Although on rare occasions carcinogens like Cd and Cr were detected they were not of concern in terms of long-term exposure risks. S primarily originates from sulfur dioxide (SO₂) emitted by fossil fuel and biomass burning, with additional contributions from fertilizers and industrial activities like metal smelting. Seasonal variations show the highest concentrations in winter, attributed to increased biomass burning and open waste incineration. Cl concentrations particularly during the monsoon and pre-monsoon seasons could be attributed to garbage burning and sea spray. Increased Potassium (K) concentrations were recorded significantly higher during post-monsoon and winter due to regional biomass smoke. Crustal elements like Si and Al showed higher concentrations during colder seasons and pre-monsoon, which could be attributed to shallow mixing layer depth and elevated windspeeds respectively. Metal concentrations such as iron (Fe), lead (Pb), barium (Ba), and copper (Cu) stem from local industries and waste burning, with Fe and Pb showing higher levels in colder months, while Ba peaks in post-monsoon. Overall, these TEs exhibit distinct seasonal patterns influenced by various combustion sources. The non-carcinogenic risks calculated for elements like Zn, Pb, and Cu were calculated to reveal that the annual mean HQ for Pb was found to be over 17 for adults and over 24 for kids which is quite Hazardous. The risks significantly increase during the colder seasons even for Zn, especially for kids. The concentrations of Pb were found to exceed the NAAQS 24-hour daily limit of $1 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ for 10% of the total samples which occurred during post-monsoon and winter. The annual mean ECR value for Pb in adults was found to be less than 10 persons per million which is still quite high.

CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of TEs in PM_{2.5} showed significant seasonal variations determining the importance of different sources and meteorology and also revealed the presence of toxic metals among which the concentrations of Pb were found to be very high. Further risk assessments of

metals found that Pb posed the risks of alarming non-carcinogenic health impacts, especially for non-industrial semi-urban areas further encouraging similar studies in other similar areas of IGP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The study was funded by the National Carbonaceous Aerosol Program (NCAP) of MoEFCC, Govt of India (No. 14/10/2014-CC (Vol. II)). The authors would like to thank Mr. Sabyasachi Majee for technical help and collection of data as well as for logistic support.

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EVALUATING PM DISTRIBUTION AND CALIBRATING LOW-COST SENSORS FOR PRECISION IN OUTDOOR AND LABORATORY SETTINGS

R. DHIMAN^{1*}, A. AMBEKAR¹, T. THAJUDEEN¹, AND S. K. GUTTIKUNDA²

¹School of Mechanical Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Goa, India 2TRIP-Centre, Indian Institute of Technology New Delhi, India

*Email: rubal20263104@iitgoa.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Air Quality, Low-Cost PM Sensors, Characterisation Chamber, Fine and Ultrafine Particles

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution, notably fine particulate matter (PM), is a leading cause of premature death, especially in developing nations. Our grasp of PM levels relies on regulatory monitoring networks, satellite data interpretations, and air quality models, often revealing concentrations exceeding WHO guidelines and national standards. However, many regions lack adequate monitoring due to the high initial and operating costs of monitoring diverse and multiple locations. Exposure to ambient and indoor PM_{2.5} significantly contributes to an estimated 2 million premature deaths in India, per Global Burden of Disease (GBD) studies. Addressing this requires concerted efforts to bolster monitoring infrastructure and mitigate health risks from air pollution. PM_{2.5} mass concentration monitoring advancements increasingly utilize low-cost sensors (LCSs), necessitating rigorous calibration and performance evaluation. Advancements in monitoring PM_{2.5} mass concentrations rely on low-cost sensors (LCSs), highlighting the need for meticulous calibration and performance assessment. This study emphasizes the field calibration of PMS 5003, PMS 7003, Winsen ZH03, and SPS 30 using the gravimetric sampler and beta attenuation monitor. Additionally, this study concurrently assesses various LCS models—PMS 5003, PMS 7003, SPS 30, New Gen PM sensor, Winsen ZH 06, HM3301, Pira IPS-7100, and Nova Fitness SDS011—by comparing them to reference instruments such as the DustTrak 8344, Optical Particle Sizer (OPS) TSI, and Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS). The sensors' ability to detect short-term pollution spikes (approximately 10 minutes), which simulate real-world outdoor conditions, is examined to understand their suitability for outdoor air quality monitoring, personal exposure assessment, and mobile applications. Key performance metrics include measurement precision, detection limits, inter-unit variability, and the impact of environmental factors. Despite inherent limitations, the results demonstrate that, with careful calibration and environmental adjustments, LCSs can reliably track pollution events, offering significant potential for low-cost air quality monitoring in various settings.

METHODS

The laboratory evaluation was carried out in a sealed 75 × 75 × 70 cm³ chamber with siliconized edges to prevent particle leakage. Four fans were mounted at mid-height to ensure uniform particle distribution. Aerosols were introduced through a tube at the top of the chamber, with 30 LCSs positioned inside, along with DustTrak and OPS reference instruments.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of laboratory evaluation (chamber test)

A SMPS was placed outside the chamber. The LCSs and reference equipment inlets were positioned close together to ensure comparable particle sampling and measurement accuracy. Two types of polystyrene latex (PSL) particles were tested: mono-disperse (0.3 μm) and monodisperse (1.1 μm) to simulate $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ distributions. PSL particles were generated using a TSI Atomizer, passed through a diffusion dryer to remove moisture, and introduced into the chamber to increase particle concentration. The generation ceased once the concentration plateaued, after which it was monitored until undetectable by the LCSs. The instruments first measured baseline indoor aerosol concentrations for 10 minutes. Then, aerosol sources such as cooking oils and candles were ignited inside the chamber and allowed to burn for 10 minutes to generate particles. After this period, the aerosol source was extinguished, and the particle number concentration was continuously monitored. The measurements continued until the particle levels gradually returned to baseline, ensuring that any lingering particulates dissipated and the chamber was restored to its pre-ignition conditions. This process allowed for assessing how well the sensors track changes in particle concentrations during both the generation and dissipation phases.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Field evaluation results reveal a correlation coefficient (R^2) for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ between the LCS and DustTrak, ranging from 0.62 to 0.73, indicating a moderate to strong relationship. However, when comparing the LCS with the BAM, the correlation decreases (0.20 to 0.26), suggesting a weaker association. The study also highlights significant variations in LCS performance with changes in relative humidity. Furthermore, results indicate an improved correlation when dividing $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration into low and high sections, enhancing measurement accuracy. The $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration results demonstrated typical seasonal patterns of winter highs and summer/monsoon lows (Figure 3).

The results revealed R^2 values between the DustTrak and various LCS models for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ranging from 0.75 to 0.97, indicating a robust relationship between them (Figures 2 & 3). However, the slope ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) values were approximately two and exhibited variations across different aerosol sources. The R^2 and least-square errors of the assessed $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sensors showed optimal linearity at a low $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurement range of 0–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The impact of humidity was also investigated, revealing that the sensors exhibited a strong linear relationship at lower humidity levels (40 to 60%). However, as humidity levels increased, the sensors predicted higher concentrations for the same aerosol sources, decreasing the correlation coefficient. The study reiterates the potential of low-cost sensors in monitoring particulate matter but emphasizes the need for careful calibration, showing promising correlations with reference equipment and revealing variations in performance based on humidity levels.

Figure 2: The PM_{2.5} Concentration between DustTrak and LCS for candle and cooking oil aerosol

Figure 3: The seasonal variation of PM_{2.5} Concentration and R2 Variability Across Low-Cost Sensors for Different Aerosol Sources

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge funding from the Science and Engineering Research Board, India, through the project 2020/SRG/0698.

HEALTH RISK EVALUATION FROM EXPOSURE TO AMBIENT PM AND VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN DIFFERENT FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF LUCKNOW CITY

H.O. PRASAD^{1,2}, S.S K MAHANTA^{1,2} AND S. BOJJAGANI^{1,2}

¹Environmental Monitoring Laboratory, ASSIST Division CSIR-Indian Institute of Toxicology Research, Vishvigyan Bhawan 31-Mahatma Gandhi Marg, Lucknow, UP, India

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad-201002, India

Corresponding author: sreekanth.b@iitr.res.in

KEYWORDS: Volatile Organic Compounds, Particulate Matter, Hazard Quotient, Cancer Risk

INTRODUCTION

The activities of rapid urbanization, particularly the increase of transport, gasoline, and natural gas fuel stations, landfill sites, combustion of biomass and industrial emissions, etc., influence ambient PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, and VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) exceedance (Jain et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2024). Non-uniform distribution of sources, land use conditions, and public exposure timings to the toxic compounds of airborne PM and VOCs affect the health risks in different ways (Liao et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2023). Understanding the variability of fine PM# (: 10 and 2.5) along with VOC concentrations, their associated toxic species, and health risks in different functional sites are limitedly studied in the literature (Malik et al., 2023). Therefore, the present study aimed to address (i) the diurnal changeability of ambient VOCs, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, and (ii) cancer and non-cancer risks associated with the exposure of toxic VOC species to the public under different functional sites of Lucknow city.

METHODOLOGY

Monitoring of PM# (: 10 and 2.5) and VOCs (i.e., Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, Xylenep, Styrene, Hexane-n, Chlorobenzene, Carbon tetrachloride, Vinyl Chloride) was conducted in commercial-Charbagh, residential-Gomti Nagar, and industrial area-Amausi in Lucknow city. Simultaneous measurements were taken for PM# and VOCs using ARA-N-FRM dust sampler and Honeywell VOC-Analyzer (Model: RAE by Honeywell, ppbRAE3000+) of CSIR-IITR for consecutive 15 days of the pre-monsoon season, where morning (7:00 AM – 10:00 AM), afternoon (12:00 PM – 3:00 PM), and Night (7:00 PM – 10:00 PM) periods are covered. Diurnal variability and likely interdependency between PM# and VOCs of three functional sites were compared. Further, cancer risks and non-cancer risks due to exposure to nine-toxic VOCs in adults laid in the three different sites are evaluated in terms of Hazard Quotient/Hazard Index (USEPA, 2009; Malik et al., 2023).

Figure 2: Concentration of PM10 & PM2.5 and volatile organic compounds in the morning, afternoon, and night in commercial, residential, and industrial regions of Lucknow city.

Table 1 Predictive health risks assessment of humans laid in different functional zones of Lucknow city

Volatile Organic Compounds	Hazard Quotient/Non-Cancer Risk			Cancer Risk		
	Commercial Site	Residential Site	Industrial Site	Commercial Site	Residential Site	Industrial Site
Benzene	1.42E-03	1.97E-03	1.01E-03	3.31E-05	4.62E-05	2.36E-05
Toluene	2.51E-06	2.40E-06	1.42E-06	--	--	--
Ethylbenzene	1.30E-05	2.19E-05	1.07E-05	9.75E-06	1.65E-05	8.00E-06
Xylene-p	1.92E-04	2.05E-04	1.12E-04	--	--	--
Styrene	2.30E-06	2.93E-06	1.87E-06	1.31E-06	1.67E-06	1.06E-06
Hexane-n	3.71E-06	3.79E-06	2.52E-06	--	--	--
Chlorobenzene	8.12E-04	1.32E-03	5.95E-04	--	--	--
Carbon tetrachloride	8.48E-05	1.24E-04	6.12E-05	5.09E-05	7.43E-05	3.67E-05
Vinyl Chloride	1.98E-05	1.75E-05	1.47E-05	8.72E-06	7.72E-06	6.48E-06
HIVOC / \sumCRVOC	2.55E-03	3.67E-03	1.81E-03	1.04E-04	1.46E-04	7.59E-05

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean concentration of PM# (: 10 and 2.5) and 10-toxic VOCs for morning, afternoon, and night periods at commercial, residential, and industrial sites are delineated in Figure-1. The variability in PM# and VOC levels between morning and evening is found to be higher than afternoon period because of the increased peak hour urban traffic and other city activity emissions. Another key reason is that increased temperature and lower humidity in the atmosphere intensify the reaction of atmospheric NOX and VOCs during the afternoon for tropospheric ozone formation, which results in lowering the concentration of VOCs in the afternoon period. Because of the dense and non-uniform distribution of sources at the commercial site, and the encircle of traffic movement, DG sets, and biomass burning to the residential site, PM#, and VOCs concentrations are recorded higher than industrial site. The high presence of Xylene-p, Toluene, and Carbon Tetrachloride compounds at all three sites is associated with the significant influence of traffic emission, solid fuel combustion, and gasoline vehicular emission sources in Lucknow city. Further, the specific ratio of T/B (i.e., toluene (T) / benzene (B)) ranges between 2.88 - 3.09, 1.89 – 2.17, and 2.29 – 2.40 in the commercial, residential, and industrial sites respectively, which reveals that the commercial and industrial sites are strongly impacted by traffic and fuel combustions in the city. The non-cancer risk and cancer risk due to exposure to nine toxic VOCs by adults laid for the three functional sites of Lucknow are evaluated and results are illustrated in Table-1. The relative risk of non-cancer and cancer is found to be more prominent at residential sites than

in commercial and industrial areas, as the exposure time of public in residential places is usually greater than the other two sites. It is observed that the hazard HQ and HI of VOCs to the public is identified as ≤ 1 for all three sites, therefore, the non-cancer risk can be minimal (USEPA, 2009). However, the cancer risk related to LCR (lung cancer risk) in humans laid at commercial and residential sites was observed to exceed the range of 1×10^{-5} , which declares probable risk, and where the industrial site exists greater than 1×10^{-6} has possible risk (Singh et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

The diurnal changeability of VOCs and PM₁₀ (: 10 and 2.5) is at a greater level in commercial and residential sites than industrial sites due to the respective sites' source of emission strength and their mix, and immoderate meteorological conditions. The results of risk analysis due to exposure to nine-toxic VOCs in the three study sites revealed that the public is at minimal non-cancer risk, however, prone to cancer at probable and possible LCR range. The study results have special attention to setting up suitable abatement measures of air pollution for the humans exposed to VOCs under different function sites of urban areas.

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QUANTIFICATION OF THE TRANSPORT-INDUCED PM EMISSIONS OVER THE NON-ATTAINMENT CITY: CONTRIBUTION OF EXHAUST AND NON-EXHAUST SOURCES

M. SHARMA, B. BHUPAL, V.*, A. A. KUMAR, AND S. JAIN

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Tirupati

Email: ce24d005@iittp.ac.in, sureshjain@iittp.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Emission Inventory, Vehicle Exhaust, Road Dust, Silt Load.

INTRODUCTION

The deteriorating air quality in Tier 2 non-attainment cities in India is a rising issue, with pollution levels ascending at an alarming rate, much like those in metropolitan cities. Effective urban air quality management in Tier 2 non-attainment cities necessitates a detailed emission inventory to reinforce air pollution reduction strategies (Sharma and Jain, 2024; Aggrawal and Jain, 2015).

METHODS

This study aims to quantify particulate matter (PM) emissions from on-road transport in Tier2 non-attainment cities in India, specifically focusing on the Vijayawada urban area. It also examines the relative contributions of exhaust and non-exhaust sources. This study adopted the Activity-Structure-Emission Factor (ASF) modelling framework by multiplying the sector specific activity data and emission factors:

$$E = \sum_x \sum_y F_{x,y} [\sum_z EF_{x,y,z} A_{x,y,z}]$$

E = cumulative emissions; x, y, z are the sector, fuel type, and technology; F = sector-wise fuel amount;

EF = country-specific technology emission factors, A = activity data of the urban sector

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The total annual emissions of PM10 and PM2.5 for 2021 are reported as 3.69 Gg y⁻¹ and 1.35 Gg y⁻¹, respectively. Figure 2 presents the spatial representation of vehicle exhaust emissions.

CONCLUSIONS

Non-exhaust emissions, particularly resuspended road dust, are the dominant contributors to PM10 and PM2.5 levels in Vijayawada, significantly exceeding exhaust emissions. Heavy traffic and a high proportion of diesel vehicles drive these non-exhaust emissions. The study's findings offer crucial insights for developing more effective PM control strategies under India's National Clean Air Program (NCAP), aiming to improve air quality and public health. Traffic urban hotspots in Vijayawada require more rigorous control measures to reduce pollutant levels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by the Andhra Pradesh

Pollution Control Board (APPCB) and UGC under the NCAP initiative.

Figure 2: Exhaust emissions spatial map.

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ASSESSING PARTICULATE MATTER CONCENTRATION IN INDOOR AIR: INTERVENTION STUDY ON IMPROVED VS. TRADITIONAL COOKSTOVES

R. SHARMA^{1,2}, P. HARIPRASAD³, S. K. TYAGI²

¹School of Interdisciplinary Research, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, 110016, India.

²Department of Energy Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi

³Centre for Rural Development and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi

INTRODUCTION

Globally, around 3 billion people are affected by harmful household air pollution (HAP) due to their reliance on biomass fuels for cooking [1]. In rural India, biomass fuels account for approximately 90% of household energy consumption, leading to increased exposure for women and children [2]. Chronic exposure to HAP has been linked to severe health issues, including respiratory infections, low birth weight, and chronic diseases such as ischemic heart disease and lung cancer. This study proposes the scaling up of lab-scale improved cookstoves that utilize crop-residue-based pellets, aiming to achieve two main objectives: enhancing indoor air quality and reducing the environmental impacts associated with stubble burning. Additionally, the study will evaluate the health impacts and efficiency of these clean cooking devices for rural households.

METHODS

A one-year experimental study was conducted to assess the indoor environmental, biological, and behavioral effects of traditional and improved cookstoves in rural low-income settings. Sixty households were surveyed, and based on stove usage/fuel types, 40 were selected for intervention. Improved cookstoves were introduced; their effect on pollution levels/health indicators was evaluated. Crop-residue-based pellets were used as fuel to decrease emissions and improve cooking efficiency. Indoor air quality (PM_{2.5}) real-time exposure monitoring was carried out with EPA-approved samplers; health assessments were conducted at three-month intervals. Pollution levels/health parameters between traditional/improved cookstoves were compared.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study comprehensively assessed indoor PM_{2.5} concentrations from both traditional and improved cookstoves through distinct day and night monitoring. The results revealed that daytime PM concentrations for the improved cookstove ranged between 100–180 µg/m³, whereas nighttime concentrations were notably lower, fluctuating between 10–40 µg/m³. Conversely, the traditional cookstove exhibited significantly elevated PM_{2.5} levels, with daytime concentrations exceeding 500 µg/m³ and nighttime levels remaining above 90 µg/m³. Notable peaks in PM_{2.5}

Figure 2: Day and night PM_{2.5} concentration levels from improved and traditional cookstoves over seven days.

concentrations were recorded on Day 2 for the improved cookstove and on Day 4 for the traditional cookstove, both associated with low wind speeds and high humidity, compounded by construction activities that further heightened indoor pollution levels.

The analysis indicates a pronounced influence of daytime cooking activities on nighttime pollution levels, with the use of improved cookstoves yielding substantially lower PM concentrations during the night compared to traditional cookstoves. Quantitatively, the PM_{2.5} emitted from improved cookstoves demonstrated a 61% reduction in PM levels during daytime hours and a 68% reduction at nighttime. Throughout the study, improved cookstoves consistently outperformed traditional models, aligning more closely with Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) guidelines, thereby underscoring their potential to mitigate health risks associated with indoor air pollution.

Time	Improved cookstove (µg/m ³)	Traditional cookstove (µg/m ³)	% Improvement
Day	131.21	336.06	61%
Night	28.82	91.30	68%
CPCB daily average = 60 µg/m ³			

Table 1. Comparison between overall improved and traditional cookstove PM_{2.5} concentration.

CONCLUSIONS

The study underscores the significant impact of improved cookstoves on indoor air quality and health outcomes in rural households reliant on biomass fuels. The comprehensive assessment of PM concentrations revealed that improved cookstoves not only maintain indoor PM levels within recommended guidelines but also substantially reduce pollution during both daytime and nighttime hours. Notably, a 61% reduction in daytime PM emissions and a 68% reduction at night were observed, highlighting the efficacy of these cleaner cooking technologies in mitigating harmful household air pollution.

The pronounced differences in PM concentrations between traditional and improved cookstoves, particularly during periods of low wind and high humidity, demonstrate the critical role of environmental conditions in indoor air quality. Furthermore, the persistent emissions from traditional cookstoves during non-cooking hours pose ongoing health risks, emphasizing the need for sustainable cooking solutions. The findings advocate for the broader adoption of improved cookstoves, which not only enhance indoor air quality but also contribute to reduced health risks associated with chronic exposure to household air

pollution. These results provide a compelling case for scaling up the implementation of improved cookstove technologies, particularly in rural settings where the reliance on biomass fuels remains high, thereby promoting public health and environmental sustainability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

One of the authors (RS) thankfully acknowledges the financial assistance in the form of a fellowship due to the School of Interdisciplinary Research, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi.

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INVESTIGATING A WIDE RANGE OF INDOOR AEROSOLS CONCENTRATION DURING FESTIVE SEASONS IN URBAN HOUSEHOLDS

M. SHARMA¹ AND M. KHARE²

¹Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University, Delhi

²Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, New Delhi

KEYWORDS: Indoor Aerosols, Fireworks, Household Pollution, Particle Number Concentration.

INTRODUCTION

Delhi has been known for poor air quality for the past two decades. Episodic events like fireworks make Delhi's air quality poor, along with a blanket of smog and air loaded with aerosols (Ghei & Sane, 2018; Sharma et al., 2024). Diwali festival falls in autumn (October-November) during this period, Delhi experienced severe pollution events. The festival celebrations deteriorate outdoor air quality due to cracker emissions (Rajagopal et al., 2024; Yadav et al., 2022). In terms of indoor air quality along with outdoor concentrations, several other factors contribute to poor indoor air quality. The study measured and analyzed the different size aerosols in an indoor environment during different phases of the festival. The results of the study suggest that the indoor concentration of the aerosol during the festival season (Diwali) is not only influenced by the firecrackers but also depends on the various other indoor activities such as cleaning, cooking, and worship, which contribute to a significant concentration of indoor aerosols making indoor air more vulnerable.

METHODS

Study Area and Instrumentation

The study was conducted in the Rohini district in the northwest part of Delhi. The study region represents the typical urban household setting, which is located in the region where both commercial and residential sources play a major role in air pollution. The study was conducted using a Grimm optical particle counter (Model 11A). The instrument works on the principle of light scattering (90) with a wide size range of the particle measurement capacity. The instrument measures particles ranging from 250 nm to 32µm along with the concentration of PM10, PM2.5, and PM1. The study was conducted during Diwali 2023 from 11 November 2023 to 19 November 2023 for a period of 9 days, which includes different periods such as the period before the festival, during, and after the festival.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The temporal variation analysis shows that the indoor aerosol concentration in households varies significantly during different activities.

Figure 2: Temporal variation of particle number concentration during the different phases of the festival: Before Diwali (BD), Diwali Day (DD), After Diwali (AD), and Normal Day (ND).

Figure 4: Diurnal variation comparison of particle number concentration during the different phases of the festival: Before Diwali (BD), Diwali Day (DD), After Diwali (AD), and Normal Day (ND).

During festival seasons like Diwali, firecrackers emit large amounts of aerosols, which influence the indoor air quality. On the occasion of festivals, other subsidiary activities in the households, such as cleaning, cooking, and worship activities also occur parallelly. Fireworks contribute to a higher concentration of indoor aerosols, followed by cooking and cleaning. During fireworks, the concentration reached $5.5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Fig. 2). The diurnal variation analysis shows that the concentration on a normal day increases during indoor activities such as cooking and cleaning, and on Diwali day the concentration in the late evening increases steadily and this increasing trend was found till early morning of the next day ($4 - 5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) (Fig. 4).

CONCLUSION

Indoor air quality is one of the major issues in developing countries where different sources contribute to higher aerosols concentration. Apart from regular indoor aerosol sources, festivals contribute to extreme indoor aerosols, causing serious health effects. The study suggests that indoor aerosols should be monitored properly, and household infrastructure should be designed in a well-ventilated manner to reduce exposure to the residents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Delhi Technological University for providing research facilities.

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COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS-BASED ASSESSMENT OF EXHAUST FAN PLACEMENT FOR IMPROVED INDOOR AIR QUALITY

S. JINNAWAR¹, N. SACHIDANANDAN¹, M. PAREEK¹, P. SINGH¹,
V. SETHI² AND K. SINHA^{1*}

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai

²Department of Environment Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai – 400 076, India.

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: krish@aero.iitb.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), Air Residence Time (ART).

INTRODUCTION

Maintaining indoor air quality is essential for ensuring health and comfort in confined environments. Elevated levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) have been shown to negatively affect cognitive performance and overall well-being (Xu et al., 2011). Prior research highlights the significance of exhaust fan positioning in enhancing ventilation efficiency through computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations (Ren et al., 2022). In this work, we use CFD to compute airflow patterns and air residence time (ART) to study the placement of exhaust fans in a ventilation testbed at IIT Bombay. To validate the CFD simulations, CO₂ decay experiments were conducted in the testbed, and data was collected using an Internet of Things (IoT)-based CO₂ sensor. This paper presents a comparative analysis of the CFD and experimental results to evaluate the effectiveness of the ventilation strategies employed.

METHODS

The ventilation testbed, measuring 3.16 m × 3.61 m × 3.25 m, is shown in Fig. 1(a). It features an exhaust fan that extracts air from the testbed while fresh air enters through the door. In the computational model shown in Fig. 1(b), the exhaust fan's position was varied to observe changes in air circulation and ART, which represents the age of air in the room. ART is used as a parameter governing ventilation in indoor spaces (Mullick et al., 2023).

The door was modeled as a pressure inlet with a gauge pressure of zero, and the exhaust fan was modeled as a velocity outlet with a velocity of 4.4 m/s, as determined experimentally using a hot-wire anemometer. The motion of the exhaust fan blades was neglected for simplicity. The computational mesh comprised 1.63 × 10⁵ polyhedral cell elements with grid refinement implemented near the exhaust fan to enhance solution accuracy; see Fig. 1(b).

ANSYS Fluent (2022 R2) was used to solve the Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations for incompressible flow. The realizable k-ε model, with enhanced wall treatment, was selected for turbulence closure, and the SIMPLE algorithm was employed for pressure-velocity coupling. For the convective terms, a second-order upwind scheme was implemented, and first-order discretization was applied to the turbulence transport equations. Convergence was achieved when residuals fell below 10⁻⁶.

Figure 3: (a) Isometric view depicting the model geometry and (b) Mesh grid representation of the model.

Figure 5: Comparison of CFD solution for two exhaust fan locations: (a) velocity vectors and Air Residence Time (s) contours in horizontal and vertical planes, and (b) ART of both exhaust fans.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the computational fluid dynamics solution of airflow and ART in the ventilation testbed. Data is shown in two representative planes in Fig. 2(a) comparing the exhaust fan positioned at a height of 3.0 m vs. at 2.3 m from the floor. Fig. 2(b) shows a line plot of ART values along the line of intersection of the horizontal and vertical planes in Fig. 2(a). The computational fluid dynamics results show a low ART in the stream of outdoor fresh air entering the room via the open door, while higher values are observed in the recirculation zone between the door and the side wall (exhaust fan wall). Interestingly, the maximum ART in the high-exhaust fan case is around 410 s, which is much higher (by about 100 s) than the ART values in the low exhaust fan simulation. The computational fluid dynamics methodology is validated by comparing with CO₂ data from build-up and decay experiments conducted in the test bed.

CONCLUSIONS

This work investigates the impact of exhaust fan placement at different heights on ventilation effectiveness in a testbed at IIT Bombay using CFD simulations. Results show that lower fan placements near breathing zones reduce air residence time, decreasing exposure to potentially contaminated air and lowering infection risks. Future research may explore thermal buoyancy effects and further optimize fan placement for both health and practical considerations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the support provided by the Technology Innovation Hub (TiH), IIT Bombay, for facilitating this research.

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ESTABLISHING INFECTION RISK FROM AIRBORNE DISEASES IN CLASSROOMS THROUGH REAL-TIME CO₂ MONITORING

S. BALASUBRAMANIAN^{1,2}, *, R. ARIGELA¹, S. KANNAN¹, P. JEJURKAR¹, V. SETHI¹, K. SINHA³

¹Environmental Science and Engineering Department,
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay

²Center for Climate Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai, India

³Department of Aerospace Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai,

KEYWORDS: Ventilation, Carbon Dioxide Monitoring, Airborne Disease Modelling, Classrooms.

MOTIVATION FOR THIS STUDY

The COVID-19 pandemic has starkly highlighted the need to reduce airborne transmission of diseases, especially in high-occupant density spaces such as classrooms [2]. Appropriate ventilation can help reduce the high rebreathed fraction of air and minimize the spread of diseases [4]. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is emitted naturally by occupants, is widely used to quantify air change rates as an indicator of ventilation effectiveness [3]. According to ASTM D6245, CO₂ concentrations under 1000 ppmv (or 650 ppmv above outdoor concentration) are recommended for occupant comfort [1]. However, it is not yet known if such a limit would also correspond to minimal health risk. This study assesses ventilation effectiveness and infection probability in a model classroom under live occupancy conditions and for different mitigation scenarios using real-time CO₂ measurements.

METHODS

Figure 1: (a) Classroom setting and (b) Positions of sensors

A CO₂ measurement campaign was conducted in April 2024 under live classroom conditions at IIT Bombay. As shown in Figure 1, the classroom (8.57 m × 7.4 m × 3.66 m) included a door, eight top-hung windows opposite the door, two exhaust fans above the windows, four ceiling fans (0.82 m below ceiling height), and three air conditioners (ACs). Sensors were placed on a lofted platform in the center of the room. Occupancy and ventilation conditions were tracked for every lecture. Controlled decays were conducted for different ventilation scenarios including turning on AC-Door-Exhaust, AC-Exhaust-Window, and Exhaust-Fan-Window options.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2a shows a typical profile of the evolution of CO₂ concentrations in a classroom, which typically increase with occupancy, plateau, and then decay once occupants leave the classroom.

Measured CO₂ concentrations in the classroom consistently exceeded proposed limits (ASHRAE 62.1:2022 ~ 1000 ppm, REHVA ~ 800 ppm, ASTM D6245 ~ 1287 ppm, ISHRAE ~ 1137 ppm) suggesting poor ventilation under all conditions. Safe CO₂ concentration assuming one COVID19 infected person was estimated from rebreathed fractions using airborne disease models [4] (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: (a) Measured CO₂ concentrations in a classroom with occupants. (b) Safe CO₂ concentration estimated using rebreathed and critical rebreathed fractions

One key ventilation metric, the air change rate (ACR), was estimated using decay analysis. ACR was very low under no ventilation conditions typically observed overnight (0.13 h^{-1}). Implementation of various interventions improved the ACR significantly, with large gains (7.54 h^{-1}) for the AC-Door-Exhaust condition and the best improvement for the Exhaust-Fan-Window combination (12.88 h^{-1}). The critical rebreathed fraction indicated that CO₂ concentration was approximately 1066 ppm, which aligns with the ASTM D6245 standard.

CONCLUSIONS

The measured CO₂ concentrations in a live classroom under varying occupancy conditions revealed that CO₂ levels frequently exceeded the limits recommended by various standards. Safe CO₂ concentrations were estimated using airborne disease transmission models and compared against existing guidelines. These findings highlight the need for improved ventilation strategies to ensure occupant productivity and health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Technology Innovation Hub (TiH), IIT Bombay for funding support. Srinidhi Balasubramanian acknowledges the Young Faculty Award at IIT Bombay, and Ravinder Arigela acknowledges the IIT Bombay Institute Postdoctoral Fellowship.

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ASSESSING INDOOR AIR QUALITY IN POLLUTED URBAN ENVIRONMENTS: A CASE STUDY OF PRAYAGRAJ

PROF. S. RAI^{1,2}, P.N. VISHWAKARMA¹, AND A. MOHAN¹

¹K. Banerjee Centre of Atmospheric and Ocean Studies

²M. N. Saha Centre of Space Studies University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality, Particulate Matter, Total Volatile Organic Compounds, Urban Pollution, Health Risk Assessment

INTRODUCTION

The rapid urbanization in India has led to significant environmental challenges, particularly concerning air pollution. While outdoor air pollution has been widely researched, indoor air quality (IAQ) has received less attention, despite its profound impact on public health. Urban areas like Prayagraj often accumulate pollutants, such as particulate matter (PM) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), from both outdoor infiltration and indoor activities like cooking, smoking, and the use of household products (Kumar et al., 2020; Gupta et al., 2021). This study conducted in 12 locations across Prayagraj revealed alarming levels of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, and TVOCs in indoor environments. Areas like Baswar and Old Katra recorded particularly high levels of these pollutants, with PM₁₀ concentrations reaching up to 650.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, far exceeding the World Health Organization's (WHO) recommended limit of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for outdoor air (WHO, 2021). PM_{2.5} and PM₁ levels were also critically high, posing serious health risks due to their ability to penetrate deep into the lungs and bloodstream, leading to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Sharma et al., 2019).

Additionally, TVOC levels in Old Katra were as high as 988.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, exacerbating health risks such as irritation, organ damage, and cancer (Singh et al., 2022). The study's spatial analysis identified central urban areas as high-risk clusters, with young women being particularly vulnerable to the harmful effects of indoor pollutants due to physiological factors and increased indoor exposure (Bansal et al., 2023). Long-term exposure to PM and VOCs can result in chronic conditions like asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and cardiovascular diseases (Ravindra et al., 2018).

These findings underscore the urgent need for public health interventions, including improved ventilation, the use of low-emission products, and raising awareness about the dangers of indoor air pollution (Mishra et al., 2022). The insights gained will inform future policies and urban planning to reduce the health risks associated with indoor air pollution in urban settings.

METHODS

Study Area Description

The study was conducted in Prayagraj city (25.43° N, 81.84° E), Uttar Pradesh, from November 2022 to February 2023. Sampling took place in 12 urban houses across various locations: Old Katra, Kareli, Civil Lines, Chowk, Salori, Ashok Nagar, Sulem Sarai, Baswar, ADA Naini, Rudra Enclave Naini, George Town, and Teliyarganj. Prayagraj, situated 98 meters above sea level and covering 3,204 square kilometers, ranks among the top 50 most polluted cities globally, with PM_{2.5} levels exceeding WHO recommendations

(IQAir 2024 report).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section analyzes particulate matter (PM) deposition in the respiratory system using the Multiple Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model. Simulations for PM1, PM2.5, and PM10 were

Figure 1- Concentration of PM 1, Figure 2- Concentration of PM_{2.5},
Figure 3- Concentration of TVOCs

conducted across different age groups (pre-teen, teen, post-teen women), revealing how these particles deposit in the head airways, tracheobronchial, and pulmonary regions. Larger particles like PM10 and PM2.5 predominantly deposit in the head airways, while ultrafine PM1 reaches deeper into the lungs. The model highlights age-specific patterns, with post-

teens showing higher pulmonary deposition. These findings emphasize the health risks of ultrafine particles, particularly for young women, and the need for targeted interventions. The plot analyzes how particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁) deposits in the respiratory system across three age groups: 6-11, 11-16, and 16-21 years. In younger children (6-11 years), PM₁₀ primarily deposits in central airways (0.331), while finer particles like PM_{2.5} and PM₁ show increasing deposition in the peripheral lung regions. As the respiratory system matures, peripheral deposition of PM_{2.5} and PM₁ becomes more pronounced, particularly in the 11-16 age groups, where PM₁ predominantly reaches the alveolar sacs. The findings highlight how ultrafine particles penetrate deeper into the lungs as individual's age. In the 16-21 age group, with a fully developed respiratory system, PM₁₀ predominantly deposits in the central airways (0.035) with minimal peripheral deposition (0.007). PM_{2.5} shows a significant shift toward peripheral deposition (0.289), indicating the deeper penetration of finer particles into the lungs. PM₁ continues to exhibit strong peripheral deposition (0.165), underscoring its ability to reach the alveolar regions. Overall, the data highlights that as the respiratory system matures, finer particles increasingly penetrate deeper into the lungs, posing greater health risks. These findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions to mitigate particulate matter exposure.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of particulate matter (PM) deposition across different age groups highlights significant respiratory health risks associated with air pollution. As individuals transition from childhood to young adulthood, the ability of PM_{2.5} and PM₁ to penetrate deeper into the lungs increases, particularly in the alveolar regions. In younger children (6-11 years), larger particles like PM₁₀ mainly deposit in the central airways due to their narrower respiratory tracts, while finer particles can reach peripheral areas. This trend continues into adolescence (11-16 years), where respiratory system maturation allows for greater deposition of PM_{2.5} and PM₁ in peripheral regions. By young adulthood (16-21 years), even finer particles can effectively deposit in the alveoli, raising concerns about their health impacts. Given these findings, targeted public health interventions are essential to reduce exposure to harmful particulate matter, particularly for vulnerable populations like children and young adults, ensuring better respiratory health outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the K. Banerjee Centre of Atmospheric and Ocean Studies, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj.

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ENHANCING THE ACCURACY OF LOW-COST SENSORS AND ITS APPLICATIONS TO ASSESS INDOOR AIR QUALITY EXPOSURE

Y. DAHIMA¹ AND A. VAISHYA^{1,2}

¹School of Arts and Sciences, Ahmedabad University, Ahmedabad – 380 009, India.

²Global Centre for Environment and Energy, Ahmedabad University, Ahmedabad

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality, Low-Cost Sensors, Machine Learning, Particulate Matter Exposure.

INTRODUCTION

According to the “State of Global Air” report, poor air quality caused nearly 8.1 million deaths in 2021, with 58% linked to outdoor PM_{2.5} exposure and 38% to indoor pollution. It is crucial to measure indoor particle concentrations as people spend most of their time at home or workplace. Using conventional high-end instruments for continuous indoor monitoring is not feasible, as they are bulky (15-30 kg), expensive (₹5-30 lakhs), and require significant maintenance (Castell et al., 2017). Therefore, affordable and lightweight optical PM sensors are emerging as a viable alternative to these instruments. The accuracy of these low-cost sensors (LCS) may suffer, particularly when ambient RH exceeds 50%, as they don’t dry sampled air, leading to PM_{2.5} overestimation due to particle size growth from hygroscopic effects (Zamora et al., 2019; Hagler et al., 2018). Zimmerman (2022) recommends prioritizing simplicity and interpretability when choosing data correction methods for LCS. Consequently, we used multiple linear regression (MLR) for PM_{2.5} correction, as it offers the simplest interpretability. While previous research on indoor air quality exposure primarily focuses on classrooms, commercial buildings, and homes (Kabirikopaei et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020), our study highlights the need for more research in higher education institutions, especially in indoor environments other than classrooms, which are underexplored in India.

METHODS

The PurpleAir (PA) devices were employed in this study to measure PM_{2.5} concentration and meteorological parameters. Reference measurements for correction were gathered using a Beta Attenuation Monitor (BAM). PA devices were co-located with BAM for roughly 10 weeks. Quality Checks (QC) were performed on both datasets, and PA data were averaged into 1-hour intervals for comparison with reference data. Comparison metrics included mean absolute bias (MAB), root mean squared error (RMSE), and Pearson’s correlation coefficient (*r*). The PM_{2.5} data from each sensor were corrected using the following equation:

$$\text{Corrected PM}_{2.5} = (\text{Raw PM}_{2.5} \times a) + (\text{RH} \times b) + c, \quad (1)$$

where, constants *a*, *b*, and *c* were evaluated by linear regression (least squares method) using the machine learning library scikit-learn, minimizing RMSE between reference and corrected LCS data. Sensors were deployed across various locations on a university campus for one semester, representing different indoor microenvironments, such as those without active emission sources (e.g., library, classroom, lounge) and with active sources (e.g., cafeteria, fabrication workshop). Time-weighted daily mean PM_{2.5} exposure was estimated for students, assuming three probable scenarios of how much time they spend at different locations within the university campus on weekdays.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The comparison of uncorrected sensor data with reference data indicated that the sensors tend to overestimate reference $PM_{2.5}$ with increasing RH. Hence, RH-based correction was applied to sensor $PM_{2.5}$ as per equation (i). The corrected sensor data showed good agreement with reference data as MAB decreased from $9.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (before correction) to $6.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (after correction), RMSE decreased from $13.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $10.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and r^2 increased from 0.92 to 0.93. Exposure of students to $PM_{2.5}$ during the semester is shown in Figure 1 under distinct scenarios. The particulate air quality in confined indoor spaces without emission sources is better than the rest, primarily due to the physical separation from ambient air. However, indoor environments with active emission sources, contribute to higher concentrations, posing significant health concerns. For the first two cases, the daytime mean $PM_{2.5}$ exposure has the highest frequency around $30\text{-}40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $90\text{-}100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, whereas in the last case, it is $30\text{-}40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $110\text{-}120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a bit higher than the previous two cases due to active emission sources present in the microenvironments where they are spending the time. The average exposure during the semester ranges from $45\text{-}60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Spending more time in microenvironments having active emission sources increases students' exposure to particulate pollution. Effective combustion and better ventilation can help in improving the air quality in such indoor spaces.

Figure 1: (Left) Violin plots showing daily exposure distributions. (Right) Bar plots showing average contributions of microenvironments to exposure.

CONCLUSIONS

The RH-based correction significantly improved the accuracy of sensor $PM_{2.5}$ data, reducing MAB and RMSE. Our analysis further revealed that students' exposure to particulate matter is highly dependent on the type of indoor microenvironment. Indoor environments without active emission sources exhibited better air quality, while those with emissions posed higher exposure risks. These findings highlight the critical need for targeted interventions, such as effective combustion and improved ventilation, to mitigate the adverse impacts of indoor air pollution and protect occupant health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by Ahmedabad University via its Start-up grant (URBSASI20A1). Yash Dahima is supported as a PhD student by Ahmedabad University via University Assistantship. The authors are grateful to the university administration for assistance during the deployment of sensors on the university campus.

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INVISIBLE THREATS: ASSESSING INDOOR AIR QUALITY RISKS FOR YOUNG WOMEN IN POLLUTED URBAN ENVIRONMENTS: A CASE STUDY OF UTTARAKHAND

M. A. ALI¹, S. K. SINGH²

^{1,2}K. Banerjee Centre of Atmospheric and Ocean Studies, University of Allahabad

E-mail: findakbar9@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Urban Pollution, Health Risks, Young Women.

INTRODUCTION

Indoor air quality (IAQ) has emerged as a critical public health concern, particularly in urban areas where environmental pollution is pervasive. Despite widespread awareness of outdoor pollution, the invisible threats posed by indoor air contaminants often go unnoticed, particularly in vulnerable populations. Among those most at risk are young women, who spend significant amounts of time indoors due to cultural, social, and economic factors. This study focuses on assessing the indoor air quality risks faced by young women in the urban environment of Uttarakhand, a region grappling with rapid urbanization and increasing pollution levels.

METHODS

This study employs a combination of the ICRP (International Commission on Radiological Protection) and MPPD (Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry) models to assess the inhalation risks and particle deposition in the respiratory systems of young women exposed to indoor air pollutants. The Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation technique was used to map and analyze air quality variations, allowing for accurate spatial distribution of pollutant concentrations in different indoor environments. Additionally, the rigging method was applied to fine-tune and validate data collection processes, ensuring robust and reliable results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results from the central and peripheral deposition analysis reveal a higher particle deposition fraction in the peripheral regions (0.1723) compared to the central regions (0.0358), indicating that fine particles are more likely to accumulate in the deeper areas of the lungs. This suggests a higher risk for adverse health effects, as peripheral deposition is often associated with increased potential for particle retention and long-term respiratory damage.

The deposited mass visualizations demonstrate the spatial distribution of particulate matter in the respiratory system for different age groups, showing significant variations in deposition patterns based on lung geometry and breathing parameters. For younger individuals, the deposition mass is relatively lower, while for older age groups, the deposition mass is higher, particularly in the deeper regions of the lungs. This indicates that age-related factors, such as lung capacity and tidal volume, play a crucial role in how indoor pollutants impact respiratory health.

Figure 2: Spatial Distribution of Air Pollutants in Uttarakhand

The deposition fraction visualizations further support these findings by showing the concentration of particles deposited across different lung regions. The simulations suggest that larger particles tend to deposit in the central regions, while smaller particles penetrate deeper into the peripheral regions. These results align with previous research on particle deposition dynamics in urban environments, confirming that young women, who may spend significant time indoors, are at increased risk of inhaling harmful particulate matter in polluted areas like Uttarakhand.

CONCLUSIONS

The data generated through the ICRP and MPPD models, along with visualizations of central and peripheral deposition, highlight significant disparities in the deposition of airborne particles within the respiratory systems of individuals in polluted environments. The results indicate a higher particle deposition in the peripheral regions compared to central regions, which could suggest a heightened risk of respiratory complications, particularly among young women exposed to indoor air pollutants.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the K. Banerjee Centre of Atmospheric and Ocean Studies, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj.

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**THEME 2: BIOAEROSOL AND THEIR IMPACT ON
HUMAN HEALTH**

EXPOSURE & HEALTH RISK OF PM_{2.5} AT TOLL PLAZAS IN THE AGRA REGION

Bhavana.¹, D. D. MASSEY¹, Ajay. TANEJA², Mahima. HABIL¹, Susan. VERGHESE P.¹

¹Department of Chemistry, St. John's College, Agra-282002, U.P, India

²Department of Chemistry, Dr. B.R.A University, Agra-282002, U.P, India

Email: pk Yadav941146@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Air Pollution, Toll Plazas, PM_{2.5}, Health Risks, Pollution Control

INTRODUCTION

Road traffic-related air pollution is a major global issue with significant environmental and public health consequences. This problem is particularly acute in developing countries like India, where rapid urbanization, increasing vehicle ownership, rapid economic growth, and inadequate pollution control infrastructure contribute to deteriorating air quality in metropolitan areas. Among the various sources of vehicular emissions, toll plazas represent significant hotspots where vehicle congestion and idling exacerbate pollution levels. The specific operational characteristics of toll plazas, including rapid vehicle acceleration, idling, and deceleration, contribute to elevated pollutant emissions, particularly fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). PM_{2.5} is known to have severe health effects, including cardiovascular and respiratory diseases¹. Air pollution is a growing concern in India, especially in urban areas where rapid industrialization and transportation have led to a significant increase in the levels of particulate matter (Limaye et al., 2018)². Exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) has been linked to several adverse health effects, including premature mortality, stroke³, heart disease, lung cancer, asthma, and other respiratory diseases⁴. The Agra region, home to the iconic Taj Mahal, is no exception to this problem, with toll plazas being identified as potential hotspots for elevated PM_{2.5} levels. In this research paper, we aim to investigate the exposure and health risks associated with PM_{2.5} concentrations at toll plazas in the Agra region.

METHODS

This study assesses the health risks of PM_{2.5} and heavy metal exposure for the public and workers at toll plazas along major highways in the Agra region, including NN-19, NH-11, NH-3, NH-2, NH-93, Noida Yamuna Expressway, and Agra Lucknow Expressway. Air samples will be collected using high-volume air samplers equipped with PM_{2.5} filters at these locations, and analyzed for heavy metals using ICPMS. Exposure assessments will consider traffic volume, time spent at toll plazas, and proximity to emissions. Health risks will be evaluated through established methodologies, calculating health risk indices based on PM_{2.5} and heavy metal concentrations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Our study reveals a troubling reality at Agra's toll plazas, where PM_{2.5} levels are alarmingly high, surpassing both India's national air quality standards and WHO guidelines. The average mass concentrations for PM_{2.5} was found 260 µg/m³ to 270 µg/m³ at toll booths. Concentrations of PM_{2.5} have been compared with WHO, and NAAQS standards were found to exceed than prescribed limit. This elevated pollution is primarily due to heavy vehicular traffic, especially diesel trucks idling or moving slowly, compounded by nearby industrial

emissions and open waste burning. The health risks associated with this exposure are significant, with PM_{2.5} linked to respiratory issues like asthma and bronchitis, and serious cardiovascular conditions, including heart attacks and strokes. Vulnerable groups children, the elderly, and those with pre-existing conditions are particularly at risk, even with short-term exposure. Toll plazas, meant to facilitate transportation, have inadvertently become air pollution hotspots, endangering the health of millions who pass through or work nearby, highlighting the urgent need for action.

Figure 2: Average mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} in the summer season at a toll booth.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the urgent need to address the air pollution problem at toll plazas in the Agra region. Implementing measures to reduce vehicular emissions, such as improved traffic management, promotion of cleaner fuels, and installation of air filtration systems at the toll plazas, could help mitigate the health risks associated with PM_{2.5} exposure.

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AIRBORNE BACTERIAL COMMUNITIES ENRICHED WITH PATHOGENS OVER NEW DELHI EXHIBIT STRONG DEPENDENCY ON TEMPERATURE AND POLLUTANTS IN WINTER

S.R. SAIKH^{1*}, A. PRAMANICK¹, N. YASUTOMI², A. BISWAL², S. GHUDE³,
A. SHARMA⁴, A.P. DIMRI⁴, P.K. PATRA^{2,5}, AND S.K. DAS^{1*}

¹Department of Physical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, India

²Research Institute for Humanity and Nature, Kyoto, Japan

³Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, India

⁴School of Environmental Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

⁵Research Institute for Global Change, JAMSTEC, Yokohama, Japan

*Corresponding authors: shahinasheikh39@gmail.com, sanatkrdas@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Delhi, Pathogens, Urban, Health

INTRODUCTION

Atmosphere is less explored for microorganisms than soil and aquatic ecosystems (1,2). Airborne bacteria have a significant role in the structural variation of atmospheric microorganisms; however, little is known about their composition and geographical distribution. Understanding its effect on public health is essential as their substantial spatial and temporal variation highly depends on meteorological conditions and air pollution levels. The current study presents the composition, diversity, and variability of airborne pathogenic bacteria in aerosols collected from two sites in New Delhi during Jan-Feb 2024.

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected on 0.2 μm pore size filter papers (47mm) simultaneously at 10m height from 09 January to 15 February 2024 at two locations in a densely populated and highly polluted metropolitan city, New Delhi, India. Sampling sites were chosen within the campus of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology (IITM, 28.63°N, 77.17°E), near a busy traffic and highly populated area in New Delhi, and Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU, 28.53°N, 77.16°E), well within the canopy, isolated from local traffic and relatively less populated area in New Delhi. Microbial cell suspension is prepared from aerosol samples collected on filter papers (1). Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) has been extracted from microbial cell suspension, and DNA sequencing is performed targeting v3-v4 regions of 16S rRNA genes using the Illumina NextSeq platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on meteorological conditions and pollution levels, total 36 samples are grouped into four periods: low haze (surface air temperature- $T = 11.4 \pm 0.4$ °C, particulate matter of 2.5 μm diameter - $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 190.7 \pm 8.8$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), high haze ($T = 13.3 \pm 0.7$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 278.9 \pm 3.6$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), rain ($T = 16.9 \pm 1.5$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 100.1 \pm 22.9$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), and seasonal transition ($T = 18.9 \pm 1.0$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 187.6 \pm 5.2$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$). The abundance of airborne bacterial loading over New Delhi varied strongly with air temperature (Spearman's correlation coefficient - $r = 0.70$, $p < 0.001$) and visibility ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$) with a strong positive correlation. However, Relative Humidity ($r = -0.41$, $p < 0.05$), $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.01$), and Air Quality Index (AQI) ($r = -0.31$, $p < 0.05$) have a negative effect on airborne bacterial loading

as shown in Figure 1. The highest bacterial diversity is observed during high haze days followed by transition, low haze, and rainy winter days over New Delhi. Beta diversities formed separate ellipses exhibiting distinct bacterial diversities; however, there is an overlap between low haze and high haze conditions, indicating a similar atmosphere for the survival of the same type of airborne bacteria. High concentrations of pathogenic OTU's causing various respiratory, skin, gastrointestinal, and oral infections are present over New Delhi. There is a 7-fold increase in the loading of all types of pathogenic bacteria during rain events at JNU due to increased atmospheric moisture.

Figure 2: Spearman's correlation between meteorological parameters and bacterial load. Significance levels: ***, $p < 0.001$; **, $p < 0.01$; *, $p < 0.05$.

CONCLUSIONS

Human pathogens like *Bacillus cereus*, *Acinetobacter lwoffii*, and *Clostridium sordellii*, responsible for respiratory diseases and skin infections, are highly loaded, indicating an alarming situation for human health in winter over New Delhi. The present study provides new insights and direction in interdisciplinary science, including detailed investigations of the effects of meteorological conditions on airborne bacteria and human pathogens and their implications on the health of people living in an urban location over New Delhi, India.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is in collaboration with the Aakash Project, Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN), Kyoto, Japan.

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LONG-RANGE TRANSPORTED DESERT DUST PERTURBATING EASTERN HIMALAYAN ATMOSPHERIC BACTERIAL BIODIVERSITY

ANTARA PRAMANICK*¹, S. R. SAIKH¹, MD. A. MUSHTAQUE¹, AND SANAT KUMAR DAS*¹

¹Department of Physical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, India

*Corresponding author: antarastb@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Airborne Bacteria, Dust, Long-Range Transport, Biodiversity, Eastern Himalayas, Health

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, long-range transported desert dust has been a prime interest of research for atmospheric scientists due to their potential capability to impact human health, agriculture, and climate processes by introducing unique types of airborne microorganisms over downwind regions (Pöschl and Shiraiwa 2015). There are several pieces of evidence in the literature regarding the long-range transport of bacteria attached to dust particles traveling long distances, like crossing the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, and can act as pathogens and allergens and contribute significantly to regional biogeochemical cycles (Maki et al. 2022). The present study focuses on the long-range transported bacteria and their cause-and-effect relationship on the perturbation of atmospheric bacterial biodiversity over the Eastern Himalayas.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Darjeeling (27°03'N, 88°26'E), a high-altitude site (2.2 km amsl) over the Eastern Himalayas. Total fifteen aerosol samples were collected on filter papers with 0.22µm pore size and 47 mm diameter from winter ($6.2 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 85.2 \pm 9.6\%$) and summer season ($16 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 93.5 \pm 6.5\%$). Aerosol particle concentrations were measured using ground-based particle counter SMPS, while observations from spaceborne sensors like MODIS, OMI, and CALIPSO provide information about the horizontally transported dust layer at the measurement site. A back-trajectory analysis was carried out to identify the possible dust emission source. DNA was extracted from filter papers and DNA sequencing was carried out to identify the bacteria using the Illumina NextSeq platform targeting the v3-v4 region of 16S rRNA. Further bioinformatics analysis was performed to investigate bacterial composition, Shannon diversity index and identification of pathogenic genera present in the atmosphere over the Eastern Himalayas (Saikh et al. 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A significant seasonal variation in aerosol and microbial characteristics is noticed over Darjeeling. SMPS data shows a 70% increase in particle concentration during summer, with a modal size shift from 110 nm in winter to 150 nm in summer, suggesting the presence of bigger particles. Satellite data indicates an increase in AOD from 0.4 ± 0.3 to 0.7 ± 0.3 and a decrease in angstrom exponent from 1.6 ± 0.04 to 0.3 ± 0.1 , reflecting the dominance of coarser particles in summer. The spatial distribution of aerosol index (AI) exhibits a significant enhancement of about 2.1 from 0.8, indicating UV-absorbing particles spreading from the Thar desert to the Eastern Himalayas. CALIPSO detects a 1 km thick aerosol layer

in between 2 to 3 km altitude over the study area as shown in figure 1. 7-days back-trajectories computed over Darjeeling coincides with the patches of higher values within the spatial distribution of AOD and AI connecting from Thar desert to Eastern India. The combined results indicate long-range transport of desert dust within 2 to 3 km altitude from the Thar Desert to the Eastern Himalayas. Microbial analysis reveals an enhancement of total cell counts of about $24 \pm 0.4\%$ over hill-top regions during dusty days, with significantly higher Shannon diversity indices (4.4 ± 0.8). As shown in figure 2, beta diversity exhibits a distinct bacterial community during the dusty period in summer with unique type of bacteria, dominated by *Flavobacterium* ($5.4 \pm 3.6\%$), *Nocardioides* ($4.2 \pm 3.0\%$), and *Corynebacterium* ($4.2 \pm 1.4\%$) while in winter dominating bacteria are *Corynebacterium* ($2.4 \pm 0.5\%$), *Acinetobacter* ($1.8 \pm 0.9\%$), and *Massilia* ($1.3 \pm 0.3\%$). Pathogenic bacteria like *Afipia* and *Clostridium*, responsible for infections in humans and animals, are detected only in summer and associated with dust particles, indicating increased potential health risks. Present findings suggest that transported dust-associated airborne bacteria directly perturb airborne bacterial communities over downwind Himalayan regions.

Figure 2: PCoA plot of beta diversities computed from each sample collected in the summer and winter seasons of 2022. Two separate ellipses are observed for winter and summer conditions. Atmospheric bacteria on dusty summer days exhibit a unique community of bacteria distinct from winter over the Eastern Himalayas.

Figure 2: CALIPSO observation on a typical day in winter (06 January 2022, top) and summer (10 April 2022, bottom). From left to right, satellite path and star represent the location of Darjeeling; vertical profiles of aerosol extinction coefficient at 532nm (green) and 1064 nm (red); angstrom exponent; depolarization ratio. Shaded regions represent the optically thick dust layers.

CONCLUSION

Long-range transport of desert dust from the Thar Desert significantly impacts aerosol characteristics and airborne microbial communities over the Eastern Himalayas. The dust influx alters bacterial composition, introducing distinct and potentially pathogenic species during summer. These findings suggest important implications for both environmental dynamics and public health in downwind regions, emphasizing the need for further investigation into the region's ecological and health effects of dust-associated microbes.

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LONG-TERM EXPOSURE TO AMBIENT FINE PARTICULATE MATTER AND ITS CONSTITUENTS ON DEPRESSION & ANXIETY IN INDIAN ADULTS

P. KUNDU¹, S. DEY^{1,2,3,4}, A. KRISHNAN⁵, S. GHOSH⁶,
G. N. RAO⁷, G. GURURAJ⁷, M. VARGHESE^{6,8,9}, AND V. BENEGAL⁹

¹School of Interdisciplinary Research, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,

²Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,

³Centre of Excellence for Research on Clean Air, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi

⁴Adjunct Faculty, Department of Health, Policy and Management, Korea University,
Seoul, South Korea

⁵Centre for Community Medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi

⁶St. John's Medical College, Bangalore – 560 034, India

⁷Department of Epidemiology, Centre for Public Health, National Institute of Mental Health,
and Neurosciences (NIMHANS), Bengaluru, Karnataka – 560 029, India

⁸Kasturba Medical College (KMC), Manipal – 576 104, India

⁹Department of Psychiatry, Centre for Addiction Medicine, National Institute of Mental
Health, and Neurosciences (NIMHANS), Bengaluru, Karnataka – 560 029, India

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5} Species, Mental Health, Depression, Anxiety, India

INTRODUCTION

Emerging evidence has indicated that exposure to ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) may be associated with an increased risk of mental disorders. However, there remain limited studies regarding which specific PM_{2.5} constituents have a detrimental impact on mental health outcomes, such as depression and anxiety. Moreover, evidence supporting these associations is very scarce in low and middle-income countries like India. Therefore, we investigate the association between long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} and its constituents and mental disorders in Indian adults.

METHODS

We utilized data from the National Mental Health Survey (NMHS) conducted in 2015-16, which was integrated with high-resolution 1km × 1km satellite-derived PM_{2.5} exposure and its constituents (elemental carbon (EC), organic carbon (OC), nitrate, sulfate, ammonium, soil, and other species) obtained from the WRF-CMAQ model. The Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) version 6.0.0 was used to evaluate depression and anxiety disorders in adults. We conducted a logistic mixed-effects regression analysis to assess the relationship between PM_{2.5} components averaged over 12 months with depression and anxiety, controlling for relevant confounders including sociodemographic variables and diurnal temperature range. We applied a penalized cubic spline to illustrate the non-linear relationship and multiplicative interaction models used to investigate possible effect modification by season, residence type, region, marital status, wealth quintiles, and education level.

Figure 2: Odds ratio with 95% confidence intervals for depression and anxiety associated with per IQR increase in 12-month average PM_{2.5} and its constituents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Among 34,357 participants, the weighted prevalence of the current depressive and anxiety disorders among adults was 2.69% (95% CI: 2.66 - 2.72) and 2.96% (95% CI: 2.93 - 2.99), respectively, with an estimated 12-month mean PM_{2.5} exposure of 44.3±13.5 µg/m³. A 10 µg/m³ increase in PM_{2.5} exposure was significantly associated with depressive disorders (OR= 1.06; 95% CI: 1.01 to 1.12) and anxiety disorders (OR= 1.11; 95% CI: 1.05 to 1.17) after adjusting for potential confounders.

In the interaction analysis, the association between PM_{2.5} and depression were significantly higher during the monsoon and pre-monsoon seasons, particularly among individuals with high school education. In contrast, PM_{2.5} -related anxiety was more prevalent among individuals with primary education, those who are married, those in the lowest income categories, and those who live in urban non-metro areas compared to urban metros. The exposure-concentration curve indicates that elevated PM_{2.5} exposure markedly enhances the probability of anxiety, but a more gradual increase was noted for depression. Furthermore, with each interquartile range increase in sulfate, the odds of anxiety increased by 1.27 (95% CI: 1.13, 1.44), followed by ammonium and EC (1.20, 95% CI: 1.10, 1.31) and nitrate at 1.11 (95% CI: 1.01, 1.22). For depressive disorders, only sulfate, ammonium, and EC showed significant effects.

CONCLUSIONS

Our study suggests that long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} and its constituents, particularly sulfate, ammonium, and EC, significantly aggravates depression and anxiety among adults, with different species exhibiting varying levels of neurotoxicity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is funded by a research grant from the Clean Air Fund at IIT Delhi. The presenting author acknowledges the UGC funding for the doctoral fellowship.

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FUNGAL GROWTH AND DIVERSITY ON FRUITS AND VEGETABLES IN RELATION TO ESTIMATION OF PASSIVE SPORE RELEASE

R. ARIGELA^{1,2}, S. KRISHNAMOORTHY^{3,*}, S.S. GUNTHER^{3,4}, AND R. RAGHUNATHAN^{1,4,*}

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, Chennai

²Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, IIT, Bombay, Mumbai, India

³EWRE Division, Department of Civil Engineering, IIT Madras, Chennai 600036, India

⁴Center for Atmospheric and Climate Sciences, IIT Madras, Chennai, India

KEYWORDS: Foodborne fungi, airborne fungi, DNA sequencing, Passive spore release

INTRODUCTION

Fungal spores are a significant component of bioaerosols and play a crucial role in human health, agriculture, and climate. In developing countries like India, where open dumping of municipal solid waste is common, these open waste dumpsites serve as significant breeding grounds for fungal growth, leading to the subsequent release of spores. Fruits and vegetables are highly susceptible to fungal growth due to their nutrient-rich composition and ideal water activity (Francis et al., 2012). Traditionally, culture-based methods have been used to document fungal species on various food substrates (Houbraken & Samson, 2017). However, these methods capture only a small fraction of fungal diversity (Edet et al., 2017). Next-generation sequencing (NGS) provides a more comprehensive view of microbial communities, and numerous studies have used NGS to investigate fungal diversity in fruit and vegetable samples (Abdelfattah et al., 2021).

Fungal growth on food substrates can result either from inherent fungal spore contamination or from airborne deposition. Despite extensive research, there are no studies that compare the relative contributions of these contamination pathways (inherent vs. airborne deposition). This study aims to assess the relative importance of these two contamination routes and their implications for modelling fungal spore release

METHODS

Experiments were conducted to examine fungal growth and diversity on various fruits and vegetables under varying air exposure conditions. Fresh fruits and vegetables were purchased in sterilized bags from a local shop (IIT Madras). They were washed with sterile water and dried in a laminar flow cabinet (Everflow Scientific Instruments, India) for 30 minutes. Fresh fruits and vegetables were sliced using a sterile scalpel.

Two types of experiments were performed:

No Exposure to Ambient Fungal Spores: Five substrates—brinjal (*Solanum melongena*), capsicum (*Capsicum annum*), orange peel (*Citrus aurantium*), apple (*Malus domestica*), and papaya (*Carica papaya*)—were freshly sliced and incubated in a sterile chamber to prevent external airborne fungal contamination. The substrates were incubated for 10–11 days under sterile conditions to allow the growth of inherent fungal spores.

Ambient Air Exposure: Various substrates, including four fruits (apple, papaya, orange peel, and watermelon peel) and three vegetables (brinjal, capsicum, and tomato), were

exposed to ambient air. Three treatments were applied: a) cut fruits and vegetables exposed to air (AES), b) boiled vegetables exposed to air (AEBS), and c) a mixture of fruits and vegetables exposed to air (AEMS). Substrates were incubated on the rooftop of a building (30 m high) in a metal mesh cage for 11 days. In both experiments, DNA was extracted from the food substrates and analyzed using NGS. Fungal diversity in ambient air, fresh-cut unincubated fruits, and vegetables was also assessed via NGS. Data analysis was conducted to compare fungal contamination from inherent and airborne sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary experiments of fungal growth on food substrates showed that fungal spores are already present in the fresh-cut food substrates, even without exposure to ambient air. The

Figure 2: Chord diagram representing fungal species in food (AES/AEBS/AEMS) and air samples.

analysis of NGS data also confirmed fungal growth in the absence of airborne fungal spore deposition. Figure 2 shows the fungal species in food and air samples, highlighting significant species overlap between the two groups. A diverse fungal community was observed, with 156 operational taxonomic units (OTUs) detected in air samples and 76 OTUs in food substrates exposed to ambient air.

The fractions of species present in AES, FS, and air were determined through DNA data analysis. The overlap between FS and AES consists of 9 species (5%), while the overlap between air and AES consists of 11 species (6%). This suggests that contamination of food substrates occurs similarly through both routes—via inherent species and deposition from the air. The dominant genera identified in food samples were *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, *Kluyveromyces*, and *Debaryomyces*, while the most prevalent genera in air samples were *Aspergillus*, *Perenniporia*, and *Scopuloides*. These dominant genera can serve as surrogates for representing overall fungal diversity and estimating spore emissions.

CONCLUSIONS

Fungal diversity data on various substrates suggests that even when substrates are not exposed to ambient air, fungal growth can occur and that this route is equally important as the route where fungal growth occurs after spore deposition on food substrates. In the overall context of fungal spore release from food substrates, this study contributes to the understanding of factors and stages of potential fungal growth and consequent spore release

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EXPLORING THE BIOAEROSOL OVER A LENTIC ECOSYSTEM IN AN URBAN AREA IN EASTERN INDIA

B. CHATTERJEE¹, V. K. SINGH¹, S. DEY², A. K. MITRA¹

¹Post-graduate and Research Department of Microbiology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Kolkata, Kolkata-70001

²Department of Environmental Studies, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Kolkata,

Corresponding author: bidishachatterjee06@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosol, Urban Lentic Ecosystem, Human Health

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are aerosols of biological origin including metabolites, toxins and various kinds of microbes and pollens. These components co-exist in the atmosphere. In the global scientific community sampling, identification and characterisation of bioaerosol have led to an enhanced interest in the health impact of bioaerosol which mainly consists of allergy, respiratory diseases, infectious diseases and cancer (Gollakota et al., 2021). Urban bioaerosol includes pollutants combined with biological components as a result of anthropogenic activities. The immediate impact of these urban bioaerosol will have an impact on the city dwellers (Kim et al., 2018). According to the literature review microbial study over pristine lentic ecosystems have led to the detection of pathogenic bacteria in Chilean Patagonian Lake (Escalante et al., 2014). However, the impact of the aquatic ecosystem on its ambient bioaerosol is not fully understood (Dueker et al. 2018). Meteorological parameters have been known to influence the abundance and viability of airborne bioaerosol. (Bragoszewska et al., 2018) The Rabindra Sarobar Lake hosts a versatile biodiversity in the lentic ecosystem and this lake is ecologically important for the urban ecosystem of Kolkata. There have been some isolated studies on the aquatic ecosystem but the ambient bioaerosols over this area to remain unexplored. Information on the nature of the ambient bioaerosols over this area will help in understanding the impacts of bioaerosols on both the environment and human beings. The present study aims to analyse and characterize the microbial population of the bioaerosol in the atmospheric environment of this lentic ecosystem and understand the influence of meteorology on the microbial abundance.

METHODS

The sampling was conducted near the waterfront at the onset and outset of winter to analyse the impact of the winter season. Bioaerosol sampling was carried out using a six stage TISCH Anderson Sampler (Andersen, 1958). The sampler has six stages containing 400 pores in each stage with decreasing pore diameter (Fang et al.2007). The data on air pollutants and meteorological parameters have been collected from the CPCB website. The bacterial isolates were cultured after incubation for 24 hours at 37°C. They were characterised using Gram character, colony morphology and hicrome bacillus and hicrome UTI agar. They were further cultured on BHI agar to understand their fastidious and pathogenic character. Then capsule staining and biofilm assay were also conducted. These are virulence characteristics that help the bacterial isolate to adhere and survive in unfavourable conditions. Extracellular enzymatic characterization was performed to identify

the probable pathogenicity of the strains. The strains were tested for protease, lipase, DNase, and Haemolysin (Renjan et al. 2014). This was followed by a siderophore assay to study the uptake of iron which is an important co factor for pathogenic enzyme pathways. The strains were also tested for enzymes such as pyocyanin and fluorescein to understand their potential to survive against the host cell immunity. Antibiotic disk diffusion assay using tobramycin, ceftriaxone, doxycycline, amoxiclav, co-trimoxazole, levofloxacin, azithromycin, meropenem, clindamycin, vancomycin and streptomycin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The isolated strains showed a higher percentage of Gram-positive bacteria in the bioaerosol sample as compared to Gram negative and the percentage of Gram-positive coccus was almost 40%. All the samples showed luxuriant growth on BHI agar except one sample from March (5RMC7). Approximately 50% of the samples from November, 100% from December and 66.67% from February exhibited high biofilm formation. Four bacterial strains showed positive results for extracellular DNase, protease and lipase production. These four bacterial strains might show probable pathogenicity as stated by Renjan et al. in his study on *Stenotrophomonas* sp. isolated from urban bioaerosol. Only 17% of the November samples and 50% of December samples showed beta haemolysis, 50% of the December samples showed alpha haemolysis and the rest showed gamma haemolysis. Pyocyanin and fluorescein were absent in all the samples indicating a lower probability of survival under stressed conditions (Azman et al. 2018). The samples were resistant to most of the antibiotics. The data of air pollutants and meteorological parameters were analysed to study their relationship with the microbial abundance in the bioaerosol sample.

CONCLUSION

The study indicates the presence of bacterial strains with potential pathogenic characteristics in the bioaerosol across Rabindra Sarobar. They have a higher probability of being opportunistic pathogens. This might be a health hazard, especially for children, aged people and immunocompromised people. As per previous studies conducted on bioaerosol, they have the potential of being transported over long distances. (Petroselli et al. 2021). So further study on the transport mechanisms of ambient bioaerosols will provide important insight into the sources of these obtained bioaerosol over the study area. Further study on the specific health outcome of exposure to bioaerosol of a particular character is required for exposure-response assessment and impact on human health (Gollakota et al., 2021).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the Intramural Research Grant IMSXC2022-23/012 of St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Kolkata, for funding the research.

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PHOTOCATALYTIC DISINFECTION OF BIOAEROSOLS USING TiO₂ BASED NANOPARTICLES

C. MANDAL, P. NAWALE, AND M. SAHU

Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Environmental Science and Engineering
Department, Powai, Mumbai – 400 076, India.

KEYWORDS: Nanoparticles, Bioaerosols, Photocatalytic Disinfection

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols have proved to be a significant threat to human health in the last few decades. Various studies such as filtration, ozonation, UV irradiation, ionization and photocatalytic oxidation have been used to eliminate the bioaerosols and to reduce the threat of infections in humans caused due to bacteria present in indoor environments. Photocatalytic oxidation uses nanoparticles as a catalyst in disinfection of bacteria. The disinfection process is dependent on variables such as the type of nanoparticles, residence time, relative humidity, the type of bioaerosols and bacteria size. TiO₂ is the most popular nanoparticle used in photocatalytic studies due to its stable and strong oxidation reactions however it requires UV irradiation for generation of reactive oxygen species. Copper is used as a doping material with TiO₂ for irradiation in the visible spectrum of light and enhances the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂. Therefore, in this study, we have synthesized TiO₂ and Cu doped TiO₂ with varying concentrations for the photocatalytic inactivation of bioaerosols. The materials were characterized and coated onto a steel plate inside a continuous flow photocatalytic reactor for the disinfection of bioaerosols. The study also aimed to investigate the effect of residence time, relative humidity, type of nanoparticles and type of bioaerosols in disinfection efficiency of the photocatalytic process.

METHODS

TiO₂ and doped TiO₂ with Cu were synthesized by the sol-gel method of nanoparticle synthesis. The nanoparticles were characterized by doing XRD analysis, FEG-SEM and UV-Vi's spectroscopy. The photocatalytic reactor of length 440 mm and diameter of 120 mm was fabricated. Inside the reactor quartz tube of 508 mm was placed containing UV lamps of 254 nm and 390 nm having power of 15 W. Around the quartz tube stainless steel plates immobilized with NPs via spray coating method were placed. The disinfection efficiency was calculated by using the plate counting method.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The XRD analysis revealed an anatase phase tetragonal structure for TiO₂. Cu doped TiO₂ showed the presence of both anatase (majority) and rutile phase. The surface morphology of TiO₂ and doped TiO₂ nanoparticles are spherical in shape. The doping concentration does not seem to affect the particle shape. The EDX spectrum and elemental mapping results confirm the presence of desired elements in the NPs. Increasing the doping percentage of Cu in TiO₂ decreases the band gap significantly from 3.28 to 2.51 eV for TiO₂ to 5% Cu-TiO₂.

The three tested relative humidity (RH) at 254 nm on *E. coli* were 25±5%, 60±5% and 80±5%. The highest disinfection efficiency was 78.13% observed at moderate (RH of 60±5%), 55.34% at (RH 25±5%) and 71.63% at high (RH 80±5%). Low disinfection

efficiency under low humidity can be attributed to the lack of water molecules for ROS generation. However, the less efficiency at high humidity conditions can be due to occupancy of active sites by the water molecules itself. The *E. coli* disinfection results at different residence times of 10 to 90 minutes were found to be 43.4%, 57.9% and 65.8%, 71.4%, 75.4%, 78.4%, 81.1%, 82.1%, and 82.6% for 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80 and 90 minutes respectively. The disinfection efficiency can be observed to increase with an increase in the residence time to 60 mins after which not much rise in disinfection efficiency can be observed. This can be due to the unavailability of oxidative radicals inside the reactor for disinfection after a certain time. The effect of different photocatalysts (i.e. TiO₂, and different doping concentrations of Cu doped TiO₂) was studied for the investigation of the disinfection efficiency of NPs against *E. coli* shown in Figure 1(a). The disinfection efficiency of NPs when irradiated with 390 nm was found to be around 13.88%, 67.23%, 73.76% and 84.65% for TiO₂, 1% Cu-TiO₂, 3% Cu-TiO₂, and 5% Cu-TiO₂ respectively. The disinfection potential of NPs at 254 nm was found to be 78.43%, 81.44%, 86.57% and 93.87% respectively. 5% Cu-TiO₂ shows maximum efficiency which can be mostly due to the increase in ROS generation and decrease in band gap. The disinfection efficiency of TiO₂ and 5% Cu-TiO₂ against gram-positive bacteria and gram-negative bacteria was found to be around 70.36 % and 87.84% for *M. smegmatis* and 78.43% and 93.87 % for *E. coli* shown in Figure 1(b). This may be attributed to the unique cell wall structure and mycolic acid found in mycobacterial cell wall which plays an important role in photocatalytic cell inactivation efficiency, since the cell wall is the first barrier of the inactivation process.

Figure1- (a) Disinfection efficiency of synthesized NPs with respect to aerosolized *E. coli*
 (b) Impact of type of bioaerosol on disinfection efficiency

CONCLUSIONS

TiO₂ and varying concentrations of Cu doped TiO₂ were synthesized and coated on a steel plate and tested for bioaerosol disinfection efficiency inside a customized photocatalytic reactor under varying experimental parameters. The disinfection efficiency was found to be maximum at residence time of 90 mins which was 82.63 however not much rise is seen compared to disinfection efficiency achieved at 60 mins which was found to be 78.43%. For three RH conditions, efficiency was found to be (dry condition 55.34%, moderate RH 78.13% and high humidity 71.63%). Synthesized Cu-TiO₂ showed a decrease in the band gap and could excite electrons in the visible range, 5% Cu-TiO₂ was found to have a maximum disinfection efficiency of 93.87%. Disinfection efficiency for gram positive bacteria *M. smegmatis* was found to be less than gram negative *E. coli*.

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EVALUATION OF BIOAEROSOL POLLUTION IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN: IMPACTS AND INSIGHTS

M. IKBAL, R. SINGH, A. BHATNAGAR, AND R. KUMAR¹

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute,
(Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005 (India)

¹ Corresponding Author: R. Kumar, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra-282 005, India.

ABSTRACT

Aerosols play a crucial role in both climate change and public health, significantly influencing cloud condensation nuclei and contributing to the spread of various epidemic diseases. The relationship between aerosols and disease transmission is primarily attributed to their biotic components. This study focuses on the measurement and characterization of bioaerosols over the Indo-Gangetic Plain, where levels of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} exceed the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) set in India. Both bacterial and fungal concentrations were found to be within the reported ranges, with bacterial concentrations notably higher than those of fungi. Gram-positive bacteria constitute 75% of the bacterial population, while Gram-negative bacteria make up the remaining 25%. Seven different fungal species were identified, with *Aspergillus niger* being the most prevalent. Meteorological factors, such as temperature and relative humidity, play a key role in determining microbial presence in the atmosphere. Bacterial concentrations are primarily influenced by temperature, whereas fungal concentrations are more closely linked to relative humidity.

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Air Quality, Fungal Spores, Bacterial Aerosols, Airborne Pathogens

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are particles of biological origin that include bacteria, fungi, viruses, and pollen, sourced from plants, animals, soil, water, and the waste products of living organisms (Ingole et al., 2020). They can make up between 5% and 80% of ambient aerosol particles. Exposure to outdoor bioaerosols can lead to adverse health effects in humans. For instance, outdoor airborne allergens like pollen and fungal spores are linked to respiratory allergies and asthma (Kumari et al., 2011). Additionally, outdoor bacterial bioaerosols are commonly associated with agriculture, as they tend to deposit on plant leaves and stems. Therefore, monitoring outdoor bioaerosol concentrations is crucial for preventing and managing respiratory diseases (Kumar et al., 2021).

METHODS Culture Preparation for bacteria & fungi: For bacterial cultivation, Nutrient Agar Media (NAM) was prepared by combining a beef extract solution with agar and autoclaving at 121°C for 20 minutes. Fungal cultivation used Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) prepared similarly, with chloramphenicol added to inhibit bacterial growth. Aerosol samples were inoculated onto sterile media plates in a laminar flow hood, and plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours for bacteria and 25°C for 5-7 days for fungi.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the mass concentration of particulate matter PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}.

Sample No.	Time	Location	Concentration ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	
			PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}
1.	10 AM to 5 PM	Sub-Urban	330.4	249.2
2.	10 AM to 5 PM	Sub-Urban	228.3	190.1
3.	10 AM to 5 PM	Sub-Urban	230	150
4.	10 AM to 5 PM	Sub-Urban	190.6	139.1
5.	10 AM to 5 PM	Sub-Urban	215.7	110.7

Table 1: Aerosol Mass Concentration During the Study Period

Culture Technique was used to determine the microbiological components of aerosol.

Figure 2. Culture Image of Bacteria and Fungi

CONCLUSIONS

The concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were measured in ambient air at a suburban site in Agra, located within the Indo-Gangetic Plain. Both particulate matter levels significantly exceeded the limits set by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) in India. Agra has been one of the most polluted cities in India for over a decade, with little improvement in air quality. The biological components of the aerosols, specifically bacteria and fungi, were analyzed. Total microbial concentrations in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} ranged from 100 to 1000 colony-forming units per cubic meter (cfu/m^3), with bacterial concentrations exceeding those of fungi. The majority of bacteria observed were white, with 75% being gram-positive and 25% gram-negative. Seven types of fungi were identified in the aerosol samples, with *Aspergillus niger* being the most prevalent species. Temperature was found to be a key factor influencing bacterial growth and concentration, while relative humidity significantly affected fungal populations.

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EVALUATING DEPOSITION EFFICIENCY IN RESPIRATORY SYSTEMS USING A COMBINED LOSS FUNCTION AND OPTIMIZATION METHOD

R. DEY^{1,3}, H.K. PATNI², AND S. ANAND^{1,3}

¹Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai - 400085, India.

²Radiation Safety Systems Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai - 400085,

³Homi Bhabha National Institute, Anushaktinagar Mumbai - 400094, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Transport, Regression Analysis, Deposition, CFPD.

INTRODUCTION

Understanding deposition efficiency in respiratory systems is crucial for evaluating the impact of aerosols on human health. This study employs a model function incorporating parameters related to aerosol dynamics to analyse two datasets representing different respiratory flow conditions. We identified the key parameters governing deposition efficiency (DE) in the first bifurcation (BB₁) and then employed Huber loss function combined with L-BFGS-B (Limitedmemory Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno with Box constraints) optimization to obtain the fitting parameters.

METHODS

Computational fluid particle dynamics modelling in Respiratory geometry

In this study Adult Mesh Reference Computational Phantom (MRCP) [1]-based geometry is implemented in Computational Fluid and Particle Dynamics (CFPD) simulations using Aerosolved code [2, 3] to explore regional and local aerosol deposition patterns. The study examined two inhalation flow rates, 7 L/min and 15 L/min, with a polydisperse aerosol size distribution (CMD 1 μm , $\sigma_g = 2.5$) at the inlet, resolved using 15 sections for droplet diameters ranging from ~ 35.5 nm to 12.67 μm .

Deposition Patterns and Stokes Number Analysis

To explore the deposition patterns within the bronchial bifurcations, the DE in the BB₁ region was analysed as a function of the Stokes number (Stk). The Stokes number was numerically calculated using the average velocity (U) and diameter (D) of the BB₁ region. In this region, the deposition is mainly governed by inertial impaction and gravitational sedimentation and the combined deposition efficiency (DE_{i+s}) can be expressed in terms of linear or non-linear term of the individual deposition efficiencies (DE_i, DE_s) with the following form [3]

$$DE_{i+s} = (DE_i^p + DE_s^p)^{1/p} \quad (1)$$

where DE is the impaction and/or sedimentation induced deposition efficiency for a given bifurcating section and $p = 1 - 3$. Furthermore, DE_i and DE_s can be expressed as a function of Stokes number (Stk) and Stk/Re^2 , where Re is fluid Reynolds number as given by [5,6]

$$DE_i = 100(1 - 1/aStk^b + 1) \quad (2)$$

$$the DE_s = 100(1 - 1/c(Stk/Re^2)^d + 1) \quad (3)$$

where, a , b , c , d are fitting parameters and $Stk = \frac{\rho_p d_p^2 U C_c}{18 \mu D}$ with C_c being Cunningham slip correction factor and μ being viscosity of the fluid and ρ_p and d_p are particle density and diameter respectively.

Regression Analysis for Optimization of Parameters

To establish a relationship between DE and Stk , we need to determine the values of the fitting parameters (a , b , c , d and p as given in Eq. 1, 2 and 3). Thus, we performed parameter optimization using a robust statistical approach to enhance accuracy. A Python-based routine was developed, and the process involved three steps: (1) Defining a robust loss function used in regression problems, which was accomplished by employing the Huber loss function, (2) Defining an objective function to minimize the Huber loss between observed and predicted values while incorporating a regularization term to mitigate overfitting, and finally, (3) Employing an optimization algorithm tailored for large-scale optimization problems. The L-BFGS-B method was utilized, which is particularly advantageous when dealing with high-dimensional parameter spaces. The analysis involved two primary datasets corresponding to two flow rates. Both datasets consisted of simulated values for DE and corresponding average Stk values. An objective function was defined to minimize the Huber loss between observed and predicted values while incorporating a regularization term to mitigate overfitting. The Huber loss [7] is defined as follows:

$$L_{\delta}(y, f(x)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(y - f(x))^2 & \text{for } |y - f(x)| \leq \delta \\ \delta \cdot \left(|y - f(x)| - \frac{1}{2}\delta \right) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where y is the true value, $f(x)$ is the predicted value, δ is a threshold parameter that determines the sensitivity of the loss function to outliers. For values of the prediction close to the true value (within δ), the loss is quadratic, while for larger residuals, it becomes linear, thus mitigating the influence of outliers. In our study, the objective function was crafted to evaluate the discrepancies between the observed deposition efficiency values and those predicted by our model. The objective function was expressed as follows:

$$\text{Objective} = L_{Huber}(\text{Data 1}) + L_{Huber}(\text{Data 2}) + \text{Regularization} \quad (5)$$

Additionally, a regularization term was incorporated to penalize large values of the parameters, thus preventing overfitting. This term is typically structured as $\lambda \sum_i r_i^2$, where r_i represents the model parameters, and λ is a regularization coefficient. The combination of the Huber loss and regularization in the objective function enables a balance between fitting the data well and maintaining model simplicity.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The deposition profile on BB1 for a particle size of $0.19 \mu\text{m}$ is shown in Fig. 1, revealing a non-identical deposition pattern at the front and back sides of this region. Fig. 2 shows that the deposition efficiency increased with the Stokes number and was also a function of the Reynolds number, following a non-linear trend described by a logistic function with parameters $a = 0.232$, $b = 0.635$, $c = 1.52$, $d = 0.259$, and $p = 3$. Local deposition profiles can only be revealed through CFPD simulations.

Fig. 1 Front and back aerosol deposition profile for a particle size of $0.19 \mu\text{m}$ on BB1 revealed from CFPD simulations

Fig. 2 Particle deposition efficiency at different Reynolds numbers vs. non-dimensional parameter (Stk) for first bifurcation (BB1)

CONCLUSIONS

This regression analysis successfully models an analytical expression for deposition efficiency in relation to the Stokes number under varying respiratory conditions. The analysis highlights the importance of flow conditions in respiratory aerosol dynamics. Further improvements are suggested for higher Stokes numbers by employing higher flow rates and particle sizes. However, local deposition patterns remain resolvable only through CFPD simulations.

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EFFECTS OF AMBIENT AIR POLLUTION ON LEARNING OUTCOMES AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN IN INDIA

N. SINGH¹, P. JOSHI², AND S. DEY¹

¹ Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi, India.

² Amity Institute of Public Health and Hospital Administration, Amity University, Noida.

KEYWORDS: Air Pollution, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and child learning outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Ambient air pollution has been linked to cardiovascular and respiratory diseases and is increasingly recognized for its impact on children’s neurodevelopment. However, the evidence on how current air pollution affects children’s academic performance is more limited. Studies from the UK and the US have shown that traffic-related air pollution and exposure to particulate matter are associated with reduced cognitive development. This study seeks to investigate the relationship between exposure to ambient air pollution and the learning outcomes of school-going children. We will utilize nationally representative learning outcome datasets—the National Achievement Survey (NAS)—in conjunction with India-specific ambient air pollution exposure data.

METHODS

We used NAS, a comprehensive assessment carried out at the national level to gather data on the learning achievements (language and mathematics) of students in Classes 3. Approximately 3.4 million students were assessed on learning outcomes in 2017. The satellite-derived annual PM_{2.5} concentrations were taken from Dey et. al., 2020 and Katoch et. al., 2023. For NO₂ exposure, we used a new 100 m × 100 m spatial scale database we developed using satellitebased land use regression modelling (Singh et al., 2024). We conducted the epidemiological analysis using generalized linear mixed-effects models with Gaussian and logit links to assess learning outcomes and air pollutants—the model was adjusted for potential confounders.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A 10-unit increase in air pollution is associated with a decrease in children’s learning performance.

	PM_{2.5}	NO₂
Language	−0.13*** (−0.17, −0.87)	−0.12* (−0.25, −0.01)
Mathematics	−0.08*** (−0.11, −0.05)	−0.04 (−0.14, 0.05)

Table 1: Odds ratio of air pollution (single pollutant model) and NAS 2017 learning outcomes—class 3. Note: ***p_i0.005, **p_i0.05, *p_i0.5

Figure 2: District-wise spatial distribution of NAS’s overall average performance (%) of all questions surveyed for Language and Mathematics for Class 3 in 2017.

Specifically, a 10-unit increase in PM2.5 is associated with reductions in language learning and mathematics performance by 0.13% and 0.08%, respectively, according to NAS 2017 data. For NO2, the reductions are 0.12% in language learning and 0.04% in mathematics performance. These findings are in line with existing literature from the US, which reported a 0.03% reduction in 3rd-grade math scores with maximum PM2.5 exposures, and the UK, which found a 0.04% reduction in math scores with short-term NO2 exposure.

CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary modeling results from the NAS 2017, a government-based survey, show a consistent alignment in the impact of air pollution on academic performance among class 3 students.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Clean Air Fund.

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AIR QUALITY AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OVER A METROPOLITAN CITY IN EASTERN HIMALAYAN FOOTHILL

J. BISWAS¹, B. K. BANERJEE¹, B. PATHAK^{2,3}, P. DUTTA⁴

¹Department of Physics, Pandu College, Guwahati-781012, Assam, India

²Department of Physics, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh-786004, Assam, India

³Centre for Atmospheric Studies, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh-786004, Assam, India

⁴Department of Mathematics, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh-786004, Assam, India

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) is considered the most dangerous pollutant in almost all the urban areas of the world. The main man-made sources contributing to particles smaller than 10 micrometers (PM₁₀) in diameter are basically traffic, industry, construction, agriculture and forestry, fossil fuel power plants etc. PM₁₀ particles can get deep into human lungs and some may even get into the human bloodstream. Respiratory disorders for example Asthma, Bronchitis and Chronic inflammation, are mainly due to PM that appears as dust. Exposure to fine dust particles can cause health effects such as eye, nose, throat and lung irritation, sneezing, coughing, runny nose, shortness of breath etc. The rapid growth of urban areas highlights a major issue, as expansion increases air pollution and poses serious risks to human health. Road dust (Guttikunda et al., 2014), which accounts for up to 30-40% of PM₁₀ pollution in most cities, poses a significant concern, with manual sweeping often leading to the resuspension of dust into the air. Unplanned land use and land cover (LULC) changes, driven by rapid urbanization, significantly worsen air pollution leading to increased public health risks (Saha et al., 2024). Transportation is a significant contributor to PM_{2.5} pollution in India, with emissions from vehicles adding to the overall levels of fine particulate matter, particularly in urban areas (Venkataraman et al., 2018, Brauer et al., 2019). Respiratory disorders for example Asthma, Bronchitis and Chronic inflammation, are the most frequent illnesses caused by PM which appears as dust particles (Zaheer et al., 2018). The PM contained resulting from different sources upon human breathing produces serious effects on the lungs, heart, skin, arteries, and eyes (Jeong et al., 2011; Neghab et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2012).

In this study, we have analyzed the air pollutants and their effects on air quality over Guwahati from March 2019 to August 2024, one of India's rapidly growing cities. The land use and land cover of the Guwahati have changed significantly. Owing to the expansion of the city, more land is being used for various purposes, particularly in built-up regions used for habitation. We have also investigated LULC changes during 2019 and 2024 and compared air quality data from the Guwahati metro area with nearby rural locations. This comparative analysis indicates how urbanization impacts air quality and the urban-rural dynamics of pollution levels.

METHODS

To assess air quality in Guwahati, data are obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of India (<https://cpcb.nic.in/real-time-air-quality-data/>). The CPCB operates a network of 233 monitoring stations across the country, collaborating with State Pollution Control Boards and other agencies under the National Air Quality Monitoring Programme (NAMP). Air quality measurements focused on pollutants like Particulate Matter i.e. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂), Nitrogen Monoxide (NO), Ammonia (NH₃) etc. The Air

Quality Index (AQI) is calculated based on CPCB standards. The sub-index (I_p) for a given pollutant concentration (C_p) as based on the ‘linear segmented principle’ was computed using the formula:

$$I_p = [(IHI - ILO) / (BHI - BLO) \times (C_p - BLO)] + ILO$$

Where:

BHI and BLO are the breakpoint concentrations,

IHI and ILO are the corresponding AQI values.

The final AQI was determined as the maximum sub-index:

$$AQI = \max(I_p) \text{ (where, } p = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

Additionally, Land Use Land Cover (LULC) data was downloaded from Landsat 8, which provides detailed imagery that enables the analysis of land use changes over time. This dataset includes nine spectral bands that capture various wavelengths, facilitating the assessment of vegetation, urban development, and other land cover types.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The temporal variations of $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} and AQI from March 2019 to August 2024 over Guwahati are shown in Figure 1(a), Figure 1(b) and Figure 1(c) respectively. During winter, $PM_{2.5}$ levels range from $150 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $250 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The pre-monsoon season of April and May in 2023 and 2024 shows a remarkable rise in both $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations, significantly higher compared to previous years.

Figure 1(a): Monthly variations of $PM_{2.5}$ over Guwahati from March 2019 to August 2024.

The monsoonal months consistently suppress PM concentrations due to heavy rainfall, which efficiently clears particulate matter from the atmosphere. A standout observation is

the spike in March 2021, where PM_{2.5} concentrations exceeded 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Similarly, January 2022 holds the record for the highest PM levels throughout the entire 6-year study, indicating it as the most polluted month during this period.

Figure 1(b): Monthly variations of PM₁₀ over Guwahati from March 2019 to August 2024.

Over this period, the AQI consistently fluctuates within the poor to moderate range, with values typically between 200 and 300. Notably, significant spikes occur in January, where AQI levels exceed 350 points. During the pre-monsoon season, March emerges as the most critical month, with AQI values rising sharply from 200 to 350.

Figure 1(c): Monthly variations of AQI over Guwahati from March 2019 to August 2024.

After this peak, air quality gradually improves in the subsequent pre-monsoon months. The monsoon season brings relief, with AQI values generally falling into the good category, as heavy rainfall helps clear the air of particulate matter, keeping values below 100. However, in the post-monsoon season, air quality again begins to deteriorate steadily from October to November. The most polluted period during these 6 years was observed in January 2022, with AQI levels nearing 400, marking the worst air quality during the study.

The variations of air pollutants along with AQI across urban and rural locations of Guwahati are also compared for the years 2019 and 2023. Figure 2 presents a comparative analysis of these pollutants across the two monitoring stations, highlighting the trends and variations observed throughout 2023. The Guwahati Railway Monitoring Station indicates higher PM_{2.5} concentrations during the winter months; however, values generally remain consistent during the post-monsoon period. In contrast, the Guwahati Airport exhibits significant increases in PM₁₀ concentrations during the monsoon months of 2023 year. Despite this, the PM₁₀ levels at the railway station are typically lower than those observed at the airport, making it a more favourable site when compared to historical climatology.

Figure 2: Comparison of monthly average pollutant levels (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO, AQI, NO₂, and SO₂) in 2023 between Railway Guwahati and Airport Guwahati station

The elevated PM₁₀ levels at the airport may be attributed to ongoing construction activities and infrastructure development in the surrounding area, which likely impacts the AQI during the monsoon months. Additionally, SO₂ concentrations at the railway monitoring station are

notably higher, averaging around 25 to 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, compared to those measured at the airport. NH_3 concentrations remain relatively stable during the winter months. In contrast, NO concentrations at the railway monitoring station fluctuate, typically ranging between 4 to 6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, the airport monitoring station recorded a significant peak in NO levels

during December, reaching approximately 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This notable increase warrants further investigation to understand the underlying causes and implications for air quality in the area.

Figure 3: Land Use Land Cover (LULC) maps for 2019 and 2024 in land cover categories between the two years

Considering the observed variations in air quality, it is crucial to examine the Land Use Land Cover (LULC) changes in the region, as these can significantly influence pollutant concentrations. Figure 3 illustrates the LULC maps from 2019 to 2024, revealing a substantial increase in built-up areas, particularly on the eastern side of the metropolitan district.

Figure 4: Percentage wise comparison of LULC features between 2019 and 2024

Over this period, approximately 10% of vegetation cover has diminished, while built-up areas have expanded by 15% (Figure 4). This drastic shift in LULC is likely contributing to the rising levels of particulate matter (PM) pollutants, particularly during construction activities. Additionally, the increase in population density and transportation infrastructure plays a major role in exacerbating air quality issues in the region.

CONCLUSIONS

The Air Quality Index (AQI) over the past five years predominantly fluctuated within the

poor to moderate range, with January 2022 recording the highest pollution level with an AQI of nearly 400. Monsoon rains improved air quality significantly, keeping AQI values below 50. Winter PM_{2.5} concentrations ranged from 150 to 250 µg/m³, with a notable spike above 400 µg/m³ in March 2021. The years 2023 and 2024 saw significant increases in PM concentrations during the pre-monsoon months compared to previous years. Monitoring station comparisons showed that the Ghy Railway Station had higher PM_{2.5} levels in winter, while the Ghy Airport experienced increased PM₁₀ concentrations during monsoon months, likely due to nearby construction. SO₂ levels at the railway station averaged 25 to 30 µg/m³, surpassing those at the airport. Notably, fluctuations in NO levels at both stations highlight the need for further investigation into air quality. The Land Use Land Cover (LULC) changes from 2019 to 2024 revealed a 15% increase in built-up areas and a 10% decrease in vegetation cover, contributing to rising PM levels amid urbanization.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB). The authors are thankful to the Central Pollution Control Board for Live Air Quality Monitoring Station Data.

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ESTIMATING LONG AND SHORT-TERM PREMATURE MORTALITY ATTRIBUTABLE TO CROP RESIDUE BURNING IN PUNJAB, HARYANA AND DELHI

P. JOSHI¹, A. BISWAL[†], P. MANGARAJ, K. UEDA, R. KHAIWAL, Y. MATSUMI, T. NAKAYAMA, F. IMAM, S. DEY

Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN), Kyoto, Japan
Amity Institute of Public Health and Hospital Administration, Amity University, Noida, Uttar Pr Hokkaido University, Hokkaido, Japan
Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research (PGIMER), Chandigarh, Ind Nagoya University, Nagoya, Japan Nagasaki University, Nagasaki, Japan
Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India
Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), Japan

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Premature Mortality, Crop Residue Burning, Health Risk

INTRODUCTION

Crop residue burning (CRB) plays a major role in air pollution and the associated health burden in India. At the start of the Rabi season, particularly in October and November, the northern states of Punjab, Haryana, and Delhi experience high CRB activity. While current research primarily focuses on modelling the resulting air pollution, updating emission inventories, evaluating optimal residue management practices, and analysing the advantages of adjusting burning times, there is a notable lack of studies that specifically assess the population level health impacts of CRB pollution.

METHODS

We estimate long and short-term health impacts attributable to CRB at a fine spatial scale such as the district level, which has not been explored before. The annual or long-term CRB-attributable premature deaths are calculated using the MRBRT risk functions for five major diseases: IHD, Stroke, COPD, Type 2 Diabetes, and Lower Respiratory Infections. The annual district level PM_{2.5} exposure and CRB share to total PM_{2.5} are taken from the SAANS data and WRF simulations as part of the Aakash Project, respectively. We utilize daily gridded PM_{2.5} concentrations derived from in-situ observations (CUPI-G) and WRF-Chem simulations to calculate short-term burden using pre-estimated mortality risk functions at 9x9 km².

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We observe that the annual premature deaths attributed specifically to crop residue burning (CRB) are highest in Punjab's districts, with Ludhiana, Sangrur, Patiala, Firozpur, and Amritsar reporting over 1,000 to 1,500 deaths each. Additionally, daily spikes in CRB exposure could lead to more than a 20% increase in daily mortality in districts heavily affected by burning. Out of the total mortality attributable to PM_{2.5}, the CRB-attributable deaths are approximately 40% based on WRF simulations during the peak CRB days in the entire region. At the state level on a daily scale, the CRB-attributable mortality (as a portion of total PM_{2.5}-attributed deaths) goes up to 22% in Delhi, 43% in Haryana, and 51% in

Punjab on the peak burning days.

CONCLUSIONS

To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first attempt at estimating long and short term crop residue burning attributable to premature deaths at the district level. Our findings help identify the most vulnerable districts to the adverse impact of crop residue burning and underscore the public health benefits of mitigating crop residue burning in Northern India.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported under the Aakash Project at the Research Institute of Humanity and Nature, Kyoto, Japan (RIHN: a constituent member of NIHU) Project No. 14200133.

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HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF BIOAEROSOLS AND PARTICULATE MATTER ISOLATED FROM DUMPING SITES, DEHRADUN, INDIA

S. DEOLI¹, *, SHIVI SHROTRIYA¹, SHAKUNTALA RANA¹, *, VIJAY SHRIDHAR¹

¹Environmental Pollution and Assessment Laboratory, SENR, Doon University, Dehradun

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Particulate Matter, Dumping Site, Hazard Quotient, Bacterial Dosage, HYSPLIT, MPPD.

INTRODUCTION

The dumping sites in Dehradun are significant sources of environmental pollution, contributing to air quality contamination and posing health risks to nearby communities. This study focuses on bioaerosols and particulate matter (PM) measured at two prominent dumping sites in Dehradun, Uttarakhand, namely Kargi Chowk and Keshavpuri Doiwala. The assessment of their concentrations and potential health risks provides crucial insights into environmental contamination at these locations.

METHODS

The dispersion and health risks associated with bacteria, fungi, and particulate matter (PM_{1.1}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀) were evaluated at the two dumping sites. Bioaerosol concentrations were measured using appropriate bioaerosol and particulate sampling techniques. Dispersion was assessed using the HYSPLIT trajectory model, while health risks were quantified through the hazard quotient (HQ) method, considering values greater than 1 as significant. PM concentrations were measured, and the Multiple Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model was used to assess particulate matter deposition in the respiratory system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

At Kargi Chowk, bacterial and fungal concentrations were (5023.2±223) CFU/m³ and (3737± 219.3) CFU/m³, respectively, while at Keshavpuri Doiwala, they were (4821 ± 128.6) CFU/m³ and (3429±116) CFU/m³. Landfills are major bioaerosol sources, releasing bacteria and fungi due to organic waste decomposition [Sánchez-Monedero et al., 2008; Kamdi et al., 2024]. HYSPLIT model predictions showed bioaerosol dispersion from Kargi Chowk (max. 5.92E-11 mass/m³) toward Clement Town, while Keshavpuri Doiwala had higher concentrations (1.17E -10 mass/m³), dispersing toward Bhanja Wala. HQ analysis indicated significant health risks for landfill workers, especially at Keshavpuri Doiwala

[Pankhurst et al., 2011].

PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM_{1.1} concentrations at Kargi Chowk were (397.5 ± 257.6) µg/m³, (244.9 ± 125.14) µg/m³, and (132.5 ± 21.8) µg/m³, respectively, while at Keshavpuri Doiwala, they were (388.7 ± 200.2) µg/m³, (169.3 ± 44.1) µg/m³, and (51.3 ± 7.3) µg/m³. High PM levels at landfill sites were attributed to vehicular activity, waste handling, and decomposition [Sakai et al., 2006]. The MPPD model was employed to estimate PM deposition in various respiratory regions across age groups, highlighting the heightened vulnerability of older individuals [Madhwal et al., 2020].

Figure 2: Particle size distribution of Bioaerosol and Particulate Matter concentration at two dumping sites.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the need for routine bioaerosol level monitoring and further research on bioaerosol impacts to mitigate health risks in landfill sites. The significant health risks identified, particularly for landfill workers, emphasize the importance of control measures to reduce exposure to bioaerosols and particulate matter.

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AMBIENT BIOAEROSOL CONCENTRATIONS AND HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT ON CHAR DHAM YATRA ROUTE IN GAUCHAR, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA: A STUDY FROM A HILLY REGION

S. SHROTRIYA^{1*}, S. RANA¹, AND V. SHRIDHAR¹

Environmental Pollution and Assessment Laboratory, SENR, Doon University, Dehradun,

KEYWORDS: Aerosol, Bioaerosol monitoring, Pilgrim services, Char Dham Yatra, Health risk, HYSPLIT, MPPD.

INTRODUCTION

This study investigates aerosol and bioaerosol concentrations, including bacteria, fungi, and other microorganisms, along the Char Dham Yatra route in Gauchar, Uttarakhand, India, assessing their associated health risks. The influx of pilgrims during the Yatra contributes to increased particulate matter (PM) and bioaerosol levels, particularly in high-traffic and ecologically sensitive areas. This study evaluates aerosol and bioaerosol exposure and aims to provide data for future public health interventions.

METHODS

Particulate matter (PM_{1.1}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀) and Bioaerosol concentrations were measured across three distinct periods: before the Yatra (baseline period), onset of the Yatra (active phase when pilgrim traffic was at its peak), and after the Yatra opened (post-opening period with a stabilized but ongoing flow of pilgrims). Concentrations were measured using standard equipment, and microbial analysis was conducted to identify species of bacteria and fungi. The HYSPLIT model was employed to assess the transport of bioaerosols (Kamdi et al., 2024) and with the MPPD model estimates particle deposition in different lung regions based on particle size and respiratory parameters.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Before the Char Dham Yatra, bioaerosol concentrations averaged (231 ± 543) CFU/m³ for bacteria and (301 ± 502) CFU/m³ for fungi. At the Yatra's onset, bacterial levels rose to (874 ± 1554) CFU/m³ and fungal levels to (600 ± 1012) CFU/m³, followed by a slight decrease during the Yatra. Bacterial concentrations increased to (874 ± 1554) CFU/m³ and fungal concentrations to (600 ± 1012) CFU/m³. HYSPLIT modelling indicated increased pollutant dispersion, with high-concentration zones expanding and lower concentrations spreading beyond Gauchar. Similarly, PM concentrations rise from $45.476 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (PM_{1.1}), $89.394 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (PM_{2.5}), and $135.672 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (PM₁₀) before the Yatra to $120.75 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $194.75 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and $234.275 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at the onset of the Yatra. During the Yatra, PM_{1.1} at $113.156 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, PM_{2.5} at $142.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and PM₁₀ at $210.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ were observed. These trends, driven by tourism and traffic, are consistent with studies by (Ghosh et al., 2015) and (Kulshrestha et al., 2009). Statistical analysis revealed strong correlations between traffic, PM, and bioaerosols. Health risk assessments showed no significant risk (HQ and HI \leq 1), but MPPD results highlighted higher PM_{1.1} deposition in older individuals (18 and 21 years), suggesting greater respiratory vulnerability (Madhwal et al., 2020).

Figure 2: Particle Size Distribution of Bioaerosol and Particulate Matter Concentration at Three Phases of Char Dham Yatra.

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights the need for air quality management during the pilgrimage season. Elevated PM and bioaerosol levels emphasize the importance of monitoring and mitigating health risks for pilgrims and residents in these high-traffic areas.

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MICROBIAL CONCENTR

ATION ON THE NATURAL SURFACE OF TULSI (OCIMUM SANCTUM)

MAMTA ¹, G.P. SATSANGI ¹, AND R. KUMAR ²

¹ Department of Botany, ² Department of Chemistry
Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute (Deemed University),
Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005

Email: ashjangid@gmail.com / rkschem@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Natural surfaces either may be plants and tree leaves or the deposition in the form of water vapor or ice nuclei into the atmosphere. Tree or plant leaves have wide open surfaces for the deposition of the aerosol matter present in the atmosphere and their cultivation on natural surfaces makes it easy to detect the presence of atmospheric biogenic material in the air. Leaves of Tulsi (Ocimum) are being chewed in India and if it is contaminated it affects human health. This study compares microorganisms on leaf surfaces of Ocimum on roadside and non-roadside environments. The mean dry deposition flux of total microbial components on leaf surface of Ocimum during the present study at site A is 843.6 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and varies from 12.5 to 1253.1 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹; bacterial deposition flux is 772.0 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and varies from 438.6 to 1253.1 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ while fungi deposition flux is 71.6 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and ranges from 12.53 to 125.3 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹. At site B, mean value of TMC flux is 241.3 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and ranges from 7.6 to 383.7 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹, flux of bacteria is 216.6 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and ranges from 89.5 to 383.7 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ while flux of fungi is 24.7 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹ and ranges from 7.6 and 36.2 cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹. The deposition flux is highest for bacteria at both sites. It may be due to the fact that bacterial concentration in the atmosphere is higher than fungal concentration. 16s rRNA sequencing methods have been used to identify bacterial isolates.

KEYWORDS: Atmospheric deposition, Ocimum leaves, dry deposition flux, microbial component.

INTRODUCTION

The deposition of air pollutants in roadside area plants is a significant environmental issue, particularly in urban and high-traffic regions. Plants growing near roads are constantly exposed to a variety of air pollutants from vehicular emissions and industrial activities. Among many of the major mechanisms, by which air pollutants can be delivered to sensitive surfaces, 'Dry deposition' is an important mechanism (Kumar et al., 2006). The natural surface like plant leaves is exposed as leaves have a broader surface area. They permit air to deposit its particulate matter onto its open natural surface and play a significant role in transferring atmospheric pollutants to terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. It is estimated that the terrestrial leaf surface area that might be colonized by microbes is about 6.4×10^8 km². The microbial communities in the atmosphere varied including numerous of the different genera of bacteria, fungi, yeasts, and algae (Mamta et al., 2015). But bacteria are by far the most abundant inhabitants of the phyllo sphere and fungi which are considered as temporary inhabitants of leaf surfaces. Seasonally the highest colonization of microbes is seen in the rainy season compared to dry and warm seasons (Ercolani, 1991). However, in a country

like India where dry conditions prevail for most of the year, dry deposition is an important process for the transfer of materials from the atmosphere to the earth's surface. A limited study on the dry deposition of abiotic components to surfaces has been reported however, none has been reported on dry deposition flux biotic components on natural surfaces. Ocimum popularly known as 'Tulsi' in India has a unique position in the Indian community as they worship it as well as chew its leaves as they are anti-allergic materials. Hence, the study on dry deposition of bacteria and fungi on leaves of the Ocimum plant is of paramount importance.

METHODS

The dry deposition samples on Ocimum leaves were collected using the surface washing method. Ten leaves of Ocimum were tagged, cleaned with ultra-pure water, air dried, and exposed for ten days on non-dewy, non-foggy, and non-rainy days. Aliquots of the dry deposition samples were used for microbial analysis using culture techniques. Bacteria were isolated using Nutrient Agar Medium (NAM) and fungi were isolated using the PDA media. Identification was carried out on the basis of the shape, size, and color of the colonies under a light microscope and compared with a standard description of fungi and bacteria. The dry deposition flux was determined by dividing the colony forming unit of bacteria and fungi deposited on leaves with a surface area of leaves (m²) and exposed time (day). The concentration of fungal and bacterial concentrations in the air is expressed as a number of colonies forming unit per cubic meter in air (cfu m⁻³) while dry deposition flux was represented as cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹. The phylloplane of bio aerosol on Ocimum leaf was analyzed by Scanning Electron microscope (JEOL JSM 5800I) from the National Institute of Oceanography, Goa and information about the morphology of bacteria, fungi, and other particulate matter which adhere to the surface were obtained.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Microbial deposition on leaf surface is a natural phenomenon but it shows the variation between polluted and non-polluted sites. Once the microbial components get released in the atmosphere from the sources, they may find particles as a substrate or they may individually travel from one place to another and finally reach the earth's surface via dry and wet deposition. The dry deposition is the major pathway of removal of microbial pollutants from the atmosphere to earth's surface in the country like India as dry condition prevails for most of the year.

Parameter	Polluted Mean ± SD (Min. to max.)	Non-polluted Mean ± SD (Min. to max.)
Total microbial count	843.6 ± 345.9 (12.5 to 1253.1)	241.3 ± 114.2 (7.6 to 383.7)
Bacterial count	772.0 ± 298.4 (438.6 to 1253.1)	216.6 ± 132.9 (89.5 to 383.7)
Fungal counts	71.6 ± 47.6 (12.5 to 125.3)	24.7 ± 11.3 (7.6 to 36.2)

Table 1: Average, standard deviation and range of dry deposition flux ($\text{cfu cm}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) of microbial components on *Ocimum sanctum* leaves.

The table shows the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum of dry deposition flux of the total microbial component (TMC), fungi components, and bacterial components on the leaf surface (phylloplane) of *Ocimum* (Tulsi). The deposition flux is the highest for bacteria at both sites. It may be due to the fact that bacterial concentration in the atmosphere is higher than the fungal concentration. Amongst the sites, the deposition flux at site A is higher than at site B. It is akin to site characteristics. Site A is close to the road and hence polluted, while site B is away from the main road and hence less polluted. About seven genera of fungi were observed and the relative abundance was highest for *Aspergillus*. Gram-positive bacteria are more in comparison to gram-negative bacteria. White and red color bacteria were more abundant compared to others, while coccus-shaped bacteria were maximum compared to rod-shaped. Molecular characterization of dominant bacterial isolates was carried out by NCBI, Gene Bank, USA and two bacteria were found to be common i.e., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Korcuria* sps. (Accession number of *Korcuria* sps.: KU937323).

CONCLUSION

The *Ocimum* (Tulsi) leaf exhibits a high rate of dry microbial deposition, largely due to its rough, textured surface that enhances particle accumulation. The presence of fungi and bacteria on Tulsi leaves is notably higher in roadside areas compared to non-polluted environments, highlighting the impact of pollution on microbial deposition. For health considerations, some of these microbial species are potentially harmful, so it is crucial to properly wash *Ocimum* leaves before consumption to minimize health risks. These findings underscore the importance of environmental factors in determining microbial load on plant surfaces, suggesting a need for caution when using plants from polluted areas for medicinal or dietary purposes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The financial assistance from the ugc major project is gratefully acknowledged.

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EVOLUTION OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN THE INDOOR BIOAEROSOLS VIA EXPOSED ANIMAL DIVERSITY

A. SINGH, Y. K. VISHWAKARMA, R. S. SINGH

Department of Chemical Engineering, IIT (BHU), Varanasi 221005, Uttar Pradesh, India

Email: rssingh.che@iitbhu.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Antibiotic Resistance, Bacteria, Toxicity Assessment, Indoor Air.

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are the microbial component of aerosols, which mainly originate from biological origin. The common examples of bioaerosols are bacteria, fungi, viruses, pollen, and some allergens from plants and animals. Due to their size, they can be suspended in the air and can travel long distances, affecting the climate. Apart from the climate, their size, and chemical properties, their exposure affects the health of humans, animals, and plants, too. Due to their biological nature, they show multiplication properties, and sometimes they are more harmful during mutation. Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) represent an emerging and uncertain threat to public health and pose ecological risks that have garnered global attention. While ARG contamination has received considerable attention, most studies concentrate on ARGs in water or soil, overlooking those present in bioaerosols (Chen et.al., 2022, Baghdadi et.al., 2023). This study shows how bioaerosols play a role in ARG transfer, adding to the atmosphere through the in-situ measurement (indoor bioaerosols study).

METHODS

Air sampling was done in the cowshed, where cows were treated with various antibiotics for routine treatment. The Anderson Six-stage viable air sampler was chosen for the air sampling using various culture media. In addition, the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was performed for toxicity assessment to analyse the antibiotic resistance properties of the various isolated bacterial bioaerosols. Further qPCR was also done for the following samples to identify ARG genes carrying microorganisms.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

This study quantified the abundance of ARGs and MGEs in both air and feces during winter and summer using qPCR. The distribution and abundance of ARGs were found to be closely associated with environmental bacterial communities. We found a strong ($r > 0.5$) and significant ($p < 0.05$) positive correlation between bacterial taxa and ARGs, which serve as an indicator of ARGs hosts within bioaerosols.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a significant amount of bioaerosols added to the atmosphere via cattle excreta. This is one of the most challenging issues in the field of bioaerosols study and the new path of antibiotic resistance development via air. Along with this, the present study will help policymakers address the new challenges of air pollution and antibiotic resistance

bioaerosols.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the ARFI project of the ISRO-Geosphere Biosphere Programme.

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BIOAEROSOLS OVER WASTE TREATMENT FACILITY AND ITS IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH: AN ANTHROPOGENIC SOURCE EMISSION

Y. K. VISHWAKARMA¹ AND R. S. SINGH², *

Department of Chemical Engineering and Technology, IIT (BHU), Varanasi 221005, UP

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Antibiotic Resistance, Bacteria, Toxicity Assessment, Outdoor Air.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, urbanization and the population in urban areas are the major sources of solid waste generation. The rate of urbanization is higher in developing nations, so waste generation is also increasing. However, unfortunately, they do not have the good infrastructure to properly manage and treat their MSW. Because of that, the developing countries find that open dumping is the cheapest option for solid waste management (Srivastava et al., 2015). These types of waste disposal sometimes make large waste hills and create different types of environmental problems (UNEP, 2015). In the disposal activities of the MSW, such as tipping, spreading and waste shorting, aerosolization takes place, and these contain microbes. There is limited research has been done on the bioaerosols in the dumpsite in comparison to the landfill and composting processes. Although many activities like tipping and spreading of waste are common at the dumpsite and they have greater health effects and there is no significant control over the safety during the handling, treatment and exposure limit to particulates associated with the bioaerosols (Hoorweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). This study aims to investigate the bacterial and fungal bioaerosols concentration and their size distribution at different points of the waste processing site.

METHODS

Air samples were collected at the Karsara, Varanasi waste-to-energy processing plant and its nearby area using Anderson's six-stage viable impactor. Where different culture media were used to collect the bacterial and fungal bioaerosols. Apart from the size segregations, the metagenomic study was conducted to identify the bioaerosols and the nature of the bioaerosols and determine the possible health impacts of the collected bioaerosols.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Here, the total bacterial concentrations were higher at the leachate treatment facility, while total fungal concentrations were higher at (the loading and unloading sector). The highest bacterial concentration was observed at the fine size range and fungal concentrations were highest in the coarse to fine range of the particle. Isolated bacteria *Alcaligenaceae* and *Stenotrophomonas* are dominant and resistant towards higher concentrations of several antibiotics, while some strains are sensitive towards lower concentrations of some antibiotics.

CONCLUSIONS

Waste treatment processes are one of the major sources of bioaerosols, most of them are pathogenic and resistant to many antibiotics. Apart from the toxicity analysis, this study will

help in the improvement of the waste processing plant infrastructure development and the workers working there.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the ARFI project by the ISRO-GBP program.

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WINTERTIME CHARACTERISTICS OF AEROSOLS IN MIDDLE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN AND ITS TOXICITY ASSESSMENT

S. RANJAN¹, Y. K. VISHWAKARMA² AND R. S. SINGH³

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, IIT (BHU), Varanasi 221005, Uttar Pradesh, India

Email: - rssingh.che@iitbhu.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Oxidative Potential, Particulate Matter, Biomass Burning, Reactive Oxygen Species

INTRODUCTION

Indo-Gangetic plain is one of the major hotspots of aerosols due to its geographical location and various natural and anthropogenic activities. The health effects of the aerosols are significantly associated with their physico-chemical properties. Oxidative potential (OP) of the particulate matters is the most evolving technique for toxicity assessment. This metric measures an aerosol's capacity to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can cause oxidative stress, inflammation, and cellular damage when they come into contact with biological systems. In the present study, the particulate matter was collected by high volume sampler and fine particulate sampler for PM10 and PM2.5 respectively (Nawrot et al., 2009, Perrone et al., 2013). Our results show a significant increase in the OR during biomass burning and anthropogenic activities. Additionally, OP was strongly correlated with certain metals and meteorological variables. Because the OP contains significant new information about PM compositions and features that may assist enhance existing air quality management tools, we recommend using it as a supplementary measure to the PM mass concentration in light of these findings.

METHODS

By transferring electrons from DTT to oxygen through the recycling of molecules like quinones, the DTT assays detect the presence of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by forming DTT disulfide. In short, 340 μ l of ultrapure water and 100 μ l of 0.5 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) are incubated with 10 μ l of PM suspension for 10 minutes at 37 °C. The reaction is then initiated with 50 μ l 1 mM DTT (Sigma, Zwijndrecht, Netherlands) and terminated at predetermined intervals of 0, 10, 20, and 30 minutes. Next, 5,5'-Dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB) (Sigma, Zwijndrecht) is added. A spectrophotometer (SpectraMax 190, Molecular Devices, Sunnyvale, CA) is used to record the absorbance at 412 nm. A spectrophotometer (SpectraMax 190, Molecular Devices, Sunnyvale, CA) is used to record the absorbance at 412 nm. Based on the average of two duplicate readings, the rate of DTT consumption is determined by linear regression of the data as shown in an absorbance versus time plot.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The oxidative potential has been investigated in connection with air quality, specifically because of pollution from automobiles, factories, and other causes. Important conclusions include:

Air Quality: The region's elevated oxidative stress is a result of high particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM10) concentrations.

- 1) Temporal Variation: Because of temperature inversions and higher emissions throughout the winter, oxidative potential frequently fluctuates with seasonal variations, peaking during this time.
- 2) These results highlight the environmental and health challenges posed by the oxidative potential in Varanasi.

CONCLUSIONS

Our findings reveal that there is a significantly higher OP at the sampling location which results in adverse health impacts. The OP measurements data is used to establish information on the toxicity of PM.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was supported by the ARFI-ISRO Grant.

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**THEME 3: APPLICATION OF GEOSPATIAL TECHNIQUES
IN AIR QUALITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE**

MAPPING DIWALI'S ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: AIR QUALITY MONITORING IN AGRA USING QGIS

U. SINGH, S. SINGH¹ And K. YADAV

Department Of Civil Engineering, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra

Email: - Karishmayadav@Dei.Ac.In

KEYWORDS: Qgis, Diwali, Particulate Matter, Firecrackers.

INTRODUCTION

Diwali, the festival of lights, is celebrated with great enthusiasm across India every October and November, with firecrackers playing a central role in the festivities. The detonation of these firecrackers releases trace gases and particulate matter, including metals, into the atmosphere, resulting in dense smoke clouds that vary in concentration based on the composition of the firecrackers used (Chatterjee et al., 2013). To understand the impact of this celebration on air quality, short-term investigations of atmospheric pollutants—specifically PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and CO—were conducted in six sites in Agra, Uttar Pradesh including Sanjay Palace, Manoharpur, Shastri Puram, Shahganj, Avas Vikas and Rohta over three years, from 2021 to 2023. Air pollution, driven by human activities, is a pressing global concern, posing significant risks to environmental health and public well-being, including respiratory diseases, cardiovascular issues, and exacerbated climate change (Pal et al., 2022). This study aims to analyse the levels of pollutants released during Diwali and assess their implications for the environment.

Figure1. Points highlighting the different sites in Agra

METHODOLOGY

Air pollution levels during the Diwali festival were assessed at six sites in Agra, over a three years period. Pollutant data (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and CO) were sourced from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) and further results were processed with the help of QGIS.

RESULTS

The 24-h average concentration of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂ and 8-h average concentration of CO and O₃ in Ambient air during Diwali days from years 2021 to 2023 in Agra are

considered in this study and Figure-2 depicts the result for PM10 and CO for 2023 and 2022 year. In general, out of all pollutants, PM10 and PM2.5 have the highest concentration on days other than Diwali day(Pal et al., 2022).

Health Impact Corelation

During Diwali in Agra, the spike in pollutants significantly correlates with increased emergency room admissions for respiratory issues, including asthma exacerbations, and eye irritation as shown in various studies. This study highlights the emergency room services in Agra in addressing the health risks associated with festive air quality degradation.

Figure 2 and table 1 Shows the Comparison between PM10 and CO for the year 2023 and 2022 & AQI category

AQI category	Colour	
Good	Green	
Satisfactory	Light Green	
Moderate	Yellow	
Poor	Orange	
Very poor	Red	
Severe	Maroon	

	Pre Diwali		During Diwali		Post Diwali	
	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022
PM10						
CO						

CONCLUSION

As the Diwali celebration falls in the winter, the air quality deteriorates due to extreme weather conditions and the deposition of air pollutants at lower levels (Pal et al., 2022). This study analyzed Agra's air pollution levels across three phases: pre-Diwali, during Diwali, and post- Diwali for the years 2021-2023. PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations remained within the permissible range (Moderate AQI category), while CO, NO2, SO2, and O3 levels stayed within the acceptable limit (Good AQI category). Firecracker use during Diwali has a substantial impact on air quality, leading to environmental harm and posing health hazards (Pal et al., 2022). We should strive to celebrate Diwali in a more environmentally friendly manner

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DECADAL CHANGES IN AEROSOL POLLUTION OVER DIFFERENT PARTS OF THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN AND HIMALAYAS

S. RAUL¹, M. DUTTA², A. CHATTERJEE²

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, Bose Institute, Block-EN, Sector-V, Salt Lake, Kolkata

²Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW), New Delhi, India

KEYWORDS: Aerosol, Aerosol Optical Depth, Indo-Gangetic Plain, Himalayas.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the continuous increase in anthropogenic aerosols has raised significant concerns regarding their impacts on climate and the hydrological cycle. Himalayas, which is adjacent to the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), has experienced a considerable increase in air pollution over the past few decades attributed to rapid urban growth, leading to increased industrial activities, construction, vehicular emissions and biomass burning (Dutta and Chatterjee, 2022) and has been identified as the primary source areas of aerosols for the high-altitude Himalayas. As a result of rapid industrialization and urbanization in South Asia, emissions in the atmosphere have increased drastically, which has a significant detrimental impact on Himalayan glaciers (Bond et al., 2013). The Himalayan region with the third-largest ice mass on the earth outside the polar region is at the forefront of climate change. Himalayan glaciers are of immense importance as they provide water resources for the transboundary rivers in Asia and fresh water to more than 1.4 billion people (Immerzeel et al., 2010). The accelerated melting of Himalayan glaciers and the management of water resources are the most important concerns for society, in recent times. Several studies have addressed the aerosol pollution over the IGP and Himalayan region however, the IGP region's impact on the Himalayan environment is less explored and it is crucial to address the recent trends and sources of aerosol pollution over the fragile Himalayan region.

METHODS

Aerosol optical depth (AOD), obtained from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), a remote sensing satellite onboard the Terra and Aqua satellites launched in 1999 and 2002 respectively, was derived using combined dark target and deep blue algorithms from Aqua's daily level 3, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ AOD the recent collection of 6.1; C6.1 (MYD08) data spanning 2000 to 2022. Monthly data of differential AODs were extracted from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA-2) for the same timeframe. MERRA-2 utilizes version 5.12.4 of the GEOS atmospheric data assimilation system, employing a grid resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$ and comprising 72 hybrid vertical layers spanning from the surface up to 0.01 hPa. The analysis of long-term trends over the different parts of the Himalayas, NE India and IGP region was conducted using the well-established Mann-Kendall test. The slope of the trend was determined using the Senslope estimator. Relative Percentage changes every 3 years after 2009 were calculated with respect to the 2000s decade (2000-2009) in every region for the AOD and differential AODs.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Over the Himalayan region, higher AOD is mainly associated with the eastern Himalayas (0.4-0.6) whereas relatively less AOD was observed in the central and western Himalayas (<0.4). Over IGP, the highest aerosol loading is found over the lower IGP (0.4-0.8) followed

by the middle IGP (0.3-0.75) and NE India (0.23-0.54) (figure 1a). Similarly, the highest trend was observed over lower IGP, (0.007-0.016 yr⁻¹) followed by Middle IGP (0.003-0.13 yr⁻¹) and lower IGP (0.007-0.016 yr⁻¹). All the mentioned trends are significant (p-value < 0.05) (figure 2b). Several studies have shown that the high aerosol loading over the eastern part of IGP is associated with its geographical location and meteorology leading to the accumulation of aerosols over this region. We observed that aerosol loading over the Himalayas, IGP as well as NE India was comparatively higher in the 2010s decade than in the 2000s (1b and c). Where anthropogenic activities peaked and played a significant role in the highest increase (0.013-0.019 yr⁻¹) over the eastern part of IGP. During the 2010s, there was a less pronounced upward trend (0.002-0.018 yr⁻¹) of AOD in the study region compared to the preceding decade (2b and c).

Figure 1. Mean AOD over the study region during the years a) 2000-2022 b)2000-2009 (2000s) c) 2010-2019 (2010s)

Figure 2. Trend (per year) of AOD over the study region during the years a) 2000-2022 b)2000-2009 (2000s) c) 2010-2019 (2010s).

CONCLUSION

AOD is highest in both the eastern part of IGP and the eastern Himalayan region. Rapid urbanization and population growth in this region are the most important factors of the high aerosol loading associated with extensive emissions from anthropogenic sources. Mean AOD is comparatively much higher in the last decade than the previous decade in the IGP region as well as in the Himalayan region. Due to uncontrolled emissions in the early 21st century, the policymakers prioritized the IGP region, implementing stringent policies that likely contributed to a reduction in the rate of aerosol pollution in these regions in the last decade.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Bose Institute, Govt. of India for providing the infrastructure to carry out this work. The fellowship of the first author was provided by UGC (University Grants Commission), Govt. of India.

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ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF URBANISATION ON VEGETATION AND AIR QUALITY OVER A SEMI-ARID ENVIRONMENT

R. AGARWAL¹, R. K. BUKHARI¹, T. TURAKHIA² AND R. IYER¹

¹Department of Physics and Electronics, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous) Ahmedabad

²Research Scholar, Gujarat Technological University, Ahmedabad – 382424, India

KEYWORDS: NDVI, NDBI, Air Quality, Pollution, Remote Sensing.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is essential for the economic growth of cities, providing access to better infrastructure facilities, cultural development and employment opportunities. However, unplanned urban development leads to devastating environmental consequences such as reduced vegetation cover, increased air pollution compromising the health and well-being of urban residents. Globally, various studies have recorded this negative impact revealing a direct correlation between increased urban sprawl and deteriorating air quality. This research focuses on analysing specific consequences in Ahmedabad by examining the relationship between urbanization, vegetation health, and air quality, utilizing remote sensing techniques like the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI).

METHODS

The dataset required for the study was sourced via Google Earth Engine (GEE) for Central Ahmedabad from 2018–2024, a region known for its hot semi-arid climate (India Meteorological Department (IMD)). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) were extracted from the MODIS (MOD13A1) dataset, while the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) was calculated using Landsat 8 data from the Shortwave Infrared (SWIR) and Near-Infrared (NIR) bands. Air quality data including Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂), and Carbon Monoxide (CO), was retrieved from Sentinel-5P Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) whereas PM10 and PM2.5 from Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB). Cloud masking and atmospheric correction were applied using the QA bands to filter out poor-quality data. The data was then normalized via Min-Max normalization, and an annual analysis was conducted. Pearson correlation was used to assess the relationships between vegetation indices and pollutants.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure describes the change in NDBI over Ahmedabad for the years 2018 and 2024. With the passage of time, the built-up index value has moved towards the positive side in 2024 (Figure 1 (b)) in comparison to 2018 (Figure 1 (a)). Figure 2 indicates a significant negative correlation between NDVI and SO₂, with a Pearson correlation coefficient value (r) of -0.93, suggesting that vegetation health declined as air pollution increased. Additionally, a positive correlation was observed between NDBI and air quality parameters, indicating that urban built-up areas expanded in conjunction with rising nitrogen dioxide levels.

Figure 1. Variation of NDBI with time over Ahmedabad

Figure 2. Pearson Correlation of Indices, AOD and air pollutants.

CONCLUSIONS

The study reveals the negative impact of air pollution on vegetation, with PM2.5 reducing NDVI, and NO2 correlating with urban growth. We can also conclude that PM2.5 and PM10 are highly correlated ($r = 0.94$) and thus can be used to fill missing values. To reduce pollution, steps such as expanding green spaces, enforcing stricter vehicle emissions, improving public transport, among cleaner industries are recommended. Remote sensing can also enhance monitoring for timely interventions.

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TRENDS IN AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH OVER UTTARAKHAND DURING THE LAST TWENTY YEARS

SHARMA¹, AND M. MEHTA ²

¹Department of Computer Science, Banasthali Vidyapith, Jaipur – 304022, India.

²Indian Institute of Remote Sensing, Dehradun- 248001, India.

KEYWORDS: Trends, AOD, MODIS, Uttarakhand

INTRODUCTION

The geological record of the Earth provides multiple pieces of evidence that climate has not been uniform and has been significantly altered from time to time (Dash and Hunt, 2007). To this end, increasing aerosol levels, driven by natural and anthropogenic activities, are responsible for affecting air quality as well as radiative forcing (Cao et al., 2017). Aerosol levels have been found to increase in the Indian region in the last few decades (Mehta et al., 2020). Uttarakhand, located in the north Indian region, has experienced increasing urbanisation, high temperatures, and rising air pollution in the last few decades. This study examines the spatio-temporal variability of aerosol optical depth (AOD) in Uttarakhand over the winter season spanning the last two decades using satellite datasets.

METHODS

Data extraction and analysis are performed using Google Earth Engine (GEE). GEE provides easy processing of large-scale satellite datasets. MODIS/061/MCD19A2_GRANULES product was used to study the Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD). Linear regression and Mann Kendall analyses were performed to calculate the trends of AO 2..

Figure 1. Linear trends over Uttarakhand during the last twenty years

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Changes in AOD over the last twenty years (2003-2023) have been computed. Figure 1 shows the spatial-variability of trends using linear regression. Table 1 illustrates the trends of AOD over four cities of Uttarakhand using the linear regression technique.

	Dehradun	Haridwar	Haldwani	Kashipur
Location	30.31° N, 78.03° E	29.94° N, 78.16° E	29.21° N, 79.51° E	29.21° N, 78.96° E
Trends	+ 0.172	+ 0.121	+ 0.149	+ 0.134

Table 1 Trends of AOD over different locations of Uttarakhand during the last twenty years (2003 – 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

The study reveals the increasing trends in AOD over Uttarakhand in the last twenty years. Rising aerosol levels in changing climatic scenarios need further investigation in terms of different aerosol types, their sources and trajectories.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks are due to the Director, Indian Institute of Remote Sensing (IIRS) for the encouragement and support to this research. The first author is thankful to Banasthali Vidyapith for supporting this work. We thank the MODIS team for providing the data access. GEE is also acknowledged to support the analysis for this study.

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RECENT CHANGES IN SATELLITE-DERIVED PM 2.5 OVER INDIA

ARDRA D AND S. PHILIP

Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Satellite, Remote Sensing, India

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution poses a significant global threat to health, with India ranking among the top five countries for ambient air pollution (Pandey et al., 2021). PM_{2.5} exposure caused approximately 0.98 million deaths in India in 2019, according to the Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) study (Pandey et al., 2021). Exposure assessments over India are limited primarily due to the sparsity of in situ PM_{2.5} observations. Satellite-based retrievals of aerosol optical depth, along with chemical transport model simulations, can be used to derive surface PM_{2.5} (van Donkelaar et al., 2021). In this study, we assess air quality in India from 2005 to 2019 using the high-resolution (1 km × 1 km) satellite-derived surface PM_{2.5} data developed by van Donkelaar et al. (2021). We examine the long-term changes in PM_{2.5} exposure in urban and rural regions over Indian states.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We analyse the changes in satellite derived PM_{2.5} over India from 2005 to 2019. The satellite-derived PM_{2.5} data is from van Donkelaar et al. (2021). To evaluate population exposure to PM_{2.5}, population-weighted PM_{2.5} was estimated using population data from the World pop research program. We used Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) level 2 data, classifying each 1 km × 1 km grid into one of eight classes (“Urban Centre grid cell”, “Dense Urban Cluster grid cell”, “Semi-dense Urban Cluster grid cell”, “Suburban or per-urban grid cell”, “Rural cluster grid cell”, “Low Density Rural grid cell”, “Very low-density rural grid cell”, “Water grid cell”). We combined three rural grids into a single rural grid and four semi-urban and urban grids into a single urban grid. The data is available for 2005, 2010, and 2015. The exposure analysis is conducted at the state level in urban versus rural regions. We also assess changes in PM_{2.5} over different districts in India.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of satellite-derived data indicates that PM_{2.5} concentrations in India range up to ~130 µg/m³, with the highest concentrations in the densely populated Indo-Gangetic Plain region. Approximately 99.5% of districts in the Indian subcontinent, excluding some areas in Ladakh, fail to meet the World Health Organization's 2021 Air Quality Guidelines value of 5 µg/m³. The population exposed to PM_{2.5} has steadily increased from 2005 to 2019.

The PM_{2.5} exposure across all states and union territories consistently showed an upward trend during 2010 – 2014 compared to 2015 – 2019. The enhancements in PM_{2.5} levels in India are in both urban and rural regions. Figure 1 shows an increasing trend in PM_{2.5} concentration from 2005 to 2015 in urban and rural areas across various states in India. Future research includes assessing the factors contributing to the changes in PM_{2.5} over the 15 years (2005 – 2019).

Figure 1. Difference in PM_{2.5} exposure from 2015 and 2005 in the urban and rural areas of different states in India.

CONCLUSIONS

The study analyzes the recent changes in PM_{2.5} levels and human exposure in India, derived from high-resolution satellite-retrieved data. We find a continuous increase in PM_{2.5} exposure from 2005 to 2019 in India. The enhancements in PM_{2.5} levels in India are in both urban and rural regions. Moreover, PM_{2.5} exposure in India over urban and rural areas increased during 2005-2019.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Ardra D is supported by the Prime Minister's Research Fellowship, Ministry of Education, Government of India. We thank Aaron van Donkelaar and Randall Martin, Washington University in St. Louis, for the PM_{2.5} data. The authors acknowledge the Joint Research Centre (JRC) for providing GHSL Settlement Model grid (GHS SMOD) data and the Worldpop Research program for the population data. The GHSL data is available at <https://human-settlement.emergency.copernicus.eu/download.php?ds=smod> and population data is available at <https://hub.worldpop.org/geodata/listing?id=75>.

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ASSESSING UNCERTAINTIES AND VALIDATING MERRA-2 OZONE DATA ACROSS INDIA: INSIGHTS FROM 2004 TO 2022

T. GANGWAR¹, S. PAYRA², P. GUPTA^{1,3}, S. VERMA^{1,4*}

¹Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

²Department of Remote Sensing, Birla Institute of Technology Mesra, Ranchi, Jharkhand,

³India Meteorological Department, New Delhi, India.

⁴DST-Mahamana Centre of Excellence in Climate Change Research, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India.

Presenting author: gangwartanu28@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Surface Ozone, Merra-2, Trace Gases, Green House Gas, CPCB.

INTRODUCTION

Air quality management has become a global concern due to increasing emissions from industrialization, urbanization, and transportation (Zhang et al., 2016). In India, rapid population growth (over 1.15 million) and expanding emission sources highlight the need for continuous surface ozone (SfO₃) monitoring. Kumar et al. (2016) and David et al. (2019b) reported 8-hour average ozone exceedances on 451 days (~62%) between August 2011 and September 2013 in Mohali, especially in May. David et al. (2019b) also found that 1-hour ozone levels in Delhi surpassed 180 µg/m³ on 100+ days, with similar patterns in Chennai and Mumbai. Resmi et al. (2020) observed elevated tropospheric ozone over north-eastern India and the Indo-Gangetic Plains. This study employs MERRA-2 reanalysis data to assess surface ozone trends and distribution across India from 2004 to 2022, focusing on spatial-temporal variations and biases. The study by Sharma et al., (2017) examines the seasonal decoupling of SfO₃ and particulate matter (PM) for the year 2012 to 2014 and shows, PM peaking in winter (PM_{2.5}: 34.9–270.2 µg/m³, PM₁₀: 76.7–367.1 µg/m³) and SfO₃ in summer. Weak correlations (R: 0.23–0.27) were observed, influenced by boundary layer dynamics. Regression analysis revealed that PM components—elemental carbon, nitrate, and sulfate reduce SfO₃ by 9.7–23.9% (PM_{2.5}) and 16.6–17.8% (PM₁₀), primarily through radiation absorption and altered photolysis rates.

METHODS

This study employed MERRA-2 reanalysis data at 985 hPa to analyse surface ozone (SfO₃) trends across India from 2004 to 2022. The model output, at a resolution of 0.5° × 0.625°, was validated against CPCB observations from 12 ground stations for 2021-2022. We assessed spatial and temporal variations using Theil-Sen analysis and calculated Percentage Change (PC%). Model performance was evaluated using Pearson correlation (r), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Frequency Bias (F-Bias). These metrics quantify linear relationships, deviation from observations, and model accuracy.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Station ID	Station name	RMSE	r	F-Bias
1	Talcher Coalfields Talcher	36.191	0.623	2.392
2	RK Puram Delhi	27.063	0.515	1.474
3	Bhopal Chauraha Dewas	29.588	0.541	1.667
4	GM Office Brajrajnagar	38.224	0.575	2.098
5	Punjab Agricultural University Ludhiana	49.135	0.518	2.851
6	RIICO Ind. Area III Bhiwadi	46.438	0.537	2.906
7	Sector-62 Noida	39.046	0.546	2.057
8	Loni Ghaziabad	34.080	0.636	1.767
9	Deshpande Nagar Hubballi	32.593	0.759	2.174
10	Sector-25 Chandigarh	54.394	0.627	3.173
11	Tirumala Tirupati	29.985	0.617	2.114
	Kunjaban Agartala	43.893	0.627	3.567

Table:1 Metric of validation and error calculation from Ground-based CPCB.

This study evaluates the accuracy of MERRA-2 ozone data by comparing it with surface measurements from 12 CPCB stations across India for 2021-2022. Correlation coefficients ranged from 0.515 to 0.759, indicating strong agreement at six stations ($r > 0.6$) and moderate at others, while RMSE values (27.063 to 49.135) suggested overestimations. A long-term analysis (2004-2022) using MERRA-2 showed high ozone levels (50-70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in pre-monsoon months, peaking in May, and lower levels (34-42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) during the monsoon due to rain-induced precursor removal. The Western Himalayas experienced the highest long-term increase (9.33%), while South India slightly declined (1.546%). These results underscore the need for regional ozone variability studies to enhance air quality management.

CONCLUSIONS

This study validated MERRA-2 surface ozone (SfO_3) data against CPCB observations across 12 Indian stations (2021–2022), finding moderate to strong correlations (r : 0.515–0.759) but a tendency to overestimate, especially in the Indo-Gangetic Plain. Pre-monsoon ozone peaks were linked to emissions and meteorology, while monsoon rains reduced concentrations. The Western Himalayan showed a 9.33% long-term ozone increase (2004–2022), driven by altitude and transport, while South India saw a slight decline. Findings by Sharma et al. (2017) emphasize the chemical coupling of PM and SfO_3 , underscoring the need for further research on their photochemical interactions and implications for air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to extend gratitude to the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Application Version 2 (MERRA-2) for providing the necessary facilities to collect Dataset. The corresponding author would like to express thanks for funding support under the Ministry of Earth Science (MoES /16/18/2017-RDEAS) Project.

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SPATIAL HETEROGENEITY IN AEROSOL CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND MORPHOLOGY OVER EASTERN HIMALAYAN REGION

B. DAS¹, B. PATHAK², J. BISWAS³, K. J. BAISHYA² AND P.K. BHUYAN²

¹Department of Physics, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh 786004, Assam, India

²Centre for Atmospheric Studies, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh 786004, Assam, India

³Department of Physics, Pandu College, Guwahati 781012, Assam, India

KEYWORDS: TSP, SEM, EDX, Biogenic, Geogenic, Anthropogenic.

INTRODUCTION

Northeast India (NEI) is influenced by natural aerosols, especially biological aerosols (Pathak et al., 2022), as well as is altered by remote aerosols from Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP) and West Asia. The complex topography makes the region vulnerable to resuspension of all kinds of aerosols, mainly in the post-harvesting period when crop residue burning, and favourable meteorological conditions lead to the increase in the concentration of anthropogenic fine-mode particles. In the aerosol type discrimination, most aerosols could not be identified and remained as mixed types, which were supplemented by the identified biological aerosols like culturable microbial populations, pollens, animal debris, and fungal spores in different seasons. However, a quantitative study on aerosols' chemical composition or morphological properties over the location has not been addressed so far and thus this study aims to explore the same.

METHODS

The study was conducted over seven locations based on the nature of the site in the NEI over the North bank of Brahmaputra Valley comprising from the easternmost location (EL) (Sadiya) to the westernmost location (WL) (Dhubri). A high-volume sampler (STAPLEX, TSP-2) was used to sample TSP on glass filter paper (8×10 inch) at a 1 m³/min flow rate from Oct-Nov 2023 during fair weather conditions. 3 samples were collected from each location. Morphological and elemental analysis has been carried out using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (JEOL JSM 6390 LV), an Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer (EDX), and an INCAx Sight microanalysis system (Oxford Instruments, Model 7582). The categorization of the biogenic aerosols is done by the following clustering rule (Coz et al., 2010) based on the constituent element's weight percentage: (C+O) > 75% and 1% < P; K; Cl < 10%.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The weight percentage (wt.%) of different elements has been evaluated by using EDX. The wt.% of major elements such as C, O, and Si is in the range of 20-45% in all the locations along with minor elements: Na, Mg, Al, P, S, Cl, Ca, K, Fe, Cu, Zn, Sb and Ba have also been observed (wt.% < 10%). High Carbon content in Sadiya (32%) and Dhubri (30%), followed by Guwahati and Itanagar, which reflects the dominance of carbonaceous aerosols emitted primarily from biomass burning and fossil fuel combustion. Based on the single compound analysis, Majuli has the highest contribution of biogenic aerosols (70%), followed by Dibrugarh (35%). This region has an abundance of vegetation and is surrounded by the almighty Brahmaputra River making the region less vulnerable to remote aerosols. Further, biogenic were classified based on their microstructural features. The highest percentage

contribution of pollens/fungal/animal debris has been seen over Dibrugarh/Majuli /Bongaigaon. Moreover, the contribution of geogenic aerosols is significant in all locations except River Island Majuli. The highest percentage contribution is found in Guwahati (68%) followed by Itanagar (50%). Being a hilly region, it often has exposed rock surfaces and is subject to weathering and erosion processes that release particulate matter into the atmosphere. These regions have less vegetation cover, which can lead to increased soil erosion and dust generation which leads to the abundance of geogenic aerosols. Apart from that, Anthropogenic aerosols with high Carbon content in Sadiya (32%) and Dhubri (30%) have been observed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage contribution of different groups: Biogenic (Pollens, Fungal, Plant/animal debris), Geogenic, and Anthropogenic in the total PM during different locations.

Enrichment Factor analysis confirms that C, Al, Cl, Cu, Zn, Sb, and Ba are non-crustal ($EF > 10$) in all the locations. A Strong correlation between Ca, Mg, Si, and K, exists in EL (Sadiya, Dibrugarh, etc) derived from soil or resuspension of road dust. The same between Cu, Zn, Al and Ba exists over WL (Dhubri, Bongaigaon, etc) indicating vehicular emissions, and industrial activity. Principal Component Analysis reveals that Dibrugarh, Majuli, and Sadiya have a mixed source of crustal and industrial origin, whereas Itanagar, Bongaigaon, and Dhubri are from industrial and vehicular emissions.

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights that Total Suspended Particles (TSP) have a wide distribution of aerosol chemical composition leading to variability in types, that can be well evaluated based on single particle spectrum analysis along with morphological features. A dominance of anthropogenic aerosols, particularly carbon-rich particles in Sadiya and Dhubri, while Majuli and Dibrugarh have significant biogenic contributions. Based on Source apportionment we can conclude that biomass-burning/fossil fuel-generated aerosols dominate eastern locations/western locations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The ISRO-GBP-ARFI project supports this work. B.D. is grateful to SERB WEA Project: WEA/2021/000013, Department of Science and Technology, Govt. of India for the fellowship.

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CLIMATOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH (AOD) IN BHAVNAGAR DISTRICT: LONG-TERM TRENDS AND IMPACTS

N. TURAKHIA¹ AND K. TAILOR¹

¹Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar, Gujarat - 364001, India.

KEYWORDS: Climatology, Aerosol Optical Depth, Trend Analysis, Remote Sensing.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are also regarded as the largest contributor to the uncertainty of present-day climate change attribution (IPCC, 2021). In aerosol measurements, aerosol optical depth (AOD) is often used to describe its column properties, which represent the vertical integration of aerosol extinction coefficients. AOD is an important physical quantity for estimating the content, atmospheric pollution, and climatology of aerosols (Zhang et al., 2020). The present study has been carried out over Bhavnagar, a city in the state of Gujarat, India, an urban area blended with industrial, commercial, and residential zones. It is known for its historical significance, trade, and proximity to the Gulf of Khambhat. The region has a significant industrial base, including ship-breaking yards in Alang and various manufacturing industries. Surrounding Bhavnagar, there are also agricultural and rural areas, making it a mix of urban and semi-urban environments.

METHODS

Initially, the MODIS Terra and Aqua V6.1 dataset is acquired, which provides daily AOD values at wavelengths of 0.55 μm . Quality assurance flags are applied to filter out unreliable data, ensuring the integrity of the dataset. The study area is defined, and the AOD data is extracted for this specific region, allowing for a focused analysis of aerosol concentrations.

Following data acquisition, monthly and yearly averages of AOD are calculated to observe trends and seasonal variations over the 24-year period. This temporal analysis enables a clearer understanding of how aerosol levels fluctuate throughout the year. To further enhance the analysis, statistical methods are employed to investigate correlations between AOD and various meteorological variables, such as temperature and humidity. Additionally, trend analysis is conducted to identify significant changes in AOD over time, contributing valuable insights into aerosol climatology in the study area.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Trend and Scatter plot of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) observed from MODIS Terra and Aqua Satellite over Bhavnagar district.

Figure 2. Spatial maps of AOD over Bhavnagar district for the year 2002, 2013 & 2023.

The analysis of aerosol optical depth (AOD) over the 24-year period from 2000 to 2024 indicates a notable increasing trend, characterized by fluctuations observed in both Terra and Aqua satellites. This trend (Figure 1. & Figure 2.) suggests a rise in aerosol concentrations, which may be attributed to various factors such as urbanization, industrial activities, and increased vehicular emissions within the study area. The consistency of this trend across both satellite datasets reinforces the reliability of the findings, as both sensors provide complementary data on atmospheric conditions. Further examination reveals that while there are periods of increase, there are also notable decreases in AOD, highlighting the dynamic nature of aerosol distribution influenced by seasonal changes and regional climatic events. The analysis aligns with previous studies that have identified similar increasing trends in AOD globally, emphasizing the importance of continuous monitoring using satellite data to understand the implications of aerosols on climate change and air quality. The findings contribute valuable insights into the evolving landscape of aerosol climatology over the past two decades.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of aerosol optical depth (AOD) using MODIS data from the Terra and Aqua satellites over the period from 2000 to 2024 reveals a significant increasing trend in AOD values, indicating a rise in aerosol concentrations in the study area. Moreover, this study highlights the complex interplay between aerosols and meteorological factors, as well as seasonal influences. These results emphasize the need for ongoing monitoring and research to understand the implications of aerosols on climate change and air quality. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into aerosol climatology, underscoring the necessity for continued investigation into the sources and impacts of aerosols in our atmosphere.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is acknowledged by the Department of Statistics, Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India.

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EMISSIONS OF CARBON-CONTAINING TRACE GASES FROM FOREST FIRE OVER THE SOUTH ASIA

KUMARI ADITI¹ AND TIRTHANKAR BANERJEE¹

¹Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi,

KEYWORDS: Biomass Burning; Emission; FIRE; VIIRS.

INTRODUCTION

Forest areas worldwide are experiencing unprecedented fire activity with associated emissions. In recent decades, mega fires have become common in most forests across the globe, opposing years of greenhouse gas emission reductions (Jerrett et al., 2022; van der Velde et al., 2021). While forest fires have certain ecological benefits, fire can also threaten forest ecology and may held responsible for damaging infrastructure (McLauchlan et al., 2020). Of the 40.6 million sq. km of global forest coverage, 0.98 million sq. km was affected by fire in 2015, representing 2.41% of total forest cover (FAO, 2020). Annual estimates suggest around 3.4% of Earth's land surface burns each year (Giglio et al., 2018). In contrast, wildfires in the U.S. and Australia are linked to changes in climate and forest characteristics (Deb et al., 2020). In South Asia, fires are irregular, with India, Nepal, and Bhutan seeing annual forest burned areas of 13-15 thousand sq. km. India alone had 11 thousand sq. km burned in 2019-20 (FSI, 2020). Detecting thermal anomalies by remote sensing has developed fire tracking, improving estimates of active fires and emissions (Wooster et al., 2021). Suomi-NPP VIIRS retrievals, in particular, offer improved detection of fires due to their higher spatial resolution (Vadrevu et al., 2018). This study explores emissions of carbon-containing trace gases (CO and CO₂) from forest fires in South Asia using VIIRS-based fire anomalies.

DATASET AND METHODS

The study used Terra/Aqua MODIS L3 V6.1 Global Land Cover (MCD12Q1) data at 0.5 km resolution to assess forest cover in South Asia from the year 2017, excluding shrublands. VIIRS 375 m active fire data (VNP14IMG) was used to track fire activity across South Asia while emissions of CO and CO₂ were estimated using the VIIRS based Fire Emission Inventory (VFEI, Version 0) by Ferrada et al. (2022). Fire counts, emissions, and trends were analysed across the forest over South Asia (SA), the Himalayan belt (HF), and the Deccan Plateau or Peninsular Plateau (PP). Specific attention was made to assessing fire incidence over spatial and seasonal scales. The Mann-Kendall test with Theil-Sen's slope method were applied to assess fire trends, providing insight into regional variations in fire activity and emissions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1. Annual fire counts across three regions from 2017 to 2021, Figure 2 Emission estimates (kg yr⁻¹) of carbon-containing trace gases from forest fire

Figure 1 shows annual fire count trends for South Asia (SA), Himalayan Forest (HF), and Peninsular Plateau (PP) from 2017 to 2021. In SA, fire counts began at 18,000 in 2017, peaked at 28,000 in 2018, dropped to 18,000 in 2020, and rebounded to 29,000 in 2021 (a 61% increase). HF fire counts fluctuated between 7,000 and 10,000 until 2021, when they rose to 17,000 (a 70% increase). PP fire counts declined from 10,000 in 2017 to 2,000 in 2020 before rising sharply to 11,000 in 2021.

The figure 2 depicts CO₂ (blue) and CO (orange) levels from 2017 to 2021. Initially, both gases increased, but CO₂ remained relatively stable afterwards, while CO continued rising. Both emissions initially declined slightly but showed an upward trend from 2020 onwards.

In 2021, CO₂ emissions reached approximately 1.35E+10 (an increase of about 5-10% from its lowest point), while CO emissions reached approximately 7.5E+08 (an increase of about 10-15% from its lowest point).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express their gratitude to the VIIRS Science Team for their work in processing and preserving the thermal anomaly and fire data, as well as to the VFEI team for developing and sharing the biomass-based fire emission inventory data.

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EXPLORING URBAN-RURAL GRADIENT IN AEROSOL LOADING

AKANKSHA PANDEY AND TIRTHANKAR BANERJEE

Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Loading, Carbonaceous Aerosols, Indian Cities, Urban Planning

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is transforming global landscapes, with the urban population projected to rise from 56% in 2021 to 68% by 2050, adding 2.2 billion residents, primarily in Asia and Africa (UN-Habitat, 2022). In India, urban residency is expected to grow from 31% in 2011 to 44% by 2035. This growth increases exposure to air pollution, linked to health issues such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and cardiovascular diseases. In 2015, air pollution caused about 9 million premature deaths globally, with 6.7 million attributed specifically to air quality issues (GBD, 2021). In 2019, PM_{2.5}-related mortality in urban areas reached 1.8 million, with 86% of the urban population in non-compliant areas (Shaddick et al., 2020). South Asia, with 36% urbanization (World Bank, 2024), is a major aerosol hotspot. Research shows strong links between aerosol concentrations and regional meteorology (Banerjee et al., 2021), particularly in the Indo-Gangetic Plain, which faces high aerosol burdens from residential and agricultural emissions (Gautam et al., 2023). Despite documented declines in air quality, comprehensive studies on spatial dynamics in South Asian cities are lacking. This research utilizes advanced satellite data to analyze urban and peri-urban aerosol characteristics, aiming to inform effective air quality management strategies.

DATASETS AND METHOD

This study leverages MODIS MAIAC Collection 6.1 Level-2 aerosol optical depth (AOD) data (1 km resolution) from Aqua and Terra satellites to examine aerosol loading in and around selected cities between January 2017 and December 2021, excluding monsoon months to avoid cloud contamination. Only high-quality MAIAC AOD data were considered to minimize the influence of cloud cover and sun glint.

The analysis is based on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid centered over each city, which was further divided into three distinct zones (Fig. 1), a 20 km inner circle representing the "city core" with concentrated urban emissions, a 30 km buffer zone influenced by emissions from both the core and surrounding areas, and an outer suburban region extending up to the edges of the $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid, covering rural and semi-urban regions with limited contributions from urban emissions. The geometric mean (GM) and geometric standard deviation (GSD) were used to describe the temporal and spatial variability of AOD, avoiding potential biases from arithmetic means in non-normal data distributions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The spatial distribution of AOD (Fig. 1) highlights significant aerosol loading in the core areas of Mumbai and Pune. In Mumbai, AOD values exceed 0.56 near the center, while Pune's core shows AOD values exceeding 0.58, represented by red areas. The surrounding regions exhibit lower AOD, with values below 0.32 in Mumbai and below 0.36 in Pune, indicating cleaner environments in these peripheral zones compared to the densely populated city cores.

Yearly variations in geometric mean AOD (Fig. 2a) reveal distinct patterns between Mumbai and Pune's core urban areas and surrounding regions. Mumbai's core consistently exhibits higher AOD values, indicating a concentrated impact of urban activities and emissions. In contrast, Pune's core shows lower AOD values, suggesting potential pollution sources in surrounding areas, such as industrial clusters or agricultural practices, contributing to higher AOD levels.

Fig. 2b compares the AOD between the city cores (blue) and surroundings (red) for Mumbai and Pune. Both cities show higher AOD values in the cores than in the surrounding regions, with median values around 0.5. Outliers in both areas indicate some variability in AOD, particularly in Pune

Figure 1 Spatial variations in decadal geometric mean aerosol optical depth (AOD) across Mumbai and Pune. The inner circle, at a 20 km radius from the city center, represents the city core, while the second concentric circle, at 30 km, indicates the extent of the buffer zone.

Figure 2 (a) Yearly deviations in geometric mean aerosol optical depth (AOD) for the core and surrounding areas of Mumbai and Pune. (b) AOD variation between the city core and its surrounding regions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the MODIS MAIAC science team for data availability and maintenance.

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SEASONAL AND TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF PARTICULATE LEVELS IN A SUBTROPICAL HIGHLAND CLIMATE REGION IN INDIA USING GROUND OBSERVATIONS

A. HUSSAIN¹, T. TURAKHIA², A. VAKOT¹, D. PANDYA¹, A. SETHWALA¹, S. PUROHIT¹

¹Department of Computer Science, GUJARAT UNIVERSITY, Gujarat, India.

²Research Scholar, Gujarat Technological University, Gujarat, India

KEYWORDS: Climatology, Particulate Matter, Trend Analysis, Diurnal Variation, Climate Change.

INTRODUCTION

Dehradun, nestled in the Doon Valley, is increasingly facing challenges related to air quality, particularly concerning particulate matter (PM). PM, especially fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), poses significant health risks, as it can penetrate deep into the lungs and enter the bloodstream, leading to serious respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. The World Health Organization links PM_{2.5} exposures to millions of premature deaths globally, underscoring its critical impact on public health.

In Dehradun, the seasonal variations in PM_{2.5} levels are particularly concerning, with higher concentrations observed during winter months due to factors like temperature inversions and increased emissions from heating sources. Understanding these variations is essential for developing effective air quality management strategies that safeguard the health of residents and enhance the overall liveability of this rapidly urbanizing area. Addressing particulate matter pollution is not only vital for protecting public health but also for ensuring a sustainable environment for future generations.

METHODS

The current study focuses on the variation of PM_{2.5} over the subtropical highland climatic environmental region, of Dehradun, India. The methodology for studying the variation of PM_{2.5} levels in Dehradun involves a systematic approach using data sourced from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB). The dataset includes PM_{2.5} measurements recorded at 15-minute intervals from 2022 to 2024. To analyze this data, monthly averages were computed to identify trends and fluctuations in particulate matter concentrations over time. This aggregation allows for a clearer understanding of seasonal variations and long-term trends in air quality.

In addition to monthly averages, the study also examines variations across different times of day—specifically morning, afternoon, evening, and night—to uncover diurnal patterns in PM_{2.5} levels. Statistical analyses, including the calculation of the coefficient of variation, are employed to assess the significance of observed changes in PM_{2.5} concentrations over the study period. Quality assurance measures are implemented to ensure data integrity, adhering to CPCB guidelines, thereby enhancing the reliability of the findings and contributing valuable insights into air quality dynamics in Dehradun.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Trend and monthly and seasonal variation of Particulate Matter (PM2.5) observed in Dehradun, India.

In Dehradun, PM2.5 levels exhibit significant seasonal variation, with elevated concentrations observed in January, October, November, and December, indicating a pronounced winter spike. This increase can be attributed to several factors, including lower temperatures that hinder the dispersion of pollutants and increased emissions from heating sources such as biomass burning. Additionally, the city's geographical location in the Doon Valley traps pollutants, exacerbating air quality issues during the colder months when atmospheric inversion is common, leading to stagnant air conditions that prevent effective pollutant dispersion.

Conversely, PM2.5 levels tend to decrease during the summer months due to higher temperatures and increased rainfall during the monsoon season, which helps in settling particulate matter and improving air quality. However, post-monsoon months see a resurgence in PM2.5 levels as humidity decreases and vehicular emissions rise with the return of dry conditions. The combination of urbanization, increased vehicular traffic, and construction activities further contributes to this pattern, as dust and emissions become more prevalent once the rains subside. Understanding these seasonal dynamics is crucial for developing effective air quality management strategies in Dehradun.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of PM2.5 variations in Dehradun reveals distinct seasonal patterns, with higher concentrations observed during the winter followed by summer, post monsoon and monsoon seasons. This trend is primarily influenced by meteorological factors such as temperature inversions and increased emissions from heating sources. The hot months show a decrease in PM2.5 levels due to higher temperatures and monsoon rains that help mitigate air pollution. However, a subsequent rise in particulate matter is noted during the post-monsoon period, due to urban activities and vehicular emissions. These findings underscore the need for targeted air quality management strategies that address seasonal variations and mitigate pollution sources throughout the year.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is acknowledged to the Department of Physics, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India.

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EVALUATING RESPONSES OF VEGETATION TO ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS IN THE INDIAN HIMALAYAN REGION

LAXITA PANT¹, UJJWAL KUMAR¹

¹Atmosphere & Environment Modelling Lab, SENR, Doon University, Dehradun

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Aod, Partial Correlation, Eof, Vegetation, Ndvi

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are known to have profound effects on ecosystem productivity and vegetation growth (Jiao et al, 2021; Zhang et al, 2021; Yamaguchi and Izuta, 2017). Aerosols in the Himalayan region have shown significant variability over the years, the region experiences higher aerosol optical depth (AOD) in spring and summer, primarily due to mineral dust (Nelli et al., 2021). The Himalayan region is also home to great biodiversity, ranging from very dense forests to meadows. Although several studies exist about increasing aerosols and their characteristics in the Indian Himalayan region (e.g., Joshi et al, 2019; Soni et al, 2019; Nelli et al., 2021) and its vegetation characteristics (e.g., Ramachandran et al, 2018; Gangopadhyay et al., 2021), the study of the impact of atmospheric aerosols on vegetation in IHR has been lacking till date. The present study is an attempt to fill this gap by evaluating the responses of vegetation to atmospheric aerosols in IHR based on satellite data analysis from 2003 to 2023.

METHODS

The monthly mean datasets of aerosol optical depth (AOD) from MERRA-2, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) from MODIS, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) from MERRA-2, surface solar radiation (SSR) from ERA-5, land surface temperature (LST) from MODIS, total precipitation (TP) from CHIRPS 2.0, wind speed (WS) from GDLAS-2.1, and actual evapotranspiration (ET) from FEWS (USGS) for the years 2003 to 2023 have been analyzed. To analyze the effect of aerosols on vegetation, the partial correlation analysis and the empirical orthogonal function analysis have been performed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

To analyze the impact of aerosols on vegetation, the Indian Himalayan region (IHR) was divided into three vegetation regions, viz., Dense vegetation, Moderate vegetation and Sparse vegetation based on annual NDVI values (Fig 1(a)). Fig 1(b) presents the correlation coefficients between AOD and NDVI for the years 2003 to 2023. Clearly correlation coefficient is strongly to moderately negative for the dense and moderate vegetation regions indicating a negative impact of aerosols on vegetation. The possible reason is that increased aerosols in the atmosphere might adversely affect the available photo-synthetically active radiation (PAR) which, in turn, might affect the vegetative growth and spread. Therefore, a partial correlation analysis between NDVI and PAR has been performed with and without AOD. The partial correlation analysis shows that the correlation between NDVI and PAR is greatly affected by the presence of AOD for the dense vegetation region, as the correlation coefficient dramatically decreases from 0.74 to 0.5 in the presence of AOD for the dense vegetation region. Similar effects have been observed for the moderate vegetation region where the correlation between NDVI and PAR decreases from 0.71 to 0.68 in the presence of

Figure 1: (a) the classification of IHR vegetation into dense vegetation, moderate vegetation and sparse; (b) correlation between NDVI and AOD for the years 2003 to 2023.

CONCLUSION:

The study of AOD, NDVI, and the climatic variables from 2003 to 2023 revealed significant variations and patterns in the Indian Himalayan Region and Nepal. The correlation and partial correlation analysis showed a significant impact of aerosols on vegetation, particularly, in the dense vegetation region. The region having moderate vegetation had also been affected by the increasing aerosols in the IHR. The study provides an insight into the complex relationship between aerosols and vegetation in the Indian Himalayan Region and the complexities of climatic interactions with aerosols that indirectly affect vegetation dynamics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The part of the research was supported under UNEP's TEEBAgriFood program for Assam, India, coordinated by IARI-CAFRI, Jhansi.

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ESTIMATION OF PARTICULATE MATTER (PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀) CONCENTRATIONS OVER INDIA USING SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUE

D.S. RAWAT¹, SHAIK DARGA SAHEB² AND H.C. CHANDOLA³

¹School of Allied Sciences (Physics) Graphic Era Hill University, Bhimtal Campus,
Sattal Road. Nainital– 263132, India.

²India Meteorological Department, Bengaluru – 560001, India.

³Department of Physics (UGC-Centre of Advanced Study) D.S.B. Campus, Kumaun
University, Nainital – 263001, India.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Modis, Aerosols.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) is an indicator of air pollution and consists of a complex mixture of aerosols particularly sulfate, nitrate, black carbon, and mineral dust particles. Epidemiological studies have consistently shown that negative human health effects including premature mortality can be caused by long-term exposure to atmospheric aerosols especially PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} (particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter of less than 10 μm and 2.5 μm, respectively). In India, several studies have examined PM distribution due to anthropogenic emissions (Bhattu et al., 2024; Bisht et al., 2016; Sahu et al., 2021). The ground-based in-situ monitoring networks provide the most accurate measurements of PM but these measurements are generally representative of local conditions and scattered in space and time which makes it difficult to use them in the assessment of regional scale. The measurement of aerosol optical depth (AOD) from satellites provides an alternative tool to assess the ground-level PM at a regional to global scale. The present study focuses on estimating the spatial distribution of PM by the synergy of satellite AOD and regional meteorological conditions over the Indian region.

METHODS

The ambient PM concentrations can be estimated by using satellite AOD and meteorological parameters. The methodology commonly used for the estimation of surface PM concentrations are multivariable linear regression technique (Gharibzadeh & Saadat Abadi, 2022). The multivariable linear regression model was developed as the following equation:
 $[PM] = \alpha_0 + \alpha_T(T) + \alpha_W(W) + \alpha_{Dir}(Dir) + \alpha_{RH}(RH) + \alpha_{AOD}(AOD) + \alpha_{PBLH}(PBLH) \text{ ----- (1)}$

Where T, W, Dir, RH, AOD, PBL are the temperature, wind speed, wind direction, relative humidity, aerosol optical depth and planetary boundary layer height parameters, respectively. α_0 is the intercept of the general equation and α_n is the regression coefficient of the independent variables. This simple equation is presented in PM equation (1), and the coefficients are shown in Table 1.

S.NO.	Station	α_0	α_{AOD}	α_T	α_W	α_{Dir}	α_{RH}	α_{PBLH}
1	Amritsar	6.7	124.08	-0.1	0.5	-0.1	-0.02	-0.007
2	Dehradun	16.08	100.9	-0.84	1.5	8.04	-0.09	-0.03
3	New Delhi	246.7	10.85	-2.7	-41.1	-1.7	-0.09	-0.08
4	Alwar	265.9	53.03	0.15	-1.4	5.8	-1.2	-0.07
5	Kanpur	180.1	28.9	-3.7	4.6	20.11	0.17	0.02
6	Varanasi	165.5	93.7	-2.5	-1.8	1.5	-0.7	0.009

7	Nagpur	5.96	79.1	-0.4	9.1	-19.8	0.13	-0.02
8	Chandrapur	103.6	40.23	-1.8	-7.4	-8.1	-0.39	-0.02
9	Mumbai	116.5	3.12	-3.1	43.4	0.005	0.26	-0.07
10	Hyderabad	-13.04	54.6	1.04	0.21	0.31	0.18	-0.02
11	Bengaluru	70.8	67.7	-1.02	-1.7	-16.1	-0.5	0.01
12	Chennai	0.44	108.7	-0.31	0.006	0.007	0.12	-0.004
13	Thiruvananthapuram	22.12	26.4	1.7	-4.6	8.2	-0.17	0.02

Table 1: The estimated regression coefficients for PM equations during 207-2019 using AOD and meteorological parameters

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig 1. Shows the correlations between the daily average estimated by the multivariable linear regression model and measured values of PM_{2.5} (a) and PM₁₀ (b) at 13 locations in India. Overall Indian region, the correlation between predicted and observed PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ has a strong correlation coefficient (R) of 0.92 and 0.94 with RMSE as 0.12 and 0.24 respectively. The correlation for each station has a positive output with different regression coefficients and bias. The highest coefficient of PM_{2.5} has been recorded in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh (R = 0.95) with MAE = 24.6 and Bias = 0.05, followed by Amritsar, Punjab, values are R = 0.94, MAE = 6.43 and Bias = 0.009 while low coefficients are observed in Alwar and Hyderabad (R = 0.61 and 0.61; MAE = 52.14 and 12.3 and Bias = 0.07 and 0.17 respectively. For PM₁₀ the highest correlation was found in Bengaluru R = 0.81, MAE = 22.7 and Bias = 0.2 followed by Chennai (R=0.78, MAE=4.8 and Bias = 0.02). Meteorological variations are particularly wind direction effective in variations of the PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations.

Figure 1. Scatter plots between predicted and measured for PM_{2.5} (a) and PM₁₀ (b) over the Indian region.

CONCLUSIONS

The study involved the predictive analysis of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels by utilizing a multivariable linear regression model. The accuracy of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ estimations was enhanced by including the meteorological and boundary layer conditions along with satellite AOD over the Indian region. The overall correlation between predicted and observed PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are found to be R~ 0.92 and 0.94 respectively.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank MODIS science teams for the availability of AOD data and PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ data provided by CPCB are duly acknowledged.

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ESTIMATING SURFACE PM10 CONCENTRATION FROM MODIS AND VIIRS S-NPP INTEGRATED AOD DATASET USING MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

RAJAT PANDEY¹, UJJWAL KUMAR¹

¹Atmosphere & Environment Modelling Lab, SENR, Doon University, Dehradun – 248001,

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, PM10, AOD, MODIS, VIIRS, Linear Regression, Random Forest Model.

INTRODUCTION

The estimation of surface PM10 concentrations using satellite data has gained significant attention in air quality research, particularly in the regions where ground-based monitoring is limited. Hejazi et al. (2014) developed a semi-empirical model enhanced by a genetic algorithm to estimate near-surface PM10 concentrations in Tehran, Iran. Guevara Luna et al. (2019) evaluated the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) datasets for estimating PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations in Colombia. Their results indicated a strong correlation between satellite-derived Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and ground-based measurements. Tomar and Singh (2023) utilized the MODIS AOD dataset to estimate PM10 levels during an intense dust storm in India, specifically examining the Thar Desert and Delhi. Their analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between satellite-derived and ground-based PM10 measurements during the dust storm event, highlighting the capability of satellite data in extreme conditions. The present study is attempts to utilized utilise both MODIS and VIIRS/SNPP AOD datasets to estimate surface PM10 concentration for the North Indian region by applying a machine learning approach, specifically, linear regression and random forest model.

METHODS

The study uses MODIS/Aqua Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 3km and the VIIRS/SNPP Deep Blue Level 2 product. The level 2.0 AOD and SDA ground data were obtained from AERONET for AOD and Ångström exponent values for four Indian sites: Gandhi College (25.9N, 84.1E), IIT Delhi (28.5N, 77.2E), Jaipur (26.9N, 75.8E), and Kanpur (26.5N, 80.2E). The data from Doon University Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Station (AAQMS) were used for surface PM10 as well as meteorological factors such as temperature, barometric pressure, rainfall, relative humidity, and wind speed and direction. The linear regression and random forest model were applied in order to estimate surface PM10 concentrations

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The AOD datasets were analysed for the year 2021. The integration of MODIS and VIIRS datasets resulted in a significant enhancement of spatial coverage for AOD data in the study region. At the study site, the MODIS has AOD data for 162 days and VIIRS contained data for 154 days but the Integrated dataset had AOD data for 181 days thus making it spatially as well as temporally robust. The random forest model was employed for integrated MODIS and VIIRS datasets along with meteorological parameters temperature, relative humidity, barometric pressure, wind speed and direction. A 20% test set and an 80% training set were created and a five-fold cross validation was carried out to verify the consistency of the model.

The best model performance was obtained with R2 as 0.86 and RMSE 14.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure1. The estimated PM10 concentration over Dehradun region using MODIS and VIIRS dataset.

CONCLUSION

The study employed random forest model on integrated dataset of MODIS and VIIRS to estimate surface PM10 concentration. The model evaluation and its comparative analysis shows that random forest on integrated datasets outperform linear regression approach and it is also advantageous to use integrated dataset over individual MODIS or VIIRS. The integrated approach can be useful for estimating surface PM10 concentration, particularly, in the data deficit Himalayan region.

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ANALYZING THE TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL PATTERNS OF AIR POLLUTION DYNAMICS IN NEPAL

^{1,2*}S. PANDEY, ¹B. ADHIKARI, ¹B. D. GHIMIRE, ¹N. NAKARMI, ²B. THAPA

¹St.Xavier's College, Maitighar, Tribhuvan University Kathmandu, Nepal

²BOTS Industries Pvt Ltd, Kathmandu, Nepal

INTRODUCTION

Nepal, a land of diverse geographical topology and unique regional features, is strategically located amidst heavily industrialized nations, which contributes to varied air quality even within a small geographical area. This study highlights a significant rise in pollution levels across the country, especially in the Kathmandu Valley, where PM_{2.5} levels exceed both national and international air quality standards. Analyzing the spatial and temporal trends of air quality in Nepal using data from ground-based monitoring stations along with Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data for Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) reveals the dependency of air pollution on topographical attributes and meteorological factors. The results demonstrate considerable inequalities in pollution levels across different regions and elevations, underscoring the complex relationship between geographical factors and air quality. Regions above 5000 meters above sea level generally experience lower PM_{2.5} levels throughout the year. Furthermore, the seasonal variation analysis of AOD data across Nepal over the last 20 years reveals a consistent air pollution pattern, offering valuable insights into understanding and mitigating air pollution. Additionally, the analysis of pollutant transport using HYSPLIT back trajectories and AOD data highlights the significant impact of transboundary pollution on increasing PM_{2.5} levels in Nepal.

Keywords: Pm_{2.5}, Aod, Transboundary Pollution, Aerosol Modeling

METHODS

- Data Collection: PM_{2.5} data from monitoring stations, MODIS AOD for aerosols, meteorological data (temperature, precipitation), and forest fire occurrences.
- HYSPLIT Model: 72-hour back trajectory analysis to trace transboundary pollution pathways.
- Temporal Scope: 20-year seasonal analysis (2003–2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Parameter	Spring (Mar-May)	Summer (Jun-Aug)	Autumn (Sep-Nov)	Winter (Dec-Feb)
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	62.19	15.93	17.19	95.06
AOD	0.639	0.206	0.189	0.825
Precipitation (mm)	230 (23 days)	969 (63 days)	257 (19 days)	27 (6 days)
Temperature (°C)	Min: 8.8, Max: 29.2, Mean: 20.2	Min: 19.3, Max: 29.5, Mean: 24.2	Min: 8.4, Max: 28.6, Mean: 20.1	Min: 2.8, Max: 22.1, Mean: 12.3

INTERPRETATION BY SEASON

- Winter: High PM_{2.5} (95.06 µg/m³) and AOD (0.825) due to cold conditions, biomass burning, and transboundary pollution from NW India.
- Spring: Moderate PM_{2.5} (62.19 µg/m³) influenced by transboundary dust from northern Pakistan and India, offset by 230 mm precipitation.
- Summer: Lowest PM_{2.5} (15.93 µg/m³) and AOD (0.206), with monsoon rains effectively reducing pollutants.
- Autumn: Moderate increase in PM_{2.5} (17.19 µg/m³) due to reduced rainfall and internal pollution from forest fires.

CONCLUSION

- Seasonal Impacts: Winter shows the highest pollution due to cold weather and biomass burning, while summer monsoons provide the cleanest air quality.
- Transboundary Influence: Notable, especially in spring, emphasizing the need for regional cooperation.
- Recommendations: Expand low-cost monitoring, provide real-time data access, and establish seasonal pollution reduction policies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

St. Xavier's College, BOTS Industries, NOAA HYSPLIT, NASA Giovanni, Department of Environment (Nepal)

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**THEME 4: EXTREME EVENTS (DUST STORMS,
CLOUDBURST, RAINFALL AND EARTHQUAKE)**

CYCLONE INDUCED AEROSOL TRANSPORT AND EXTREME TEMPERATURES IN JUNE 2023- A CASE STUDY

S. BANERJEE, B. PADMAKUMARI

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, 411008, India.
Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), New Delhi, 11000, India.

Email: - shravani.banerjee@tropmet.res.in; padma@tropmet.res.in

KEYWORDS: Heatwave, Dust, Cyclone, Aerosols

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the rise in aerosol optical depths, extreme temperatures, and heat waves has become a major concern. In June 2023, cyclone Biparjoy, an Extremely Severe Cyclonic Storm, originated in the Arabian Sea and travelled overland from 13th-23rd June, impacting northwestern India and the Gangetic plains (Dhara and Koll, 2023). During its landfall, the existing heatwave regions in the eastern and western peninsulas intensified, extending the duration, and spreading to new areas along the east coast, peninsular India, and central India. This study examines the unusual compound event of a tropical cyclone and extreme temperatures leading to heatwave events in June 2023, with a focus on the aerosol transport mechanism from the Middle East during this event.

METHODS

The data utilized in the study are ERA5 Air Temperatures, Vertical Velocity, Geopotential Height, wind speed and direction, SENTINEL 5P aerosol Index, and cloud cover. The study is based on the analysis of the above data sets during the journey of the cyclone Biparjoy.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Before Cyclone Biparjoy's landfall (05th-12th June 2023), the heatwave primarily affected eastern India and the Konkan region. However, during landfall (13th-20th June 2023), the heatwave expanded across peninsular India and adjacent eastern regions, intensifying existing extreme temperatures, while increasing rainfall in Western India and adjoining Gangetic Plains (Figure 1). A composite analysis of key meteorological variables revealed significant upward motion over western India, linked to cyclonic activity, while subsidence dominated over eastern and peninsular India, intensifying the heatwave conditions.

Figure 1. INSAT-3D Visible image of 15th June 2023. (The black marker shows the cyclone position, and the boxes show the study area affected by extreme temperatures.

Additionally, dust entrainment from the Middle East and Central Asia, driven by the cyclone and westerly winds, increased aerosol concentrations over the Indian Peninsula. The dust aerosols, characterized by the absorption of solar radiation, heat the atmosphere, thereby contributing to atmospheric heating (Dave et al., 2020; Mondal et al., 2020). Thus, along with atmospheric dynamics, the dust aerosols also would have likely worsened the heatwave conditions in the present scenario.

CONCLUSIONS

The temperature increase over the Indian region during June 2023 was driven by the strengthening of the anticyclone over Eastern India and the formation of another system over Peninsular India, influenced by mid-tropospheric air intrusion from the cyclone Biparjoy. As the cyclone advanced, it intensified high-pressure zones and facilitated the subsidence of dust aerosols, raising the aerosol index and dust concentration over Eastern and Peninsular India. The absorbing dust aerosols and subsidence motion during the cyclone's landfall likely intensified the heatwave.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Director, IITM for all the support. Also, acknowledge ISRO-MOSDAC, ERA5, and SENTINEL 5P data teams.

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INDICATOR OF TROPICAL CYCLONE WEAKENING: HELICITY AND DUST AEROSOL

ARPITA MUNSI, AMIT KESARKAR AND JYOTI BHATE

National Atmospheric Research Laboratory Gadanki, Chittoor, Andhra Pradesh –517112,

KEYWORDS: Extreme Weather, Tropical Cyclone, Helicity, Dust Aerosol.

INTRODUCTION

Tropical cyclones (TCs) are one of the deadliest natural extreme weather events. It is associated with a helical flow uprooting the trees and other structures which come in its track. Helicity is the measure of the tendency of a convective system to rotate in a ‘helical’ way. Though helicity has been widely used to analyze tornadoes and supercell storms in the mid-latitude region, it is very limitedly utilised for the study of TC. We have analysed the development of large-scale vortex dynamo during tropical cyclogenesis through the mutual intensification of primary and secondary circulation in terms of helical evolution in Munsi et al. 2023. Generally, after the landfall, while travelling over the land mass, a TC starts weakening due to various causes like cut off of moisture supply from the warm ocean, boundary layer frictions etc. In this study, we have analysed a few causes of the weakening of TC when it was travelling over the ocean. At its development stage, the heat and moisture flux from the ocean surface increases with the increase in intensity of the TC. This time, TC-Ocean interaction works in a positive feedback mechanism. However, after a particular stage, the very intense wind of the TC causes strong turbulent mixing in the underlying ocean. Hence, the upper ocean layer temperature starts decreasing, leading to a decrease in heat and moisture flux exchange to the TC. We have analysed the emergence of vortex helical structure in TC and the role of helicity in modulating surface heat and moisture fluxes. The result shows that there is no definite TC intensity at which the initiation of negative feedback of TC-upper ocean interaction occurs. However, the increase in helicity above $200 \times 10^{-2} \text{ ms}^{-2}$ reversed the TC-ocean interaction trend. Therefore, TC helicity evolution and upper ocean interaction are essential to understand TC evolution. Rajasree et al. (2016) have discussed the delayed intensification of TC Florence due to the entrainment of dust aerosol. In this study, for TC Ockhi, it is observed that in spite of a higher diabatic heating rate, experienced rapid weakening over the ocean due to the intrusion of a very dry layer in the middle troposphere in the TC inner core disrupting the convection.

METHODS

The 3-hourly IMD tropical cyclone best track data for maximum surface wind and minimum sea level pressure has been used in this study. Reanalysis datasets have been developed using the Advanced Research Weather Research and Forecasting (ARW) model coupled with a 1D simple ocean model and 3-Dimensional Ensemble Variational (3DEnVAR) techniques for assimilation of Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS) satellite radiance data and scatterometer derived ocean surface wind data assimilation. The GFS analysis data was used to initialize the model to generate high resolution ($2 \text{ km} \times 2 \text{ km}$) reanalysis. The model has been configured in two-way nesting domain consisting of three domains with horizontal resolutions of 18 km (first domain), 6 km (second domain), and 2 km (third domain). Developed reanalysis has been used in this study to analyze the dynamics. Total helicity density in three dimensions at a given space point (H) used for this study has been calculated using the formula:

$$H = \mathbf{V} \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{V}) = u \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) + v \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + w \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right), \text{ where}$$

$$\mathbf{V} = \hat{i} u + \hat{j} v + \hat{k} w = \text{wind vector.}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The life cycle of TC depends on moisture and heat flux through air-sea interaction at the upper ocean layer. Helicity is an indicative characteristic of TC evolution. In this study, we have analyzed the feedback of TC and the upper ocean by figuring out the TC intensity evolution with the variation of lower tropospheric helicity density, moisture, and heat flux at the air-sea interface. At the formation stage of the vortex, the southeast sector of the eyewall region showed a negative H for TC Fani and Ockhi. However, at the developed stage, the helicity density in the whole eyewall region becomes highly positive due to the dominance of convective plumes with cyclonic vorticity. At the time of helical formation, maximum column integrated moist static energy (CIMSE) tends to converge at the TC center, and the streamline started showing comma comma-shaped coiling structure in place of the circulation pattern. A very dry layer in the middle troposphere at the dissipation stage of TC Ockhi has been observed, which is associated with the dry air intrusion in the TC inner core disrupting the convection, leading to rapid weakening.

Primarily, at the development stage of a TC, the heat and moisture flux from the ocean surface increases with the increasing intensity of the TC. However, further increment in the TC intensity causes strong turbulent mixing in the underlying ocean after a particular stage. Hence, the temperature of the upper ocean layer starts decreasing, leading to a decrease in heat and moisture flux. While analyzing the maximum surface wind speed and minimum sea level pressure as a proxy of the TC intensity, it has been observed that the negative TC-Ocean feedback initiates when the TCs Fani, Luban, and Ockhi intensify more than 48 ms⁻¹, 22 ms⁻¹, 35 ms⁻¹ in maximum surface wind speed, and 955 hPa, 995 hPa, 980 hPa in minimum sea level pressure respectively. Thus, there is no specific level of intensity in terms of either maximum surface wind speed or minimum sea level pressure, which ensures further intensification leading to a decrease in heat and moisture flux. On the other hand, the evolution of helicity density showed that intensification more than the H value around 200×10^{-2} ms⁻², irrespective of TC's maximum surface wind speed or minimum sea level pressure, exhibited decreasing trends in heat and moisture flux. It may be due to the representation of the screw-like motion of helicity, which better characterizes the churn-up of upper ocean layers. This study suggests that more importance should be paid to the evolution of helicity and consequent mutual TC-ocean exchanges, not only to understand the TC genesis but also to understand better the TC-induced heat and moisture flux from the upper ocean. Further study in the other TC basins is required to clarify the importance of helicity evolution in reversing the heat and moisture flux trend.

CONCLUSIONS

Feedback between helicity and ocean surface fluxes controls the life cycle of tropical cyclones. There is no definite tropical cyclone intensity level, which ensures the initiation of a decreasing trend of heat moisture flux. Increased helicity density above 200×10^{-2} ms⁻², irrespective of intensity, caused a decrease in heat and moisture flux trends. A very dry layer in the middle troposphere at the dissipation stage of TC Ockhi has been observed, which is associated with the dry air intrusion in the TC inner core disrupting the convection, leading to rapid weakening.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank NCAR, USA, for making the WRF model available for simulations. The authors are also grateful to ESA, ISRO, NCEP, NOAA, and NRL for providing datasets for cyclic data assimilation.

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LONG-RANGE TRANSPORTED DESERT DUST PERTURBATING EASTERN HIMALAYAN ATMOSPHERIC BACTERIAL BIODIVERSITY

A. PRAMANICK^a, *, S.R. SAIKH^a, MD. ABU MUSHTAQUE^a, S.K DAS^a, *

^aDepartment of Physical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, India

*Corresponding author- antarastb@gmail.com, sanatkrdas@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Airborne Bacteria, Dust, Long-Range Transport, Biodiversity, Eastern Himalayas, Health

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, long-range transported desert dust has been a prime interest of research for atmospheric scientists due to their potential capability to impact human health, agriculture, and climate processes by introducing unique types of airborne microorganisms over downwind regions (Pöschl and Shiraiwa 2015). There are several evidence in the literature regarding the long-range transport of bacteria attached to dust particles traveling long distances, like crossing the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, and can act as pathogens and allergens and contribute significantly to regional biogeochemical cycles (Maki et al. 2022). The present study focuses on the long-range transported bacteria and their cause-and-effect relationship on the perturbation of atmospheric bacterial biodiversity over the Eastern Himalayas.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Darjeeling (27°03'N, 88°26'E), a high-altitude site (2.2 km amsl) over the Eastern Himalayas. Total fifteen aerosol samples were collected on filter papers with 0.22µm pore size and 47 mm diameter from winter ($6.2 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 85.2 \pm 9.6\%$) and summer season ($16 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 93.5 \pm 6.5\%$). Aerosol particle concentrations were measured using ground-based particle counter SMPS, while observations from space-borne sensors like MODIS, OMI, and CALIPSO provide information about the horizontally transported dust layer at the measurement site. A back-trajectory analysis was carried out to identify the possible dust emission source. DNA was extracted from filter papers and DNA sequencing was carried out to identify the bacteria using the Illumina NextSeq platform targeting the v3-v4 region of 16S rRNA. Further bioinformatics analysis was performed to investigate bacterial composition, Shannon diversity index and identification of pathogenic genera present in the atmosphere over the Eastern Himalayas (Saikh et al. 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A significant seasonal variation in aerosol and microbial characteristics is noticed over Darjeeling. SMPS data shows a 70% increase in particle concentration during summer, with a modal size shift from 110 nm in winter to 150 nm in summer, suggesting the presence of bigger particles. Satellite data indicates an increase in AOD from 0.4 ± 0.3 to 0.7 ± 0.3 and a decrease in angstrom exponent from 1.6 ± 0.04 to 0.3 ± 0.1 , reflecting the dominance of coarser particles in summer. The spatial distribution of aerosol index (AI) exhibits a significant enhancement of about 2.1 from 0.8, indicating UV-absorbing particles spreading from the Thar desert to the Eastern Himalayas. CALIPSO detects a 1 km thick aerosol layer in between 2 to 3 km altitude over the study area as shown in figure 1. 7-days back-trajectories computed

over Darjeeling coincides with the patches of higher values within the spatial distribution of AOD and AI connecting from Thar desert to Eastern India. The combined results indicate long-range transport of desert dust within 2 to 3 km altitude from the Thar Desert to the Eastern Himalayas.

Microbial analysis reveals an enhancement of total cell counts of about $24 \pm 0.4\%$ over hill-top regions during dusty days, with significantly higher Shannon diversity indices (4.4 ± 0.8). As shown in figure 2, beta diversity exhibits a distinct bacterial community during the dusty period in summer with unique type of bacteria, dominated by *Flavobacterium* ($5.4 \pm 3.6\%$), *Nocardioides* ($4.2 \pm 3.0\%$), and *Corynebacterium* ($4.2 \pm 1.4\%$) while in winter dominating bacteria are *Corynebacterium* ($2.4 \pm 0.5\%$), *Acinetobacter* ($1.8 \pm 0.9\%$), and *Massilia* ($1.3 \pm 0.3\%$). Pathogenic bacteria like *Afipia* and *Clostridium*, responsible for infections in humans and animals, are detected only in summer and associated with dust particles, indicating increased potential health risks. Present findings suggest that transported dust-associated airborne bacteria directly perturb airborne bacterial communities over downwind Himalayan regions

Figure- 1: CALIPSO observation on a typical day in winter (06 January 2022, top) and summer (10 April 2022, bottom). From left to right, satellite path and star represent the location of Darjeeling; vertical profiles of aerosol extinction coefficient at 532nm (green) and 1064 nm (red); angstrom exponent; depolarization ratio. Shaded regions represent the optically thick dust layers.

Figure- 2: PCoA plot of beta diversities computed from each sample collected in the summer and winter seasons of 2022. Two separate ellipses are observed for winter and summer conditions. Atmospheric bacteria on dusty summer days exhibit a unique community of bacteria distinct from winter over the Eastern Himalayas.

CONCLUSION

Long-range transport of desert dust from the Thar Desert significantly impacts aerosol characteristics and airborne microbial communities over the Eastern Himalayas. The dust influx alters bacterial composition, introducing distinct and potentially pathogenic species during summer. These findings suggest important implications for both environmental dynamics and public health in downwind regions, emphasizing the need for further investigation into the region's ecological and health effects of dust-associated microbes.

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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS ON LIGHTNING ACTIVITY OVER INDIA

SUBHOJIT GHOSHAL CHOWDHURY¹, DILIP GANGULY¹, SAGNIK DEY^{1,2,3}

¹Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

²Arun Duggal Centre of Excellence for Research in Climate Change and Air Pollution, Delhi

³Department of Health, Policy and Management, Korea University, Seoul, South Korea

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Lightning, Aerosol Composition

INTRODUCTION

Electrification in deep convective clouds, which produces lightning, accounts for nearly one-third of annual accidental deaths in India (NCRB, 2022). Recent studies have focused on understanding lightning-producing thunderstorms in the Indian subcontinent, emphasizing meteorological factors like large-scale circulations that enhance atmospheric instability and lightning frequency (Pawar et al., 2012; Chakraborty et al., 2021). While global research shows that aerosols significantly influence mesoscale convective activities, the exact mechanisms remain unclear (Altaratz et al., 2017). Some studies suggest that elevated aerosol layers stimulate lightning, particularly where aerosol-cloud interactions dominate (Li et al., 2019). The size and composition of aerosols play crucial roles in modulating lightning intensity (Stolz et al., 2017), but only a few studies (Chaudhury & Middey 2013; Lal et al., 2018; Jnanesh et al., 2022) in India have examined aerosol properties in relation to lightning characteristics. This study addresses these gaps by investigating the relationships between aerosol characteristics and lightning flash rates in three climatologically distinct regions during the premonsoon season (March-May) based on data from 1998 to 2022. Additionally, we conducted numerical simulations of extreme lightning events to better understand the underlying processes.

METHODS

We analyzed lightning flash count data from the Lightning Imaging Sensor (LIS) on the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM, 1997–2014) and the International Space Station (ISS, 2017–2022). Hourly aerosol optical depth (AOD) data from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Application version 2 (MERRA-2) at $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$ resolution supported our analysis. To investigate cloud microphysical properties related to lightning activity, we utilized ERA-5 datasets for ice water path and liquid water path at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution, capturing atmospheric convection effectively. We classified days as '**lightning days**' if at least 50% of grid cells in the study regions recorded lightning. For these days, we extracted total and species-specific AOD from MERRA-2 one hour prior to the lightning event, along with cloud and meteorological variables from ERA-5. Additionally, we conducted numerical simulations using the WRF model with spectral bin microphysics, modifying initial cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) concentrations and size spectra for sensitivity studies, assuming a constant vertical CCN concentration up to 2 km, followed by an exponential decrease.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

We observed a total aerosol optical depth (AOD) increase of about 0.1 across all regions. Dust concentrations rose significantly before lightning events, particularly in northeast India and

Bangladesh, where anthropogenic aerosols are prevalent. On lightning days, carbonaceous aerosols increased notably in two dust-heavy regions, while sulfate aerosols rose across all areas.

Figure 1: Cumulative distribution frequency of mean optical depth for total and different aerosol species during lightning and non-lightning days over (a-d) Region1, (e-h) Region2 & (i-l) Region3. The shaded areas in (a-l) represent the standard deviation of the datasets.

To examine the relationship between aerosol species and lightning flash rates, we categorized aerosol concentrations into percentiles. As dust fractions increased from the 5th to the 95th percentile, lightning flash rates rose by approximately 0.25 flashes/km². Although carbonaceous aerosols had a minimal overall impact, they correlated positively with flash rates up to the 50th percentile in dust-dominated areas. Convective strength was closely linked to local meteorological conditions; increases in Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE) and specific humidity enhanced updrafts and deep convective cloud formation. Model simulations showed that both increased aerosol number concentration and modifications to size spectra heightened lightning flash intensity, with sensitivity more pronounced for number concentration changes. Overall, enhanced updrafts and moisture availability boosted lightning flash intensity across all regions.

Figure 2: Model derived lightning flash intensity over the study domain from (a-b) ccn number concentration & (c-d) Size spectra sensitivity simulations.

CONCLUSION

Observational and model simulations reveal that aerosol characteristics significantly modulate convective activity. In arid regions where dust is the dominant aerosol, increased carbonaceous aerosols on lightning days enhance dust's efficacy as ice nuclei. This optimal aerosol composition, coupled with favourable meteorological conditions, leads to convective intensification. Conversely, in humid regions, higher dust concentrations within a fine aerosol matrix facilitate deep convective cloud formation. Additionally, aerosols influence thermodynamic properties, modifying cloud microphysics and promoting cloud invigoration. Therefore, assessing aerosol composition is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the aerosol-lightning relationship.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The First author acknowledges IIT Delhi for the institute assistantship. We would like to thank IIT Delhi high performance computing facilities for providing the computational resources required for the work.

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IMPACT OF DUST AEROSOLS ON ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THUNDERSTORMS

Abhijeet Gangane, S. D. Pawar and V. Gopalakrishnan

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Pune, India.

Corresponding Author: abhijeet.gangane@tropmet.res.in

KEYWORDS: Lightning, Thunderstorm, Dust Storm, Northern India.

INTRODUCTION

Dust storms are common meteorological natural hazards that occur in dry, arid, and semi-arid regions. Usually, they result from convection created by intense heating of the ground and the lifting of small particles by strong winds. Occasionally, severe dust storms are reported during pre-monsoon season over the northern parts of India. Lightning flashes were reported in dust storms; however, the electrical nature of such thunderstorms has not been studied extensively in the Indian region. Lightning is one of the most widespread and deadly hazards, with the highest death rates in India. The Main Objective of this research is to understand the Effect of dust particles on lightning flash rate and polarity of dust storms over the Indian region.

METHODS

Here, we present some cases of thunderstorms associated with dust storms that occurred in 2019 and 2020 over north and northwest India. It is expected that such thunderclouds associated with dust storms can have a large number of dust particles entered into them. These dust particles can affect the microphysical and electrical characteristics of these storms. We studied the significant impact of these dust events on thunderstorm's electrical characteristics using Indian Lightning Location Network (ILLN) data of IITM, Pune, which provides 95% CG lightning efficiency and can classify as Intra-Cloud (IC), Cloud to Ground (CG) +, and CG – discharges. The effect of increased dust particles on polarity and lightning flash rate in these thunderclouds has been discussed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We have analyzed six cases of convective dust storms that occurred over north and northwest India. Satellite observations show significant dust content in the atmosphere over those locations. In India, dust storms are mainly convective, and most of the time, they are accompanied by heavy winds and lightning, which cause substantial damage to human lives and property. Along with high lightning flash rates, high surface winds, and High Peak currents (Table 1), an increased number of positive CG lightning makes these storms more hazardous. Six cases of dust storms shown in Table 1 below are taken from Gangane et al., 2023.

Sr. No	Dust storm cases	April 7, 2019 (Northwest)	May 11, 2019 (Northwest)	May 15, 2019 (Northwest)	June 6, 2019 (Northern)	June 12, 2019 (Northern)	May 10, 2020 (Northern)
1	Total duration of the storm in hour	8	6	8	12	11	12
2	Average surface wind speed in km/hr	54	36	28.8	43.2	43	79.2
3	Total IC flashes during storm	5682	5990	5684	71,470	13,896	117,518
4	Total positive CG flashes during storm	123	196	312	3164	321	6133
5	Total negative CG flashes during storm	272	424	440	2781	626	13,673
6	Positive to negative CG ratio	0.45	0.46	0.71	1.13	0.51	0.45
7	Peak flash rate per minute (1 h Avg.)	24.25	24.82	24.92	200.4	48.4	349
8	Positive CG averaged peak current (kA)	43.03	42.36	44.27	54.60	44.21	56.26
9	Negative CG averaged peak current (kA)	22.26	36.01	32.36	39.68	23.62	29.27

Table 1. Summarization of the characteristics of all six dust storm cases. It gives information about all dust storm cases in the region, total storm duration, surface wind speed, and lightning characteristics. When a thunderstorm is loaded with dust aerosols, it exhibits more positive CG Lighting throughout the storm's lifetime. All six cases of Convective dust storms produce more than 30 percent of Positive CG lightning in the total CG lighting (Figure 1), which is considered to be very high compared to ordinary thunderstorms. Positive CG lightning was observed in the storm's initial, active, and dissipation stages. Also, our observation clearly suggested that severity is not the cause of more positive CG discharges observed in dust storms. All these six dust storms exhibit positive CG lightning, whose peak current is much higher than that of negative CG lightning. Such occurrence of positive lightning with a high peak current may result in a higher number of lightning-related hazards.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of positive CG and negative CG lightning for six dust storm cases that occurred over Northern and Northwestern parts of India.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been proposed that increased dust particles inside thunderstorms can affect thunderclouds' microphysical and electrical characteristics. Dust particles over the study region act as ice nuclei; a recent study of a dust storm over IGP by Shukla et al. (2022) shows that a dust intrusion into the storm acts as ice nuclei and Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN) induced a favorable condition for charge separation leading to the generation of an electric field and triggering the lightning activity. With the abundance of dust particles in the thundercloud and increased positive CG discharges, it has been proposed that increased dust particles can modify the vertical distribution of ice particles inside a thundercloud and affect

the lightning flash rate as well as polarity. The dust aerosols, serving as effective IN and CCN within the thunderstorm, likely increased the presence of ice-phase particles and supercooled water, leading to a higher proportion of +CG lightning.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by IITM, which is funded by the Ministry of Earth Sciences and the Government of India. The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Director of the IITM for his support and encouragement.

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PM_{2.5} BOUND CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT ANALYSIS DURING STUBBLE BURNING PERIOD IN PUNJAB: IMPLICATIONS FOR DELHI'S AIR QUALITY

ANJANAY PANDEY¹, MOHD FAISAL¹, AJIT KUMAR², UMER ALI¹, VIKAS GOEL²,
SOMBIR PANNU¹, SUMAN MOR³, KHAIWAL RAVINDRA⁴, MAYANK KUMAR^{2*}
AND VIKRAM SINGH^{1*}

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi Hauz Khas, Delhi

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi

³ Department of Environment Studies, Panjab University, Chandigarh, 110014, India

⁴ Department of Community Medicine and School of Public Health, Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research (PGIMER), Chandigarh, 160012, India

Corresponding author mail: - vs225@iitd.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Organic Aerosol, Source Apportionment, Biomass Burning, Farm Fires.

INTRODUCTION

Stubble burning (SB) in the North-Western region of Delhi is well documented to have a significant impact on air quality, especially during post-monsoon season. This is ascertained from relatively high potassium and levoglucosan (m/z 60) levels during the stated season, as mentioned in Delhi-based measurement studies (Faisal et al., 2023). However, air mass reaching Delhi has already undergone significant atmospheric transformation, thereby carrying aged aerosols to the measurement site. On-site measurements in upwind areas, including extensive PM_{2.5} characterization are required, which is crucial to better understand the chemical composition of relatively 'fresh' SB origin aerosols, studies which are scarce in the region. Thus, this study addresses this requirement by deploying high-resolution measurements in the state of Punjab during stubble burning period characterizing PM_{2.5} chemical composition and related gaseous measurements.

METHODS

A dedicated measurement campaign was conducted in Khera Village, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab during an intense crop residue burning period (27 Oct – 18 Nov 2023). High resolution and real-time suite of PM_{2.5} characterization and gaseous instruments were employed through a mobile research platform i.e., Clean Air Research laboratory (CARLab). As the measurement campaign coincided with the residue burning period under open, field-scale combustion conditions, the obtained measurements are expected to be relatively 'fresh' and dominated by CRB emissions. Firstly, variability in PM_{2.5} constituents and gaseous species during the sampling period were reported. Next, validation of the influence of fires on our measurements was made through satellite data and observations of an increase in biomass related markers as reported in the literature. Further, a composition-based source apportionment technique was employed to derive the CRB source profile. Finally, as the NCT of Delhi is located relatively downwind, a thorough discussion of the obtained results in the context of Delhi's air quality issues is included to highlight the important findings obtained in this study.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Organics constitute a major fraction of non-refractory PM_{2.5} (~75.1%) measured via aerosol chemical speciation monitor (Q-ACSM) while sulfur, potassium and chloride dominate the elemental composition measured via Xact 625i. Black Carbon (BC) was measured via an aethalometer, and an average concentration of ~12.7 µg/m³ was observed. Further, source apportionment analysis via positive matrix factorization (PMF) was conducted to develop a CRB source profile based on elemental markers validated by the higher contribution of total organics and BC. Based on PMF analysis, the following six factors were resolved: - dust (~11.2%), biomass burning (~52.5%), S-rich (~25.8%), Zn-rich (~1.4%), Pb-rich (~1.6%) and Cu-Fe-Ti (~7.6%) factor. The last three factors showed peaks in early mornings while the S-rich factor shows an insignificant diurnal pattern. Interestingly, the elemental chloride is apportioned with potassium in the biomass burning factor indicating fresh emissions due to ongoing CRB activity during the sampling period. This chloride usually comes as a separate secondary chloride factor in Delhi as reported in several studies. Thus, the study provided much-needed high-resolution measurements in a near-source environment targeting CRB activity in north-western parts of India. Finally, our obtained results were thoroughly discussed in the context of Delhi's air quality to further the understanding of regional CRB activity on Delhi's local air quality.

Figure 1. (Left) Factor profile for elemental PMF coupled with organics and black carbon and (Right) Contribution of each factor to total mass

CONCLUSIONS

This study conducted a field campaign characterizing PM_{2.5} composition in the north-west of Delhi during the crop residue burning period. Organic aerosols dominated the overall NR-PM_{2.5} composition contributing to ~75.1%. The influence of crop residue burning is clearly visible in the region highlighted by enhanced concentrations of known markers of biomass burning such as levoglucosan and potassium. Further, chloride concentration is observed to have a good correlation with potassium (Pearson's R = 0.85). Furthermore, source apportionment results based on PMF retrieved following six factors with biomass burning contributing to ~52.5%. Further, it clearly distinguished the CRB factor profile with dominant contribution from chloride and potassium which is well validated by higher contribution of

Org and BC. This clearly shows that CRB is one of the sources of primary particulate chloride in the region which is due to atmospheric transformation observed as secondary chloride in several studies based in Delhi. Lastly, understanding air pollution sources in terms of their contribution to primary and secondary aerosols is important from a policy perspective (to take actionable measures), which can only be better understood if the signature of fresh emissions is determined from dominant sources in the region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the IRD Grand Challenge Project grant, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (Grant No. 428 IITD/IRD/MI01810G), under the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India, for the funding support to carry out this work.

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INVESTIGATION OF SMOKE AEROSOL EMISSION AND FOREST FIRE INTENSITY OVER THE NORTHWESTERN HIMALAYAS USING SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

BHARATI PAUL AND U.C. DUMKA

Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences Nainital Uttarakhand India

KEYWORDS: Fire Radiative Power, Aod 550 Nm, Meteorology, Smoke Emission Rate

INTRODUCTION

Smoke emission from forest fires influences regional air quality and climate, weather and human health (ref). These impacts of smoke have been underscored by the increasing fire occurrence and intensity in the past decade over the mountainous terrain of Northwestern Himalayas, particularly in Uttarakhand (Binjola et al., 2022; Goparaju et al., 2023b; Lawand et al., 2022; Mina et al., 2023; FSI 2017); and still, the association between fire intensity, smoke emissions rate and the subsequent impact on local meteorology and aerosol concentration remains poorly constrained. Thus, this study examines how the Fire Radiative power [FRP a widely used metric for assessing the intensity of active vegetation fires] is related to the smoke aerosol emission rate, Aerosol Optical Depth [(AOD 550 nm) one of the key parameters for measuring the columnar aerosol load]. Consequently, their cumulative impact on regional meteorology. This study is important for untangling the competing effects of changing fire behaviour versus its influences on aerosol loading and meteorology.

METHODS

For this study FRP, meteorological variables namely air temperature and relative humidity, AOD 550 nm are acquired from MODIS Terra (MOD14), Aqua (MYD14) Collection 6.1 NRT (Near Real-Time processing in UTC) with high confidence (>80% confidence level) active fire products, ERA5 ECMWF, MODIS AQUA and TERRA respectively. All the data are spatiotemporally collocated for active fire days for 13 microregions across the Uttarakhand region during the 2022-2023 fire season. The 13 microregion represents the 20 km buffer area around each zonal headquarters of the state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Inter-monthly spatial distribution of AOD 550 nm across the 13 different microregions of Uttarakhand.

Fig. 2 Variation of the fire variables across the 13 microregions of Uttarakhand.

CONCLUSION

FRP and AOD 550 nm were relatively higher during April-June. In 2019 as compared to other years, fire intensity was higher, and the FRP ranged from 12.65 to 32.55 MW in all the microregions. Microregions namely Udham Singh Nagar and Bageswar from the Kumaon division, and Uttarkashi and Chamoli from the Garhwal division were the worst-hit regions in terms of fire intensity and smoke aerosols.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences for providing the lab facilities for the implementation of the work.

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FLOOD INUNDATION MAPPING FOR TWO EXTREME ENDS OF INDIA

R. K. BUKHARI¹, T. TURAKHIA² AND R. IYER¹

¹Department of Physics and Electronics, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad

²Research Scholar, Gujarat Technological University, Ahmedabad – 382424, India.

KEYWORDS: Extreme Events, Flood Inundation, Land Cover, Weather.

INTRODUCTION

Extreme weather events are intense and unusual occurrences caused by shifts in climate patterns. These events have become more frequent due to the effects of global warming (Center for Climate and Energy Solutions). Heavy downpours, coupled with urbanization, often result in waterlogging in cities. Additionally, these changes disrupt wildlife habitats, including natural parks and sanctuaries. Flood inundation mapping, using satellite data, plays a crucial role in identifying vulnerable areas and providing essential resources to affected populations.

METHODS

The present study aims to monitor the flood event in the city of Vadodara, Gujarat which lies in the Western region (WR) of India and Kaziranga National Park, Assam in Eastern India (EI). Vadodara experiences semi - arid climate with rainfall mainly in the months of June to September attributed to South West Monsoon (Anand Agricultural University) whereas the state of Assam has Tropical Monsoon Climate (Portal of Assam Chief Minister). The present study involves the use of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data for monitoring the regions and to provide flood inundation maps for the time span of January to August 2024. The true colour images were generated by employing various bands of Sentinel-2 by means of Google Earth Engine Platform (GEE). Furthermore, to detect the change of land cover Scene Classification Map (SCL) was considered. The Flood inundation maps were obtained by taking the difference between the before and after Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) product.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

(a) January 2024

(b) August 2024

(c) Flood Inundation

Figure 1. Before (January 2024), After (August 2024) imagery and Flood Inundation (red) with Vadodara's before the image in the background

Figure 1 depicts the imaging of SAR for the months of January and August with the Flood Inundation. It can be seen in Figure 1 (c) that various parts of Vadodara are exposed to flood water near the banks of river Vishwamitri as well as Ajwa Lake (Top right corner highlighted by the yellow box) whereas the city faces the water logging instances due to the urbanized

infrastructure. Similarly, there is a rise in the water level of Lake Timbi (Purple Box in Figure 1 (b)) which is also noted in Figure 1 (c).

Figure 2. Before (January 2024), After (May 2024) imagery and Flood Inundation (red) with before true color image in the background of Kaziranga National Park

Figure 3. SCL based maps of Kaziranga National Park for Before (January 2024) and After (May 2024)

The Kaziranga National Park lies near the banks of the river Bramputra as seen in Figures 2 and 3. The heavy flow of water in the river is due to the heavy downpours in the month of May (Figure 2(b)) on account of cyclone Remal (Akshit, 2024) and this led to the flood like situation in the national park. Besides this, a change in land cover type is noted. More green cover is visualized in the month of May (Figure 3 (b)) in comparison to January (Figure 3 (a)) correlating with the decrease in barren land form.

CONCLUSIONS

Global warming is one of the bases for the rise in occasion of extreme events. As a consequence of it, the lives of humans and other species are affected. Moreover, situations like floods tend to disturb the ecosystem and land properties and the after-math situation may require several days to get back to its original form. Strategies should be planned in order to implement steps to curb the effects of global warming.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the GEE platform and its team members for providing the data.

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STUDIES ON DUST RESUSPENSION FROM FREE FALL OF BULK MATERIALS USING A MECHANISTIC APPROACH

U. MEHTA^{1*}, V.S. VAMSI BOTLAGUDURU¹, M. BOSE², V. SETHI¹

¹Environmental Science and Engineering Department

²Department of Energy Science and Engineering IIT Bombay, Mumbai - 400076, India

Email: *204180002@iitb.ac.in,

KEYWORDS: Dem, Free Fall, Surface Energy, Dust Detachment, Bulk Materials

INTRODUCTION

Dust resuspension from open stockpiles is a pressing air pollution issue in port operations (Martín et al., 2007; Shipei & Bin, 2020). Dust particles are separated from bulk materials due to adhesive forces between particles and surfaces (Bagnold, 1971). Two key mechanisms drive this process: free fall, where aerodynamic forces caused by impact stress release fine particles, and forced elevation, where wind lifts and disperses dust from exposed surfaces (Chakravarty et al., 2019). Extensive studies have been conducted on dust generation from the free fall of powders over the past decades (Bach & Schmidt, 2008; Pensis et al., 2010; Plinke et al., 1995), however understanding of the physics behind the detachment of dust from bulk materials remains limited (Schulz et al., 2022, 2023). The present study uses the Discrete Element Method (DEM) to model particle-fluid interactions and quantify dust resuspension from free fall of different materials by accounting for properties such as modulus of elasticity, which affects particle deformation under stress, and surface energy, which influences adhesion forces.

METHODS

This study employs the simulation framework established by Schulz et al. (2022) as a baseline, utilizing LAMMPS to replicate and extend their findings. Key material properties and DEM parameters, including the restitution coefficient and friction coefficient were derived by Woschny et al. (2021) through single-drop tests. The study was carried out to predict the detachment of a monolayer of calcium carbonate powder (particle diameter: 20 µm) from stainless steel spheres (diameter: 0.0015 m). The present study aims to replicate this simulation and extend the matrix by quantifying the effects of different bulk materials (coal, iron ore, and limestone) and fall heights (1cm and 5 cm drop) on dust detachment processes. The parameters used for the study are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters Used for LAMMPS Modelling

Property	Schulz et al., 2022*	Coal	limestone	Iron-ore
Density (kg/m³)	2700 (L), 7700 (SS)	1060	2650	2000
Modulus of elasticity (Gpa)	7.76E+10(SS) 2.15E+11 (L)	4.00E+09	7.76E+10	7.00E+08
Poisson's Ratio	0.30 (L), 0.37 (SS)	0.25	0.3	0.2
Coefficient of Restitution (e)	0.65 (L-SS), 0.35 (L-L)	0.4	0.35	0.45
Friction coefficient (µc)	0.3	0.4	0.7	0.5

*Here, L stands for limestone and SS stands for stainless steel

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

LAMMPS script was used to replicate the findings of Schulz et al. (2022), simulating a monolayer consisting of approximately 4,597 calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) dust particles adhered to a stainless-steel surface. This setup maintains a dust coverage of $X_0 = 20\%$, aligning with the parameters established by Schulz et al. (2022). The simulation results, which validate the model employed in the present study, are displayed in Figure 1. The dust dispersion ratio, defined as the mass ratio of detached dust particles to the initial adhering dust particles, is used to quantify the degree of dust release. A comparison of the results from the present study with those of Schulz et al. (2022) is provided in Figure 2

Figure 1: Qualitative comparison of a dust-resolved DEM-JKR simulation of a single drop test between the present work and Schulz et al., 2022

Figure 2: dust dispersion ratio from a single drop test from height a) 1cm and b) 2 cm for Schulz et al., 2022, coal, limestone, and iron-ore.

CONCLUSIONS

The simulation using parameters from Schulz et al. (2022) demonstrated a dust detachment rate of $40 \pm 9\%$ within 0.0005 seconds of impact, validating our model and aligning with their findings. Extending this matrix to other materials, the 1 cm drop simulations showed coal detaching 61% of dust after the first impact, increasing to 81% after the second, while limestone remained consistent at 26%, and iron ore rose from 7% to 19%. For a 5 cm drop, coal exhibited 34% detachment after the first impact. These results highlight the significant influence of material properties, such as surface energy and modulus of elasticity, on dust detachment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to acknowledge IIT Bombay for providing the equipment and resources for this research. We also extend our thanks to the developers of the LAMMPS for providing resources that contributed to this study.

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SEASONAL BURNING AND AEROSOL TOXICITY: EXPLORING THE OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF FINE PARTICULATES AT AN URBAN SITE OF INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

M.AGARWAL, I. GOYAL AND A. LAKHANI

Department of Chemistry, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh Agra–282005, India.

KEYWORDS: Oxidative Potential, Biomass Burning, Polyaromatic Hydrocarbons, Aerosol Toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

India, with its large population and agricultural emphasis, is a major source of burning activities that carry significant environmental and health consequences. Common practices like crop residue burning, wood combustion, fuel burning, and other open fires release a variety of pollutants, particularly particulate matter (PM) rich in complex organic compounds. These emissions contribute to climate change and pose serious risks to human health. Notably, these burning activities vary seasonally, with distinct patterns and impacts observed during the summer and winter months. Thus, this study aims to evaluate the chemical composition of aerosols and their toxicity, specifically in terms of oxidative potential (OP), during the distinct burning periods of summer and winter (Hakimzadeh et al., 2020).

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected from an urban site in Agra from January to December 2023 using a low-volume sampler. The analysis included measurements of organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), water-soluble inorganic ions (WSII), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). The OP of the samples was assessed using the dithiothreitol (DTT) assay (Goyal et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results demonstrate a significant seasonal variation in PM_{2.5} concentrations, with winter burning exhibiting much higher levels ($246.7 \pm 75.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) compared to summer ($107.3 \pm 39.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). This substantial increase in PM_{2.5} during winter can be attributed to intensified burning activities, including wood and coal combustion, which are prevalent in colder months for heating and cooking purposes and lower boundary layers. The elevated PM_{2.5} levels were accompanied by increased concentrations of OC, EC, WSII and PAHs, highlighting the complex nature of emissions from burning sources. To assess the toxicity of PM, OP is a metric that refers to the capacity of a substance, particularly PM, to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) when it encounters biological tissues, such as the lungs. ROS are highly reactive molecules that can cause oxidative stress, leading to cellular damage, inflammation, and various health problems, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. It has been observed that the mass-normalized DTT activity (DTT_m) and volume-normalized DTT activity (DTT_v) during winter were $33.3 \pm 20.2 \text{ pmol min}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ and $9.7 \pm 12.6 \text{ nmol min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$, respectively, indicating higher toxicity compared to the summer values of $31.3 \pm 20.2 \text{ pmol min}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ and $1.1 \pm 2.6 \text{ nmol min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$. These findings suggest that winter aerosols are

more toxic, posing greater health risks to the urban population of Agra. The DTT_m and DTT_v values indicate that winter PM_{2.5} not only has higher mass concentrations but also a more reactive chemical profile, which may lead to increased oxidative stress in exposed individuals. Correlation analysis further strengthens these findings, revealing robust and statistically significant correlations between OP and OC ($r > 0.8$; $p < 0.05$), EC ($r > 0.9$; $p < 0.05$), and WSII ($r > 0.6$; $p < 0.05$). These results suggest that these components are major contributors to the oxidative potential of PM_{2.5}. In contrast, the lack of significant correlation with PAHs indicates that other unmeasured or unidentified compounds may play a role in the oxidative potential of winter aerosols. This highlights the necessity for further investigation into additional sources and chemical species contributing to the toxic effects of PM_{2.5}, especially during high pollution periods. Overall, these findings underscore the urgent need for targeted air quality management strategies to mitigate the health impacts of wintertime air pollution in urban areas like Agra. Source apportionment is crucial for understanding the origins of PM and its associated health impacts. By identifying the main sources of emissions, effective mitigation strategies can be developed. Thus, Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF), a receptor modeling technique, is widely used to identify and quantify the contribution of various emission sources to ambient air pollution. In this study, PMF analysis revealed that wood and coal combustion were the dominant sources of particulate matter during winter, while vehicular emissions were the primary contributors during summer. Stubble burning, however, played a significant role primarily through long-range transport, especially during the post-harvest season.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study reveals significant seasonal variations in PM_{2.5} concentrations, with winter levels ($246.7 \pm 75.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) substantially higher than summer ($107.3 \pm 39.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) exceeding the National Ambient Air Quality System (NAAQS) and World Health Organization (WHO) (15 and $5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively) limits. The increase in winter PM_{2.5} is linked to intensified wood and coal burning for heating and cooking, along with lower boundary layer conditions. Elevated PM_{2.5} levels were associated with increased OC, EC, WSII and PAHs, indicating a complex emissions profile. The assessment of OP showed higher toxicity in winter aerosols, as evidenced by mass-normalized DTT activity (DTT_m) and volume-normalized DTT activity (DTT_v). Strong correlations between OP and OC, EC, and WSII suggest these components significantly contribute to PM_{2.5} toxicity, while the lack of correlation with PAHs points to other unidentified compounds. Additionally, the strong correlation of OC, EC and WSII on the toxicity of PM suggests the involvement of secondary aerosols, which are particularly prevalent during burning events. PMF analysis identified the more influence of burning activities during winter than summer. The burning activities like wood and coal combustion are dominant winter sources, while vehicular emissions prevailed in summer, with stubble burning contributing through long-range transport. These findings highlight the need for targeted air quality management strategies to mitigate health impacts from wintertime air pollution in urban Agra.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Department of Science & Technology-Fund for Improvement of S&T Infrastructure programme, Govt. of India (CS-II/2017/38), Indian Space Research Organisation-Geosphere Biosphere Programme under Atmospheric Trace Gases- Chemistry, Transport and Modelling project.

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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF DUST STORMS ON THE HIMALAYAN RANGE AND INDO-GANGETIC BASIN: A CASE STUDY OVER NORTHERN INDIA

A. YADAV¹, S. KUMAR^{2*}, P. K. YADAWA¹, B. P. SINGH³ AND A. K. SINGH⁴

¹Department of Physics, V. B. S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur – 222003, India

²Department of Earth and Planetary Science, V. B. S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

³Department of Mathematics, M. L. K. (P. G.) College, Balrampur -271201

⁴India Meteorological Department, Lucknow

*Email: sarvanbhaskar07@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Dust Storms, Himalayan Range, Indo-Gangetic Basin, Air Quality

INTRODUCTION

The Himalayan range and the Indo-Gangetic Basin (IGB) in northern India are frequently affected by dust storms, which can have significant environmental and socioeconomic consequences (Singh et al., 2022). In June 2018, these regions experienced particularly severe dust storm events, warranting a detailed investigation of their characteristics and impacts (Dumka et al., 2019). The study was conducted in Kanpur known for its high levels of air pollution, and the impact of the dust storms was particularly pronounced in this region.

METHODS

This study employed a multi-disciplinary approach to analyze the dust storm events. Satellite data from various sources, including MODIS and CALIPSO, were used to track the spatial extent and temporal evolution of the dust plumes (Tiwari et al., 2019). Ground-based measurements, including air quality data aerosol optical depth (AOD) and meteorological parameters water vapour (WV), were collected from the monitoring station at Kanpur. Numerical modeling techniques were utilized to simulate the dust storm dynamics and understand the underlying mechanisms using HYSPLIT back trajectory Model. Data was collected from June 10th to June 20th, 2018, covering the peak of the dust storm events.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The satellite data analysis revealed that the dust storms originated from the deserts of Rajasthan and Pakistan, and were transported into the Himalayan foothills and over the IGB (Fig. 1. a, b).

Figure 1. (a.) Area averaged MODIS derived AOD over India during 10-20 June 2018, (b.) Daily Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) 550 obtained from MODIS-Terra

Ground-based measurements showed a significant increase in AOD concentrations during the dust storm events, leading to a deterioration of air quality and visibility (Fig. 2. a). Meteorological factors, such as high wind speeds and increasing WV concentration were identified during the dust storm events (Fig. 2. b). The HYSPLIT modeling results provided insights into the factors influencing the dust storm's Sources, path, and deposition patterns (not shown here). CALIPSO satellite observation shows the elevated layers of mixed type of dust layers up to 6 km in height (not shown here).

Figure 2 Day to day variation of AERONET AOD (500nm), Angstrom Exponent (AE440–870nm) and water vapour (cm) during the dust storm events in June 2018.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study highlight the severe impact of dust storms on the Himalayan range and Indo-Gangetic basin, particularly in Kanpur. The high levels of air pollution and the associated environmental and health consequences emphasize the need for comprehensive mitigation strategies and early warning systems to enhance the resilience of the affected communities. The research provides valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and environmental agencies in the region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are thankful to MODIS, CALIPSO and AERONET NASA scientific research team for providing aerosol data. We acknowledge the NOAA HYSPLIT model for back trajectory analysis. This work is supported by UGC New Delhi by UGC Start-up Research Grant (30-573/2021(BSR); Diary No. 1632; Dated: 15 June 2022).

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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF URBANIZATION ON LOCAL CLIMATE CHANGE: ANALYSING AIR QUALITY AND TEMPERATURE EXTREMES OVER THE LAST TWO DECADES (2000-2010 AND 2010-2020) OVER INDIA

ROHAN ANANDA, AMARENDRA SINGHA, SOFIA RAOA AND SAGNIK DEYA
Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi – 110016, India.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Human Settlement, Urbanization, Air Pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization, defined as the increasing population and infrastructure in urban areas, significantly alters local climates and environmental conditions, particularly through the development of urban heat islands (UHIs). These UHIs result from anthropogenic changes to the land surface, including the replacement of vegetation with concrete, asphalt, and other impervious materials that absorb and retain heat. As cities expand, they disrupt the natural surface energy balance, leading to elevated temperatures compared to rural areas. Understanding these temperature variations is vital, as they can contribute to broader climate change implications and skew land temperature records. The effects of urbanization extend beyond rising temperatures, also exacerbating air pollution levels. As urban areas grow, so too do emissions from vehicles, industries, and construction activities, leading to deteriorating air quality. This situation is particularly concerning in densely populated urban centres, where high population density and traffic congestion contribute to significant air pollution. Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is a critical concern, recognized for its harmful health effects, including cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. In fact, studies indicate that a considerable portion of the global population is exposed to unsafe levels of air pollution, with urban residents facing even greater risks. The increasing concentration of people in urban environments, combined with higher temperatures and poor air quality, creates a public health crisis. Research shows that urban areas are not only hotter but also experience a higher incidence of health problems associated with air pollution, leading to premature deaths and reduced quality of life. Given that approximately 86% of urban dwellers live in areas exceeding the World Health Organization's guideline for PM_{2.5}, it is crucial to assess how urbanization affects air pollution and temperature extremes. This study aims to investigate the specific impacts of urbanization on air quality and temperature variations, focusing on different settlement types within a 1x1 km² region. By exploring the complex relationship between urban development, temperature changes, and air pollution, the research seeks to illuminate the challenges posed by urbanization and provide insights into effective mitigation strategies for improving environmental health in urban settings.

METHODS

The research will utilize ERA5 reanalysis data from the Copernicus Climate Change Service to obtain daily temperature records, including minimum (T_{min}), average (T_{avg}), and maximum temperatures (T_{max}) for the region of interest over the period from 2000 to 2020. For air quality assessment, PM_{2.5} concentration data will be sourced from the Randall Martin dataset provided by the University of Washington, which offers high-resolution estimates of particulate matter levels during the same timeframe. Additionally, the Global Human Settlement Data (GHSL) from the European Union will be used to analyse urbanization trends and land use changes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Human settlements are rapidly changing due to factors like population and economic growth, urban transformation, and rural-urban migration. Urbanization drives rapid growth in both large and smaller cities, leading to challenges like air pollution, unplanned development, and increased demand for transport and energy. In middle-income countries like India, with limited land and a large population, spatial growth driven by demand for services is a key factor in the recent rise in PM_{2.5} levels. The present study assesses the change in human settlement during 2000-2020 using global human settlement layer (GHSL) data and corresponding change in satellite derived PM_{2.5} concentration during the period. In 20 years (2000-2020), the PM_{2.5} concentration increased by nearly 47.17% across the country. We found that ‘very low density rural’ areas, which covered 61% of the total geographical area in 2000, declined to 52.29% in 2020, and there is an increase of 11.65 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in PM_{2.5} concentration. The ‘urban centre’ became double in area within that time frame that led to an increase in PM_{2.5} concentration from 36.12 to 56.13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Even though ‘low density rural’ areas, which cover most geographical areas after ‘very low density rural’, did not change much (grew by $\sim 1\%$) in 20 years, the PM_{2.5} concentration increased drastically from 30.87 to 45.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Similarly, the waterbody was almost unchanged (decreased by 0.013%) during the time frame but PM_{2.5} levels increased by 33.54 to 51.71 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

CONCLUSION

This shows that even areas with minimal population growth or spatial expansion experienced significant increases in air pollution, likely due to factors such as industrialization, increased vehicular emissions, and agricultural activities. These findings highlight that not only urban areas but also rural regions have contributed to the rise in PM_{2.5} levels during the last two decades.

MODERATION IN THE RADIATIVE FORCING DURING A CYCLONIC EVENT

NISHI SRIVASTAVA¹

¹Department of Physics, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi – 835215, India.

KEYWORDS: Radiative Forcing, Cyclone, Aerosol, Dust, Sea Salt, Aerosol Optical Depth,

INTRODUCTION

Cyclones-caused disasters are a significant problem with wide-ranging socio-economic effects and a major threat to countries bordering the ocean, similar to the Indian Ocean. The Indian Ocean region witnesses many depressions, deep depressions, cyclonic activity, and severe cyclonic activity (Wahiduzzaman et al., 2022). The socio-economic impact of cyclones is well explored, though their effects on radiative forcing have not been studied well. In the present work, we aim to explore the moderation in radiative forcing due to aerosols generated and redistributed due to cyclonic activity. Aerosols are present everywhere in the lower atmosphere. Aerosol radiative forcing is one of the crucial components of the earth's radiation budget. The moderation in the composition of aerosols or the total mass of the aerosols in the air will change their radiative forcing. Aerosols interact with radiation and clouds in a complex way. Despite drastic improvements in our computational capacities, aerosol radiative forcing still makes up the most uncertain part of the radiative forcing estimations (Bellouin et al., 2020). In the present work, we will observe the changes in the radiative forcing caused by occurrences of a severe cyclone. Research has shown that aerosols play a part in the occurrence of cyclones (Cotton et al., 2012). We know that the aerosols act as condensation nuclei and that the horizontal and vertical movement linked to cyclones causes different aerosol generation (mostly sea salt and dust aerosols) and is transferred to higher altitudes in the atmosphere due to the vertical motion of the wind. Thus, aerosols indirectly contributed to cyclone strength modulation (Rosenfeld et al., 2007; Carrió and Cotton, 2011). However, the role of cyclones in the redistribution and generation of aerosol and associated changes in the radiative forcing is less explored. In the present work, we have studied the change in radiative forcing of aerosols owing to redistribution and aerosol generation associated with a severe cyclone 'Mocha' in the Bay of Bengal region in May 23.

METHODS

During the development of severe cyclone Mocha and its landfall, we assess the changes in aerosols' spatial and vertical distribution across the Bay of Bengal in this work. The Mocha cyclone started to form on 9 May 23 and dissipated by 15 May 23. We selected five days before and after the cyclone time duration to monitor the background conditions before and after the cyclone development. The time duration chosen for this study is from 4 May 23 to 20 May 23. The region selected for the study ranged from 6 °N-22 °N; 84 °E-94 °E. The aerosol concentration and aerosol optical depth are assessed with the help of MERRA-2 reanalysis daily data. The associated change in radiative forcing due to a change in the aerosol concentration due to cyclonic landfall is estimated with the help of the SBDART model (Ricchiuzzi et al., 1998).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In the present work, we assessed the changes in the radiative forcing of aerosols generated and distributed due to cyclonic activity. In order to get the radiative forcing, we should have

an estimate of the concentration of various aerosols. Thus, an initial investigation was carried out to track variations in aerosol concentration as cyclones develop. We looked at the vertical and spatial distribution of sea salt, dust and black carbon (BC) aerosols, as well as aerosol optical depth (AOD). The formation of a cyclone over this area led to a rise in the concentration of various aerosols, primarily the sea salt aerosol and dust aerosols. The variation of sea salt aerosol concentration is shown in the Figure1. The concentration of sea salt was approximately $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ before the cyclonic activity, but as the cyclone developed, it increased to approximately $2400 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the vicinity of the core and its surroundings. Sea salt aerosols are produced by wind over the ocean, and wind stress is a major factor in bubble bursting (Monahan and Muircheartaigh, 1980; Stokes et al., 2013). Enormous wind stress is experienced at the ocean's surface during cyclonic activity, producing many sea salt aerosols. Before the cyclone, the region's dust concentration was less than 5 ppm; however, when the storm approached the land and its landfall, it increased to almost 60 ppm. A notably elevated concentration of dust aerosol was noted following the cyclone's landfall. Increased soil erosion brought on by the cyclone's strong winds and the devastation activities that occur after it makes landfall are the two leading causes of the increase in dust aerosols. As BC is also one of the vital aerosols, thus we investigated the distribution of BC aerosols. Although the concentration of BC does not alter significantly, there is a shift in its spatial distribution. As the spatial variation of aerosols shows a drastic change in concentration, they will also contribute to the change in the distribution of AOD. During this event, there were notable variations in AOD variation. Since the AOD is a measure of aerosol loading in the atmosphere, variations in any of the aerosol components will show up in the AOD variation. AOD spatial distribution showed that sea salt aerosols mainly contributed to the cyclone's formation, and dust aerosol substantially contributed after landfall. The above findings have shown the drastic change in the distribution of various aerosol masses during the process of formation and landfall of a cyclone. The radiative forcing of an aerosol system changes as its mass concentration and distribution change. Thus, the radiative forcing associated with the cyclone will also change significantly. We have used the SBDART model to assess the moderation of radiative forcing, which provides radiative forcing for a specific system. Significant changes in the radiative forcing have been noticed during the life cycle of a cyclone.

Figure 1. Spatial variation of sea salt aerosols over the Bay of Bengal during the development and dissipation of Cyclone (4-19 May 23) (Units: $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

CONCLUSIONS

The prime objective of the study was to study the changes that occurred in the radiative forcing due to changes in the distribution and concentration of aerosols as a result of cyclonic activity. To achieve this, we looked into how the various aerosol components changed throughout a cyclonic activity and also associated changes in AOD. The concentration of dust and sea salt aerosols increased significantly during the cyclonic activity. These aerosols have been observed to grow in duration multiple times during the cyclone's creation and dissipation. The concentration of sea salt aerosols was also seen to be increasing along the same trajectory as the concentration of dust aerosols over Bangladesh and Myanmar, as well as in the vicinity of West Bengal, India. These aerosols are both produced by wind, and during a cyclone, wind stress increases dramatically at the ocean's and land's surface. The concentration of BC aerosol did not exhibit a significant shift. Since AOD levels are a good indicator of atmospheric aerosol loading, they changed noticeably as cyclones formed. Notable changes are observed in the radiative forcing and its distribution during a cyclonic activity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

- We acknowledge the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), India for funding the MATRICS project (MTR/2022/000095)
- We acknowledge GES DISC for MERRA, Version 2 data download.

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CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF PM_{2.5} DURING BIOMASS BURNING PHASES AT AN UPWIND OF SITE OF DELHI-NCR

V. SINGH^{1*}, D. GANGULY¹, J. RATHORE¹, R.K. KUNCHALA¹, SAGNIK DEY^{1,2,3}, S. GANI^{1,4}

¹Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi, India

²Centre of Excellence for Research on Clean Air, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

³School of Public Policy, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

⁴Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research/Physics, University of Helsinki

Email: -*Vasu.Singh@cas.iitd.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Tof-Acsm, Carbonaceous Aerosol, Biomass Burning, Aerosol Composition, Source Apportionment

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols play a crucial role in influencing climate, visibility, and human health, with their impacts largely dependent on their chemical composition as well as their mass (Fuzzi et al., 2015; Park et al., 2018). The Indo-Gangetic Plain, particularly New Delhi, suffers from severe air pollution during the post-monsoon season, driven by both local emissions and regional sources. This period coincides with the practice of stubble burning in the nearby states of Punjab and Haryana, compounded by firecracker emissions from Diwali and unfavorable meteorological conditions, which lead to dangerous air quality levels. The long-range transport of biomass-burning aerosols significantly worsens pollution levels, contributing to the occurrence of dense haze and smog. Although previous studies have focused on offline PM_{2.5} analyses (Tiwari et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2018), real-time chemical characterization remains underexplored. This study fills that gap by analyzing the chemical composition and source apportionment of PM_{2.5} during distinct phases of biomass burning at an upwind site in Sonipat, Haryana, during October-November 2023. The findings provide valuable insights into aerosol transport mechanisms and their impacts on air quality in the region (Chin et al., 2009).

METHODS

This study examines three distinct biomass-burning phases during the post-monsoon season of 2023 at an upwind site in Delhi. Real-time measurements of total PM_{2.5} were taken using a DustTrak and a compact air quality measurement instrument (CUPI-G) sensor, along with continuous monitoring of non-refractory PM_{2.5} (NR-PM_{2.5}) components such as organic aerosols (Org), nitrate (NO₃), sulfate (SO₄), ammonium (NH₄), and chloride (Chl) using a Time-of-Flight Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (ToF-ACSM). Black Carbon (BC) was monitored using an Aethalometer from 01/10/2023 to 24/11/2023. Meteorological data, including wind speed, direction, and temperature, were obtained from an automatic weather station (AWS). Backward trajectory analysis was employed to identify the sources of air masses contributing to the increased aerosol concentrations. The ToF-ACSM data were analyzed to differentiate between primary and secondary aerosols and fresh and aged particles, providing critical insights into the chemical composition and atmospheric processing of the aerosols.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The time series analysis showed significant variability in the concentrations of individual C-PM_{2.5} species throughout the study period. Black carbon (BC) data revealed a strong correlation with organic aerosols during the November 1-15 period. The final week of October and early November saw notably high pollution levels, primarily due to intense biomass burning in Punjab and Haryana. While most C-PM_{2.5} species, particularly organics, peaked after the biomass-burning phase, BC remained an exception, showing unique temporal behavior. Sulfate concentrations exhibited a weak diurnal cycle and diminished after the pre-biomass burning phase. Organic aerosols dominated the composition of NR-PM_{2.5}, with significant temporal variability that closely mirrored the elevated aerosol concentrations during the study. Rain events temporarily reduced aerosol concentrations, providing periods of relief. The prevailing winds from the northwest gradually weakened over time, influencing the transport of aerosols to the observation site.

CONCLUSIONS

This two-month real-time characterization of PM_{2.5} revealed the dominance of organic aerosols (OA), contributing $45.4 \pm 44.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to the total C-PM_{2.5} concentration. A marked increase in non-refractory PM_{2.5} species (Org, Chl, NH₄, NO₃, SO₄) was observed during the second half of the biomass burning period, highlighting the significant contribution of agricultural fires in Punjab and Haryana, particularly during the Parali (stubble) burning season. Meteorological conditions, including the transition to winter, further exacerbated air pollution levels, although occasional rain events provided temporary relief by washing out the aerosols. Analysis of f44 vs. f60 plots confirmed the presence of fresh biomass burning aerosols, while f44 vs. f43 plots indicated aerosol aging, suggesting the significant influence of long-range transport in shaping the region's air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Sonipat Atmospheric Observatory team support and fellowship received from IIT Delhi for conducting this research.

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SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF BLACK CARBON IN RURAL SITE OF PUNJAB USING AETHALOMETER MODEL AND POSITIVE MATRIX FACTORIZATION MODEL: A CASE STUDY

AJIT KUMAR¹, VIKAS GOEL¹, MOHD FAISAL², UMER ALI², ANJANAY PANDEY¹,
MAYANK KUMAR¹, VIKRAM SINGH²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi Hauz Khas

² Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi Hauz Khas

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Source Apportionment, Biomass Burning, Farm Fires, Aethalometer Model, PMF Model.

INTRODUCTION

Black Carbon is a product of the incomplete combustion of fossil fuel, wood, and another biomass. It has detrimental effects on climate and human health. It is well known for its high light absorbing properties, which makes it the second most warming species in the atmosphere after CO₂. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) identifies BC as an important contributor to global warming due to its positive Radiative Forcing (RF) (warming effect). Agricultural waste residue burning is a typical phenomenon that occurs majorly in the Punjab and Haryana districts of India and in Eastern Pakistan during summer and post-monsoon seasons. This emits BC and other pollutants in great amounts and deteriorates the air quality of the Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP) region. In the summers, the residue of the rabi crop is burned in the field post harvesting from mid-April till mid-May and in post-monsoon season kharif crop residue is burned from mid-October till November. The post-monsoon events are proven to be more deadly for the IGP region in reference to air quality. Every year the government impose a ban on these activities and implements policies to improve the air quality of the region but still it is measured in the hazardous category. The main objective of the study is to do source apportionment of BC by two globally used models Aethalometer model (AM) and the PMF model during the stubble burning period.

METHODS

The sampling was conducted at a community health center in Khera Village of Punjab, India (30.604312, 76.489195). The sampling location is surrounded by agricultural fields and adjacent to a road connecting a state highway (12A) and a national highway (NH44). Both the highways were approximately 5 Km away from the sampling site. A thermal power plant (Rajpura Thermal Power Plant) was approximately 10 Km away from the sampling site. The instruments were housed in a temperature controlled mobile laboratory called Clean Air Research Laboratory (CARLab). The campaign was conducted from 27th October – 18th November 2023.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The BC measurements were done using the seven wavelength Aethalometer (AE33; Magee® Scientific). The light attenuation was measured at 370, 470, 520, 590, 660, 880, and 950 nm. The real-time elemental concentration of PM_{2.5} was measured with Xact (625i, Cooper®). Source apportionment of BC has been done by using the Aethalometer model and positive matrix factorization (PMF) model. The BC concentration was measured every minute, and the study averaged BC concentration was 12.6 µg/m³ ranging from 1.45 – 85.0 µg/m³ on a

minute scale. The measured BC concentration is lower than the BC concentration reported over Delhi during the post-monsoon season by Goel et al. (2023) (i.e., 17.23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Goel et al. (2021) (19.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), but similar to what reported over Agra by Gupta et al. (2017) (~ 13.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Aethalometer model has an intrinsic limitation to apportion BC into only two sources such as biomass burning and fossil fuel combustion. The apportionment is done assuming AAE values as 1 for ff and 2 for bb. The assumption is based on the previous studies and the dominant BC sources present at the sampling site. The results represent significant temporal and diurnal variations in BC_{bb} and BC_{ff} concentrations during the study period. The temporal variation of BC_{bb} and BC_{ff} is shown in figure 1b. The study averaged BC_{bb} concentration was 6.22 ± 4.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ranging from 0.50 – 26.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on an hourly scale and BC_{ff} was 6.59 ± 2.76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ranging from 0.71 – 17.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on an hourly scale. The lowest 24 hours averaged BC_{bb} concentration was observed on 11th November and highest on 1st November. Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) identified a six-factor solution for black carbon (BC) sources. Out of the six factors, five were attributed to specific sources of BC. Biomass burning was determined to be the major contributor, accounting for 47.7% of the total BC, followed by power plants (24%), traffic emissions (20.2%), Pb-rich sources (6.1%), and waste incineration (2%). Contribution of different factors to black carbon; a comparison of aethalometer model and PMF results are shown in table 1.

Figure 1: Temporal variations of BC (a), BC_{bb}, and BC_{ff} (b) and AAE (c).

Punjab campaign					
	BC _{bb} % and (mean conc. \pm std.) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	BC _{ff} % and (mean conc. \pm std.) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$		BC _{Miscellaneous} % and (mean conc. \pm std.) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	
Aethalometer model	48.5% (6.22 ± 4.64)	51.5% (6.59 ± 2.76)		N/A	
PMF model	BC _{BB} (5.40 ± 5.27)	BC _{VE} (2.30 \pm 1.95)	BC _{PP} (2.72 \pm 0.97)	BC _{WI} (0.23 \pm 0.29)	BC _{Pb-rich} (0.70 \pm 1.45)
	47.7%	20.2%	24%	2%	6.1%

Table 3: Contribution of different factors to black carbon; a comparison of aethalometer model and PMF results.

CONCLUSIONS

This study identified and quantified black carbon (BC) sources using both the Aethalometer model and Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF). The Aethalometer model apportioned BC into biomass burning (BC_{bb}) and fossil fuel combustion (BC_{ff}), with BC_{bb} contributing 48.6% and BC_{ff} contributing 51.4% to the total BC concentration. PMF analysis provided a more detailed source breakdown, identifying biomass burning as the largest contributor

(47.7%), followed by power plants, traffic emissions, Pb-rich sources, and waste incineration. These results emphasize the need for emission control strategies, especially for biomass burning and power plants, to improve air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the IRD Grand Challenge Project grant, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (Grant No. 428 IITD/IRD/MI01810G), under the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India, for the funding support to carry out this work.

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PM_{2.5}/CO ENHANCEMENT RATIOS TO CHARACTERISE THE INFLUENCE OF AGRICULTURAL FIRES IN URBAN REGION

A. ARORA^{1,2}, S RAMACHANDRAN¹, PRABIR K PATRA^{3,6}, YUTAKA MATSUMI^{3,4},
TOMOKI NAKAYAMA⁵

¹Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad-380009, India

²Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar, India

³Research Institute for Humanity and Nature, Kyoto 6038047, Japan

⁴Institute for Space-Earth Environmental Research, Nagoya University, Nagoya Japan

⁵Faculty of Environmental Science, Nagasaki University, Nagasaki 8528521, Japan

⁶Research Institute for Global Change, JAMSTEC, Yokohama 2360001, Japan

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Co, Monte Carlo, Crop Residue Burning, Flexpart, Indo Gangetic Plain, Agricultural Fires

INTRODUCTION

The daily mean levels of surface particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) pollution in Delhi and its neighboring regions frequently exceed the thresholds established by the World Health Organization (WHO). In Delhi, PM_{2.5} concentrations surpass these limits throughout the year, with an annual mean PM_{2.5} concentration exceeding 100 µg/m³, which poses significant health risks. During the post-monsoon period, large episodic peaks of PM_{2.5} are observed which combined with stagnant meteorological conditions, primarily caused by calmer northwesterly winds, further deteriorates the air quality in the Indo Gangetic Plains (IGP). Additionally, crop residue burning (CRB), which occurs after the harvesting of kharif crops in the post-monsoon season, primarily in Punjab and Haryana, is believed to substantially contribute to the rising levels of air pollution in IGP. Previous studies suggest that the rise in air pollution in Delhi can be linked to CRB, while many research studies indicate that agricultural fires may not have a significant impact. The extent of CRB's contribution to elevated PM_{2.5} levels in the Delhi NCR region remains highly uncertain. Moreover, these fires are often obscured by thick haze and clouds, making them difficult to detect via satellite monitoring. This study aims to address this uncertainty by using enhancement ratios of commonly measured pollutants (PM_{2.5} and carbon monoxide (CO)) from various Air Quality Monitoring sites to assess the contribution of CRB emissions to urban Delhi's air pollution in 2022.

METHODS

Daily mean PM_{2.5} data from September to November 2022, collected at two monitoring sites using Compact and Useful PM_{2.5} Instrument with Gas sensors (CUPI-Gs) (Singh et al., 2023) under AAKASH intensive measurement campaign, in the Delhi NCR region—Gurugram and Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU)—are analyzed (Fig. 1a). JNU is located in the southwest region of Delhi, within an environmentally sensitive area, covering approximately 800 acres of natural vegetation. Gurugram City is situated around 20 miles southwest of New Delhi and is located in the southernmost part of Haryana. During episodic events, the concentrations of atmospheric species rise significantly above background levels. Normalized Enhancement Ratios (NERs), defined as the ratio of the excess concentration of species X to that of species Y ($NER = \Delta X / \Delta Y$, where Δ represents the enhancement over background concentration), are used to quantify these increases. At each monitoring site, in order to identify the contribution

of crop residue burning (CRB) to urban pollution in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), PM_{2.5}/CO NERs are calculated for fire events and compared with Ambient Enhancement ratio (AERs) and background emission ratio. The fire events are selected when the transport from fires to monitoring sites is observed. The transport from fire locations is calculated by tracing the daily back trajectory of PM_{2.5} particles for 5 days using the FLEXPART dispersion model. Only fire events with substantial increases in PM_{2.5} and CO and exhibit a strong correlation (0.65) are selected. The annual average background concentrations for PM_{2.5} (42 µg/m³) and CO (558 µg/m³) give the emission ratio as 84 µg m⁻³ ppm⁻¹. NERs for each selected event are calculated by determining the regression slope between PM_{2.5} and CO concentrations. For background emission ratios over the Delhi region, the study utilizes PM_{2.5} and CO background concentrations from Chaurasia and Mohan (2022), with annual average background concentrations of 42 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5} and 558 µg/m³ for CO, resulting in an emission ratio of 84 µg m⁻³ ppm⁻¹. The data are segregated based on a PM_{2.5}/CO threshold of 84 µg m⁻³ ppm⁻¹ to distinguish CRB contributions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The NERs for background vs data containing CRB influence at the two chosen sites (Fig. 1b, c) for September - November 2022 are significantly different, clearly highlighting the influence of CRB. The regression is steeper at both sites when CRB emissions influence the atmosphere. In the absence of CRB influence, the PM_{2.5} and CO values differ between the two study locations. The slope representing $\Delta\text{PM}_{2.5}/\Delta\text{CO}$ NER in JNU is comparable to the values obtained over Boise, USA (Laing et al., 2017) during a wildfire event, whereas the slope in Gurugram is lower. It should be noted that the range of slopes varies widely due to wildfires (Laing et al., 2017). The results reveal that the correlation and slopes are not strongly influenced by the choice of PM_{2.5}/CO ratios, for example, using the threshold ratio of 50 and 104, we get slopes of segregated datasets as 0.039, 0.112 0.056, and 0.123 µg m⁻³ ppm⁻¹. The observations from the other sites in IGP will be analysed further to derive the spatial features of the influence of CRB on Delhi NCR pollution. Further, using Monte Carlo simulations in an approach proposed by Jaffe et al. 2022, the fraction of PM_{2.5} due to CRB is determined, details of which will be presented.

Fig. 1 (a) Study sites marked by stars, Observed PM_{2.5} vs. CO with PM_{2.5}/CO threshold of 84 µg m⁻³ ppm⁻¹ at (b) JNU (c) Gurugram

CONCLUSIONS

A clear difference in PM_{2.5}/CO emission ratios between typical urban pollution and agricultural fire emissions is evident over Delhi NCR, thus emphasising that this ratio can be effectively used to quantify the contribution of crop residue burning and its impact on air pollution. Further, the quantitative method using Monte Carlo simulations will provide a

range of probability of contribution of PM_{2.5} due to fires, which will be discussed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We sincerely thank the data team for providing the PM_{2.5} and CO data collected under the AAKASH intensive measurement campaign, which is financially supported by the Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN: a constituent member of NIHU). We sincerely acknowledge the developers of the FLEXPART model for providing a model and related software which were obtained from <http://flexpart.eu/>. We acknowledge the use of FIRMS data for satellite fires. We acknowledge the PARAM Vikram-1000 hpc Cluster of the Physical Research Laboratory (PRL) for model calculations.

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ASSESSMENT OF LIGHT ABSORBING CARBONACEOUS AEROSOL AND ITS ABSORPTION PROPERTIES FROM FOREST FIRE IN HIMALAYAN CRITICAL ZONE OBSERVATORY

P. TIWARY, S. KUKRETI, V. SHRIDHAR*.

School of Environment and Natural Resources, Doon University, Dehradun 248001, India

KEYWORDS: Forest fire, optical properties, Himalaya, and carbonaceous aerosol.

INTRODUCTION

A significant amount of carbonaceous aerosols such as Black carbon (BC), Organic aerosol (OA) and Particulate Matter (PM) are released into the atmosphere during forest fires and they significantly impact both global and regional climate (Roeckner et al., 2006; C. Wang, 2004). As per the IPCC's fifth assessment report, the scattering and absorption due to fire cancel out each other but models used in the report typically lack an explicit representation of BrC (IPCC, 2014). The Himalayan region's coniferous forests are highly prone to forest fire, especially in areas dominated by Chir pine or blue pine, which are commonly found at 1000-1800 meters altitude (Vadrevu et al., 2012). The study emphasizes the scarcity of data in the Himalayan region, drawing attention towards the need for policy and decision making focused on forest fires in this critical region. To the best of the author's knowledge, this study is pioneering in ground-based measurement of BC mass concentration, and its absorption properties due to forest fire in the Himalayan critical zone observatory.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study assesses light-absorbing carbonaceous aerosol (LAC) and its optical properties during forest fires in the Himalayan Critical Zone Observatory (1800 m a.s.l) from 2022-2024. The BC mass concentration showed significant variability, with a 66.7% increase during forest fires, driven by biomass burning (58.52%) and fossil fuel combustion (41.48%). Regional sources of BC during summer extended from northern India to Pakistan and Afghanistan, while winter emissions were more localized. BrC absorption was substantial, especially in winter due to residential wood burning, contributing 55.1% to total light

absorption. The feedback loop between forest fire emissions of BC and BrC and atmospheric heating suggests that these aerosols accelerate snow and ice melt in the Himalayas. BrC's contribution to radiative forcing is often underestimated, emphasizing the need for improved climate models and targeted mitigation strategies for biomass burning and fossil fuel emissions in vulnerable regions like the Himalayas.

Figure 1 Violin plot includes box plot comparing babs eBC (880) and babs BrC (370).

CONCLUSIONS

% increase in BC mass concentration was observed to be 66.7% during forest fires. In addition to biomass burning, anthropogenic sources like vehicular emission and other fossil fuel activities also contribute to BC during the forest fire, at the studied site. During forest fire events BrC contribution to aerosol absorption is more diverse and dynamic than BC. BrC absorption shows a rising trend from 2022 to 2024, correlating strongly with BC concentration, indicating intensified atmospheric warming.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Authors are grateful to the MOES (GOI) for funding for conducting the study through grant no.: - Geo-95/2017, Dated 21.06.2021.

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INVESTIGATING DIWALI FIREWORKS CONTRIBUTION TO URBAN HOUSEHOLDS PNC IN MEGACITY DELHI

M. SHARMA¹, M. KHARE², R. J. MISHRA^{1*}

¹Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University, Delhi 110042,
²Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, New Delhi 110016,

KEYWORDS: Indoor Aerosols, Fireworks, Household Pollution, Particle Number Concentration.

INTRODUCTION

Delhi has been known for poor air quality for the past two decades. Episodic events like fireworks make Delhi's air quality poor, along with a blanket of smog and air loaded with aerosols (Ghei & Sane, 2018; Sharma et al., 2024). Diwali festival falls in autumn (October-November) and during this period, Delhi experienced severe pollution events. The festival celebrations deteriorate outdoor air quality due to cracker emissions (Rajagopal et al., 2024; Yadav et al., 2022). In terms of Indoor Air quality along with outdoor concentrations, several other factors contribute to poor indoor air quality. The study measured and analysed the different size aerosols in indoor environments during different phases of the festival. The results of the study suggest that the indoor concentration of the aerosol during the festival season (Diwali) is not only influenced by the firecrackers but also depends on the various other indoor activities such as cleaning, cooking, and worship which contribute to a significant concentration of indoor aerosols making indoor air more vulnerable.

METHODS

STUDY AREA AND INSTRUMENTATION The study was conducted in the Rohini district, northwest part of Delhi. The study region represents the typical urban household setting, located in the region where both commercial and residential sources play a major role in air pollution. Grimm optical particle counter (Model 11A) was used to collect the data. The instrument works on the principle of light scattering (90°) with a wide size range of the particle measurement capacity. The instrument measures particles ranging from 250 nm to 32µm along with the concentration of (PM10, PM2.5, and PM1). The study was conducted during Diwali from 11 to 19 November 2023 for a period of 9 days, including different periods such as the period before the festival, during, and after the festival.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The temporal variation analysis shows that the indoor aerosol concentration in households varies significantly during different activities.

Figure 1. Temporal variation of particle number concentration during the different phases of the festival: Before Diwali (BD), Diwali Day (DD), After Diwali (AD), and Normal Day (ND).

During festival seasons like Diwali, firecrackers emit large amounts of aerosols, which influences the indoor air quality. On

the occasion of festivals, other subsidiary activities in the households, such as cleaning, cooking, and worship activities also occur parallelly. Fireworks contribute to a higher concentration of indoor aerosols, followed by cooking and cleaning. During fireworks, concentration reached $5.5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Fig.1). The diurnal variation analysis shows that the concentration on a normal day increases during indoor activities such as cooking and cleaning and on Diwali day the concentration in the late evening increases steadily and this increasing trend was found till early morning of the next day ($4-5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) (Fig.2).

Figure 2 Diurnal variation comparison of particle number concentration during the different phases of the festival: Before Diwali , Diwali Day , After Diwali , & Normal Day .

CONCLUSION

Indoor air quality is one of the major issues in developing countries where different sources contribute to higher aerosols contribution. Apart from regular indoor aerosol sources, festivals contribute to extreme indoor aerosols, which are causing serious health effects. The study suggests that household infrastructure should be designed in a well-ventilated manner to reduce the exposure to the residents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Delhi Technological University for providing research facilities.

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OPTIMIZING BIO-CHAR PRODUCTION FROM PADDY STRAW: EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF KILN PARAMETERS

AKASH ABHINAV, AND VIJAY SHRIDHAR

SENR, Doon University, Dehradun– 248001, India.

KEYWORDS: Optimization Of Kiln, Biochar.

INTRODUCTION

Kilns have been used for centuries in various applications, including pottery, metallurgy, and biochar production (Garcia-Nunez et al., 2017). In the context of biochar, kilns play a crucial role in the thermochemical conversion of biomass into charcoal, contributing to renewable energy efforts and sustainable agriculture (Panwar et al., 2019). Kilns are used to burn biomass in a controlled oxygen environment to maximize biochar yield while minimizing emissions. Several kilns have been developed for biochar production, each offering distinct efficiency, productivity, and environmental impact features (Garcia-Nunez et al., 2017). Traditional kilns, such as earth-mound and brick kilns, are widely used in developing regions due to their simplicity and low cost (Panwar et al., 2019). However, these kilns have significant disadvantages, including low carbonization efficiency, high emissions of greenhouse gases and particulate matter, and poor control over the carbonization process. These limitations have spurred innovation in kiln design, leading to more efficient technologies like the Adam Retort Kiln, which has become a prominent solution in biochar production (Ighalo et al., 2022). The Adam Retort Kiln is a modern, efficient biochar kiln developed with a focus on sustainability and productivity. Its design includes an insulated chamber and a retort system for better heat control and more efficient biomass carbonization. One of the primary advantages of the Adam Retort Kiln is its ability to increase biochar yield by up to 35% compared to traditional kilns (Namaswa et al., 2023). This kiln also burns biomass more efficiently, using the heat generated during carbonization to pre-dry the incoming biomass, thereby reducing energy consumption. Another significant benefit is the reduction in emissions. Unlike traditional kilns, which release large amounts of smoke and harmful gases into the atmosphere, the Adam Retort Kiln captures these gases, reducing CO₂ and methane emissions by up to 75% (Cornelissen et al., 2016). This makes it an environmentally friendly alternative in regions where kiln-based biochar production is a major source of air pollution. Regarding productivity, the Adam Retort Kiln offers significantly higher efficiency, producing biochar faster and more consistently. By optimizing the carbonization process and reducing fuel consumption it not only lowers operational costs but also enhances the overall quality of the biochar. The kiln's ability to generate a higher fixed carbon content, as indicated in the experiments conducted with traditional kilns, demonstrates its effectiveness in producing high-quality biochar rich in carbon and useful for soil enhancement, carbon sequestration, and renewable energy.

METHODS

To optimize bio-char production from paddy straw, experimental analysis was conducted on a specific kiln, focusing on key operational parameters such as feedstock weight, combustion duration, and fan operation time. The study involved multiple trials where the initial feedstock and combustion conditions were systematically varied to observe their effects on bio-char yield and quality.

1. **Experimental Setup:** A kiln designed for bio-char production was utilized, with paddy straw serving as the biomass feedstock. Each experiment began with weighing the biomass, followed by controlled combustion. The fan duration (to regulate air supply) and overall combustion time were varied across different trials.
2. **Key Variables:**
 - **Feedstock weight:** Biomass weights ranged between 28.981 kg to 43.03 kg across trials.
 - **Fan duration:** Airflow was controlled via fan operation, with durations varying from 25 to 50 minutes.
 - **Combustion duration:** Time allowed for the combustion process was adjusted, influencing the degree of carbonization.
3. **Data Collection:** For each trial, the final weight of the remaining bio-char was measured to calculate the yield. Additionally, proximate and ultimate analysis was conducted on the bio-char to assess quality parameters such as calorific value, fixed carbon content, and carbon percentage. These analyses were used to correlate combustion parameters with bio-char yield and composition.
4. **Analytical Techniques:**
 - **Proximate analysis:** Used to measure moisture, ash, and volatile matter content in the bio-char.
 - **Ultimate analysis:** Focused on the carbon content and calorific value, which provided insight into the energy potential of the produced bio-char.

By systematically varying combustion parameters, the experiments aimed to optimize bio-char yield and enhance its quality for energy and agricultural applications.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Several factors were varied in the experiments conducted on the kiln, such as feedstock weight, final weight after combustion, fan duration, and combustion duration. One clear trend is the relationship between the duration of combustion and the amount of biochar produced. For example, in the first experiment, a significant reduction in biomass weight was noted, from 28.981 kg to 7.9 kg, with a fan duration of 25 minutes and combustion lasting 4 hours. This process yielded 0.5 kg of bio-char, resulting in a bio-char yield of only 1.72%. On the other hand, in Experiment 4, despite using a lower initial feedstock weight (33 kg compared to 43.03 kg in Experiment 3), the final weight of bio-char was much higher, resulting in a substantial 15.87% biochar yield. This increase in yield can be linked to a longer combustion duration (50 minutes of fan duration), highlighting the impact of combustion duration on yield.

Table 1: Experiment conducted on Kiln

Experiment Conducted on Kiln							
S.No	Date	Experiment Number	Initial weight of feedstock (kg)	Final weight (kg)	Fan Duration (min)	Duration of combustion (hrs)	Residence time (hrs)
1	13-03-2024	1	28.981	7.9	25	4	3
2	18-03-2024	2	31.53	10	20	2.6	4
3	19-03-2024	3	43.03	14	10	4	Overnight
4	15-04-2024	4	33	5.24	10	50	1.5

PROXIMATE AND ULTIMATE ANALYSIS OF BIO-CHAR FROM KILN:

The analysis of the biochar produced in these experiments reveals critical information on the quality and composition of the biochar. For example, calorific values (CV) vary considerably between experiments, with the highest being 4821.84 cal/g in Experiment 4, which coincides with the highest biochar yield (15.87%). Higher calorific values indicate that the biochar produced is of better quality for energy generation. Other parameters, such as carbon content (C%) and fixed carbon percentages, suggest that a longer combustion process leads to a higher fixed carbon percentage. For instance, experiment 4 has a fixed carbon value of 61.293%, while Experiment 1 has a significantly lower fixed carbon content (44.587%). This demonstrates that optimizing the residence time in the kiln can enhance the carbonization process, improving the biochar's energy density.

CONCLUSIONS

The experiments conducted on the kiln aimed to investigate bio-char production from biomass, specifically paddy straw. Several trials were performed, each varying in parameters such as the initial weight of the feedstock, combustion duration, and fan operation. The results demonstrated that the combustion process and residence time played significant roles in determining the final weight of the biochar produced. Moreover, proximate and ultimate analyses of the biochar revealed variations in calorific value, moisture, and ash content across different trials. These findings suggest that optimizing these parameters can improve the efficiency and yield of biochar, contributing valuable insights for biochar production from biomass.

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VARIABILITY OF AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH DURING DUST STORM EVENTS OVER THE HIMALAYAN REGION AND VERTICAL STRUCTURE OF ATMOSPHERIC PARAMETERS IN THE LOWER ATMOSPHERE

SUBHAJIT DEBNATH¹, SHISHIR KUMAR SINGH¹, NARENDRA SINGH¹, MAYANK CHAUHAN^{1,2} AND VIKAS RAWAT^{1,3}

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital – 263001, India

²Gurukul Kangri (Deemed to be University), Haridwar – 249404

³Department of Physics & Astrophysics, University of Delhi, Delhi – 110007,

ABSTRACT

Aerosol optical depth (AOD) has been investigated during dust storm events over the Himalayan region from MODIS-Terra and CALIPSO satellite data. AOD is very high during dust storm events ranges 0.6-0.9. MERRA reanalysis also confirmed these variabilities. We have analysed AOD during pre, during and post dust storm events. Zonal and meridional wind are analysed during this period from ERA-5 data. Temperature potential gradient and wind perturbation are observed during this period in the troposphere from the university of Wyoming balloon data.

KEYWORDS: Dust Storm, Aerosol Optical Depth, MODIS, CALIPSO.

INTRODUCTION

Strong winds near the Earth's surface carry large amounts of mineral dust from dry and desert regions worldwide into the atmosphere during dust storms. This dust is a major source of natural aerosols and particulate matter (Chin et al., 2007; Sarkar et al., 2019). In South Asia, dust particles have been found to influence the monsoon and change rainfall patterns (Lau et al., 2006). In India, especially over the Indo-Gangetic Plain in the north, the lower atmosphere heats up significantly during dust events, which usually happen from March to June (Pandithurai et al., 2008). Studies have shown that the transport of pollutants to the central Himalayas is influenced by boundary layer dynamics and mountain-valley winds (Ojha et al., 2012). The high terrain of the Himalayas and its foothills can block wind flow, causing dust to accumulate and settle more in these areas.

METHODS

Dust aerosols and atmospheric properties are investigated using CALIPSO (Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations) and MODIS-Terra (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer on the Terra satellite) data. 1. CALIPSO level 2 Vertical Feature Mask (VFM) for identifying aerosol and cloud layers. 2. MODIS-Terra level 2 Aerosol (MOD04_L2) for aerosol optical depth (AOD) information. Analyse aerosol vertical profiles using CALIPSO's Level 2 aerosol data. Identify dust layers by filtering based on altitude and aerosol subtype information. Calculate vertical aerosol optical depth (AOD) and extinction profiles to study the distribution of dust within the atmosphere. Vertical aerosol profiles using CALIPSO to show how dust layers are distributed by altitude. Aerosol optical depth (AOD) maps using MODIS-Terra to show the spatial extent of dust storms. Vertical temperature and wind structure are also investigated from the University of Wyoming radiosonde data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A major dust storm event is observed during 2018 over the Himalayan foothill region and Himalayan region. Here, we investigated Aerosol Optical Depth (550nm) on 13th June 2018 (during a major dust storm event). The zonal wind (U) component intensifies during dust storm events (Figure 2), carrying dust pollutants from the western regions of India towards the Himalayas. This movement also influences various tropospheric atmospheric parameters. We investigated the temperature potential gradient and vertical wind structure from radiosonde data. We also examined the variability of AOD pre, post and during dust storm events and the vertical structure of the atmosphere in different fields like temperature and wind.

Figure 1. Aerosol Optical Depth (550nm) on 13th June 2018 (Major dust storm event)

Figure 2. Zonal wind (U) component on 13th to 17th June, 2018 (During a major dust storm event)

CONCLUSIONS

1. AOD is significantly increasing during dust storm events over the western part of India and also over the Himalayan foothill region.
2. Temperature parameters in the troposphere are significantly changing their characteristics profile.
3. Zonal and meridional wind perturbation is also significant during dust storms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital under a post-doctoral fellowship grant.

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FIRE EVENTS AND THEIR IMPACT ON AIR QUALITY IN THE INDIAN HIMALAYAN REGION: A TWO-DECADE REVIEW

R. MASIWAL¹, A. SHARMA², S. K. SINGH³ & R. SINGH⁴

¹Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi

²Delhi Skill and Entrepreneurship University, Dwarka Campus, Delhi-110077

³Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Nainital, India – 263001

⁴Climate, LEA Associates South Asia pvt Ltd., New Delhi

KEYWORDS: Forest Fire, Himalayas, Emissions

INTRODUCTION

Forest fires play a crucial role in shaping forest ecosystems. In recent decades, both the frequency and intensity of these fires have risen, as fire seasons become longer, chiefly due to climate change driven by human activities (Slezakova et al., 2013; Huerta et al., 2022). Wildfires represent one of the most significant threats to ancient ecosystems globally, hindering their ability to regenerate. Additionally, these fires emit large amounts of pollutants into the atmosphere (Wu et al., 2024), including primary pollutants such as particulate matter (PM), carbon monoxide (CO), methane (CH₄), and black carbon (BC). Smoke plumes from wildfires and agricultural burns also introduce pollutants like sulphur dioxide and nitrogen oxides, which can transform into secondary pollutants (Luo et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2024), adversely affecting air quality, human health, and climate (Huerta et al., 2022). Elevated levels of PM_{2.5} over a region can disrupt radiation dispersion, impacting surface solar radiation (Luo et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2024). Greenhouse gases, including carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide, present significant long-term climate risks, while particulate matter degrades air quality in the short term and can often be more toxic than gaseous pollutants (Wu et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2019). Furthermore, past research indicates that severe forest fires may contribute to the depletion of stratospheric ozone (Bernath et al., 2022). Every year, numerous forest fires occur worldwide, including in the Himalayan regions. The Himalayas are particularly susceptible to wildfires due to the prevalence of pine trees in the area. In this region, fires are common throughout the year, especially during the summer season. This study aims to analyze the fire events that have occurred in this region over the past 22 years.

METHODS

This study utilized data from the Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS), which is based on the European Forest Fire Information System and the Global Terrestrial Observing System (GTOS) Global Observation of Forest Cover and Land Dynamics (GOFC-GOLD). The analysis focused on fire event occurrences and pollutant emissions in Uttarakhand, a state in the Indian Himalayas.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

According to the Global Wildfire Information System, approximately 97,841 hectares of land is burnt in Uttarakhand, with 33% of this being forest land and 39% grass and shrubland. The highest frequency of forest fires occurs during the months of April, May, and June, with more than 30% of fire events happening during this time. Between 2002 and 2023, the year 2016 saw the largest area burnt, with 39% of the affected land being forests, 34% grassland and shrubland, and 24% cropland. The year 2016 recorded nearly 0.2 million hectares affected,

followed by 2012 and 2019, while 2002 recorded the least burnt area. Over this period, fire events released approximately 0.05 Gt of pollutants into the Himalayan atmosphere, including 0.34 Mt of PM_{2.5}, 15 kt of black carbon, 0.1 Mt of CH₄, 2.5 Mt of CO, and 47.6 Mt of CO₂. However, the emissions from these fire events were not always proportional to the area burned. From 2002 to 2023, approximately 0.34 Mt of PM_{2.5} were emitted in the Himalayan region, with the highest emissions occurring in 2012, followed by 2016. The variability in PM_{2.5} emissions was influenced not only by the extent of the area burnt but also by the type of land cover burnt more, such as forest, grassland, or cropland. Even though, 2016 had the largest burnt area, the highest emissions were observed in 2012, followed by 2016. The trend analysis indicates that the number of fire events has risen since 2002, leading to a substantial increase in pollutant emissions and is expected to increase more in future. Studies reported that the Himalayas are warming faster than the plains and other mountain ranges (Pandit, 2013; Chauhan et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

Trend analysis indicates that the number of fire events has risen since 2002, leading to a substantial increase in pollutant emissions. The recurring forest fires pose a serious threat, not only by disrupting forest growth and ecosystems but also by affecting the livelihoods of people who depend on these resources. The rise in black carbon and greenhouse gases in the Himalayan region could have profound impacts on water resources and the region's climate, which will directly and indirectly impact and shape the life of the Himalayan community.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS) for providing the data.

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IMPACT OF FOREST FIRE ON ATMOSPHERIC PARAMETERS IN THE NAINITAL REGION

S. K. SINGH¹, S. DEBNATH¹, N. SINGH¹, M. CHAUHAN^{1,2} AND V. RAWAT^{1,3}

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital – 263001, India.

²Gurukul Kangri (Deemed to be University), Haridwar – 249404, India.

³Department of Physics & Astrophysics, University of Delhi, Delhi – 110007, India.

KEYWORDS: Forest Fire, Nainital, Aerosols, Modis, Tropomi.

INTRODUCTION

Forest fires occur as a natural or human-induced phenomenon that has increased in frequency around the globe in recent decades (Cochrane, 2003; Giglio et al., 2016). Lightning strikes, volcanic eruptions, and the spontaneous combustion of dry vegetation under intense heat are all natural causes of forest fires. Unattended campfires, discarded cigarettes, agricultural burning, and deliberate arson all constitute significant contributors to forest fires (Holden et al., 2005). These fires have detrimental impacts on forest ecosystems and the surrounding atmosphere. The occurrence and pattern of forest fires are influenced by factors including vegetation types, seasonal variations, and local climatic conditions (Levine, 1991). During the dry season, fires are more likely to occur due to high temperatures, especially in areas with very low precipitation. Research indicates that forest fires and biomass burning emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases and aerosol particles into the atmosphere (Ray et al. 2019; Renard et al. 2012). These fires, whether natural or man-made, have a significant impact on the environmental health of forest regions, impacting biodiversity, air quality, and climate. Anthropogenic activities are responsible for about 90% of the forest fires that occur in India (FSI, 2021).

Forest fires pose a serious environmental threat, especially in areas with dense forest cover and diverse topography, such as Nainital. The Nainital district, located in Uttarakhand's mountainous region, suffers a peak fire season from the end of March to June when the number of fires is significantly higher. For understanding how these fires affect atmospheric parameters such as carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and the absorbing aerosol index (AAI) is essential to generating effective forest management and conservation approaches for the Himalayan ecosystem (Negi et al. 2016). This study attempts to provide a comprehensive understanding of the environmental consequences of forest fires in the Nainital region.

METHODS

This study used satellite data from MODIS onboard Terra and Aqua satellites, as well as active fire data from MODIS and VIIRS sensors onboard SUOMI NPP, NOAA-20, and NOAA-21 satellites, to assess the adverse impacts of a forest fire event in the Nainital district. In addition to this data, other satellite data products such as CO column number density, NO₂ column number density, and absorbing aerosol index provided by the sensor, TROPOMI onboard ESA's (The European Space Agency) Sentinel-5 precursor (Sentinel 5P) satellite are also used in this work.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In the current study, the satellite data related to forest fires from 21st April to 01st May 2024

were analysed and used to obtain the atmospheric properties of aerosols and gases. Figure 1 illustrates the fire counts that occurred in the ARIES campus and its surrounding area during forest fire occurrence (25-27 April). The marker in the map (inside circle) shows the location of the ARIES Campus. The red boxes represent the active fire counts during the study period. Due to this fire event, the concentration of atmospheric parameters increased drastically, which can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 2 illustrates the variation in the emission of (a) carbon monoxide, (b) aerosol absorbing index and (c) nitrogen dioxide caused due to the occurrence of a forest fire. The occurrence is divided into three parts, (i) pre-fire (21-24 April), (ii) during fire (25-27 April), (iii) post-fire (28 April- 1 May). As we can see the concentration of all these parameters was low before the fire event. The concentration of these parameters was observed high during (25-27 April) and post (28 – 01 May) the forest fire event due to increase in their emissions. Due to this fire event, the atmospheric condition became undesirable for humans and the ecosystem.

Figure 1. The active forest fire counts occurred in Nainital region (ARIES)

Figure 2. The variation in the emission of (a) Carbon monoxide (b) Absorbing aerosol index (c) Nitrogen dioxide in the Nainital (ARIES) region

CONCLUSIONS

The investigation of forest fire events and atmospheric parameters using multi-satellite data in the Nainital region has given substantial insights into the environmental fluctuations that occurred due to forest fires. The high concentration of atmospheric parameters (Carbon monoxide, Nitrogen dioxide, and aerosol absorbing index) is due to the burning of forest vegetation cover of the region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital under a post-doctoral fellowship grant.

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THE EFFECT OF FOG PROCESSING ON AEROSOLS' OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL IN THE ITALIAN PO VALLEY: FAIRARI 2021/22

A. PATEL^{1,2,¥}, M. PAGLIONE³, A. NEUBERGER^{1,2}, F. MATTSSON^{1,2}, Y. GRAMLICH^{1,2}, D. HADDEN^{1,2}, S. L. HASLETT^{1,2}, M. RINALDI³, C. MOHR^{1,2,\$}, I. RIIPINEN^{1,2}, P. ZIEGER^{1,2}, S. DECESARI³ AND S. S. STEIMER¹

¹Department of Environmental Science, Stockholm University, Stockholm, 114 18, Sweden

²Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm, 114 18, Sweden

³Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council, Bologna, Italy

¥Now at: Bagchi School of Public Health, Ahmedabad University, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad

\$Now at: Laboratory of Atmospheric Chemistry, Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen PSI, Switzerland

KEYWORDS: Reactive Oxygen Species (Ros), Dtt, Fog-Scavenging

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosol can catalytically generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the nasal airway, depleting the antioxidant pool (Li et al., 2003). This potency of aerosols is known as its oxidative potential (OP). Numerous studies have shown that elevated OP can cause cellular damage through oxidative stress, contributing to various cardiopulmonary diseases. Particulate matter (PM) emitted from various processes and sources often differ in size distribution and chemical composition, leading to variations in OP. Atmospheric transport and aging further alter PM's properties by enriching secondary species through oxidation, particularly in forming secondary organic aerosols (SOA) (Pöschl & Shiraiwa, 2015). The OP of aged PM can vary based on SOA formation pathways, e.g., aqueous-phase vs. non-aqueous-phase reactions.

Recent studies conducted in the Po Valley, Italy (Decesari et al., 2017) and the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), India (Patel and Rastogi, 2018) observed an increase in PM's OP due to fog processing, where aqueous-phase SOA formation could have played a critical role. Although fog formation serves as a removal mechanism for reactive fine PM, additional SOA formed within fog droplets could be more redox-active which may pose a heightened health risk when the fog dissipates. However, specific SOA species formed during fog events remain speculative in these studies, requiring further investigation to mitigate potential toxicity in polluted regions.

STUDY SITE & METHODS

The Po Valley, Europe's most polluted region (Daellenbach et al. 2020), is home to around 16 million people, approximately one-third of Italy's population. With its unique orography, the Po Valley creates conditions that facilitate the accumulation of PM during winter. Atmospheric aging processes oxidize these particles, increasing their hygroscopicity – a phenomenon intensified by fog formation even at lower relative humidity ($\leq 100\%$). So, it presents an ideal setting to study the influence of fog processing on PM toxicity. The campaign, FAIRARI (Fog and Aerosol InterAction Research Italy), was set up in San Pietro Capofiume, Italy, during the winter of 2021/22 (Neuberger et al., 2024, under review). This was a joint effort between Stockholm University and CNR-ISAC in Bologna. Several PM1 and PM10 samples were collected before, during, and after fog events using different samplers (DIGITEL for PM1 and LECKEL for PM10). In addition, an automated computer-

controlled active string collector was used for fog water sampling. This approach enabled an in-depth analysis of the changes in particle size distribution, chemical composition, and OP within fog droplets. The collected samples were analyzed for mass concentration and chemical composition. The consumption rate of Dithiothreitol (DTT) (nmol DTT/min) was measured at physiological conditions in the presence of PM, also termed OP. The OP exposure/dose has been estimated by normalizing OP with sampled air volume (i.e., OPV), and the particles' intrinsic OP has been represented as mass-normalized OP (OPM).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

There were six episodes encountered in which we gathered information on the fog-processing of aerosols' OP. On average, PM1-OPV during non-foggy days and nights occupied ~ 52% of PM10-OPV, meaning that OP was also governed significantly by coarser particles ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$). PM1 mass concentration and its OP have significantly been observed to be influenced by fog formation. A reduced PM1 mass and OPV during a foggy night (interstitial part) compared to its prior clear day for all the episodes suggests the possibility of fog scavenging (Gilardoni et al., 2014) and/or that the PM1 might have grown to a coarser size ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$) as a condensation process. In the latter case, the particles that grew coarser during foggy nights could become a part of PM10, which was not investigated in this study. The particles' scavenging can occur based on their size and composition. This could be the reason behind the observed difference in the magnitude of PM1 mass and OPV during fog in contrast to a clear night. The fog water OPV was also significant, which could be this scavenged part of PM1. The composition governs OPM. So, the water-soluble organic matter (WSOM, likely redox-active) and secondary inorganic aerosol (SIA, redox-inactive) ratio could provide valuable information on particles' reactivity. A clear day following a foggy night was associated with an enhanced WSOM/SIA ratio and OPM compared to its previous clear day, which could mean that fog processing makes the particles more reactive and, thus, enhances OPM. However, OPV showed an opposite trend, which is under investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

OP was observed to be governed significantly by both fine ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) as well as coarser particles ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$). Reduced PM1 mass and OPV during foggy nights compared to prior clear days hints towards fog scavenging or condensational growth of PM1. The results of this study will contribute to the development of strategies to mitigate the health impacts of air pollution in the Po Valley.

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THEME 5: AEROSOL MONITORING

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL (SDG-3.8) IS ACHIEVABLE BY ADDRESSING THE DISPARITY IN THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LONG-TERM PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE AND HEALTH OUTCOMES AMONG THE SUB-POPULATIONS IN INDIA

D. SARKAR¹, *SAGNIK DEY^{1,2,3}, S. GHOSH⁴

¹Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India, 110016

²Adjunct Faculty, Korea University, Seoul, South Korea

³Centre of Excellence for Research on Clean Air, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India,

⁴St. John's Medical College, Bangalore, India

KEYWORDS: Ambient PM_{2.5}, Sdgs, Ncds, Disparity, India.

INTRODUCTION

Ambient air pollution exposure (PM_{2.5}) is a risk-factor for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. However, the association may vary across population sub-groups from total PM_{2.5}, which is unknown in India. The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (SDG-3.8) aims to provide equal healthcare access and risk protection for all, it is necessary to investigate if the subpopulations would obtain equal benefits if India meets the clean-air targets.

METHODS

We used a hierarchical logistic mixed effect model to estimate the association between the odds of four diseases (diabetes, hypertension, COPD, heart disease) with satellite-derived PM_{2.5} and its sectoral contributions stratified by gender, wealth, and ethnic subpopulations. We adjusted our model using various potential confounders; and estimated the combined effects of air pollution with solid fuel usage, unhealthy diet, and poor lifestyle practices using the interaction model. And lastly, we used an empirical equation to estimate health benefits for the subpopulations due to exposure mitigation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We found higher health risks attributed to air pollution among males as compared to females. The estimated odds ratio (ORs) of diabetes, hypertension, COPD, and heart disease among males were 1.037, 1.026, 1.044, and 1.03, respectively than in females (1.027, 1.018, 1.037, and 1.016). Among the wealthier population subgroups, we found the larger effect of air pollution in richer than poorer for diabetes (1.07 vs 1.058) and heart disease (1.07 vs 1.017); however, the ORs were larger in deprived sub-populations for hypertension and COPD (1.016 and 1.068, respectively). In comparison, intermediate ORs were estimated among the middle SES sub-population for all the diseases (1.059, 1.015, 1.062, and 1.025). The minorities were more susceptible to ambient PM_{2.5} risk for most diseases than the ethnic majors [HD (1.023 vs 1.019), COPD (1.011 vs 1.005), diabetes (1.048 vs 1.036)], except for hypertension (1.024 vs 1.034). We further stratified the whole population into the urban and rural populace and found that the effect of chronic PM_{2.5} exposure was higher among the urban population [HD (1.094 vs 1.078),

hypertension (1.098 vs 1.087), COPD (1.016 vs 1.014), and diabetes (1.014 vs 1.01)] as compared to the rural residents.

Figure 1. The association between ambient air pollution exposure and the health outcomes among the population subgroups stratified by gender, wealth, and ethnic categories for NFHS-5. The aggregated stratified analysis among the urban and rural populations was also depicted in this figure. The black circles denote the mean estimates of the association between PM_{2.5} exposure and the odds of the health outcomes, while the whiskers indicate the 95% confidence intervals. The associations are statistically significant (p<0.005).

CONCLUSIONS

India should implement targeted policies for deprived subpopulations to alleviate air pollution exposure and prioritise dietary and lifestyle-related risk-factors simultaneously, which may lead to achieving the aspirational SDG-3.8 goal.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is supported by a research grant from the Clean Air Fund and from the SERB, Department of Science and Technology, GoI under the SUPRA scheme. DS acknowledges the financial support from the CSIR, GoI. SD acknowledges financial support for the Institute Chair fellowship and DST-FIST program (SR/FST/ESII-016/2014) for computing support.

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DETAILED INVESTIGATION OF THE CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOLID FUELS EMPLOYED FOR DOMESTIC HEATING ACTIVITIES

D. SAHU¹, S. PERVEZ¹ AND A. TAMRAKAR¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh,

KEYWORDS: Solid Fuel, Chemical Composition, Proximate Analysis, Ultimate Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Solid fuels such as coal balls (CB), dung cake (DC), rice straw (RS) and fuel woods (FW) are widely used for domestic and industrial energy production, especially in developing countries. Understanding the chemical composition and characteristics of these fuels is essential for optimizing combustion processes and minimizing gaseous emissions to reduce adverse environmental impact. This study presents a detailed characterization of solid fuels by analyzing the moisture content, ionic and elemental compositions (C, H, N, S, O) of these fuels. The results show significant variations in the chemical composition, which can influence the emission of gases during combustion. The findings are crucial for understanding the suitability of these fuels in various combustion applications, especially in regions where traditional biomass fuels are prevalent.

METHODS

The methodology employed in this study involved collecting samples of CB, DC, RS and FW from various sources, followed by air-drying to remove excess moisture. The dried samples were then pulverized into a fine powder to ensure uniformity. To determine moisture content, a known weight of each sample was dried at 105°C until a constant weight was achieved. Ion chromatography (Dionex HPIC 20043027 Model, ThermoFisher Scientific Pvt. Ltd.) was used to analyze the anionic and cationic composition of the samples, focusing on specific ions such as fluoride, chloride, and sulfate, as well as metals like lithium, sodium, and calcium. Additionally, elemental analysis was conducted using CHSN/O elemental analyzer (FlashSmart Model, ThermoFisher Scientific Pvt. Ltd.) to determine the carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulfur, and oxygen content of the samples, with oxygen content calculated by difference. This comprehensive approach aimed to provide a detailed understanding of the chemical composition of the CB, DC, and FW samples.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Moisture Content

The moisture content of the samples varied significantly, with CB samples having the lowest moisture content (2.92 - 3.44%), followed by FW samples (3.65 - 10.54%), and DC samples exhibiting the highest moisture content (6.85 - 12.58%). High moisture content in DC samples may affect combustion efficiency by lowering the calorific value and increasing the energy required for drying during combustion.

Anionic Composition

The anionic composition analysis revealed considerable variation among the sample (Table 1). Fluoride: Detected in all sample types, with DC samples showing higher concentrations (0.024-3.440 mg/kg) compared to FW (0.204-1.395 mg/kg) and CB (0.3-1.38 mg/kg). Chloride: Found in substantial amounts across all samples, particularly in DC (1.936-15.370

mg/kg). Nitrate and Nitrite: Present in low concentrations, with DC samples exhibiting the highest nitrate content, indicating potential nitrogenous fuel emissions.

Cationic Composition

Sodium and Potassium: Notably higher in DC samples, which could influence ash formation and slagging during combustion. Calcium and Magnesium: Present in all sample types, with DC samples containing higher calcium levels (0.245-2.655 mg/kg).

Fuel Type	Moisture (%)	Total Anions (mg/Kg)	Total Cations (mg/Kg)	Elements				
				N	C	H	S	O
DC	6.85 -	82.00 -	215.09 -	2.01 -	23.63 -	4.26 -	3.17 -	2.18 -
	12.58	1,530.44	1,256.28	2.96%	35.35%	5.09%	5.31%	5.27%
FW	3.65 -	52.70 -	17.55 -	1.09 -	61.22 -	3.47 -	3.10 -	3.12 -
	10.54	974.55	425.88	1.72%	74.44%	4.17%	3.68%	7.26%
CB	2.92 -	197.58 -	18.90 -	1.22 -	33.19 -	3.26 -	2.56 -	6.19 -
	3.44	395.85	255.95	1.88%	73.27%	4.29%	6.23%	7.68
RS	7.07 -	330.31 -	40.13 -	1.76 -	37.33 -	5.34 -	5.57 -	13.68 -
	27.89	692.12	115.51	2.28%	54.47%	6.29%	9.31%	32.43%

Table 1. Chemical characterization of solid fuel samples by ultimate and proximate analysis.

Elemental Composition

Carbon Content: FW samples had the highest carbon content (61.22-74.44%), reflecting their potential for higher energy output during combustion. CB samples showed moderate carbon content (33.19-73.27%), while DC samples had the lowest (23.63-35.35%). Nitrogen and Sulfur Content: These elements were present in varying amounts across all samples, with potential implications for NO_x and SO_x emissions during combustion.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates significant differences in the chemical compositions of coal balls, dung cake, and fuelwood and rice straw these differences are likely to influence their combustion characteristics, including energy output and emissions. Fuel wood, with its high carbon content and low moisture, appears to be the most efficient fuel among the three, while dung cake, with its high moisture and anion concentrations, may lead to higher emissions of pollutants. These findings are essential for developing strategies to optimize the use of these fuels in different combustion applications, particularly in rural areas where such traditional fuels are commonly used.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was primarily funded by the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), India, under project CRG/2022/003926, with additional support from the Department of Science and Technology (DST) Promotion of University Research and Scientific Excellence (PURSE) program (SR/PURSE/2022/145).

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IMPACT OF AEROSOLS AND CLOUDS ON SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION OVER NAINITAL

U. C. DUMKA^{1,2}, PANAGIOTIS G. KOSMOPOULOS³

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Nainital 263001, India

²Graphic Era (Deemed to be University), India

³Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, National Observatory of Athens (IERSD/NOA), 15236 Athens, Greece

KEYWORDS: Aerosol, Clouds, Solar Energy Production, Financial Losses

INTRODUCTION

Renewal energy has become an important issue, particularly for developing countries, to meet the regular need for rapid population and economic growth (Xia et al., 2010; Dumka et al., 2021). In this context, solar energy has drawn increasing attention over the last two decades because it is clean and sustainable (Kumar et al., 2020). Further, it has been promoted intensely by governments in many countries. It significantly contributes to total energy production, focusing on reducing carbon dioxide, aerosols, and air pollution, especially carbonaceous aerosols from anthropogenic activities (Yang et al., 2018). Rapid developments and high population density demand a large amount of energy; hence, it is necessary to know the availability of solar energy resources throughout the region to meet this demand. In the present work, we analyze the aerosol optical depth (AOD) and cloud optical depth (COD) over the Indian subcontinent from MODIS and CAMS MSG, quantify their impacts on GHI and BHI, and perform the financial analysis.

Experimental site, data, and methodology

The experimental site is ARIES< Nainital, a high-altitude remote location in the central Himalayan region. Therefore, this site is far from any anthropogenic pollution source and is considered a better regional representative background site (Dumka et al., 2021). In the present work, we used the AOD data from the AERONET sun photometer, CAMS, and MODIS. The COD data was taken from the MSG. Further, the Surface Solar Radiation Data Set-Heliosat (SARAH) provides the solar surface irradiance (SIS) or global horizontal irradiance (GHI), surface direct normalized irradiance (BHI) from the visible channels of MVIRI and SEVIRI instruments onboard the geostationary Meteosat Satellites. The libRadtran radiative transfer model (RTM) estimates the gridded GHI and BHI under aerosol and cloud conditions. The main input parameters for the RTM simulations under clear sky conditions are AOD, SZA, Angstrom Exponent, and single scattering albedo, column ozone, column water vapor, while under cloudy conditions the main parameters are SZA, column ozone with COD. Further details are presented in several earlier papers (Dumka et al., 2021) and hence not repeated here. To study the financial loss (FL) and energy loss (EL), we performed a hypothetical scenario of photovoltaic and CSP systems with a nominal power of 1 MW assumed to be installed at the experimental site, and details are presented by Dumka et al., (2021).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1a shows the monthly mean AOD at 550 nm over the Indian subcontinent. The AOD values range from 0.01 to 1.65, clearly indicating the intense loading of aerosol during the

study period. The higher aerosol loading is attributed to the significant contribution of dust from the western region (Dumka et al., 2021). Similar to aerosol patterns, the GHI and BHI percentage attenuations are observed during the period under consideration (Figure 1b, 1c). The results presented in this study are important, and the mean GHI over the Indian subcontinent is dominated by 16-20% (Figure 1b), clearly indicating that the higher AOD values during the summer months can be justified by moderate attenuation of BHI values (12-15%) over Nainital. Further details of the results are well presented in Dumka et al. (2021) and will be discussed during the presentation.

Following the methodology presented in Dumka et al., (2021), we have estimated the financial and energy losses over Nainital. We observed the PV and CSP for 2308 kWh m⁻² and 2769 kWh m⁻², respectively, for Nainital, along with the annual revenue is 8.47 million INR and 6.66 million INR, respectively, for PV as well as CSP (see Figure 2). Further, the energy losses due to aerosols are 539 kWh m⁻² in GHI and 344 kWh m⁻² in BHI.

Figure 1. Monthly variation of (a) AOD, (b) GHI, and (c) BHI over the Indian subcontinent.

Figure 2. Financial analysis of aerosols, dusts, and clouds.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn from the present work.

1. High values of AODs are observed throughout the study period, with AOD ranges from 0.01 to 1.65.
2. The GHI percentage attenuation was 0 to 14%, whereas the BHI percentage attenuation varied from 0 to 20%.
3. The economic impact of AOD on PV and CSP shows a financial loss of 1.05 million INR and 1.55 million INR, respectively.

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EFFECTS OF METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON PARTICULATE MATTER (PM_{2.5}) CONCENTRATION IN DELHI

SARVAN KUMAR¹, NABIN SHARMA² AND KALPANA PATEL²

¹Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, VBS Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, UP

²Department of Physics, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Delhi-NCR Campus, Modinagar, Ghaziabad-201204, India

KEYWORDS: Modis, Temperature, Surface Pressure, Delhi.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric particulate matter (PM) has significant impacts on urban and regional air pollution, visibility and regional to global climate change. It also poses health hazards when concentrations are high. In recent years, PM has received considerable attention as the primary air pollutant in metropolitan regions of emerging Asian countries, including China and India. The primary sources of air pollution caused by human activity are industrial emissions, residential fuel combustion, emissions from power plants, and transportation activities (Ghosh et al., 2024). Several researches have been conducted to study the spatial and temporal distribution of particulate matter and its effects on health in India. Due to its high pollution levels and industrial activity, Delhi is known as one of the most polluted cities in India. This study aims to analyze the changes in PM_{2.5} levels in Delhi from 2021 to 2022 and establish a correlation between PM_{2.5} and the MODIS-retrieved AOD along with different meteorological parameters using an MLR model.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data sets

In the current study, we used Aqua-MODIS daily data (MYD08_D3 v6.1) from Jan 2021 to Dec 2022, from NASA Giovanni (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). The atmospheric parameters temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, dew point, and surface pressure were obtained from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications v2 (MERRA-2) reanalysis on a daily basis (<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>). We have taken the average of PM_{2.5} values of all 40 Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) stations of Delhi from Jan 2021 to Dec 2022 (<https://air-quality.cpcb.gov.in/ccr/#/caaqm-dashboard-all/caaqm-landing>).

2.2. The Proposed Model

To study the correlation between PM_{2.5} with factors such as MODIS-AOD and atmospheric parameters in Delhi the study employed PM_{2.5} as the dependent variable, whereas MODIS-AOD (M), temperature (T), dew point (DP), relative humidity (RH), wind speed (WS), and surface pressure (SP) were included as the independent variables. The impact of these independent factors on the dependent variables was assessed using time series analysis, standard deviation, R-value, and root mean square error (RMSE). The multiple linear regression (MLR) models utilize multiple independent variables to predict a dependent variable. The MLR model is mathematically formulated as:

$$y = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n \quad (1)$$

Here, y is the dependent variable, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the independent variables, n represents the total number of independent variables, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are the slope of the lines, and a_0 is the y-intercept.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

It was found in the regression analysis the parameters M, DP, RH, and WS are significant (p-value < 0.05) and the parameters T and SP are not significant (p-value > 0.05). Then we exclude both parameters T and SP and we consider the significant parameters M, DP, RH, and WS as independent variables as shown in Tables 1 & 2. The regression equation is given as:

$$y = 98.44 + (76.26 \times M) + (-8.51 \times DP) + (2.12 \times RH) + (-19.69 \times WS)$$

Model	t-value	p-value
MODIS-AOD (M)	9.81984	2.94621×10^{-20}
Dew Point (DP)	-19.00243	8.79917×10^{-56}
Relative Humidity (RH)	14.05381	7.26525×10^{-36}
Wind Speed (WS)	-6.95106	1.7896×10^{-11}

Table 1: All significant parameters for PM_{2.5}

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.75
R Square	0.56
Adjusted R Square	0.56
Standard Error	46.48
Observations	354.0
	0

Table 2: MLR test for PM₂

Comparison of observed and modelled PM_{2.5}

The observed and predicted values show an increasing pattern as shown in Fig.1 is evidence that the 56% concentration of PM_{2.5} is obtained by four parameters using the MLR model. The average values of observed and predicted (y) were 114.5863 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 115.387 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively which are exactly near to each other. The natural and anthropogenic activities like CFC, NO₂, biomass burning, industrial, heavy transportation, etc. are the main causes of showing an increasing pattern in PM_{2.5} (Chetna et al., 2023). These are the main reasons that affect the environment and increase health problems in Delhi.

Figure 1. Time series of observed and modelled PM_{2.5} (y) over Delhi using daily data from 2021 to 2022.

CONCLUSION

In the current study, we employed the MLR model to examine the relationship between PM_{2.5} and MODIS-retrieved AOD as well as various meteorological parameters over Delhi from 2021 to 2022, including temperature, DP, RH, WS, and SP. The regression analysis of PM_{2.5} demonstrated a statistically significant variation ($p < 0.05$) with meteorological parameters such as DP, RH, and WS, rather than T and SP ($p > 0.05$). The regression model indicated that the MODIS retrieved AOD had a moderate contribution (~56%) to the concentration of PM_{2.5} over Delhi throughout the study period. This study focuses on the relationship between PM_{2.5} and meteorological indicators in Delhi.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to NASA and the CBCP team for providing the AOD, PM and met data. One of the authors Dr. Sarvan Kumar is thankful to UGC for providing funds through the UGC Start-up research grant (File No. - 30-573/2021(BSR), Dated-15 June 2022).

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CLASSIFICATION OF AEROSOLS WITH A MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

SWAGATA MUKHOPADHYAY¹, SHANTIKUMAR S. NINGOMBAM¹, B.L. MADHAVAN², AMOGHAVARSHA A. V.³, PRATHAMESH SANJAY KADAM⁴, E.J.L. LARSON⁵, PRADEEP KHATRI⁶

¹Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Bengaluru, India,

²National Atmospheric Research Laboratory (NARL), Gadanki, India

³Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Pune, India

⁴Sardar Vallabhbhai National Institute of Technology, Surat, India

⁵University of Colorado, Boulder, USA

⁶Center for Atmospheric and Oceanic Studies, Graduate School of Science, Tohoku University, Japan

KEYWORDS: Aerosol, Single Scattering Albedo, Absorption Angstrom Exponent

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols are tiny particles suspended in the atmosphere as solids or liquids. Their composition varies widely due to factors such as topography and climate conditions, leading to significant inhomogeneity. Additionally, their spatial and temporal distribution is influenced by both local and broader meteorological conditions. Various methods have been proposed for the classification of aerosols using optical and microphysical properties of aerosols. The current study employs a machine-learning spectral clustering algorithm to identify and categorize various types of aerosols across 150 sites worldwide, including Asia, Africa, Europe, Australia, South America, and North America.

METHODS

We employed a multivariate spectral clustering algorithm to analyse the different types of aerosols in the six continents. The classification was performed based on continent wise, instead of studying each individual site. The Spectral clustering algorithm is a variant of k-means clustering that uses the eigenvectors of a similarity matrix. The details of the spectral clustering algorithm are illustrated by Ningombam et al.,2024. The clustering algorithm utilized five aerosol optical parameters from the inversion AERONET data product, namely AOD_Fine-mode, EAE (Extinction Angstrom Exponent), SSA (Single Scattering Albedo), Absorption Angstrom Exponent (AAE), and RRI (Real Refractive Index) from 150 AERONET sites that distributed in six continents. The data used in the current work is cloud-screened, quality assured AERONET data product, version 3.0 and Level 2.0 from July, 1993 to March, 2022.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The clustering analysis has identified four primary aerosol types such as dust, urban, biomass burning, and mixed aerosols. It is found that dust Aerosols are dominated in Africa by 40% and Asian sites by mixed aerosols by 51%. On the other hand, Australia, Europe, North America, and South America are relatively far away from major dust sources, resulting in a higher prevalence of fine-mode aerosols, which include urban and biomass burning aerosol types. The current study observed that the urban aerosols are highly dominated in the South American, North American, European and Australian sites by 84%, 65%, 51%, and 50%,

respectively as seen in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Global classification of aerosol using machine learning algorithm from 150 AERONET sites

CONCLUSIONS

Our study demonstrates that the spectral clustering algorithm is a powerful tool for aerosol classification across different regions. The clustering analysis has identified four primary aerosol types such as dust, urban, biomass burning, and mixed aerosols. It is found that dust Aerosols are dominated in African and Asian sites as the region has significant global dust sources. On the other hand, Australia, Europe, North America, and South America are relatively far away from major dust sources, resulting in a higher prevalence of fine-mode aerosols, which include urban and biomass burning aerosol types.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The AERONET data used in the present work are taken from 150 sites across the globe from the website: <https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov> and the authors are thankful to the PI, Co-PIs and their staff of the respective AERONET sites who maintain the data for scientific use.

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STUDY OF SPATIOTEMPORAL VARIABILITY, SOURCES AND HEALTH RISKS ASSESSMENT OF AMBIENT VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN CENTRAL INDIA

A. TAMRAKAR¹, S. PERVEZ¹, JUDITH C. CHOW^{2,3}, J. G. WATSON^{2,3}, Y.F. PERVEZ⁴,
MANAS KANTI DEB¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh

²Division of Atmospheric Sciences, Desert Research Institute, Reno, NV, USA

³Institute of Earth and Environment, Chinese Academy of Science, Xian, China

⁴Government Dr. Waman Wasudev Patankar Girls PG College, Durg, Chhattisgarh, India

KEYWORDS: Volatile Organic Compounds (Vocs), Ambient Air, Sources, Health Risks Assessment

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are important owing to their participation in ozone (O₃) and particulate matter (PM) formation as well as adverse health effects. Among the Asian countries, India is the second-largest emitter of non-methane VOCs (Li et al., 2015), contributing about one third (5–47 Tg) of global VOC emissions (110 Tg) (Stewart et al., 2021). Important VOC emission sources include: incomplete combustion from industrial and domestic heating, vehicular engine exhaust and unprocessed solid fuel cooking and cultural burning practices (Pervez et al., 2019). This research aims to enhance the information on VOCs and measurements from the Raipur urban area of Chhattisgarh in central India. Research objectives include: 1) investigating VOCs spatiotemporal variations and sources; 2) evaluating ozone (O₃) and secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation, and 3) assessing health risks.

METHODS

The Raipur urbanization in the state of Chhattisgarh (population~ 1.8 million) is located southeast of India's central plateau. This region contains the largest producers of steel and iron in the country. Six sampling sites were selected for the measurement of VOCs. Samples were acquired twice per week (weekdays and weekends) from November 2021 to February 2022 and from April to June 2022. Tenax TA sorbent tubes were used with ACTI- VOCs sampler. Twenty-one VOCs were determined by TD-GC-MS/MS.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average sum of 21 VOCs (Σ 21VOCs) ranged from 54.81 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ at BA to 352.97 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ at GS followed by 322.27 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ at TA and 258.17 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ at IA. The overall mean was 222.32 \pm 110.37 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$. Average Σ 21 VOCs at CA was 223.74 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ and 153.97 $\mu\text{g-m}^{-3}$ at RA, three to four times that at BA. Ratios to BA were higher for IA at 4.7, GS at 6.4, 5.8 at TA, and 2.9 at RA.

Sampling Site	Background area (BA)	Residential area (RA)	Traffic area (TA)	Gasoline station (GS)	Commercial area (CA)	Industrial area (IA)
Σ 21VOCs	54.81	153.97	322.27	352.97	223.74	258.17
Winter	68.76	187.79	372.60	386.70	271.62	323.18
Summer	38.50	110.80	256.69	304.81	163.99	180.18

Table 1. Statistical summary of site wise average concentration and seasonal average concentration of 21 VOCs ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 40 sampling events conducted at each of six monitoring sites [commercial (CA), residential (RA), industrial (IA), gasoline Station (GS), highway road-traffic junction (TA) and background (BA)], in Chhattisgarh of India during the study period 2021-2022.

The highest to lowest differences in seasonally averaged $\Sigma 21$ VOCs between winter and summer were IA ($143 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) > TA ($115 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) > CA ($107 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) > GS ($81 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) > RA ($77 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) > BA ($30 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$).

Figure 1. Spatial distributions of $\Sigma 21$ VOCs in the study area during the first (November 2021 to February 2022) and second (April to June 2022) sampling periods. An inverse distance weighted (IDW) technique was used to interpolate between measurement locations.

CONCLUSIONS

VOCs characteristics in different areas of the Raipur showed large winter/summer and spatial variations. $\Sigma 21$ VOCs levels ranged from 54.81 to 359.97 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Benzene concentrations were higher than the permissible limit of India's NAAQS of 5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. BeZ showed higher cancer risk via inhalation above the minimum acceptable limit (1×10^{-6}) for children and adults. Tol and xylenes were the most important contributors to ozone formation. Among the 21 VOCs; Tol, m, p- X, Oct and B124 were the major contributors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is mainly supported by the SERB, India project proposal (CRG/2022/003926) and the DST-PURSE project (SR/PURSE/2022/145).

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EXPLORING CARBONACEOUS AEROSOL COMPOSITION AND AGING: INSIGHTS FROM MULTIWAVELENGTH OPTICAL AEROSOL ABSORPTION AND TOTAL CARBON MEASUREMENTS

M. RIGLER, M. IVANČIČ¹, I. JEŽEK BRECELJ¹, B. ALFÖLDY¹, G. LAVRIČ¹, V. PILKO³,
A. MUÑOZ⁴, M. RÓDENAS⁴, R. SOLER⁴, E. BORRÁS⁴, T. VERA⁴, E. YUBERO⁵, R.
PODLIPEC⁶, I. Stavroulas⁷, E. Liakakou⁷, G. Grivas⁷, P. Kalkavouras⁷, N. Mihalopoulos⁷
AND A. GREGORIČ^{1,2}

¹Aerosol d.o.o., Ljubljana – 1000, Slovenia

²Center for Atmospheric Research, University of Nova Gorica, Nova Gorica – 5000, Slovenia

³Robomed d.o.o., Kranj – 4000, Slovenia

⁴EUPHORE Labs., CEAM Foundation, Paterna, Valencia – 46980, Spain

⁵Atmospheric Pollution Laboratory (LCA-UMH), Miguel Hernández University, Elche -
03202, Spain

⁶Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e.V., Ion Beam Center, Dresden - 01328, Germany

⁷National Observatory of Athens, Athens – 11527, Greece

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosol, Aethalometer AE36s, Black Carbon, Brown Carbon

INTRODUCTION

The recommended guidelines for particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) issued by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) have been reflected in the updated directives of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in the United States and the European Union. Specifically, the annual mean concentration for PM_{2.5} has been reduced to 9 µg/m³ in the United States and 10 µg/m³ in the European Union. Under the extant standards in Europe, less than 1% of the population is exposed to air with PM_{2.5} concentrations exceeding the prescribed limits. However, this proportion escalates to 97% when evaluated against the WHO guidelines. To be able to decrease PM_{2.5} concentrations further, mitigation strategies must be targeted to specific sources, and source apportionment needs to be implemented in monitoring networks. Carbonaceous aerosols (CA) contribute significantly to the PM_{2.5} mass concentration. CA predominantly contribute to the mass of PM_{2.5}, but their composition varies significantly depending on the sources and aging processes. Different fractions have varying impacts on human health, with some posing significant health risks. Black Carbon (BC) and Brown Carbon (BrC), in particular, have been associated with a range of adverse health effects, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and even birth defects.

METHODS

Long-term measurements with the new Aethalometer model AE36s and Total Carbon Analyzer TCA08 were conducted at an urban background site in Ljubljana (Slovenia) and Athens (Greece), and compared with results obtained in the EUPHORE simulation chamber for different fuel types, burning condition and ageing state. Absorption Angstrom Exponent (AAE) was analyzed for the long (AAE₅₉₀₋₉₅₀; 590-660-880-950 nm) and short spectral range (AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀; 400-470-520 nm) separately, which allowed us to distinguish between different absorption fingerprints. Coupled with the apportionment of the CA, which is based on the simplified TC-BC method, where the organic carbon (OC) content is calculated as the difference between total carbon (TC) and BC, and the BC tracer method to separate organic carbon into the primary and secondary OC, the new method allows for enhanced insight to the

CA composition and aging.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Chamber experiments have revealed significant absorption of BrC at 340 nm for fresh BrC emitted during the smoldering phase of biomass burning. Soon after emission the absorption at 340 nm decreases relative to the absorption in the short range (400 – 520 nm). In the first part of the aging phase, when the aerosol is exposed to sunlight, a significant absorption increase was observed in the middle wavelength range (470 – 660 nm), thus decreasing short-range AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀ and increasing long-range AAE₅₉₀₋₉₅₀. A small absorption decrease in the middle wavelength range follows with further photochemical aging. Freshly emitted diesel exhaust and the flaming phase of biomass burning are characterized by lower BrC contribution and about 20% lower absorption at 340 nm than expected if AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀ would be extrapolated to 340 nm. We combined findings from chamber experiments and 2D analysis of AAE (Gregorič et al., 2024) with a high temporal resolution with an advanced TC-BC method (Fig 1) (Ivančič et al. 2024). TC-BC method allows the separation of CA to BC from biomass burning and fossil fuel (BC_{bb}, BC_{ff}), primary and secondary organic aerosol and further differentiation to BrC and non-absorbing species (POABrC, POA_{non-abs}, SOABrC, SOA_{non-abs}). Both methods were applied to ambient measurements in Ljubljana and Athens. This allowed us to obtain the seasonal fingerprint of CA, identify main pollution sources and specific pollution episodes (wildfires, industrial fires), and assess the impact of particle aging on the optical properties of aerosols.

Figure 1. Combination of advanced TC-BC method and 2D analysis of AAE using 9-wavelength Aethalometer.

CONCLUSIONS

Advanced carbonaceous aerosol apportionment and the 2D AAE analysis were integrated for the first time in this study. The proposed approach relies on high-time-resolution measurements of TC and BC concentrations using the additional wavelengths provided by the new Aethalometer model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of a project that is supported by the EC under the Horizon 2020 – R&I FP, through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under GA N. 101008004.

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SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF VENTILATION COEFFICIENT ON FINE PARTICLE POLLUTION IN INDIA

VIKAS^{1,3*}, VIKAS SINGH², JYOTI BHATE¹, VAISHNAVI^{1,3}

¹National Atmospheric Research Laboratory, Gadanki -517112

²Commission for Air Quality Management in National Capital Region and Adjoining Areas,

³Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Valiamala - 695547

KEYWORDS: Air Quality, Local Emissions, Background Concentration, Long-Range Transport

INTRODUCTION

India faces a growing challenge of poor air quality resulting from the high density of anthropogenic emissions due to rapid urbanisation, vital construction projects, and economic expansion. The elevated pollution levels, particularly the fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), is a major environmental concern that has a detrimental effect on human health and regional climate. The particulate matter (PM) concentration over a region is influenced by emissions, ventilation coefficient, temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric stability, chemistry, long-range transport etc. These factors contribute to the spatio-temporal variation in particulate matter concentrations by influencing the conglomeration and dispersion of pollutants. One of the important factors that determines pollution dispersion is the Ventilation coefficient (VC). VC is a product of wind speed and planetary boundary layer height that is defined as the ability of the atmosphere to dilute and disperse pollutants over a region. VC plays a decisive role in the spatial distribution and seasonal variability of PM concentration.

DATA

This study aims to study the impact of the emissions, and meteorological factors on the spatial and temporal distribution of PM concentration over India. We use MERRA-2 (Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, version 2) reanalysis data for zonal wind speed (10m), meridional wind speed (10m), PBLH and PM_{2.5} concentration at the resolution of (0.5 x 0.625) degrees for the year 2022. The surface PM_{2.5} concentration was calculated using the following formula:

$$PM_{2.5} = [DUST_{2.5}] + [SS_{2.5}] + [BC] + (1.6) \times [OC] + (1.375) \times [SO_4] + 1.4 \times [SO_4]$$

We have obtained the monthly PM_{2.5} anthropogenic emission from the Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR v6.1). A global 1-km resolution land surface digital elevation model (DEM) derived from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) 30 arc-second SRTM30 gridded DEM data created from the NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) is used to assess the dispersion parameters. We conducted spatial and temporal correlation analysis to investigate the relationship between particulate pollution, emissions and meteorological parameters.

METHODS

Our analysis focused on Pearson's correlation coefficients, which gauge the linear relationship between two sets of data, under the assumption of normal distribution of variables. The spatial and temporal correlations were calculated between the MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} concentration and meteorological variables, local anthropogenic emissions (primary

PM2.5), and background concentration. Background concentration was obtained by removing the local emission influence by keeping the lowest concentration value around the grid. To assess the spatial and temporal effects of ventilation on PM2.5 levels across India, we calculated the correlation between surface PM2.5 concentration and the Ventilation Coefficient (VC). Since ventilation can disperse pollutants from regions of high emission to areas with lower emissions, potentially leading to higher concentrations in low-emission areas, it is crucial to consider local emissions alongside the ventilation coefficient. To address this, we introduced a metric termed "emissions over ventilation," represented by the ratio of local emissions (Q) to the ventilation coefficient (VC). This metric captures the combined effect of emission intensity and atmospheric ventilation on PM2.5 levels, with higher values indicating elevated local emissions relative to ventilation and vice versa.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The correlation between VC and PM2.5 concentration varies with season and location. The VC and PM2.5 exhibit a negative correlation during September to March and a positive correlation during pre-monsoon and monsoon months. Our analysis revealed a distinct seasonal pattern in the correlation between Q/VC and PM2.5 concentrations. Specifically, we observed a strong positive correlation during winter months, indicating that periods of reduced ventilation coupled with heightened local emissions contribute to elevated PM2.5 concentrations during this season. The absence of a significant correlation between emissions over ventilation (Q/VC) and PM2.5 concentrations during summer months suggests non-local dispersion of pollutants due to strong convection and horizontal transport. This results in the enhancement of the background concentration in the areas of low or zero anthropogenic emissions. To account for the background pollution, the correlation between 'Q/VC+background' and PM2.5 concentrations was calculated. The consistently high positive correlation between 'Q/VC+background' and PM2.5 concentrations underscores the significant role of background pollution in shaping PM2.5 levels. This emphasizes the necessity of accounting for background pollution sources, including regional and long-range transport, alongside local emissions in PM2.5 assessments.

Figure 1: Spatial and temporal correlation between (a) PM2.5 and VC (b) PM2.5 and Q/VC (c) PM2.5 and Q/VC + Background

CONCLUSIONS

1. Ventilation Coefficient plays a pivotal role in influencing air quality, as it enables better ventilation and mixing of pollutants, leading to a decrease in PM levels. However, it also has a negative impact by transporting pollutants to regions with lower emissions, thereby exacerbating air quality issues in those areas. Ventilation is also associated with enhancing dust related pollution.
2. The ventilation coefficient is not the only parameter that determines the air pollution potential of an area, the local emissions and background concentration need to be considered to determine the air pollution potential of an area of interest.

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FLUOROPHORIC COMPOSITION OF AQUEOUS BROWN CARBON IN THE NORTHWESTERN HIMALAYAS USING EEM PARAFAC

R.K. YADAV¹, A. RANA¹, S. SARKAR¹

¹School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IIT Mandi, Kamand, HP, 175005, India.

KEYWORDS: HULIS, PRLIS, EEM PARAFAC, fluorescence indices.

INTRODUCTION

The fraction of aerosol organic carbon (OC) which absorbs light strongly towards UV and near-visible is referred to as brown carbon (BrC). Water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC) contributes 20-80% by mass to OC (Kirilova et al., 2013), and one of its major constituents is humic-like substances (HULIS), which comprise of self-assembled supramolecular conformations, with small heterogenous humic molecules consisting of polycyclic ring structures with hydrocarbon chain and polar functional groups (Chalbot et al., 2014,). BrC and HULIS influence regional climate by absorbing solar radiation and altering cloud microphysics, and influence tropospheric photochemistry by UV attenuation (Laskin et al., 2015). With increased warming observed over the Himalayas over the past few decades (Ramachandran et al., 2023), it is crucial to evaluate the roles of BrC and HULIS in aerosol-induced climate forcing in this region. In view of this, the present work reports the fluorophoric composition of BrC via 3-D fluorescence coupled with PARAFAC during summertime in the NW Himalayas in order to understand prevalent emission regimes.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} sampling was conducted in Kamand (31.78° N, 76.99° E) situated in the NW Himalayas using high-volume PM_{2.5} samplers (Ecotech Hi-Vol 3000) on pre-baked (550°C) 8×10-inch quartz filters (QMA, Whatman). Samples were collected on a 12-h (daytime and nighttime) basis with a total of 46 samples (day = 24 and night = 22). To obtain the water-soluble fraction, 10 cm² of each filter was extracted in 20 ml ultrapure water, and ultrasonicated twice for 15 mins (total: 30 mins). The extracts were filtered using 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters (Rankem), and analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (250–700 nm). Fluorescence excitation emission measurement was performed with an excitation range of 250–400 nm and an emission range of 290–500 nm, followed by parallel factor analysis (PARAFAC) in the non-negativity constrained mode (Murphy et al., 2013). Calculation of fluorescence indices (humidification index (HIX), biological index (BIX), and fluorescence index (FI)) was carried out (Huguet et al., 2009; Wu et al., 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average babs_aq_365 (absorption coefficient of water extract at wavelength 365 nm) in the summer for the day and night time are $2.74 \pm 1.53 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$ and $3.02 \pm 0.88 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 1a). The reduced absorbance of BrC_{aq} in the daytime might be linked to chromophores with lower absorption properties, potentially generated through photochemical processes and/or photobleaching (Laskin et al., 2015). For BrC_{aq}, The Angstrom exponent (AE) was similar between day and nighttime (6.74 ± 1.06 and 6.55 ± 0.35 , respectively), with slightly higher absorption towards longer wavelengths during summer nights. The strong association between babs_aq_365 and WSOC ($r=0.75-0.79$, $p<0.001$; Fig. 1b) indicates that most water-soluble organics that contribute to WSOC mass are also chromophoric. Significant correlations between WSOC and NO₃⁻ ($r=0.65$, $p<0.01$; Fig. 1c) suggest the

potential formation of nitroaromatics, possibly via photochemistry.

Averaged nighttime HIX (0.96 ± 0.08) was higher than daytime (0.83 ± 0.12), suggesting more conjugated aromatic and humified fluorophores from nighttime processing/polycondensation. This along with higher BIX and FI during night (1.58 ± 0.85 ; 1.75 ± 0.31) compared to day (1.30 ± 0.51 ; 1.70 ± 0.31) confirms that nighttime fluorophores are indeed more humified. The averaged summertime HIX (0.89 ± 0.12) is higher than that from the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (0.8 ± 0.4) (Dey and Sarkar, 2024), revealing the significantly humic nature of NW Himalayan BrC.

Figure 1: Absorption coefficient of BrCaq for the 300-700 nm range for the summer season (a), correlation of b_{abs_365} with WSOC (b), and correlation of NO_3^- with WSOC (c).

Figure 2: Daytime and nighttime distribution of HIX vs BIX (a) and HIX vs FI (b) in the summer.

Three components are identified by EEM PARAFAC with an explained variance of 98.64% and core consistency of 86.13%. Among these, H1 and H2 correspond to HULIS (contributions of 32% and 29%) and P1 corresponds to protein-like substances (PRLIS; contribution of 39%) (Fig. 3). H1 represents HULIS with more conjugated structures from condensation reactions whereas H2 represents HULIS produced from the breakdown of macromolecules (with a concurrent reduction in aromaticity) via photodegradation. P1 represents tyrosine-like PRLIS, which is mostly associated with terrestrial environments (Chen et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Fluorophoric composition of BrC as identified by EEM PARAFAC.

CONCLUSIONS

Summertime BrC in the NW Himalayas are slightly more aromatic and humified in the nighttime as compared to day, and are characterized by three types of fluorophores: two humic-like with varying oxidation states and one protein-like component.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Ministry of Earth Sciences is acknowledged for funding, and AMRC, IIT Mandi for instrumentation.

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RESPIRATORY DEPOSITION DOSE OF FINE PARTICULATE MATTER (PM_{2.5}) NEAR NATIONAL HIGHWAY IN NORTHERN INDIA

SHIKHA* and AJAY TANEJA

Department of Chemistry, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra-282002, India

KEYWORDS- FINE PM, RDD, REGIONAL DEPOSITION

INTRODUCTION

Different agencies and federal authorities recognize particulate matter (PM) as a criterion air pollutant due to its chemical structure, morphology, and origin (Mushtaq et al. 2023), and its exposure causes respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Kim et al. 2015). Out of different sizes of PM, PM_{2.5} has the most consistent association with adverse health effects (Shikha et al. 2023) as these particles cause approximately 1.2 million deaths in India (Mushtaq et al. 2023). Fine PM pollution in India is not merely urban; it also affects nonurban areas (Ravishankaraa et al. 2020). Monitoring stations available in bigger cities have good data quality compared to smaller cities. So, Stations must be installed in rural, town, and semi-urban areas where none exist to better characterise air quality and pollution sources in India (Sharma and Mauzerall 2022).

MATERIALS & METHODS

The sampling was done in tundla (semiurban city) belonging to the Taj Trapezium Zone (TTZ) in the north-central region of India. (Shikha et al 2023). Cascade impactor (SKC Inc. Eighty-Four PA USA) operating at 9 litres per minute was for PM_{2.5} monitoring. In the current study the Respiratory Deposition Dose (RDD) was estimated using the method given by International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP; 1994). The calculation was done using Equations as mentioned below: (ICRP; 1994)

$$RDD = (V_T \times f) \times DF_i \times PM_i$$
$$DF_{HD} = IF \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(6.84 + 1.183 \ln d_p)} + \frac{1}{1 + \exp(0.924 - 1.885 \ln d_p)} \right)$$
$$IF = 1 - 0.5 \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + 0.00076 d_p^{2.8}} \right)$$

$$DF_{TB} = \left(\frac{0.00352}{d_p} \right) \left[\exp(-0.234(\ln d_p + 3.40)^2) + 63.9 \exp(-0.819(\ln d_p - 1.61)^2) \right]$$

$$DF_{AL} = \left(\frac{0.0155}{d_p} \right) \left[\exp(-0.416(\ln d_p + 2.84)^2) + 19.11 \exp(-0.482(\ln d_p - 1.362)^2) \right]$$

Where, RDD is Respiratory Deposition Doses, VT is Tidal volume (m³ per breath), *f* is Typical breathing frequency (breath per minute), DF_i is the Deposition fraction of a size fraction *i*, IF is an Inhalable fraction and PM_i is Mass concentration in *i* size (Hinds,1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concentration levels of Fine PM

The highest average concentration of PM_{2.5} was found in November 2023 i.e., (93.22 & 99.61 µgm⁻³) while the lowest concentration was recorded as 36.74 & 55.05 µgm⁻³ in December. This may be due to increased exhaust emissions, vehicle part wear and tear, and dust re-suspension in addition the use of biomass as domestic fuel also releases these particles

(Rajouriya et al 2023). Comparing the day and night variation, it was found that the nighttime results were higher than the daytime. Smoke from biomass burning, coal burning, and particle deposition under inversion circumstances increases the night PM concentration. In Contrast, late mornings reduce vehicular activity, lowering PM concentrations in the winter season (Deshmukh et al 2013). The RDDs of PM in the Head (HA), Tracheobronchial (TB), and Alveolar (AL) regions of the respiratory tract, were assessed for adult males during heavy exercise, and light exercise respectively. Generally, adult males do heavy or light exercises or work while consuming less or more energy so, PM exposure in the outdoor environment was analyzed. From Fig. 1, we can state that heavy exercise has the highest amount of deposition in our respiratory system, with a mean ($3.25 \mu\text{gmin}^{-1}$) in the night and $2.58 \mu\text{gmin}^{-1}$ in the day compared to light exercise which had $1.63 \mu\text{gmin}^{-1}$ in the night and $1.29 \mu\text{gmin}^{-1}$ in the day for males respectively. Higher RDD values for heavy exercises were due to due to physical activities that increase breathing frequency which also causes an increment in PM deposition in the respiratory tract (Hinds, 1999). The observed result for regional variation shows a considerable variation in the RDD during the day and nighttime respectively.

Figure 1 Total respiratory deposition doses for Light and Heavy exercises.

During the Night-time, the RDD in the heavy exercises had higher deposition showing a trend HA (2.63)>TB (0.48)>AL (0.22) while for light exercises the RDD values were HA (1.30)>TB (0.2037)>AL (0.1148). The trends were similar for heavy and light exercise during the day time respectively. RDD value reveals that PM_{2.5} particles dominate toxicity in HA and AL regions, while Tb regions are less harmful. The present study sampling was done in the winter season showing the higher deposition at night which explained that the exercisers should limit daily activity based on pollution.

CONCLUSIONS

The scarcity of monitoring stations in smaller towns impedes data quality improvement. So, our study focuses on Tundla, a small town that is densely populated and congested near an industrial area. Due to the traffic-prone site, the PM_{2.5} concentration was found to be higher during the nighttime ($75.67 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) followed by the day ($60.10 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$). The day and night variation at this site explains the different sources present in the sampling area. Additionally, the respiratory deposition dose for male adults across different exercise levels found that the head region had the highest RDD values at 80% deposition, followed by AL at 13% and TB at 7%. There is a strong connection between PM_{2.5} exposure and health effects, but further research is required in various locations. The results of this study will assist localities and health personnel in dealing with respiratory concerns.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are highly thankful to the Department of Chemistry, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar

University, Agra for the support and facilities that were required for the completion of the present study.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF LONG-TERM SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION IN AN URBAN LOCATION IN INDIA

M. SEBASTIAN¹, V. P. KANAWADE^{1,2}, N. MITTAL³, AND T. JOKINEN²

¹Centre for Earth, Ocean and Atmospheric Sciences, University of Hyderabad, India

²Climate and Atmospheric Research Centre, Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

³TSI Instruments India Private Limited, Bangalore, India

KEYWORDS: Ultrafine Particles, Size-Segregated Particles, New Particle Formation and Growth

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols vary in a wide size range with four orders of magnitude difference between the smallest and the largest particles. The spatial and temporal variability in aerosol emissions strongly modulates the dynamical behaviour and associated properties of aerosols [Costabile et al., 2009; Kerminen et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2015]. The primary emissions and secondary formation via gas-to-particle conversion are the major contributors to the total aerosol numbers in the atmosphere [Rönkkö et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2008]. The growth of newly formed particles or primary particles can significantly alter the total aerosol mass and composition which has implications for Earth's radiation budget and hydrological cycle via aerosol's direct and indirect effects, respectively.

METHODS

In this study, we have used long-term (2019-2022) observations of particle number size distribution from the nano Condensation Nucleus Counter (nCNC) in the size range from 1 to 3 nm and Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) from 10 nm to 600 nm in an urban location, Hyderabad (University of Hyderabad campus site), in India. The observation days were broadly classified into three event types, namely NPF, non-event, and undefined, based on the visual evaluation of the contour plot of particle number size distributions. We have calculated size-segregated particle number concentrations in four major modes such as cluster mode (sub-3nm), nucleation mode (10-25 nm), Aitken mode (25-100 nm) and accumulation mode (100-600 nm). We further used in-situ measured particulate matter of less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) to identify polluted days following the NAAQS criteria (days with PM_{2.5} > 60 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The size-segregated particle number concentrations followed a clear seasonal pattern, with the highest concentrations during pre-monsoon (March - May) and the lowest in the winter (December - February). The largest particle number concentrations during pre-monsoon correspond to the highest frequency of NPF event occurrence (Figure 1). Cluster-mode particles constituted the largest fraction of particle number concentrations, while accumulation-mode particles constituted the least. Cluster mode particle number concentrations were observed to be highest on NPF event days compared to other event types. The positive correlation between cluster mode particles and PM_{2.5} suggests that NPF is not inhibited by high pre-existing particle concentrations. This shows that the balance between precursor vapour concentrations and pre-existing particle concentrations determines when NPF will occur in the contaminated border layer under a particular atmospheric environment.

However, the negative relationship between nucleation mode particles and PM_{2.5} implies that not all cluster mode particles reach nucleation mode size (Figure 2). Seasonal variation in particle number concentrations is highly related to planetary boundary layer evolution, temperature (which determines the oxidation extent of the atmosphere), and pre-existing particles (efficient scavenging of smaller particles).

Figure 1. Monthly percentage of occurrence of NPF, non-event polluted and undefined events days based on total valid observations days at Hyderabad from 1 April 2019 to 7 December 2022.

Figure 2. Correlation between PM_{2.5} concentration and particle number concentration in each mode during the winter season (December-February).

CONCLUSIONS

- Cluster mode particles constitute the largest fraction of particle number while accumulation mode contributes the largest fraction of aerosol mass for different event types.
- NPF contributes significantly to cluster, nucleation, Aitken and accumulation mode number concentrations while insignificantly to accumulation mode mass concentration.
- The balance between pre-existing particles and precursor concentrations possibly decides when NPF will take place in urban areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

VPK acknowledge financial support from the Department of Science & Technology (DST)-Science Engineering Research Board (SERB; ECR/2016/001333) and DST-Climate Change Division Program (Aerosol/89/2017). MS acknowledge the Institute of Eminence, University of Hyderabad (sanction no. UoH/IoE/RC1/RC1-20-014).

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TEMPORAL VARIABILITY, METEOROLOGICAL INFLUENCES, AND LONG-RANGE TRANSPORT OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS OVER TWO CONTRASTING ENVIRONMENTS IN INDIA

PARMINDER KAUR¹, PRANAB DHAR¹, ONAM BANSAL², DARSHAN SINGH²,
ANIRBAN GUHA¹

¹Department of Physics, Tripura University, West Tripura, Tripura, India

²Department of Physics, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, India

KEYWORDS: Equivalent Black Carbon: Meteorology: Boundary Layer Height: Cwt: Long-Range Transport.

INTRODUCTION

This study investigates the temporal variability, meteorological influences, potential sources, and long-range transport of atmospheric aerosols over two contrasting environments during 2011-2013. The research focuses on Agartala (AGR) city in Northeast India, representing a rural-continental environment, and Patiala (PTA), an urban site in Northwest India.

METHODS

The study employed a comprehensive approach to analyze atmospheric aerosols using multiple instruments and data sources. eBC concentrations were measured using an Aethalometer (AE-31), while AOD was obtained through both ground-based (Microtops II) and satellite-based (MODIS) observations. To identify aerosol sources and transport patterns, the research utilized the CWT model and HYSPLIT back trajectories. Additional data from MERRA-2 reanalysis provided BC concentrations and wind patterns, while ERA5 reanalysis supplied PBL height information. This multi-faceted methodology allowed for a thorough investigation of aerosol characteristics, sources, and transport mechanisms in the study areas.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The seasonal averaged equivalent black carbon (eBC) concentration in AGR ranges from 1.55 to 38.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with an average value of $9.87 \pm 8.17 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while at PTA, it ranges from 1.30 to 15.57 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with an average value of $7.83 \pm 3.51 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Notably, the annual average eBC concentration over AGR was observed to be approximately three times higher than PTA. Two diurnal peaks (morning and evening) in eBC have been observed at both sites, with more prominence at AGR compared to PTA. Spectral aerosol optical depth (AOD) ranges from 0.33 ± 0.09 (post-monsoon) to 0.85 ± 0.22 (winter) at AGR and 0.47 ± 0.04 (pre-monsoon) to 0.74 ± 0.09 (post-monsoon) at PTA. The concentration of eBC and its diurnal and seasonal variations indicate that the primary sources of eBC are local sources, synoptic meteorology, planetary boundary layer (PBL) dynamics, and distant transportation of aerosols. The higher wintertime values of eBC at AGR compared to PTA are linked with the transportation of eBC from the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). Furthermore, evidence suggests that eBC aerosols are transported from both local and regional sources, supported by Concentration Weighted Trajectory (CWT) and cluster analysis. This comprehensive study provides valuable insights into the complex dynamics of atmospheric aerosols in contrasting environments, contributing to our understanding of air quality and climate impacts in the region.

Figure 1 (a) Monthly mean variation in eBC mass concentration over AGR and PTA (b1) seasonal mean variation in eBC mass concentration for AGR and (b2) seasonal mean variation in eBC mass concentration for PTA. The standard deviation ($\pm\sigma$) variation is shown as vertical bars over each data point.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this research have significant implications for air quality management strategies and climate change mitigation efforts in both rural and urban areas of India. The observed differences between AGR and PTA highlight the need for location-specific approaches to address air pollution challenges. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of considering long-range transport of aerosols in air quality assessments and policy formulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the Indian Space Research Organisation-Geosphere Biosphere program (ISRO-GBP) for supporting this work by funding the Aerosol Radiative Forcing over India (ARFI) project.

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MINERALOGICAL ANALYSIS OF PM10 IN ALMORA: A HIGH-ALTITUDE TOWN IN THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAS

S. GUPTA^{1,2}, SHOBHNA SHANKAR³, PREETI TIWARI^{1, 2}, ARCHANA BAWARI⁴, SHEETAL CHAUDHARY⁴, ANIL SALAL⁴, JAGDISH CHANDRA KUNIYAL⁴, RANU GADI³, S. K. SHARMA^{1,2}

¹CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, Dr. K. S. Krishnan Road, New Delhi-110012, India.

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad-201002, India.

³Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Kashmere Gate, New Delhi-110006

⁴G. B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment, Kosi-Katarmal-263643, Almora

KEYWORDS: Mineralogical Analysis, Pm10, Central Himalayas, Geochemical Analysis, XRD

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, originating from both natural and anthropogenic sources, significantly impact air quality, climate dynamics, and human health. In the central Himalayan region of India, coarse mode particulate matter (PM10) is a major contributor to poor air quality, driven by industrial emissions, vehicular pollution, and biomass burning (Choudhary et al., 2022). While past studies (Sheoran et al., 2021; Choudhary et al., 2022) have explored the chemical composition of aerosols, limited research has focused on the mineralogical characteristics of PM10 using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) techniques (Gupta et al., 2024a; b). This study aims to conduct a geochemical analysis to investigate the mineral composition of PM10 particles in the region. Through this analysis, the research identifies the significant minerals present in the PM10, including dolomite, illite, kaolinite, and chlorite. The understanding of mineralogical compositions of PM10, the present study provides the valuable insights into the sources and environmental impact of airborne particles in this area. Understanding these mineralogical features will help to trace dust sources and inform strategies for mitigating air pollution and protecting public health in this sensitive region.

METHODS

PM10 sampling was conducted at NIHE, Kosi-Katarmal, Almora, from April 2019 –October 2020. XRD analysis identified minerals by comparing peak positions with the RRUFF database. FTIR spectroscopy detected inorganic ions and organic groups that contribute to the mineral compositions, while SEM-EDX examined particle morphology and elemental composition, with results reported as average weight percentages after ZAF correction (Gupta et al., 2024a; b).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

XRD analysis has quantified a variety of mineralogical compositions present in the PM10 samples. The study revealed that minerals such as kaolinite, montmorillonite, quartz, dolomite, calcite, magnetite, hematite, gypsum, halite, mascagnite, augite, albite, and wollastonite are found in significant abundance (Fig. 1). In contrast, calcium ammonium sulfate hydrate and illite was detected in lower proportions. The analysis of PM10 samples collected on quartz fiber filters consistently revealed the presence of well-crystallized quartz minerals, suggesting their widespread distribution in the region. Other identified minerals in the PM10 samples include dolomite, albite, and augite, which are largely derived from natural

geological processes such as soil and rock weathering. Among the clay minerals, kaolinite, and montmorillonite were prominent in the samples. These minerals likely originated from a combination of geological sources, industrial activities, agricultural practices, and combustion processes, including fossil fuel and biomass burning. Iron-bearing minerals such as hematite and magnetite were also found, and their presence is attributed to both natural sources like soil erosion, rock weathering, and dust storms, as well as anthropogenic activities such as iron and steel production, vehicular emissions, and emissions from power plants. The identification of ammonium sulfate (mascagnite) points to secondary atmospheric reactions, mainly driven by fossil fuel combustion, industrial emissions, biomass burning, and waste incineration. FTIR and SEM-EDX analyses confirmed the mineral compositions and identified the molecular bonds and elemental compositions, further supporting the XRD findings.

Figure 1. XRD pattern for the PM₁₀ sample. Quartz (Q), dolomite (D), albite (Al), augite (Au), illite (I), kaolinite (K), montmorillonite (M), Hematite (H), magnetite (Mg), gypsum (G), wollastonite (W), mascagnite (AS), Calcite (C) and halite (Ha)

CONCLUSIONS

The combined analyses from XRD, FTIR, and SEM-EDX offer a thorough understanding of the mineral composition and particle morphology of PM₁₀ in the study area. The findings show that the PM₁₀ contains minerals like kaolinite, montmorillonite, quartz, dolomite, calcite, magnetite, hematite, and gypsum, indicating both natural processes such as soil erosion and rock weathering, as well as human activities like construction, industrial emissions, and fossil fuel burning. FTIR analysis confirms specific bonding structures in the minerals, while SEM-EDX provides insight into the elemental composition and shape of the particles. Together, these methods confirm that PM₁₀ in the region is a complex combination of natural and human-related sources.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The study financially supported by DST, New Delhi, India is greatly acknowledged (DST/CCP/Aerosol/88/2017).

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THE IMPACT OF HYDRATED AEROSOLS AND FOG DROPLETS ON VISIBILITY DEGRADATION IN NEW DELHI, INDIA

PRIYANGSHU CHOUDHURY¹, SANDEEP WAGH² AND SACHIN D GHUDE²

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, MH, India 411008

KEYWORDS: AEROSOLS, FOG, HAZE, VISIBILITY, MIE SCATTERING.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) experiences prolonged and dense fog during winter which considerably impacts air traffic and other economic aspects. The present study delves into the contributions of aerosols and fog droplets that result in low visibility (Vis). The study employed Mie theory to calculate light extinction due to hydrated aerosols and fog droplets at Indira Gandhi International Airport, New Delhi.

METHODS

Data was collected at IGI Airport from December 2017 to January 2018. A Fog Monitor (FM-120) was deployed to measure fog droplet sizes and concentration in 30 bins. SMPS particle counter that measured aerosol size distribution; and a visibility meter for atmospheric visibility measurements. Extinction coefficients for aerosols and fog droplets were established using the Mie scattering theory. Extinction coefficients for aerosols were measured at wavelengths of 450 nm, 532 nm, and 637 nm while fog droplets were measured at 532 nm.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Aerosol Contribution to Visibility Reduction

Aerosols, particularly below 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}), significantly obscure light through scattering and absorption of light. This phenomenon becomes pronounced when humidity is high, as aerosols begin to absorb water grow in size and scatter more light. In the present study aerosols alone accounted for 81.56% of total extinction during haze. Among all the 8 events, on the 2nd and 27th January 2018, noted the visibility reduction below 500m even without the presence of significant fog suggesting 100% of the attenuation was due to aerosols, whereas the remaining days showed a contribution above 50% even during the dense fog phase. Safai et al., 2017 and Tiwari et al., 2015 showed major inputs were black carbon and sulphate coming from anthropogenic sources because of their long-term presence in the atmosphere and high capacity for scattering and absorbing light.

Fog Droplet Contribution to Visibility Reduction

Despite the small number compared to aerosols, fog droplets had a profound impact on visibility in foggy regimes. During instances of dense fog (Vis < 200 m) fog droplets contributed about 41.50% to total extinction. The longest fog duration observed on 4th January 2018, showed the highest droplet extinction coefficient upto 69.95%, whereas during other days, the coefficient percentage stayed remain below 50%. Nevertheless, during periods of thick fog events the role of aerosol particles remained significant because these droplets require them in order to serve as condensation nuclei for accumulation and droplet growth.

Diurnal Variations A clear tri-phase pattern is exhibited by the aerosol extinction coefficient, they rise during the day, peak in the late afternoon, and fall towards night-

time. Solar radiation, heat activity, and photochemical processes facilitate aerosol suspension and mixing during the day, influencing the trend. At night temperature inversions and nocturnal stability reduce extinction coefficients, while increases in photochemical reactions during the daytime contribute to mid-day peaks. The extinction that is started by the start of a day is furthered by the rise in aerosol concentration brought on by the morning warming.

Condition	3rd Jan 2018	4th Jan 2018	7th Jan 2018	19th Jan 2018	28th Jan 2018
Haze	-	6.00% ± 0.01%	26.35% ± 0.15%	20.89% ± 0.12%	20.53% ± 0.98%
Severe Haze	31.38% ± 0.81%	10.28% ± 0.03%	19.51% ± 0.16%	25.93% ± 0.19%	24.55% ± 1.43%
Moderate Fog	38.28% ± 0.32%	19.77% ± 0.78%	21.19% ± 0.13%	21.01% ± 0.09%	12.85% ± 0.56%
Fog	30.34% ± 0.58%	69.95% ± 4.50%	32.95% ± 0.25%	32.17% ± 0.21%	42.08% ± 2.81%

Table 4: Ratio of attenuation of light due to droplet to that of aerosol in percentage.

Figure 1: Representative plot for (A) Droplet extinction coefficients (B) Aerosol extinction (C) Box plot for Aerosol extinction coefficient during different visibility regime (D) Droplet extinction coefficient, for the case of 4th January 2018.

CONCLUSIONS

To a large extent, the present study highlights aerosols' contribution to the decline in visibility in New Delhi when there are severe haze cases. Fog droplets make it worse but they do not have as much impact on this compared to aerosol components and fine particulate matter during intense haze events. Aerosols facilitate fog droplet creation; on the other hand, they can also support the dropping of visibility because of their ability to collect different visible particles. In summary, we found that visibility reduction due to aerosols was dependent on more than just the concentration of aerosols, atmospheric states, mixing processes, and relative humidity also contributed. In contrast, fog droplet extinction coefficients exhibited a more pronounced contribution during dense fog.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my gratitude to the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES) and the Director of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology (IITM) for their very essential help and resources.

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LONG-TERM OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF BROWN CARBON ABSORPTION IN ATHENS, INFERRED BY AETHALOMETER MEASUREMENTS, WATER-SOLUBLE AND METHANOL-SOLUBLE ORGANIC MATTER

D. PARASKEVOPOULOU^{1,2}, D. G. KASKAOUTIS^{1,3}, G. GRIVAS², A. BOUGIATIOTI², E. LIAKAKOU², M. TSAGARAKI², E. GERASOPOULOS¹ AND N. MIHALOPOULOS¹

¹Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, National Observatory of Athens, Palaia Penteli, 15236 Athens, Greece

²ECPL, Department of Chemistry, University of Crete, Heraklion, 71003, Greece.

³Department of Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani 50100, Greece.

KEYWORDS: Brown Carbon, Water-Methanol Soluble, Biomass Burning, Spectral Absorption.

INTRODUCTION

Combustion of fossil fuels, biomass burning, as well as natural biogenic emissions are recognized as major sources of light-absorbing organic carbon (Brown Carbon, BrC) that strongly contribute to radiative forcing at regional scales (Paraskevopoulou et al., 2023). It's well known that BrC strongly absorbs solar light in the ultraviolet and near-visible spectrum, while the magnitude and spectral characteristics of this absorption highly depend on the emission source (combustion type or else), burning material, secondary formation processes, aging and photobleaching in the atmosphere (Kaskaoutis et al., 2021). Much more complexity exists in urban environments with multiple sources of carbonaceous aerosols and variable chemical composition. The present study examines the BrC characteristics in the Athens urban environment, covering a period of about 5 years (from 2018 to 2022), emphasizing both ambient BrC absorption, inferred by aethalometer measurements, as well as the water-soluble and methanol-soluble BrC-absorption component, determined through chemical analysis of daily (24-hrs) samples. The analysis covers contrasting seasons regarding the major emission sources of BrC, like wood burning for domestic heating in winter and forest fires in summer, as well as enhanced secondary organics formation due to strong photochemical processing in summer and increased levels of natural biogenic organics in the same season, which presented significantly lower absorption efficiency than the combustion sources.

METHODS

The measurements were performed at the Aerosol Monitoring Supersite of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA), at Thissio premises (38° 0.00' N, 23° 43.48' E, 110 m a.s.l.). In this work, we analysed aethalometer (AE-33) measurements of BC and BrC absorption during 2018-2022 (Liakakou et al. 2020), along with absorption properties of water-soluble (WS) and methanol-soluble (MeS) BrC, which were analyzed spectrophotometrically on PM_{2.5} filter extracts (Paraskevopoulou et al., 2023). Furthermore, organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) concentrations were determined using a Sunset Analyzer, while water-soluble OC (WSOC) concentrations were determined using a Shimadzu TOC-VCSH analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 shows the monthly mean absorptions due to WS_BrC and MeS_BrC in Athens. The main findings from this ~ 5-years analysis revealed that during the coldest months of the year,

with the intense residential wood burning emissions, the average WSOC and MeS_BrC levels reached $3.67 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 6.03 Mm^{-1} , respectively, while online aethalometer measurements recorded a mean BC concentration of $2.23 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (with a 34.18% contribution from biomass burning). The wintertime WS_BrC absorption at 365 nm was about 44 % that of MeS_BrC, demonstrating that there is an important fraction of absorbing water-insoluble OC, while in summer the WS_BrC contributed about 70% to that of MeS_BrC. The ambient BrC absorption, calculated via aethalometer measurements, presented 10 times higher values compared to the soluble extracts, indicating significant contribution from primary origin sources (not water or methanol soluble). The ambient absorption Angstrom Exponent (AAE) values in winter were higher compared to those in summer, probably due to vaporization and photo-bleaching of BrC chromophores. The winter mass absorption efficiency (MAE) of WSOC at 365 nm was found to be $0.81 \text{ m}^2\text{gC}^{-1}$, slightly increasing to $1.01 \text{ m}^2\text{gC}^{-1}$ in summer, indicating the influence of absorbing aerosols from fossil-fuel combustion. The MeS_BrC was similarly absorptive in winter ($0.82 \text{ m}^2\text{gC}^{-1}$), though decreasing to baseline levels in summer ($0.26 \text{ m}^2\text{gC}^{-1}$). These specific organic components that drive BrC absorption and their intensive properties are scarce in Europe, notably for the atmospheric particulate matter.

Figure 1. The absorptions due to WS_BrC and MeS_BrC at 365 nm (left axis) and 590 nm (right axis) in Athens, on a monthly basis, from 2018 to 2022.

CONCLUSIONS

The current study investigated long-term light-absorbing properties of ambient, water- and methanol-soluble brown carbon (BrC) for the first time in the Eastern Mediterranean. BrC from residential wood burning exhibited the highest magnitude during the winter season, while the water-soluble and methanol-soluble absorptions followed a similar seasonal pattern. Methanol-soluble and water-soluble absorptions correspond to a small part of the total BrC absorption inferred from the aethalometer, indicating lesser absorptivity from the soluble BrC and a significant insoluble absorption fraction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF BLACK AND BROWN CARBON LIGHT ABSORPTION FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES AND ATMOSPHERIC PROCESSING

D. G. KASKAOUTIS^{1,2}, G. GRIVAS², I. STAVROULAS², E. LIAKAKOU², A. BOUGIATIOTI², R. E. P. SOTIROPOULOU³, U. C. DUMKA⁴, E. TAGARIS¹ AND N. MIHALOPOULOS²

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani, Greece.

²Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, National Observatory of Athens, Palaia Penteli, 15236 Athens, Greece

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani, Greece.

⁴Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Nainital 263001, India.

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Brown Carbon, Biomass Burning, Spectral Absorption

INTRODUCTION

Absorbing carbonaceous aerosols are classified into two categories i.e. Black Carbon or Elemental Carbon (BC, EC) and Brown Carbon (BrC), exhibiting different sizes and shapes, hygroscopicity, chemical composition, sources, formation mechanisms, spectral optical properties, and radiative impacts (Kaskaoutis et al., 2022). The current study assesses the contrasting spectral absorption properties of carbonaceous aerosols (BC and BrC) in Ioannina during the winter and summer campaigns, mostly based on aethalometer measurements. The work aims to examine the contributions of the BC and BrC absorptions from different sources, the characteristics of the secondary BrC absorption, the influence of aging, oxidation, photo-enhancement, and photo-bleaching processes on BC and BrC spectral absorptions, as well as their absorption properties between winter and summer due to different emission sources, and atmospheric oxidation processes. Understanding the optical properties and sources of carbonaceous aerosols, particularly those of BrC, are of paramount importance for constraining current radiative transfer models, as well as formulating effective strategies for emission abatements.

METHODS

The measurements were performed in Ioannina, the largest city (~120,000) in NW Greece, which is highly suffered by residential wood burning (RWB) emissions for domestic heating during winter. In this work, we analysed aethalometer (AE-33) measurements, along with inorganic species (as supporting data) obtained during two research campaigns in summer (11 July – 22 August 2019) and winter (12 December 2019 – 17 February 2020) at an urban background site in Ioannina (Kaskaoutis et al., 2022; Paraskevopoulou et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

During wintertime, the site experiences a heavy burden of RWB aerosols, characterized by high concentrations of PM_{2.5}, organic carbon (OC) and BC from wood burning (BC_{wb}). Conversely, in summer, mostly regional atmospheric conditions dominate with a larger relative contribution from vehicle emissions (see Fig. 1). During winter, the absorption due to BrC dominates that of BC (64% of total absorption at 370 nm), significantly affected by the emission rates, meteorology, secondary aerosol formation and oxidation processes due to OH, O₃ (daytime) and NO₃ radicals (nighttime). Secondary BrC formation (BrC_{sec}) is highly

affected by RWB emissions during nighttime, while evidence for increased BrCsec absorption occurs under enhanced O₃ and low NO_x conditions around noon. In summer, the absorption characteristics differ notably, mostly driven by BC from fossil-fuel combustion and regional aerosols (Fig. 1). These characteristics also display distinct diurnal patterns and dependence on the emission source, aging and photo-bleaching processes. Furthermore, analysis of spectral absorptions at near-UV and visible spectrum (370 vs 660 nm) reveals notable differences between the seasons and hours of the day. During winter, the substantial coating of BC with BrC and inorganic species leads to absorption enhancement, especially at shorter wavelengths, and contributes to a curvature of spectral absorption evidenced by an increase in Ångström exponent (AAE) with decreasing wavelength. These effects are weak in summer due to the near absence of BrC from combustion sources and the photo-bleaching processes.

Figure 1. Mean diurnal patterns of PM_{2.5} concentrations in winter and summer color-coded with the total absorption at 370 nm. The insert graphs show the absorption/PM_{2.5} ratios, suggesting a mean diurnal pattern of the mass-absorption efficiency (MAE). The grey area corresponds to one stdev of the hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations.

CONCLUSIONS

During winter, high emissions from RWB controlled the atmospheric composition, with a BrC contribution to total absorption at 370 nm of 64%. The RWB effect maximized during winter nights, while reduced BC and BrC absorptions were observed during daytime. The spectral absorption characteristics were highly differentiated during summer due to the dominance of BC absorption, mostly related to regional sources and vehicle emissions during the morning traffic, while the BrC₃₇₀ absorption exhibited a fraction of only ~17%, mostly attributed to the absorption from secondary organic aerosols during daytime. Therefore, BC and BrC revealed different sources i.e. fossil-fuel combustion and SOA formation, respectively, which also exhibited different spectral absorption characteristics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.

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TEMPORAL CHANGES IN THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF PM_{2.5} FROM 2018-2024 IN DELHI NCR

ARKABANEE MUKHERJEE^{1*}, ATAR SINGH PIPAL¹, NAGESHWAR RAO¹, R LATHA¹, PRAMOD KORI¹, VIKASH KUMAR¹, HARDEEP SHARMA¹, SANDIP NIVDANGE², DAMODAR KARRI¹, NAVEEN GANDHI¹, AND SACHIN GHUDE¹

¹Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology Pune 411008, India

²Department of Environmental Science, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune 411016

KEYWORDS: GRAP, PM_{2.5}, Chemical Characterization, Metal Concentration

INTRODUCTION

Implementation of Graded Response Action Plan (GRAP) I, II, III, and IV for mitigation during high pollution days in Delhi NCR has been initiated since 2021 by the Commission of Air Quality Management (CAQM). Due to the stringency imposed by CAQM, the major contributor to high AQI PM_{2.5} has reduced significantly. A previous offline sampling campaign conducted at one of the prominent residential areas of Delhi for chemical characterization of PM_{2.5} and source apportionment study during January and February 2018 has already been published (Latha et al 2022). Another recent offline sampling campaign was conducted in 2024 during the same period and location. After the revocation of GRAP IV and III, GRAP I and II were implemented majorly during the sampling period. This comparative study focused on the temporal change of PM_{2.5} from winter 2018 (before GRAP implementation) to winter 2024 (during GRAP I and II) and its change in chemical constituents after these years.

METHOD

Offline sampling campaigns during both 2018 and 2024 were conducted in the Delhi IMD Lodhi Road campus. The Envirotech model low volume sampler (LVS) APM 550 was deployed in the field for PM_{2.5} sampling during both sampling periods. During 2018 the daily samples were collected for 13 hours which included PM deposition during meteorologically stable (02:00-09:00 hrs) and unstable (10:00-16:00 hrs) conditions. In 2024 the daily samples were collected in a 24-hour sampling mode. A detailed method of sample collection, preparation, and analysis was mentioned in the published paper of Latha et al. (2022). Metal concentrations (Cr, Ni, Mn, Cu, Pb, Zn) of all samples collected during 2018 and 2024 were analyzed using AAS (Analytik Jena made Contra 800) and ICPMS (Agilent-made) respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The stringency of GRAP I, II, III, and IV during poor to severe air quality index (AQI) since 2021 in Delhi NCR has significantly reduced the total PM load in the last few years. The details of GRAP classification are mentioned in table 1. In this comparative experimental observation, the maximum deposition of PM_{2.5} on filter paper during January and February was reported to be 357.19 and 292.14 µg/m³ in 2024 whereas; the same values were 480.62 µg/m³ and 356.14 µg/m³ in 2018 respectively (Fig 1). The monthly average values of PM_{2.5} depositions in the sampling campaign during January and February were 75% and 12%

GRAP IMPLEMENTATION	AQI RANGES	CATEGORY
GRAP I	200-301	Poor
GRAP II	301-400	Very Poor
GRAP III	401-450	Severe
GRAP IV	>450	Severe plus

Table 1 Classification of GRAP according to AQI.

higher in 2018 than in 2024 respectively. After considering the disparity of 13 hours and 24-hour sampling duration in 2018 and 2024, the actual reduction of total PM_{2.5} concentrations would be much higher than the reported values respectively.

Fig 1 Temporal change in the PM_{2.5} in Delhi NCR.

After understanding the metal components of the PM Interestingly, along with the reduction, concentration magnitudes of elements like Cr and Ni were observed with a significant increase of 1.93 and 2-fold during only January 2024 from 2018. The same values remain as high as 9.1- and 14.4-folds during February respectively. The monthly average concentration of Zn was also noticed to follow a similar trend, an increase of 23-fold from January 2018 to 2024 was observed in this case. This comparative study has indicated that despite a significant decline in the total PM_{2.5} concentrations from 2018 to 2024, the contribution of certain elemental loads has notably increased simultaneously. Another study by Gulia et al (2021) compared the impact of GRAP on 4 different locations in Delhi NCR and reported the efficiency of particulate reduction varies within locations as local activities play an important role. Hence, a detailed study on source identification and apportionment has become the need of the hour for precise policymaking.

CONCLUSION

The study showed a significant reduction in PM_{2.5} concentrations in winter (January and February) from 2018 to 2024 as an impact of implementing GRAP in Delhi NCR. However, changes in anthropogenic activities state increase in the heavy metal concentration acts as a potential threat to human health in case of long-term exposure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the Director, IITM, and Secretary, Ministry of Earth Sciences (Govt. of India) for their encouragement and support. This research was funded by MOES.

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CARBONATION OF SODIUM AEROSOL GENERATED BY SODIUM COMBUSTION WITH AMBIENT AND ZERO AIR

USHA PUJALA^{1,2}, R. ANANTHANARAYANAN^{3,2}, V. SUBRAMANIAN², AMIT KUMAR^{4,2}, A. JASMIN SUDHA^{4,2}, and M. SIVARAMA KRISHNA³

¹Health and Industrial Safety Division, ³Security and Innovative Sensors Division, ⁴Radiation Shielding and Aerosol Transport Studies Division, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research (IGCAR), Kalpakkam-603102, India.

²HBNI, Training School Complex, Anushaktinagar, Mumbai- 400094, India.

KEYWORDS: Sodium Aerosol, Combustion, Relative Humidity, Speciation

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of hazards associated with NaOH species of sodium compound aerosol during accidental sodium fire is critical for fast reactor safety. In a confined environment, the aerosol species are progressively converted from hydroxides to carbonates and bicarbonates with time for an initial concentration of 2 to 4 g/m³ (Ananthanarayanan et al., 2015). Open atmospheric sodium aerosol dispersion experiments observed that the aerosol samples at all downwind distances contained only bicarbonate. This may be due to the low particle concentrations (mg/m³) in the dispersed plume (or) conversion during aerosol sampling from the atmospheric air with abundant CO₂ and moisture (Subramanian et al., 2019). This study investigates the threshold aerosol concentration for instantaneous carbonation through closed chamber experiments.

METHODS

The estimated threshold sodium aerosol concentration derived from chemical kinetic equations for 410 ppm of ambient CO₂ level is 1.5 g/m³ for instantaneous carbonate conversion, and 0.75 g/m³ if parallel bicarbonate species formation is considered. With this basis, experiments are conducted inside a leak-tight 1 m³ aerosol test chamber (Figure 1). The aerosols generated in the combustion cell are simultaneously allowed to flow into the aerosol chamber soon after the liquid sodium ignition. The time-varying speciation is studied for two combustion conditions separately, using ambient air (with moisture 75±3% RH and 410 ppm CO₂) and zero air (moisture and CO₂ free), and in each, for 3 different initial RH conditions of the aerosol chamber about 23%, 47%, and 78%. In ambient air combustion, carbonation occurs considerably inside the combustion cell, and these species reach the test chamber. Only oxides are formed in zero air combustion, and the carbonation starts once the aerosol reaches the test chamber conditioned with ambient air. Filter paper (FP) sampling is used to collect the aerosol samples from the test chamber at different instants up to 1300 s to analyse the chemical speciation. Each FP sample is immersed in a separate deionized demineralised water matrix immediately after the sampling and analysed for the speciation of NaOH, Na₂CO₃ and NaHCO₃ within 4 hours after sampling using a high-resolution pulsating conductometric titration technique (Ananthanarayanan et al., 2015). Gas analyser & Air velocity meter are used to monitor the aerosol chamber's CO₂, RH, and temperature levels (Figure 1).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The list of experimental conditions is given in Table 1. The variation of sodium aerosol speciation with time is presented in Figure 2 for ambient and zero conditions at 23% RH only.

The speciation during generation (-ve time) is the combination of carbonate and bicarbonate, with bicarbonate dominant. After the generation of a specified total concentration, the speciation is the combination of carbonate and bicarbonate, with carbonate being dominant. Overall, the carbonate is converted to bicarbonates in all three RH cases in both combustion conditions. Except at 23% RH, ambient combustion condition with 1.1 g/m³, the aerosol species are a combination of carbonates and bicarbonates all the time, and NaOH species are entirely absent (Figure 2). The aerosol species does not have NaOH in zero air combustion conditions at 23% RH, with 0.75 g/m³.

Figure 1. Schematic of test

Figure 2. Chemical speciation at 23% RH in ambient (left) and zero air combustion conditions (right).

The CO₂ and moisture consumptions are faster with an increase in RH condition for the given aerosol concentration, due to the rapid diffusion of CO₂ and moisture into the liquid state of particles, and faster conversion to carbonate and bicarbonate (Palntamp et al., 2016). The estimated cumulative CO₂ consumed within the total time from the chemical analysis, is compared with measured CO₂ from the analyser, presented in Table 1). The measured and estimated CO₂ consumption levels agree and support the measured speciation within 5 to 15%, except at 23% RH with ambient air combustion. At 23% RH, 1.1 g/m³, the large deviation is due to additional uncertainty in un-identifying small quantities of NaOH, which may present in FP samples but could convert when transferred to DI water in the presence of dissolved CO₂.

RH (%)	Concentration (g/m ³)	Time of last sampling (s)	Estimated CO ₂ (ppm)	Measured CO ₂ (ppm)	% deviation
Ambient air combustion					
78±2	1.1±0.2	1220	320	360±18	13.5
47±2	1.1±0.2	1215	327	284±14	15.1
23±2	1.1±0.2	1340	316	187±9	63.0
Zero air combustion					
78±2	1.5±0.2	1200	361	333±17	8.5
47±2	0.81±0.1	1250	305	323±16	5.6
23±2	0.75±0.1	1200	172	187±9	8.0

Table 1. Measured and estimated total CO₂ consumption by sodium aerosol inside the aerosol chamber.

CONCLUSIONS

At 78% RH, the carbonation is instantaneous, bicarbonate formation is faster, and the threshold conc. is of 1-1.5 g/m³. At 47% RH, the carbonation is instantaneous, but bicarbonate formation is comparatively slower, and the threshold conc. is of 1 g/m³. At 23% RH, the carbonation and bicarbonate formations are much slower, and the threshold conc. is of 0.75 g/m³. The aerosol concentration below this threshold gets rapidly converted to

NaHCO₃ due to abundant CO₂ and moisture levels as observed in an open atmosphere.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors sincerely thank former Director IGCAR, Director EIG, Director RDG, AD SQRMG, AD EPG, Head HISD, Head HPS for supporting the work; team of SISD, in the chemical analysis of the samples.

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ROLE OF AEROSOL PH AND LIQUID WATER CONTENT ON GAS-PARTICLE PARTITIONING AND DEPOSITION OF TOTAL NITRATE AND AMMONIA

SWATI JOSHI¹, CHANDRIMA SHAW², NEERAJ RASTOGI², ATINDERPAL SINGH¹

¹Department of Environmental Studies, University of Delhi, Delhi 110 007, India

²Geosciences Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad 380 009, India

KEYWORDS: Inorganic Ions, ISOROPIA-II, Sensitivity Regime, ALWC

INTRODUCTION

Fine-mode aerosols, particularly those containing inorganic nitrate and ammonium, play a significant role in atmospheric chemistry and air quality (Gupta et al., 2023). The interaction between aerosol liquid water content (ALWC) and pH is critical in determining the partitioning of these species between the gas and particulate phases (Nenes et al., 2020). Gas-particle partitioning also influences the depositional velocity of these reactive nitrogen species (Nr) since gas-phase species typically have different atmospheric residence times than those in the particle phase. As a result, this difference in depositional velocity, controlled by aerosol pH and ALWC, significantly influences the atmospheric residence time of Nr. The current research focuses on applying the framework developed by Nenes et al. (2020) to real-time measurements in the Delhi region. This application aims to identify the chemical domains where aerosol particulate matter is sensitive to NH₃ and HNO₃ availability, specifically regarding aerosol pH and ALWC. This knowledge is crucial to understanding the behaviour of secondary inorganic aerosols under different environmental conditions, thereby suggesting strategies to mitigate pollution in a particular area.

METHODS

The measurements were carried out at the Department of Environmental Studies, University of Delhi (28.68° N, 77.21° E), New Delhi, India, from August 18, 2023, to December 14, 2023. The extensive data for fine mode aerosols (PM_{2.5}) used in this study is from the hourly measurements of inorganic ions (NH₄⁺, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, K⁺, NO₃⁻) and trace gases (SO₂, HCl, HONO, HNO₃, NH₃) from 2060 Monitor for Aerosols and Gases in Ambient Air (MARGA-R, Metrohm) instrument installed inside an ambient air quality monitoring van stationed at one of arterial road outside the department. The following meteorological parameters were obtained from MERRA2 Native Resolution Hourly Data: temperature (T), relative humidity (RH), wind speed (ws), and wind direction (wd). Further thermodynamic model ISOROPIA-II was utilized to estimate the ALWC and pH.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

For the purpose of estimating pH and ALWC, the thermodynamic equilibrium model ISOROPIA-II (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007) was run in forward mode with gas and particulate phase as inputs along with T and RH. Daily average pH during the study period ranged from (4.1 ± 0.74), whereas ALWC ranged from (8.86 ± 11.0 µg/m³). The present study showed that the pH and ALWC condition during the study period favoured the gas-particle partitioning between HNO₃-pNO₃⁻. Therefore, the change in PM mass concentration was highly sensitive to the formation of NO₃⁻ rather than the formation of NH₄⁺. This means NH₄⁺ mostly resided in its gaseous counterpart (NH₃), and the opposite is true for NO₃⁻.

Moreover, the depositional velocity and residence time of these reactive nitrogen species (total gas and particulate phase of nitrate and ammonia respectively) depend on their phase, with the gas phase having higher depositional velocity.

Gases generally have higher depositional velocities than aerosols due to their smaller size and higher diffusivity. In this study, NH_3 to NH_4^+ partitioning was not favoured, so NH_x ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4^+$) likely had a faster depositional velocity. Conversely, HNO_3 - NO_3^- partitioning was favoured, resulting in slower deposition. Fast deposition suggests a regional source, while slower deposition indicates more localized sources, which is crucial for source apportionment and effective mitigation strategies.

Fig.1: Showing pH Vs ALWC for the study site. The blue zone denotes where change in PM mass concentration is sensitive to gas-particle partitioning in nitrate, the orange zone denotes the NH_3 sensitive zone, and the purple area is where PM mass concentration change corresponds to both NH_3 and HNO_3 partitioning. The white zone is where change doesn't depend on HNO_3 and NH_3 partitioning. Deposition (fast or slow) is also marked to correspond to the different zones by the black arrow.

CONCLUSIONS

The implication for this depositional pattern during the study period is that, the total NH_3 preferred to remain near the region of its source. Total NO_3^- , on the other hand, could build up and participate in long-range transport depending upon other parameters that control its transport and deposition.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to IoE, FRP and University of Delhi for providing logistic and financial support during the study. UGC-India is gratefully acknowledged for the financial assistance in the form of a non-NET fellowship.

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CHARACTERISTICS AND TRENDS IN AEROSOL PROPERTIES OVER A TOURIST CITY IN WESTERN INDIA

V.K. DHAKER AND T. A. RAJESH

Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad, Gujarat - 380009, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Optical Depth, Trends, Black Carbon, Dust, Sea Salt.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols have a significant impact on the Earth's energy balance, climate, and hydrological cycle by scattering and absorbing the incoming solar radiation (IPCC, 2021). Aerosols adversely affect human health and air quality (IPCC, 2021). They are produced in the atmosphere through anthropogenic and natural sources. One of the important aerosol optical parameters used in radiative transfer models to investigate their climatic impact is the aerosol optical depth (AOD). AOD is the measure of aerosols distributed within a column of air from the Earth's surface to the top of the atmosphere in a finite field of view. The contributions of various aerosols to AOD are complex; thus, quantitative analysis of columnar aerosols is challenging. In the present study, we have investigated the characteristics and trends of total and various aerosol species AOD using the MERRA-2 aerosol products for the period 2000 to 2023 over a tourist city in Western India.

STUDY REGION, DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The study location, Udaipur (24.36°N, 73.40°E, 595 m AMSL), is an urban city of Rajasthan in the Aravalli ranges of Western India. Udaipur city has a population of more than 0.6 million (<https://censusindia.gov.in>). Udaipur is a tourist destination famous for its natural lakes, which play a crucial role in its ecosystem and tourism industry. We have utilized the data from MERRA-2 (Modern Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, version 2). It has a native resolution of 0.5° (latitude) x 0.625° (longitude) at 72 pressure levels. MERRA-2 simulates five aerosol species: sulfate, sea salt, organic carbon (OC), dust, and black carbon (BC) aerosols. We have used MERRA-2 averaged monthly data M2TMNXAER v5.12.4 at 550 nm from Jan 2000 to Dec 2023 over Udaipur. We have not considered the AOD data corresponding to the year 2020, as 2020 was a COVID-19 pandemic effect. The trends in the total and species AOD are estimated following the weighted least squares fitting method. In the weighted least squares fitting method, a weight factor ($1/\sigma^2$, where σ is uncertainty) is assigned to AODs, which gives lower weight to AODs with higher uncertainty, and vice versa. The annual mean trends in AOD are expressed in terms of percentage change and are calculated as $((\text{Slope between year and AOD} \times 23) / (\text{AOD in the year 2000})) \times 100$. The annual mean trends obtained in the study have p-values < 0.05 , and the confidence level in the trends is $>95\%$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The species-wise (sulfate, sea salt, OC, dust, and BC) AOD contributions were obtained from MERRA in order to provide an estimate of the chemical composition of aerosols over Udaipur (Figure 1a). The dust and sulfate AOD contribute significantly to the total AOD throughout the year and are found to be maximum during May (67%) and Dec (51%), respectively (Figure 1a). The transport of wind from the Thar Desert and Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP) brings in more dust and sulfate particles to the study location, respectively, during those

months. The sea salt AOD contributes significantly during the monsoon (Jun - Sep) as the winds are from the Arabian Sea (Figure 1a). The OC and BC AODs are found to be maximum during Nov (24%) and Dec (12%), respectively, attributed to low surface wind speed, and the winds are from the IGP region, which brings more absorbing type aerosols (Figure 1a). The annual average percentage contribution of dust AOD is maximum (40%) to the total AOD, followed by sulfate (33%), OC (11%), sea salt (10%), and BC (5%). The long-term trends analysis shows that sulfate, OC, and BC AODs have increased by 38%, 49%, 39%, and 26% during the period 2000-2023 over Udaipur (Figure 1). On the contrary, the annual average trends in sea salt and dust AODs show a decrease of 13% and 3%, respectively, although these are not statistically significant (Figure 1). The observed increase in anthropogenic AODs can be ascribed to the increase in urbanization, which is attributed to an increase in the amount of aerosols from fossil fuel and biomass burning. These findings become important and useful in the context of regional and global climate change due to aerosols.

Figure 1. (a) Monthly percentage contributions of sulfate, sea salt, organic carbon (OC), dust, and black carbon (BC) AOD to the total AOD. Annual mean trends in (b) total, (c) sulfate, (d) sea salt, (e) organic carbon (OC), (f) dust, and (g) black carbon (BC) AOD over Udaipur from MERRA-2 for the period 2000 to 2023 at 550 nm. Vertical bars represent $\pm 1\sigma$ deviation from the mean. Dashed red lines represent the trends that are obtained by weighing the annual mean AODs with their intra-annual variations.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The mean percentage of species-wise AOD contribution from MERRA-2 shows that dust-type and sulfate aerosols are the most common over Udaipur. Annual mean trends in total, sulfate, sea salt, OC, dust, and BC AOD were also examined using monthly averaged MERRA-2 data. Annual mean total, sulfate, OC, and BC AODs exhibit statistically significant increasing trends of 38%, 49%, 39%, and 26%, respectively, whereas the annual average trends in sea

salt and dust AODs show a decreasing trend of 13% and 3%, respectively, during the period 2000-2023. The increase in AOD can be attributed to the increase in urbanization, which attributes to an increase in the number of aerosols from fossil fuel and biomass burning. Results on the long-term interannual variability in aerosol properties will be useful in modeling the radiative effects of aerosols and for the assessment of their role on regional climate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge MERRA-2 for the production of model data and maintaining the website.

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EVALUATION OF LONG-TERM BLACK CARBON CHARACTERISTICS OVER THE NORTHERN INDIAN OCEAN

SHYAMLI K. SINGH^{1,2}, SHANI TIWARI*^{1,2}

¹Aerosol and Cloud Research Lab, Geological Oceanography Division, CSIR–National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, India

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, India.

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Northern Indian Ocean, Merra-2

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) is one of the most critical pollutants and mainly produced during the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biofuels, and biomass (Bond et al. 2013). The substantial increase in human activities over recent decades has led to a significant build-up of BC in the environment, which directly or indirectly impacts global climate change and aquatic ecosystems. India has witnessed a large BC emission (388 – 1344 Gg yr⁻¹) mainly because of the rapid urbanization, economic development and associated energy demands which led to an overall increasing trend in BC (Kant et al., 2020). A large amount of BC emitted from the Indian landmass is transported to the adjacent oceans (i.e. Arabian Sea: AS and Bay of Bengal: BoB) through long range transportation. Recent studies have also highlights the role of long-range transportation and atmospheric circulation in BC deposition in oceanic region (Budhavant et al., 2023; Tiwari et al., 2020). In recent years, BC characteristics over the Indian Ocean have been mainly examined through short-term, campaign-based studies like Indian Ocean Experiment (INDOEX) and Integrated Campaign for Aerosols, gases, and Radiation Budget (ICARB) etc. However, there is a significant lack of long-term research on BC characteristics in this region. Therefore, current study focuses on a comprehensive long-term analysis of BC characteristics over the Indian Ocean.

STUDY REGION, DATASET AND METHODOLOGY

The study area mostly covers the Northern Indian Ocean area, extending from 0° to 30°N latitude and from 60°E to 100°E longitude. The Indian subcontinent divides this area into two distinct basins i.e. AS and BoB which are further divided into five regions (viz. R1, R2, R3, R4, and R5) based on long term BC surface mass concentration climatology. Long term (i.e. 43 years, 1980 to 2022) MERRA-2 monthly mean BC surface mass concentration (M2TMNXAER v5.12.4) has been analysed. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model was used for trend analysis (Hess et al. 2001) and given below.

$$Y_j = \alpha + \beta*j + \epsilon_j,$$

Y_j is the response for year j and $1 \leq j \leq n$, so j represents the year with the initial year taken as year 1, α = intercept, β = slope, and ϵ_j = random errors. The specified OLS model was fitted to the data using Python's Statsmodels library, which calculated the trend coefficients (intercept and slope). In addition, EDGAR emission inventory dataset is also used to investigate the historical BC emission trend over Indian region. Five days' air mass back trajectories are also computed using HYSPLIT model to investigate the transport pathways

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A large variability in spatial distribution of atmospheric BC is found over the entire NIO where all regions i.e. R1 – R5 exhibited a pronounced BC increasing trend during the 1990s to 2000s, with certain regions experiencing accelerated growth. However, in the last decade, these trends have largely stabilised or shown a slight decline, particularly in regions R1 and R3. The spatial distribution of annual-averaged BC mass concentration in the NIO shows a higher trend over BoB than AS. The observed BC trend is well correlated with EDGAR inventory derived BC emission over Indian landmass region and air mass back trajectories derived transport pathways of BC (figure not shown here).

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of long-term mean (1980-2022) concentration BC concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and annual trend for sub-regions for four different decades.

CONCLUSIONS

The sudden increase in the BC concentration after the 1990s for all the regions could be linked with the increase in the BC emissions pertaining to the industrial boom that followed India's New Economic Policy (NEP) 1991.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, and the University Grant Commission. We acknowledge the MERRA-2 reanalysis science team for the dataset used in this study.

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AEROSOL SCIENCE RESEARCH: PRESENT STATUS AND FUTURE SCOPE IN INDIA

PANUGANTI C.S. DEVARA

Centre of Excellence in Ocean-Atmospheric Science and Technology (ACOAST) / Environmental Science and Health (ACESH) / Air Pollution Control (ACAPC), Amity University Haryana (AUH), Gurugram, 122413, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Physico-Chemistry, Clouds, Radiative Forcing, Health Exposure and Climate Sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols can be natural or anthropogenic, and some human-produced aerosols are considered pollutants. Thus, aerosols are a part of air pollution and are dangerous to human health. Moreover, aerosols are small particles but with big climate effects. Aerosol was first invented by Erik Rotheim, a Norwegian chemical engineer in 1927. Since then, numerous investigators over the globe have studied its several aspects through laboratory and field experiments, models and satellites. In recent times, numerous researchers in India have also contributed to the field of ‘Aerosol Science and Technology’, employing a variety of low-cost portable for easy networking to complex giant instruments over different sites associated with varied environmental and meteorological conditions. Most of these studies involve surface-level and columnar aerosol features, and vertical profile measurements at very limited stations from both ground-based and spaceborne platforms. Some Organizations in India have also contributed to the long-term trends and variability while some have studied the aerosol behaviour during episodic situations. However, the present status of aerosol pollution is not clear in terms of their intrinsic characteristics, underlying transport mechanisms and influence on earth-atmosphere radiation balance through various natural and anthropogenic activities. The present article begins with a brief review of the study of aerosol characteristics over a rural (pristine) site, Panchgaon, Haryana for the past one decade, and ends with a brief discussion on the status of aerosol research and gap areas despite their research commenced in India in 1950s through various programs and initiatives.

SOME GLIMPSES OF AEROSOL RESEARCH AT AMITY UNIVERSITY, HARYANA

The aerosol science research at Amity University Haryana (AUH), situated in a rural environment, surrounded by Aravali hillocks, began with the formation of a Centre of Excellence in Ocean-Atmospheric Science and Technology (ACOAST) in 2014. Almost at the beginning of 2015, this centre established its activity by launching major collaborations with IITM, Pune and ARIES, Nainital, and thereafter, it enhanced the activity by launching various National and International Cooperative Research Programs. The first frame in the alongside figure, namely, Climate Research Laboratory (CRL) was established at AUH in 2015 in collaboration with IITM, Pune and ARIES, Nainital. At present, AUH has been continuously operating

synchronous 22-parameter Air Quality Monitoring and diagnosis System (AQMS) and AE-33 Aethalometer, in close collaboration with IITM, Pune, MoES, GoI, India; and NASA-AERONET Sun-Sky-Moon-Polarimetric Multi-spectral Radiometer, Low-cost MAIA-AMOD, Clarity Node-S and SAMOSA sensors. Several studies have been carried out during quiescent/pristine and episodic situations such as COVID-19, Dust Storms, Festive/Celebration periods etc, and results have been published, time-to-time, in different journals (for example, Devara, 2017; 2018; Devara et al., 2017; 2024; Sonbawne et al., 2021).

PRESENT STATUS AND GAP AREAS

Aerosols are present everywhere in the Universe. They affect air quality, clouds, precipitation, earth-atmosphere radiation balance and climate. Of these, the interaction/coupling processes between aerosols, clouds, and climate are one of the important and complex problems in Aerosol Science. Another problem is Gas-to-Particle Conversion (GPC). Water vapor plays a critical role in these connections, depending on the aerosol phase (hygroscopic or hydrophobic). Transport and Industries are the two critical anthropogenic sources besides natural ones such as dust storms and volcanic eruptions. Climatologically two critical pollutants, namely, nitrates (warm) and sulphates (cool) the atmosphere. It should be remembered in this context that satellites provide large-scale, multi-dimensional mapping of pollutants. However, satellite observations need validation and calibration with ground-based and in-situ measurements.

OBSERVATIONS AND MODELS

We know that both observations and models should go together because observations serve as the calibration / validation checks of models while the models guide the observation schemes. Although the aerosol observational data is very rich in India, the modelling activities are relatively low. This may be due to input information on a large number of missing parameters, inadequate accuracy, lack of information on interactions, types, transport characteristics and influence of meteorology. Recently, by using long-term aerosol data inventories in conjunction with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) modelling techniques, pollution forecast studies have been published. The results warrant the simultaneous development of mitigation methods to make these results more realistic.

RESEARCH GAPS AND WAY FORWARD

Characterization of Bioaerosols and their role in Environment and Human Health * Cloud-Aerosol-Climate Interactions under extreme weather conditions * Gas-to-Particle Conversion (GPC) Processes vis-à-vis Water Vapor, * Stubble-Burning activities and their implications on Energy and Health Budgets * Pollution-induced Wave Energy Activity * Linkages between surface and columnar aerosols and gases * Science and Technology for Sustainability Development * Modelling of Aerosols and Clouds for climate * Long-term Trends, Data inventories * Application of Modern Analysis Techniques for Aerosol pollution forecast * Association between indoor and outdoor pollution and its composite effect on ambient air quality * Impact of surface-level BC concentration on stratospheric ozone under favorable transport conditions * Develop methods to isolate the background , particularly the effect due to long-lived gases, committed versus fresh emissions.

CONCLUSIONS

The present communication explains typical rural aerosol properties, representing background

levels that can be useful to estimate the changes in aerosol levels during episodic situations. Such data would also be useful for accurate model estimations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was carried out at AUH, founded by Dr. Ashok K Chauhan, Ritnand Balved Education Foundation & Chairman, Amity Science, Technology & Innovation Foundation (ASTIF); IITM, Pune, Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES), Government of India, New Delhi; NASA-AERONET, GSFC, MD, USA; Emory University, Georgia Tech., USA; Univ. of California, USA; and ACOEM, Australia.

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INSIGHTS INTO THE MAJOR SOURCES OF NO_x AND FORMATION PATHWAYS OF PARTICULATE NO₃⁻ USING DUAL ISOTOPE PROXY

CHANDRIMA SHAW^{1,2}, RITWICK MANDAL³, ATINDERPAL SINGH⁴, PRASANTA SANYAL³, NEERAJ RASTOGI¹, *

¹ Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad 380009, India

² Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar, Gujarat 382355, India

³ Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Kolkata, Mohanpur 741246, India

⁴ Punjabi University, Patiala, 147002, India (presently at University of Delhi)

KEYWORDS: IGP, Dual Isotope, Nitrate formation pathways.

INTRODUCTION

Nitrate is an important component of particulate matter in the atmosphere. It has significant implications for air quality, climate, and human health, and rapid accumulation of which can increase PM load by aiding in secondary aerosol formations. Particulate nitrate also participates in haze formations, influences radiative forcing, and has a direct effect on ecosystems in the form of nutrients (Li et al., 2018). In the atmosphere, particulate nitrate is primarily formed through the transformation of NO_x via four distinct pathways: (P1) the oxidation of NO₂ by OH (NO₂ + OH) in the gas phase, (P2) the hydrolysis of N₂O₅ on existing aerosols (N₂O₅ + H₂O, and N₂O₅ + Cl⁻, a heterogeneous process), (P3) the reaction between NO₃ radicals and VOCs and (P4) reaction of NO₃ radical and ClO. The latter two mechanisms predominantly occur at night and are thus referred to as 'nocturnal chemistry'. However, studies on the sources and formation pathways of particulate nitrate from its precursor gas NO_x are limited pertaining to the globe as well as the Indian subcontinent. Dual isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of particulate nitrate are excellent tools for understanding the formation mechanism and sources of nitrate (thus NO_x) in the atmosphere. In this work, we have utilised the stable isotopic signature of nitrate in PM_{2.5} to understand its sources and formation pathways in the northwest Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) during a large-scale paddy-residue burning period. Furthermore, diurnal variations in formation pathways and sources of nitrate are also explored.

METHODS

Diurnal samples of PM_{2.5} were collected from 11 October to 16 November on the terrace of the Department of Physics at Punjabi University, Patiala. Samples were analysed water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC), total water-soluble nitrogen (WSTN), elemental carbon (EC), organic carbon (OC), and inorganic anions. Stable isotopic analysis ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of nitrate was done following the Titanium Chloride one step reduction method (Altabet et al., 2019). Estimation of different formation pathways was done following methods described by Walter et al. (2015). A stable Isotope Mixing Model (MixSIAR) was utilised for source apportionment of NO_x thus nitrate over the study area.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NO₃⁻ of samples was 57.2 ± 8 ‰ was -1.9 ± 5 ‰. The major pathways contributing to the formation of NO₃⁻ was OH (~ 92%) followed by N₂O₅ (~ 5%), whereas, P3 and P4 contributed ~ 1.3 and ~ 1.5% only. NO₃⁻ formed via the OH pathway was the dominant pathway during both day and night. This could be because the sampling duration

(8-10 hours) is much less than the average life-time of particulate nitrate (a few days). Further, the contribution of the N₂O₅ pathway is significantly high ($p < 0.05$) during the night. This is expected since during night in the absence of sunlight photochemically mediated processes (OH-pathway) to cease and heterogenous hydrolysis becomes dominant. Source apportionment using MixSIAR shows no significant difference in source contribution between day and night. Furthermore, biomass burning and traffic exhaust were the major contributors to NO_x followed by combustion and soil emissions during the study period (Figure. 1).

Figure:1 Major sources of NO_x during day and night based on the MixSIAR model.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study, the first of its kind over India, investigates the sources and formation pathways of particulate nitrate over the northwest Indo-Gangetic Plain during a biomass burning episode, and found traffic emissions and biomass burning as the major sources followed by coal combustion and soil emissions. Further, particulate NO₃⁻ formed through the OH pathway is found to be a major fraction of total NO₃⁻ observed during day and night over the study region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Physical Research Laboratory, Department of Space, Govt. of India.

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THE EFFECT OF FOG PROCESSING ON AEROSOLS' OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL IN THE ITALIAN PO VALLEY: FAIRARI 2021/22

ANIL PATEL^{1,2,¥}, M. PAGLIONE³, A. NEUBERGER^{1,2}, F. MATTSSON^{1,2}, Y. GRAMLICH^{1,2}, D. HADDEN^{1,2}, S. L. HASLETT^{1,2}, M. RINALDI³, C. MOHR^{1,2}, \$, I. RIIPINEN^{1,2}, P. ZIEGER^{1,2}, S. DECESARI³ AND S. S. STEIMER¹

¹Department of Environmental Science, Stockholm University, Stockholm, 114 18, Sweden

²Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm, 114 18, Sweden

³Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council, Bologna, Italy

¥Now at: Bagchi School of Public Health, Ahmedabad University, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad

\$ Laboratory of Atmospheric Chemistry, Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen PSI, Switzerland

KEYWORDS: Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS), DTT, Fog-Scavenging

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosol can catalytically generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the nasal airway, depleting the antioxidant pool (Li et al., 2003). This potency of aerosols is known as its oxidative potential (OP). Numerous studies have shown that elevated OP can cause cellular damage through oxidative stress, contributing to various cardiopulmonary diseases. Particulate matter (PM) emitted from various processes and sources often differ in size distribution and chemical composition, leading to variations in OP. Atmospheric transport and aging further alter PM's properties by enriching secondary species through oxidation, particularly in forming secondary organic aerosols (SOA) (Pöschl & Shiraiwa, 2015). The OP of aged PM can vary based on SOA formation pathways, e.g., aqueous-phase vs. non-aqueous-phase reactions. Recent studies conducted in the Po Valley, Italy (Decesari et al., 2017) and the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), India (Patel and Rastogi, 2018) observed an increase in PM's OP due to fog processing, where aqueous-phase SOA formation could have played a critical role. Although fog formation serves as a removal mechanism for reactive fine PM, additional SOA formed within fog droplets could be more redox-active, which may pose a heightened health risk when the fog dissipates. However, specific SOA species formed during fog events remain speculative in these studies, requiring further investigation to mitigate potential toxicity in polluted regions.

STUDY SITE & METHODS

The Po Valley, Europe's most polluted region (Daellenbach et al. 2020), is home to around 16 million people, approximately one-third of Italy's population. With its unique orography, the Po Valley creates conditions that facilitate the accumulation of PM during winter. Atmospheric aging processes oxidize these particles, increasing their hygroscopicity – a phenomenon intensified by fog formation even at lower relative humidity ($\leq 100\%$). So, it presents an ideal setting to study the influence of fog processing on PM's toxicity. The campaign, FAIRARI (Fog and Aerosol InterAction Research Italy), was set up in San Pietro Capofiume, Italy, during the winter of 2021/22 (Neuberger et al., 2024, under review). This was a joint effort between Stockholm University and CNR-ISAC in Bologna. Several PM1 and PM10 samples were collected before, during, and after fog events using different samplers (DIGITEL for PM1 and LECKEL for PM10). In addition, an automated computer-controlled active string collector was used for fog water sampling. This approach enabled an in-depth analysis of the changes in particle size distribution, chemical composition, and OP within fog droplets. The collected samples were analyzed for mass concentration and

chemical composition. The consumption rate of Dithiothreitol (DTT) (nmol DTT/min) was measured at physiological conditions in the presence of PM, also termed OP. The OP exposure/dose has been estimated by normalizing OP with sampled air volume (i.e., OPV), and the particles' intrinsic OP has been represented as mass-normalized OP (OPM).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

There were six episodes encountered in which we gathered information on the fog-processing of aerosols' OP. On average, PM1-OPV during non-foggy days and nights occupied ~ 52% of PM10-OPV, meaning that OP was also governed significantly by coarser particles ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$). PM1 mass concentration and its OP have significantly been observed to be influenced by fog formation. A reduced PM1 mass and OPV during a foggy night (interstitial part) compared to its prior clear day for all the episodes suggests the possibility of fog scavenging (Gilardoni et al., 2014) and/or that the PM1 might have grown to a coarser size ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$) as a condensation process. In the latter case, the particles that grew coarser during foggy nights could become a part of PM10, which was not investigated in this study. The particles' scavenging can occur based on their size and composition. This could be the reason behind the observed difference in the magnitude of PM1 mass and OPV during fog in contrast to a clear night. The fog water OPV was also significant, which could be this scavenged part of PM1. The composition governs OPM. So, the water-soluble organic matter (WSOM, likely redox-active) and secondary inorganic aerosol (SIA, redox-inactive) ratio could provide valuable information on particles' reactivity. A clear day following a foggy night was associated with an enhanced WSOM/SIA ratio and OPM compared to its previous clear day, which could mean that fog processing makes the particles more reactive and, thus, enhances OPM. However, OPV showed an opposite trend, which is under investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

OP was observed to be governed significantly by both fine ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) as well as coarser particles ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$). Reduced PM1 mass and OPV during foggy nights compared to prior clear days hints towards fog scavenging or condensational growth of PM1. The results of this study will contribute to the development of strategies to mitigate the health impacts of air pollution in the Po Valley.

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INTER-ANNUAL VARIABILITY IN SOURCES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS USING DUAL CARBON ISOTOPES OVER A MEGA CITY IN EASTERN INDIA

M. DEVAPRASAD¹, N. RASTOGI¹, *, S. K. DAS², P. S. JENA¹, A. DHABI¹, R. BHUSHAN¹

¹Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad-380009, India.

²Environmental Sciences Section, Bose Institute, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosols; $\Delta^{13}C$; Radiocarbon; Source Apportionment

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization in many regions has led to a significant rise in air pollution worldwide. Among the various pollutants, carbonaceous aerosols (CA) are a major component, emitted predominantly from the incomplete combustion of biomass and fossil fuels. Studying CA is crucial due to its wide-ranging effects on human health, Earth's radiation budget, the hydrological cycle, and ocean biogeochemistry (Andreae and Crutzen, 1997; Bond et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2020). This study focuses on Kolkata, a highly populated and fast-growing urban city in India that frequently receives transported pollutants from the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) during winter. Sampling was conducted across two consecutive years, covering the post-monsoon, winter, and spring seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22. The study involved chemical (organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), water-soluble OC, and organic speciation using HR-ToF-AMS) and isotopic (^{13}C and ^{14}C) analyses of the filter based PM_{2.5} samples, with key results are discussed below

METHODS

Twenty-four-hour averaged PM_{2.5} samples were collected (Using a High-Volume sampler) from the rooftop (~20 meters above ground) of a multi-story building at Bose Institute's Shyamnagar Campus in Kolkata. Sampling occurred between November 6, 2020, and March 16, 2021 (n = 40), and from October 22, 2021, to April 4, 2022 (n = 30). Sampling periods were classified as post-monsoon (October-November), winter (December-January), and spring (February-April), based on wind direction and daily temperatures. Concentrations of EC and OC were measured using an EC-OC analyzer, WSOC via a TOC-TN analyzer, major ions using ion chromatography, organic speciation through HR-ToF-AMS, and carbon isotopes through an isotope ratio mass spectrometer and accelerator mass spectrometer. Radiocarbon in total carbon (TC) was expressed as fbio_TC, with fbio_TC = 1 representing 100% biomass/biogenic source and fbio_TC = 0 indicating completely fossil sources.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM_{2.5} concentrations and other chemical species such as OC, WSOC, and water-soluble inorganic species (WSIS) were significantly higher during 2020-21 compared to 2021-22. PM_{2.5} concentrations were 176 ± 45 , 207 ± 27 , and 190 ± 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during post-monsoon, winter, and spring of 2020-21, respectively, compared to 134 ± 42 , 147 ± 42 , and 103 ± 32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2021-22. These reductions are attributed to factors like increased precipitation, Cyclone Jawad (Chakraborty et al., 2023), and delayed crop residue burning in the IGP (Govardhan et al., 2023) due to government restrictions on the usage of ground water in the Punjab and Haryana regions. While PM_{2.5} concentrations varied seasonally and annually,

OC, WSOC, and WSIS followed similar trends, implying common sources of emissions and meteorological influences. Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) was the dominant WSIS, aligning with prior findings in Kolkata. Analysis of chemical species ratios like OC/EC, WSOC/OC, and nss-K+/EC indicated reduced biomass burning (BB) in 2021-22. The OC-EC regression slope decreased from 10 in 2020-21 to 7.3 in 2021-22, reinforcing the decline in BB aerosols. The WSOC/OC ratio, AMS derived f44 showed relatively lower values indicating transported aerosol signatures are not seen in this study. Radiocarbon-derived fbio_TC (Figure 1) values ranged from 0.73 ± 0.03 in the post-monsoon, 0.70 ± 0.02 in winter, and 0.66 ± 0.02 in spring during 2020-21, showing a decline in 2021-22, where corresponding values were 0.71 ± 0.02 , 0.67 ± 0.02 , and 0.63 ± 0.02 . This decline was further supported by lower nss-K+/EC ratios and OC/EC slopes. However, no significant changes were observed in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, indicating either overlapping source signatures or alterations due to atmospheric processing. The reduction in fbio_TC could be attributed to the removal of BB-dominated transported aerosols by precipitation.

Figure 1: Time series of fbio_TC during post-monsoon, winter and spring seasons of the year 2020-21 and 2021-22

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study highlights significant seasonal and annual variations in PM_{2.5} and carbonaceous aerosol components over Kolkata, influenced by meteorological factors and emission sources such as biomass burning. A substantial reduction in PM_{2.5} concentrations, OC/EC ratios, and fbio_TC between 2020-21 and 2021-22 reflects the impact of weather patterns like increased precipitation and policy measures limiting crop residue burning. These findings underscore the importance of continued monitoring and targeted mitigation efforts to reduce air pollution in urban areas.

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VARIABILITY OF AIR POLLUTION AND HEAT STRESS OVER KOLKATA

¹MANU MEHTA, ²SHIVANI, ²SOMYA GARG

¹Indian Institute of Remote Sensing, e-mail: manu@iirs.gov.in

²Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Kashmere Gate, New Delhi, India

KEYWORDS: PM2.5, PM10, NOX, WBGT, KOLKATA

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution poses a significant global environmental threat, primarily due to its detrimental impacts on public health and its contribution to climate change [Poschl 2005]. One of the major threats posed by air pollution could be linked with the rising global temperatures. India has experienced steadily rising temperatures, with frequent heat waves, particularly in northern and central regions, causing widespread environmental and health impacts. It has been found in previous studies that there can be a linkage between air pollutants and heat stress (Dey et al., 2021 and Ajay et al. 2023). Kolkata, as the economic growth center of eastern India, faces significant challenges due to its high levels of air pollution. Health Effects Institute (HEI) reported that Kolkata is the second most polluted city in the world in terms of PM2.5 (Global Air Report 2022 and 2023). This study aims to assess the diurnal variability of air pollutants (PM2.5, PM10, ozone, SO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, NO_x, NH₃) over Kolkata urban city for an 8-year duration (2016-2023). Diurnal variability of heat stress is also assessed.

METHODS

A comprehensive view of the long-term trends in air pollution in Kolkata is studied using air pollutants data from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) for 8 years (2016-2023). The diurnal variability of air pollutants (PM2.5, PM10, ozone, SO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, NO_x, NH₃) were plotted during pre-monsoon, monsoon, post-monsoon and winter seasons over Kolkata region. The heat stress is computed in terms of Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The diurnal variation of air pollutant concentrations (PM2.5, PM10, ozone, SO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, NO_x, NH₃) and heat stress indicator (WBGT) in Kolkata during pre-monsoon, monsoon, post-monsoon, and winter seasons are presented in Figure 1a, b, c and d respectively. PM2.5 and PM10 levels were higher during winter compared to other seasons which is on account of low temperatures and atmospheric inversion effects that trap pollutants. The heat stress indicator (WBGT) was higher during monsoon and comparable for the rest of the seasons (Fig 1b). During the monsoon season, WBGT exhibits the most stable pattern, characterized by a flatter diurnal variability compared to winter, pre-monsoon, and post-monsoon. This indicates that high humidity contributed to warmer nights and less diurnal temperature variation which means, that heat stress consistently elevated throughout the day and night has a critical impact on public health. The overall WBGT values are higher throughout the 24-hour cycle, with only a slight peak in the afternoon. However, the difference between morning, afternoon, and evening temperatures is much less pronounced than in the other seasons. This indicates that WBGT remains consistently elevated during both day and night, likely due to the high humidity and warmer nights of the monsoon period.

Particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) generally exhibits an inverse variability compared to WBGT, with concentrations decreasing as WBGT increases, especially during the winter and post-monsoon seasons. In contrast, ozone shows co-variability with WBGT, rising during the warmer parts of the day when sunlight promotes its formation. NO_x and CO also tend to display inverse variabilities, with declining concentrations as temperatures rise. During the monsoon season, WBGT remains more stable, and pollutant concentrations fluctuate less, leading to weaker co-variability of WBGT with most pollutants, likely due to the effects of high humidity and rainfall. This overall trend indicates that temperature and sunlight-driven processes have a significant impact on air pollutant levels, particularly particulate matter and ozone. It has been observed that ozone diurnal variability correlates positively with WBGT, while in the case of PM especially during winter and post-monsoon seasons, variation is negative as indicated in the graphs (Fig1). This implies that a positive correlation of WBGT with ozone could be incorporated in air quality models for the prediction of O₃ levels in different temperature ranges. Correlation and cause effect analysis between air pollutants and heat stress has not been covered. These findings suggest that further studies to examine the correlation of variability in air pollutants with heat stress indicators are required.

Figure 1. Diurnal variations in air pollutant concentrations in Kolkata for a) Pre monsoon, b) Monsoon, c) Post Monsoon, d) Winter seasons along with WBGT (Wet Bulb Globe Temperature) as a heat stress indicator.

CONCLUSIONS

The diurnal variation of air pollutants and WBGT in Kolkata shows distinct seasonal patterns. Particulate matter levels are highest during winter, while WBGT is most elevated and stable during the monsoon, likely due to high humidity and warmer nights. WBGT shows an inverse co-variability with PM, in contrast to ozone, particularly during the warmer parts of the day. These results highlight the influence of temperature and sunlight on air quality, suggesting that further studies are needed to explore the relationship between air pollution and heat stress

indicators.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the CPCB team for providing data access. Thanks are due to the Director, IIRS for support and encouragement. The authors are thankful to the Vice Chancellor, IGDTUW for supporting the work.

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AIRBORNE BACTERIAL COMMUNITIES ENRICHED WITH PATHOGENS OVER NEW DELHI EXHIBIT STRONG DEPENDENCY ON TEMPERATURE AND POLLUTANTS IN WINTER

SHAHINA RAUSHAN SAIKH^{1, *}, ANTARA PRAMANICK¹, NATSUKO YASUTOMI²,
AKASH BISWAL², SACHIN GHUDE³, AKA SHARMA⁴, A. P. DIMRI⁴, PRABIR K.
PATRA^{2,5}, SANAT K. DAS^{1, *}

¹Department of Physical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, India

²Research Institute for Humanity and Nature, Kyoto, Japan

³Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, India

⁴School of Environmental Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

⁵Research Institute for Global Change, JAMSTEC, Yokohama, Japan

KEYWORDS: Bioaerosols, Delhi, Pathogens, Urban, Health

INTRODUCTION

Atmosphere is less explored for microorganisms than soil and aquatic ecosystems (1,2). Airborne bacteria have a significant role in the structural variation of atmospheric microorganisms; however, little is known about their composition and geographical distribution. Understanding its effect on public health is essential as their substantial spatial and temporal variation highly depends on meteorological conditions and air pollution levels. The current study presents the composition, diversity, and variability of airborne pathogenic bacteria in aerosols collected from two sites in New Delhi during Jan-Feb 2024.

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected on 0.2 μm pore size filter papers (47mm) simultaneously at 10m height from 09 January to 15 February 2024 at two locations in a densely populated and highly polluted metropolitan city, New Delhi, India. Sampling sites were chosen within the campus of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology (IITM, 28.63°N, 77.17°E), near a busy traffic and highly populated area in New Delhi, and Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU, 28.53°N, 77.16°E), well within the canopy, isolated from local traffic and relatively less populated area in New Delhi. Microbial cell suspension is prepared from aerosol samples collected on filter papers (1). Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) has been extracted from microbial cell suspension, and DNA sequencing is performed targeting v3-v4 regions of 16S rRNA genes using the Illumina NextSeq platform.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Based on meteorological conditions and pollution levels, total 36 samples are grouped into four periods: low haze (surface air temperature- $T = 11.4 \pm 0.4$ °C, particulate matter of 2.5 μm diameter - $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 190.7 \pm 8.8$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), high haze ($T = 13.3 \pm 0.7$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 278.9 \pm 3.6$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), rain ($T = 16.9 \pm 1.5$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 100.1 \pm 22.9$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$), and seasonal transition ($T = 18.9 \pm 1.0$ °C, $\text{PM}_{2.5} = 187.6 \pm 5.2$ $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$). The abundance of airborne bacterial loading over New Delhi varied strongly with air temperature (Spearman's correlation coefficient - $r = 0.70$, $p < 0.001$) and visibility ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$) with a strong positive correlation. However, Relative Humidity ($r = -0.41$, $p < 0.05$), $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.01$), and Air Quality Index (AQI) ($r = -0.31$, $p < 0.05$) have a negative effect on airborne bacterial loading as shown in Figure 1. The highest bacterial diversity is observed during high haze days followed by

transition, low haze, and rainy winter days over New Delhi. Beta diversities formed separate ellipses exhibiting distinct bacterial diversities; however, there is an overlap between low haze and high haze conditions, indicating a similar atmosphere for the survival of the same type of airborne bacteria. High concentrations of pathogenic OTU's causing various respiratory, skin, gastrointestinal, and oral infections are present over New Delhi. There is a 7-fold increase in the loading of all types of pathogenic bacteria during rain events at JNU due to increased atmospheric moisture.

Figure 4: Spearman's correlation (r) between meteorological parameters and airborne bacterial loadings. Asterisks indicate significance levels: ***, $p < 0.001$; **, $p < 0.01$; *, $p < 0.05$.

CONCLUSIONS

Human pathogens like *Bacillus cereus*, *Acinetobacter lwoffii*, and *Clostridium sordellii*, responsible for respiratory diseases and skin infections, are highly loaded, indicating an alarming situation for human health in winter over New Delhi. The present study provides new insights and direction in interdisciplinary science, including detailed investigations of the effects of meteorological conditions on airborne bacteria and human pathogens and their implications on the health of people living in an urban location over New Delhi, India.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is in collaboration with the Aakash Project, Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN), Kyoto, Japan.

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OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF BROWN CARBON FROM ANTHROPOGENIC BIOMASS BURNING IN INDIA

CHIMURKAR NAVINYA¹, TAVEEN SINGH KAPOOR², GUPTA ANURAG^{1,3},
CHANDRA VENKATARAMAN^{1,4}, HARISH C. PHULERIA^{1,3}, AND RAJAN K.
CHAKRABARTY²

¹Centre for Climate Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai – 400076,

²Center for Aerosol Science and Engineering, Department of Energy, Environmental and Chemical Engineering, Washington University in St. Louis, St. Louis, MO – 63130, USA.

³Environmental Science and Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay

⁴Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Brown Carbon, Biomass Fuels, Imaginary Refractive Index, Organic Carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols, including black and organic carbon, dominate fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) emissions and constitute about 40% of PM_{2.5} emissions in India. Key sources in the region include residential biomass burning for cooking, heating, agricultural residue burning, and brick kilns. These aerosols disturb the Earth's energy balance, but the extent of this impact remains uncertain, partly due to the highly varying light-absorbing properties of organic carbon (brown carbon, BrC). This study examines BrC emissions from major biomass sources in India, leveraging aerosol samples collected during the COALESCE (<https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0030.1>) campaign. By analyzing BrC light absorption using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, the study aims to link BrC properties to carbon fractions and the BC-to-organic aerosol (OA) ratio to improve BrC parameterization in climate models.

METHODS

Field-based emissions measurements were conducted between Oct 2021 and Apr 2022 in rural parts of Gujarat and Maharashtra, India. The study focused on emissions from agricultural residue burning, brick clamps, cooking, and heating. Particulate emissions were sampled on quartz filter papers via a multi-arm inlet probe. These filters were analyzed for methanol-soluble BrC light absorption using UV-visible spectrophotometry and organic carbon (OC) content using thermo-optical methods. The absorption coefficients were calculated to determine the imaginary refractive index (kBrC). Spatial variations of kBrC were mapped using nationwide emission inventories and established a relationship between kBrC and BC-to-OA ratio.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Our study revealed a wide range of kBrC₅₅₀ values, spanning from 0.0007 to 0.1199. We observed an inverse correlation between kBrC and w , with w values ranging from 7.52 to 1.00. This relationship aligns with previous research on synthetic fuels under various combustion conditions (Saleh et al., 2018). Interestingly, we found that the variation in BrC properties within a single source category exceeded the differences between distinct categories, implying a larger dependence on combustion condition than fuel type. The mean kBrC₅₅₀ values for different emission sources were relatively similar: 0.026 (± 0.035) for agricultural residue burning, 0.015 (± 0.026) for brick production, 0.015 (± 0.003) for cooking, and 0.010 (± 0.006) for heating. We identified a strong correlation between the BC to OA ratio

and BrC properties ($k_{BrC,550}$, $R^2=0.93$; w , $R^2=0.60$), which we used to establish a relationship between these parameters. Our findings suggest values that are significantly larger than those in previous research (Luo et al., 2022; Saleh et al., 2014) in other regions, or under laboratory conditions, implying that smaller magnitudes of w values and $k_{BrC,365}$ estimates, could cause uncertainty and a low bias in radiative forcing calculations, particularly in South Asia. Using emission-weighted spatial data, we estimated $k_{BrC,550}$ values ranging from 0.006 to 0.023, which supported $k_{BrC,365}$ calculations. The resulting $k_{BrC,365}$ values ranged from 0.05 to 0.14, indicating significant absorption in the UV-visible spectrum. We observed higher k_{BrC} values in the Himalayan foothills compared to other regions in India, likely due to emissions from space heating activities (Navinya et al., 2023). Recent research has also suggested that BrC in Himalayan regions may have a lower photobleaching rate due to colder temperatures (Choudhary et al., 2022). The combination of dark BrC particle emissions and their extended atmospheric lifetimes could contribute to snow darkening upon deposition, potentially accelerating snow and glacier melting in these sensitive regions.

Figure 1. (a) BrC-BC light absorption continuum in semi-log scale, showing the wavelength dependence (w) of the imaginary part of the refractive index (k_{550}) versus the imaginary part of the refractive index at 550 nm (k_{550}). (b) The spatial distribution of $k_{BrC,365}$.

CONCLUSIONS

This study enhances the understanding of BrC light absorption by estimating source- and fuel-specific k_{BrC} values through field measurements. The BrC parameterization developed in this study can aid climate and radiative models. Spatial variation of k_{BrC} in India shows strong BrC over the Himalayan foothills, highlighting the increased risk of glacier melting.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Fulbright Program {Fulbright-Kalam Climate Fellowship Award No. 2913/FNDR/2023-2024 to CN} and the IIT Bombay – WashU program for financial support to conduct a part of this work at Washington University in St. Louis. This work was supported by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change under the NCAP-COALESCCE project {Grant No.14/10/2014-CC(Vol.II)}.

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SPATIAL AND SEASONAL VARIATION OF LIGHT ABSORPTION BY NEAR SURFACE AEROSOLS OVER INDIA

TAVEEN S. KAPOOR^{1,2}, CHIMURKAR NAVINYA², ADISHREE APTE^{1,3}, NSHIT J. SHETTY¹, PRADNYA LOKHANDE², SUJIT SINGH⁴, SADASHIVA MURTHY B. M.⁴, MEENA DESWAL⁵, JITENDER S. LAURA⁵, AKILA MUTHALAGU⁶, ASIF QURESHI^{6,7}, ANKUR BHARDWAJ⁸, RAMYA SUNDER RAMAN⁸, YANG LIAN⁹, G. PANDITHURAI⁹, POOJA CHAUDHARY¹⁰, BAERBEL SINHA¹⁰, SHAHADEV RABHA¹¹, BINOY K. SAIKIA¹¹, TANVEER AHMAD NAJAR¹², ARSHID JEHangIR¹², SAURYADEEP MUKHERJEE¹³, ABHIJIT CHATTERJEE¹³, HARISH C. PHULERIA^{2,14}, RAJAN K. CHAKRABARTY¹, AND CHANDRA VENKATARAMAN^{2,3}

¹ Center for Aerosol Science and Engineering, Department of Energy, Environmental and Chemical Engineering, Washington University in St. Louis, St. Louis, MO, USA

² Centre for Climate Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai, India

³ Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai,

⁴ Department of Environmental Engineering, SJCE, JSS Science and Technology University

⁵ Department of Environmental Sciences, Maharshi Dayanand University Rohtak, Rohtak,

⁶ Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad, Kandi, India

⁷ Department of Climate Change, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad, Kandi, India

⁸ Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education & Research Bhopal, Bhopal, India

⁹ Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Pune, India

¹⁰ Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Mohali, Mohali, India

¹¹ Coal & Energy Division, CSIR North-East Institute of Science & Technology, Jorhat, India

¹² Department of Environmental Science, School of Earth and Environmental Science, University of Kashmir, Srinagar, India

¹³ Department of Chemical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, India

¹⁴ Environmental Science & Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Brown Carbon, Carbonaceous Aerosols, Optical Properties

INTRODUCTION

Climate models show large uncertainties in radiative forcing from carbonaceous aerosols due to limited knowledge of their abundance and optical properties (Sand et al., 2021). This is especially notable in regions like India, where aerosol sources are diverse and unregulated. Black carbon (BC) absorbs strongly in the near-UV to the infrared spectrum, while organic carbon and dust absorb preferentially in the near-UV. Ambient aerosol absorption varies with emissions sources and atmospheric processing (or aging). Limited papers have studied the spatial variability of surface aerosol absorption over the Indian landmass. This research aims to improve the understanding of aerosol absorption across India by using ground measurements to refine radiative forcing estimates.

METHODS

Measurements were taken at nine COALESCE network (Venkataraman et al., 2020) sites across India during the summer of 2020, with additional sampling at three sites (Rohtak, Hyderabad, and Mysuru) during other seasons. Most summer data were collected before COVID-19 lockdowns, while monsoon and winter measurements occurred post-lockdown.

Aerosol absorption was analyzed using PTFE filters and UV-visible spectrophotometry, applying correction factors to estimate particle-phase absorption coefficients (Pandey et al., 2019). The study focused on BC and brown carbon (BrC) contributions, employing a Mie theory optimization method to estimate BC absorption at near UV wavelengths (Kapoor et al., 2022). Satellite data was compared to ground measurements to explore relationships between ground measurements and columnar aerosol absorption.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

During the summer of 2020, aerosol absorption across nine Indian sites showed significant spatial variation. Near-IR absorption, dominated by BC, ranged from 54 to 124 Mm^{-1} , peaking at Shyamnagar. Near-UV absorption, influenced by BrC in addition to BC, was highest at Shyamnagar (691 Mm^{-1}) and Kashmir (447 Mm^{-1}). Seasonal variation showed lower absorption during summer and monsoon, in comparison to winter and post-monsoon. Sites with larger absorption Ångström exponents (AAEs), like Kashmir (2.6), suggested higher brown carbon contributions. The contribution of BrC in total light absorption at 410nm was between 20-70% (Figure 1) across the sites, with larger values likely due to biomass burning emissions.

Figure 1. Site and season specific brown carbon absorption contribution (% babs, BrC,410/babs,410).

Ground-measured spectral absorption correlates strongly with columnar absorption properties, indicating that boundary layer aerosols dominate absorption in the atmospheric column over the region. Preliminary multivariate regression models show promise for predicting ground-measured properties like BrC absorption using satellite-derived properties.

CONCLUSIONS

This study finds large aerosol absorption at both 880 and 410 nm, with significant fractions of BrC absorption at regional sites across India. We also find high values of mass absorption cross section, i.e. highly absorbing nature of particles, both at polluted and cleaner sites. Since surface aerosols dominate columnar absorption, surface absorption datasets can be estimated at higher resolution using satellite measurements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change

under the NCAP-COALESCE project {Grant 14/10/2014-CC(Vol.II)}. The views expressed in this document are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Ministry. The Ministry does not endorse any products or commercial services mentioned in this publication. TSK, RKC, AA, and NJS thank the WashU-IITB Joint Research and Education Initiative for supporting this study.

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WINTER TIME SEASONAL STUDY ON TRACE METALS AND THEIR DIURNAL PATTERNS AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT USING PMF ON PM 10 FROM STATE-OF-THE-ART HTDMA INSTRUMENTATION CAMPAIGNING STUDY AT DELHI DURING 2020

M.V. MOHAMMED HANEEF¹, GAZALA HABIB¹, TARUN GUPTA²
ADNAN MATEEN QADRI², M.A. MAHAJABEEN³

¹Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering

²Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering

³Utracon Structural Systems, New Delhi – 110029, India.

KEYWORDS: Trace Elements, Source Apportionment, PMF, ED-XRF, HTDMA, Biomass Burnings.

INTRODUCTION

The study, a comprehensive exploration of PM10 and its associated trace metals in the heavily polluted Delhi NCR region, was conducted at IIT Delhi. The research, which took place from February 2020 to March 2020, during the peak winter time of Delhi, involved 12-hour intervals between day and night samples every day in February and March 2020. A portion of the offline filter-based study is analyzed for chemical characterization on ED-XRF with the help of the IIT Kanpur ED XRF unit.

METHODS

The aerosol experiments are carried out in South Delhi's central urban area at an elevation of 30 M from the ground at the IITD Delhi main campus building (28 ° 35'N; 77 ° 12'E). The setup is inclusive of filter-based PM measurements, hygroscopicity, mass concentrations, number concentrations of aerosols, BC measurements, aerosol scattering effects, and using the state-of-the-art instruments from HTDMA, MPSS, OPS, Aethalometer, and Nephelometer. The area is predominantly residential, and much of its background pollutants were from vehicular emissions and mineral dust. PM 2.5 and PM 1 atmospheric rates are high because of higher urban extensions and developments in Delhi (NCR) and increased energy use. Gupta et al.2007. The main PM10, PM2.5, and PM1 sources are windblown dust, secondary aerosol, coal combustion, traffic suppressions, and biomass burning. Trace elements such as K, Sc, V, Cr, Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Ga are included in this current study of PM 10 source apportionment,

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

ELE.	DAY MEAN	SD	RANGE	NIGHT MEAN	SD	RANGE
K	3.578719	2.140961	8.109192	3.640926	1.360945	5.891635
Sc	0.00125	0.00409	0.022226	0.001394	0.002804	0.012098
V	0.315848	1.014628	4.064125	0.077201	0.203697	0.614842
Cr	0.005275	0.000834	0.004572	0.00539	0.000834	0.004572
Mn	0.079986	0.069619	0.244798	0.079353	0.034721	0.1407
Ni	0.001272	0.001617	0.000141	0.00136	0.001617	0.008862
Cu	0.081463	0.128255	0.511625	0.053792	0.032876	0.153051
Zn	0.704643	0.65893	2.812842	0.603703	0.324695	1.466086
Ga	0.004094	0.009271	0.031852	0.002536	0.002909	0.012721

Table 1. Comparison between 12-day and nocturnal mean concentration of trace elements in ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)

The site is source specific it has mixed number of apportionments ranging from biomass burning, secondary inorganic aerosols, Crustals, Vehicular, Industrial, Road dust and coal burning industries., Being the primary marker species for biomass burning element K at mean day for 12 hr avg ranges from $3.578 \pm 2.14 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Nocturnal 12 hr mean range between $3.64 \pm 1.36 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Element Sc as the signature species of coal burning the mean day time 12 hrs average for winter season is very trace $0.0012 \pm 0.004 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and for 12 hr night time average is $0.001 \pm 0.002 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Element V day time 12 hr mean ranges from $0.315 \pm 1.01 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and night time concentration ranges from trace amount $0.077 \pm 0.20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Cr ranges from $0.005 \pm 0.0008 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to very negligible level in PM 10, and night time mean range from $0.00539 \pm 0.0008 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Mn mean averages in day between $0.079 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and night between $0.079 \pm 0.034 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Ni as a trace element ranges between $0.0012 \pm 0.0016 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in day time and $0.0013 \pm 0.0016 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in night time 12 hrs mean for winter, Cu ranges $0.081 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at day mean and $0.053 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at night mean for 12 hrs, Zn and Ga ranges between $0.704 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $0.004 \pm 0.009 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 12 hrs Mean day time average for winter season and $0.603 \pm 0.324 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $0.0025 \pm 0.0029 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively for winter season night time 12 hrs mean.

Figure 1. Main Trace elements Mean average for winter 2020, Day and Night 12 hrs Mean.

CONCLUSIONS

- Influence of signature species of biomass burning K at night time 12 hrs mean than day time mean could be due to winter firewood burning in NCR regions,
- The presence of vanadium in source apportionment indicates oil-burning activities in the NCR region during winter.
- Zn daytime averages between $0.704 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and nighttime averages between $0.603 \pm 0.324 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, indicating the presence of atmospheric pollution load from straw burning and Iron industries.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by IIT Delhi and Tropoz Leibniz Institute of Research Germany combined.

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IDENTIFICATION OF MINERAL CONTENT IN FINE AND ULTRAFINE PARTICULATE MATTER (PM₁ & PM_{2.5}) IN URBAN AREA OF DELHI, INDIA

PREETI TIWARI^{1,2}, SAKSHI GUPTA^{1,2}, MANISHA^{1,2}, MANOJ KUMAR^{1,2}, S.P. SINGH^{1,2},
S. K. SHARMA^{1,2}

¹ CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, Dr. K. S. Krishnan Road, New Delhi 110012, India.

² Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad 201002, India

KEYWORDS: PM₁, PM_{2.5}, Mineralogical Composition, Delhi

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, though present in small quantities and with short residence times, play a crucial role in altering the atmospheric radiation budget on a regional scale. They affect this balance through direct mechanisms like scattering and absorbing solar energy, and indirectly by promoting cloud formation. Rapid urbanization, industrialization, and increased vehicular traffic, particularly in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), have contributed significantly to the rising levels of atmospheric particulate matter. At present studies related to the mineralogical content of air pollutants are available for coarse mode particulate matter only (Gupta et al. 2024). In this study we have attempted to investigate the mineralogical composition of fine and ultrafine mode particulates of aerosol which includes: dolomite, illite, montmorillonite, quartz, kaolinite, and chlorite. The study's analysis of the mineralogical composition of PM₁ & PM_{2.5} offers critical insights into the sources and environmental impacts of airborne particulate matter in Delhi, situated over the IGP region because there is a limited study reported regarding the physical characteristics of PM_{2.5} and PM₁ (Shankar et al., 2022). Characterizing these mineralogical properties aids in identifying the origin of aerosols and contributes to the development of targeted strategies for mitigating air pollution and safeguarding public health.

METHODS

PM₁ and PM_{2.5} samples were collected at the CSIR-National Physical Laboratory (NPL) in Delhi (28.38°N, 77.10°E, 217m amsl) from March to September 2024. XRD analysis of the samples, using a Rigaku Ultima IV X-ray diffractometer with a Cu K α -line (1.54 Å), scanned between 10° to 60° at 3°/min for mineral identification, cross-referenced with literature and the RRUFF database. FTIR analysis was performed with a Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS50 spectrometer equipped with a QUEST ATR accessory, collecting spectra from 4000–400 cm⁻¹ to validate minerals via functional group detection. Particle morphology and elemental composition were examined with SEM-EDX at 10 kV, and results were reported as atomic weight percentages after ZAF correction. Samples were gold-sputter coated prior to SEM analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Identification of minerals in PM₁ & PM_{2.5}:

Analysis through XRD quantified a diverse range of mineralogical compositions in PM₁ & PM_{2.5} samples (Fig.1), revealing significant concentrations of minerals such as kaolinite, montmorillonite, quartz, dolomite, calcite, magnetite, hematite, gypsum, halite, mascagnite, augite, albite, and wollastonite. In contrast, calcium ammonium sulfate hydrate (C-A-S-H) and illite were found in lower proportions. The consistent detection of well-crystallized quartz

indicates its widespread distribution, while dolomite, albite, and augite are primarily attributed to natural geological processes like crustal/soil dust and construction. Clay minerals such as kaolinite and montmorillonite likely originate from both natural and anthropogenic sources, including industrial and agricultural activities (Gupta et al. 2024; Neupane et al., 2020). Iron-bearing minerals (hematite, magnetite) are linked to natural erosion and anthropogenic sources such as Diesel engine combustion, waste combustion, steel manufacturing, vehicular brake ware, and coal burning. Calcium-rich minerals (gypsum, C-A-S-H, wollastonite) are associated with crustal/soil dust, construction and mining activities. The presence of ammonium sulfate suggests secondary atmospheric reactions, driven by combustion processes. Long-range dust transport from the upper IGP and arid regions significantly influences particulate matter composition in this region. FTIR analysis provided peak assignments and bonding information for various mineral components based on wavenumber values (Gupta et al. 2024). SEM-EDX revealed diverse particle morphologies (irregular, spherical, flaky) and elemental composition, with Na and Ca being the most abundant. These findings validated the mineral structures identified through XRD.

Figure.1. XRD pattern for PM1 & PM2.5 samples

CONCLUSION

The combined XRD, FTIR, and SEM-EDX analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of PM1 & PM2.5 composition and morphology in the study area. The results show PM1 & PM2.5 contain minerals like kaolinite, quartz, and hematite, originating from natural processes (soil erosion, weathering) and human activities (construction, industrial emissions, fossil fuel burning). Dust from distant regions also contributes. These methods confirm that PM1 and PM2.5 are complex mixtures originating from both natural and anthropogenic sources, providing essential insights into air quality and its environmental implications. This research contributes significantly to understanding the PM pollution profile in Delhi, over the IGP region, offering a novel approach that integrates multiple analytical techniques to thoroughly examine the mineralogical, physical characteristics, and sources of pollution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors (SKS, PT) are thankful to the Director, CSIR-NPL, New Delhi, and the Head, Environmental Sciences and Biomedical Metrology Division (ES&BMD), CSIR-NPL, New

Delhi, for their encouragement and support for this study.

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BLACK CARBON, TRACE GASES AND PARTICULATE MATTER CHARACTERISTICS AT DELHI

A. RANA^{1,2}, A. MALL^{1,2}, S. K. SHARMA^{1,2}, S. SINGH^{1,2}

¹Environmental Sciences and Biomedical Metrology Division, CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi-110012, India.

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), HRDC Campus, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, PM2.5, PM10, Trace Gases, Aethalometer

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) is a major environmental threat, posing significant risks to both human health and ecosystems. This is particularly evident in Delhi, one of India's most polluted mega-cities, which grapples with severe air quality challenges that profoundly affect public health and the environment. The composition, size, and sources of particulate matter (PM) play a crucial role in both air quality and climate change. Among its components, black carbon (BC) is particularly significant due to its strong light-absorbing properties, contributing to atmospheric warming (Chung et al., 2005). The present study focuses on the variation of BC concentrations in 2021, with the highest levels observed between October and December. The ratio of fine to coarse particles was assessed, and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis determined the elemental composition of PM. Subsequently, the enrichment factor (EFs) was calculated to distinguish between natural and anthropogenic sources of PM. Additionally, the influence of trace gases, such as sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO₂), ammonia (NH₃), carbon monoxide (CO), and ozone (O₃), on PM concentrations was examined. Hence, this comprehensive approach enables a deeper understanding of the sources, chemical composition, and environmental impacts of particulate matter, as well as its interactions with atmospheric pollutants.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

Sampling was conducted at CSIR-National Physical Laboratory (NPL), Delhi, a polluted mega-city with a semi-arid climate and extreme weather conditions (28.4°N, 77.1°E; 218 m above sea level). PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were collected using a fine particle sampler and a high-volume respirable dust sample respectively. Black carbon concentrations were measured with an Aethalometer at seven optical wavelengths, from near-infrared to near-ultraviolet. Trace gases (NO, NO₂, CO, O₃, NH₃, SO₂) were measured at CSIR-NPL using various instruments: SO₂ with a calibrated UV fluorescence analyzer, O₃ with a UV-based analyzer, and NO/NO₂ with a NO_x-Analyzer. CO was measured using a non-dispersive infrared analyzer. Elemental composition and enrichment factors were determined using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis. Also, Crustal enrichment factors (EFs) were calculated to indicate the origin of elements, whether from natural sources or anthropogenic activities, and their abundance in ambient particulate matter. The EFs of elements found in atmospheric PM₁₀ samples are calculated following the outlined method (Taylor and McLennan., 1995).

$$EF = \frac{E_{sample}/X_{sample}}{E_{crust}/X_{sample}}$$

where, E_{sample} is element (E) concentration, X_{sample} is reference element (X) concentration, E_{crust} is element (E) concentration in upper continental crust, X_{crust} is

reference element (X) concentration in upper continental crust and Aluminium (Al) is used as the reference element in this study.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Daily Black Carbon (BC) concentrations were measured with a 1-minute temporal resolution and averaged over 24 hours. The highest monthly average, $22.85 \pm 10.37 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, occurred in December, while the lowest, $3.55 \pm 1.59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, was observed in August during the monsoon, as shown in Fig. 1. BC levels were notably higher in winter due to lower atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and wind speed (WS). The stable ABL and reduced surface convection in winter limit vertical air mixing, trapping pollutants near the ground. The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio, shown in Fig. 2, highlights the dominance of fine or coarse particles. Lower summer ratios (0.14 in April) indicate coarser particles, likely from dust particles from nearby deserts during pre-monsoon and monsoon months. Higher winter ratios (0.93 in November) reflect an increase in fine particles, trapped by low-level inversion, mainly from biomass burning, fossil fuels, power plants, and vehicle emissions. XRF analysis of PM₁₀ identified 16 elements, with high concentrations of Ca ($6.66 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Na ($0.74 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Cl ($5.75 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), K ($4.73 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Al ($10.47 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and Fe ($3.97 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Low enrichment factors (EF < 5) for elements like Na, Mg, Al, and Fe indicated natural sources, while high EFs (EF > 10) for Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Pb pointed to anthropogenic sources, mainly from industrial and vehicular emissions.

Fig 1. Daily mass concentration of BC 2021 (green line: Average conc. and dash lines:

Fig 2. To investigate the presence of fine/coarse mode particles by evaluating PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio during the year 2021.

Fig 3. Impact of trace gases (NO₂, NH₃, O₃, SO₂ and CO) on PM₁₀ in their calculated units.

The influence of trace gases on particulate matter (PM) concentrations has been assessed through regression analysis of pollutants against PM₁₀ in this study. The results suggest a notable interaction between PM₁₀ levels and key trace gases. Specifically, for every 1 µg/m³ increase in PM₁₀ concentration, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) increases by 0.03 ppb, ammonia (NH₃) and ozone (O₃) both rise by 0.01 ppb, sulphur dioxide (SO₂) by 0.001 ppb, and carbon monoxide (CO) by 0.001 ppm are shown in Fig 3. These findings underscore the interconnectedness of PM₁₀ and gaseous pollutants, highlighting their potential to jointly contribute to atmospheric pollution and health risks in Delhi.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights the seasonal variation of black carbon and particulate matter in Delhi, with the highest BC concentrations in December due to stable atmospheric conditions. Also, coarse particles dominate in summer, while fine particles increase in winter. Elemental analysis shows natural sources for elements like Ca and Al, while elements like Cr and Pb are linked to anthropogenic activities. Additionally, trace gases, particularly NO₂, significantly influence PM₁₀ levels, underscoring the combined impact of pollutants on air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Author (AR) would like to acknowledge the University Grant Commission (UGC) for providing financial support as a JRF Fellow and Author (AM) would like to acknowledge the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) for providing financial support as CSIR Fellow (18599).

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CHARACTERIZATION OF POLY-AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (PAHs) IN TOTAL SUSPENDED PARTICULATES IN AN URBAN AREA OF NEW-DELHI, INDIA

SHWETA RUHIL^{1,2}, SAKSHI AHLAWAT^{1,2}, SHOBHNA SHANKAR³, RANU GADI³,
TUHIN KUMAR MANDAL^{1,2}

¹ Environmental Sciences & Biomedical Metrology Division, CSIR National Physical Laboratory, Dr. K S Krishnan Road, New Delhi 110012, India

² Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research (AcSIR), Headquarters CSIR-HRDC Campus, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh-201002, India

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, deterioration in air quality has been a global concern as the pollutants often exceed the permissible limits set by WHO and CPCB of India, leading to several health problems and affecting the environment¹. Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) matter are widely distributed particles having a broad range (0.005 to 100 μm) and compositions including Poly-Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), which are chemically stable hydrocarbons with more than two benzene rings and are potent carcinogens, mutagens and teratogens. Long term exposure to high PAHs in the atmosphere, they can enter the lungs' alveoli via inhalation, and be absorbed into the blood circulation, leading to severe diseases such as cardiovascular and respiratory, ultimately increasing mortality and morbidity rate³, therefore this present study undertook sentinel monitoring of 16 PAHs present in the TSP samples and sources are identified.

STUDY SITE AND METHODS

Ambient air sampling was carried out at CSIR-NPL, located in New Delhi, a metropolitan city in North India having a semi-arid climate. A total of 20-TSP samples were collected using a portable TSP sampler from Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 for 8 hrs (10:00-18:00), using Pall Tissue-Quartz fibre filter. After sampling, collected samples were weighed and concentration was calculated in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The method in “determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in TSP samples by using gas chromatograph (Shimadzu, GC-2010 Plus) system, equipped with an Rtx-5 molecular sieve column of 0.25 μm thickness. The sample filter was extracted using 15 ml Dichloromethane (DCM) using an ultrasonicator for 30 min. The extracted sample was then reduced to 1ml using the rotary evaporator at 30-40°C and then filtered out using a PVDF membrane filter of 0.5 μm pore size, afterwards transferred into gas chromatography amber vials for further analysis in GC. It detects 16 PAHs listed by US-EPA [naphthalene (Nap 2 ring), acenaphthylene (Acy 3 ring), acenaphthene (Ace 3 ring), fluorene (Flu 3ring), phenanthrene (Phe 3ring), anthracene (An 3 ring), fluoranthene (Flt 4 ring), pyrene (Pyr 4 ring), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA 4 ring), Chrysene (Chr 4 ring), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF 5 ring), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF 5 ring), benzo[a]pyrene (BaP 5 ring), indeno[1,2,3-cd] pyrene (IcP 6 ring), dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DBA 6 ring), and benzo[g,h,i]pyrene (BjhiP 6 ring)]. The calibration curve was obtained for all PAHs standards for the quantification.

SOURCE APPORTIONMENT TECHNIQUE

The DR (diagnostic ratios) method was used to qualitatively identify principal pollution sources of PAHs based on the characteristic ratios.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Over the study period i.e., from mid-February to mid-April, 2024, the TSP concentration in ambient air ranged from 207.29 to 465.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a mean mass concentration of $307.07 \pm 72.12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, of which concentration of April, 2024 is highest ($389.25 \pm 48.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). TSP concentration of all the 20 samples collected exceeded the 24-hourly ambient air quality standard level of Suspended Particulate matter (SPM), according to the CPCB 2009 guidelines. The concentration shows a large standard deviation which shows the heterogeneity in local sources and their contribution to TSP concentration. Fig 1 shows the concentration of all samples collected during the study period. PAHs constitute a minute fraction of TSP concentration and are classified as carcinogens, thus important to understand the concentration range. The $\sum\text{PAHs}$ concentration, over the study period ranged from 19.49 ± 1.9 to $148.6 \pm 8.9 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ over New Delhi during Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 of which Chr is the most abundant and Acy is the least. The 16 PAHs are divided into three classes based on the aromatic ring structure, 2-3 rings of PAHs, mainly present in the gas phase; 4

FIG 1: CONCENTRATION OF TSP SAMPLES IN $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ IN THE AMBIENT AIR.

FIG 2: PERCENTAGE CONTRIBUTION OF PAHs RING TO THE TOTAL PAHs CONCENTRATION IN THE AMBIENT TSP.

rings of PAHs present in solid and gas phases and 5 or 6 rings of PAHs distributed in the solid phase of TSP, out of which 4- ring PAHs accounts in the maximum amount, followed by 6-rings and 2-3 ring PAHs, represented in FIG 2.

For the identification of sources present in the TSP, we have considered eight characteristics of molecular diagnostic ratios. Calculations are performed to infer the indicative sources (highlighted) based on the ratios and are enlisted in Table 1.

DIAGNOSTIC RATIO	PRESENT STUDY RESULT	RATIO RANGE	SOURCES	REFERENCES
InP/(InP+BghiP)	0.36	< 0.2 0.2–0.5 > 0.5	Oil source Liquid fossil fuel combustion Coal and biomass combustion	Wu et al. (2024)
BaA/(BaA+Chr)	0.45	< 0.2 0.2–0.35 > 0.35	Oil source Oil or combustion sources Combustion source	Wu et al. (2024)
BaP/(BaP+Chr)	0.34	0.73 >0.35	Gasoline Traffic emissions	Pandey et al. (1999)
Phth/(Phth+Anth)	0.42	<0.7	Biomass burning	Kavouras et al.

		>0.7	Fossil fuels	(1999)
BaP/BghiP	0.81	<0.6 >0.6	Non traffic Traffic	Pandey et al. (1999)

TABLE 1: Diagnostic of Different Pahs in The Ambient Air Tsp in Delhi

CONCLUSION

- The TSP concentration in ambient air ranged from 207.29 to 465.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a mean mass concentration of $307.07 \pm 72.12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, of which the concentration of April, 2024 is highest ($389.25 \pm 48.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), the variation was possibly due to a change in the meteorological conditions.
- The ΣPAHs concentration, over the study period ranged from 19.49 ± 1.9 to 148.6 ± 8.9 New Delhi during Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 of which Chr is the most abundant and Acy is least.
- The diagnostic ratio method results revealed the different PAH origin sources and biomass burning, traffic emissions, diesel engine, liquid fossil fuel combustion were the main sources of pollution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author (AR) would like to acknowledge the University Grant Commission (UGC) for providing financial support as a Junior Research Fellowship.

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BALLOON-BORNE MEASUREMENT OF AEROSOL PARTICLE SIZE (B-MAPS)

V. RAVI KIRAN¹, M. VENKAT RATNAM¹, SPYROS BEZANTAKOS², GEROGE BISKOS²

¹National Atmospheric Research Laboratory (NARL), Gadanki – 517 112, India.

²The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Size Distribution Profiles, Balloon-Borne In-Situ Measurements

INTRODUCTION

The profiles of aerosol particle sizes are sparse yet crucial in understanding the influence of aerosols on the climate. The Balloon-borne Measurement of Aerosol Particle Size (B-MAPS) is an intensive field campaign projected for the measurement of aerosol particle size distribution profiles using balloon-borne in-situ measurements from the TIFR balloon facility, Hyderabad. The B-MAPS campaign focuses on obtaining a high-quality data set on the diurnal variation of size distribution profiles of aerosol both during the day as well as night time using a light-weighted balloon-borne OPC (Optical Particle Counter). The B-MAPS campaign is aimed to validate collocated optical sensors, investigate aerosol-cloud interactions by separating the aerosol, and clouds in profiles, and understand the boundary layer confinement of pollutants, UTLS aerosol information, and Radiative transfer through the atmosphere due to aerosol profile. The results from the BACIS campaigns (Kiran et al., 2022) illustrate the capabilities of balloon-borne measurements for the studies of aerosol-cloud interactions.

METHODS

A miniaturized, customized optical particle counter (OPC) made of alpha sense; UK was deployed to obtain the size distribution profiles. This OPC was previously tested successfully for UAV operations (Bezantakos et al., 2018). However, in this campaign, for the first time the OPC was launched to higher altitudes using a balloon. In addition to the OPC, a COBALD (Compact Optical Backscatter Aerosol Detector) sonde, a CPS (Cloud Particle Sensor) sonde, a micro-Aethalometer, a PM sensor, and a radiosonde were also launched along with the OPC. These Sondes will provide the much-needed information on aerosol back scatter, cloud particle concentration, and meteorological information. Prior to the launch, the OPC performance was tested for variable vacuum conditions using the thermo-vac facility available at TIFR, Hyderabad. The B-MAPS campaign was conducted from 17-20th May, 2024 which included one-day time (19th May 2024) launch and two nights (17th, and 22nd May 2024) launches. The entire data obtained from the various sensors is brought to the same time resolution of 1 min. The profiles of particle size are constructed by assigning the corresponding altitude information from the radiosonde GPS coordinates.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

From the first-cut results, it is interesting to note that the response of the OPC is remarkably similar to that of COBALD sonde (shown at blue wavelength) up to an altitude of around 5 km above the surface both during the ascent as well as descent. However, at higher altitudes slightly above 15 km during ascent (as well as descent) there is a sharp rise in the COBALD

backscatter (for example for the launch held on 22nd May) which could not be reproduced by the OPC. This may be attributed to the presence of a thin ice cloud (a sharp rise in RH is noticed corresponding to this height), and/or the presence of small particles preferably above and below the detection limits of the OPC. The particles of size 0.35-1 μm were noticed in the profiles with the concentration of 0.35 μm particles being the maximum ranging from $\sim 10^2$ to 10^1 #/cc with altitude.

Figure.1. Profiles of (a). Temperature (0C), (b). Relative humidity (%), (c). Total aerosol number concentration (#/cc), (d). Back scatter ratio was measured during the ascent of a B-MAPS campaign held on 22nd May 2024. The bottom panel (e-h) shows the same but for the measurements during the descent. The blue coloured lines in fig.(a)-(b) and (e)-(f) refers to the T, RH inside the OPC thermocole enclosure (box).

CONCLUSIONS

The B-MAPS campaign is aimed at measuring the aerosol size profiles both during the day and night using the balloon borne in-situ measurement. The first campaign was initiated from the TIFR, Hyderabad during the 17-22nd May 2024 using a customised balloon borne OPC made of alphasense, UK. The results show, that OPC measurements are comparable with those of the collocated COBALD sonde. The particle size of 0.35 μm is prominent indicating the presence of smaller size particles at higher altitudes. More launches planned shall support intercomparison of sensors, and shed into the details of aerosol size information.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are thankful to the Director, NARL for extending his kind support for conducting the B-MAPS balloon experiment at TIFR, Hyderabad.

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EFFECT OF SURFACE-TO-VOLUME RATIO OF CONTAINMENT ON THE EVOLUTION OF AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS

VARUN¹, AMIT KUMAR^{1,2} JASMIN SUDHA A.^{1,2} AND JOHN ARUL A.^{1,2}

¹Engineering Physics Group, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam

²Homi Bhabha National Institute, Training School Complex, Anushaktinagar Mumbai

KEYWORDS: SMRS, Sodium Aerosol, Surface Area to Volume Ratio, Reactor Containment, Mass Median Diameter.

INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are a promising new generation of nuclear reactors, typically with a capacity of 300 MWe or less. Their compact, modular design allows for off-site fabrication and easy transportation to various locations. Besides their compact and modular design, SMRs have some notable features, such as reduced exclusion zones varying from 0.4 km to 0.8 km (Lulik, 2020) and passive safety systems requiring negligible human intervention. Even though the safety margins of these reactors have been claimed to be improved, safety analysis in severe accident cases is crucial to cope with the functional requirement of containment in the event of an accidental release. The surface area to volume (S/V) ratio of traditional large reactors is much smaller than that for SMRs and experimental reactors, and for experimental facilities, it is an order higher. The present work considers reactor containment/ chambers with different S/V ratios, bottled up with sodium combustion products aerosols and fission product aerosols after a sodium fire. While radioactive fission product aerosols pose significant health risks, sodium combustion aerosols can also present severe chemical hazards. To evaluate aerosol removal rates and particle size growth, the S/V ratio of the containment is a critical parameter. By simulating the evolution of mass median diameter (MMD) and aerosol concentration under various S/V ratios, this study aims to provide valuable insights into containment aerosol behaviour.

NUMERICAL METHODS

The general aerosol dynamics equation governing the evolution of aerosols is given by equation [1].

$$\frac{dn(v)}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^v \beta(u, v-u)n(v-u)n(u)du - \int_0^\infty \beta(u, v)n(u)du - R(v)n(v) + S(v) \quad (1)$$

where, $n(v)$ is the number density of aerosol particles of volume v , β is the coagulation kernel of two colliding particles, u and v is the volume of colliding particles, $S(v)$ is the external aerosol source rate, $R(v)$ is aerosol removal rate due to various phenomena such as diffusion, gravitational settling, thermophoretic etc. A simplified, validated numerical model, based on linear first-order differential equations for mass and number concentrations coupled with mass conservation, was employed for the simulations. These equations were solved using the finite difference method to predict aerosol characteristics as a function of time in a confined environment (Kumar et al., 2016). The model incorporated Brownian coagulation and coagulation correction for the entire range of particles. Several assumptions were made in this model: (i) the aerosols were assumed to be uniformly distributed throughout the containment, (ii) the influence of bulk gas flow on aerosol dynamics was neglected, and (iii) deposition due to particle impaction on containment surfaces was not considered. The S/V ratio of

containment can significantly influence aerosol removal rates and retention within the containment. This ratio varies widely among traditional commercial reactors, experimental reactors, and SMRs. The S/V ratio of different containments, namely PFBR, FBTR and a typical SMR are 0.1 m⁻¹, 0.2m⁻¹ and 0.8m⁻¹ respectively. The S/V ratio of the smaller experimental facilities will have significantly higher S/V ratios, like MINA (S/V=1.2 m⁻¹) and ATF (S/V=6 m⁻¹). For the present calculations, it is assumed that sodium fire is instantaneous, and the temperature and aerosol mass concentration have already reached saturation. The initial aerosol concentration, MMD and Geometric Standard Deviation (GSD) are assumed to be 4 g/m³, 0.4 μm and 2.0, respectively (Kumar et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The evolution of sodium aerosol characteristics (concentration and median size) inside various facilities is simulated for the hypothetical severe accident scenario. Fig. 1 illustrates the evolution of sodium aerosol concentration and median size for different containment S/V ratios. The aerosol concentration decays rapidly for higher S/V ratios (ATF), decreasing ~ 100% within 300 minutes. Conversely, the decay is slowest for the lowest S/V ratio (PFBR), decreasing only 57% over the same time. In the case of FBTR, deposited aerosol mass is 89% in 300 min. However, for the MINA facility, the deposited aerosol mass is ~ 99% and for SMRs, the concentration decreases by 90% in 300 minutes. The faster concentration decay in containments with higher S/V ratios is attributed to the larger surface area available for deposition and the smaller volume for aerosol suspension. In contrast, the MMD growth is most rapid for the lowest S/V ratio, reaching 7.5 μm after 300 minutes, while it is slowest for the highest S/V ratio, saturating at 3.5 μm after 60 minutes. The aerosol size growth of SMRs and FBTR is similar, reaching approximately 6 μm and 6.1 μm, respectively. The particle size growth rate slows down over time for all containment types due to a decrease in coagulation rate. This effect is more pronounced in containments with smaller S/V ratios due to the faster decay of concentration, which reduces the coagulation rate and ultimately limits particle size growth.

Fig: 1. Evolution of aerosol concentration and size growth for different S/V ratios of containments.

CONCLUSIONS

From the study, it is found that aerosol concentration decreases rapidly in an SMR containment when compared to larger power reactors because of its higher S/V ratio leading to a lower in-containment source term. Additionally, the aerosol particle growth is less pronounced in SMR containments compared to large reactor containments. These findings provide valuable insights into aerosol behaviour within SMRs and other containments and

highlight that the S/V ratio is one of the critical parameters that influence the in-containment source term.

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SPATIOTEMPORAL VARIATION OF PM1 CARBONACEOUS MATTER IN AMBIENT AIR OF AN URBAN-INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENT

SURYAKANT MANIKPURI¹, MANAS KANTI DEB¹ AND SHAMSH PERVEZ¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur – 492010, India.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, PM1, Spatiotemporal Variation, Carbonaceous Matter, OC, Ec.

INTRODUCTION

PM1 (particulate matter size less than 1 μm) measurement campaigns are steadily growing in India. About 25 studies in India have reported the PM1 mass concentration in the ranges of 30 to 247 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ with a mean concentration of 104.48 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Chakraborty and Gupta, 2009; Gupta and Mandariya, 2013; Rajput et al., 2018) and PM1/PM2.5 ratios of 0.48 to 0.70 (Deshmukh et al., 2010; Rajput et al., 2018). Ionics (F^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and Ca^{2+}), heavy metals (As, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, Ni, Pb, Se, Ti, V, Zn.) were reported in the chemical composition of PM1 (Gupta and Mandariya, 2013; Talwar et al., 2012). PM1 carbonaceous matter [Organic carbon (OC) and Elemental Carbon (EC)] concentrations of 64.5 ± 36.6 and 41.3 ± 21.7 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ and $\text{EC} = 8.2 \pm 4.7$ and 3.6 ± 3.0 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ for non-foggy and foggy conditions, respectively, were also reported for Kanpur (Rajput et al., 2018). Similarly, Delhi PM1-OC = 34.12 ± 22.94 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ and PM1 EC = 13.91 ± 11.45 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ were also reported for Delhi (Singh et al., 2021). PM1 Source apportionment results were reported for Kanpur where secondary aerosols formation was found to be the major source of PM1 followed by vehicular emissions (Chakraborty and Gupta, 2009). In Delhi, the contributions of various sources for PM1 were found to be secondary aerosol (38.6%), secondary chloride (19.4%), soil dust (6.2%), iron (4.0%), biomass burning (6.7%), and vehicle emissions (3.6%) (Prakash et al., 2016). This study presents first-hand information on PM1 mass and carbonaceous matter in ambient air over an urban-industrial environment (Raipur, Chhattisgarh) of central India.

METHODS

24-hourly PM1 samples were collected from four environmentally distinct sites namely urban-background (free from any local dominating source), industrial, residential and road-traffic sites in Raipur, Chhattisgarh ($22^{\circ}33'$ to $21^{\circ}14'$ N latitude and $82^{\circ}6'$ to $81^{\circ}38'$ E longitude). Weekly measurements were conducted by operating a low volume PM1 sampler (Envirotech APM 577, flow rate 10 LPM) equipped with 47 mm tissue quartz filters (Whatman QM/A) for 24 hours at a height of 15 m from the ground in each site. A total of 96 PM1 samples that comprise 24 samples (12 in each winter and summer) from each of the four sites were collected during the period of the sampling campaign (November 2022-January 2023 and March 2023-May 2023). After the mass measurements, the filter deposited PM1 samples analysed for temperature resolved thermal fractions of organic (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) using a multiwavelength thermal optical OC/EC carbon analyzer (DRI Model 2015).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Significant seasonal variation is exhibited by PM1 in all the sites. Concentration levels of PM1 were highest for industrial sites followed by residential, traffic and background sites

during the study period 2022-2023. Higher concentration of PM1 in industrial sites is due to the industrial emissions and anthropogenic activities around the site. Anthropogenic activities like biomass burning during winter are one of the reasons for higher concentrations during winter. Additionally, low mixing height and calm conditions encouraged more stable air conditions, which in turn decreased particulate matter dispersion. Table 1 summarises the mass concentration of PM1 ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) conducted at four monitoring sites. Figure 1 shows the Seasonal average concentration of OC and EC ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) at four representative monitoring sites of Central India. Concentration of OC and EC also follows the same trend industrial > residential > traffic > background. A higher concentration of OC suggests anthropogenic activities like coal combustion and biomass burning and the EC fraction suggests emissions from vehicles.

Season	Residential	Industrial	Background	Traffic
Winter ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	92.70 ± 30.90	105.87 ± 14.43	68.46 ± 33.13	84.61 ± 22.22
Summer ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	55.26 ± 20.77	71.80 ± 17.29	40.94 ± 24.12	49.08 ± 15.66

Table 1. Statistical summary of site wise seasonally averaged mass concentration (mean ± standard deviation) of PM1 for four representative monitoring sites of Raipur, Chhattisgarh of Central India

Figure 1. Seasonally averaged concentration of OC and EC ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) at four representative monitoring sites of Raipur, Chhattisgarh of Central India

CONCLUSIONS

PM1 showed significant seasonal and spatial variation patterns. Across the monitoring sites, the PM1 concentrations were found to be in the order of industrial > residential > traffic > background. The highest and lowest variability in the measured concentrations of PM1 and carbonaceous matter is observed at background and industrial sites, respectively. Total carbonaceous aerosols were found to be more than 67 % of the PM1. Higher concentrations of

both PM1 and carbon fractions were observed in wintertime compared to those found in summer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the DST-PURSE project (SR/PURSE/2022/145).

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EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF LAND USE CHANGES ON PM_{2.5} LEVELS: A DYNAMIC GEOGRAPHICALLY WEIGHTED REGRESSION ANALYSIS

RAHUL JAISWAL¹, HIMANSHU SHEKHAR⁵, SWAGATA PAYRA³, MANISH KUMAR PANDEY⁴, SUNITA VERMA^{1,2}

¹Department of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221105, Uttar Pradesh, India.

²DST-Mahamana Centre of Excellence in Climate Change Research, Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

³Department of Remote Sensing, Birla Institute of Technology Mesra, Ranchi, Jharkhand

⁴Centre for Quantitative Economics & Data Science, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra

⁵Central Pollution Control Board, Delhi

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Land Use, Land Cover, Remote Sensing, Geographically Weighted Regression

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization and migration have resulted in a significant rise in anthropogenic pollutants, particularly PM_{2.5}. The impact of changes in land surfaces on these pollutants is substantial. PM₁₀ and SPM concentrations surpass the Indian air quality guidelines in this Dehradun region. Previous research has shown a strong correlation between PM_{2.5} pollution and land use patterns at a micro-scale. By examining this relationship, the current study aims to propose proactive strategies for mitigating PM_{2.5} pollutions, emphasizing land use and land cover changes (LULCC) as critical factors affecting air quality. This research investigates how various LULC categories and changes in land use influence PM_{2.5} concentrations in Dehradun, Uttarakhand.

METHODS

The classification of land use and land cover was conducted using satellite imagery from LANDSAT 5 and LANDSAT 8 through a support vector machine in the study area which is Dehradun, Uttarakhand. Resulting in the generation of LULC maps for the years 2000 and 2020. At the same time, PM_{2.5} data underwent preprocessing. Ultimately, a Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) analysis was carried out to evaluate the relationship between changes in LULC and PM_{2.5} concentrations, focusing on their spatial interactions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Between 2000 and 2020, the LULCC analysis reveals that the built-up area expanded by 249.25%, while the peak recorded PM_{2.5} levels rose by 17%, increasing from 41.6 µg/m³ to 49.70 µg/m³. Over the same period, agricultural land grew by 371.86% across the study region. Areas with the most development had the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations, whereas regions with dense vegetation had the lowest. The GWR analysis indicates a significant correlation between PM_{2.5} levels and LULCC which is 0.96 which employ a good fitting effect and 94.79% of standardised residuals were between -2 and 2 which demonstrates model fitting is stable.

The table 1. compares land use and land cover changes between 2000 and 2020. Dense forests saw a decline in average values from 38.72 to 33.53 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with an increase in variability (STD rising from 1.72 to 6.34). While barren land showed a drop from 37.09 to 30.32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with greater variability (STD rising from 1.37 to 2.93). Open forests and agricultural land both saw increases in their means, from 38.56 to 41.38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 40.06 to 41.38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, while built-up areas showed growth from 40.07 to 42.42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Variability increased across most land types, indicating more fluctuations in 2020. Overall, built-up areas and agricultural land saw increases, while forests showed more inconsistent changes.

LULC TYPE	2000				2020			
	MIN	MAX	MEAN	STD	MIN	MAX	MEAN	STD
Dense Forest	34.80	41.80	38.72	1.72	27.60	49.70	33.53	6.34
Water	35.40	41.60	39.09	1.64	28.30	48.60	42.31	5.04
Barren Land	34.90	41.80	37.09	1.37	27.80	47.30	30.32	2.93
Open Forest	34.70	42.00	38.56	1.96	28.50	48.60	41.38	5.07
Built-up	35.90	41.70	40.07	1.33	28.50	49.30	42.42	4.86
Agriculture	37.70	41.90	40.06	1.04	28.50	48.60	41.38	5.07

Table 1. PM2.5 concentrations of different LULC types (units: $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

CONCLUSIONS

The results reveal a clear connection between land use/land cover changes (LULCC) and environmental factors, such as air quality (likely PM2.5 levels). It was found that built-up and agricultural areas expanded significantly between 2000 and 2020, with built-up areas showing the highest levels of PM2.5. The GWR analysis explained Local R-Squared values, confirms a strong correlation in urbanized regions, where the relationship between LULCC and PM2.5 is most pronounced. In contrast, areas with dense vegetation show weaker correlations. This suggests that urbanization has a substantial impact on air quality, while more natural landscapes help mitigate these effects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the United States Geological Survey, (USGS) and Land Remote-Sensing Satellite (LANDSAT) (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) for providing the necessary facilities to collect surface reflectance data. The authors also like to acknowledge the Dehradun Pollution Control Board, Uttarakhand UP

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ESTIMATION OF AIR POLLUTION EMISSION LOAD AND ITS DISPERSION DUE TO THE OPERATION OF A STONE CRUSHER

NEETU, HEENA CHAUHAN, SUNIL GULIA AND S.K. GOYAL

CSIR-National Environmental Engineering Research Institute Delhi Zonal Centre Naraina
Industrial Area, New Delhi 110028.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Stone Crusher, Emission Load, Dispersion Modelling, Management Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) is the dominant pollutant responsible for poor ambient air quality in Indian cities. Various sources/activities generate PM in the ambient air including the fugitive emission from the stone crusher industry and its associated activities. The stone crusher industries are growing rapidly to meet the demand of the construction industry in Real Estate, Highways, airports, etc. The main source of air pollution from stone crushers is fugitive dust emission which is very difficult to control (Gupta A, 2019; Sivacoumar et al., 2009). The major dust emission activities in a stone crushing plant, are unloading of raw material, primary, secondary and tertiary Crusher, Screening, transfer through conveyor belts, stockyard, product loading and further movement of trucks for transport of raw material as well as product. Generally, the stone crusher activities are established on the outskirts of large cities. The overall contribution of the stone crusher industry emission to the city's air pollution load is generally low compared to other sources, but its impact on the local surrounding environment can be significant. Considering, the severity of the PM pollution at the local scale due to stone crushers, the present research work is planned to understand the issues of fugitive PM emission from stone crusher industries, its air pollution load and dispersion in the surrounding area and to suggest management strategies to reduce the PM emission.

METHODS

The methodology adopted for this study includes, i) understanding the operation/functioning of the stone crusher, its process and the machinery used in a typical stone crusher, ii) a review of literature on the fugitive emission from stone crushers, pollutant emission factors, and applicable guidelines issued from various state pollution control boards, iii) estimation of emission load by multiplying the emission factor and capacity of the stone crushing in per unit time, iv) evaluate the zone of influence through dispersion modelling using AERMOD model, and v) suggestions of management strategies for reduction of PM emission from stone crusher and its dispersion. The analysis was carried out for individual stone crushers of a capacity of 1000 TPD for the winter and summer seasons using the meteorology of the Delhi NCR area.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the PM₁₀ emission load has been estimated for an individual stone crusher of capacity 1000 TPD considering no control option. The PM₁₀ emission factor was 44.50 g/ton respectively for dry conditions as per the USEPA AP-42 emission booklet (USEPA, 2003). However, for wet conditions, this emission factor is defined as 2.07 g/ton which means the water sprinkling system efficiently suppresses the dust emission by around 95%. The emission load for 1000 TPD was 44.5 kg/day for dry conditions. The prediction results

indicate the maximum PM10 ground level concentration (GLC) in the study region for 1000 TPD stone crusher capacity in the summer and winter periods were 838 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 1197 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The PM10 predicted concentration isopleths for 1000 TPD for the summer and winter seasons are shown in Fig.1 (a & b), respectively.

Further, Table 1 gives the predicted PM10 concentration in the downwind distance from the boundary of the stone crusher for different scenarios. The ground-level concentrations of PM10 were predicted 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 0.1 km, 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 0.5 km, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 1 km and <1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 2 km, in the summer period whereas during winter the pattern is more or less same with comparatively higher concentration i.e., 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 0.1 km, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 0.5 km, 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 1 km and <10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 2 km.

Figure 1: Predicted PM10 Isopleth emitted from 1000 TPD capacity stone crusher in Summer and Winter Periods

Seasons	PM ₁₀ Concentration on the downwind side ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)					
	Max. GLC	0.1 km	0.5 km	1 km	2 km	5 km
Summer Period	838	120	20	10	<1	-
Winter Period	1197	200	100	60	10	<10

Table 1: PM10 Concentration in the downwind side without sprinkling system

Considering the high particulate matter pollution level within the stone crusher premises as well as in the near field region, it is necessary to control the fugitive dust generated through the crusher's processes, equipment leakages and transport of vehicles on unpaved roads. Subject experts suggested numerous control options to reduce dust emissions. Some of them are improving the stone crushing techniques, covering the conveyor belts with suitable fabric and material transfer locations, paving the road used by trucks, wind-breaking walls, water sprinkling system throughout the material crushing and transport process, developing a greenbelt around the boundary of the plant. However, the efficiency and effectiveness of these systems are yet to be assessed. USEPA has assessed the effectiveness of water sprinkling systems fixed at machinery and found it to be very effective by reducing it by up to 95%.

Therefore, the emission load for 1000 TPD stone crusher which is 44.5 kg/day can be reduced to 2.07 kg/day by implementing a water sprinkling system at crusher units as well as along the conveyor belts and other places.

CONCLUSIONS

The uncontrolled fugitive dust emission is a major concern in stone crusher plants and generates a significant impact on air quality up to 0.5 km of the plant premises. There is a need to control this pollution through scientific and technological solutions. The establishment of stone crushers in remote locations helps in the reduction of pollution exposure to the public.

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INTER-ANNUAL VARIABILITY IN SOURCES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS USING DUAL CARBON ISOTOPES OVER A MEGA CITY IN EASTERN INDIA

M. DEVAPRASAD¹, N. RASTOGI^{1,*}, S. K. DAS², P. S. JENA¹, A. DHABI¹,
R BHUSHAN¹

¹Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad-380009, India.

²Environmental Sciences Section, Bose Institute, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosols; $\Delta^{13}C$; Radiocarbon; Source Apportionment

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization in many regions has led to a significant rise in air pollution worldwide. Among the various pollutants, carbonaceous aerosols (CA) are a major component, emitted predominantly from the incomplete combustion of biomass and fossil fuels. Studying CA is crucial due to its wide-ranging effects on human health, Earth's radiation budget, the hydrological cycle, and ocean biogeochemistry (Andreae and Crutzen, 1997; Bond et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2020). This study focuses on Kolkata, a highly populated and fast-growing urban city in India that frequently receives transported pollutants from the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) during winter. Sampling was conducted across two consecutive years, covering the post-monsoon, winter, and spring seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22. The study involved chemical (organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), water-soluble OC, and organic speciation using HR-ToF-AMS) and isotopic (^{13}C and ^{14}C) analyses of the filter based PM_{2.5} samples, with key results are discussed below.

METHODS

Twenty-four-hour averaged PM_{2.5} samples were collected (Using a High-Volume sampler) from the rooftop (~20 meters above ground) of a multi-story building at Bose Institute's Shyamnagar Campus in Kolkata. Sampling occurred between November 6, 2020, and March 16, 2021 (n = 40), and from October 22, 2021, to April 4, 2022 (n = 30). Sampling periods were classified as post-monsoon (October-November), winter (December-January), and spring (February-April), based on wind direction and daily temperatures. Concentrations of EC and OC were measured using an EC-OC analyzer, WSOC via a TOC-TN analyzer, major ions using ion chromatography, organic speciation through HR-ToF-AMS, and carbon isotopes through an isotope ratio mass spectrometer and accelerator mass spectrometer. Radiocarbon in total carbon (TC) was expressed as fbio_TC, with fbio_TC = 1 representing 100% biomass/biogenic source and fbio_TC = 0 indicating completely fossil sources.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM_{2.5} concentrations and other chemical species such as OC, WSOC, and water-soluble inorganic species (WSIS) were significantly higher during 2020-21 compared to 2021-22. PM_{2.5} concentrations were 176 ± 45 , 207 ± 27 , and 190 ± 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during post-monsoon, winter, and spring of 2020-21, respectively, compared to 134 ± 42 , 147 ± 42 , and 103 ± 32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2021-22. These reductions are attributed to factors like increased precipitation, Cyclone Jawad (Chakraborty et al., 2023), and delayed crop residue burning in the IGP (Govardhan et al., 2023) due to government restrictions on the usage of groundwater in the Punjab and Haryana regions. While PM_{2.5} concentrations varied seasonally and annually,

OC, WSOC, and WSIS followed similar trends, implying common sources of emissions and meteorological influences. Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) was the dominant WSIS, aligning with prior findings in Kolkata.

Analysis of chemical species ratios like OC/EC, WSOC/OC, and nss-K+/EC indicated reduced biomass burning (BB) in 2021-22. The OC-EC regression slope decreased from 10 in 2020-21 to 7.3 in 2021-22, reinforcing the decline in BB aerosols. The WSOC/OC ratio, AMS derived f44 showed relatively lower values indicating transported aerosol signatures are not seen in this study.

Radiocarbon-derived f_{bio_TC} (Figure 1) values ranged from 0.73 ± 0.03 in the post-monsoon, 0.70 ± 0.02 in winter, and 0.66 ± 0.02 in spring during 2020-21, showing a decline in 2021-22, where corresponding values were 0.71 ± 0.02 , 0.67 ± 0.02 , and 0.63 ± 0.02 . This decline was further supported by lower nss-K+/EC ratios and OC/EC slopes. However, no significant changes were observed in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, indicating either overlapping source signatures or alterations due to atmospheric processing. The reduction in f_{bio_TC} could be attributed to the removal of BB-dominated transported aerosols by precipitation.

Figure 1: Time series of f_{bio_TC} during post-monsoon, winter and spring seasons of the year 2020-21 and 2021-22

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study highlights significant seasonal and annual variations in PM_{2.5} and carbonaceous aerosol components over Kolkata, influenced by meteorological factors and emission sources such as biomass burning. A substantial reduction in PM_{2.5} concentrations, OC/EC ratios, and f_{bio_TC} between 2020-21 and 2021-22 reflects the impact of weather patterns like increased precipitation and policy measures limiting crop residue burning. These findings underscore the importance of continued monitoring and targeted mitigation efforts to reduce air pollution in urban areas.

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VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION OF AEROSOLS: LAYER WISE QUANTIFICATION TO TOTAL EXTINCTION OVER AN URBAN ENVIRONMENT

NITINKUMAR^{1,2}, T.A. RAJESH¹, S. RAMACHANDRAN¹, VISHNU K. DHAKER¹

¹Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad – 380058, India.

²Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, Gandhinagar – 382355, India

KEYWORDS: Lidar, Vertical Profile, Aerosols Layer, Aerosol Optical Depth

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are tiny suspended particles in the air that alter the earth's energy budget through direct and indirect effects. Globally, anthropogenic aerosols are estimated to produce a net cooling effect of approximately $-1.3 \pm 0.7 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ at the top of the atmosphere carbon (IPCC, 2021). This net cooling is composed of $-0.3 \pm 0.3 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ attributed to aerosol–radiation interactions, $-1.0 \pm 0.7 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ from aerosol–cloud interactions, about -1.15 W m^{-2} from scattering aerosols, and approximately $+0.12 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ from black carbon (IPCC, 2021). Aerosols are emitted by both anthropogenic activities and natural sources. After aerosols are emitted, they are vertically distributed by convection, advection, and other meteorological conditions, forming various layers that influence radiative forcing both locally and globally. Utilizing the vertical profile of aerosols allows for a more precise quantification of this radiative forcing and improves the uncertainty in the calculation of radiative forcing.

METHODS

Light detection and ranging (Lidar) is a state-of-the-art instrument used to study the vertical distribution of aerosols. Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad has deployed a multi-wavelength Lidar system operating at 532 nm and 1047 nm. After applying corrections for background noise (average of $> 15 \text{ km}$), range, and overlap to the raw signals, the aerosol extinction coefficient profile is derived from the below listed Lidar equation and the solution given by Fernald (Fernald, 1984).

$$P(r) = P_0 C \frac{1}{r^2} \beta(r) T^2(r)$$

- $P(r)$ is power received from range r (PhE/ μs)
- P_0 transmitted power (PhE/ μs)
- C is system constant
- $T(r)$ is $\exp[-\int_0^r \sigma(r') dr']$
- $\beta(r)$ is volume backscattering coefficient of the atmosphere ($\text{m}^{-1} \text{Sr}^{-1}$)
- $\sigma(r)$ is volume extinction coefficient of the atmosphere (m^{-1})

$$\beta(r) = \frac{S(r) \cdot \exp[2 \cdot (LR - LR_{mol}) \cdot \int_{r_{ref}}^r \beta_{mol}(r') dr]}{\frac{S(r_{ref})}{\beta(r_{ref}) + \beta_{mol}(r_{ref})} + \int_{r_{ref}}^r S(r') \exp[2 \cdot (LR - LR_{mol}) \cdot \int_{r_{ref}}^{r'} \beta_{mol}(r'') dr''] dr'}$$

- $S(r)$ = Range corrected signal
- $S(r_{ref})$ = Range corrected signal for reference height
- $\beta_{mol}(r)$ = Molecular backscattering coefficient at height r ($\text{m}^{-1} \text{Sr}^{-1}$)
- $\beta_{mol}(r_{ref})$ = Molecular backscattering coefficient at reference height r ($\text{m}^{-1} \text{Sr}^{-1}$)
- LR = Lidar ratio of aerosols (Sr)
- LR_{mol} = Lidar ratio for molecular (Sr)

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The profiles indicate significant variability in the vertical distribution of aerosols across

different months over Ahmedabad (Figure 1). The number of vertical peaks observed during February is higher than that of May (below 6 km altitudes) because during February the surface temperature and surface winds are lower than in May, which is attributed to more stratification in the vertical distribution of aerosols (Figure 1a). However, the aerosol extinction values are higher at elevated altitudes in May, indicating the dominance of convection and advection processes during the month of May which brings in the dust from the Thar Desert. Further, we have quantified the layer wise contribution of extinction to the total aerosol optical depth (AOD, the total integration of aerosol extinction coefficient is called as AOD) (Figure 1). The maximum percentage contribution is found between 0.5 to 2.0 km in both months (Figure 1). The contributions from 4.0 to 8.0 km and 8.0 to 15.0 km to the total AOD are higher during May as compared to February due to strong convection and advection processes over the study location (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Aerosol extinction profiles obtained on (a) 7th February 2024 and (b) 8th May 2024 over Ahmedabad.

CONCLUSIONS

The vertical distribution of aerosols derived using Lidar exhibits significant seasonal and altitudinal variability over Ahmedabad. An analysis of the contribution of layer wise AOD to the total columnar AOD revealed that the maximum percentage contribution to the total AOD comes from 2.0 km and below. The contributions from 8.0 km and above are higher during May as compared to February due to convection and advection processes. In contrast, during February, the temperature gradient is smaller, leading to reduced convection, with the higher altitude layers contributing less to the total AOD. The insights gained on the seasonal and altitudinal variability of aerosol extinction are crucial to deduce the altitude variations in aerosol radiative forcing, thus, reducing the uncertainty in aerosol radiative effects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Physical Research Laboratory is supported by the Department of Space, Government of India.

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PM_{2.5} AND O₃ ASSOCIATION IN URBAN AND RURAL INDIA: SPATIAL, TEMPORAL, AND METEOROLOGICAL INFLUENCES

A.S. KRISHNAVENI, B.L. MADHAVAN, CHAITHANYA D. JAIN, M. VENKATRATNAM

National Atmospheric Research Laboratory, Gadanki, 517112, India

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Ozone Deweathering, Aerosol/Air Quality Modelling

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a global challenge with significant impacts on public health, ecosystems, and climate, particularly due to pollutants like PM_{2.5} and ground-level ozone (O₃). In India, PM_{2.5} and O₃ exposure have been linked to approximately 570,000 (due to PM_{2.5}) and 12,000 (due to O₃) premature deaths (Ghude et al., 2016). The Government of India has implemented policies like the National Air Quality Monitoring Program (NAMQP) to assess air quality, along with the National Clean Air Program (NCAP) aiming to reduce PM_{2.5} levels. Also, several policies and strategies were instituted globally to improve air quality (Jonidi Jafari et al., 2021), it is important to note that not all the pollutants exhibited concurrent reduction, highlighting the complex interactions between them. O₃ and PM_{2.5} are chemically linked (Meng et al., 1997), and understanding their changing concentrations alongside meteorological conditions is crucial for managing and regulating their levels effectively. In India, studies often focus on these pollutants individually, understanding their association is critical, especially in urban areas with diverse emission sources and meteorological conditions. This study investigates the spatial and seasonal variability of PM_{2.5} and O₃ relationships across Indian urban and rural locations, focusing on key meteorological influences and the impact of emission sources, including a case study of the COVID-19 lockdown.

METHODS

This study used robust linear regression, instead of conventional linear regression, to examine the relationship between PM_{2.5} and O₃, as it better handles outliers. Weather plays a pivotal role in determining atmospheric pollutant levels and, consequently, the quality of ambient air (Stull, 1988). In this context, deweathering is a key technique for isolating emission source impacts by accounting for meteorological variations using statistical modelling. The deweathering procedure was applied through the “rmweather” package in R, utilizing a random forest model (Grange et al., 2018).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The study identified significant spatial and seasonal variability in the PM_{2.5} and O₃ relationship across Bengaluru's 7 monitoring stations, reflecting localized emissions and meteorological influences. Citywide aggregated data showed strong correlations in all seasons except monsoon, emphasizing the value of multiple-site data. In urban areas like Kolkata (5 stations) and Bengaluru, PM_{2.5} and O₃ exhibited a consistent positive relationship year-round, driven more by emission sources and atmospheric chemistry than by meteorological conditions. Conversely, negative correlations dominated in Delhi (12 stations) and Ahmedabad (9 stations), with unique seasonal variations observed in Ahmedabad. In the rural area of Gadanki, deweathering shifted the correlations from positive to negative, underscoring

the greater influence of meteorology in rural settings. Key factors such as relative humidity (RH), temperature (T), and wind direction (WD) influenced the relationship, though their impact varied by season and location. The analysis during the COVID-19 lockdown revealed the combined effects of meteorology and anthropogenic emissions on PM_{2.5} and O₃

associations.

Figure 1. Association between PM_{2.5} and O₃ across study locations before and after de-weathering, with pie charts showing the meteorological factors' (%) influence on their relationship.

CONCLUSIONS

Data from multiple sites across a city provides a more accurate representation of spatial pollutant variations. Deweathering is crucial for understanding the factors driving the PM_{2.5} and O₃ relationship, which was positive and independent of meteorological impacts in Kolkata and Bengaluru, while inversely related in Delhi and Ahmedabad, with consistent trends observed before and after deweathering. In the rural area of Gadanki, meteorological factors had a more pronounced effect, leading to significant shifts in correlations post-deweathering. Key influential factors included RH, T, and WD. The analysis during the COVID-19 lockdown highlights the combined influence of meteorology and anthropogenic emissions on this relationship, indicating the need for detailed investigations. These findings emphasize the importance of region-specific air quality management strategies that consider local meteorological and environmental conditions across India.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) for air quality data and the NASA POWER project for essential meteorological data for our study.

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SACCHARIDES COMPOSITION IN AMBIENT AEROSOLS OVER INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN DURING WINTERS

PRADHI RAJEEV¹, TARUN GUPTA² AND LESZEK MARYNOWSKI³

¹Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Patna

²Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur

³Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Silesia in Katowice, Sosnowiec – 41-200, Poland.

KEYWORDS: Saccharides, Aerosols, Indo-Gangetic Plain, Biomass Burning.

INTRODUCTION

Organic aerosols significantly influence climate, human health, radiative forcing, and atmospheric processes (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006). Saccharides serve as key biomarkers for identifying organic aerosols. These compounds are essential for understanding the origins, formation mechanisms, movement, and behavior of organic matter. Saccharides in aerosols come from various sources, including plant material burning, food and organic waste combustion, wood burning, biofuel use, coal combustion, municipal and industrial waste burning, fireworks, incense burning, and cooking (Rajeev et al., 2024). This research examines the concentration, properties, and sources of saccharides in particulate matter in the heavily polluted Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), contributing to the understanding of aerosol saccharide sources in this region.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} aerosol samples were collected on pre-baked quartz filters using a high-volume air sampler (Ecotech Instruments, Model AAS 217NL, flow rate: 0.95 m³/min) during nighttime in Prayagraj (formerly Allahabad; n = 24), India, between December 2015 and February 2016. Prayagraj (25.49°N, 81.86°E, 98 m above sea level) is a highly polluted urban area situated in the central region of the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) in Uttar Pradesh, India (Rajeev et al., 2024). Air mass back trajectory analysis for the sampling days in winter indicates the air mass arrived from the northwest and moved toward the Bay of Bengal, carrying IGP outflow. For neutral saccharide analysis, the samples were extracted and derivatized prior to GC-MS analysis; further details can be found in Rajeev et al., 2024.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The concentrations of total anhydrosaccharides, monosaccharides, disaccharides, and sugar alcohols in ambient aerosols at Prayagraj range between 1199.1 and 6477.0 ng/m³ (mean: 3697.8 ± 1609.2), 49.9 and 501.7 ng/m³ (mean: 285.4 ± 136.2), 17.5 and 137.1 ng/m³ (mean: 67.3 ± 32.9), and 42.7 and 392.1 ng/m³ (mean: 162.9 ± 101.5), respectively. Levoglucosan (LG) is the most abundant saccharide, followed by galactosan (GA), (1,6)-anhydroglucofuranose, and mannosan (MA). Table 1 compares the diagnostic ratios (LG/MA, LG/GA, MA/GA, and LG/GA+MA) from this study with other locations in India. LG/GA and LG/(GA+MA) ratios at the ALD site ranged from 20.4 to 42.5 (average 21.1 ± 6.2) and 10.8 to 24.2 (average 12.7 ± 3.6), respectively, which are notably higher than those observed at the IGP outflow (LG/GA = 5.5 ± 3.5; LG/(GA+MA) = 3.9 ± 2.1) (Bikkina et al., 2019). At the ALD site, the LG/GA ratio, falling within a range of approximately 10 to 50, suggests a potential contribution from wood combustion during winter. The ratios of LG/MA and MA/GA are influenced by factors such as the type of biomass burned, the combustion temperature, and variations linked to long-distance aerosol transport (Bikkina et al., 2019;

Marynowski and Simoneit, 2022). The saccharides found in IGP aerosols mainly originate from the combustion of hardwood, crop residues, or agricultural waste. Biomass burning, fungal spores (indicated by myo-inositol), and potentially coal combustion (quininic acid) are the major contributors of saccharides and sugar alcohols at the site.

Table 1. Comparison of diagnostic ratios (LG/MA, LG/GA, MA/GA and LG/GA+MA) of the studied sites with other sites from India.

Site	Sample	Time period	LG/MA	LG/GA	MA/GA	LG/(GA+MA)	Reference
Indian sites							
Allahabad	PM _{2.5}	Winter	31.6 ± 9.0	21.1 ± 6.2	0.7 ± 0.1	12.7 ± 3.6	This study
Delhi	PM _{2.5}	Pre-monsoon	9.5	14.5	1.5	5.7	(Kumar et al., 2017)
IGP outflow (Bay of Bengal)	PM _{2.5}	Winter	14.7	4.7	0.3	3.6	(Bikkina et al., 2019)

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of saccharides points to the burning of hardwood, crop straw, and grass as significant contributors in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). In this region, saccharides are primarily associated with biomass burning, resuspension of soil, road dust, and lignite combustion. Hardwood and agricultural waste burning are the main sources of saccharides in IGP aerosols, with hardwood combustion being the most prominent contributor, followed by agricultural waste burning, particularly during the winter season.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the support from the Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur and the University of Silesia in Katowice for conducting the research work.

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TRACKING DAILY AVERAGE AND REAL-TIME AIR QUALITY CONCENTRATION AND PM_{2.5} CHEMICAL COMPOSITION IN AN INDUSTRIAL CITY IN INDIA

VYSHNAVI K K¹, ANANDU N R¹, VIBHU VAIBHAV¹ AND SHUBHA VERMA¹

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, West Bengal

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Extreme Gradient Boosting (Xgboost) Model, Long Short-Term Memory (Lstm), Wrf-Chimere Models

INTRODUCTION

Forecasting air pollution is crucial because of its influence on human health, especially in metropolitan regions. Air pollution forecasting provides prior alerts, enhances the standard of living, and supports environmental sensing research, enabling authorities to implement essential measures (Lee et al., 2020). Machine Learning (ML) models have demonstrated superior accuracy, adaptability, and self-correction capabilities, making them suitable for developing air pollution forecasting systems in recent times. The Extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) model outperformed the Random Forest Algorithm and Deep learning models in predicting the concentration of PM_{2.5} (Particulate matter having an aerodynamic diameter of less than 2.5 μ m) in Tehran (Joharestani et al., 2019). Studies conducted in Kolkata and Delhi (Bera et al., 2021) have shown that Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) performed better than Multi Linear Regression (MLR) and Support Vector Regression (SVR). Aggarwal et al., 2021 utilized the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to predict PM_{2.5} levels in 15 prominent Indian cities. Liu et al., 2022 created a method to monitor the chemical composition of PM_{2.5} daily in China by integrating WRF-CMAQ models, ground observations, and machine learning algorithms. Previous studies have primarily focused on PM_{2.5} forecasts, neglecting other air quality parameters like Carbon monoxide (CO), Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and Ozone (O₃) and PM_{2.5} chemical composition forecasts. Although India has been greatly affected by air pollution, there is a lack of research on air pollution forecasting, highlighting the importance of this work. The research uses machine learning models to forecast air quality parameters and PM_{2.5} chemical compositions, that allow government officials to provide timely warnings and make appropriate preparations.

METHODS

The study is conducted in an industrial town in Uttar Pradesh's central-western region, Kanpur. The study utilized the ML models XGBoost and LSTM to forecast daily average and hourly data for five air quality parameters, and designed an XGBoost model to forecast the PM_{2.5} chemical compositions (Black carbon (BC), Nitrate (NO₃-), Sulfate (SO₄2-), Ammonia (NH₄+) and Organic carbon (OC)). The meteorological and air quality data obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) from 2016 to 2023 is used in the study to forecast air quality parameters. The CPCB data and the modeled PM_{2.5} species ratios from the WRF-CHIMERE model are used to forecast PM_{2.5} species concentration. Root means square error (RMSE), Coefficient of Determination (R² score), and daily percentage error are metrics for model validation. The model is split as per time series split, trained using 80% of data, and tested or validated using 20% of data. The raw data obtained need to be initially pre-processed to improve the data quality by performing missing data correction, outlier removal and normalization of the dataset. The model is trained by optimizing the

hyperparameters using a grid search method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The designed XGBoost model validated for Kanpur with a lower RMSE and R2 score in the range of 0.86-0.96 for all the five air quality parameters (CO, SO₂, NO₂, O₃ and PM_{2.5}). The validation of real-time data (hourly data) with the designed LSTM models performs well. The LSTM model is designed to perform real-time data forecasts due to its supremacy in capturing complex real-time meteorological and air quality data. Overall, the designed ML models produced satisfactory results in validation and forecasting for daily and real-time data, yielding lower percentage errors (less than 15-20%, four days in advance). The model also aimed to predict PM_{2.5} species concentration for Black carbon (BC), Nitrate (NO₃⁻), Sulfate (SO₄²⁻), Ammonia (NH₄⁺) and Organic carbon (OC), with an R2 score in the range of 0.94-0.99. Figure 1 (a to e) validates that the observed ratios from the WRF-CHEMERE model are well predicted using the designed XGBoost model. Figure 1 (f) shows the trend in chemical composition, with OC concentration dominating the cumulative PM_{2.5} concentrations. Species-wise concentration forecasts help in the source-based mitigation measures taken by government authorities.

Figure 1.(a) to (e) Validation plot of observed and predicted ratios of chemical composition
(f) PM_{2.5} species concentration segmentation, in Kanpur

CONCLUSIONS

The designed XGBoost (daily average data) and LSTM (real-time data) model validated with a lower RMSE, R2 score in the range of 0.86-0.96, and with lower percentage error (less than 15-20%, four days in advance) for all five air quality parameters. The designed ML models produced satisfactory results in validation and forecasting for daily and real-time data, yielding lower percentage errors. The outcomes of the present study have substantial implications for environmental policy, public health in highly polluted locations, and the broader application of ML in environmental research. The PM_{2.5} speciated concentration forecast produced satisfactory results, which help government authorities in source-based mitigation.

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EVALUATING HYPERLOCAL AIR POLLUTION IN BHUBANESWAR: INSIGHTS FROM LOW-COST SENSOR-BASED MEASUREMENTS

A. ASUTOSH¹, M. MONALIN²

¹Aurassure, iHub, E/43, Infocity Ave, Patia, Bhubaneswar, Odisha 751024, India.

²Aerosol and Trace Gases Laboratory, Environment and Sustainability Department, CSIR-Institute of Minerals and Materials Technology (CSIR-IMMT), Bhubaneswar, Odisha

KEYWORDS: Low-Cost Sensors, Air Pollution, Smart City, Hyperlocal Air Quality.

INTRODUCTION

High levels of air pollution in cities pose significant health risks, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), as noted by the World Health Organization (WHO). India has 22 of the world's 30 most polluted cities, with Odisha state being notably affected. While cities like Delhi and Mumbai often receive attention, Bhubaneswar has been identified for poor air quality due to vehicle emissions, road dust, and industrial activities. To address this issue, accurate ground-level Particulate Matter (PM) measurement is essential for effective pollution management. This study monitored PM levels in Bhubaneswar using manual and sensor-based methods, allowing for a comprehensive air quality assessment and supporting targeted pollution reduction strategies (Mallik et al., 2019; Panda et al., 2016).

METHODS

Aurassure has implemented advanced IoT-based sensor devices and cloud systems for air quality monitoring in Bhubaneswar. A network covers a five-square-kilometer grid with 20 strategically placed sensors, collecting real-time data on pollutants like PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} and CO₂ and SO₂. Supported by the Software Technology Parks of India (STPI), stationary sensors gather data from various environments. These sensors use 4G LTE technology for secure data transmission, filtering out erroneous data with algorithms. Regular calibration ensures accurate measurements, while a diagnostic module tracks any malfunctions. A collocation study conducted from March 2023 to April 2024 confirms results align with United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) performance targets for PM_{2.5}. This study emphasizes the importance of precise air quality monitoring and the reliability of Aurassure's technology.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The sensors-based measured data shows a significant correlation with PM derived from MERRA-2 reanalysis data ($r^2 = 0.6749$) and with gravimetrically measured data from the CSIR-IMMT location site ($r^2 = 0.8807$). Figure 1 identifies the hotspot based on the low-cost sensor data in the city map for both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. Thus, two individual sensor stations exceeded the NAAQS for both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ over 50% of the time. The primary and minor sectors contributing to air pollution in the city have already been identified, and the emission hotspots have been quantified in a previous study in Bhubaneswar (Sahu et al., 2023). A positive weekend impact can be seen at almost every station in the city, with the values ranging from 1.80 to 12.39 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 1.55 to 12.34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ respectively, showing that the PM concentration was higher on weekends than on weekdays. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ have a negative correlation with wind speed (WS) and temperature, indicating that high PM concentrations are associated with stagnant conditions with lower

wind speeds and low temperatures. The highest PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations were observed with wind speeds lower than 2 m/s, predominantly coming from the north and northwest directions. Conversely, the lowest PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations are recorded when WS exceeds 6 m/s, primarily from the southeast direction. These findings confirm that PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations varied significantly with WD.

Figure 1. Hotspot identification based on low-cost sensor data.

CONCLUSIONS

Reliable air pollution assessment is essential for effective air quality management. Various methods, including low-cost sensors (LCS), gravimetric systems, and satellite data, have strengths and weaknesses. This study evaluated a 20-device LCS network in Bhubaneswar, finding that LCS data closely matched gravimetric and satellite data (R^2 values of 0.88 and 0.67). The data showed a weekend improvement in air quality and highlighted the influence of meteorological factors. Overall, LCS offers a cost-effective, reliable means for urban air quality monitoring, supporting pollution mitigation strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge Google LLC, Our esteemed technology partner and sponsor. Their unwavering support and collaboration have played a pivotal role in the success of the "Hyperlocal Air Quality Monitoring Network for Bhubaneswar" project. Their expertise and resources have enabled us to implement state-of-the-art monitoring solutions and gather valuable insights into the air quality of the city. M.M. is acknowledged by CSIR-IMMT for all the research support provided to her.

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IMPACT OF NATURAL RAINFALL ON REDUCING WINTER AIR POLLUTION IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

JASMINE MARY KURIAKOSE¹, MARINA ALOYSIUS¹, VIJAYAKUMAR S NAIR²

¹Assumption College, Changanassery- 686101, Kerala, India

²Space Physics Laboratory, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Thiruvananthapuram- 695022,

Keywords: Particulate Matter, Winter, Rain, Air Quality.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) experiences severe air pollution during winter, primarily due to elevated levels of PM_{2.5}, which pose significant health risks to millions of people. Natural rainfall has the potential to reduce these pollution levels by removing particulate matter from the atmosphere. This study aims to investigate the effect of rainfall on PM_{2.5} concentrations across key locations in the IGP during the winter season, focusing on the role of rain events in mitigating air pollution. Data from 11 monitoring stations, including urban and rural areas, were analysed to assess how varying rain intensities influence PM_{2.5} reductions. By examining metrics like the coefficient of variation, frequency of extreme pollution events, and shifts in mode and median values, the study provides insights into the effectiveness of rainfall in improving air quality. The findings offer valuable evidence for exploring natural and artificial rainfall as potential strategies for reducing winter air pollution in the IGP.

METHODS

Data were collected for 11 monitoring stations maintained by Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) located in highly polluted urban and rural areas, in IGP. The stations are: Panchkula, Kanpur, Muzaffarpur, Punjab Agricultural University, Amritsar, Varanasi, Noida, Faridabad, Institute of Human Behaviour and Allied Sciences (IHBAS) Delhi, R K Puram, and Gaya. PM_{2.5} data over multiple winter seasons in these stations were analysed together with the rainfall data from India Meteorological Department (IMD). To observe changes in air quality, PM_{2.5} data from rainy and non-rainy days were compared. Changes in the spread, frequency distributions, frequency of extreme events, and shifts in mode and median values were analysed for each station.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of PM_{2.5} data from eleven stations across the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) revealed a significant impact of rainfall on reducing winter air pollution. On non-rainy days, PM_{2.5} levels frequently surpassed the Indian air quality standard of 60 µg/m³, often exceeding this limit by two to three times. In contrast, rainy days consistently exhibited a substantial reduction in PM_{2.5} concentrations, with reductions ranging between 25% and 60% depending on the station. However, some anomalies were observed where rainfall did not significantly reduce or even increase PM_{2.5} concentrations. These isolated cases can be attributed to meteorological factors, including wind, humidity and higher regional emissions (Li et al., 2024). Additionally, regional differences in air pollution sources, such as industrial emissions, agricultural practices, and vehicular traffic, may influence how rainfall impacts PM_{2.5} levels. The analysis reveals that rainfall has a significant impact on reducing PM_{2.5} concentrations across the IGP, as evidenced by several key metrics. The coefficient of variation (CV) decreases with increasing rainfall, indicating a reduction in data variability. However, stations such as IHBAS exhibited an opposite trend, with the CV increasing with

more rainfall, likely due to factors like varying meteorological conditions. The number of extreme PM_{2.5} concentration events (above the 95th percentile) significantly decreased with increased rainfall at stations such as Varanasi, Gaya, and Panchkula. For instance, Varanasi saw extreme events drop from 10 to zero as rain events increased from 2 to 14. Even stations like Faridabad, which did not show a reduction in the data spread, saw fewer extreme pollution events with more rain. The calculated fractional difference due to rain indicates that heavier rain tends to result in more significant pollution decreases. The fractional difference in PM_{2.5} due to rain was defined as follows.

$$\Delta PM\% = (PM_{rain} - PM_{control}) \times 100 / PM_{control}$$

Where,

$\Delta PM\%$ - Percentage of fractional difference in PM_{2.5} concentrations.

PM rain - PM_{2.5} concentrations on the day of the rain event.

PM control - PM_{2.5} concentrations on the day before the rain event.

However, even moderate rainfall events proved effective in mitigating pollution, underscoring the potential of rainfall as a natural intervention for improving winter air quality in the IGP.

Figure 1. The plot of the percentage of fractional difference in PM_{2.5} due to different rain intensities.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that winter rainfall plays a crucial role in reducing PM_{2.5} concentrations across the Indo-Gangetic Plain, with an overall decrease of up to 60% in some locations. The relationship between rainfall intensity and PM_{2.5} reduction suggests that natural rainfall could serve as a viable strategy to mitigate air pollution in this region. The decrease in PM_{2.5} variability, extreme events, and median concentrations across the IGP suggests rainfall could serve as a viable solution for addressing winter air pollution. The strong impact of even minimal rainfall further underscores its potential as a mitigation tool in heavily polluted areas like the IGP.

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INVESTIGATION ON AIR QUALITY PARAMETERS OVER VARIOUS CITIES IN KERALA

JAYAMOL. P¹ AND MARINA ALOYSIOUS¹

¹Department of Physics, Assumption College Autonomous, Changanassery, Kottayam

KEYWORDS: CPCB, AIR POLLUTION, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀, AQI.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution and related air quality deterioration have far-reaching impacts including adverse impacts on human health, agriculture, ecosystems, the environment, and the climate. Air pollution is influenced by various factors, including industrial activities, emissions from power plants and vehicles, open landfills and incineration, fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning, ore smelting, excessive irrigation, and changes in land use and land cover. Particulate matter (PM) is a major group of pollutants composed of small solid or liquid particles that are suspended in the air. This study is focused on evaluating air pollutants and air quality over various places in Kerala.

METHODS

The seasonal distribution of particulate matter pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) and the air quality (AQI) at all the nine CPCB stations (Plamoodu, Kariavattom, Polayathode, Vyttila, Udyogamandal, Kacheripady, Corporation ground, Palayam, Thavakkara) across six districts in Kerala (Thiruvananthapuram, Kollam, Ernakulam, Thrissur, Kannur, and Kozhikode) over a four-year period (2020-2023) is studied. Analysis has been done for four seasons: Pre-Monsoon/ Summer (March, April, and May), Monsoon (June, July, August, and September), Post-monsoon (October, November) and Winter (December, January, and February). The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio is also analysed to assess the impact of anthropogenic emissions on rising pollution levels. The daily data of various pollutants are collected from the Central Pollution Control Board

(CPCB)<https://airquality.cpcb.gov.in/ccr/#/caaqm-dashboard-all/caaqm-landing/data>.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

a. Mean Seasonal Variations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀

The average seasonal distribution of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ from 2020 to 2023 shows a clear pattern across all stations, with the highest concentrations observed during the winter and the lowest during the monsoon season. In Kochi, particulate matter pollution is significantly higher in the post-monsoon season compared to the pre-monsoon season, which is contrary to the general trend observed in most areas. Compared to Kochi, Kollam has higher values of particulate matter during pre-monsoon and monsoon. Eloor, despite being an industrial area, shows the lowest winter PM_{2.5} levels compared to other monitoring stations. On an average Kochi (Ernakulam) shows the highest PM_{2.5} values and Kollam shows the highest PM₁₀ values, whereas Plamoodu (Thiruvananthapuram) experiences the lowest particulate matter pollution.

b. Mean Seasonal Air Quality Index(AQI)

All stations report higher AQI values during the winter season, indicating poorer air quality.

Kochi shows the highest AQI values especially in winter, while Plamoodu has the lowest, reflecting significantly better air quality in Thiruvananthapuram compared to Ernakulam during this season. For every station, AQI values in the post-monsoon season are higher than during the monsoon, with Eloor being the exception. Throughout the year, Plamoodu maintains an AQI within the 0-50 range (good category), except in the winter season. In contrast, AQI levels at other stations for most seasons fall between 51-100 (satisfactory), which may cause breathing discomfort to sensitive groups. During post-monsoon and winter, Kochi's AQI exceeds 100 (101-200, moderately polluted), potentially leading to respiratory issues for individuals with heart and lung diseases, children, and the elderly. Kollam also has a slightly elevated AQI (~101) during winter, just above the satisfactory level. Overall, Kochi records the highest AQI across seasons, indicating poorer air quality, while Plamoodu consistently records the lowest, signifying comparatively cleaner air

c. Mean Seasonal PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio

The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio reflects the proportion of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) to coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀) and provides insights into the sources of pollution. Higher ratios indicate that pollution is primarily from anthropogenic sources, while lower ratios suggest a significant presence of coarse particles, often from natural sources. The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio is observed to be the highest during winter at six of the nine stations. In winter, seven out of nine stations report PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratios above 0.52, indicating a very slight dominance of fine particulate matter. Across all seasons, Kochi consistently has the highest PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratios on average, highlighting a higher proportion of fine particulate pollution compared to other stations. The probability distribution (PDF) of PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ shows that the pollution at Kochi is primarily derived from anthropogenic sources.

Figure 1. Mean Seasonal Variations of AQI

CONCLUSIONS

Air pollution is the highest in Kerala every year during winter compared to the other seasons. This could be because of the lack of removal of particulate matter via wet scavenging, and the lower boundary layer height during the winter, which limits the dispersion of pollutants, resulting in higher values near the surface. Both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ show this seasonal trend, with higher values in winter and least during monsoon. On Kerala, Kochi (Ernakulam) shows the highest PM_{2.5} values and Kollam the highest PM₁₀ values, whereas Plamoodu (Thiruvananthapuram) experiences the lowest particulate matter pollution. The seasonal distribution of AQI also shows a similar trend of higher values during winter compared to monsoon. On an average, the AQI over Kochi has the highest values pointing towards poor air quality over the region while the lowest values over Plammodu clearly shows that air quality is the best over this region. Compared to PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, the variability in the seasonal

distribution of $PM_{2.5}/PM_{10}$ is less. Even then, most of the stations during the winter season show slight dominance of fine particulate matter over coarse particles ($PM_{2.5}/PM_{10} > 0.52$). On an average Kochi has the highest $PM_{2.5}/PM_{10}$ values. Probability Distribution Function analysis reveals that the majority of the pollution in Kochi is from fine particles. The analysis reveals that Kochi (Ernakulam) experiences the highest levels of air pollution, predominantly from anthropogenic (human-made) sources. In contrast, Plamoodu (Thiruvananthapuram) records the lowest particulate matter pollution, with higher contributions from dust sources.

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URBAN ROADSIDE AEROSOL MEASUREMENTS IN DELHI CITY: COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DIFFERENT EMISSIONS CONDITIONS

KANAGARAJ RAJAGOPAL¹, S. RAMACHANDRAN², RAJEEV KUMAR MISHRA^{1*}

¹Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University, Delhi, India

²Space and Atmospheric Sciences Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad.

KEYWORDS: Urban Aerosols, Roadside Measurements, Transport Emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Urban regions are known for complex mixtures from different aerosol sources of aerosols (Rajagopal et al., 2024). Among the different sources, transport sources play a major role in the urban regions (Rajagopal et al., 2023). The engine exhaust of various vehicles emits particles in different size ranges based on the type of fuel used and ignition technique used (Mohan, et al., 2024 a). The emitted particles interact with different atmospheric conditions in roadside conditions making it complex to mitigate (Mohan et al., 2024 b). The aerosol concentration in the urban region is directly proportional to the intensity of the sources. In the present study, urban aerosols measured during 2021 and 2023 during different transport emission scenarios are analyzed to estimate the role of transportation sources in aerosol concentration in roadside conditions.

METHODS

STUDY AREA AND INSTRUMENTATION

The measurements of aerosol concentrations were performed in a busy urban street corridor adjacent to the Delhi Technological University campus, which is located in the northwest part of Delhi. The study region is a proper representation of the urban roadside microenvironment. The measurements done using a scanning mobility particle size with an L-DMA having the capacity to measure particles from 10 nm to 1090 nm are used in the study. The measured data are classified into five major seasons (winter, spring, summer, monsoon, and autumn) and analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The total particle number concentration (PNC) during the years 2021 and 2023 shows variations based on the intensity of emission sources. Especially during summer 2021, when restrictions for the transportation sources were in place, PNC is less compared to the spring, whereas PNC in summer 2023 is higher than in spring due to the increase in emissions from transportation sources (Fig. 1). The PNC is less during monsoon in both years. The PNC is higher during the winter season, followed by autumn.

Figure 1. Seasonal variation of N_{total} (10 to 1000 nm) particle number concentration during 2021 and 2023 over Delhi.

The percentage contribution of different-size particles to the total PNC between 2021 and 2023 reveals that the Aitken mode particles remain more or less the same (varying within $\pm 5\%$). The concentrations in the nucleation and accumulation modes change between the two years as the particles in this size range are more influenced by the surrounding environmental conditions in the atmosphere. Thus, seasonal changes in the contribution of different sizes dominate in smaller and larger particles.

Figure 2. Percentage contribution of different size fractions of aerosols (nucleation (10 to 30 nm), Aitken (50 to 100 nm) and accumulation (100 to 1000 nm) to total PNC) during the years 2021 and 2023 over Delhi.

CONCLUSIONS

The concentration and behavior of urban aerosols in different seasons (winter, spring, summer, monsoon, and autumn) in the megacity of Delhi are analyzed. The results suggest that urban aerosol measurement and mitigation are two of the major areas to focus on to reduce the exposure of urban residents. Developing better emission standards and low-emitting engines and fuel technology in transportation sectors can significantly reduce urban aerosol concentrations. Reducing emissions in urban regions will pave the way for a sustainable lifestyle, one of the major sustainable development goals (SDGs).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The measurements were conducted in the Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University.

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CHEMICAL COMPOSITION ANALYSIS OF PARTICULATE MATTER USING DIFFERENT CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

P. K. CHAUHAN, R. TIWARI, S. PRAJAPATI, D. K. GUPTA AND A. K. SINGH

Atmospheric Physics Lab., Department of Physics, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221005, India.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Sem-Eds, ION Chromatography, AAS.

INTRODUCTION

Pollution, particularly in metropolitan and suburban areas, poses significant environmental challenges, with air pollution among the most critical issues. Particulate matter (PM) is a major contributor and consists of fine solid particles and liquid droplets suspended in the Earth's atmosphere, originating from natural and man-made sources like vehicle exhaust, industrial emissions, and agricultural practices (Alang and Aggarwal, 2022). These particles, composed of inorganic ions, metals, and other toxic substances such as Cd, Cr, Pb, and Ni, pose severe health risks and affect the environment (Pipal et al., 2011). The rapid industrialization and urbanization globally have raised concerns about heavy metal pollution, released into the atmosphere through processes like mining, manufacturing, and waste disposal. These pollutants accumulate in air, water, and soil, posing significant risks to ecosystems and human health (Pratap et al., 2020). In addition to analysing elemental composition, observing heavy metals and ionic species accurately within aerosols is crucial. The purpose of this study is to investigate the chemical characteristics of PM samples in the ambient air in Varanasi, to gain a deeper understanding of particle heterogeneity and regional complexity.

METHODS

The experimental site was at Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, located in the central Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), a densely populated city, that experiences high aerosol loading due to its mixed urban sprawl, industries, and weather patterns. The samples were weighed using the gravimetric method, dried to remove moisture, and stored in protective cases to prevent contamination or chemical alteration. The collected filter samples were sectioned into small pieces, gold-coated for conductivity, and examined via scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM provided high-resolution images, while energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to analyse the elemental composition of PM, revealing its chemical structure and potential impacts. Ion chromatography (IC) was employed to analyse the water-soluble ionic content in PM samples. One-quarter of each sample was dissolved in Milli-Q water through ultrasonic extraction. The extract was filtered twice before being analysed for cationic and anionic species using a high-precision IC instrument. For heavy metal analysis, filter samples were digested in nitric and hydrochloric acids. The mixture was heated, filtered, and diluted with Milli-Q water before being analysed using a Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1(a, b) represents the SEM images that showed the morphological characteristics of PM samples, with varied particle shapes including rectangular, irregular, and crystalline forms. Irregular particles suggest secondary formation from industrial and construction

activities. Tables show the weight percentage of elements found in the samples corresponding to figures 1(a) and 1(b) which represent the presence of high quantities of iron and Zinc respectively. After elemental analysis of the samples, Fe and Zn were also found in a higher quantity in heavy metals analysis (Figure 2). This figure shows the pie chart of heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Pb, Cu, Mn, Ni, Cr, and Cd) present in samples. High concentration of Fe could be due to primarily emissions from industrial activities and vehicle exhaust. The concentration of Pb could have originated from coal and gasoline combustion. High Zn concentration might be linked to industrial processes, and Cu comes from mining, metalworking, and combustion of fuels. Ni concentration could be due to wood burning, fossil fuel combustion, and vehicular emissions. The concentration of Mn may originate from soil re-entrainment and industrial emissions, and the presence of Cr might be due to vehicular emissions. Figure 3 shows the concentrations of ions present in the samples. In PM samples, SO_4^{2-} is found to be the most abundant anion, followed by NO_3^- , Cl^- , and F^- . For cations, Ca^{2+} is found to be the most prominent, followed by Na^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , and K^+ . The high levels of SO_4^{2-} in the samples could be linked to combustion sources, including vehicle emissions, industrial processes, and the burning of biomass and fossil fuels. Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} may be originated from crustal materials and road dust.

Figure 1. Morphology and weight % contribution of elements present in PM samples.

Figure 2. Percentage contribution of heavy metal concentrations present in PM samples

CONCLUSIONS

The key findings of this study can be summarized as follows:

- SEM images revealed diverse particle shapes, such as spherical, and irregular forms that represent the Fe and Zn elements, associated with combustion processes, soil dust, and industrial emissions.
- IC analysis identified major ions in PM, including SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , Cl^- , Ca^{++} , Na^+ , and NH_4^+ , with SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- levels rising in winter due to increased anthropogenic activities and atmospheric conditions trapping pollutants. These ions are formed from precursor gases like SO_2 , NO_x , and NH_3 , while Ca^{++} and Na^+ linked to natural sources like soil and dust.
- Heavy metals like Fe, Zn, Pb, and Cu were found in higher concentrations in PM samples, primarily from industrial emissions and vehicular exhaust. These metals pose serious health risks, emphasizing the need for stricter regulation and monitoring in industrial areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors (PKC, RT) are thankful to UGC for providing financial support under the UGC-JRF

scheme. Work is partially supported by the IoE Program to BHU (Scheme No: 6031).

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OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PM_{2.5} EMISSIONS FROM LIGHT-DUTY GOODS AND HEAVY-DUTY VEHICLES IN ON-ROAD OPERATIONS IN INDIA

MOHD SHAHZAR KHAN AND GAZALA HABIB

Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Department of Civil Engineering,
New Delhi – 110016, India.

KEYWORDS: On-Road Vehicular Emissions, Black Carbon, Mass Absorption Cross-Section.

INTRODUCTION

The on-road transport sector is one of the important sectors that contributes to urban air pollution and affects climate change and human health. Diesel powered vehicles are the dominant fuel consuming vehicles in Indian on-road fleets which are responsible for particulate emissions (Pandey and Venkataraman, (2014)). Tailpipe emissions of diesel vehicles consist of carbonaceous aerosol including particulate matter and light absorbing carbon. Mass emission and its composition from the vehicle tailpipe depend on many factors such as type of fuel, vehicle technology, maintenance and driving characteristics. Jaiprakash and Habib, (2017) suggested that the tailpipe emissions from the laboratory (chassis dynamometer) and model studies are significantly different from emissions measured through on-road measurement. Aerosol absorption and scattering properties such as mass absorption cross-section (MAC) and mass scattering coefficients (MSC) play an important role in regional climate assessment. Therefore, in the present study, the real-world mass absorption cross-section and mass scattering coefficient from exhaust emissions of light-duty (goods) and heavy-duty vehicles (Trucks and tractors) will be presented in Indian on-road conditions.

METHODS

On-road measurement of emissions from light motor vehicles (LMV)-goods, tractors and trucks were performed in real world conditions in West Bengal and Bihar using a versatile source sampling system (VS3). In VS3, a fraction of exhaust enters through an isokinetic particle sampling probe into a dilution tunnel designed for homogenous mixing, negligible wall losses and complete aerosol quenching. A turbulent and instantaneous mixing of exhaust with 40-60 times zero air inside the dilution tunnel exhibits the dilution process that happens in the atmosphere. Portability, low power requirement and continuous clean air supply are other important attributes of VS3 for its on-field use. The emission measurements were conducted on rural roads and highways with vehicles of different emission norms on a 15-30 km mixed traffic route daily followed by the driver. PM mass was collected on different filter substrates for gravimetric and chemical analysis. The particle absorption and scattering were measured with a 7-wavelength aethalometer (AE33) and Nephelometer (IN102) respectively. The carbonaceous fraction of PM_{2.5} was determined on a Quartz filter using a Thermal optical reflectance analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

BC and EC concentrations in the vehicle exhaust were found in the range of 5000-40000 µg/m³ for the tractors, LMV goods and trucks. A correlation plot was made for BC and EC concentration as shown in figure 1 and found a good correlation between them with an R² value of 0.97. Mass absorption cross-section (m²/gPM_{2.5}) was presented in a box plot as shown in figure 2 for tractor, LMV-goods and truck. MAC value was found higher for tractor

(1.4-10.4) and truck (4.4-8.3) as compared to LMV-goods (0.8-5.3) due to having a lower concentration of BC for LMV-goods. Variations of MAC for tractors, LMV-goods and trucks of different emission norms on rural roads and highways will be discussed in the paper. Mass scattering coefficients will also be discussed in the paper for the same vehicle categories.

Figure 1. Correlation plot for black carbon and elemental carbon concentration in exhaust for all sets of experiments of the tractor, LMV-goods and truck vehicles.

Figure 2. Mass absorption cross-section for tractor, LMV-goods and truck for all set of experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

The mass concentration of EC determined from the TOR method has shown a good correlation with BC obtained from an aethalometer (Figure 1). The mass absorption cross-section of particles emitted from trucks and tractors was higher than those from LMV-good (Figure 2). A strong dependence of MACs on vehicle age has been observed. The finding from this study has implications in climate assessment and framing the policies for on-road use of vehicles for improving local air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change under the NCAP-COALESCCE project {Grant No.14/10/2014-CC (Vol. II)}. The views expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Min-istry. The Ministry does not endorse any products or commercial ser-vices mentioned in this publication.

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CONTRIBUTION OF SECONDARY ORGANIC AEROSOL TO WATER SOLUBLE ORGANIC CARBON FRACTION OF PM_{2.5} OVER JAMMU IN THE NORTH-WESTERN HIMALAYAS

KONIKA SHARMA¹, RAKESH KUMAR², ANKIT TANDON¹ AND SHWETA YADAV¹

¹Department of Environmental Sciences, Central University of Jammu, Samba, J&K, India

²Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Jammu, Jammu, J&K, India

KEYWORDS: Organic Carbon, Secondary Organic Carbon, Water Soluble Organic Carbon, North-Western Himalayas.

INTRODUCTION

Organic Carbon (OC) associated with aerosols, is emitted directly as particles i.e. Primary Organic Carbon or formed through the gas to particle conversion in the ambient atmosphere i.e. Secondary Organic Carbon (SOC). A significant part of PM_{2.5} is made up of SOC. In addition to biomass burning emissions, secondary organic aerosol (SOA) in the atmosphere contributes to water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC) through photochemical reactions of volatile organic compounds (Tripathi et al., 2024). Understanding the behaviour of WSOC for chemical properties and elucidating the sources of carbonaceous aerosols is crucial. Only a few WSOC-focused studies are reported from India (Ram and Sarin 2010, 2011; Rastogi et al., 2014; Sudheer et al., 2015; Rajput et al., 2013). Perhaps this is the first study carried out on WSOC in fine aerosols over the North-Western Himalayas (NWH). In the present study, a comprehensive one-year investigation has been carried out in the Jammu region of NWH to understand the spatio-temporal variability in the contribution of SOA to WSOC in PM_{2.5} and its further implications for regional climate and environmental health.

METHODS

The PM_{2.5} sampling was done on a Quartz membrane filter using a high volume sampler at three signature sites (background, industrial, and residential) from June 2021 to May 2022. The OC-EC analysis was done on the Thermo-Optical Lab OC-EC Aerosol Analyzer (Sunset Laboratory); whereas, the WSOC analysis was done on the Total Organic Carbon (TOC) Analyzer (Shimadzu). SOC was estimated using EC- the tracer method.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The WSOC concentration in PM_{2.5} ranged from 1.51µgC/m³ to 15.42µgC/m³ at the background site, CUJ; from 1.36µgC/m³ to 14.09µgC/m³ at an industrial site, BBN; and from 1.03µgC/m³ to 14.94µgC/m³ at a residential site, KCN. The annual average WSOC concentration was 5.45±3.50µgC/m³, 5.44±2.88µgC/m³ and 5.97±3.48µgC/m³ at background, industrial, and residential respectively. The WSOC abundance contributed ~50% of OC which is higher than that reported from other urban locations in India. On an annual average basis, WSOC constituted ~11% of PM_{2.5} mass at Jammu, with the highest contribution (12.47±4.93%) at residential sites. Season-wise and site-wise WSOC concentration is listed in Table 1.

Seasons	WSOC ($\mu\text{gC}/\text{m}^3$)		
	Background	Industrial	Residential
Winter	13.61 \pm 1.59	8.68 \pm 3.14	9.12 \pm 4.07
Spring	5.23 \pm 2.07	5.10 \pm 2.39	5.39 \pm 2.25
Summer-monsoon	2.86 \pm 0.97	3.21 \pm 1.39	3.24 \pm 1.29
Autumn	6.46 \pm 3.35	5.45 \pm 1.50	6.65 \pm 3.23

Table 1. Spatio-temporal variations in the average WSOC concentration over three different sites over four seasons.

The average WSOC/OC ratio was found to be the highest at the background site (0.53 \pm 0.15) similar to that reported by Ram and Sarin, 2010 for the high-altitude site; while the ratios observed at the industrial (0.45 \pm 0.14) and residential (0.47 \pm 0.13) sites were similar to that reported for a rural site in their study. The higher WSOC/OC ratios could be due to the ageing and atmospheric conversion of organic compounds amid their advective transport, or SOA formation (Ram and Sarin, 2010, 2011; Rastogi et al., 2014; Sudheer et al., 2015; Rajput et al., 2013; Tripathi et al., 2024). Regression analysis of WSOC on estimated SOC showed a strong correlation between them at all three sites ($R^2 > 0.64$) as shown in Figure 1. Background and residential sites showed maximum correlation indicating towards increased contribution of SOA formation at these sites (Figure 1 (A) and (C)) whereas scattered relationship at industrial sites indicates additional POC emissions to WSOC.

Figure 1. Annual distribution of WSOC versus SOC concentrations in PM_{2.5} at (A) background site, CUJ, (B) industrial site, BBN and (C) residential site, KCN.

CONCLUSIONS

The WSOC contributed up-to ~11% of PM_{2.5} mass and ~50% of the OC fraction. Strong correlations between WSOC and SOC confirmed WSOC as a reliable and independent proxy for SOA formation in NWH. The results of our study are significant for the atmospheric processing and SOA formation of carbonaceous aerosols and their implication on regional climate processes as well as environmental health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

SY acknowledges the financial support received from JKPC as research project Source Apportionment of Ambient Aerosols and Carrying Capacity in Non-Attainment Cities of Jammu/Srinagar, from MoES, GoI and SNSF in the form of Indo-Swiss joint research project MoES/INDO-SWISS/2/2022-PC-), from DST as PURSE grant SR/PURSE/2023/204. KS acknowledges the University Grants Commission for providing financial assistance in the form of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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QUANTIFICATION AND SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF BACKGROUND BLACK CARBON AEROSOLS OVER INDIA

VINOJ V*, SMARAN MAJI

*Indian Institute of Technology Bhubaneswar, Jatni – 752050, Odisha, India
School of Earth, Ocean, and Climate Sciences

KEYWORDS: Air Pollution, Black Carbon, Regional Air Quality, Pollution Transport, Background Aerosols

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) pollution poses a significant and growing threat to public health and environmental quality across India. While mitigation efforts often target urban hotspots, the pervasive nature and quantitative impact of background BC (resulting from regional and long-range transport) levels remain poorly understood. This study aims to estimate baseline/background BC mass concentrations using the Moving Mean Subtraction (MMS) technique. The objectives are (1) determining the optimal averaging window for local and regional BC estimation, (2) assessing the feasibility of applying the Moving Mean Subtraction (MMS) technique to MERRA-2 reanalysis datasets, and (3) exploring additional insights from MMS on high-frequency MERRA-2 data.

METHODS

The background BC concentration at a site indicates the minimum loading of BC, which may be from sources both within and outside the region, either by continuous emission or ongoing influx. This study employs the Moving Mean Subtraction (MMS) method, originally developed by Watson and Chow (2001), to distinguish background BC from local contributions, later modified by Both et al. (2011). BC concentrations are smoothed at intervals of 6 hours, 3 hours, 1.5 hours, 45 minutes, and 15 minutes, retaining the lowest values after comparing with actual BC data. This method, effectively removes short-term spikes, identifying local contributions as deviations from the background.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Our study shows that the background black carbon accounts for approximately 90% (Aethalometer BC) and around 88% (MERRA-2 BC) yearly over Bhubaneswar using two different datasets. Such close agreement over both datasets over Bhubaneswar City provides the confidence to extend the same analysis across the whole Indian region using MERRA-2 BC. Figure 1 illustrates the background BC concentration across India exhibiting peak levels in winter, followed by post-monsoon, pre-monsoon, and the lowest concentrations during the monsoon season. The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) constantly exhibits elevated background BC levels ($>2.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) during winter, attributable to biomass combustion and transport. Conversely, Southern India, comprising Karnataka, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu, exhibits lower levels of background BC ($1.25\text{--}2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). In winter, central regions such as Maharashtra and Telangana exhibit background BC concentrations ranging from 2.2 to $2.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, whereas Eastern India has lower levels. During the post-monsoon period, the IGP exhibits values ranging from 2 to over $2.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while central India maintains higher levels between 1.25 and $2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. During summer, only IGP (1 to $1.75 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and some regions of central and eastern India have higher levels. During the monsoon, the majority of India experiences levels below $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, except the Indo-Gangetic Plain, which ranges from 1 to $1.75 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This

analysis further reveals that seasonally, the peak background BC concentration occurs in winter (2.32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 86%), succeeded by post-monsoon (1.54 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 85%), pre-monsoon (0.94 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 81%), and monsoon (0.60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 79%). Annually, background BC accounts for approximately 83% of total BC. Overall This investigation shows irrespective of the seasons the entire Indian subcontinent experiences a higher loading of background BC throughout the year.

Figure 1. a) Background BC concentration over India during (a) DJF (winter), (b) MAM (pre-monsoon), (c) JJA (monsoon), (d) SON (post-monsoon) season, and (e) bar plot showing the seasonal and annual total and background BC over India

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis illustrates the importance of MERRA-2 reanalysis data in precisely capturing the regional and temporal variations of BC. This data demonstrates similar properties of background BC to those recorded on the ground. This study established that a 48-hour averaging period is appropriate for identifying the most consistent level of BC in a specific location. MERRA-2 data revealed a winter background BC concentration of approximately 90%, but Aethalometer data indicated around 88%, with both datasets corroborating a yearly background BC percentage exceeding 75%. The minimum background BC concentrations were recorded during the monsoon, with MERRA-2 indicating 0.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and the Aethalometer at 1.26 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. MERRA-2 data indicated elevated background BC levels (>75%) throughout the year, with concentrations over 80% in numerous regions, especially in winter. Our findings offer critical insights for policymakers, highlighting the dominant role of background BC in India's air quality challenges.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study utilized BC surface concentration data from an Aethalometer AE-33 funded by the Ministry of Earth Sciences, India, and MERRA-2 data from NASA GES DISC, with BC emission data from EDGAR. The authors thank the funding sources, including ISRO's ARFINET program, and acknowledge IIT Bhubaneswar for infrastructure support.

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ANALYSIS OF AMBIENT PARTICULATE MATTER ASSOCIATED OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL IN AN URBAN ATMOSPHERE LUCKNOW

SS KALIKINKAR MAHANTA^{1,2}, HARI OM PRASAD^{1,2}, SREEKANTH BOJJAGANI*^{1,2}

¹Environmental Monitoring Laboratory, ASSIST Group CSIR-Indian Institute of Toxicology Research, Vishvigyan Bhawan 31-Mahatma Gandhi Marg, Lucknow-226001, UP, India

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad-201002, India

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Oxidative Potential, Dithiothreitol Assay, Human Health

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a widely recognized health impactor and ~12% of deaths in India happen due to inhalation of polluted air (Manisalidis et al., 2020). Inhaled PM (particulate matter) generates ROS (reactive oxygen species) in the human body which imbalance the anti-oxidants and oxidants ratio toward the increase of oxidative stress in the body (Singh et al., 2023). The oxidative potential (OP) of breathing PM can lead to different health issues and the death of cells or organisms in the human body (Linchen and Zhang, 2023; Calas et al., 2019). Literature reported that the significant generation of OP depends on the nature and composition of the chemicals and relative toxins that exist in ambient PM (Patel et al., 2022), where the chemical mix of PM varies for different sizes of particles, seasons, and near-source characteristics. Urban source-mix contribution complexed the chemical characteristics of PM# (particles with aerodynamic diameter \leq #:10 μ m and 2.5 μ m), and the relative comparison between PM# induced OP is less studied. Understanding the potential development of volume-normalized OP (OP_v) and mass-normalized OP (OP_m) due to the inhalation of PM# is important to protect public health and frame action plans to abate air pollution. Therefore, the present study aimed to discover the inhalable PM# association with the relative generation of OP_v and OP_m in an urban area of Lucknow city.

METHODOLOGY

The study site is a commercial location i.e., the Vishvigyan campus of CSIR-IITR of Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh state capital city in India. Ambient air sampling of PM# (#:10 μ m and 2.5 μ m) was conducted for weekly frequency covering the entire winter season of 2023 (i.e., from 15/11/2023 to 15/02/2024) using the ARA-N-FRM instrument of the institute. The OP generation from soluble PM# was assessed through the DTT (Dithiothreitol) chemical technique, where, the concentration of OP is recorded in two ways i.e., volume-normalized (calculated through the nmol of DDT consumed per minute per m³ of air sampled during PM# sampling, OP_v) and mass-normalized (calculated as the pmol of DDT consumed per minute per μ g of PM# mass sampled, OP_m). Singh et al., 2023 and Patel et al., 2022 have illustrated the analysis details of OP_v and OP_m from the chemical mix-based PM#. Every week variability of OP_v and OP_m and their significant association with respective atmospheric PM# concentration is evaluated through trend and correlation statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mass concentrations of PM# (#:10 μ m and 2.5 μ m) were recorded by a range between 93.4 μ g/m³ to 426.7 μ g/m³ (mean: 228.5 \pm 80.9 μ g/m³), and 58.8 to 269.2 μ g/m³ (mean: 151.2 \pm 60.1 μ g/m³) respectively (Figure-1). The concentration of PM# breached the national air quality limits (i.e.,100 μ g/m³ for PM₁₀ and 60 μ g/m³ for PM_{2.5}) throughout the winter

season and the variability in PM# concentration is due to the low mixing height, stable conditions and prevailing reactions between gaseous and particles in the atmosphere. Over the sampling days, PM10-associated mean concentration of OPv and OPm is found in the range of $5.7 \pm 2.2 \text{ nmol DDT min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $23.6 \pm 7.3 \text{ pmol DDT min}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-3}$, and PM2.5 associated concentrations in the range of $3.7 \pm 1.4 \text{ nmol DDT min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $14.7 \pm 5.7 \text{ pmol DDT min}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-3}$ respectively. OPv and OPm concentrations are observed to vary according to the concentration of PM# throughout the sampling days, where, a consistent trend is observed between OPv and OPm concentrations of the soluble PM#, however, the levels of OPm are found to increase with a factor of 4 to OPv of PM10 and a factor of 3 to OPv of PM2.5. The significant association between the mass concentration of PM# with the respective OPv and OPm is presented in Figure-2. There is correlation variability between OPv and OPm to respective PM# which represents the inhomogeneous contribution of the city source mix to the ambient PM#. Further, the strong correlation of OPv and OPm with the soluble PM10 than PM2.5 indicated the possibility of excess generation of ROS and OP in the human body due to the exposure of ambient PM10 than PM2.5. The city-specific air pollution sources of traffic exhaust, biomass burning, and fossil fuel combustion have prevailed influence on the complex chemical nature of PM#, which has a greater impact on ROS and OP generation for the humans exposed to the site of these sources. Health exposure standards related to OP in humans are yet to be set, however, the identified OPv and OPm associated with PM# in Lucknow city and previous research on other cities comparison reveals an exceedance in OP for Lucknow than some cities. Excess ROS generated from OP-associated PM# can result in the generation of oxidative stress inside the human body, which can harm proteins, RNA, DNA and induce the death of cells. According to this study, the toxicity of the OP and ROS levels could rise if precautions are not taken to bring down the concentration of pollutants in Lucknow city.

Figure -1: Weekly trend of PM10 and PM2.5 and their associated OPm and OPv Concentration

Figure -2: Correlation analysis between (A) PM₁₀, (B) PM_{2.5} with their respective OPm and OPv

CONCLUSION

The current study evaluated the PM# (#:10 μ m and 2.5 μ m) associated with OPv and OPm concentration and their significant correlation in the urban atmosphere of Lucknow city. The study results indicated a similar trend series between the concentration of OPv and OPm and their association with PM# levels, however, the PM₁₀-associated OPv and OPm generation is higher than their association with PM_{2.5}. The trend comparisons between PM# and the associated OPv and OPm revealed that the generation of ROS and OP is significant and consistent in the human body when exposed to ambient PM₁₀. Further, the strong correlation coefficient of OPm and OPv with PM₁₀ than PM_{2.5} confirms the higher inflation to produce ROS by PM₁₀ to cause adverse health in humans. There is a significant variation in the OPv and OPm present in the PM# from city to city (compared to the results between present and previous studies). This is because of the variability in the distribution of sources near monitoring sites, source profile characteristics, and their relative contribution to ambient PM#. The results of the present study give regulatory attention to imposing potential measures towards public exposure from the ambient PM# and control the generation of ROS in the human body.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for the instrumental facility of DSIR-CRTDH at CSIR-IITR, which was provided for the collection of samples from the field and their analysis in the lab. This manuscript submission has followed the publication procedures of SEC and AcSIR provisions at CSIR-IITR and the SEC committee has provided the manuscript number: IITR/SEC/AB/2024/99 for its publication.

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USE OF UAVS TO ASSESS VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION OF CRITERIA POLLUTANTS: A REVIEW OF ADVANCEMENT OVER THE PAST DECADE

SACHIN PANT¹, KARTIKEY MISHRA¹, SHUBHAM RATHI¹, ANUBHA GOEL^{1,2,3*}

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208016, India

²Centre for Environmental Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur

³Kotak School of Sustainability, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Aerosol Monitoring, Uavs, Vertical Profiling

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution poses significant risks to human health and the environment, especially in urban areas where concentrations often exceed permissible levels. The vertical expansion of cities, driven by high-rise buildings, has significantly altered local climates and the dispersion patterns of air pollutants. (Zhu et al., 2019). Understanding the vertical distribution of pollutants is crucial for assessing their health impacts. Traditional ground-based monitoring systems are insufficient to capture this variation comprehensively. This review leverages unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) with low-cost sensors to address these limitations. The findings contribute to a better understanding of atmospheric pollution and support the development of sustainable urban air quality management strategies.

METHODOLOGY

This study covers the scope of “Aerosol Monitoring and Characterization” at this conference. An examination of relevant research papers using Google Scholar and Scopus advanced search was conducted. The keywords used for search include: “UAV”, “unmanned aerial vehicle”, “drones”, “rotary wing”, “air quality”, “gas sensor”, “low-cost sensors”, “vertical profiling”, “vertical distribution”, “3 D investigation”, etc. The papers that contained the development of sensors or UAV systems but did not measure vertical pollutant profiles were excluded from the search. While this approach yielded a selection of relevant literature, it may not have been exhaustive in capturing all available research in the field.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Research on the vertical profiling of air pollutants using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has shown a significant upward trend over the past decade (Fig 1).

Fig1. Number of research publications from

Fig2. Number of research publications by 2014 to 2023

Notably, there has been a surge in research articles since 2018, highlighting the growing significance of vertical profiling of pollutants. Fig 2 indicates that China has contributed the highest number of articles, suggesting substantial funding from the Chinese government to enhance the country's air quality. Other countries, including India, have lagged in research on this topic. Our review reveals that lightweight UAVs, which generally consist of Quadcopters (drones), equipped with miniaturized sensors have greater flexibility and operability and have been successfully applied to explore their potential application in air quality monitoring (Li et al., 2017). UAVs are more operationally versatile compared to other aerial approaches, such as manned aircraft or tethered balloons. Besides, a number of further advantages of small UAVs, such as minimal logistical requirements (i.e. no airport necessary), the reduced cost of the platforms and instrumentation, and simplicity make them suitable for different practical operations and academic research (Brady et al., 2016). Results from our review will be presented about the different types of UAV systems developed which measure multiple pollutants, including CO, SO₂, NO₂, and O₃, in relation to altitude, providing insights into the influence of inversion layers and boundary layers on pollutant concentration profiles (Guan et al. 2021). We will present information about the inferences drawn from various studies conducting the vertical and horizontal distribution of particulate matter, gaseous pollutants and black carbon near urban infrastructures, like roadways and campuses, and their seasonal and diurnal changes illustrating how different emission sources and weather conditions affect the vertical layering of pollutants in the lower troposphere.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the review highlights the rapid advancement and increased use of UAV-based sensors in air quality monitoring over the past few years, driven by global concerns over air pollution and stricter regulations. UAVs offer clear advantages over traditional ground-based methods and other aerial platforms due to their operational versatility, cost-effectiveness, and ability to cover extensive and remote areas. However, challenges remain in developing more accurate, lightweight, and affordable sensors to maximize the effectiveness of these systems.

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SEASONAL AND SPATIAL VARIABILITY OF PM₁₀-BOUND METALS AND THEIR POTENTIAL HEALTH IMPACTS IN TWO URBAN SETTINGS OF GUJARAT

UTSAV GANDHI^{1,3}, NITASHA KHATRI¹, ANIL PATEL², DEBLEENA BHATTACHARYA³

¹Gujarat Environment Management Institute (GEMI), Forests and Environment Department, Gandhinagar - 382016, Gujarat, India.

²Bagchi School of Public Health, Ahmedabad University, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad

³Marwadi University, Rajkot- 360003, Gujarat, India

KEYWORDS: PM₁₀, Heavy Metals, Ladd, IELCR, Urban Air Quality.

INTRODUCTION

This study assesses PM₁₀-bound metal concentrations across different urban environments in Ahmedabad and Rajkot, Gujarat, chosen for their rapid industrialization and diverse pollution sources. Lifetime Average Daily Dose (LADD) and Inhalation Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (IELCR) metrics were applied to estimate health risks from long-term exposure to carcinogenic metals in PM. IELCR values exceeding 1×10^{-6} indicate significant risk, especially in urban areas with high levels of toxic metals (Gandhi et al. 2021). This analysis highlights seasonal and spatial variability in metal concentrations, with winter showing notably higher pollutant retention due to atmospheric conditions. Findings reveal consistently elevated chromium levels in both industrial and non-industrial areas due to vehicular emissions, construction, and road dust, presenting moderate to high cancer risks. Cadmium, primarily from vehicular emissions and waste disposal, also contributes to moderate risks. Comparing IELCR values between Ahmedabad and Rajkot identifies specific risk hotspots, with industrial and high-traffic zones as key areas of concern. The study underscores the need for targeted emission control measures, particularly in high-exposure zones, to address long-term health impacts and enhance urban air quality management.

SITE DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

PM₁₀ samples were collected from five locations in Ahmedabad (summer & winter 2017-18) and Rajkot (winter & summer 2022-23), representing diverse microenvironments: Low-income residential area (LRA), Industrial location (IND), Bus Transport hub (BTS), Heavy Running Traffic (HRT) and High-income residential area (HRA). The sites were strategically chosen to capture the influence of varying microenvironments on PM₁₀-bound metal concentrations, reflecting a broad spectrum of pollution sources. Metals, including carcinogenic metals were measured after acid-microwave digestion of PM₁₀ filter samples. LADD and IELCR for key carcinogenic metals were estimated based on inhalation exposure pathways, using established methodologies from previous research (Patel et al. 2021)

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

During winter, arsenic (As) levels remained within the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS, 2009) at all sites in both cities, except in Ahmedabad's industrial area. Nickel (Ni) exceeded NAAQS limits across most sites, except for low-income residential and high-traffic zones in Ahmedabad. Lead (Pb) stayed within NAAQS limits at most sites, though it was elevated in industrial areas of both cities and at the bus hub and high-income

residential area in Rajkot. Chromium was high not only in industrial zones but also across non-industrial areas, mainly due to vehicular emissions, diesel combustion, and road dust as shown in Table 1. Cadmium levels, while moderate, were also raised by vehicular emissions and waste incineration.

Table 1. Mass Concentration of carcinogenic Metals over different locations during summer

City	Location	Pb (ng/m ³)		Cr (ng/m ³)		Ni (ng/m ³)		Co (ng/m ³)		Cd (ng/m ³)		As (ng/m ³)	
		Summer	Winter										
NAAQS limit		500		-		20		-		-		6	
AMD	LRA	217.91	145.97	14.34	24.45	5.80	17.82	11.26	2.93	3.32	7.01	2.01	3.46
RAJ		23.65	229.91	5.17	32.18	1.25	119.19	1.09	2.99	1.55	85.80	0.14	2.51
AMD	IND	384.17	502.85	32.72	72.93	59.03	31.64	16.55	13.59	3.45	17.99	4.99	9.24
RAJ		354.21	624.56	50.17	61.15	2.42	105.04	5.73	5.16	16.69	91.44	0.57	3.78
AMD	BTH	68.04	140.67	16.66	20.14	6.91	78.30	5.76	2.93	1.47	13.07	1.54	3.50
RAJ		541.64	197.01	100.99	46.03	1.16	67.21	12.98	5.09	2.17	20.24	0.61	2.92
AMD	HRT	56.97	119.32	11.97	20.38	15.27	8.87	2.16	2.89	0.89	8.05	1.36	3.37
RAJ		43.50	233.20	5.59	75.47	1.03	19.49	1.05	3.73	2.97	40.34	0.22	3.05
AMD	HRA	24.49	166.41	7.65	14.60	50.49	59.32	1.69	2.13	0.55	6.46	1.13	3.04
RAJ		519.41	132.44	103.44	53.16	1.42	43.69	12.43	6.89	2.42	13.72	0.58	3.45

& winter.

In terms of health risks, the estimated IELCR values for Cr were significantly higher than acceptable norms, indicating a moderate to high cancer risk ($\geq 1 \times 10^{-4}$) in both cities, particularly in industrial and traffic-heavy areas. The IELCR values for Ni, As, and Co showed increased levels across all locations, suggesting a moderate to lower cancer risk. For Cd, the high IELCR values indicate a moderate cancer risk across most locations. Pb presented elevated IELCR values only at industrial sites, while the rest of the locations stayed within or near acceptable thresholds as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Calculated the IELCR value of key carcinogenic metals over different locations during winter.

CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals spatial and seasonal variability in PM₁₀-bound metals across two major cities in Gujarat, highlighting significant health risks from long-term exposure to carcinogenic metals, especially in high-traffic areas. Chromium levels were high across both industrial and non-industrial zones due to vehicular emissions, construction, and road dust, posing moderate to high cancer risks. Cadmium from vehicle emissions and waste disposal also presented moderate risks. IELCR analysis underscores the need for targeted controls in industrial and traffic-heavy areas, with higher risks in winter due to pollutant retention, emphasizing the importance of reducing vehicular emissions to minimize urban exposure.

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MEASUREMENTS OF VOCS AT A RURAL SITE IN INDIA: VARIABILITY, SOURCES AND THEIR IMPACT ON OFP, SOAP AND VOC/NOX SENSITIVITY

S. SINDHU, CHAITHANYA D. JAIN AND M. VENKAT RATNAM

National Atmospheric Research Laboratory (NARL), Gadanki - 517 112, India.

KEYWORDS: VOCS, Rural Atmosphere, OFP, PEC, SOAP, Ozone Isopleths, VOC /NOX Sensitivity

INTRODUCTION

Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) measurements in tropical rural environments are very sparse and in urgent demand to better understand their role in tropospheric chemical processing. They serve as precursors for tropospheric ozone (O₃) and Secondary Organic Aerosol (SOA) formation which are the direct indicators of the oxidative capacity specific to a given chemical environment. Many factors influence the oxidative capacity and it differs between urban and rural atmospheres. The current study investigates the oxidizing capacity of the less explored tropical rural atmosphere Gadanki in southern peninsular India using VOC measurements, OH loss rates and ozone isopleth diagrams.

METHODS

The concentrations of VOCs have been measured using Gas- Chromatography technique coupled with Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID) (Broadway and Tipler, 2012; Sindhu et al., 2023). The oxidizing capacity of the site has been investigated by estimating the parameters Ozone Formation Potential (OFP), Propylene Equivalent Concentration (PEC), Secondary Organic Aerosol Formation Potential (SOAP) and OH Loss Rate (LOH) of measured VOCs from December 2021 to November 2022. Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) model has been utilized for the source apportionment of measured VOCs (Sindhu et al., 2023). The ozone production regime indicator has been used to identify the sensitivity regime. OZIPR model has been used to generate ozone isopleths.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A total of 31 potential ozone precursor VOCs has been measured. There is a strong seasonal and diurnal variability among the VOC composition. The source apportionment resulted in four potential emission source factors: biogenic, biomass burning, fossil fuel, and natural gas emissions. Further using the measured VOC data, the potentials for O₃ (OFP) and SOA formation (SOAP) along with the source contribution have been estimated. The aromatic VOCs exhibit the highest OFP as compared to alkanes and alkenes. Among seasons, the post-monsoon period exhibits the highest OFP. The increased presence of biogenic VOCs, likely due to heightened vegetation cover, could account for the elevated OFP. The long-chain alkanes show the highest SOAP as compared to alkenes and aromatic VOCs. The summer season has the highest SOAP, owing to the enhanced concentrations and photochemistry initiated by OH radicals. Within the sources, biomass-burning VOCs make a substantial contribution to both OFP and SOAP, distinguishing the rural atmosphere from its urban counterpart, where traffic emissions predominantly influence OFP and SOAP.

Figure 1. Percentage contribution of VOC seasons and sources to total OFP and SOAP

Several factors impact ozone formation which includes precursor concentrations, meteorological conditions, and transport. Even though OFP and PEC quantify the ozone formation from individual VOCs, they do not consider the factors such as meteorological conditions and transport. The Ozone Isopleth Plotting Package (OZIPR) model overcomes this limitation. Subsequently, efforts have been made to understand the role of the precursor concentrations, along with meteorological conditions and transport, in quantifying the seasonal variation of ozone formation in terms of VOC/NO_x sensitivity at the observational site using the photochemical model OZIPR. The VOC cross-over points obtained from the ozone isopleth diagrams have shown a significant correlation between OFP and PEC values, supporting the variability in ozone formation in most of the seasons at the observational site. Additionally, the highest ozone concentration measured in the summer season is also well reproduced by the VOC cross-over correlations with the OFP and PEC values. Biomass burning VOCs have been found to be the highest contributors to ozone formation due to their higher emission in the summer season and higher contribution to both OFP and PEC.

Figure 2: a) Variation of O₃ with VOC and NO_x during winter, summer, monsoon and post-monsoon seasons

CONCLUSIONS

The oxidizing capacity of the rural atmosphere differs from the urban atmosphere, characterized by distinct VOCs, VOC groups (alkanes, alkenes and aromatic VOCs) and emission sources contributing to OFP and SOAP. Biomass-burning and biogenic factors together contribute 63% to OFP and biomass burning factors alone contribute 55% to SOAP, distinguishing the rural atmosphere from its urban counterpart, where traffic emissions

predominantly influence OFP and SOAP. PEC is best suited parameter with significant correlation with cross-over points. The results of this study have significantly contributed to the gap area of sparse VOC measurements and associated photochemistry in the Indian rural atmospheres

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Department of Space, Government of India for the financial support to carry out VOC measurements at NARL through the ISRO-GBP ATCTM project.

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ANALYSIS OF BLACK CARBON AND SULFUR DIOXIDE (SO₂) CONCENTRATIONS OVER THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN (IGP)

ABHISHEK SAXENA & VIKRAM SINGH BHATI

Sangam University Bhilwara Rajasthan -311001

ABSTRACT

There is a substantial atmospheric loading in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), especially in terms of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and black carbon (BC). The effects of these contaminants on the environment and public health are extensive. The simulated and observed BC surface concentrations over the heavily populated IGP, however, differ significantly. Additionally, the research investigates how BC and SO₂ may affect regional air quality, visibility degradation (which may affect aviation and agriculture), and radiative forcing, which may have an impact on monsoon patterns and other regional climate trends. The results of this dissertation have the potential to greatly advance our knowledge of how these pollutants behave over the IGP, which is important information for wise policy choices and practical mitigation techniques. By helping to close the gap between observed data and model simulations, this research improves our knowledge of BC and SO₂ in relation to air quality and climate change over the IGP region.

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon (Bc), Sulfur Dioxide (So₂), Indo-Gangetic Plain (Igp), Air Pollution, Seasonal Variations, Source Apportionment, Radiative Forcing, Visibility Etc.

INTRODUCTION

With more than 600 million inhabitants, the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) is a large and fertile region that is cradled by the Himalayas in the north. Air pollution has become a global hotspot in this heavily populated region, which includes sections of Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, and Nepal. Black carbon and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) are two major pollutants that stand out among the many other factors that contribute to this environmental problem.

METHODS

Data for the study of Black Carbon and Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂) was gathered for 5 major cities (Delhi, Agra, Kanpur, Patna, Kolkata) of the Indo-Gangatic Plain for a Period of 10 years (2011 to 2020). The dataset for the study was obtained from a NASA affiliated project (GIOVANNI).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) Analysis: The analysis of the SO₂ dataset reveals a general increase in the SO₂CMD (column mass density) values over time, as demonstrated by both the trends and yearly mean data plots.

Delhi: The SO₂CMD values alternated each year, showing lower levels during the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons, and remaining roughly the same during summer and winter, with a slight increase during the winter months.

Agra: SO₂CMD values were significantly higher during winter, with a slight decrease in summer and a noticeable drop during the monsoon season.

Kanpur: SO₂CMD showed alternating increases throughout the year, with lower values during the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons and a slight increase in winter compared to summer.

Patna: SO₂CMD values were relatively stable during summer and winter, with a slight winter increase and lower levels during the pre-monsoon and monsoon periods.

Kolkata: SO₂CMD was substantially higher in winter, with a slight decrease in summer and a sharp decline during the monsoon season.

Black Carbon (BC) Analysis: The BC dataset also demonstrated an overall increase in BC CMD (column mass density) values over the analysis period (Ref.No-1, 5, 16, 21, 11, and 27).

Delhi: BC CMD values were steady during monsoon, pre-monsoon, and summer, with a sharp rise in winter.

Agra: BC CMD remained consistent through summer, monsoon, and pre-monsoon, but saw a significant increase in winter.

Kanpur: Similar to other cities, Kanpur's BC CMD was steady through the non-winter months, with a sharp winter increase.

Patna: BC CMD values were comparable across summer, monsoon, and pre-monsoon, with a dramatic increase observed in winter.

Kolkata: BC CMD followed a similar pattern, remaining stable during the non-winter seasons and rising sharply during the winter months.

CONCLUSIONS

Rising sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and black carbon (BC) in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) harm air quality, public health, and the environment. SO₂ from industry and vehicles causes respiratory issues, while BC accelerates glacier melt, worsening climate change. Addressing this requires stricter emissions controls, cleaner technologies, renewable energy, and regional cooperation for a healthier, sustainable future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

NASA Giovanni provides data for the study.

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CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER MUMBAI DURING DIWALI AND WINTER 2023

VIDIT PARKAR¹ AND ABHISHEK CHAKRABORTY¹

¹Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai – 400 076, India.

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosol Sampling System, Online Sampling System, Carbonaceous Fractions.

INTRODUCTION

Fine atmospheric aerosols (PM_{2.5}) majorly impact climate forcing, visibility/fog events, air quality, and human health (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). PM₁ particles contribute to most of these effects as their size is near wavelengths in the visible spectrum and their ability to penetrate and deposit on human alveoli (Costa et al., 2015; Marseglia et al., 2019). These aerosols mainly consist of organic and inorganic compounds. There is a significant contribution of carbonaceous aerosol (CA) to fine particulates (20-60%) (Huang et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). There is still a great deal of uncertainty as to how CA affects the environment and human health due to its complex physical and chemical properties. Real-time monitoring of CA is carried out using the Carbonaceous Aerosol Sampling System (CASS), which determines total carbon (TC) and black carbon (BC) based on thermal analysis of TC (TCA08) and optical method to measure EC, i.e. BC (AE33). The main advantages of CASS include high time resolution, no sample break time, and the possibility of adjusting the filter-loading effect online for BC measurements.

METHODS

Carbonaceous aerosols were measured at the IIT Bombay campus during the post-monsoon (Diwali) and winter seasons of 2023 with the CASS, and filter samples were collected with Envirotech Air Samplers (flow rate ~ 16.67 lpm). CASS is an online sampling system, a combination of a total carbon analyzer (TCA08, Magee Sci.) and aethalometer, where TCA measures total carbon (TC) by thermal combustion, and Aethalometer measures BC by measuring optical attenuation. Organic carbon is calculated as the difference between total carbon and BC. The instrument measures CA at a time resolution of 30 mins. CASS and an air sampler were installed atop the ESED department building. The filter samples were collected at a time resolution of 12 hours during the entire campaign. These filters were then analyzed in a Thermal-Optical analyzer (TOA, Sunsetz lab) by IMPROVA protocol.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The online instrument (CASS) measures EC (BC) based on optical methods, whereas the EC of filter samples was measured by the thermal-optical method. To make the BC measurements from the aethalometer coherent with the thermal-optical method of TCA, we established a relation between the two methods for EC measurements, where the CASS data was averaged to the 12h resolution to match the resolution of filter samples. Fig 1 shows the correlation between the EC concentrations of thermal-optical and optical methods of filters and CASS resp. The results show that the optical method overestimates the elemental carbon. So, a correction factor equal to the slope of the EC-BC correlation is applied to the online BC measurement for all the online measurements for both seasons. Further, the OC values were recalculated. **Diwali 2023** – The CAs peaked at midnight on the night of Diwali, as shown in

Fig 2. On average, post-Diwali concentrations are 1.6 higher than pre-Diwali concentrations, implying the lasting effects of firecrackers and bio-mass burning during Diwali, despite good ventilation in the coastal city of Mumbai. **Winter 2023** – The CAs during winter show a consistent decline as the winter subsides, but a sharp dip (~ 4.3 times) is observed around the festivals of Makarsankranti/Pongal/Lodhi as high wind speeds are observed. Post the festivals, the variation during the daytime and night is striking, with lows lower and highs higher than the pre-festivals, as shown in Fig 2. A significant amount of data is lost in filter sampling as compared to the real-time method. Online methods can prove to be important for exposure assessment, especially during high-pollution events like Diwali.

Figure 1. Correlation EC from filter samples with the BC measured by CASS.

Figure 2. Timeseries Diwali 2023 (Left) and Winter 2023-24 (Right).

CONCLUSIONS

CAs are a significant component of PM. The online measurement method with CASS gives real-time insight into the highly variable emissions during the Diwali and Winter seasons at a high time resolution. The difference in the measurement method of CASS can lead to inaccurate data, which was corrected by simultaneously deploying filter samples along with it. The real-time method can prove to be important for exposure assessment.

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ASSESSMENT OF PARTICULATE POLLUTANTS (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} & PM₁) AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS: A CASE STUDY FROM KATARMAL, UTTARAKHAND, INDIAN HIMALAYAN REGION

ANIL SINGH SALAL¹, ARCHANA BAWARI¹, JAGDISH CHANDRA KUNIYAL²,
SUMIT RAI¹

¹G. B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment, Kosi-Katarmal-263 643, Almora

²Department of Forest Resource Management, College of Forestry, Veer Chandra Singh Garhwali Uttarakhand University of Horticulture and Forestry (VCSGUUHF), Ranichauri-249 199, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India.

KEYWORDS: PM, Seasonal Variation, Meteorological Factors, Himalaya.

INTRODUCTION

The recent rapid economic expansion and urbanization, especially in emerging countries, have drawn a lot of attention to the problem of air pollution (Zhao et al., 2019). PM, a significant environmental issue, can originate from both fixed and mobile sources and can be controlled through emission reduction initiatives (Zhao et al., 2019). Particle dilution, nucleation, condensation, and evaporation are all strongly influenced by meteorological conditions such as temperature, precipitation, wind direction, and speed (Zhang et al., 2015). Submicron aerosols (PM₁) are important airborne particles with a diameter smaller than 1 μm that contribute to climate change, haze formation, and exposure risk (Wang et al., 2021).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site Description and data collection: The study used Respirable Dust Samplers, Fine particulate Samplers and PM₁ Sampler to monitor PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ samples and an Automated Weather Station at NIHE, Kosi-Katarmal, Uttarakhand, (29.64°N, 79.62°E, 1225 m amsl) from January 2021 to December 2023. Continuous sampling of PM₁, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} was conducted alternately 24 and 8 hours and Mass concentration was calculated using gravimetric estimation.

$$C_{PM} = (W_f - W_i) \times 10^6 / V$$

Here

C_{PM} = Concentration of PM₁₀ in μgm⁻³, W_f= final weight of filter in g, W_i= Initial weight of filter in g, 10⁶=Conversion of g to μ, V = Volume of air sampled, m³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seasonal variation: The results show maximum concentrations of PM₁ (38.30 μgm⁻³) and PM_{2.5} (46.69 μgm⁻³) in winter, while PM₁₀ (62.68 μgm⁻³) in pre-monsoon and these PM (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) shows minimum average concentration (PM₁= 28.13 μgm⁻³, PM_{2.5}= 35.42 μgm⁻³, PM₁₀= 37.03 μgm⁻³) in the monsoon season due to the washout effect

Monthly Variation: During the study period, PM₁ ranges from 10.45 μgm⁻³ to 49.17 μgm⁻³ with an average of 30.44 μgm⁻³, PM_{2.5}, ranges from 21.8 μgm⁻³ to 53.50 μgm⁻³ with the average value of 39.01 μgm⁻³ respectively. While the concentration of PM₁₀ ranges from

13.01 μgm^{-3} to 101 μgm^{-3} , with an average of 41.26 μgm^{-3} .

Influence of Meteorological parameters on PM Concentration: PM1, PM2.5 and PM10 have a negative correlation with relative humidity with the Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient ($r = -0.18$, $r = -0.08$ & $r = -0.51$) and PM1 has weak positive correlation ($r = 0.05$), with wind speed because as wind speed increases PM1 concentrations might slightly increase. PM2.5 also shows a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.03$) with wind speed. This could be due to localized sources of fine particulate matter that are not significantly affected by wind speed.

Figure 1 Monthly variation of Particulate Matter.

PM10 has a negative correlation ($r = -0.51$) with wind speed which indicates a stronger relationship where higher wind speeds are associated with lower concentrations of PM10. This might happen because increased wind can disperse larger particles more effectively. While all PM (PM1, PM2.5, PM10) has a negative correlation ($r = -0.02$, $r = 0.07$, $r = 0.05$) with precipitation due to the washout effect.

CONCLUSION

The study found that particulate matter (PM) concentrations from January 2021 to December 2023 were within the National Ambient Air Quality Standards. However, during forest fire outbreaks, PM concentrations exceeded these limits. The study also found a correlation between PM levels and meteorological parameters like relative humidity, and wind speed and precipitation. Future studies should concentrate on recognizing the long-term health effects of increased PM exposure during fire incidents and creating efficient response and mitigation plans to better safeguard communities impacted by these environmental problems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Director, NIHE, Kosi-Katarmal, Almora, Uttarakhand for providing facilities that could make the present study possible. The authors are also thankful to ISRO for partial financial support under Aerosol Radiative Forcing over India (ARFI) and Atmospheric Chemistry Transport and Modelling (AT-CTM) under Environmental Observatory. The work was carried out in NIHE. The corresponding author also wishes to acknowledge the Dean, College of Forestry, Ranichauri, and Hon'ble Vice Chancellor,

VCSGUUHF for providing facilities to the corresponding author (JCK) which could make it possible to finalise the present work.

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TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL DYNAMICS OF AEROSOL OPTICAL PROPERTIES IN THE CENTRAL AND NORTHWESTERN HIMALAYAN SITES

ARCHANA BAWARI^{1,2}, JAGDISH CHANDRA KUNIYAL³,
SHEETAL CHAUDHARY¹, BIMAL PANDE²

¹G. B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment, Kosi-Katarmal-263 643, Almora
²Department of Physics, D S B Campus, Kumaun University, Nainital-263 001, Uttarakhand
³Department of Forest Resource Management, College of Forestry, Veer Chandra Singh Garhwali Uttarakhand University of Horticulture and Forestry (VCSGUUHF), Ranichauri-249 199, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India

KEYWORDS: MWR, Microtops II Sunphotometer, MODIS, AOD, Radiative Forcing

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols significantly influence atmospheric processes by absorbing and scattering radiation (direct radiative effect) and indirectly affect cloud properties by enhancing droplet concentration and extending cloud lifetime, thereby impacting climate dynamics (Tomasi et al., 2017). Aerosol optical depth (AOD) is a key parameter in radiative transfer calculations. This study examines the aerosol radiative effects over Mohal and Katarmal, semi-rural sites crucial for understanding regional climate patterns. Findings will improve climate models and inform sustainable environmental management in these sensitive areas.

METHODS

Sampling and Site Description: AOD sampling was conducted at Kosi-Katarmal (29.59°N, 79.65°E, 1225 m) and Mohal-Kullu (31.90°N, 77.12°E, 1154 m) from July 2019 to June 2022. AOD at Mohal was measured with a Multi-wavelength Radiometer (MWR) across ten wavelength bands (0.38–1.025 μm), while at Katarmal, it was measured using a MICROTOPS-II Sunphotometer (MTOPI) covering five bands (0.38–1.020 μm). MODIS TERRA level 3 AOD data (550 nm, 1°×1° grid) were used for analysis and correlation with ground observations.

Aerosol radiative forcing (ARF): The OPAC model (Hess et al., 1998) was used to simulate aerosol optical properties, i.e., Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Single Scattering Albedo (SSA), and asymmetry parameter (g) based on a given composition of water-soluble, water-insoluble, and soot (or black carbon) particles. Monthly relative humidity data were incorporated to account for aerosol hygroscopic growth. The simulated properties, along with surface albedo, total precipitable water vapor from MERRA-2, and ozone column data from OMI, were inputs into the SBDART model (Ricchiuzzi et al., 1998) to estimate aerosol radiative forcing.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Variation of AOD: Figure 1 shows daily AOD variations at 550 nm from ground-based measurements and MODIS from 2019 to 2022. AOD values in Katarmal ranged from 0.01 to 1.66 for MTOPI and 0.05 to 1.84 for MODIS. At Mohal, MWR recorded AOD values between 0.01 and 0.94, while MODIS ranged from 0.03 to 1.29. At Mohal, 53.3% of MWR and 34.3% of MODIS AOD values were below the annual mean, while Katarmal had 43.9% and 46.6% for MTOPI and MODIS, respectively. Aerosol loading peaked in the pre-monsoon

season, with the highest AOD recorded at Mohal (0.39 ± 0.06) and Katarmal (0.38 ± 0.06). The lowest AOD occurred post-monsoon at Mohal (0.25 ± 0.03) and during winter at Katarmal (0.21 ± 0.07). MWR and MODIS AOD showed a moderate correlation ($R^2 = 0.57$) at Mohal, while MTOPS and MODIS had a weak correlation ($R^2 = 0.26$) at Katarmal. The Ångström Exponent (AE) averaged 1.07 ± 0.22 at Mohal and 0.87 ± 0.53 at Katarmal, with AE peaking in post-monsoon and winter at Mohal, and in winter at Katarmal, indicating smaller aerosols like smoke during these periods.

Aerosol radiative forcing: The average radiative forcing at the surface (ARFSFC), top of the atmosphere (ARFTOA), and atmosphere (ARFATM) were -46.01 ± 1.63 , -18.65 ± 0.65 , and 27.36 ± 1.0 Wm^{-2} at Mohal, and -40.18 ± 1.21 , -18.31 ± 0.66 , and 21.87 ± 1.21 Wm^{-2} at Katarmal. The highest ARFATM (34.34 Wm^{-2}) with a heating rate of 0.96 Kday^{-1} was observed at Mohal during pre-monsoon, while the lowest ARFATM (15.78 Wm^{-2}) with a heating rate of 0.44 Kday^{-1} occurred at Katarmal during monsoon (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Daily ground-based and MODIS AOD variations at (a) Katarmal and (b) Mohal.

Figure 2. Seasonal variation of ARF at TOA, SFC, and ATM at Katarmal and Mohal.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals significant variations in aerosol optical properties and radiative forcing over Mohal and Katarmal from 2019 to 2022, with distinct seasonal trends. AOD values peaked in pre-monsoon, driven by larger particles like dust, while lower values in post-monsoon and winter reflected smaller aerosols such as smoke. AE analysis confirmed these seasonal differences. ARF findings show strong atmospheric warming, especially in pre-monsoon, with positive ARFATM values. These results highlight the impact of aerosols on regional climate, particularly in the sensitive Himalayan region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors heartily thank the Director of G.B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan

Environment for facilities, ISRO for partial funding under ARFI, and DST, Government of India, for support under NMSHE-Task Force 3, Phase II, 'Forest Resources and Biodiversity'. The work was carried out in NIHE. The corresponding author also wishes to acknowledge the Dean, College of Forestry, Ranichauri, and Hon'ble Vice Chancellor, VCSGUUHF for providing facilities to the corresponding author (JCK) which could make it possible to finalise the present work.

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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF AEROSOLS OPTICAL DEPTH AND ÅNGSTRÖM EXPONENT OVER IGP REGION IN INDIA

A. DEEP^{1*}, T. KANDARI², K. SINGH³, A. S. GAUTAM³, P. S. SONI⁴

^{1*}Department of Physics, Dhanauri P. G. College, Dhanauri, Haridwar, 247661, Uttarakhand

²Department of Physics, Municipal P. G. College, Mussoorie, 248179, Uttarakhand, India

³Department of Physics, H N B University, Garhwal (A Central University) Srinagar

⁴Department of Physics, Agra College, Agra, Dr, Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra, UP

KEYWORDS: Statistical Analysis, AOD, AE, Modis.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols comprise solid and liquid particles suspended in the air, which can be categorized into natural (primary) and anthropogenic (secondary) aerosols. The optical and chemical characteristics of these aerosols, along with trace gases, significantly influence radiative forcing and contribute to climate change (IPCC, 2001). Addressing climate change has become a major focus in environmental sciences. Over the past two decades, there has been a notable increase in research exploring aerosols and their impacts on both global and local climates (Claquin et al., 1997; Dammann et al., 2000; Shaocai et al., 2001; Han et al., 2012). For example, Kaskaoutis et al. (2007) conducted a comprehensive study on aerosol climatology using the Ångström Exponent (AE) at selected AERONET sites. In India, initiatives spearheaded by the Indian Space Research Organization as part of the Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (ISRO-GBP) have been instrumental in advancing this research (Moorthy et al., 1999).

METHODS

The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) stands as a space-borne remote sensor, operational aboard the polar orbiting Aqua and Terra satellites. Launched by NASA on May 4, 2002, and December 18, 1999, respectively (Savtchenko et al., 2004), these satellites provide a diverse array of data products covering the atmosphere, land, ocean, and cryosphere. The data collections are defined by MODIS data versions, representing the iterations of the MODIS data production algorithm (Savtchenko et al., 2004; Remer et al., 2005). This study utilizes Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) data from the MODIS sensor, obtained from daily and monthly data of MOD08_D3_6 L3 (Terra platform) and MYD08_D3_6 (Aqua platform). The AOD data product from MODIS over land (corrected at 0.55 μm) is employed, available at a spatial resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$. This product is chosen over the Deep Blue (DB) algorithm for its appropriateness in the context of this research, ensuring accurate and reliable results for further analysis and interpretation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and Ångström Exponent (AE) data were analyzed statistically to assess monthly, seasonal, and annual variability at the selected sites throughout the study period. The monthly mean AOD was found to be 0.18 (± 0.14), while the mean AE was 1.05 (± 0.43). These findings provide important insights into the climatic impacts associated with atmospheric aerosols in the studied regions of Uttar Pradesh. The maximum seasonal mean AOD recorded for the Delhi region during the monsoon season was 0.89 (± 0.28), whereas in the Chamoli region, the highest AOD of 0.32 (± 0.12) occurred in the pre-

monsoon season. For Agra, the highest mean AOD of 1.69 (± 0.08) was observed in winter, with the lowest AE value of 0.72 (± 0.21) occurring in the post-monsoon season. While the influence of monsoonal moist air and rainfall was not notably significant during the monsoon, the post-monsoon period displayed lower AOD values.

Figure 1. Seasonal variation of AOD and AE at selected sites in Uttarakhand during the study period.

CONCLUSIONS

Correlation coefficients, computed through Pearson's method, highlight a range between 0.56 to 0.77 for all conceivable correlations between the Angstrom exponent and AOD. The monthly mean AOD and mean AE values are calculated, resulting in 0.18 (± 0.14) and 1.05 (± 0.43) respectively. These outcomes offer valuable insights into the climatic repercussions attributed to atmospheric aerosols over the selected regions in Uttar Pradesh. It is important to highlight the uncertainty, limitations, and prospects of our present investigation. MODIS data sets are available with different spatial resolutions; further internal algorithms for data retrieval also differ for both of these instruments. The comprehensive analysis of AOD and AE parameters from MODIS satellite retrievals contributes significantly to understanding the complex dynamics of aerosols, providing a foundation for addressing climatic implications in the studied region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank, NOAA Air Resources Laboratory for the provision of the HYSPLIT transport and dispersion model and NASA Langley. The authors would like to thank "NASA (The National Aeronautics and Space Administration)" for providing the data for this study. I also thank to Department of Physics, Dhanauri P. G. College, Dhanauri, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, for the providing all facilities.

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NOVEL APPROACH CHARACTERISING POLLUTANT SOURCES USING ONLINE AEROSOL MEASUREMENTS OVER A HIGH-ALTITUDE SITE IN CENTRAL HIMALAYAS

P. SRIVASTAVA¹, M. NAJA¹, P. BHARDWAJ², R. KUMAR³, T. R. SESHADRI⁴

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Manora Peak, Nainital - 263001

²Center for Study of Science, Technology and Policy, Bengaluru - 560094, India

³National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, CO - 80307-3000, USA

⁴Department of Physics and Astrophysics, University of Delhi, Delhi - 110007, India

KEYWORDS: BC, CO, POC, SOC, High-Altitude Himalayas, Online Measurements.

INTRODUCTION

The Himalayan region is adversely affected by the increasing anthropogenic emissions from the adjacent Indo-Gangetic plain. However, source apportionment studies for the Himalayan region that are crucial for mitigating pollutant concentrations (CO and organic aerosols), are grossly insufficient, to say the least. It is in this context that our study reported here assumes significance. This study utilizes five years (2014–2018) of simultaneous online ground-based observations of black carbon (BC), organic and elemental carbon (OC & EC) and carbon monoxide at a high-altitude (1958 m) site in the Central Himalayas. A novel machine learning based approach is used to segregate the fossil fuel combustion and biomass burning of CO by using online mass absorption cross-section corrected BC measurements. The approach is contrasted against the CO from MOPITT, MERRA2 and the tagged tracer runs with WRF-Chem over the region which have a bias of more than 50 % compared to the observed CO over this Himalayan region. Further high-resolution delineation of primary organic carbon (POC) and secondary organic carbon (SOC) content over the region are presented. Multiple methods are employed to segregate these primary and secondary components and their discrepancies are brought to light. The change in aerosol trend over the two decades (2004–24) is also discussed.

METHODS

In-situ: Carbonaceous species (OC and EC) are measured (2014–17) hourly by an online EC-OC analyser based on the NIOSH 5040 temperature protocol with thermo-optical transmittance for charring correction Srivastava and Naja (2023). The eBC measurements (2004–present) were made using an Aethalometer (AE-42), which measures the mass concentration based on the optical attenuation of a light beam at seven wavelengths. Importantly, the conversion of the absorption coefficient to eBC is done using monthly site-specific mass absorption cross-sections (MAC) Srivastava et al. (2024). CO observations (2014–2018) are made using an instrument (Picarro G2401) based on the cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) technique.

Models and Satellite: WRF-Chem v3.9.1 is used to track the contribution of different sources of tropospheric CO with four artificial species “tracers” for anthropogenic, biomass burning, photo-chemical production and inflow from lateral boundaries. CO from MERRA2 and MOPITT and fire events and AOD from MODIS are also used from 2014–17 around 1 degree

region of the site are also used. A multiple linear regression machine learning model (MLR) is developed to ascertain the sources of CO. Concentration-weighted trajectory (CWT) is estimated with 5-day-backward trajectories from HYSPLIT for 5 particles for a $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ grid around the site at 1000 m a.g.l. from with 0.5° GDAS meteorology. Radiative Forcing estimates are made using SBDART and OPAC models.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

CO and its sources from BC: The results show that MERRA2 always underestimates the observed CO; MOPITT has a high monthly difference ranging from -32% to $+57\%$ while WRF-Chem simulations underestimate CO from February to June and overestimate in other months. In contrast, CO estimated from MLR replicates diurnal and monthly variations and estimates CO with an $r^2 > 0.8$ for 2014–2017. The CO predicted during 2018 closely follows the observed variations, and its mixing ratios lie within $\pm 17\%$ of the observed CO (figure 1). The results reveal a unimodal diurnal variation of CO, CO_{ff} (ff: fossil fuel) and CO_{bb} (bb: biomass burning) governed by the boundary layer evolution and upslope winds. CO_{ff} has a higher diurnal amplitude (39.1–67.8 ppb) than CO_{bb} (5.7–33.5 ppb). Overall, CO_{ff} is the major contributor (27%) in CO after its background fraction (58%). CO_{bb} fraction reaches a maximum (28%) during spring, a period of increased agricultural and forest fires in Northern India. In comparison, WRF-Chem tracer runs underestimate CO_{bb} (-38% to -98%) while they overestimate the anthropogenic CO during monsoon.

Sources of Carbonaceous Aerosols: Four different methods are employed to deconvolute organic carbon (OC) into POC and SOC. Unlike SOC, POC exhibits significant unimodal diurnal variations with higher values during daytime in all four methods (figure 1). These methods show intra-annual variations in POC (56–80%) and SOC (20–44%) concentrations but they agree that overall POC ($4.7\text{--}8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) dominates over SOC ($2.4\text{--}3.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The role of crop residue burning in northern India and forest fires is shown to be dominant in spring while local heating-purpose emissions dominate in winter. Further, we show that the contribution of fossil fuel combustion (eBC_{ff}) is 3.5 times greater than that of biomass burning (eBC_{bb}). Atmospheric forcing from both eBC_{ff} and eBC_{bb} is higher (19.8 and 13.0 W m^{-2} , respectively) in the afternoon than morning. The trend in surface BC and its sources shows a faster decline in fossil fuel combustion sources compared to biomass ones.

Figure 1. (Left) Variation of observed and MLR predicted CO. (Right) Variation of POC and SOC as derived from the four methods

CONCLUSIONS

This study addresses the lack of high-resolution aerosol and CO monitoring, specifically over the Central Himalayas, by employing a novel observation-based method to constrain the pollutant sources which is shown to perform better than MERRA2, MOPITT and WRF-Chem. It further shows the impacts of these various sources in deteriorating the regional air quality and enhanced radiative effects thus underlining the dire need to mitigate these incomplete combustion activities to maintain the sanctity of the pristine region of the Himalayas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the ARIES-DST, ISRO-ARFI, and ISRO-ATCTM.

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SECONDARY ORGANIC AEROSOLS IN NON-URBAN ENVIRONMENT: LEVELS AND CHARACTERISTICS

PAKKI JAYARAJU¹, MEGHA ANAND¹, ABHISHEK CHAKRABORTY¹

¹Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Environmental Science and Engineering Department, Powai, Mumbai – 400 076, India.

KEYWORDS: SOA, VOCS, PM, Biogenic Emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary Organic Aerosols (SOA) are a major component of particulate matter (PM) and contain harmful compounds affecting human health and the environment. Urban factors, such as VOCs from vehicles and industries, drive SOA formation. However, recent research reveals that anthropogenic activities in non-urban areas, including biogenic emissions from BVOCs, also contribute to SOA through reactions with NO₂ and RO₂, particularly during summer (Shannigrahi et al., 2014) and winter haze (Bharali et al., 2024). This study aims to understand the mechanisms of secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation in non-urban environments in the summer season. The primary hypothesis is that low NO_x levels influence SOA formation through photo-oxidation in summer. The investigation includes both particulate matter levels and their carbonaceous components.

METHODS

Samples were collected at Wayanad (11.6741° N, 75.9426° E) using high-volume samplers for PM_{2.5} (1 m³/min) and PM₁₀ (1.1 m³/min), operating for 8 hours daily during winter and summer. Quartz filters (Whatman, 1851-10011, 8" x 10") were pre-baked at 550 °C for at least 12 hours, then wrapped in butter paper and stored in Ziplock bags. After sampling, filters were again wrapped and stored at -20 °C. PM concentrations were determined by measuring pre- and post-weight using a balance (sensitivity: 0.01 mg), calculating the difference, and dividing by the flow rate. The ECOC Analyzer (Suncet Laboratory) was utilized to measure the levels of carbonaceous fractions in the collected PM, operating under the IMPROVE_A (Interagency Monitoring of Protected Visual Environments) protocol. VOCs and NO_x data used to analyse ozone formation, obtained from CAMS reanalysis data (Inness et al., 2015).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 shows that PM concentrations are consistently below the daily standard of NAAQS in Wayanad. The PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ ratio in Wayanad indicates a greater presence of coarser particles, likely due to biogenic emissions.

Figure 1. Concentrations of PM over time in non-urban environment [Wayanad].

As shown in figure 2, the levels of OC1, OC4, and EC3 were significantly lower than those of OC2, OC3, and EC1, EC2. The OC3 fraction at the sampling site comprised the largest proportion of organic carbon, indicating that road dust emissions were the primary source of pollution at that location. Both OC1 and EC3 were less than 5%, respectively indicating that the contributions from biomass burning and diesel emissions were minimal. Table 1 presents the OC and EC concentrations recorded in the Wayanad forest area, highlighting the mean, minimum, and maximum values of OC/EC measured over 12 hours per day in May 2024. Our OC and EC concentrations are significantly higher than those recorded at various rural sites in Europe (Pio et al., 2011), and they also exceed the levels found in the rural study of Rajnandgaon, India (Ambade, 2016).

Figure 2. OC and EC fractions (left) and their percentage contributions (right) in PM10 over the Wayanad.

	Max ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Min ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Average \pm Standard Deviation ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
OC	11.85	4.90	7.61 ± 2.00
EC	5.19	1.95	3.57 ± 1.18
OC/EC	3.02	1.67	2.22 ± 0.45

Table 1. OC and EC concentrations and OC/EC ratio in PM10 at Wayanad, Kerala in Summer 2024.

In this non-urban area during summer, the water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC) has the absorption coefficient (babs) and mass absorption cross-section (MAC) values of $15.93 \pm 5.22 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$ and $2.86 \pm 1.32 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively, which are lower than those observed in Mumbai (Rathod et al., 2024). As shown in figure 3, ozone formation transitions from concentrations of a low-NO_x, high-VOCs regime to a high-NO_x, high-VOCs regime.

Figure 3. Ozone isopleths (ppb) across varying TVOC and NO_x levels in Wayanad during Summer 2024

CONCLUSIONS

The high PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ ratio in Wayanad suggests a predominance of coarse particles, likely originating from biogenic emissions. In this non-urban area, the ratio of organic carbon (OC) to elemental carbon (EC) was measured at 2.22 ± 0.45 , with babs and MAC values of $15.93 \pm 5.22 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$ and $2.86 \pm 1.32 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively. Under a low NO_x–high VOC regime and a high NO_x–high VOC scenario contribute to ozone formation, potentially leading to secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation in this non-urban environment. These background measurements can enhance our understanding of aerosol characteristics and sources in non-urban regions of India.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to my supervisor, Prof. Abhishek Chakraborty, for his invaluable guidance and for providing me with the opportunity to analyze the data. Additionally, I appreciate IIT Bombay for granting access to the UV-Vis and ECOC Analyser instruments.

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NUCLEATION MODE AEROSOL PARTICLES ESTIMATION USING SATELLITE-BASED PROXIES OVER THE WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA

K. SINGH¹, A. S. GAUTAM¹

¹Himalayan Atmospheric and Space Physics Research Laboratory, Department of Physics, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar, Uttarakhand – 246174, India.

KEYWORDS: Nucleation Mode Aerosols, Nucleation, Satellite-Based Proxies, Predictability, Western Himalaya.

INTRODUCTION

The nucleation mode aerosol particles are smaller particles than about 25-30 nm in diameter (Kulmala et al., 2011). These aerosol particles are formed by nucleation (gas-to-particle conversion) in the continental boundary layer as well as the free troposphere (Kulmala & Kerminen, 2008, Manninen et al., 2010). The chemical proxies serve as the indicators of nucleation mode aerosol formation and growth and also represent the chemical composition and properties of nucleation mode aerosols (Sullivan et al., 2016). Combination of satellite data with either model simulations or situ observations has been successfully used in several applications such as air quality predictions (Martin, 2008; Hoff and Christofer, 2009), evaluation of emission inventories (Lamsal et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2011) and constraining the radiative effects by aerosols (Myhre, 2009). Very few measurements of estimating nucleation mode aerosol particles using satellite data were carried out at SMEAR II station in Hyytiala, Southern Finland (Kulmala et al., 2011), the north-eastern part of South Africa (Sundstrom et al., 2015) and forested location in southern Indiana (Sullivan et al., 2016). Therefore, the method of satellite-based proxies to trace the nucleation mode of aerosol particles on regional and global scales needs to be further explored. In this study, we examined the proxies, i.e., parameterizations for the nucleation mode aerosol particle concentrations in terms of satellite-observed quantities.

METHODS

The whole study was driven at the Himalayan Cloud Observatory (HCO) established at Swami Ram Teerth (SRT) Campus (30.34 N, 78.40 E, 1706 m AMSL), Badshahithaul, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India and it is situated at 3 km from the town Chamba of district Tehri Garhwal and 13 km from the district headquarter Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand. The particle number size distribution (PNSD) data was collected from 1 January, 2021 to 31 December, 2021 at HCO using a NanoScan Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) which measures the PNSD from 11.5 nm to 365.2 nm in diameter. The satellite data including sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), formaldehyde (HCHO), and ultraviolet irradiance at 310 nm (UV) are retrieved from the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) on the AURA satellite (overpass ~0700 to 0900 local standard time (LST)) (Sullivan et al., 2016; Nee et al., 2024). Aerosol optical depth (AOD) at 550 nm and angstrom exponent (AE) at (412-470 nm) are retrieved using the 'dark-target' algorithm from MODIS on the Terra (~0730-0830 LST) satellite (Levy et al., 2015). The proxies are calculated using the equations which were introduced by Kulmala et al., (2011) and further explored in Sundstrom et al., (2015). After calculating proxies, we have estimated the nucleation mode aerosol particle concentration.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.24$, Nobs = 53) is found as expected between the satellite proxy NO_2/AOD and nucleation mode aerosol particle concentration (Nnuc) while a weak correlation ($R^2 = 0.07$, Nobs = 49) is obtained between the satellite proxy SO_2/AOD and Nnuc. If the source term in the $\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{UVB}/\text{AOD}^2$ proxy was replaced by $\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{UVB}$, the correlation with Nnuc at HCO would be $R^2 = 0.26$. This implies that over areas where SO_2 and NO_2 are affected by some common factors such as emission sources, the satellite NO_2 could be a better estimate for the source term than SO_2 .

CONCLUSIONS

This study explores the use of proxies using satellite data to obtain information on the nucleation mode aerosol particle concentration (Nnuc). The relation between satellite-based proxies and Nnuc was obtained for SO_2/AOD ($R^2 = 0.07$) and NO_2/AOD ($R^2 = 0.26$). It is found that the satellite NO_2 column correlates better than the satellite SO_2 column.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like thanks to my supervisor Dr. Alok Sagar Gautam for guidance and support. I also thank to Department of Physics, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal for the providing all facilities.

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THE PERSISTENT BURDEN OF AIR POLLUTANTS: A LONG-TERM TREND ANALYSIS OVER MAJOR INDIA'S METROPOLISES

VIKRANT TOMAR^{1,2}, MANISH NAJA¹, SHYAM LAL³, UPENDRA KUMAR²

¹Arybhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Nainital – 263001, India

²Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly - 243006, India

³Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad - 380009, India

KEYWORDS: Long Term Trend, Air Quality, South Asia

INTRODUCTION

Air quality in South Asia, particularly in Indian megacities, has worsened due to rapid population and urbanization growth, leading to frequent air quality crises. With 22 of the world's 30 most polluted cities, India faces serious global health risks. High Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) values indicate elevated particulate matter, which correlates with poor air quality and health risks. Prolonged exposure to pollutants like ozone (O₃), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and carbon monoxide (CO) contributes to cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, leading to premature mortality. CO is a colorless, odorless gas produced by burning biomass, fossil fuels, and hydrocarbons, influencing radiative forcing through ozone, methane, and CO₂ production. NO₂, a key NO_x component, affects lung health, with trends decreasing in the US and Europe but rising in India (Elshorbany et al., 2024). Tropospheric ozone, driven by precursors CO and NO_x, impacts air quality, health, and climate, with significant increases in India due to urbanization. AOD, a measure of atmospheric aerosols, is high in the Indo-Gangetic region, primarily from biomass burning, worsening regional air quality. Ground-based networks in India are sparse and prone to shutdowns, while satellite-based sensors provide continuous, reliable data for long-term air quality analysis. This study focuses on the long-term trends of key pollutants Total Columnar CO (TCO), AOD, Tropospheric NO₂ (TrNO₂), and Tropospheric O₃ (TrO₃), over major Indian metropolitan areas, using satellite data and global models to examine their variability and sources over the past two decades.

METHODS

A long-term study was conducted across six major Indian cities—Delhi (DL), Kolkata (KL), Mumbai (MB), Bangalore (BG), Hyderabad (HY), and Guwahati (GHY) using a 1° spatial box. The major urban centres in India face distinct air pollution challenges due to rapid population growth, industrial activities, and vehicular emissions. These cities are characterized by diverse industries, including power plants and unorganized sectors, contributing significantly to pollution levels. The study utilizes satellite-based data for key air pollutants. Tropospheric ozone is derived from OMI/MLS, while NO₂, CO, and AOD data are retrieved from the OMI, MOPITT, and MODIS instruments on the Aura and Terra satellites, respectively. Gridded satellite data for each pollutant is averaged over the study sites for analysis. Columnar data from global reanalysis datasets, including CAMS for CO, NO₂, and AOD, and MERRA2 for AOD and CO, are used to compare with satellite data over the same region. For long term trend analysis, we have used Generalized Least Square (GLS) method for tropospheric ozone and its precursors along with AOD. Starting with the deseasonalized monthly time series for each parameter and then employing GLS for trend analysis. To address autocorrelation in time series data by using moving block bootstrap in conjunction with GLS to account for uncertainty in trend analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1: Long term trend in anomaly of TCO, AOD from 2000-2023 at all six urban sites using distinctive satellite and reanalysis data.

The long-term trend of TCO from 2000 to 2022 for six sites (Figure 1), with most sites exhibiting a negative trend, except for HY, which shows a slightly positive but insignificant trend. Delhi (DL) shows the steepest decline, with TCO decreasing at the highest rate among the sites. Northern India urban sites, like DL and KL, show a more pronounced decreasing trend compared to southern cities like BG and HY. Comparisons with reanalysis models reveal that MERRA2 reflects the negative trends, while CAMS shows significant positive trends, except for GHY. Figure 1 shows a positive long-term trend in Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) for all sites from 2000 to 2022. KL has the highest AOD increase, while DL shows the lowest. Unlike the global decline in AOD over regions like the USA and China (Buchholz et al., 2021), India has seen an increase, particularly in southern cities, likely due to rising anthropogenic activities such as coal power emissions, rapid growth in vehicular emission exacerbated by inadequate traffic management systems. Both CAMS and MERRA2 models capture similar significant trends with slightly lower rates. The long-term trend of TrNO₂ for all sites from the early 2000s to 2023, reveals a positive trend at all sites. HY exhibits the highest increase (about 3.7×10^{13} molecules/cm²/yr), while DL shows negligible change. The rise in HY is attributed to coal power plants and increased anthropogenic activities. The insignificant trend in DL, combined with the decline in TCCO, reflects the impact of recent policies on emissions and encourages the use of electric vehicles and CNG (Verma and Nagendra, 2022). Comparisons of satellite data with CAMS total columnar NO₂ indicate an increasing trend, though slope values are likely overestimated due to model resolution and emission inventory factors. TrO₃ shows a significant increasing trend at all sites from 2005 to 2020, with high certainty. This trend aligns with regional patterns in India. HY exhibits the highest rate of increase in ozone precursors, NO₂ and CO, contributing to a notable increase of 0.3 DU/yr. In contrast, Delhi shows the lowest TrO₃ trend (0.2 DU/yr), influenced by a significant decrease in CO and an insignificant NO₂ trend. However, the role of volatile organic compounds can significantly contribute to the long-term changes in the TrO₃.

CONCLUSION

This study analyses long-term trends in CO, AOD, NO₂, and O₃ using data from space-borne sensors and global reanalysis models at urban sites. Total Columnar CO (TCO) shows a decreasing trend at all sites except HY, reflecting global patterns, influenced by improved vehicular emissions and increased lower tropospheric water vapor. AOD derived from MODIS exhibits an increasing trend, particularly at KL, indicating heightened regional

sources. TrNO₂ also shows a significant upward trend, driven mainly by power generation. The trends of CO and NO₂, as key ozone precursors, correlate with TrCO₃ trends, especially at HY (0.3 DU/yr) and DL. Overall, MERRA2 reflects better long-term trends for TCO and AOD.

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ESTIMATION OF MASS INTERCEPTION FACTOR USING BE-7 AS A TRACER AT RAWATBHATA, RAJASTHAN

TEJPAL MENARIA¹, A. K. JAIN¹, S.N. TIWARI¹, I.V. SARADHI²

¹Environmental Survey Laboratory, EMAD, BARC, Rawatbhata, 323307.

²Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division (EMAD), BARC, 400085

KEYWORDS: Beryllium-7, Mass Interception, Gamma Spectrometry, Deposition Velocity

INTRODUCTION

The fraction of deposited materials intercepted and finally retained by standing biomass of vegetation is termed as mass interception fraction (α). Interception of dry and wet deposited radionuclides by plants depends on various factors such as the stage of development of the plant canopy, the capacity of the canopy to retain water, chemical properties of the radionuclide, amount of rain during a rainfall event and intensity of precipitation [Prohl, 2007]. Mass interception factor has been estimated by modelling (multi-linear regression model, process-based model, pollutant sub-model, equilibrium reversible model and kinetic irreversible models), using stable element (Be, Cs and iodine vapour) and tracer (⁷Be, ⁸⁹Sr, ⁵¹Cr, ²¹⁰Pb) (Keim, et al. 2006, Gonze and Sy, 2016, Karunakara, et al. 2017, Jacob, et al., 1993). There are few experimental data available in the literature that account for the kinetics of Cesium attachment to crop leaf surface, air-to-grass mass interception factor using stable iodine in elemental form (Hoffman, et al. 1992) and ⁷Be as tracer. ⁷Be is a naturally occurring cosmogenic radionuclide produced in the atmosphere through spallation reactions with atmospheric nuclei of nitrogen and oxygen. ⁷Be atoms diffuse in the atmosphere in the form of BeO or Be (OH)₂ and get attached to aerosol particles (0.04 to 2 nm) and are intercepted by vegetation due to fallout, washout or resuspended matter (IAEA-119). Continuous production of ⁷Be coupled with its short half-life, and the similarity of its physico chemical properties with ¹³⁷Cs renders it a useful tracer to study environmental processes. This paper presents studies carried out on the mass interception factor using ⁷Be as a tracer in Rawatbhata, Rajasthan, India.

METHOD

Concentrations of ⁷Be in rain water, surface deposition, biota, vegetation and particulate air samples were measured by gamma-ray spectrometry technique using gamma photopeak of 477 keV employing P-type HPGe detector, (110% relative efficiency, resolution of 1.9 keV) and counting time of 80,000 sec. Efficiency and energy calibration of the HPGe detector were carried out using the certified reference material from the IAEA. Grass and plant leaves of various endemic plant species common to this area were collected in different seasons of the year, weighed, dried, homogenised and counted in Marinelli beaker geometry. ⁷Be activity in vegetation was estimated by standard method and decay correction for ⁷Be activity was applied to account for the delay time during the sampling and counting. The mass interception factor (α) is calculated using the following equation:

$$\alpha = \frac{C_v \lambda_E}{[d]_i \{1 - e^{(-\lambda_E t_E)}\}}$$

where α , mass interception factor (m².kg⁻¹), is the fraction of deposited activity intercepted by the vegetation per unit mass as a result of both wet and dry deposition processes, C_v (Bq kg⁻¹ dry matter) is the concentration of the ⁷Be radionuclide, d_i is the total deposition rate

from wet deposition processes, λE is the effective rate constant for the reduction of the activity concentration of radionuclide due to radiological (λ_i) and environmental processes (λ_w) and t_e is duration for which vegetations are exposed to ^7Be contamination in days. Table 1 gives the details of parameter values used for the estimation of the mass interception factor (α).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Measured ^7Be activity in the collected vegetation samples ranged from 5.3 to 335.7 Bq.kg⁻¹ with a mean activity of 73.1 Bq.kg⁻¹ dry weight. The highest mean ^7Be activity was observed in Cariaca papaya leaves and lowest in Lagenaria Siceraria. The observed ^7Be concentration trend in studied leaf samples was Cariaca papaya > Ricinus Communis > Musa Acuminate. The estimated mass interception factor ranged from 0.1 to 3.2 with mean values of 0.8 m².kg⁻¹ (Table-2). The estimated ^7Be activity and mass interception factor in this study are similar to a study carried out in Narora environment (0.7-2.5 m².kg⁻¹) [Goutam et al. 2022] and Kudankulam environment (0.7-2.3 m².kg⁻¹) [Selvi, et al. 2020] but lower than Kaiga environment (0.7-5.6 m².kg⁻¹) [James et al. 2010] and reported value of (3.0 m².kg⁻¹) IAEA-119]. As plant surfaces are negatively charged, they have properties of cation exchangers. ^7Be being a bivalent cation, seems to be more strongly retained on plant surfaces. The difference in measured values in mass interception factor among different varieties can be attributed to surface roughness, interface area of interaction, water storage capacity and biomass density of leafy vegetation. Also, the present study was compared with similar studies carried out using different methods and are presented in Table 3.

Table 1: Parameter values used for estimation of mass interception factor for Rawatbhata

Dry deposition rate (Bq.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹) (Jain et al., 2023)	Wet deposition rate (Bq.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹) (Tejpal et al., 2023)	λ_i (per day)	λ_w (per day)	λ_E (per day)	T_e (days)
6.30	0.47	0.01	0.0	0.063	45
		3	5		

Table-2: Measured ^7Be activity and estimated mass interception factor in different vegetation samples

Common Name	Biological name	^7Be Activity (Bq.kg ⁻¹)			Mass interception factor (m ² .kg ⁻¹)		
		Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean
Katuka	Picrochiza Kurroa	62.5	92.5	77.5	0.7	1.0	0.8
Madar	Calotropis Gigantea	74.9	140.6	114.9	0.8	1.5	1.2
Arandi	Ricinus Communis	123.8	132.8	128.1	1.3	1.4	1.4
Banana	Musa Paradisiaca	8.5	125.0	49.8	0.1	1.2	0.5
Banyan	Ficus	33.4	46.4	38.7	0.3	0.4	0.4

	Benghalensis						
Grass	Sorghastrum Nutans	30.8	55.2	49.8	0.3	0.6	0.5
Gulmohar	Delonix regia	39.8	71.1	53.4	0.4	0.7	0.5
Jamun	Syzygium Cumini	48.3	66.0	57.2	0.5	0.6	0.5
Khair	Acacia Senegal	27.9	117.2	71.1	0.4	1.2	0.5
Mango	Mangifera Indica	19.2	58.0	32.4	0.2	0.4	0.3
Neem	Azadirachta Indica	71.3	119.9	95.1	0.7	1.2	0.9
Pappaya	Cariaca pappaya	79.5	224.3	151.9	0.8	2.2	1.5
Banana	Musa Acuminata	44.5	335.7	125.4	0.3	3.2	1.2

Table 3: Comparison of mass interception factor for Rawatbhata site with a study using different methods

S	Studied method	Mass interception factor	Reference
N		m ² .kg ⁻¹	
1	Elemental iodine in an environmental chamber	2.2	Karunakara, 2017
2	Lycopodium spore's deposition on grass	3.0	Chamberlain, 1970
3	Derived mass interception factor from Chernobyl fallout	0.9-1.9 for Iodine 0.5-1.2 for Cesium	IAEA TECDOC 857
4	Using simulated rain	1.6	Angeletti, 1977

CONCLUSIONS

Using cosmogenic ⁷Be as a tracer, aerosol deposition rates, and mass interception factors in various vegetations have been evaluated for Rawatbhata Rajasthan. Mass interception factors for vegetation were found to range from 0.1 - 3.2 m².kg⁻¹ dry weight with a mean value of 0.8 m².kg⁻¹ dry weight.

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EMPORAL CHANGES IN THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF PM_{2.5} FROM 2018-2024 IN DELHI NCR

ARKABANEE MUKHERJEE^{1*}, ATAR SINGH PIPAL¹, NAGESHWAR RAO¹, R LATHA¹, PRAMOD KORI¹, VIKASH KUMAR¹, HARDEEP SHARMA¹, SANDIP NIVDANGE², DAMODAR KARRI¹, NAVEEN GANDHI¹, AND SACHIN GHUDE¹

¹Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology Pune 411008, India

²Department of Environmental Science, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune 411016

KEYWORDS: GRAP, PM_{2.5}, Chemical Characterization, Metal Concentration

INTRODUCTION

Implementation of Graded Response Action Plan (GRAP) I, II, III, and IV for mitigation during high pollution days in Delhi NCR has been initiated since 2021 by the Commission of Air Quality Management (CAQM). Due to the stringency imposed by CAQM, the major contributor to high AQI PM_{2.5} has reduced significantly. A previous offline sampling campaign conducted at one of the prominent residential areas of Delhi for chemical characterization of PM_{2.5} and source apportionment study during January and February 2018 has already been published (Latha et al 2022). Another recent offline sampling campaign was conducted in 2024 during the same period and location. After the revocation of GRAP IV and III, GRAP I and II were implemented majorly during the sampling period. This comparative study focused on the temporal change of PM_{2.5} from winter 2018 (before GRAP implementation) to winter 2024 (during GRAP I and II) and its change in chemical constituents after these years.

METHOD

Offline sampling campaigns during both 2018 and 2024 were conducted in the Delhi IMD Lodhi Road campus. The Envirotech model low volume sampler (LVS) APM 550 was deployed in the field for PM_{2.5} sampling during both sampling periods. During 2018 the daily samples were collected for 13 hours which included PM deposition during meteorologically stable (02:00-09:00 hrs) and unstable (10:00-16:00 hrs) conditions. In 2024 the daily samples were collected in a 24-hour sampling mode. A detailed method of sample collection, preparation, and analysis was mentioned in the published paper of Latha et al. (2022). Metal concentrations (Cr, Ni, Mn, Cu, Pb, Zn) of all samples collected during 2018 and 2024 were analyzed using AAS (Analytik Jena made Contra 800) and ICPMS (Agilent-made) respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The stringency of GRAP I, II, III, and IV during poor to severe air quality index (AQI) since 2021 in Delhi NCR has significantly reduced the total PM load in the last few years. The details of GRAP classification are mentioned in table 1. In this comparative experimental observation, the maximum deposition of PM_{2.5} on filter paper during January and February was reported to be 357.19 and 292.14 µg/m³ in 2024 whereas; the same values were 480.62 µg/m³ and 356.14 µg/m³ in 2018 respectively (Fig 1). The monthly average values of PM_{2.5} deposition in the sampling campaign during January and February were 75% and 12%

Table 1 Classification of GRAP according to AQI.

GRAP IMPLEMENTATION	AQI RANGES	CATEGORY
GRAP I	200-301	Poor
GRAP II	301-400	Very Poor
GRAP III	401-450	Severe
GRAP IV	>450	Severe plus

higher in 2018 than in 2024 respectively. After considering the disparity of 13 hours and 24-hour sampling duration in 2018 and 2024, the actual reduction of total PM2.5 concentration would be much higher than the reported values respectively.

Fig 1 Temporal change in the PM2.5 in Delhi NCR.

After understanding the metal components of the PM Interestingly, along with the reduction, concentration magnitudes of elements like Cr and Ni were observed with a significant increase of 1.93 and 2-fold during only January 2024 from 2018. The same values remain as high as 9.1- and 14.4-folds during February respectively. The monthly average concentration of Zn was also noticed to follow a similar trend, an increase of 23-fold from January 2018 to 2024 was observed in this case. This comparative study has indicated that despite a significant decline in the total PM2.5 concentrations from 2018 to 2024, the contribution of certain elemental loads has notably increased simultaneously. Another study by Gulia et al (2021) compared the impact of GRAP on 4 different locations in Delhi NCR and reported the efficiency of particulate reduction varies within locations as local activities play an important role. Hence, a detailed study on source identification and apportionment has become the need of the hour for precise policymaking.

CONCLUSION

The study showed a significant reduction in PM2.5 concentrations in winter (January and February) from 2018 to 2024 as an impact of implementing GRAP in Delhi NCR. However, changes in anthropogenic activities state increase in the heavy metal concentration acts as a potential threat to human health in case of long-term exposure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the Director, IITM, and Secretary, Ministry of Earth Sciences (Govt. of India) for their encouragement and support. This research work has been funded by MOES.

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SIZE SPECIFIC OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF PARTICULATE MATTER AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH AIR QUALITY INDEX

ATAR SINGH PIPAL¹, HARDEEP SHARMA¹, M. NAGESWAR RAO¹, ARKABANEE MUKHERJEE¹, SANDIP NIVDANGE², SACHIN D. GHUDE¹

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Pune, 411008, India
Department of Environmental Sciences, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, 411007

KEYWORDS: Oxidative Potential, Synoptic Variability, Hazard Index, AOI

INTRODUCTION

High levels of particulate matter (PM) during the severe winter air pollution episodes pose significant health risks in Delhi. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the temporal variations in air toxicity, the chemical composition of PM and its source apportionment for a better understanding of the health risk assessment and air quality management strategies. The exposure to PM pollution is a significant health risk, thus, search for advanced metrics that more precisely reflect the possible impairment to human health. In this regard, the oxidative potential (OP) has been measured in different size aerosol particles along with their relationship with the air quality index (AQI) which was collected from Delhi during the winter period. OP is emerging as a promising health-based metric that could have different properties to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) and is believed to be a predictor of toxicity.

METHODS

OC and EC analysis was carried out by DRI Thermal/Optical Carbon Analyzer (Model 2001, Atmoslytic Inc., USA) using the IMPROVE protocol with thermal-optical reflectance (TOR). The first phase of analysis is in a non-oxidizing (pure He) atmosphere which occurs at different temperature heating cycles such as 140 °C, 290 °C, 480 °C, and 580 °C, and the carbon fractions were obtained as OC1, OC2, OC3, and OC4, respectively. The second phase of analysis is in the oxidizing atmosphere (2% O₂ and 98% He) arising at high temperatures such as 580 °C, 740 °C, and 840°C and the carbon fractions were quantified as EC1, EC2, and EC3, respectively. The oxidative potential (OP) of water-soluble PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ was measured using the dithiothreitol (DTT) assay method. Briefly, 2 ml of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ extract with 1 ml of K-buffer (0.5 mM) solution followed by 2 ml of DTT (1 mM) was placed in an Amber centrifuge tube in the incubator bath at 37 °C. Further, 1 ml of extract was taken from incubation vials at various time intervals (such as 0, 10, 20, 30 min), and 50 µl of 10 mM 5,5'- Dithiobis-2-Nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) was added in the reaction vials. At each time point (0, 10, 20, and 30, min), the reaction between DTT and redox-active components was quenched by adding 50 µL 0.5 mM DTNB to form a chromophore with absorbance at 412 nm. The absorbance at 412 nm was recorded by an ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu (UV-1800) Spectrophotometer, Japan).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The carbonaceous species such as organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) along with their estimated primary and secondary fractions (POC and SOC) are depicted in Figure 1. The average value of OC and EC was found to be $37.76 \pm 20.98 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $3.30 \pm 2.00 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for PM₁ while in PM_{2.5} OC and EC was $43.64 \pm 26.68 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $3.54 \pm 1.75 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The primary organic carbon (POC) (PM₁: $29.70 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and PM_{2.5}: $27.58 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) was found

higher as compared to secondary organic carbon (SOC) (PM₁: 8.10 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and PM_{2.5}: 16.00 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in Delhi. This inferred that carbonaceous aerosol particles were mostly emitted from combustion activities (fossil fuels, coal combustion and biomass burning). The OP results showed significant variability as a function of PM size fractions as well as temporal scale (Figure 2). The mean OPm values for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ in Delhi were 2.17 ± 0.89 (range: 0.13–4.95), 0.19 ± 0.15 (range: 0.03–0.63), and 0.21 ± 0.16 (range: 0.04–0.65) $\text{nmol min}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. Higher OPm was found for coarser particles as compared to finer particles. The hazard index (HI) was also estimated to understand the variation of toxicity using WHO and CPCB standards. Higher HI suggests that the PM mass concentration should not be sufficient to explain the PM toxicity.

Figure 1: Concentration of organic and elemental composition of PM samples.

Therefore, it is required to measure the PM toxicity directly or indirectly to better understand their health effects in addition to the exposure level. The comparison of OP and HI allows us to see how OP activity can be different from the HI values consequently showing the additional benefits of OP measurements. The comparison of OP with the AQI scale and hazard index (HI) showed the days having satisfactory air quality exhibiting high OP which was like very poor and severe air quality days. This means that OP is the independent parameter that depends on various factors like chemical composition, inhalation rate and aerosol characteristics.

Figure 2: Time series of oxidative potential (a) for PM₁₀, (b) for PM_{2.5} and PM₁ in the study area.

CONCLUSION

- The result showed that the oxidative potential (OP) does not depend on PM concentration and is not significantly related to AQI categories.
- The higher OP_m as compared to OP_v, and compared with other studies, it was found that OP_v was lower than other studies but OP_m was several times higher indicating a high risk of chemical speciation.
- Higher HI suggests that the PM mass concentration should not be sufficient to explain the PM toxicity.
- Therefore, it is required to measure the PM toxicity directly or indirectly to better understand their health effects in addition to the exposure level.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Director IITM for the support and encouragement during the research work. MoES, the Government of India funded the MAPAN project. We also thank the Department of Chemistry, Savitribai Phule Pune University (SPPU) for using the chemical laboratory and their support to analyse aerosol toxicity.

CHARACTERISTICS OF LONG-TERM SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION IN AN URBAN LOCATION IN INDIA

M. SEBASTIAN¹, V. P. KANAWADE^{1,2}, N. MITTAL³

¹Centre for Earth, Ocean and Atmospheric Sciences, University of Hyderabad, India

²Climate and Atmospheric Research Centre, Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

³TSI Instruments India Private Limited, Bangalore, India

KEYWORDS: Ultrafine Particles, Size-Segregated Particles, New Particle Formation and Growth

INTRODUCTION

New particle formation has been extensively studied globally, particularly in Europe, the USA and China (Kerminen et al., 2018a; Kulmala et al., 2004), while it has not yet been extensively explored in the Indian context (Kanawade et al., 2021). Atmospheric aerosols vary in a wide size range with four orders of magnitude difference between the smallest and the largest particle diameter. The spatial and temporal variability in aerosol emissions strongly modulates the dynamical behaviour and associated properties of aerosols in the atmosphere (Costabile et al., 2009; Kerminen et al., 2018b; Zhang et al., 2015). The airborne production of aerosols is the largest source of aerosol numbers in the atmosphere (Kulmala, 2003; Zhang, 2010). The growth of newly formed particles and primary particles can significantly alter the total aerosol mass and composition which has implications for Earth's radiation budget and hydrological cycle via direct and indirect effects, respectively.

METHODS

In this study, we have used long-term (2019-2022) observations of particle number size distributions from the nano Condensation Nucleus Counter (nCNC) in the size range from 1 to 3 nm and Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) from 10 nm to 600 nm in an urban location, Hyderabad (University of Hyderabad campus site), in India. The observation days were broadly classified into different event types, such as NPF event (NPF), non-event, polluted event (PE), and undefined, based on the visual evaluation of the contour plot of particle number size distributions. The pollutant event days were identified based on measured particulate matter of less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) to identify polluted days following the NAAQS criteria (days with PM_{2.5} > 60 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). We have calculated size-segregated particle number concentrations in four particle modes, such as cluster mode (sub-3nm), nucleation mode (10-25 nm), Aitken mode (25-100 nm) and accumulation mode (100-600 nm).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The size-segregated particle number concentrations followed a clear seasonal pattern, with the highest concentrations during pre-monsoon (March - May) and the lowest in the winter (December - February). The largest particle number concentrations during pre-monsoon correspond to the highest frequency of NPFs occurrence (Figure 1). Cluster-mode particles constituted the largest fraction of particle number concentrations, while accumulation-mode particles constituted the least. Cluster mode particle number concentrations were observed to be highest on NPF days compared to other event types. We also observed the positive association between cluster mode particles and PM_{2.5}, indicating airborne secondary production of aerosols is not inhibited by high pre-existing particle concentrations. This can

be explained by precursor vapour-laden polluted air and the balance between precursor vapour concentrations and pre-existing particle concentrations, which determines when aerosol formation will occur in the atmosphere. On the contrary, we observed the negative association between nucleation mode particles and PM_{2.5} implies that not all cluster mode particles grow to nucleation mode size.

Figure 1. Monthly percentage of occurrence of NPF event, non-event polluted event and undefined event days based on total valid observations days at Hyderabad from 1 April 2019 to 7 December 2022.

CONCLUSIONS

Cluster mode (1-3 nm diameter) particles constitute the largest fraction of particle numbers throughout the year. Accumulation mode contributes the largest fraction of aerosol mass. Airborne secondary aerosol production contributes significantly to cluster, nucleation, and Aitken mode number concentrations while insignificantly to total aerosol mass.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

VPK acknowledge financial support from the Department of Science & Technology (DST)-Science Engineering Research Board (SERB; ECR/2016/001333) and DST-Climate Change Division Program (Aerosol/89/2017). MS acknowledge the Institute of Eminence, University of Hyderabad (sanction no. UoH/IoE/RC1/RC1-20-014).

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INFLUENCE OF SEA SALTS ON NUCLEATION PRECURSOR INTERACTIONS: A STUDY OF CLUSTER FORMATION UNDER VARIABLE ATMOSPHERIC CONDITIONS

D. VADGAMA¹, R. SRIVASTAVA¹ AND S. SHINDE¹

¹Department of Physics, School of Energy Technology, Pandit Deendayal Energy University, Raisan, Gandhinagar – 382426, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Sea Salts, Nucleation Precursors, Thermodynamic parameters, Binding Energy.

INTRODUCTION

The formation of aerosols is crucial for understanding cloud formation, as aerosols affect the climate by changing the radiation budget and serving as cloud condensation nuclei. Experimental investigations are difficult for the initial stages of prenucleation complex formation, which leads to larger aerosols. To understand the formation of these complexes, the interaction between the sea salts (NaCl, KCl and MgCl₂) and nucleation precursors (H₂O and H₂SO₄) is investigated (Elm et al., 2020).

METHODS

Each step of nucleation has been comprehensively examined and thermodynamical parameters have been computed to find the stabilities of the molecular complexes (Elm et al., 2023).

Fig. 1 Computational Methodology utilized to derive structure with the lowest energy

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. II The identified lowest free energy molecular structure (298.15 K, 101.325 kPa)

Fig. III Calculated Binding Free Energies at 298.15 K
 (A: $(SS)_1(W)_1 \rightleftharpoons SS + W$ B: $(SS)_1(W)_2 \rightleftharpoons SS + 2*W$ C: $(SS)_1(W)_3 \rightleftharpoons SS + 3*W$ D: $(SS)_1(SA)_1 \rightleftharpoons SS + SA$ E: $(SS)_1(SA)_2 \rightleftharpoons SS + 2*SA$ F: $(SA)_1(SA)_3 \rightleftharpoons SS + 3*SA$ G: $(SS)_1(W)_1(SA)_1 \rightleftharpoons SS + W + SA$ H: $(SS)_1(W)_1(SA)_2 \rightleftharpoons SS + W + 2*SA$ I: $(SS)_1(W)_1(SA)_3 \rightleftharpoons SS + W + 3*SA$)

Energy comparison of different cluster configurations can be helpful to identify the most stable structures and to understand the factors that drive cluster growth. Among all complexes, the binding energies of the cluster $(SS)_1(W)_1(SA)_3$ are found to be the lowest due to the formation of HCl, hydrogen bonding and weak Van der Waal forces. The addition of H_2SO_4 increases the reactivity of the cluster $(SS)_1(W)_n$, while the addition of H_2O molecules reduces the reactivity of the cluster $(SS)_1(SA)_n$.

CONCLUSION

The strong stabilization upon the addition of H_2SO_4 to salts indicates that the formation of stable aerosol particles is favourable in the atmosphere where sulfuric acid and sea salts are present. The exothermic nature of the interaction between sea salt, H_2SO_4 and H_2O clusters across various compositions indicates that these complexes are stable and likely to persist, contributing to the growth of aerosol particles. The mechanisms that govern aerosol generation in marine and coastal environments can be understood by the interactions. This work offers a new understanding of sea salts' role in clusterization, formation of CCN and aerosols' activation.

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AEROSOL DYNAMICS UNVEILED: COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION ACROSS TWO KEY HIMALAYAN SITES IN UTTARAKHAND, INDIA

A. S. GAUTAM¹, K. SINGH¹

¹Himalayan Atmospheric and Space Physics Research Laboratory (HASPRL), Department of Physics, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar, Uttarakhand – 246174,

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Particle Number Size Distribution, New Particle Formation, Growth Rate, Western Himalayan Region.

INTRODUCTION

New particle formation (NPF) is the process by which tiny particles form and grow from gaseous precursors in the atmosphere. These particles can act as cloud condensation nuclei, influencing cloud formation, precipitation patterns, and air quality (Maso et al., 2005; Kulmala et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2012; Sebastian et al., 2021). In this study, aerosol particle number size distribution (PNSD) was observed using a NanoScan Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS), measuring particles ranging from 11.5 nm to 154 nm, at two distinct locations in the Himalayan region of Uttarakhand, India. A year-long observation of PNSD was conducted at a high-altitude location, Swami Ram Teertha (SRT) Campus (30.34°N, 78.40°E, 1706 m AMSL), Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Tehri Garhwal, from January 1, 2021, to December 31, 2021. Another year-long observation was carried out at the Himalayan Atmospheric and Space Physics Research Laboratory (HASPRL), Department of Physics, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University (A Central University), Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand, in the Alaknanda Valley (30°13'37.3"N, 78°48'14.2"E, 640 m AMSL), from January 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023.

METHODS

The size-segregated particle concentrations were derived by integrating the nucleation mode, Aitken mode, accumulation mode, and total particle number concentration in the size ranges of 10–25 nm (4 size bins), 25–100 nm (4 size bins), 100–154 nm (2 size bins), and 10–154 nm (10 size bins), respectively. We classified NPF events into three types based on visual inspection of the contour plot of the aerosol size distributions (Maso et al., 2005). The identification of NPF was determined by the presence of a distinct new mode of particles with diameters smaller than 25 nm, showing steady growth in diameter for at least 6 hours, during which the aerosol size distributions displayed a 'banana'-shaped aerosol growth pattern. The particle growth rate (GR) was calculated by fitting a first-order polynomial line through the growing particle mode diameter (10–25 nm) as a function of time and determining its slope, following the methodology of Maso et al. (2005), modified and updated by Westervelt et al. (2013). Additionally, the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model was used to investigate transport directions from primary aerosol sources in the boundary layer of the sampling site

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The PNSD spectrum for both locations show similar morning and evening peaks in particle concentration. The average total particle number concentration, with standard deviation, was measured at $4.28 \times 10^4 \pm 1.90 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at HCO, Tehri Garhwal, and $7.18 \times 10^4 \pm 1.20 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$

at HASPRL, Chauras. The morning peaks at Chauras indicated an increase in larger-sized particles, primarily emitted from anthropogenic sources such as vehicular activity on the national highway. In contrast, the evening peak suggested a minor increase and growth in particles due to new particle formation, observed between 1400 and 1700 LT, originating from nucleation mode particles. Analysis of meteorological parameters revealed that the wind speed was highest from the southwest direction (valley area) at HCO, while at HASPRL, the strongest winds came from the southeast direction (Srinagar Garhwal Valley area).

Figure 1. Particle number size distribution (PNSD) with total particle concentration at two distinct locations (left for HCO, Tehri Garhwal and right for HASPRL, Chauras).

CONCLUSIONS

At HASPRL, smaller aerosol particles showed an increase in the morning, likely due to emissions from anthropogenic sources originating from the southwest. In the evening, larger aerosol particles exhibited an increase, probably driven by various human activities such as vehicular emissions, sand and stone transportation, and other anthropogenic contributions from the southeast. At HCO, the particles were likely transported from the valley area, moving in a trajectory from the southeast to the southwest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

ASG and KS thank the Department of Physics, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal for providing all facilities.

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ASSESSMENT OF ATTACHED AND AEROSOL-BOUND RADON AND THORON PROGENY IN THE MAIN BOUNDARY THRUST, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA

TUSHAR KANDARI¹, SUDIPTA KANDARI², AMAR DEEP³ AND ALOK SAGAR GAUTAM⁴

¹Municipal Post Graduate College, Department of Physics, Mussoorie-248179, Uttarakhand

²Shri Gulab Singh Govt. Degree College Chakrata, Department of Physics Chakrata-248123,

³Dhanauri P.G. College, Department of Physics, Dhanauri-247661, Haridwar, Uttarakhand,

⁴Department of Physics, H.N.B. University Garhwal, Srinagar Garhwal

KEYWORDS: DTPS/DRPS, Main Boundary Thrust, Dose Conversion Factor, Equilibrium Factor.

INTRODUCTION

Radon and its decay products, particularly polonium-212 and polonium-214, pose significant health risks through α -particle emissions, which can damage lung tissue and increase the risk of lung cancer. Classified as a Group 1 carcinogen by IARC, radon exposure is a key public health concern due to its link to radiation exposure and potential DNA damage. Airborne radon decay products, deposited in the respiratory tract, can damage tissues and DNA, with their impact dependent on size distribution. Unattached progeny (AMD < 10 nm) causes more damage due to high diffusion rates, while attached progeny (AMD 10–1000 nm) adhere to particles and release energy during decay. Assessing both fractions is crucial for understanding radiation dosimetry.

METHODS

The present study focuses on the measurement of Radon, Thoron and Progeny concentration in the Main Boundary Thrust region of Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand, India. For this purpose, pin-hole based single entry Radon/Thoron discriminating dosimeters and DTPS/DRPS have been deployed in 12 locations consisting of 76 samples on and along the Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) region. The measurements were performed on four campaigns i.e. Summer (April-June), Rainy (July-September), Winter (October- January) and Autumn (February and March). With the present data from these campaigns; we analyzed the EETC and EERC hence estimating the annual effective doses.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

With the below graphs, it is clearly visible that Radon, Thoron and progeny concentration is on the higher side during the winter campaign. 30% and 31% of the total samples depict that radon concentration ranges from 100 to 120 Bq/m³ which is on the higher side as compared to the other samples. Similar are the results for Thoron, EERC and EETC during the winter campaign. These higher concentrations in the winter campaigns are due to the lower ventilation conditions in the indoor environments of the sampling locations. The obtained experimental results are helpful for calculation of the total annual effective dose, dose

conversion factor, equilibrium factor etc.

Figure 1: Frequency distribution curve for the Radon, Thoron and their progeny concentration with reference to the Seasonal variation.

CONCLUSIONS

The results reveal that the winter campaign delivers the maximum concentration of Radon, Thoron and their progeny concentration in the present sampling locations. Winter campaign delivers a higher concentration because of the minimum ventilation conditions as the sampling site is located in the Himalayan Region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Corresponding Author (TK) expresses his deep sense of gratitude to Nodal Radon/Thoron Calibration Centre, HNB Garhwal University, SRT Campus, Tehri Garhwal, for providing laboratory facilities.

STUDY OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR POLLUTANTS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN THE FOOTHILL HIMALAYAN REGION OF UTTARAKHAND, INDIA

SUDIPTA^{1*}, A. DEEP², T. KANDARI³, K. SINGH⁴, A. S. GAUTAM⁴

^{1*}Department of Physics, Shri Gulab Singh Govt. Degree College, Chakrata, Uttarakhand

² Department of Physics, Dhanauri P. G. College, Dhanauri, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India

³ Department of Physics, Municipal P. G. College, Mussoorie, 248179, Uttarakhand, India

⁴ Department of Physics, H N B University, Garhwal Srinagar (Garhwal), 246174

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has become a prominent issue for many nations in recent years. Air pollution, particularly concerning particulate matter, has escalated into a significant global public health challenge (Anderson et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2015; Stanaway et al., 2018). Pollutants in the atmosphere can originate from both natural and human activities and are typically found in the form of solid particles, gases, or liquid droplets (Gupta et al., 2003). These natural and anthropogenic aerosols are critical in influencing the climate and weather of specific regions (Deep et al., 2018). The severity of atmospheric pollution has increased markedly over the past two decades, leading many countries to confront its rapid rise (Pandey et al., 2015). This issue is particularly acute in developing countries and densely populated nations such as India, China, and the USA. A key factor contributing to this problem is the dramatic increase in energy and fuel demand in these regions. The growth of urban areas and industries has resulted in the depletion of forests and other natural resources, which further drives up energy consumption and emissions of pollutants like aerosols and black carbon (Tsang et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2015).

METHODS

The comprehensive dataset covers the period from 2011 to 2022 and was obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) in Dehradun, available at <http://ueppcb.uk.gov.in>. Alongside the air quality data, critical meteorological parameters—including temperature (Temp), relative humidity (RH), rainfall (RF), wind speed (WS), and wind direction (WD)—were acquired from publicly accessible resources at <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>.

Figure 1 Monthly variations of air pollutants and meteorological parameters in Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The highest concentrations of PM10 and PM2.5 were recorded at 157.93 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in May 2019 and 112.61 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in July 2022, respectively. Conversely, the lowest values were noted at 5.98 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 7.62 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in April 2020. To further explore the relationships among various air pollutants and meteorological parameters, correlation coefficients were calculated. A strong positive correlation was observed between SO₂ and NO₂, with a coefficient of $r = 0.85$, indicating a significant association between these two pollutants.

CONCLUSIONS

The results reveal that the highest levels of air pollutants were predominantly recorded in the urban centre of Dehradun. Over the past decade, Dehradun has seen a significant population increase, while Haridwar, recognized as a key commercial hub in Uttarakhand, demonstrated the most elevated pollution levels. During the study period, a negative correlation was found between rainfall and all measured air pollutants in Dehradun, with correlation coefficients of -0.166 for SO₂, -0.104 for NO₂, -0.207 for PM10, and -0.075 for PM2.5. Similarly, in Haridwar, rainfall exhibited negative correlations with PM10 (-0.295), SO₂ (-0.184), and NO₂ (-0.155). Notably, the data from 2020, which coincided with the COVID-19 lockdown, showed a significant decrease in pollutant concentrations across all selected sites, attributed to reduced vehicular activity. The substantial decline in pollution levels observed in April 2020 during the lockdown underscores the direct impact of transportation, industrial operations, and human activities on gaseous pollutants. These findings highlight the critical relationship between urbanization, weather patterns, and air quality management in the region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Dehradun branches of the Central Pollution Control Board and NASA web (<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>) for providing observation data used in this paper.

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DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE SIZE-RESOLVED SECONDARY ORGANIC CARBON AND WATER-SOLUBLE ORGANIC CARBON (WSOC) IN THE WESTERN GHAT REGION AND INDO-GIANTIC PLANE, INDIA

YASARAPU SATHISH¹, ABHISHEK CHAKRABORTY^{2*}

¹Indian Institute Technology Bombay, Environmental Science and Engineering Department, Powai, Mumbai – 400076, India.

KEYWORDS: Size-resolve PM, Secondary Aerosols, SOC, WSOC.

INTRODUCTION

Experimental and epidemiological research has mostly focused on source apportionment of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ (Bhandari et al., 2020; Jain et al., 2020). Moreover, not all particles pose the same health risks. Human health effects are directly correlated with particle size distribution, chemical composition, and exposure to particulate matter (PM) (like breathing and indoor or outdoor activities) (Brown et al., 2013). Particulate matter (PM) consists of carbonaceous aerosols (CA), which are an important component that leads to severe air pollution (Cao et al., 2005). CA (=EC+OM) consists of elemental carbon (EC) and organic carbon (OC). Anthropogenic emissions with finer particles are the primary source of EC (Chow et al., 2007; Pachauri et al., 2013). At the same time, OC can be formed through secondary formations and direct primary emissions into the atmosphere. WSOC accounts for 20 to 60 % of the total OC and can affect the formation of cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and hygroscopic properties, which contribute to indirect radiative forcing (Li et al., 2016; Tang et al., 2016; Xiang et al., 2017). In addition, CA contributes to haze conditions and poor visibility, and WSOC has strong solar absorption properties that majorly affect climate change (Chen et al., 2016, 2020). Hence, it is crucial to study the origin and formation of CA and WSOC to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of its various roles. However, there is still a research gap on the difference between the size-resolved CA and WSOC over the western coast of the peninsula of Mumbai and the IGP of Kanpur, India.

METHODS

Particulate matter (PM) was collected using the ACI with nine size ranges. A sample collection was done in two different parts of India; one was the Indo-Gigantic plane at Kanpur, and the other was the western Ghat region in Mumbai. In both regions, sampling was collected during the post-monsoon, winter, and summer seasons. The PM was collected on quartz filters (dia=81mm) before filters were placed in the muffle furnace at 700 °C for 5 hours to remove the organic impurities. Each sample was taken as pre-weight and weight with the help of a semi-micro balance (ACZET-CY-series). After that, organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) were analysed using the EC-OC Analyser (Sunset Laboratory Inc, USA). Also, the water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC) will be analysed with the help of total organic carbon (Shimadzu TOC-LCSH/CPH). We took the 3 cm² punch area and soaked the filter using milli-Q water 8.2 (MΩ) in the torsion tube. After that, samples were ultrasonicated for 45 minutes at 50 °C. Then, filters were extracted using the 0.225µm nylon filters; then, samples were analysed in the TOC analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The size-resolved mass concentrations and percentages are shown in Fig 1. In Kanpur, fine mode (PM_{2.1}) mass concentrations were higher in post-monsoon (mean=229.68µg/m³),

followed by winter and summer. The mass concentrations of 0.65-1.1 μm and 1.1-2.1 μm size ranges were higher in winter (45.6%), followed by post-monsoon (38.9%), and summer (27.1%), similarly observed in Mumbai. These results indicate that high PM pollution, low boundary layer height, and calm atmosphere conditions lead to higher pollution in winter compared to other seasons. In both regions, OC concentrations were found post-monsoon > winter > summer, but EC concentrations were observed in winter > post-monsoon > summer, respectively. In both locations, higher EC concentrations at 0.43 μm size range due to coal combustion and vehicular emissions were observed in Mumbai (mean=1.44 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Kanpur (mean=0.95 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), respectively.

Figure 1. Size-resolved particulate matter (PM) concentrations at Kanpur

In both locations, OC observed bimodal distributions, but higher concentrations were observed in fine mode, and lower concentrations were in coarser mode in Kanpur, while fine and coarse mode contribute approximately equal concentrations in Mumbai. This indicates that the IGP region mainly dominates the finer particles, which have a potential source of anthropogenic emissions such as coal/fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning, and vehicular emissions. Meanwhile, in the western Ghat region, approximately equal contributions from the fine and coarse modes indicate that the coarse mode is mostly dominated by natural sources such as sea spray, construction works and mineral dust.

CONCLUSIONS

In Kanpur, the highest fine mode (PM_{2.1}) concentrations occurred during the post-monsoon season, followed by winter and summer. Both locations showed higher EC concentrations in the 0.43 μm size-range, attributed to coal combustion and vehicular emissions. EC concentrations are higher in Mumbai due to higher traffic-related emissions than in Kanpur.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by a start-up research grant (SRG) of the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB; project no. SRG/2020/000129).

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL IN THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAN REGION OF INDIA

D.S. BISHT^{1*}, A.S. GAUTAM², R.S. NEGI³, V. SINGH¹, A.K. SRIVASTAVA¹

¹Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology Ministry of Earth Sciences, New Delhi

²Department of Physics, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar, Uttarakhand

³Department of Rural Technology, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar, Uttarakhand

*Correspondence to: dsbisht@tropmet.res.in

KEYWORDS: Aerosol, OC-EC, Source Apportionment, Himalayan Region

INTRODUCTION

Ambient aerosols consist of organics, mineral dust, metals as well as sea salts and inorganic pollutants. The relative abundance of these components is highly variable both temporally and spatially (Ram et al., 2010; Gawhane et al., 2017). Several researchers have reported the chemical properties of aerosols and source apportionment of aerosols over the Indian region; however, very limited studies have been reported over the Himalayan region (Kuniyal et al., 2014, Gautam et al., 2018). The assessment of ambient air quality of the Himalayan region of India is one of the major issues as it has been affected due to rapid urbanization and mass tourism activities. In this paper, we present the chemical composition and source apportionment of particulate matter <2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) and meteorological parameters collected at Srinagar of Uttarakhand, a central Himalayan region of India.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} (n=39) was collected at Srinagar (560m amsl) of Uttarakhand of the central Himalayan region of India during Jan-Dec 2017 in a year-long period. PM_{2.5} samples were collected (12 h basis) simultaneously on prebaked QM-A filters by Fine Particle Sampler. Analyses of OC, EC, WSIC of PM_{2.5} were carried out using an OC/EC carbon analyzer; Ion Chromatograph, respectively. The details of the chemical analysis of PM are discussed in Bisht et al. (2015). Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to identify the possible sources of PM_{2.5} over the central Himalayan region of India.

RESULTS

Figure 1. Seasonal variations of water-soluble ionic species in PM_{2.5} during the study period.

Figure 1 shows the Seasonal variations of water-soluble ionic species of PM_{2.5} in Srinagar's central Himalayan region. The analysed mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} accounted for 70% over the region, whereas, the unidentified mass PM_{2.5} accounted for 30%, which may be carbonate rich minerals, calcium sulphate and alumino-silicates, etc. PCA identified the three major components of PM_{2.5} corresponding to the different sources, and identified them as secondary aerosol, crustal / mineral / soil dust and biomass burning, based on the loading of the variables in the factor.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, source apportionments of PM_{2.5} were done using PCA over the central Himalayan region of India based on the chemical compositions of PM_{2.5} collected during a year-long period. PCA identified the three major sources such as secondary aerosol, crustal/mineral/soil dust and biomass burning of PM_{2.5} over the region.

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COMPARATIVE SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF FINE AEROSOL PARTICLES OF WATER-SOLUBLE AND CARBONACEOUS SPECIES: INSIGHTS INTO ANTHROPOGENIC POLLUTION SOURCES

K. DUBEY¹ AND S. VERMA¹

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur

INTRODUCTION

The constituents of fine particulate matter (PM, aerodynamic diameter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) are mainly water-soluble inorganic ions (WSII), organic and elemental carbon (OC, EC), metals; and PM itself exhibits large spatial (Dubey et al., 2023) and temporal variability in their concentration and show heterogeneity in composition. Investigating fine aerosols and interpretation of their chemical composition and sources on a regional scale is crucial for accurate quantification of their atmospheric and health effects. Most of the source apportionment studies in India are based on characterised WSII species and trace elements only, and without incorporating CA information (Dubey and Verma, 2024). There is a scarcity of information on fine aerosols with the simultaneous characterisation of both WSII and CA discretely sampled on separate substrates for better characterisation. Thus, in this study, we aim to outlook the chemical characteristics of fine aerosol ($\leq 1.6 \mu\text{m}$) in a semi-urban atmosphere (KGP) through simultaneous yet discrete aerosol sampling. We also evaluate the source of aerosol species of WSII and CA in the eastern IGP distinguishing the anthropogenic contributions in the semi-urban atmosphere relative to the megacity atmosphere.

METHODS

To investigate the chemical composition of WSII and CA in the fine fraction of aerosol samples, an indigenously designed-fabricated Submicron Aerosol Sampler (SAS) is mounted on the rooftop of the Civil Engineering Department (about 12 m above the ground level), Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur campus. The Quartz and PTFE filters were used for the collection of respectively, the CA and WSII species (separate substrates provide better characterisation). The sampled fine aerosol (PM $\leq 1.6 \mu\text{m}$) chemical concentration and the associated uncertainties in μm are provided as input to the PMF model Version 5.0. The model has been run for six factors (number of sources) decided on the basis of the minimum value of Q (goodness of fit parameters) and scaled residuals.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Chemical Composition of fine WSII and CA at Kharagpur

The monthly mean concentrations of fine WSII species in the semi-urban atmosphere (KGP) reveal a relative abundance of Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} as compared to NH_4^+ , K^+ , NO_3^- and F^- . Among the cations (anions), the relative fraction of Ca^{2+} (Cl^- : 10–17 %) in total WSII (TWSII: sum of analyzed WSII species) is the largest (48–57%) followed by Mg^{2+} (11–15%) and Na^+ (5–13%). An episodic rise in the monthly mean concentration of all WSII species is noticed during February, being twice larger than their annual mean for K^+ , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- to as large as thrice the annual mean for NH_4^+ . The episodic rise in WSII concentrations during winter and Wmon months (January and February) over the region is due to increased emissions from enhanced anthropogenic activity in wintertime temperatures, especially from residential biofuel combustion for cooking and heating, besides due to prevailing wintertime meteorological conditions

favourable to confinement of atmospheric pollutants. The episodic increase is also due to the transboundary transport of pollutants from the upper northern IGP towards the lower eastern IGP during winter and Wmon months corroborated by 7-day back trajectory analysis. A peak in SO_4^{2-} monthly mean concentration is spotted during Wmon months, September, and April, mainly due to an increase in non-seasalt (nss)- SO_4^{2-} except during February. The monthly mean concentration of K^+ is seen to exhibit a pronounced peak during November and May, while remaining typically large during Wmon months. The peaks in nss- K^+ (a biomass burning marker), during November and May are in corroboration with the prevalence of biomass burning occurrences of crop waste burning and forest biomass. The monthly mean concentration of OC (EC) exceeded the annual mean by 7% to 33% during winter and Wmon months and the summer month (May), with the highest monthly mean during December.

PMF Source profiles for Kharagpur and Kolkata

Utilising available information on chemical species profiles and insights from the emission inventory of aerosol species, six factors are identified based on the marker elements present in each source profile for both semi-urban and megacity atmospheres (Figure 1). While sources of fine aerosol species at KGP are identified to be regional dust (clean, 23%) followed by brick kilns (20%), residential biofuel combustion (17%), marine aerosols (15%), open biomass burning/agricultural farmlands (13%) and secondary inorganic aerosols (12%); these at KOL are from regional dust (polluted, 26%), followed by coal combustion (industry, 17%), solid-waste open-dumping (17%), marine aerosols (16%), vehicular emissions (12%) and open biomass burning (12%). The predominating anthropogenic sources contributing to fine aerosol burden are largely different in the semi-urban and megacity atmospheres. The contribution from open biomass burning is found at both locations but with an associated influence from agricultural farmlands (e.g., fertilizer and livestock-related pollutants) at KGP. The regional dust with aerosol components (crustal elements) primarily from non-combustion sources (marked as clean) at KGP, but that combined with significant contribution from combustion sources (primarily in the transportation sector; marked as polluted) at KOL constitutes the largest fractional contribution among the six identified factors to fine aerosols at both KGP and KOL.

Figure 1. (a-b) Source species profile identified at KGP and KOL from PMF. The numbers shown in the doughnut chart are the relative distribution (%) of each WSII and CA species in a factor (e.g., 41% of total Ca^{2+} is explained by the regional dust factor in KGP).

CONCLUSIONS

The characterization of fine aerosol particles collected with the SAS revealed the relative abundance of WSII and CA particles in the eastern IGP semi-urban atmosphere (KGP), impacting air quality and contributing to aerosol optical depth. Comparing WSII and CA between KGP and the megacity atmosphere (KOL) highlighted inter-seasonal changes in chemical species distribution. These changes were influenced by marine and crustal elements at both locations but stemmed from different anthropogenic emission sources. The study recommends targeted emission reduction from identified combustion sources to mitigate adverse climate and health impacts in the eastern IGP megacity and semi-urban atmospheres.

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MERCURY EMISSIONS FROM INDIAN INDUSTRIES AND UNREGULATED SECTORS: A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT

A. MISHRA¹, S. K. SAHU¹ AND P. MANGARAJ²

¹Dept. of Environmental Science, Berhampur University, India

²Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN), Kyoto, Japan

KEYWORDS: Mercury Emission Inventory, Fossil Fuel, Solid Waste, Crop Residue Burning.

INTRODUCTION

Mercury (Hg) is regarded as a hazardous, noxious, relentless, and movable pollutant. It can exist in vapour form or particulates and can circulate in widely dispersed form for years over the surface of the earth. Due to approximately two years of retention time, in the atmosphere, long range of transport, high toxicity, and carcinogenicity, Hg emission regulation has been the focus of various regulatory boards (Schroeder et al., 1998). Its emissions pose serious health and environmental risks, leading to global concerns and regulatory measures. Mercury exists in metallic, inorganic, and organic forms, all of which are hazardous to ecosystems and human health, causing disorders such as Acrodynia, Hunter-Russell syndrome, and Minamata disease. Mercury is released into the environment through various industrial activities, including coal combustion, cement production, metal smelting, and waste incineration. In India, mercury emissions from coal burning alone reached 89.4 tons in 2013. The country is the second-largest global emitter, releasing around 144.7 tons annually (Sharma et al., 2019). Efforts to create emission inventories and identify mercury hotspots in India, particularly due to industrial activities, are crucial. Such inventories can guide policy actions to mitigate the harmful effects of mercury on public health and the environment.

METHODS

The most commonly used emission factor-based traditional approach adopted by Sahu et al., (2023), Mishra et al., (2023), Mangaraj et al., (2022) and Klimont et al., (2002) which is similar to IPCC defined by Tier -II bottom-up methodology. This is the multiplication of activity data and emission factors used for every industry. The emission is estimated based on the individual plant activity presented across India, from which the district-level emission is calculated and then the values are added according to the states to assess the state-level mercury burden in the country.

The total emission is expressed as $E = \sum (A_i \times N_i) \times EF_i$.

where E is the total Hg emission; 'A' is the activity data i.e., yearly coal consumption, and production capacity of every sector; N is the total number of industrial plants taken in each sector and 'EF', is the emission factors. The industry-specific technological EF is in g/t (gram/Tonne) for various types of sources considered, 'i' is the individual industry or sector for which specific activity data, emission factors and emission removal are adopted.

Table 1: Emission Factor considered for Hg emission (g/t)

Sectors	Present work	Previous studies	References
Coal burning in TPP	0.3	0.5	Pacyna and Pacyna., 2001
		0.1-0.3	Pacyna et al., 2010
		0.1–0.5	Pirrone., 2010
		0.3	Mukherjee et al., 2015
		0.003-0.34	UNEP, 2014(India)
Cu Smelting	8.97	5.0-6.0 (5.5)	Pirrone., 2010
		5.8-15 (10.41)	Kumari R., 2011
		5.0	Pacyna et al., 2010
		15.0	Mukherjee et al., 2015
Pb Smelting	19.81	3.0	Pirrone., 2010
		15.7-43.6(29.65)	Kumari R., 2011
		3.0	Pacyna et al., 2010
		43.6	Mukherjee et al., 2015
Zn Smelting	9.8	7.5-8(7.75)	Pirrone., 2010
		8-25(16.5)	Kumari R., 2011
		7.0	Pacyna et al., 2010
		8.0	Mukherjee et al., 2015
Iron and Steel Production	0.03	0.04	Pacyna and Pacyna., 2001
		0.001	EMEP/EEA, 2019
		0.04	Pirrone., 2010
Cement Production	0.07	0.042	Mukherjee et al., 2015
		0.06	EMEP/EEA, 2019
		0.1	Pacyna and Pacyna., 2001
		0.065-0.1 (0.08)	Pirrone., 2010
Municipal Waste Incineration	1.0	1.0	Pirrone., 2010
		1.0	Pacyna et al., 2010
		1.0	Mukherjee et al., 2015

Medical Waste Incineration	28.5	20 37	Mukherjee et al., 2015 EPA, 1997
Aluminium Production	5.9	5.9	Amano and Asiedu., 2020
Oil Refinery	0.005	0.005	EMEP/EEA, 2019
Mercury in Indian Fly Ash	0.14	0.14	Pirrone., 2010
Rice Residue Burning	5.56 *	5.56 *	Zhou et. al., 2017
Wheat Residue Burning	11.09 *	11.09 *	Zhou et. al., 2017
Sugarcane Residue Burning	6.5 *	6.5 *	Zhou et. al., 2017
Cotton Residue Burning	3.12 *	3.12 *	Zhou et. al., 2017

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The present study quantifies the annual mercury emission from various industrial and fugitive sources from the Indian subcontinent, which shows approx. 459.4 t/yr of Hg in 2019-20. According to our estimation, Odisha (~57.5 t/yr) and Madhya Pradesh (~53.3 t/yr) are the maximum emitting states sharing 12% and 11% of the total emission respectively, followed by Chhattisgarh (50.5 t/yr), and Gujarat (47.9 t/yr) which is shown in Figure 1 (a).

Figure 1: (a) State-wise Hg emission (t/yr) (b) Unit-wise industrial Hg emission in India in 2019 (t/yr). (c) Sector-wise Hg emission share in percentage.

In line with the Minamata Convention, this study estimates unit-specific mercury emissions for 2019, identifying Central-Eastern India as a hotspot as depicted in Figure 1 (b). Hindustan Copper Limited in Madhya Pradesh emits the most (22.8 t/yr), followed by Vedanta alumina refineries in Odisha. The top 100 industries account for 50% of India's Hg emissions. The sector-wise Hg emission in Figure 1 (c) shows that Coal combustion in Power plants is the largest mercury emitter in India, releasing ~252 t/yr followed by Non-ferrous metal

production (48.8 t/yr), aluminium refineries (39.4 t/yr), Cement production (33.9 t/yr), municipal waste (7.3 t/yr), and biomedical waste (6.8 t/yr). The sectoral uncertainty of the MSW incinerator is found to be the lowest, $\pm 24\%$. However, greater variation in the emission factors of non-ferrous metal production led to a higher uncertainty of $\pm 83\%$. The current developed emission inventory has an average uncertainty of $\pm 48\%$ due to large variations in reported EFs by various researchers followed by fuel activity data.

CONCLUSIONS

Industrial processes discharge large amounts of hazardous trace elements leading to adverse effects on human health. This study is the first of its kind to estimate the district level Hg emission load across the country from various industrial processes. According to the new estimation, the total emitted Hg is found to be 459.4 t/yr in India for 2019. This study also estimated that about 233 million people living in the 10 km periphery of major industrial zones and as many as ~ 17 million people residing near the ten major hotspots are likely to be susceptible to Hg emissions. The developed dataset can be utilised by policymakers for framing appropriate mitigation strategies using cleaner energy, proper establishment of emission control techniques in industrial processing units, appropriate waste management, and implementation of green incineration techniques could be the greatest substitute to prepare against the unseen health disaster.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This full research work did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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ANALYSIS OF EDDY COVARIANCE MEASUREMENTS OF TURBULENT, WATER, AND CARBON FLUXES, AND STABILITY VARIABLES IN THE COMPLEX TERRAIN OF THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAS

MAYANK KUMAR CHAUHAN^{1,2}, NARENDRA SINGH¹, JAYDEEP SINGH³,
YOGESH KUMAR TIWARI⁴, DIPANKAR SHARMA⁴, AMEY DATYE⁴

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences, Nainital, Uttarakhand

²Gurukula Kangri (Deemed to be University), Haridwar, Uttarakhand

³Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main, Germany

⁴Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, Maharashtra

KEYWORDS: Eddy Covariance, Turbulent Fluxes, Carbon Fluxes, Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory

INTRODUCTION

Mountainous regions like the Central Himalayas regulate regional and global climate by influencing turbulence, momentum, water, and carbon fluxes between the surface and atmosphere. These fluxes are shaped by interactions between topography, vegetation, and atmospheric conditions, critical for understanding eco-hydrological processes. However, measuring and characterizing these fluxes in rugged, heterogeneous terrains pose unique challenges due to the irregular airflow, steep slopes, and variable land cover. Traditional methods often fall short of capturing the dynamic nature of fluxes in these environments, necessitating advanced techniques like the eddy covariance method. Eddy covariance (EC) systems have become indispensable tools for directly measuring turbulent fluxes of momentum, heat, water vapor, and carbon dioxide in complex terrains. This study analyzes EC observations during winter to examine flux variations and the role of terrain-induced factors like wind patterns. Additionally, in this work we have parameterized the Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory for turbulent heat fluxes by using friction velocity (u^*) and turbulent temperature scale (Θ^*).

METHODS

The experimental site is located on the campus of the Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES) at Manora Peak, Nainital (29.35°N, 79.45°E), at an altitude of 1922 meters above mean sea level. This high-altitude station is situated in the southern part of the central Himalayas and is characterized by a series of ridges and valleys (Solanki et al., 2019). The study used a Windmaster Pro sonic anemometer and a Licor LI-7200 CO₂/H₂O Analyzer, mounted on a 27-meter tower with instruments at 12 meters. Data (in .ghg format) from the sonic anemometers, measuring wind components and temperature at 10 Hz, were processed using EddyPro software. Due to the sloping, complex terrain, the data were corrected for sensor tilt by transforming them into a streamline-following coordinate system. Literature shows that the planar-fit technique offers significant advantages for sonic anemometer tilt correction compared to the double- and triple-rotation methods (Wilczak et al., 2001).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 and Figure 2 depict eddy covariance measurements during the winter months revealing significant variability in the daily and diurnal variations of turbulent fluxes and

atmospheric parameters, including H₂O and CO₂ fluxes, latent heat (LE), sensible heat (H), and variables such as friction velocity (u*), turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), and the Monin-Obukhov length (L). The H₂O flux shows a pronounced daily variation, with peak values occurring during the day when solar radiation is maximal, indicating an increase in evaporation and transpiration processes. In contrast, CO₂ flux decreases notably during the daytime, linked to photosynthetic uptake by vegetation. These patterns underscore the coupled nature of water and carbon exchanges, driven by plant activity and solar heating as shown in Figure 2. The corresponding mixing ratios of H₂O and CO₂ further highlights these relationships. Vegetation plays a pivotal role in modulating carbon uptake and water loss, by the alignment between the peak H₂O flux and maximum CO₂ assimilation during the day. Atmospheric stability, as indicated by the Monin-Obukhov length, plays a pivotal role in determining the turbulent exchange processes. Under stable atmospheric conditions ($50 \leq L \leq 500$) (Rocadenbosch et al., 2022), turbulence is suppressed, leading to lower fluxes, while unstable conditions ($-200 \leq L \leq -100$) promote higher turbulence and consequently greater fluxes. Furthermore, terrain-induced factors, such as wind patterns and topographic variations, significantly influence the temporal distribution of these fluxes. The H₂O flux peaks around midday (~12:00) at approximately 2 mmol/m²/s, driven by evapotranspiration. CO₂ flux shows an opposite trend, decreasing to around -5 μmol/m²/s, reflecting daytime photosynthetic activity. At night, both fluxes approach zero, consistent with minimal vegetative activity. The H₂O mixing ratio increases throughout the day, reaching a peak of about 15 mmol/mol by the afternoon, driven by evapotranspiration. In contrast, the CO₂ mixing ratio remains relatively steady at around 420 μmol/mol, reflecting the consistent exchange of CO₂ between the atmosphere and the vegetation.

Figure 1. Daily cycle of water, carbon, turbulent Figure 2. Diurnal cycle of water, carbon,

The w'/H_2O' covariance shows a peak of about 0.05 mmol/m²/s at midday. Similarly, w'/CO_2' covariance fluctuates but generally remains negative during the daytime, indicating downward fluxes of CO₂. Latent and sensible heat fluxes exhibit similar diurnal trends, with LE peaking at ~100 W/m² and H reaching ~200 W/m² in the midday hours. The evapotranspiration rate follows a daily cycle with a peak around noon, reaching values close to 0.1 mmol/s. TKE follows the solar cycle, peaking at around 1.5 m²/s², with higher turbulence during the daytime due to increased thermal activity. Friction velocity (u)* shows a gradual increase throughout the day, peaking at about 0.5 m/s. The TKE and u* further illustrate the increased turbulence during the daytime, which is essential for understanding the vertical transport of heat, moisture, and CO₂.

CONCLUSIONS

Water vapor fluxes exhibit a pronounced midday peak due to increased solar radiation driving

evapotranspiration, while CO₂ fluxes decline during the day as vegetation uptake dominates through photosynthesis. The correlation between vertical wind velocity and water vapor flux (w'/H_2O') peaked at approximately 0.05 mmol/m²/s around midday, indicating a strong coupling between turbulence and evapotranspiration. In contrast, the w'/CO_2' covariance generally remained negative during the day, suggesting downward fluxes of CO₂. Atmospheric stability, indicated by the Monin-Obukhov length, was pivotal in governing turbulent exchange processes. Stable conditions ($50 \leq L \leq 500$) suppressed turbulence and led to lower fluxes during the night, while unstable conditions ($-200 \leq L \leq -100$) during the daytime promoted increased turbulence and higher fluxes, crucial for understanding surface-atmosphere interaction.

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ESTIMATION OF AEROSOL SPECIES-WISE IMPACT OVER HINDU KUSH HIMALAYAN REGION: VALIDATION, SOURCES, CUMULATIVE AND RELATIVE IMPACT ON GLACIER RUNOFF

S. SANTRA¹ AND S. VERMA¹

¹Indian Institute of Technology, Department of Civil Engineering, Kharagpur – 721302, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol modeling, Aerosols over Himalaya, Aerosol impact on Himalayan Glaciers

INTRODUCTION

The snowmelt from glaciers situated in the Hindu-Kush Himalayan (HKH) region forms the primary source for many of India's major rivers. In recent times, these glaciers have been shrinking rapidly, putting densely populated areas in northern India at risk of water scarcity. Besides experiencing warming levels above the global average (Qiu, 2008), the HKH region is also subjected to substantial particulate pollution. When these aerosols settle on the untouched snow surfaces of HKH glaciers, they change the albedo of the snow's upper mixing layer, causing increased absorption of solar energy and faster snowmelt (Santra et al., 2019). However, remote locations and adverse weather conditions pose challenges to carrying out measurement studies. Additionally, a comprehensive assessment of the total and individual impacts of all aerosol species in the area is yet to be done. This study utilizes a hybrid model that combines adequate aerosol species estimations for the region with a snow, ice, aerosol radiation model and a novel hypsometric glacier energy mass balance model. This approach enables a quantitative and comparative analysis of the overall and specific impacts of various aerosol species, including black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), sulfate and other water-soluble (Sul-ows), and dust aerosols.

METHODS

The present investigation utilizes aerosol parameters derived from free-running aerosol simulations (freesimu) conducted in an atmospheric general circulation model (GCM) over the HKH region. The investigation assesses the aerosol optical depth (AOD) and single scattering albedo (SSA) as estimated by freesimu, utilizing observational data gathered from stations across the HKH region with the objective of identifying the most reliable freesimu. Furthermore, the concentrations of simulated aerosol species (i.e., OC, Sul-ows, and dust) are systematically compared with available observations to evaluate the efficacy of the most consistent freesimu. A comparative analysis is carried out between the pre-monsoon season (March to May) and the winter season (December to February) across two distinct types of stations: low-altitude (LA) and high-altitude (HA). The eight LA stations are classified based on their altitude and their proximity to heavily polluted regions. In contrast, the six HA stations are located in remote areas, predominantly affected by aerosol transport. A constrained aerosol simulation (constrsimu) has been developed, which integrates simulated aerosol characteristics from the most efficacious freesimu with available measurement data to account for the impact of elevated emission flux from heavily polluted areas near LA stations. The influence of aerosol concentration in the snow on snow albedo reduction (SAR) is assessed, while its effect on increasing annual glacier snowmelt runoff is simulated using a novel hypsometric glacier energy mass balance model. Nine glaciers that exhibit the highest susceptibility to aerosol species were identified according to their geographical proximity to areas with elevated concentrations of aerosol species in snow. The subsequent analysis evaluates both the cumulative and individual impacts of these aerosols on the identified

glaciers. Additionally, the study identifies the geographical source regions and emission sectors that contribute to the species-specific aerosol loading in the region.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Among the freesimu, GCM-indemiss exhibits better conformity with measured AOD550 and SSA550 over stations with an acceptable normalized mean bias (NMB). For atmospheric concentration of aerosol species, GCM-indemiss simulated values compare considerably well with the measurements of OC and Sul-OWS aerosols over the HA stations. However, over the LA stations, simulations using constrsimu approaches perform relatively better. A hot-spot location of higher OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust concentration is identified near Manora peak. Seasonal analysis of aerosol species concentrations over the region reveals winter-time values to be lower than pre-monsoon ones. Although OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust concentrations in snow are found to be 2 to 5 times higher than BC, SAR due to these species are estimated to be much lower than due to BC. Cumulative SAR due to all aerosols is estimated to be as high as 7% to 8% over Gangotri and Chorabari glaciers. Simulation of annual runoff increase (ARI) due to aerosol-induced SAR indicates HKH glaciers to be 2 to 3 times more sensitive to SAR than Tibetan glaciers. Five out of nine glaciers are estimated to have ARI of more than 300 mm w.e. y⁻¹ due to total aerosol-induced SAR (Pindari, Sankalpa, Gangotri, and Chorabari being the most affected ones). Pindari glacier, being more sensitive to SAR, was found to have the highest ARI despite having a lower SAR. BC aerosols, despite having less than 15% contribution to total aerosol loading over the region, contribute more than 50% to the total ARI over all the glaciers (Figure: 1). OC aerosols in the HKH region south of 30°N mainly come from biofuel and open burning in the nearby Indo-Gangetic plain (IGP) region, while north of 30°N, they originate from far-off regions. Sul-ows aerosols follow a similar pattern but are primarily from fossil fuel burning. Dust aerosols are mostly (>80%) from long-range intercontinental transport from distant regions of Africa and West Asia.

Figure 1. Percentage contribution of BC, OC, Sul-ows, and dust aerosols towards the total ARI due to aerosols along with observed average yearly recession (m y⁻¹)

CONCLUSIONS

Significant aerosol concentrations were identified near Manora Peak in the HKH region. Although other aerosol species had concentrations 2 to 5 times higher than BC, BC caused a more substantial SAR over the HKH glaciers. The cumulative SAR, due to all aerosol types, reached up to 7 to 8% over the Gangotri and Chorabari glaciers. The Gangotri glacier, crucial for the formation of the Ganges River, showed notable sensitivity. Among the glaciers studied, the Pindari glacier exhibited the highest ARI despite a lower aerosol-induced SAR compared to the Gangotri and Chorabari glaciers. Five out of the nine glaciers (i.e., Pindari, Sankalpa, Milam, Gangotri, and Chorabari) showed an ARI exceeding 300 mm w.e. y^{-1} due to aerosol-induced SAR. HKH glaciers were found to be 2-3 times more sensitive to SAR than Tibetan glaciers. This heightened sensitivity, combined with rising temperatures from global warming, is concerning. BC aerosols, despite being less than 15% of total aerosol loading, accounted for 55-70% of ARI, followed by dust (20-30%), Sul-ows, and OC aerosols. South of 30°N, OC and Sul-ows aerosols mainly came from emissions from the IGP, while dust aerosols were primarily from long-range transport.

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STUDY OF AEROSOL DEPOSITION CHARACTERISTICS IN A MECHANICALLY VENTILATED CHAMBER

SANJAY SINGH, MOHUA PAL, S. ANAND, ARSHAD KHAN AND SURESH KUMAR M. K.

¹ Health Physics Division, ² Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Deposition, Ventilation Rate, Aerosol Removal

INTRODUCTION

In nuclear facilities involved in the generation of nuclear energy, a high-quality energy source contributing to carbon neutrality, radioactive gases and aerosols are generated from various activities. Mechanical ventilation is an important engineering safety feature provided in each facility to remove airborne radioactivity. This helps minimize area contamination due to surface deposition, external exposure due to immersion, and personal internal contamination due to inhalation. Ventilation systems are designed based on the number of Air Changes Per Hour (ACPH) required in various workplace zones. Though this philosophy of ventilation design is suitable for workplaces with gaseous contaminants, it may not be an ideal choice when contaminants are particulate in nature, dispersed in air, and conventionally referred to as aerosols. Here, aerosol removal by ventilation is governed by complex processes such as flow field-induced turbulent diffusion, sedimentation, coagulation, and advective transport. Therefore, ventilation design based solely on ACPH may not be adequate. An optimization is needed between bulk removal through ventilation and deposition. Several studies in the literature have explored aerosol size-dependent deposition rates. Among the key findings are those from Corner and Pendlebury (1951), Crump and Seinfeld (1981), and Lai and Nazaroff (1999). It is felt that although these models account for various processes of flow and particle transport, they have not been rigorously tested for robustness through experimental observation. This study examines the particle size and flow-dependent deposition characteristics for aerosols ranging in size from 0.2 to 2 μm .

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Figure 1 represents a schematic diagram of the aerosol chamber used in this study, with dimensions of 2 m x 1.5 m x 1.5 m. The chamber had an air inlet at the top, fitted with a HEPA filter, and an outlet at the bottom connected to a blower equipped with a Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) for finer control of the ventilation rate. The ventilation rate was measured using a thermal mass flow meter. For aerosol sampling, the chamber was equipped with three ports located centrally at distances of 0.5 m, 1.0 m, and 1.5 m from the aerosol injection port inside the chamber. DOP (di-octyl

phthalate) aerosols were generated and injected into the chamber. The number concentration of aerosols was measured using an Optical Particle Counter (OPC)-based aerosol spectrometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before the start of the experiments, the exhaust blower was operated at the desired flow rate, and the background particle concentration was brought to zero. Aerosols were then injected continuously while keeping the exhaust blower on. Once the particle concentration inside the chamber reached a steady state, the aerosol injection was stopped, with the ventilation remaining on. It was observed that the aerosol concentration began to decay exponentially over time. Typical data of aerosol decay concentration for particles sized 0.275 to 0.449 μm is shown in Figure 2. Similar data were generated for particle sizes up to 1.6 μm . The data were fitted to a first-order exponential decay, and the decay constant (effective removal rate, $\lambda = \lambda_v + \lambda_d$), which is the sum of the removal rate due to ventilation (λ_v) and the removal rate due to deposition (λ_d), was estimated.

Figure 10: Aerosol decay at a ventilation rate of 20 CMH

The value of λ obtained for aerosol particles sized 0.44 to 1.6 μm showed that the effective removal rate was highest (5.7 h^{-1}) for particles of size 0.449 μm . Afterward, it decreased to a minimum value at 0.5 μm , and then remained constant for the particle size range of 0.5 to 1.6 μm . This experiment was repeated at various ventilation rates, with a constant aerosol injection rate, and the effective removal rate was estimated. From the effective removal rate, the particle removal rate due to deposition was estimated and presented in Figure 3. It was observed that the deposition rate increased with the ventilation rate.

For smaller particles (0.44 μm), it increased from 1 h^{-1} to 5 h^{-1} as the ventilation rate increased from 20 CMH to 80 CMH, respectively. The deposition rate for particles between 0.5 to 1.6 μm remained constant up to a ventilation rate of 50 CMH, after which it increased to 1.5 h^{-1} at a ventilation rate of 80 CMH. The observed variation in the deposition rate was compared with the well-known V-shaped deposition rate curve proposed by Lai and Nazaroff (1999), and disagreement was found for smaller particle sizes.

Figure 11: Size dependent deposition rate at different ventilation rates.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, optimizing ventilation rates in nuclear facilities is crucial to minimize aerosol deposition, particularly for particles in the 0.5 to 1.6 µm range. The study demonstrates that aerosol removal rates vary with particle size, with the highest rate observed for 0.5 µm particles. Higher ventilation rates enhance deposition, especially for smaller particles, but this effect levels off at larger sizes. Additionally, the V-shaped deposition model requires further verification for smaller particles under varying conditions. Future work should focus on refining these models and conducting experiments with different aerosol types and environmental settings to improve their applicability.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author expresses their gratitude to Shri S Wadhwa Dy. Plant Superintendent, WIP and Smt Jyoti Diwan, Superintendent EE&I, WIP for their support related to mechanical; electrical & instrumentation for conducting the experiments.

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REAL-TIME ON-ROAD MOBILE MONITORING OF BLACK CARBON ALONG HIMALAYAN VALLEYS IN UTTARAKHAND: A PILOT STUDY

ABHISHEK THAKUR^{1,2} AND CHHAVI PANT PANDEY^{1,2}

¹ Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology, Dehradun, India

² Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Himalayas, Mobile Monitoring, Air Quality

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) is a carbonaceous material formed during the combustion of carbon-based fuels and it uniquely affects Earth's climate by absorbing solar radiation, affecting cloud formation, and speeding up the melting of snow and ice (Bond et al., 2013). Additionally, it constitutes serious risks to respiratory and cardiovascular health, particularly for susceptible groups (Mendoza, Hill, Blair, & Crosman, 2024). In this study, we evaluated and measured the levels of BC along the routes that lead to the famed Char Dham yatra, which includes the pilgrimages to Gangotri, Yamunotri, Kedarnath, and Badrinath, in the state of Uttarakhand, which is located in the Himalayas of India. In recent years, the Char Dham Yatra road project has expanded highways in these areas, causing a substantial rise in vehicular traffic and thus increasing BC emissions annually due to the growing influx of pilgrims.

METHODS

In this work, the microAeth MA350 (Aethlabs, San Francisco, USA), a 965 g portable, low-power device, was used to measure BC concentration (Nazneen, Patra, Kolluru, Dubey, & Kumar, 2023). A flow rate of 100 ml/min and a time base of one minute were used for the sampling. The microAeth MA350 measures the attenuation (ATN) of BC particles deposited onto the filter medium at various optical wavelengths, which range from the infrared (IR) to the ultraviolet (UV) i.e., 880, 625, 528, 470, and 375 nm, respectively. To calculate "equivalent black carbon" (eBC), a specific measure for quantifying BC, the 880 nm wavelength (IR channel) is crucial. It is particularly useful for air quality and climate studies when assessing the absorption properties of black carbon.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Our journey spanned five days, starting from Gangnani (near Uttarkashi) to Gangotri, then to Sonprayag, and further to Dehradun. The average IR BCc concentrations for every route ranged from $7.84 \pm 10.36 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $14.63 \pm 15.73 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with an overall average of $10.1 \pm 13.33 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Table 1. Showing the average IR BCc for every route on different days

Date	Time	Location	Average IR BCc
26/09/2024	15:31:59 to 17:21:59	Gangnani to Gangotri	$10.14 \pm 16.05 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
30/09/2024	15:06:01 to 19:24:01	Gangotri to Lamgaon	$8.13 \pm 13.02 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
01/10/2024	8:53:00 to 12:59:00	Near Ghansali to Sonprayag	$7.84 \pm 10.36 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
03/10/2024	16:23:00 to 19:31:00	Sonprayag to Srinagar	$9.01 \pm 9.91 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
04/10/2024	7:05:00 to 11:40:00	Srinagar to Dehradun	$14.63 \pm 15.73 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

Figure 1. Scatter plot of IR BCc values during 5 days (26/09/2024, 30/09/2024, 01/10,2024, 03/10/2024 and 04/10/2024)

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates how vehicle traffic affects the quality of the air in this sensitive environmental region, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and mitigation measures to protect the environment and human health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology for necessary funding for field work and other infrastructure for this work. Abhishek Thakur also thanks the University Grants Commission, Govt. of India, for the research fellowship grant.

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A COMPREHENSIVE MOBILE MONITORING STUDY OF BLACK CARBON AEROSOL IN DOON VALLEY

CHHAVI PANT PANDEY^{1,2}, AMAN SHRIVAS¹ AND ABHISHEK THAKUR^{1, 2}

¹ Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology, 33, GMS Rd, Vijay Park, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

² Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, CSIR-HRDC Campus, Postal Staff College Area, Sector 19, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh 201002

KEYWORDS: Mobile Monitoring, Doon Valley, Black Carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Dehradun, located in the Doon Valley between the Himalayas and the Shivalik hills, presents a unique study area due to its geography, ecology, traffic, and air quality challenges. The city's proximity to protected forests like Rajaji National Park supports rich biodiversity, but rapid urbanization has led to increased deforestation. Rising vehicular traffic, fuelled by population growth and tourism, contributes to worsening air quality, with pollutants like particulate matter and black carbon (BC) becoming significant issues, especially in winter due to temperature inversions as suggested by (Dhankar et. al., 2023; Jain and Acharya 2022).

Mobile monitoring is considered the common method for understanding traffic, local biomass burning and health related air pollution (Upadhya et. al., 2024; Apte and Manchanda 2024). However, these measurements only represent the micro-level concentration of the area. To understand the full extent of the air pollutants a rigorous and extensive mobile monitoring campaign was designed that mapped the 4 different busy routes of the Dehradun city in the year 2022 and 2023.

METHODS

An extensive mobile monitoring campaign using an aethalometer MA350 is done throughout Doon Valley. The selection of routes was based on vehicular traffic, construction work, industries and stubble burning. This device uses a mass-specific absorption cross-section of 12.47 m²g⁻¹ at 880 nm to measure the concentration of optically absorbing aerosol particles (equivalent to black carbon, in µgm⁻³) as recommended by (Petzold et. al., 2013). It does this by monitoring the rate of change in light attenuation of a particle spot on a filter that air is pumped through. Every measurement day began with a fresh filter tape with 100 mLmin⁻¹ as the inlet flow rate, and thirty seconds as the temporal resolution for the measurements.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Mobile monitoring of BC particles as described in this study varies accordingly. R1 (15 km) indicates 19.351 ± 15.283 µgm⁻³. This route goes through a railway station and market that has high traffic with narrow roads and is highly crowded. R2 (31 km) is the longest and most travelled route of the study; R2 travels through the city centre, market, tourist destination, many colleges and also adds an elevation of ~500 m. The average BC value in R2 is depicted to be 19.368 ± 14.219 µgm⁻³. However, R3 (20 km) with an average of 27. 223 ± 17.898 µgm⁻³ is not travelled as much as it should have been, it travels through bus stands, densely populated areas with heavy traffic going through inner parts of the city. R4 (26 km) is the route that has industries in its vicinity and many colleges and universities with some greeneries depicting the average BC value of 18.094 ± 15.511 µgm⁻³.

Routes	Route area	Trips	Avg. BC Values ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and std. dev.
R1	Via railway station and hathibarkala	14	19.351 ± 15.283
R2	Via clock tower, Rajpur Police chowki, Guchhu pani and Garhi cantt.	23	19.368 ± 14.219
R3	Via Balliwala, ISBT, Rispana, Buddha chowk and clock tower.	03	27.223 ± 17.898
R4	Via FRI, IMA, Premnagar, Jhajhar and UCOST	09	18.094 ± 15.511

Table 1. Average BC values for all 4 routes.

Figure 1. Box-whisker plot for all 4 routes.

CONCLUSION

This is a preliminary study trying to understand the influence of BC particles in Doon valley using mobile monitoring techniques. In conclusion, the mobile monitoring campaign in Dehradun revealed significant variations in BC concentrations across different routes, with higher levels observed in areas with heavy traffic, dense populations, and industrial activities. These findings underscore the impact of urbanization, vehicular emissions, and localized sources of pollution on the city's air quality, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to reduce BC levels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the help of UCOST for funding this research work and the director of WIHG for providing the necessary logistical support.

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CURRENT GLOBAL TREND OF PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE AND ITS FUTURE CONSEQUENCES

N. RASTOGI¹ AND A. NAG²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Physics, School of Sciences, IFTM University, Moradabad

²Associate Professor, Department of Physics, School of Sciences, IFTM University, Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh – 244 102, India.

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5} Exposure, Air Pollution, Air Quality.

INTRODUCTION

Air quality is generally measured by a small subset of particulate matters (PMs), some of these have diameters $\leq 2.5\mu\text{m}$ (PM_{2.5}), available in the atmosphere [1]. Causing an estimated 11% of deaths worldwide, air pollution is the greatest environmental threat to human civilization. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), air pollution is responsible for an estimated 7 million premature deaths worldwide every year [2]. The worldwide study of population weighted average PM_{2.5} concentration reveals that central and south Asia is the mostly affected region as major cities in the countries like Bangladesh, India and Pakistan maintain a PM_{2.5} concentrations of over $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ i.e., exceeding 10 times the target air quality level prescribed by WHO, consistently for the last five years (2019-2023).

METHODS

This study for PM_{2.5} data relies on ground-level air quality monitoring stations, 39% of which are under government operation, while the remaining are managed by non-profit organizations/individuals employing low-cost sensors. All these data from low-cost air quality sensors gauge airborne PM_{2.5} levels through laser scattering technology. The global weighted average is obtained as:

$$\text{Population weighted average PM}_{2.5} \text{ concentration} = \frac{\sum \text{city mean PM}_{2.5} (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) \times \text{city population}}{\text{Total regional population covered by available city data}}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

According to the 2023 world air quality report, 91% of globally reporting cities have failed to achieve the WHO annual PM_{2.5} guidelines (Figure 1). This is a big alert for the whole human civilization.

Figure 1. Percentage of worldwide cities which have failed to achieve WHO annual PM_{2.5} guideline

The current study aims to quantify PM_{2.5} exposures across different cities worldwide (Figure 2) and suggestive measures on the effects of future air pollution control pathways.

Figure 2. PM_{2.5} exposure (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) across regional cities having potential threats worldwide

The future objectives would be the investigation of the contributions of different emission sources to ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations and the related disease burden across different target cities. This can be achieved by estimating the impact of different future air pollution control pathways on ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations and human health; identifying critical contributing emission sources and the impacts of future policy scenarios to quantify different atmospheric pollutant induced climatic hazards.

CONCLUSIONS

To achieve controlled ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations, the monitoring of air pollution and addressing climate change as well is very crucial. Government schemes, like the adoption of renewable, clean energy in personal and commercial transportation systems, must be undertaken worldwide for the allocation of resources to fund renewable energy initiatives. There may be initiatives such as the adoption of conscientious forest management strategies to mitigate wildfire risks; prohibition of practices for agricultural and biomass burning; promotion of eco-friendly alternatives to wood-burning ovens; control of individual waste by upcycling, recycling, and reusing existing items etc.

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VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL PROPERTIES OVER THE WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION (PALAMPUR) USING REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUES

S. K. SINGH¹, RADHAKRISHNAN S.R.^{2,3}, J. RATHORE⁴ AND V. SHARMA^{2,3}

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital – 263001, India.

²Environmental Sciences and Biomedical Metrology Division, National Physical Laboratory

³Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India.

⁴Centre For Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Optical Properties, Raman Lidar, Modis, Western Himalayan Region.

INTRODUCTION

The effects of atmospheric aerosols on the Earth's climate system are significant, still they are still not fully known. The greater spatial-temporal variability of aerosols and their complex interactions with the gases in the atmosphere, radiation, and clouds are to account for these uncertainties. We can study the properties of aerosols with the help of ground based and satellite-based observations. Accurate estimation of aerosol climatic effect is extremely difficult due to the highly heterogeneous and area-specific physico-chemical and optical properties of aerosols. Satellite measurements can provide fruitful information about atmospheric constituents over any geolocation especially over remote places where ground-based observations are not feasible due to geographical, climatic, and economical challenges. They can also help to validate and corroborate the ground-based measurements. The aim of this work is to investigate the aerosol optical properties such as aerosol optical depth (AOD), angstrom exponent (AE) over Palampur in the Western Himalayan region, obtained from ground-based and satellite-based measurements during 2017 to 2022.

METHODS

A Raymetrics Raman Lidar system is installed at the National Physical Laboratory's remote monitoring station at the campus of CSIR-Institute of Himalayan Bioresource Technology (IHBT), Palampur, Himachal Pradesh, India (32.11°N, 76.53°E and 1347m amsl). The technical specifications of the Raman lidar system are given in Table 1. In this study, the Raman Lidar measurements over Palampur from Feb 2017 to Dec 2019 during clear sky days have been used. The Raman channel was operated only during night time (non-cloudy condition) in the observation period due to its low signal strength. The lidar data was processed using the methodologies discussed in (Jaswant et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2022). The AOD measurements obtained by Raman lidar are compared with the satellite-based AOD obtained from level 3 MODIS. AOD data for Palampur was obtained from the MODIS Terra (MOD08_D3 v6.1) satellite as a daily mean gridded average in 1° × 1° spatial resolutions and is downloaded from <https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>.

Specifications of Raman Lidar	
Pulsed Laser Source	Nd:YAG (Quantel ULTRA100)
Wavelength	355 nm
Energy / Pulse	32.8 mJ
Repetition Rate	20 Hz
Laser Beam Divergence	<0.8 mrad
Telescope Type	Cassegrain
Primary Diameter	200 mm
Secondary Diameter	48 mm
Transmitter–Receiver	212 mm
Field of View	2.3 mrad (adjustable from 0.5 to
Detectors	3 PMTs

Table 1. Specifications of Raman Lidar System

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Raman lidar measurements were taken from 2017 to 2019 and MODIS observations from 2017 to 2022 have been used for the study. The monthly variation of lidar derived AOD and MODIS AOD is shown in figure 1. As can be seen that lidar derived AOD and MODIS AOD follow the similar trend throughout the observation period. We observed the correlation coefficient (0.76) between Lidar AOD and MODIS AOD. The monthly variation of aerosol optical properties and angstrom exponent is shown in figure 2. The climatological annual mean AOD is 0.19 ± 0.18 and ranges from 0.02 to 0.97 which indicates that the region's atmospheric condition varies between clean and moderately polluted conditions.

Figure 1. Variation of aerosol optical depth from Raman Lidar and MODIS from 2017 to 2019

Figure 2 (a-b). Monthly variation of aerosol optical depth and angstrom exponent during 2017-22 from MODIS

CONCLUSIONS

This study elucidates the aerosol properties (aerosol optical depth, angstrom exponent) derived from MODIS and Raman lidar. The results suggest that aerosol optical depth shows the order as Monsoon> Summer>Winter>Post-monsoon in MODIS data. The dominance of coarse mode particles during summer and monsoon while fine mode particles during post-monsoon and winter are also observed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the Director, of NPL for the necessary support., The authors are thankful to CSIR network project PSC-0112 for the necessary financial support. Mr. Shishir Kumar Singh is thankful to UGC for providing a research fellowship and also to the Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR) for facilitating as its PhD student.

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ASSESSMENT OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER THE INDIAN REGION

U. C. DUMKA^{1,2}, RAHUL SHEORAN¹, D.G. KASKAOUTIS^{3,4},
S.D. ATTRI⁵, V. K. SONI⁵, SIDHARTH SINGH⁶, S. TIWARI⁷

¹Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Nainital 263001, India

²Department of Physics, Graphic Era (Deemed to be University), Dehradun –248002, India

³Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Kozani 50100,

⁴Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development, National Observatory of Athens, Palaia Penteli, 15236 Athens, Greece

⁵India Meteorological Department, New Delhi 110003, India

⁶CSIR, Central Institute of mining & Fuel Research, Dhanbad, Jharkhand 826 015, India

⁷Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, New Delhi Branch, India

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Brown Carbon, Fossil Fuel, Biomass Burning

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosol is one of Earth's most influential factors in determining local and global climate through its influence on radiative forcing, snow albedo, cloud characteristics, and precipitation (Bond et al., 2013). Despite the importance of carbonaceous aerosols, there are still not enough studies, especially in the Indian Himalayan region, to gain reliable insight into the physical, chemical, and optical properties. The present work focuses on the equivalent black Carbon (eBC) mass concentrations measured using a 7-wavelength Aethalometer at various stations throughout the Indian region. The main objectives of this study are (a) the investigation of the spectral properties and source characteristics of absorbing carbonaceous aerosols (Black carbon (BC) and Brown carbon (BrC)), (b) the estimation of solid fuel (SD), and liquid fuel (LQ) contribution to the total BC mass using wavelength-dependent absorption of BC, (c) the estimation of the primary BrC (BrCpri) and secondary (BrCsec) spectral absorption using minimum R- square (MRS) method and determination of their contribution to BrC light absorption on diurnal, seasonal, and annual basis.

METHODS

Estimation of BrC absorption

The Ångström power law describes the dependence of aerosol absorption coefficient on wavelength. The main assumptions of the most widely used methodology to estimate the BrC absorption coefficient at a wavelength λ (b_{abs} , BrC(λ)) are that the AAE for BC (AAEBC) is equal to 1 and BC is the only absorber at longer wavelengths (880 and 950nm) [1]. The $b_{abs}(\lambda)$ can be written as the sum of BC and BrC contribution:

$$b_{abs}(\lambda) = k_1 \lambda^{-AAE_{BC}} + k_2 \lambda^{-AAE_{BrC}} \quad (1)$$

Using Eq. 1 and the above assumptions, b_{abs} , BC was estimated in the spectral range 370-660

$$\text{nm as: } b_{abs,BC}(\lambda) = b_{abs}(\lambda) \times \left(\frac{\lambda}{880}\right)^{-AAE_{BC}} \quad (2)$$

Subtracting $b_{abs,BC}(\lambda)$ from $b_{abs}(\lambda)$ in Eq. 2, b_{abs} , BrC(λ) was calculated.

Estimation of secondary BrC absorption

Secondary and primary BrC absorptions were calculated following the MRS technique (Wang et al., 2019).

$$b_{abs,BrCsec}(\lambda) = b_{abs}(\lambda) - \left(\frac{b_{abs}(\lambda)}{BC}\right)_{pri} \times [BC] \quad (3)$$

Where [BC] refers to the BC mass concentration and $(b_{abs}(\lambda)/BC)$ pri is the ratio of primary absorption coefficient and BC mass concentration from primary combustion sources.

Contribution of SD and LQ to BC concentration

For the source apportionment of BC, the ‘‘Aethalometer model’’ was used in the present work. This model assumes that eBC is only emitted from liquid (e.g., vehicles, industries, brick kilns, etc.) and solid (e.g., forest fires, anthropogenic wood burning, agricultural residue and crop burning, waste-material burning, etc.) sources.

$$\frac{b_{abs,SD}(370)}{b_{abs,SD}(880)} = \left(\frac{370}{880}\right)^{-AAE_{SD}} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{b_{abs,LQ}(370)}{b_{abs,LQ}(880)} = \left(\frac{370}{880}\right)^{-AAE_{LQ}} \quad (5)$$

To estimate the SD and LQ contributions to the total absorption coefficient, we used specific values for AAESD = 1.8 and AAELQ = 1. These are the default values presented in the aethalometer model AE33 manual.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Annual averaged BC, BCSD, and BCLQ mass concentration over different stations across the Indian region.

Table 1. Annual BCFF and BCWB mass concentration over different stations across the Indian region. The values inside the bracket are standard deviations.

The results reveal high BC concentrations in Indian cities, which are maximized in the densely populated and highly polluted New Delhi (NDL) and Kolkata (KOL), while the sites located in the Indo-Gangetic plains also reveal high BC levels (Figure. 1, Table 1). In all stations the BCFF dominates against BCWB, while the contribution of the latter changes significantly depending on the season, with higher values during autumn (agriculture burning in NW India) and winter due to residential wood burning for domestic heating. Like BCFF high value of BCLQ is observed over the Indian cities.

Site	BC-FF	BC-WB
BHJ	1.54 (± 1.75)	0.42 (± 0.56)
CHD	9.48 (± 8.94)	1.99 (± 3.97)
DNB	4.28 (± 3.43)	1.3 (± 1.61)
GWH	5.56 (± 7.11)	1.41 (± 6.38)
JDP	3.73 (± 5.15)	0.84 (± 1.54)
KOL	11.41 (± 12.94)	1.74 (± 9.56)
MUK	0.74 (± 0.72)	0.18 (± 0.23)
NDL	11.54 (± 12.60)	2.66 (± 4.18)
NGP	3.75 (± 4.59)	1.16 (± 6.45)
PBL	2.32 (± 2.11)	0.29 (± 0.38)
PNE	6.09 (± 9.11)	0.89 (± 1.67)
RCH	3.56 (± 3.91)	1.07 (± 1.55)
RNC	1.18 (± 1.14)	0.62 (± 1.12)
SRN	9.76 (± 9.81)	3.15 (± 6.63)
TRV	3.80 (± 2.55)	0.92 (± 1.09)
VKS	5.89 (± 5.08)	0.61 (± 0.71)
VNS	6.59 (± 6.19)	2.63 (± 6.25)

CONCLUSIONS

High BC mass concentrations over the Indian cities maximized in the IGP region. High (82%) percentage contributions of BCFF and BCLQ are clearly observed over all the Indian stations.

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ASSESSMENT OF OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICULATE MATTER IN DIFFERENT ROAD TYPES: INFLUENCE OF TRAFFIC CONDITIONS AND FLEET COMPOSITION

SHREYA DUBEY¹, SOHANA DEBBARMA², NAGENDRA RAPARTHI¹,
HARISH C. PHULERIA^{1,2,3}

¹Environmental Science and Engineering Department, IIT Bombay, Mumbai, 400076, India

²Centre for Climate Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai, 400076, India

³Koita Centre for Digital Health, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Oxidative Potential, Particulate Matter, Road Traffic, Vehicular Emissions

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols of vehicular origin are one of the potential sources of urban air pollution and are influenced by factors such as vehicular speed, traffic volume, and fleet composition. Both exhaust and non-exhaust vehicular components contribute to particulate matter (PM), which poses adverse health risks. PM mass concentration alone may not explain the toxic constituents of PM_{2.5}, hence, the Oxidative Potential (OP) assessment is used to examine the reactive oxygen species (ROS) induced by PM, which causes inflammation and oxidative stress (Shirmohammadi et al., 2017). This study aims to examine the toxicity of different PM size fractions inside roadway tunnels and at kerbside locations and their relationship with driving conditions and fleet characteristics.

METHODS

PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were measured in and near Mumbai, India at four different traffic sites: at the entry and exit of two roadway tunnels, and at two kerbsides and an urban background location in Mumbai — Kamshet-I tunnel (KT) on the Mumbai-Pune expressway with vehicular speed of 80 km/hr while the Eastern freeway tunnel (EFT) where the speed is 60 km/hr (Raparthi et al., 2021, Debbarma et al., 2024). LBS road, a major thoroughfare in the city with a vehicular speed of 25-30 km/hr, while the Mulund-Toll Plaza, where creeping vehicles with a speed <15 km/hr were captured. Traffic volume and characteristics were analyzed through video surveillance and random vehicle registration plates at all four locations. Light Duty Vehicles (LDVs) dominated the traffic at each road type, with varying proportions of Heavy-Diesel Duty Vehicles (HDDVs), Kamshet (20%), EFT (2%), LBS (5%), and MTP (10%). The collected PM samples were subjected to cell-free assays, OPDTT (Dithiothreitol), for examining toxicity, followed by elemental and carbonaceous analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The mass-normalized oxidative potential (OPDTT) of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} across different road types during peak hours (upper panel) and non-peak hours (lower panel) is depicted in Figure 1. During peak hours, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} show 0.5-1.5 times higher OPDTT levels at the entry site compared to the exit site, suggesting the influence of ROS active components in ambient aerosols along with vehicular sources. On comparing traffic-cum mixed environments such as tunnel entries, with kerbside locations like LBS road and MTP — OPDTT activity is more pronounced at tunnels due to excess dust resuspension (Debbarma et al., 2024) and higher vehicular speed than the kerbside. Background location, which represents urban emissions from multiple sources, shows a significantly higher OPDTT activity with respect to the

kerbside for both size fractions, indicating the presence of more redox-active species per unit of aerosol. During the afternoon period, corresponding to non-peak hours, higher OPD TT activity is observed for all road types and size fractions compared to peak hours. This suggests that photochemical activity enhances secondary aerosol formation, which is more ROS-active than freshly emitted primary aerosols from vehicles during peak hours (Ntziachristos et al., 2007). Currently, the association with traffic characteristics, elemental, and carbonaceous species is being studied to gain further insights into these results.

Figure 1. Mass-normalized OPD TT levels for different road types during (a) Peak hours and (b) non-peak hours

(Inter-city Tunnel: Kamshet tunnel; Intra-city Tunnel: Eastern Freeway tunnel; LBS road: Lal Bahadur Shastri Marg with its corresponding background; Toll-plaza: Mulund-Thane Toll-plaza with its corresponding background)

CONCLUSIONS

This piece of work suggests that OP activity varies across different road types and is strongly driven by the particle size fractions, as observed during peak and non-peak hours.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India {Grant no. RD/0119-DST0000-045} and partially supported by the Department of Science and Technology- Centre of Excellence, Phase II, Govt. of India (Grant no. DST/CCP/CoE/140/2018).

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HEAVY METALS ASSOCIATED WITH PM_{2.5} IN THE AMBIENT ATMOSPHERE OF SASARAM, BIHAR, DURING THE PRE-MONSOON SEASON

ANKITA ROY^{1#}, APARNA GUPTA^{1,2}, RAJEEV RAJAK^{1,2}, BIDYUTJYOTI BARUAH^{1,2},
SWATI YADAV¹ AND RAKESH KUMAR RANJAN^{1,2*}

¹Department of Geology, Sikkim University, Gangtok, Sikkim 737102, India

²DST's Centre of Excellence, Department of Geology, Sikkim University, Sikkim 737102,

KEYWORDS: Heavy Metals, Aerosols, PM_{2.5}, Sasaram, Pre-monsoon Season, ICP-MS

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, particularly fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), present a major risk to both human health and environmental stability worldwide. This issue is especially pressing in rapidly urbanizing regions of developing countries, where industrial activities, vehicular emissions, and construction can lead to elevated levels of air pollution. Fine particulate matter can act as carriers for various toxic substances, including heavy metals, which exacerbate their negative impacts (Martinelli et al., 2013). Studies have shown that exposure to PM_{2.5} can lead to a variety of health problems, such as respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, as well as adverse environmental effects like reduced visibility and ecosystem damage (Kim et al., 2015, Pipal et al., 2011). Sasaram, a rapidly growing city and administrative headquarters of Rohtas district in Bihar, India, is currently grappling with these challenges as it undergoes significant urban expansion and biomass burning in surrounding areas. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the concentration of heavy metals associated with fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in Sasaram during the pre-monsoon season of 2022. By analysing the composition of PM_{2.5}, we seek to understand the sources and potential risks posed by these pollutants.

METHODS

This study focuses on the characterization of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and the associated heavy metal concentrations in the ambient atmosphere of Sasaram during the pre-monsoon season of 2022. Aerosol samples were collected over a five-month period, from February to June 2022, using a high-volume aerosol sampler fitted with quartz fibre filters (QMA). The collected PM_{2.5} samples were analysed to determine the concentration of heavy metals using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). With the use of 1-N HNO₃, multi-element standards (Agilent 8500-6940) instrument was calibrated. The measurements were made with greater than 5% accuracy with helium (99.9996%) as a carrier gas. Statistical analyses were performed to assess the spatial and temporal variability of heavy metal concentrations and to compare the findings with established air quality standards.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The monthly mean concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) of selected metals is presented in table 1. The study found that aluminium (Al) had the highest concentration, peaking at $14.41 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in March 2022. Other metals, including mercury (Hg) and nickel (Ni), exhibited notable seasonal variations, with Hg peaking at $0.0058 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and Ni at $0.0737 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in April. Arsenic (As) and cadmium (Cd) had lower concentrations, with As reaching $0.0029 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in April. The concentrations of most metals are higher in the pre-monsoon months, especially from

February to April. This can be attributed to drier conditions that lead to more particulate resuspension, higher dust activity, and increased anthropogenic activities like crop residue burning and industrial emissions. March and April seem to be critical months where concentrations of heavy metals such as aluminium, mercury, nickel, and zinc peak. This could be due to stable atmospheric conditions (e.g., temperature inversions) trapping pollutants close to the ground. By June, as humidity rises and the monsoon approaches, there is a clear decline in the concentrations of heavy metals. This is likely due to increased wet deposition (rain scavenging), which cleans the atmosphere of particulate matter and associated metals. The analysis also revealed higher metal concentrations at night, likely due to temperature inversions and reduced wind speeds trapping pollutants. The pre-monsoon season's dry conditions, coupled with crop residue burning, increased particulate load, leading to higher metal concentrations. These concentrations exceed WHO recommended limits for several metals, raising concerns about public health.

Montl	Al	Fe	Ni	Pb	Rb	Li	Co	As	Se	Cd	Hg	U
Feb- 2022	10.2 900	1.1 404	0.0 356	0.0 200	0.0 094	0.0 107	0.0 023	0.0 014	0.0 020	0.0 019	0.0 029	0.0 021
Mar- 2022	11.2 238	0.9 585	0.0 356	0.0 187	0.0 088	0.0 099	0.0 018	0.0 015	0.0 025	0.0 017	0.0 030	0.0 020
Apr- 2022	9.05 44	2.0 874	0.0 509	0.0 271	0.0 177	0.0 070	0.0 050	0.0 021	0.0 027	0.0 019	0.0 034	0.0 025
May- 2022	6.07 06	0.6 565	0.0 156	0.0 122	0.0 102	0.0 067	0.0 012	0.0 011	0.0 017	0.0 012	0.0 016	0.0 016
Jun- 2022	5.25 94	0.5 362	0.0 071	0.0 129	0.0 091	0.0 065	0.0 009	0.0 011	0.0 014	0.0 008	0.0 001	0.0 018

Table 1. Monthly mean concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) of selected metals

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights the urgent need for enhanced air quality monitoring and pollution control measures in Sasaram. The presence of toxic metals such as Pb, Hg, and As raises significant public health concerns. The high levels of Al could pose a risk for neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's, if exposure persists over time. The present study underscores the need for stricter air quality monitoring and pollution control measures in Sasaram and other rapidly developing regions of Bihar. It also highlights the importance of public awareness regarding the health risks associated with air pollution, particularly in areas with significant crop residue burning.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The authors would like to thank and acknowledge DST's Centre of Excellence (CoE), at the Department of Geology, Sikkim University- (DST/CCP/CoE/186/2019 (G), dated 03/03/2020), for providing the instrumentation facilities for sample analysis. The authors also would like to acknowledge Mrs. Sheela, a resident of Lakhanusaray, Sasaram for carrying out continuous measurement of aerosol samples for the present study.

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OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PM_{2.5} EMISSIONS FROM LIGHT-DUTY GOODS AND HEAVY-DUTY VEHICLES IN ON-ROAD OPERATIONS IN INDIA

MOHD SHAHZAR KHAN AND GAZALA HABIB

Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Department of Civil Engineering, New Delhi – 110016

KEYWORDS: On-Road Vehicular Emissions, Black Carbon, Mass Absorption Cross-Section.

INTRODUCTION

The on-road transport sector is one of the important sectors that contributes to urban air pollution and affects climate change and human health. Diesel powered vehicles are the dominant fuel consuming vehicles in Indian on-road fleets which are responsible for particulate emissions (Pandey and Venkataraman, (2014)). Tailpipe emissions of diesel vehicles consist of carbonaceous aerosol including particulate matter and light absorbing carbon. Mass emission and its composition from the vehicle tailpipe depend on many factors such as type of fuel, vehicle technology, maintenance and driving characteristics. Jaiprakash and Habib, (2017) suggested that the tailpipe emissions from the laboratory (chassis dynamometer) and model studies are significantly different from emissions measured through on-road measurement. Aerosol absorption and scattering properties such as mass absorption cross-section (MAC) and mass scattering coefficients (MSC) play an important role in regional climate assessment. Therefore, in the present study, the real-world mass absorption cross-section and mass scattering coefficient from exhaust emissions of light-duty (goods) and heavy-duty vehicles (Trucks and tractors) will be presented in Indian on-road conditions.

METHODS

On-road measurement of emissions from light motor vehicles (LMV)-goods, tractors and trucks were performed in real world conditions in West Bengal and Bihar using a versatile source sampling system (VS3). In VS3, a fraction of exhaust enters through an isokinetic particle sampling probe into a dilution tunnel designed for homogenous mixing, negligible wall losses and complete aerosol quenching. Turbulent and instantaneous mixing of exhaust with 40-60 times zero air inside the dilution tunnel exhibits the dilution process that happens in the atmosphere. Portability, low power requirement and continuous clean air supply are other important attributes of VS3 for its on-field use. The emission measurements were conducted on rural roads and highways with vehicles of different emission norms on a 15-30 km mixed traffic route daily followed by the driver. PM mass was collected on different filter substrates for gravimetric and chemical analysis. The particle absorption and scattering were measured with a 7-wavelength aethalometer (AE33) and Nephelometer (IN102) respectively. The carbonaceous fraction of PM_{2.5} was determined on a Quartz filter using a Thermal optical reflectance analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

BC and EC concentrations in the vehicle exhaust were found in the range of 5000-40000 µg/m³ for the tractors, LMV-goods and trucks. A correlation plot was made for BC and EC concentration as shown in figure 1 and found a good correlation between them with R² value of 0.97. Mass absorption cross-section (m²/gPM_{2.5}) was presented in a box plot as shown in figure 2 for tractor, LMV-goods and truck. MAC value was found higher for tractor (1.4-10.4) and truck (4.4-8.3) as compared to LMV-goods (0.8-5.3) due to having a lower concentration of BC for LMV-goods. Variations of MAC for tractors, LMV-goods and trucks of different

emission norms on rural roads and highways will be discussed in the paper. Mass scattering coefficients will also be discussed in the paper for the same vehicle categories.

Figure 1. Correlation plot for black carbon and elemental carbon concentration in the exhaust for all sets of experiments of the tractor, LMV-goods and truck vehicles.

Figure 2. Mass absorption cross-section for tractor, LMV-goods and truck for all set of experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

The mass concentration of EC determined from the TOR method has shown a good correlation with BC obtained from aethalometer (Figure 1). The mass absorption cross-section of particles emitted from trucks and tractors were higher than those from LMV-good (Figure 2). A strong dependence of MACs on vehicle age has been observed. The finding from this study has implications in climate assessment and framing the policies for on-road use of vehicles for improving local air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change under the NCAP-COALESCE project {Grant No.14/10/2014-CC (Vol. II)}. The views expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Min-istry. The Ministry does not endorse any products or commercial ser-vices mentioned in this publication.

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MOS2-DERIVED MXENE FOR ALCOHOL SENSING AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

KAVITA MISHRA ^A, SAURABH RAWAT ^B,
HIMANI SHARMA ^B, CHARU DWIVEDI ^{A*}

^A School of Physical Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Doon University, Dehradun

^B School of Physical Sciences, Department of Physics, Doon University, Dehradun

ABSTRACT

KEYWORDS: Two Dimensional, Mxene, Nanocomposite, Sensor

INTRODUCTION

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are commonly used in industrial applications; however, they pose significant risks as air pollutants due to their high toxicity. Monitoring VOCs has garnered considerable attention in the field of safety control to help prevent industrial accidents [1]. Two-dimensional materials have attracted extensive attention and research due to their large specific surface area and high carrier mobility [2]. Among many 2D materials, Ti₃C₂TX MXene, as an emerging two-dimensional material, has exhibited excellent properties in many aspects, and many works have demonstrated its application potential in energy storage, gas sensing and catalysis [3]. MoS₂, with its graphene-like structure, has gained significant attention due to its excellent electrical conductivity, large specific surface area, stability, strong adsorption capabilities, and high reactivity. However, MoS₂-based gas sensors face challenges such as low sensitivity and prolonged response times [4].

METHODS

In this study, a 2D MoS₂-MXene nanocomposite was successfully prepared by hydrothermal method. The prepared sample was analyzed by various characterization techniques such as FE-SEM, FTIR, XRD and Raman spectroscopy. Gas sensing elements were fabricated from 2D MoS₂-MXene and gas sensitivity tests were carried out to detect different concentrations of alcohol at room temperature.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

MoS₂ based gas sensor exhibits great capabilities in the field of gas sensing, especially for room-temperature gas detection. Fig. 1 shows the response plot of the MXene-MoS₂ toward 10 ppm ethanol at room temperature demonstrating its repeatable, fast gas response and recovery.

Figure 1. Gas-sensing response of MXene-MoS₂ towards ethanol

CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results show that the gas sensor made from MoS₂-MXene holds great potential for detecting VOC gases, making it a promising candidate for efficient VOC gas sensing applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge DST for the INSPIRE fellowship [DST/INSPIRE Fellowship/2020/IF200420] and DST PURSE (Project no. SR/PURSE/2023/199) for providing the financial support.

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UNDERSTANDING THE INFLUENCE OF BLACK CARBON AND ORGANIC AEROSOLS IN SEMI-ARID AND ARID REGIONS OF RAJASTHAN

ASHISH GUPTA¹ AND DEEPIKA BHATTU¹

¹Department of Civil and Infrastructure Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Jodhpur

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Organic Aerosol, Light Absorption.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric black carbon (BC) and organic aerosols (OA) significantly impact climate by influencing radiative forcing. BC is the second most significant contributor to anthropogenic positive radiative forcing after CO₂ (Bond et al., 2013); however, OA also substantially affects the climate forcing in the equivalence of 27% to 70% of BC (Lin et al., 2014). Previous studies have shown that the absorption of BC spans from ultraviolet (UV) to infrared range, while that of OA is more efficient in the near UV range (Andrea et al., 2006). The absorption properties depend on the size, shape, mass, wavelength of the incident light, and chemical composition of the aerosol. They are represented using two parameters: mass absorption cross section (MAC) (m²/g), which defines absorption of light by a cross-section area per unit mass of the particle, and the Absorption Ångström Exponent (AAE), which defines the wavelength dependence of light absorption by an aerosol. However, because of variations in properties of carbonaceous aerosols due to diverse emitting sources and differences in combustion temperature, air-to-fuel ratio, and fuel used along with regional emissions, atmospheric conditions, the aging process through which it undergoes in the atmosphere, and the mixing state of BC and OA (externally or internally) further complicates the generalization of MAC and AAE.

Despite being the world's second largest emitter of BC (Rana et al., 2019), very few studies have been done in India that too focused only on the IGP region with only BC concentration measured. The light absorption characteristics of BC alone and with OA have not been explored in arid and semi-arid areas. This study compares the sources, concentration, diurnal variation, and the radiative forcing of BC and OA on the climate. Here, an approach is derived to obtain separate MAC and AAE for BC and OA, which gives a more robust estimation of India's arid and semi-arid regions.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in two distinct environments, the semi-arid region (Kota) and the arid region (Jodhpur) of Rajasthan, during Dec 2022 (winter) and October 2022 (winter), respectively. An Aethalometer (AE33) equipped with PM_{2.5} cyclones was operated at 2 lpm to measure the absorption of aerosols at seven wavelengths (0.37, 0.47, 0.52, 0.66, 0.88 and 0.95 μm) and eBC concentration was calculated at 880 nm. Additionally, gaseous measurements (CO and NO_x) and meteorological parameters relative humidity (RH), temperature (T), wind speed (WS) and Wind Direction (WD) were measured at the arid site, whereas for the semi-arid site, were sourced from Shreenathpuram Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Station (Rajasthan et al. (RSPCB)). Daily filter samples were also collected and analysed for elemental carbon (EC) and organic carbon (OC) with Sunset EC-OC analyser using NIOSH-5040 protocol.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

1. eBC and AAE Variation during the sampling

Figure 1. (a) that in the arid area box plot described before Nov 6, the average eBC concentration was $3.30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, after Nov 6, the value increased to $4.70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as emissions were increased here, similarly in the semi-arid region before Dec 7. However, very few high values were there; because of that, the mean will be high, but the overall concentration of eBC is less than after Dec 7. If we compare the concentration level of eBC, it is depicted in Figure 1. (a) that in arid regions, eBC concentration is considerably lower than in semi-arid regions; the reason behind this may be the sampling location as in arid regions is very far from the city and industries but in semi-arid region sampling was done in an industrial location which is highly influenced from industrial and traffic emissions.

Figure 1: Box plots of eBC concentrations (a) and AAE values (b) for semi-arid and arid regions, comparing pre-increase and post-increase periods, with boxes displaying the IQR, whiskers extending 1.5 times the IQR, and median values marked inside the boxes.

After using the power fitting method, AAE values were obtained after calculating the absorption at different wavelengths from the default MAC values described for the aethalometer (AE33). It is observed in Figure 1. (b) that in the semi-arid regions, during the initial days, when the activities were minimal, AAE values ranged from 1.26 to 1.38, with significantly higher values observed during the night, which indicates biomass burning activities increased. However, after December 6th, the AAE values increased rapidly, ranging from 1.42 to 1.63, while the temperature pattern was consistent during the sampling period. Similarly, in the Arid region in the initial days, the AAE values remained consistent, ranging from 1.32 to 1.45, indicating a mixture of sources, such as traffic and biomass burning, and constant temperature. However, after November 6th, the AAE values increased rapidly, ranging from 1.52 to 2.04, and temperature variation during the day rapidly decreased, suggesting a significant increase in nearby biomass-burning activities.

2. Diurnal profile of eBC

The average diurnal profile of eBC (figure 2a, 2b) shows a distinct pattern for both regions. Both the regions have minima during the daytime (11:00 – 16:00 hrs) with ~4.5 times higher value in the semi-arid region (Kota, $6.54 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) than in the arid region. However, the peak concentration during morning rush hours (07:00 – 09:00 hrs) and nighttime (19:00 – 23:00 hrs) are 83.12% higher in Kota as compared to Jodhpur. Furthermore, eBC during nighttime

stays at similar levels, whereas in Kota, it decreases after reaching a plateau. In Jodhpur, the sampling site is distant from the city with minimal emissions, primarily from a less busy highway. In contrast, the Kota site is in a major industrial area near the central circle, with significant pollution from metal and chemical plants, along with substantial traffic influence.

Figure 2: Plot depicting winter season diurnal variation of eBC concentration in (a) semi-arid and (b) arid regions.

3. Linear regression

Then the separate values of MAC for BC and OC are obtained through linear regression on the concentration obtained from EC and OC analysis, taking EC as BC and relating these with the total absorption calculated at each wavelength, and this reveals that at wavelength 880nm at which eBC is considered as BC also has absorption due to OC as well.

And AAE values are calculated using $MAC \left(\frac{m^2}{g} \right) = C_o \lambda^{-AAE}$, (where C_o is a fitting parameter independent of wavelength) for BC and OC separately.

Table 1. Values of MAC and AAE obtained from linear regression at semi-arid region

Description (@ 880 nm)	MAC (m ² /g)	AAE
BC	9.311	1.11
OC	2.017	1.20

CONCLUSIONS

This study compares the eBC concentration in semi-arid and arid regions of Rajasthan, highlighting the differences in concentration levels, sources, and diurnal variations in these two distinct atmospheric conditions. eBC relation with NO_x and CO provided insights into sources of emissions, which were confirmed through AAE values.

Furthermore, applying the linear regression method to characterize the light absorption properties of BC and OC provides more accurate information in optical instrumentation and offers a more reliable estimation. Future research should focus on obtaining climate forcing due to these aerosols in these areas and exploring the potential interactions between BC and OA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided by the Rajasthan State Pollution Control Board (RSPCB) for conducting sampling at Kota and providing the CAAQMS data. Ashish Gupta gratefully acknowledges the support of the Ministry of Education through the provision of a scholarship.

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MULTICITY CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION STUDY TOWARDS THE DETERMINATION OF TOXICITY

¹AMRUTA NAKHWA, ¹MANISH JOSHI, ¹MARIAM, ¹SHAKIL AHAMAD, ¹PALLAVI KHANDARE, ²MAHESH TIWARI, ²SABYASACHI ROUT, ¹ARSHAD KHAN & ¹B K SAPRA

¹Radiological Physics and Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai
²Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre

KEYWORDS: Multicity, Aerosol, Toxicity Score, Pah, Inorganic Ions

INTRODUCTION

Chemical characterization of aerosol particles involves identifying their composition, which has a major impact on air quality, contributes to climate change, and pose health risks by causing respiratory and cardiovascular diseases etc. such as organic compounds like PAH, inorganic ions such as sulfates, nitrates etc, metals, and elemental carbon to name a few. PAHs due to their carcinogenic, mutagenic, and teratogenic nature have gained worldwide attention in the recent past (Tapan et al, 2023). Whereas, inorganic ions play a critical role in atmospheric processes, cloud formation, and light scattering, affect climate etc in addition to health impact on humans. A multicity chemical characterisation study was carried out to assess the composition and toxicity of aerosol particles across different urban environments. To assess these impacts, quantitative estimation of PAH and ions was carried out in different cities of India. Thereafter, the toxicity score was determined using Multiple attribute decision-making (MADM) (Wanga and Luo, 2010) from the measured concentration. Understanding these aspects is crucial for determining how aerosol toxicity affects public health, particularly in terms of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases.

METHODS

Inorganic ions were analyzed using ion chromatography (IC) and PAHs using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) or high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). These methods allowed precise quantification of trace components in aerosols. Aerosol samples were collected for 24 hr duration for a week and mass concentrations were calculated by gravimetric method. The collected aerosol samples on filters were divided into two parts and then respectively digested for IC and HPLC analysis. Multiple attribute decision making (MADM) was adopted to determine the relation between the different chemical species (attribute) in different cities (attribute) in terms of score. The MADM uses the correlation coefficient and standard deviation (CCSD) method. The CCSD method determines weights by combining correlation and standard deviation of all the combinations of attributes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PAH analysis showed the presence of Phenanthrene, BghiP, ACY, Ind123cdP, D (a,h)A, BeP (Table 1) to name a few, out of which few have been classified as B2 class carcinogens. Figure 1 shows the dominance of fluorene, which can be attributed to the incomplete combustion of organic materials. A similar analysis of the inorganic ions in the aerosol sample showed the dominance of nitrate anions, followed by sulphate and phosphate. Cation concentration in most of the cities was found to be less than the anion concentration except for F- and Cl-. Mg was below the detection limit in most of the cities except Mumbai.

Fig 1. Concentration of PAHs in Bathinda.

Fig 2. Distribution of various inorganic ions as obtained in Hyderabad

CONCLUSIONS

Chemical characterization of aerosol particles was carried out in multiple cities for PAH and inorganic ions using IC and GC/HPLC respectively. The MADM model coupled with the CCSD method was used to determine the corresponding toxicity value. Understanding these aspects is crucial for determining how aerosol toxicity affects public health, particularly in terms of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. The study will help in developing targeted pollution control measures based on regional emission profiles and health impacts.

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DYNAMIC SHAPE FACTOR OF SOOT PARTICLES USING EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

S. ANAND^{1,2}, JAYANT KRISHAN^{1,2}, AMRUTA N³,
MARIAM^{1,3} AND MANISH JOSHI^{1,3}

¹Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai – 400 094, India.

²Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

³Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Dynamic Shape Factor, Fluid Dynamics, Aerosol Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The aerodynamic behavior and collision properties of aerosol particles are crucially influenced by their size distribution and morphology. While conventional models often simplify aerosol particles as spherical and fully dense, actual aerosol particles deviate from these idealized forms, necessitating the need for correction factors known as shape factors. Deviations from sphericity significantly impact deposition and aggregation rates, with dynamic shape factors addressing modifications in aerodynamic properties for non-spherical particles, in comparison to volume equivalent spherical particles. This study aims to provide a methodology for estimating the dynamic shape factor using experimental techniques. These observations are significant for the validation of the empirical relations used for the estimation of dynamic shape factors.

METHODS

Dynamic shape correction factor (χ) is defined as ratio of the actual drag force on non-spherical particle (F_D) to the drag force on a sphere of equivalent volume moving at the same velocity (F_{Dv})

$$\chi = \frac{F_D}{F_{Dv}} = \frac{d_m}{d_{mass}} \frac{C(d_{mass})}{C(d_m)} \quad (1)$$

Where, in continuum regime, drag force on the particle is; $F_D = \frac{3\pi \mu d_m u_p}{C(d_m)}$, $F_{Dv} = \frac{3\pi \mu d_v u_p}{C(d_v)}$, μ is the viscosity of air, u_p is the characteristic particle velocity, d_m is the mobility equivalent diameter of the particle, d_v is the diameter of spherical particle of same volume (v) as the particle of interest, d_{mass} is mass equivalent radius of particle (diameter of nonporous sphere composed of bulk particle material that has same mass as the particle of interest), and C is the slip correction factor. Assuming bulk density is same as the particle density of a material, $d_{mass} = d_v$. Alternatively, χ can be defined based on the aerodynamic diameter (Zeller, 1985) as,

$$\chi = \frac{d_{mass}^2}{d_a^2} \frac{C(d_{mass})}{C(d_a)} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the particle bulk density, and ρ_0 is the unit density. Substituting Eq. 1 in Eq. 2 and rearranging the dynamic shape factor can be expressed in terms of aerodynamic and mobility diameters,

$$\chi = \left(\frac{d_m^2}{d_a^2} \frac{C^2(d_{mass})}{C^2(d_m) C(d_a)} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

Similarly, the dynamic shape factor in the free molecular regime can be defined by modifying the expression for the drag force.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Two set of observations are made for silica i.e. in one case, particle mobility diameter is selected as 100 nm ($2R_m$) and in another case, it is selected as 120 nm ($2R_m$) using DMA and then sampled using ELPI. In both cases, the particles are observed in the same size bin in ELPI, i.e., in the range of 98-170 nm with a mean size of 134 nm ($2R_{ae}$). This is because the ELPI size bins are coarse as the particle size increases. The mobility diameter selected and the aerodynamic diameter observed corresponding to the given mobility diameter are then plugged in Eq 3 to estimate the dynamic shape factor of silica particles and is given by,

$$\chi = \left(\frac{d_m^2}{d_a^2} \frac{C^2(d_{mass})}{C^2(d_m)} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{1/3} = \left(\frac{110^2 \cdot 2}{134^2 \cdot 1} \right)^{1/3} = 1.1$$

where $\rho_0=1$ g/cc, $\rho = 2$ g/cc (Kimoto et al., 2017), $R_m = 55$ nm, $R_{ae} = 67$ nm, and $C(R_{ae}) = C(R_m) = C(R_{mass}) \approx 1.0$. The dynamic shape factor for silica particles is expected to be in the range of 1 since they are spherical. The experimental measurements show ~10% deviation from the expected value ($\chi = 1$), which may be due to limitations in the determination of exact particle diameter. In another case, combustion aerosols are generated by burning the smoke coil in the chamber. These particles are expected to be chain-like and non-spherical. The number concentration of aerosols generated is very high and to avoid coagulation effects, the concentration is diluted. The 100-nm diameter aerosol particles are selected using DMA and size-distribution measurements are carried out using SMPS and ELPI. The mobility and aerodynamic diameters are obtained from SMPS and ELPI (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Size distribution of combustion aerosols using SMPS and ELPI

The mode of the particle size distribution in case of mobility diameter is at 88 nm whereas the same for aerodynamic diameter is at 55 nm. The shape factor for these smoke particles is then estimated as,

$$\chi = \left(\frac{d_m^2}{d_a^2} \frac{C^2(d_{mass})}{C^2(d_m)} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{1/3} = \left(\frac{88^2 \cdot 1.5}{55^2 \cdot 1} \right)^{1/3} = 1.6$$

where $\rho_0=1$ g/cc, $\rho = 1.5$ g/cc (Sapra et al., 2013), $R_m = 44$ nm, $R_{ae} = 27.5$ nm, and $C(R_{ae}) = C(R_m) = C(R_{mass}) = 1.0$. The results show that the shape factor of combustion/smoke particles is 1.6, which may be non-spherical. Also, this study implies that if we have a silica particle and a smoke particle with a mobility size of 100 nm, a smoke particle will experience a larger drag force as compared to the silica particle and hence will remain suspended in the air for a longer duration of time. These experiments provide a real-world justification for the study carried out on the shape factors using numerical simulations.

CONCLUSIONS

The study outlines the methodology to estimate the dynamic shape factors using experimental observations. These experiments will be helpful in the validation of the empirical relations generated for the estimation of dynamic shape factors using a theoretical approach.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to acknowledge Dr D K Aswal, Director, HS&EG for support, Dr. B. K. Sapra and Shri. Arshad Khan for facilitating resources for the experiments.

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STUDY OF METALS CONCENTRATION IN AMBIENT PM1 IN CENTRAL INDIA

MANAS KANTI DEB¹, SURYAKANT MANIKPURI¹ AND SHAMSH PERVEZ¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur – 492010, India.

KEYWORDS: Particulate matter, PM1, Elements, Health Effects.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common forms of air pollution, atmospheric particulate matter (PM) has a special bearing on human health, climate change, and air quality. One of the main problems that has an impact on the environment and people in India is the steadily increasing PM. PM1 is the term for particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter smaller than one micrometre. Certain elemental species are carcinogenic, and the elemental concentrations of atmospheric PM have a negative impact on human health.

METHODS

The PM1 samples were collected from different representative sites in Raipur, Chhattisgarh (22°33' to 21°14' N latitude and 82°6' to 81°38' E longitude). The PM was collected at a height of 15 meters above the ground during 2022-2023. The study regions were bordered by densely populated areas, housing developments, industrial use, biomass burning, and other activities. Samples were collected via low volume PM1 sampler in 47 mm Quartz filters. Elemental characterisation was performed in ICP-MS.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Metals are one of the important species present in the ambient air. Most metallic species present in PM have long-term stability. But certain species in nature are harmful. As, Cr and Pb in particulate matter are associated with harmful effects in humans. Among all the elements Fe was found to be the most abundant species at all sites. As, Hg, Cr concentrations were low in the PM1

Table 1. Statistical summary of site-wise elemental average concentration in PM1 (ng m⁻³) conducted at four monitoring sites.

Site	Fe	Pb	As	Hg	Cr	Cu
Industrial	1187.9 ± 410.7	91.9 ± 17.4	66.3 ± 22.6	1.7 ± 0.6	1.6 ± 0.9	8.8 ± 2.0
Residential	858.9 ± 111.0	68.8 ± 26.4	80.0 ± 28.0	1.4 ± 0.8	1.3 ± 0.7	9.8 ± 4.1
Background	922.0 ± 207.9	42.8 ± 23.2	81.2 ± 23.5	1.1 ± 0.4	1.6 ± 1.0	7.4 ± 0.4
Traffic	789.4 ± 149.6	25.9 ± 6.7	92.8 ± 46.5	0.8 ± 0.5	1.3 ± 1.0	7.8 ± 1.5

Figure 1. The average concentration of metals presents in PM1 at four representative monitoring sites.

CONCLUSIONS

Metals were detected at all the sites. Fe content was highest in comparison to other metals. . Mean concentration of metals follows the trend Fe> As>Pb>Cu>Cr>Hg. Overall, the concentration of metals was less than the allowed exposure limits. Inhalation of PM-bound carcinogenic metals can lead to increased harmful health effects

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the DST-PURSE project (SR/PURSE/2022/145).

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CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND LIGHT-ABSORBING PROPERTIES OF BROWN CARBON AEROSOL SAMPLED IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN AREA

POOJA CHAUDHARY^{1,2}, CHRISTOPHER P. WEST¹, QIAORONG XIE¹, ARPIT AWASTHI², RAJ SINGH², VINAYAK SINHA², BAERBEL SINHA², ALEXANDER LASKIN¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana 47907, USA.

³Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Mohali, Sector 81, SAS Nagar, Manauli PO, Punjab, 140306, India.

KEYWORDS – Direct Analysis in Real Time, Organic Aerosols, Molecular-Level Information, High Resolution Mass Spectrometry, Brown Carbon

INTRODUCTION

The light-absorbing fraction of organic aerosols, known as brown carbon (BrC), significantly contributes to climate change and adversely affects human health. Biomass burning (BB) emissions of BrC are ubiquitous over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). BB is very common in India because of biofuel usage for heating and cooking, agricultural residue burning, and uncontrolled domestic waste burning. These fires emit a huge number of aerosols into the atmosphere. Despite their abundance, the molecular-level understanding of BrC composition in the IGP area is limited. To address this knowledge gap, this study employs a novel molecular-level chemical characterization approach of ambient aerosol samples collected in the IGP. We integrate temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) with direct analysis in real-time (DART) ionization and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) detection, enabling untargeted analysis of complex BrC mixtures.

METHODS

Ambient aerosol samples were collected at the rooftop Atmospheric Chemistry Facility of the IISER Mohali, India using a multi-wavelength aethalometer (AE-42), which measures BC and BrC absorbance and gives time-tagged samples. 12 evening samples were taken from two different seasons—biomass burning-dominated post-monsoon and winter—and two distinct fetch regions: an urban area northeast (NE) of the site and a rural area northwest (NW) of the site. Compositional information was obtained by employing Direct Analysis in Real-Time High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (DART-HRMS) in both ionization modes. Four source samples, namely firewood, dung cakes, mixed waste burning, and plastic waste burning, were also analysed using the same method.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1(Left). Representative TPD-(±)DART-HRMS spectra of ambient organic aerosols (OA) collected on the filter tape by AE-42. (Right) Venn plot depicts the distinct and overlapping species detected in the samples from different seasons and sectors. PM stands for post-monsoon and W stands for winter season

Figure 1(L) shows the representative mass spectra from each sector and season. We observe no seasonal differences in the aerosol composition, whereas the molecular composition of organic aerosols reaching the receptor from the urban and rural sectors was significantly different. The Venn diagram in Figure 1(R) showcases the disparities and overlaps between different seasons and wind sectors. Around 6000 unique species were detected in both ionization modes. We observe that there are over 5000 species unique to either the urban or rural wind sector, while less than 500 species are common to both sectors. This reflects the chemical complexity of aerosols over the IGP. Approximately 5,800 species are unique to either the urban (~4140) or rural (~1660) sector, while fewer than 500 species are common to both.

Figure 2. Bar graphs showing fractions of OA species detected in the positive and negative DART ionization modes for urban sector, rural sector and different sources. PM stands for post-monsoon and W stands for winter samples.

As shown in Figure 2, urban samples exhibit 5 times more peaks in positive mode and 2 times as many in negative mode compared to rural samples, indicating a considerably more complex composition in urban OA. In the urban sector, 74% of the total assigned species in (+) DART were CHON compounds, 14% were CHO, 11% were CHN, and 1% were CHNOS while rural OA samples showed a balanced distribution of 42% CHO and 47% CHON species. In (-) DART mode, urban sector samples contained 56% CHON and 41% CHO species, while rural sector samples exhibited 59% CHON and 39% CHO, with other compound groups collectively comprising less than 10% in both sectors. Additionally, urban samples show the highest overlap with peaks from the mixed household waste-burning source sample (19% of peaks), while rural samples exhibit the highest overlap with the dung-cake burning source sample (24% of peaks). However, both sample types showed a significant number of photochemically produced molecular species not detected in any source sample.

CONCLUSIONS

Air over the region is dominated by N-containing species. Urban air masses are most affected by the open burning of domestic waste with the presence of reduced N-species. The presence of long-chain aliphatic oxygenated compounds contributes to absorbance at longer wavelengths, resulting in the overestimation of black carbon and the underestimation of BrC.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE POLYMER COMPOSITION OF AIRBORNE MICROPLASTICS ACROSS DRY AND WET DEPOSITION

SHREYA NANDI¹, SAIIFI IZHAR¹, AND EJAZ AHMAD²

¹Aerosol Laboratory, Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines), Dhanbad, Jharkhand-826004, India

²GreenCat Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines), Dhanbad, Jharkhand-826004, India

KEYWORDS: Airborne, Precipitation, Microplastics, Polymers

INTRODUCTION

The versatility of plastics makes them one of the most widely used materials in daily life, and these plastics eventually become waste; breakdown occurs due to various environmental factors, producing tiny plastic debris (Dehghani & Pardakhti, 2023). This plastic debris within the size range between 5 mm to 1 μm termed microplastics (MPs) are ubiquitous throughout the environment, including the deepest parts of the oceans, rivers, lakes, soils, and even drifting into the atmosphere (Frias & Nash, 2019; Kumar & Ram, 2024). However, microplastics manufactured commercially are referred to as primary (PMPs), while environmentally degraded macroplastics produce secondary microplastics (SMPs) (Frias & Nash, 2019). Research has explicitly focused on microplastics in aquatic and terrestrial environments; their presence as airborne particles poses a potential health risk due to inhalation (Kumar & Ram, 2024). Despite this concern, there is limited knowledge about airborne microplastics. Furthermore, it is crucial to comprehend the polymer composition of airborne microplastics to evaluate their environmental impact since different polymers exhibit different persistence rates and potential toxicity. This current study will provide a thorough understanding of an appropriate methodology for extracting microplastics, and chemically characterizing polymer types found across wet and dry deposition using Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR).

METHODS

Airborne particles were collected on 47 mm diameter Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) filters using a fine particulate sampler at a constant flow rate of 16.7 litres/min and operated for 24 hours from April to June 2024. The sampler was set up within and around the mining regions of Dhanbad (Jharkhand). Rainwater sampling followed passive sampling conducted on the terrace of the Department of Environmental Science and Engineering at the Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines), Dhanbad, from July to September 2024. Digestion, density separation, and filtration were performed on all samples. The extracted microparticles deposited on the filter paper were mounted on the ATR platform in direct contact with the ATR crystal for chemical characterization. The ATR probe interacted with the suspected particles, and subsequent spectra were obtained and analysed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The N-H peak strongly correlates with amide, while peaks associated with C-H, C=O, C=C, and C-O bonds suggest the presence of organic compounds. Based on the functional groups observed, polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) were speculated to be present in the source samples. Conversely, polyamides and polystyrene were

Figure 1: ATR-FTIR spectra from source samples

Figure 2: ATR-FTIR spectra from rainwater samples

found in rainwater samples. Road dust contributes significantly to the dispersion of microplastics, along with packaging materials and synthetic textiles, which, upon degradation, release microplastics into the atmosphere.

CONCLUSIONS

Airborne microplastics are considered less dense than other particles, making them drift into the air for extended periods and travel longer distances mainly by wind currents. This study is expected to highlight the pervasive nature of plastic pollution, which can even infiltrate atmospheric precipitation.

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IMPACT OF MICROPLASTICS AND NANOPLASTICS ON HUMAN LUNG CELLS

S. SHANKAR and R. GADI

Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Delhi-110006, India.

KEYWORDS: Microplastics, MPs, Nanoplastics, NPs, Impacts of MPS and NPs.

INTRODUCTION

Plastic products are resistant to degradation and, hence, are used globally. Their lightweight, economically cheap and heat and electricity resistant nature has let their production shoot for many decades. Currently, a variety of dozens of plastics have been manufactured, globally. The ambient air now-a-days has been found to be polluted with microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs). Their widespread use has become a serious challenge for air, water and soil quality. Moreover, their ingestion through multiple pathways create long-term threats to the organisms' health. From plants to animals' lungs and placenta, every physiological system remains on target. Numerous studies have investigated their impacts on cultured epithelial cells of human lungs (Xu et al., 2019; Ali et al., 2024). Since these are smaller in size, they can disrupt and/or may cross the alveolar epithelial barrier, thus, affecting the underlying cells. This may consequently lead to lung diseases with prolonged inhalation exposure.

METHODS

Various impacts on plants and human health have been reviewed in order to evaluate the hazardous consequences of MPs and NPs. Literature (published in English) was searched during September 2024 using Web of Science and Scopus databases. The keywords used were: microplastics, MPs, nanoplastics, NPs, and impacts of microplastics and nanoplastics on plants and lungs.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The FTIR spectra for functional groups present in Polystyrene-NPs (PS-NPs) have been presented in Table 1. It was found in the surveyed literature that PS-NPs were able to reduce cell viability in a dose-dependent manner. These were also found responsible for alteration in genes. It was also found that the cell cultures reflected the symptoms of lung injury with exposure to PS-NPs. Another major impact was observed in the expression of certain metalloproteinase causing pulmonary dysfunctions. As per the studies, PS-NPs are potent in breaking the redox equilibrium inducing inflammatory effects and triggering the apoptosis revealing their cytotoxicity. Proinflammation response to PS-NPs exposure was measured in the cell culture medium at certain concentrations of PS-NPs. Another test for microarray analysis for assessing the cell viability was performed. A total of 1951 genes were found to be significantly changed with the exposure of the highest concentration of PS-NPs. It was concluded that prolonged exposure to PS-NPs might act inversely reducing the repairing ability of the lungs and leading to tissue damage and consequent cell death (Xu et al., 2019; Goodman et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2024).

Functional group	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)
=CH	3023

C=C	1487 and 1617
=C-H	695 and 756

Table 1. FTIR spectra for functional groups present in PS-NPs

CONCLUSIONS

Despite numerous studies on MNs and NPs, several knowledge gaps still remain. The growing literature suggests that MPs and NPs may cause adverse impacts on different human organ systems, of which the inhalation exposure route is unavoidable. The surveyed literature mentions oxidative stress, inflammation, impaired immune functions, altered cellular metabolism, tissue degeneration, mutagenicity and carcinogenicity of exposure of lung-cell culture to different concentrations of PS-NPs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was not funded by any Govt./non-Govt. agency.

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IDENTIFICATION & QUANTIFICATION OF AIRBORNE MICROPLASTICS OVER DELHI: THEIR POTENTIAL EFFECTS ON HEALTH

M. NAGESWAR RAO¹, A. PIPAL¹, A. MUKHERJEE¹,
N. SANDIP² AND SACHIN GHUDE¹

¹Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune– 411 008, India.

²Department of Environmental Sciences, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune– 411 007

KEYWORDS: Microplastics, Aerosol, Health Risk, Delhi.

INTRODUCTION

Plastics are now a big part of human life in the last ten years, the amount of plastic made around the world has increased by about 50%. In 2021, it reached around 400 million tons (Plastics Europe, 2022). If things continue as they are, the amount of mismanaged plastic waste could increase from ~100 million tons in 2015 to ~265 million tons by 2060 (Lebreton et al., 2019). Therefore, plastic pollution is one of the biggest environmental problems faced today. Out of the 20 most polluted cities in the world, half of them is in South Asia, and these cities have severe air pollution (WHO). Microplastics (MPs) can stay in the air for a long time, which means people might breathe them. However, there is not much known about how they can affect human health. India is one of the most developing countries in South Asia and used 18.5 million tonnes of plastic in 2018-2019, about 11 million tonnes, which is 60%, was single-use plastic mainly used for packaging. The Central Pollution Control Board found that the country produces 25,940 tons of plastic waste each day. While, Delhi produces 689.8 tons of plastic waste every day, which is the highest in India's mega cities (CPCB, 2022). The fast growth of industrialization and the rise population density have led to more plastic waste in Delhi city trash in recent years. It emphasizes the importance of measuring the amount of microplastic pieces in the air and associated health risk assessment. Therefore, as far as we know, no earlier research has been done in Delhi to find and measure microplastic particles in the air. Thus, we are trying to fill this gap by looking into where atmospheric microplastics are found and what they are like in Delhi City. The main aim of this study is to assess the status of airborne MP pollution, possible sources, and associated health risks in Delhi.

METHODS

In this study, the collection of outdoor samples of microplastics associated with aerosols by active pump samplers with specific sizes of particles (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0}). All these samplers were set up on the terrace of IMD in Delhi, located at the capital city of India (28° 58' N 77° 22' E). The sampling was conducted twice in a week for each sample on Quartz and PTFE (47 mm) filter papers (pore size 0.5-2 μm) during the winter (Jan-Feb) in 2024 by low and high-volume samplers i.e. PM_{1.0} (Model Envirotech -APM 577 M), PM_{2.5} (Model Envirotech -APM 550 MFC) and PM₁₀ (Model Envirotech -APM 460 DXNL) at a constant flow rate of ~ 10, 16.7 and 0.9 -1.4 m³/min for a period of 24 hours. which is about a 30m height above ground. All sample filter papers were placed in a desiccator, which was equilibrated at 20-30°C for 24 h, further calculated the mass deposition on the sample filters by gravimetric analysis. All collected samples were wrapped with aluminium foil and frozen at 4 °C until further analysis. 1/2 portion of PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0} sample filter as well as 1/4 portion of PM₁₀ sample filter were cut with a precleaned successor. Sample preparation of MPs by Leaching, digestion, and separation method. After sample preparation of MPs were observed and identified based on visual characteristics mainly shape, colour, and size using a

fluorescence microscope (OLYMPUS BX41). The morphological characteristics and elemental content of MPs (randomly selected) were investigated using SEM–EDX. The chemical characterisation of polymer in MPs (randomly selected) was analysed by the FTIR spectroscopy method.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results of the physical characteristics of MPs were shown in PM samples, and was detected range between 0.1 and 1.4 (items/m³) is shown in Figure 1. There was also a significant difference in MPs concentrations in PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0} during the winter season

Higher items of MPs were observed in PM₁₀ compared to PM₁ and PM_{2.5}, with similar levels of abundance in both PM₁ and PM_{2.5}. Fragments and fibres were the most noticeable shape (55 and 40 %) of identified MPs in the PM samples and the color of MPs was the most common in white/transparent. The size of MPs observed range between 20 – 5000 μm Which indicates that human and industrial activities are main source to the formation of all types of MPs. Based on the results of SEM-EDX analysis, the surface morphology of MPs was observed as smooth, rough, and split-edged. It indicates that smooth surface of MPs was recently introduced into the environment and others were past in the environment for a long time due to weathering and physical degradation. In addition, the results of the elemental composition of MPs were found to be mostly composed of C and O, with a minor amount of Si, Al and Fe, indicating that MPs adsorb them from the environment. However few results found a higher content of Zn due to it being used as fillers in the production of plastics. The assessment of human intake of MPs via inhalation indicated the possible risk for people. The results of FTIR analysis, chemical composition of airborne MPs identified five different types of polymers and the most abundant plastic types i.e. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) followed by Polyethylene (PE) in the study site (Figure.1). Which indicates MPs come from daily used life products, disposable items, packing materials, bags, bottles, textiles, and industrial products.

Figure. 1. Fluorescence micrographs and different types of MPs in PM samples

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we present the first report on the distributions, morphology and compositions of airborne MPs and associated health risk assessment in Delhi and our findings show a significant difference in MPs in particulate fraction (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0}). Fragments and fibres dominated with white/blue colored, and most of the polymers originated from daily life products and clothing materials. The surface morphology of MPs shows majorly homogenous and degraded pieces. The assessment of human intake of MPs via inhalation

suggested an average daily inhalation of 10-14 MP items per person per day for adults, indicating possible risk for individuals in Delhi. Therefore, based on the current knowledge further long-term measurements are highly required in various locations to investigate the consequences of airborne MPs on human health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the Director, IITM, Pune and IMD, Delhi, Ministry of Earth Science (MoES, Govt. of India), for providing all necessary facilities and encouraging the work. Thank you to the Environmental science department of Savitribai Phule Pune University (SPPU) for supporting instrumental facilities. Thanks to the Borehole Geophysics Research Laboratory (BGRL), Karad for support of SEM-EDX facilities.

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A MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION-BASED RETRIEVAL METHOD TO PREDICT THE 3D STRUCTURE FROM A MICROSCOPIC IMAGE OF AGGREGATED AEROSOL PARTICLES

A. SINGH^{1*} AND T. THAJUDEEN¹

¹Indian Institute of Technology, School of Mechanical Sciences, Goa – 403401, India.

***Email:** abhishek19263101@iitgoa.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Multi-Objective Optimization, Morphological Characterization, Fractal Aggregates.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol particles, prevalent in environmental pollution, climate change, and human health impacts, require detailed study. However, their micro- to nanoscale size makes direct analysis challenging. Microscopy-based image analysis is widely used to study these particles, whereas 2D features of microscopic images are utilized to infer 3D structures. These 3D structures are crucial for understanding particle morphology, which significantly influences physicochemical and transport properties, affecting the environment at both local and global scales. Previous studies show that aerosols typically form non-spherical aggregates of monomers, with aggregate morphology influenced by the surrounding medium. These aggregates, in particular, can be explained using quasi-fractal geometry, with a fractal scaling law by establishing a link between the number of monomers (N) and length scale, including the radius of gyration (R_g) and monomer radius (a) as,

$$N = k_f \left(\frac{R_g}{a} \right)^{D_f} \quad (1)$$

where ‘ k_f ’ is the fractal prefactor and ‘ D_f ’ is the fractal dimension, with values typically ranging from 0.3 to 7.0 and 1 to 3, respectively. This scaling law enables the computational generation of aerosol aggregates using tuning algorithms to study their morphology. Earlier methods attempted to retrieve 3D structures from microscopic images via regression equations linking 2D features with fractal parameters (Chakrabarty et al., 2011). A later approach used a large database of 2D images of fractal aggregates, comparing them to microscopic images to find the most similar projection and select the corresponding 3D structure (Thajudeen et al., 2015). However, refining the database was tedious and inefficient. Thus, there is a need for a fast, accurate retrieval method that eliminates the need for regression equations or databases, enabling real-time retrieval. In our previous studies, a retrieval algorithm was developed, combining tuning and optimization processes (Singh & Thajudeen, 2023). The algorithm compared 2D features of microscopic images with projections of computationally generated aggregates. The optimization process selects the most similar projection using an objective function based on the 2D features, and the associated 3D structure was considered the retrieved aggregate. Tests were conducted with synthetic aggregates, where 3D properties, such as mobility diameter, were known. The retrieved and input structures were compared based on these properties to validate the proposed method. In certain cases, instruments such as the Differential Mobility Analyzer (DMA) are used to collect particles based on their mobility diameter. This property can be incorporated as a second objective function in the optimization process. The retrieval accuracy is enhanced by including both 2D features and 3D properties, ensuring a more comprehensive comparison. This enhances the process by ensuring similarity in both 2D

features and 3D properties on each iteration. It also addresses the limitations of previous methods, where relying solely on 2D features could lead to suboptimal retrievals, as a suboptimal aggregate structure may produce a similar projection due to a favourable viewing angle. Therefore, this study proposes a multi-objective optimization-based retrieval process to resolve these challenges.

METHODS

The process starts with calculating the 2D properties of the input image, including projected area, perimeter, maximum length, perpendicular width, 2D radius of gyration, and 2D fractal dimension. Using the FracVAL algorithm (Morán et al., 2019), candidate 3D aggregate structures are generated. The optimization step then selects the most similar aggregate based on two objective functions: (a) matching the 2D properties of the generated aggregate projections with those of the input image and (b) comparing the mobility diameter (D_m) of the sample from which the input image is acquired. The particle swarm optimization method is used in this study for optimization. For (a), random projections of the generated aggregates are compared using an objective function based on 2D features. For (b), D_m is calculated using geometrical properties such as the hydrodynamic radius (R_h) and orientationally-averaged projected area (PA). The aggregate that best matches both the input image properties and mobility diameter is selected as the retrieved structure. As this is a multi-objective optimization, multiple solutions are generated. The non-dominated solutions, where a solution is considered non-dominated if no other solution outperforms it in every objective function, form a Pareto set. The solution closest to the origin from this set, or the knee point, is selected as the optimal retrieved structure.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A computationally synthesized test image was used for the analysis, and the results are presented in Figure 1. The final solution space consists of multiple solutions, represented by red dots. Among these, the non-dominated solutions, forming the Pareto front, are indicated by blue squares. The green diamond represents the optimal solution, selected based on its minimal distance from the origin.

Figure 1. Retrieval of 3D aggregate (in yellow) from test image (in Blue)

Input and predicted parameters are as follows,

Input $N = 50$, $k_f = 1.3$, $D_f = 1.8$, Predicted $N = 45$, $k_f = 1.51$, $D_f = 1.81$, $D_m(\text{in}) = 183.61$ nm, $D_m(\text{out}) = 183.42$ nm

CONCLUSIONS

The multi-objective optimization-based retrieval process improves the accuracy of retrieving aggregates by ensuring better alignment with both 2D projected features and 3D aerosol properties. The algorithm demonstrated strong performance, with predicted fractal parameters

showing less than 10% error. It was also successfully tested on SEM images. The method is tested for aggregates with point-contacted monodispersed monomers and aggregates with polydisperse and overlapped monomers.

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INFLUENCE OF THE DIWALI FIREWORKS FESTIVAL ON THE PROFILE OF MICROPLASTICS IN THE ROAD DUST OF MEGACITY DELHI

SNEHA SHEKHAR¹, SAYANTAN SARKAR¹

¹School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IIT, Mandi, Kamand, HP, 175005

KEYWORDS: Microplastic (MPs); Firecrackers; Diwali; Morphological characteristics; Microscopy

INTRODUCTION

Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants in the ecosystem, and risks associated with MPs in terms of health, climate and ecology are directly linked to their physiochemical properties. Given the large and diverse nature of their emission from various land-use practices in metropolitan cities, the potential impacts of MPs on city scales may potentially be more harmful than anticipated. In urban environments, road dust is considered an optimal indicator of environmental quality. It not only acts as a sink of pollutants (e.g., MPs) transported by other environmental media (Dehghani et al., 2017) but can also act as a source via re-suspension leading to inhalation exposure. However, in the Indian scenario, there exists a significant knowledge gap in terms of understanding the distribution and physiochemical properties of MPs in road dust, especially in polluted megacities, which are typically high-emission and high-exposure regions. This study reports the first field-based measurements of MP distribution and morphological profiles in the road dust of megacity Delhi. A special focus here is on a short-term high pollution episode, namely, the Diwali celebration due to its possible influence on MP levels in road dust through the combustion of firecrackers, which are known to contain plastic material along with other constituents (Kotnala et al., 2021).

METHODS

Road dust sampling was conducted in Azadpur (light industrial zone), Dwarka (commercial zone) and Patel Nagar (residential zone) from 21st to 29th October 2022 between 12 AM and 7 AM. The sampling period was divided into three phases: pre-Diwali (21st-23rd October), during Diwali (24th-26th October), and post-Diwali (27th-29th October). Composite road dust samples were collected in each sampling phase from 3 points (1 m²) at each site using a clean spatula and were stored in glass reagent bottles. Samples were sieved through a 5 mm and 1 mm sieve to eliminate particles > 5 mm and to obtain a homogenous mixture, respectively. Around 2.5 g of the processed air-dried soil was weighed and placed in a glass beaker, where 20 ml H₂O₂ was added for digestion (5 days), followed by the addition of 80 mL saturated ZnCl₂ solution ($\rho = 1.80 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$). After leaving it undisturbed for 1 week, the ZnCl₂ solution was filtered through pre-fired (baked at 550°C for 6 h) QMA 47 mm diameter filters (Whatman) using a glass filtration equipment and then vacuum dried with ethanol (99 vol%). The abundance and size of MPs were determined by analyzing 1/8th of the filter stained with Nile red dye (1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) in a fluorescence microscope (Nikon Corp., DTGTTAL SrGHT). Morphological features were determined by analyzing 1/8th of the filter in an optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse LV100POL) and via scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Nova Nano SEM 450).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The average concentration of MPs (<2-1000 μm) before, during, and after Diwali was $109 \pm 53 \text{ MPs g}^{-1}$, $179 \pm 59 \text{ MPs g}^{-1}$ and $144 \pm 65 \text{ MPs g}^{-1}$ respectively. The MP concentration

for three selected periods across sites were as follows: Patel Nagar (67.2 MPs g⁻¹) < Dwarka (92.8 MPs g⁻¹) < Azadpur (169.6 MPs g⁻¹) for pre-Diwali, Patel Nagar (131.2 MPs g⁻¹) < Dwarka (160 MPs g⁻¹) < Azadpur (217.6 MPs g⁻¹) for Diwali, and Dwarka (70.4 MPs g⁻¹) < Azadpur (166.4 MPs g⁻¹) < Patel Nagar (195.2 MPs g⁻¹) for post-Diwali. In terms of size, the shift of MPs from 0-10 μm and 10-20 μm size in pre-Diwali samples towards a higher size range, i.e., 20-30 μm and 30-40 μm in the Diwali samples was associated with enhanced firework activity. Around 99% of the MPs were fragments possibly owing to combustion of firecrackers during the Diwali period and from tyre particle separation in the other periods. Varying colors of MPs such as red, blue, black, and orange were noticed, out of which black was predominant, possibly indicating burnt firecracker particles. Also, SEM images (Fig 1 (e) and (f)) revealed a greater degree of surface roughness in terms of flakes, fractures, and grooves for the Diwali samples, possibly induced by firecracker combustion, as compared to the pre-Diwali and post-Diwali samples which exhibited relatively smooth surface texture. Such surface abrasions can elevate the chances of adsorption of harmful metals such as Ba, As, Co, Pb, Zn, Fe, etc. from the road dust onto the MP surface. Moreover, MPs, because of their low density can conglomerate in dust particles and undergo re-entrainment. The inhalation and ingestion of such road dust-derived MPs disseminated through the air can lead to health impacts.

Fig. 1. Fluorescence images of MPs (a, b); Optical images of MPs (c, d); and SEM images of MPs (e, f) for pre-Diwali and Diwali samples.

Fig. 2. Percentage contribution of MP sizes (left), and MP abundance (MP g⁻¹) for the pre-Diwali, Diwali and post-Diwali samples.

CONCLUSIONS

An increase of almost 60% in MP abundance was observed between pre-Diwali (109 ± 53

MPs g⁻¹) and during the Diwali (179 ± 59 MPs g⁻¹) phase in the road dust of megacity Delhi. A higher number of black MPs in the size range of 20-30 μm and 30-40 μm suggested emission from the combustion of Diwali fireworks. Also, the degraded textures of MPs in the firework-dominated samples could elevate the adsorption of metals, thereby increasing the toxicity by multifold and potentially leading to lung-related issues upon inhalation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

IIT Mandi for funding, and the Advanced Materials Research Center for providing instrumentation facilities.

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CHARACTERISATION OF POLY-AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (PAHS) IN TOTAL SUSPENDED PARTICULATES IN AN URBAN AREA OF NEW-DELHI, INDIA

SHWETA RUHIL^{1,2}, SAKSHI AHLAWAT^{1,2}, SHOBHNA SHANKAR³, RANU GADI³,
TUHIN KUMAR MANDAL^{1,2}

¹ Environmental Sciences & Biomedical Metrology Division, CSIR National Physical Laboratory, Dr. K S Krishnan Road, New Delhi 110012, India

² Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research (AcSIR), Headquarters CSIR-HRDC Campus, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh-201002, India

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, deterioration in air quality has been a global concern as the pollutants often exceed the permissible limits set by WHO and CPCB of India, leading to several health problems and affecting the environment¹. Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) matter are widely distributed particles having a broad range (0.005 to 100 μm) and compositions including Poly-Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), which are chemically stable hydrocarbons with more than two benzene rings and are potent carcinogens, mutagens and teratogens. Long-term exposure to high PAHs in the atmosphere, they can enter the lungs' alveoli via inhalation, and be absorbed into the blood circulation, leading to severe diseases such as cardiovascular and respiratory, ultimately increasing mortality and morbidity rate³, therefore this present study undertook sentinel monitoring of 16 PAHs present in the TSP samples and sources are identified.

STUDY SITE AND METHODS

Ambient air sampling was carried out at CSIR-NPL, located in New Delhi, a metropolitan city of North India having semi-arid climate. A total of 20-TSP samples were collected using a portable TSP sampler during Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 for 8 hrs (10:00-18:00), using Pall Tissue-Quartz fibre filter. After sampling, collected samples were weighed and concentration was calculated in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The method in “determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in TSP samples by using gas chromatograph (Shimadzu, GC-2010 Plus) system, equipped with an Rtx-5 molecular sieve column of 0.25 μm thickness. The sample filter was extracted using 15 ml Dichloromethane (DCM) using ultrasonicator for 30 min. The extracted sample was then reduced to 1ml using the rotary evaporator at 30-40°C and then filtered out using PVDF membrane filter of 0.5 μm pore size, afterwards transferred into gas chromatography amber vials for further analysis in GC. It detects 16 PAHs listed by US-EPA [naphthalene (Nap 2 ring), acenaphthylene (Acy 3 ring), acenaphthene (Ace 3 ring), fluorene (Flu 3ring), phenanthrene (Phe 3ring), anthracene (An 3 ring), fluoranthene (Flt 4 ring), pyrene (Pyr 4 ring), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA 4 ring), Chrysene (Chr 4 ring), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF 5 ring), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF 5 ring), benzo[a]pyrene (BaP 5 ring), indeno[1,2,3-cd] pyrene (IcP 6 ring), dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DBA 6 ring), and benzo[g,h,i]pyrene (BghiP 6 ring)]. The calibration curve was obtained for all PAHs standards for the quantification.

SOURCE APPORTIONMENT TECHNIQUE

The DR (diagnostic ratios) method was used to qualitatively identify principal pollution sources of PAHs based on the characteristic ratios.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Over the study period i.e., from mid-February to mid-April, 2024, the TSP concentration in ambient air ranged from 207.29 to 465.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a mean mass concentration of $307.07 \pm 72.12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, of which concentration of April, 2024 is highest ($389.25 \pm 48.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). TSP concentration of all the 20 samples collected exceeded the 24-hour ambient air quality standard level of Suspended Particulate matter (SPM), according to the CPCB 2009 guidelines. The concentration shows a large standard deviation which shows the heterogeneity in local sources and their contribution in TSP concentration. Fig 1 shows the concentration of all samples collected during the study period. PAHs constitute a minute fraction of TSP concentration and are classified as carcinogens; it is important to understand the concentration range. The $\sum\text{PAHs}$ concentration, over the study period, ranged from 19.49 ± 1.9 to $148.6 \pm 8.9 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ over New Delhi during Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 of which Chr is the most abundant and Acy is the least. The 16 PAHs are divided into three classes based on the aromatic ring structure, 2-3 rings PAHs, mainly present in the gas phase; 4 rings

FIG 1: CONCENTRATION OF TSP SAMPLES IN $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ IN THE AMBIENT AIR.

FIG 2: PERCENTAGE CONTRIBUTION OF PAHs RING TO THE TOTAL PAHs CONCENTRATION IN THE AMBIENT TSP

PAHs present in solid and gas phases and 5 or 6 rings PAHs distributed in the solid phase of TSP, out of which 4- ring PAHs accounts in the maximum amount, followed by 6-rings and 2-3 ring PAHs, represented in FIG 2.

For the identification of sources present in the TSP, we have considered eight characteristic molecular diagnostic ratios. Calculations are performed to infer the indicative sources (highlighted) based on the ratios and are enlisted in Table 1.

TABLE 1: DIAGNOSTIC OF DIFFERENT PAHs IN THE AMBIENT AIR TSP IN DELHI

DIAGNOSTIC RATIO	PRESENT STUDY RESULT	RATIO RANGE	SOURCES	REFERENCES
InP/(InP+BghiP)	0.36	< 0.2 0.2–0.5 > 0.5	Oil source Liquid fossil fuel combustion Coal and biomass combustion	Wu et al. (2024)
BaA/(BaA+Chr)	0.45	< 0.2 0.2–0.35	Oil source Oil or combustion	Wu et al. (2024)

		> 0.35	sources Combustion source	
BaP/(BaP+Chr)	0.34	0.73 >0.35	Gasoline Traffic emissions	Pandey et al. (1999)
Phth/(Phth+Anth)	0.42	<0.7 >0.7	Biomass burning Fossil fuels	Kavouras et al. (1999)
BaP/BghiP	0.81	<0.6 >0.6	Non traffic Traffic	Pandey et al. (1999)

CONCLUSION

- The TSP concentration in ambient air ranged from 207.29 to 465.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a mean mass concentration of $307.07 \pm 72.12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, of which the concentration of April, 2024 is highest ($389.25 \pm 48.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), the variation was possibly due to the change in the meteorological conditions.
- The $\sum\text{PAHs}$ concentration, over the study period ranged from 19.49 ± 1.9 to 148.6 ± 8.9 New Delhi during Mid-February to Mid-April, 2024 of which Chr is the most abundant and Acy is least.
- The diagnostic ratio method results revealed the different PAH origin sources and biomass burning, traffic emissions, diesel engine, liquid fossil fuel combustion were the main sources of pollution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Author (AR) would like to acknowledge University Grant Commission (UGC) for providing the financial support as Junior Research Fellowship.

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OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PM_{2.5} EMISSIONS FROM LIGHT-DUTY GOODS & HEAVY-DUTY VEHICLES IN ON ROAD OPERATIONS IN INDIA

MOHD SHAHZAR KHAN AND GAZALA HABIB

Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Department of Civil Engineering, New Delhi – 110016

KEYWORDS: On-Road Vehicular Emissions, Black Carbon, Mass Absorption Cross-Section.

INTRODUCTION

The on-road transport sector is one of the important sectors that contributes to urban air pollution and affects climate change and human health. Diesel-powered vehicles are dominant fuel consuming vehicles in Indian on-road fleet responsible for particulate emissions (Pandey and Venkataraman, (2014)). Tailpipe emissions of diesel vehicles consist of carbonaceous aerosol including particulate matter and light-absorbing carbon. Mass emission and its composition from vehicle tailpipe depend on many factors such as type of fuel, vehicle technology, maintenance and driving characteristics. Jaiprakash and Habib, (2017) suggested that the tailpipe emissions from laboratory (chassis dynamometer) and model studies are significantly different from emissions measured through on-road measurement. Aerosol absorption and scattering properties such as mass absorption cross-section (MAC) and mass scattering coefficients (MSC) play an important role in regional climate assessment. Therefore, in present study, the real-world mass absorption cross-section and mass scattering coefficient from exhaust emissions of light-duty (goods) and heavy-duty vehicles (Trucks and tractors) will be presented in Indian on-road conditions.

METHODS

On-road measurement of emissions from light motor vehicles (LMV)-goods, tractors and trucks were performed in real world conditions in West Bengal and Bihar using versatile source sampling system (VS3). In VS3, a fraction of exhaust entering through an isokinetic particle sampling probe into a dilution tunnel designed for homogenous mixing, negligible wall losses and complete aerosol quenching. A turbulent and instantaneous mixing of exhaust with 40-60 times zero air inside the dilution tunnel exhibits the dilution process that happens in the atmosphere. Portability, low power requirement and continuous clean air supply are other important attributes of VS3 for its on-field use. The emission measurements were conducted on rural roads and highways with vehicles of different emission norms on a 15-30 km mixed traffic route daily followed by the driver. PM mass was collected on different filter substrate for gravimetric and chemical analysis. The particle absorption and scattering were measure with 7-wavelength aethalometer (AE33) and Nephelometer (IN102) respectively. The carbonaceous fraction of PM_{2.5} was determined on Quartz filter using Thermal optical reflectance analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

BC and EC concentration in the vehicle exhaust were found in the range of 5000-40000 µg/m³ for the tractors, LMV-goods and trucks. A correlation plot was made for BC and EC concentration as shown in figure 1 and found a good correlation between them with R² value of 0.97. Mass absorption cross-section (m²/gPM_{2.5}) was presented in a box plot as shown in figure 2 for tractor, LMV-goods and truck. MAC value was found higher for tractor (1.4-10.4) and truck (4.4-8.3) as compared to LMV-goods (0.8-5.3) due to having lower concentration of BC for LMV-goods. Variation of MAC for tractor, LMV-goods and truck of different

emission norms on rural roads and highways will be discussed in the paper. Mass scattering coefficients will also be discussed in the paper for the same vehicle categories.

Figure 1. Correlation plot for black carbon and elemental carbon concentration in exhaust for all set of experiments of tractor, LMV-goods and truck vehicles.

Figure 2. Mass absorption cross-section for tractor, LMV-goods and truck for all set of experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

The mass concentration of EC determined from TOR method have shown good correlation with BC obtained from aethalometer (Figure 1). The mass absorption cross section of particles emitted from truck and tractor were higher than those from LMV-good (Figure 2). A strong dependence of MACs on vehicle age has been observed. The finding from this study has implications in climate assessment and framing the policies for on-road use of vehicles for improving local air quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change under the NCAP-COALESCCE project {Grant No.14/10/2014-CC (Vol. II)}. The views expressed are solely those of authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Min-istry. The Ministry does not endorse any products or commercial ser-vices mentioned in this publication.

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THEME 6 : AEROSOL INSTRUMENTS

CHARACTERIZATION OF AEROSOLS AT LEH IN THE HINDU KUSH HIMALAYAN REGION USING GROUND-BASED SKY RADIOMETER OBSERVATION

S. NINGOMBAM¹, S. MUKHOPADHYAY¹, A.K SRIVASTAVA², S. JORPHAIL³ AND DORJE ANGCHUK³

¹Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Bangaluru, India,

²Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, New Delhi, India,

³Indian Astronomical Observatory, Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Leh, India

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Microphysical, Sky Radiometer, SKYRAD, PACK

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, tiny particles suspended in the atmosphere in solid or liquid form, are difficult to characterize both temporally and spatially due to their short residing time and geographically diverse sources. Due to such variation and inhomogeneity, classification or characterization of aerosols become a challenging task in the region where there are limited spatial and temporal high-resolution aerosol measurements. According to the Hindu Kush Himalayan (HKH) Monitoring and Assessment Program (HKHMAP), there is a large gap of data over the most sensitive region of HKH (i.e., north-western Himalaya, Karakoram, Ladakh) region in particular (Sanjay et al. (2017)).

Due to the urgent requirement for enhancement of aerosol measuring station in the HKH region, the current works reported about aerosol classification at the Indian Astronomical Observatory (IAO), Raman Science Center, Leh (34.15 N, 77.56 E, 3441 m amsl) town in Ladakh region using direct solar irradiance and diffuse sky radiance measurement by a sky radiometer (POM-01L, Prede). Further, the current study of aerosol classification at Leh is supposed to be the first of such kind using high-resolution ground-based observation.

METHODOLOGY

The instrument measures direct and diffuse sky irradiance at seven discrete wavelengths (315, 400, 500, 675, 870, 940, and 1020 nm). However, for aerosol studies, we excluded 315 nm and 940 nm. The raw data are reduced using Skyrad.pack (version 4.2) software and its observing protocol described by Nakajima and Tanaka, 1986, Ningombam et al., 2015). The input parameters used in the aerosol classification are fine-mode aerosol optical depth (500 nm) and single scattering albedo (440 nm) under the threshold method of aerosol classification (Ningombam et al., 2024; Dumka., 2020). The main aerosol types under the threshold methods are dust, absorbing and non-absorbing aerosols, and mixture.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Aerosol classification at Leh is dominated by absorbing or BC with 42% from the 1935 dataset during July-October 2023. The mixture of aerosol types at Leh is 32%, while non-absorbing and dust aerosols contribute by 23% and 2%, respectively as seen in Figure 1(b). Further, average values of AOD (500 nm) and Extinction Angstrom Exponent (EAE) at Leh are 0.09 ± 0.03 and 1.03 ± 0.26 , respectively during the observing season. The dominance of absorbing aerosol at Leh is also supported by the bi-modal distribution of aerosols as seen in Figure 1(a).

Figure 5 Typical example of aerosol size distribution (a), showing strong bimodal type from fine and coarse mode aerosols during July-August 2023, and (b) aerosol classification at IAO-Leh using Sky radiometer observation during July-October, 2023.

CONCLUSION

Aerosol classification at Leh is found to be dominated by absorbing or BC aerosols with 42%, followed by a mixture of aerosol types with 32%, while non-absorbing and dust aerosols are contributed by 23% and 2%, respectively. The average values of AOD (500 nm) and Extinction Angstrom Exponent (EAE) at Leh are 0.09 ± 0.03 and 1.03 ± 0.26 , respectively during the observing season, July-October, 2023.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank Prof. Annapurni Subramaniam, Director in the Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Bangalore, for the kind support and continuous encouragement during the study period. The authors are thankful to all the Staff of IAO-Leh, namely Tashi ThseringMahay, Tsewng Dorje, Phuntsok Dorje, Tashi Pambar, Tsewang Phunchok, Vivek Kumar and others who had provided significant effort during observation in the high-altitude mountain terrain and harsh climatic conditions. Authors, SM, SSN, AKS and DA thank the Ministry of Earth Sciences, Government of India for providing financial support under the project grant number: MoES/16/02/2021-RDESS.

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INTEGRATED ELECTROSPRAY AND IONIZER SYSTEMS FOR ENHANCED AIR CLEANING APPLICATIONS

H. D. RAWATE¹, R. PARVEEN¹, A. KHAN², M. JOSHI²,
R. M. THAOKAR¹ & Y.S. MAYYA¹

¹Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Department of Chemical Engineering, Mumbai

²Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Electrospray, IONIZER, Aerosol, Air Pollution.

INTRODUCTION

The exposure of large populations to air pollution calls for the deployment of control technologies in both residential and industrial settings. Currently, filtration and electrostatic capture-based technologies are commonly used for air cleaning. These have both advantages and limitations. Among filter-less options, electrospray technology emerges as a promising alternative for air pollution control. Laboratory studies, conducted at BARC (Singh et al., 2021) and IITB (Thaokaret al., 2022), along with other international research efforts (Tepper et al., 2007), have demonstrated the feasibility of this concept. In this study, we have investigated the viability of the electrospray techniques in mitigating the aerosol levels. In addition, we have conducted a comparative study of aerosol mitigation between electrosprays and ionizers as well as a hybrid technique involving both.

METHODS

Custom setups were developed for electrospray and negative ion chambers in the experiments. The negative ion chambers used commercial brush-type negative ion generators (AC220V/50Hz input; DC 5.0-6.5 kV output) inside 5-liter plastic boxes with air intake, venting, and sampling openings. Air passed over ten generators and exited through the sampling inlet, exposing it to negative charges. The electrospray setup, made of acrylic, had converging, and diverging sections to maintain stable flow. A pin-to-plate assembly featured a copper plate at the bottom and a 0.2 mm needle at the top, fed by a syringe pump (750 μ L/h), with a DC voltage supplied by an Agilent function generator and amplified to 5 kV. The copper plate was grounded, and voltage was applied to the liquid flow. Particle characterization used a Grimm 1.108 optical particle sizer (OPS) at the outlet. Baseline particle counts were recorded before activating the electrospray, which was then used to assess particle removal efficiency.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. Particle removal efficiency in multi-needle systems at D = 2.5 cm, FL = 750 μ L/h, V = 5 kV, and FA = 0-5 + 1.2 LPM.

System	Flowrate	0.30 μ m	0.40 μ m	0.50 μ m	0.65 μ m	0.80 μ m	1.00 μ m	2.00 μ m	Total
1 Needle	1.2+0	60.6	62.9	63.4	66.1	70.5	65.3	59.9	61.2
	1.2+2	38.8	41.2	44.9	47.2	39.0	42.2	22.9	39.6
	1.2+5	18.0	18.1	17.4	16.2	29.1	28.5	46.6	18.0
	1.2+0	68.2	67.7	69.2	69.0	70.7	76.6	94.9	68.2

2 Needle	1.2+2	28.1	28.3	30.5	30.8	33.0	39.8	55.2	28.2	
	1.2+5	23.7	25.4	27.1	33.8	26.0	17.1	5.7	24.3	
		1.2+0	67.8	69.8	70.9	69.8	71.9	81.7	92.9	68.3
3 Needle	1.2+2	42.7	42.6	45.6	48.0	51.1	57.0	76.7	42.8	
	1.2+5	29.9	30.8	33.2	33.6	35.8	41.2	63.6	30.2	

Abbreviations: D-Tip to plate distance; V-Voltage; FL-Liquid flowrate, FA-Air flowrate.

Experiments were conducted at varying airflow rates (FA) from 0 to 5 LPM with systems using one, two, and three needles in stable cone-jet mode configurations. Results showed that increasing airflow decreased aerosol reduction efficiency due to reduced residence time of particles in the spray region. Additionally, experiments indicated that adding more electro-spray units can sustain high particle aerosol reduction efficiency even at elevated airflow rates. For example, at 6.2 LPM, particle removal efficiency was 18%, 24%, and 30% for one, two, and three units, respectively. The detailed results of size-wise removal efficiencies for different numbers of needles are shown in Table 1.

A comparative study has been made with conventional negative ionizers, electro-spray and a hybrid arrangement using room aerosols at an airflow rate of 1.2 LPM. The hybrid arrangement consists of a negative ion generator chamber followed by an electro-spray setup. This arrangement was chosen based on the hypothesis that the air would be facilitated with a negative charge in the ionizer chamber first, and then passed through a positively charged electro-spray, resulting in excellent particle capture rates. Results (Fig.1) showed that the ionizer and electro-spray alone had particle removal efficiencies of 56% and 60%, respectively, while the hybrid unit achieved an impressive 83%. These findings highlight the effectiveness of hybrid technology in mitigating aerosol pollution

Figure 1. Normalized Particle Count vs. Time in Electro-spray, Ionizer, and hybrid systems.

CONCLUSIONS

On the whole, the introduction of multiple electro-spray units significantly enhances overall effectiveness, particularly at higher airflow rates. While the ionizers and electro-sprays have similar performance, their integration in hybrid mode improves particle removal efficiency, achieving an impressive 83% in hybrid configurations. These findings support the potential

for hybrid technologies to effectively mitigate aerosol concentration, paving the way for more efficient aerosol reducing systems in various applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Board of Research in Nuclear Science under Sanction no. 59/14/11/2022-BRNS/34062

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TIME-OF-FLIGHT MASS SPECTROMETRY FOR AIR QUALITY MEASUREMENTS: MOBILE VOC MONITORING ON VEHICLE AND AIRCRAFT PLATFORMS

R. RAMISETTY¹, H. ALWE¹, M. ABOU-GHANEM², A. KOSS²,
O. EL HAJJ², AND V. POSPISILOVA¹

¹TOFWERK, Thun, Switzerland, ²TOFWERK USA, Boulder, Colorado, USA

KEYWORDS: Mobile Monitoring, Air Quality, Source Apportionment, Odor Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and volatile inorganic compounds (VICs) are released into the atmosphere from both natural and anthropogenic sources, significantly impacting air quality and posing risks to human health and the environment. Concentrations and fluctuations reveal critical insights into their emission sources, transport pathways, and atmospheric fate. Using fast, sensitive instrumentation and mobile laboratories enables real-time analysis of emissions and their spatial distribution, supporting the identification of point sources and providing essential data for air quality modelling and public health research. Time-of-flight (TOF) mass spectrometers are an ideal tool for air monitoring, as they can measure and track trace levels of VOCs and VICs with high sensitivity and speed, offering real-time insights into air quality and emission sources. TOFWERK's TOF instruments provide precise, simultaneous detection of numerous compounds at sub-parts per billion (ppb) levels, making them crucial for accurate monitoring of air toxics. Here, we present TOFWERK's Vocus chemical ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometers (CI-TOF-MS) as an effective air quality management tool. TOFWERK Vocus instruments provide high sensitivity and instantaneous analysis of VOCs and VICs, with a compact and energy-efficient design suited for mobile air quality monitoring applications.

METHODS

This study utilizes two separate deployments to showcase the capabilities of TOFWERK's CI-TOF-MS instruments. In the first section, landfill emission monitoring was performed using a mobile laboratory van equipped with two Vocus CI-TOF-MS instruments, the Vocus Eiger (PTR Reactor) and Vocus B (Aim Reactor), was deployed near three solid waste landfills in Colorado (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Top: Schematic view of the Vocus mobile laboratory. Bottom: working principles of Vocus B Aim reactor (left) and the PTR Reactor used on the Vocus Eiger and Elf (right).

Each instrument is designed with specialized reactors, PTR and Aim, to target specific compounds, including hydrocarbons, oxygenated molecules, and chlorofluorocarbons. Additionally, custom-developed software integrated data from these mass spectrometers with a Picarro H₂S and CH₄ analyzer and meteorological data from a weather station, enabling real-time data analysis. The second deployment for methane source apportionment by aircraft during an aircraft campaign in the Colorado Front Range used the Vocus Elf, which also employs the PTR reactor, but employs a different TOF to the Vocus Eiger. This area contains more than 40,000 active oil and natural gas wells, along with concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs), making methane source identification complex. The Vocus Elf was used to identify VOC signatures and differentiate methane sources based on pollution plumes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In the landfill emission monitoring study, combined data from the two CI-TOF-MS instruments identified a range of emissions from the landfills, including hydrocarbons, oxygenated molecules, and chlorofluorocarbons. The custom software enabled the integration of meteorological and chemical data, allowing for the precise attribution of emissions to specific landfill sources.

To identify methane source apportionment by aircraft, the Elf PTR-TOF successfully distinguished methane sources across the Colorado Front Range. VOC signatures were used to differentiate between methane emissions from oil and gas wells and agricultural practices. The instrument's ability to resolve VOC compositions within individual plumes allowed for precise source identification even in geographically overlapping emission zones, offering critical insight for regulatory compliance.

Figure 2. a) Methane mixing ratios in ppb overlaid onto a Google Earth image of a flight taken over the Colorado Front Range and b) mixing ratios in ppb of methane (grey), acetic acid (blue), ethanol (orange), and toluene (yellow), as well as the aircraft's altitude (red) as a function of time. Some of these VOC combinations have been previously reported near CAFOs by Yuan et al (2017), which suggests the methane observed in this region originates

from agricultural sources.

CONCLUSIONS

TOFWERK's Vocus CI-TOF-MS and Elf PTR-TOF instruments have demonstrated their capabilities in accurately detecting and attributing VOC and VIC emissions in both stationary and mobile monitoring setups. The integration of these advanced mass spectrometers with meteorological data and other analyzers enables comprehensive air quality assessment. These findings highlight the potential for these instruments to improve air quality management and support regulatory efforts in methane emissions monitoring and landfill emission control.

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CUTTING-EDGE OPTICAL DEVICE FOR MEASUREMENTS OF PM10, PM2.5 AND AEROSOL SIZE DISTRIBUTION

M. PESCH, D. BECKMANN

Grimm Aerosol Technik gmbh, Vordere Aue 4, 06774 Muldestausee, Germany

KEYWORDS: Optical Aerosol Measurement Device, PM10, PM2.5, Aerosol Size Distribution, En16450

INTRODUCTION

Optical measurements of aerosols are becoming increasingly important. The advantage is that the size and concentration of the aerosol are not changed by the non-contact and fast measurement using light. Furthermore, optical measuring devices enable a high temporal resolution of up to seconds and measure different fine dust fractions such as TSP, PM10, PM2.5 and PM1 as well as the size distribution of the particles continuously and simultaneously in real time.

EDM 280-NEW OPTICAL AEROSOL MEASUREMENT DEVICE

With the EDM 280, Grimm Aerosol Technik GmbH has developed a cutting-edge optical measuring device that is designed for the continuous measurement of aerosols. The EDM 280 has been developed for high time -resolved continuous measurements of particle mass fractions and aerosol size distribution. Applications are mainly in the field of measurement networks from local authorities but also for research objectives such as source apportionment of PM10 and PM2.5. The front view of the device is shown in figure 1. The structure of the device is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 6: EDM 280 - optical aerosol measurement device Figure 2: Structure of EDM 280

① The EDM 280 is designed for installation in a measuring container with roof feed-through (figure 2). The sampling system consists of a sample tube ② with sampling head ③ and meteo sensor ④, a roof flange with rain protector ⑤ and inside the water separator ⑥ and sample tube holder ⑦. The measuring insert ⑧ is mounted in the rack under the sample tube holder and connected to the sampling unit in just a few steps. The sample air ⑨ is drawn in via the Sigma-2 sampling head ③ and fed vertically via the sample tube for sample air conditioning into the optical measuring cell. The intelligent heating in the sample tube for drying the sampled aerosols is actively controlled so that no condensation can occur on the path of the aerosol to the measuring cell and, at the same time, the heating of the aerosol is kept as low as possible.

MEASUREMENT PERFORMANCE

By using a powerful laser diode and a multiplex mode of the laser power, particle sizes in the range from 0.178 μm to 29.1 μm can be determined simultaneously and precisely. Thanks to the unique full-flow analysis of the optical measuring cell, both extremely low concentrations ($< 0.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM10) and very high concentrations (up to $100 \text{ mg}/\text{m}^3$ PM10) can be reliably determined. The device has been thoroughly tested by the German TUV and has passed all tests both in the laboratory and in the field. It meets all the requirements of EN 15267, EN 16450, and VDI 4202-3. Even with a time resolution of 1 minute the EDM 280 would fulfill all requirements given by EN 16450. The comparison to the gravimetric reference for PM10 is given in Figure 3. All in all, more than 300 data sets were taken at different measurement sites (traffic, urban, industrial, rural) and seasons. The difference to the reference sampler (Low volume sampler, Leckel SEQ 47/50-RV) is less than 2 % for all data. The same measurement results have been achieved for PM2.5 as well.

Figure 3: PM10 Intercomparison of EDM 280 and the gravimetric reference (low volume sampler Leckel SEQ 47/50-RV)

The EDM 280 is meanwhile in operation at different customer sites worldwide. The comparison to gravimetric samplers at different types of sites (traffic, urban, rural, industrial) as well as for different gravimetric samplers (low and high-volume samplers) show, that the offset of a linear regression was most often in the range of $\pm 2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and the slope in the range of 0.9 to 1.1 without any local corrections or factors. The average for PM10 of all sites gives values for the offset of 0.024 and for the slope of 1.008 (for PM2.5 0.193 and 1.035). The data evaluation also show the importance of a correct set-up of the devices at the measurement site: a free ambient air flow from all directions to the sampling inlets for gravimetric sampler and optical device must be guaranteed and the sampling inlet height should not differ more than approx. 20 to 30 cm.

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TRACEABLE CALIBRATION OF THE AEROSOL ABSORPTION COEFFICIENT

L.DRINOVEC^{1,2,3}, T. MÜLLER⁴, T. BÜHLMANN⁵, M. GARCIA⁵, T. HAMMER⁵, K. VASILATOU⁵, P. SEBANC³, L. CMOK³, I. DREVENŠEK³, J.YUS-DÍEZ¹, E. WEINGARTNER⁶, J. SATURNO⁷, K. ELEFThERiADiS⁸, E. ASMI⁹ AND G. MOČNIK^{1,2,3}

¹Center for Atmospheric Research, Univ.of Nova Gorica, Nova Gorica, Slovenia

²Haze Instruments d.o.o., Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁴Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig, Germany

⁵Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology (METAS), Berne-Wabern, Switzerland

⁶University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland, Windisch, Switzerland

⁷Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Braunschweig, Germany

⁸National Centre of Scientific Research “Demokritos”, Athens, Greece

⁹Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Absorption Coefficient, Black Carbon, Light -Absorbing Aerosols, Filter Absorption Photometer, Photoacoustic Spectrometer, Photothermal Interferometer.

INTRODUCTION

Only few direct methods for in-situ aerosol absorption measurement exist. Photothermal interferometers measure the change of the refractive index caused by light absorption in (and the subsequent heating of) the sample. The change of phase in the interferometer is proportional to the aerosol absorption coefficient (Moosmüller & Arnott, 1996; Sedlacek, 2006). The detection is linear and can be traceably calibrated to first principles (Drinovec et al., 2022). In-situ absorption instruments use different calibration schemes, usually NO₂ is used for calibration in the visible range. Particles, on the other hand, allow calibration without wavelength limitations. Water soluble nigrosin is a candidate calibration material, forming spherical particles when nebulized. Mie calculations are used to determine absorption coefficients. Calibration with monodisperse aerosols provides lower uncertainties compared to polydisperse ones.

METHODS

We compare different calibration schemes in light of their measurement uncertainty and ease of implementation. Aerosol absorption was measured with a photothermal interferometer PTAAM-2λ (Haze Instruments). NO₂ calibration was performed using an SI-traceable mobile reference gas permeation generator based (METAS), pre-prepared NO₂ mixtures in cylinders or ambient NO₂. Monodisperse nigrosin was selected from the nebulized sample using a centrifugal particle mass analyser (CPMA, Combustion) and an electrostatic classifier (EC 3082, TSI) in series (Fig. 1), removing multiply charged particles and neutral particles from the sample stream. Particle number concentration was quantified using a condensation particle counter (CPC 3750, TSI).

Figure 1. Experimental setup.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results and a comparison with the Mie model monodisperse nigrosin aerosols are shown in Fig. 2. The Mie calculation is based on measured particle number size distribution, measured nigrosin refractive index and either on particle mobility diameter (SMPS) or mass-derived diameter (CPMA). Error bars represent method uncertainty. The Mie model using the mass derived diameter shows better agreement with the measurements.

Figure 2. Monodisperse nigrosin – measured and modelled absorption coefficient at 450 and 808 nm.

CONCLUSIONS

Measuring aerosol absorption for climate and source apportionment studies is not easy due to various instrumental measurement artefacts. The calibration, traceable to primary standards, is crucial for the quantification of the anthropogenic impact on the environment. While filter photometers are easy to use, the data they produce is difficult to interpret in environments with high single-scattering albedo. The linearity and traceable calibration position multi-wavelength PTI is an excellent candidate for the reference method to measure the aerosol absorption coefficient, as illustrated by laboratory and ambient measurements in contrasting environments.

The traceable calibration of the direct aerosol absorption coefficient measurement allows for further calibration of filter photometers and validation of external assumptions, such as the multiple-scattering parameter (Yus-Díez et al., 2021).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

(Co)funding from EUROCHAMP (H2020, 730997), ATMO-ACCESS (H2020, 101008004), SNSF (200021_172649), EUROSTARS (4825, 11386), ARRS/ARIS (P1-0385, P1-0099, I-0033), EMPIR (Black Carbon, AeroTox) and EURAMET/European Union (stanBC, 22NRM02) is gratefully acknowledged.

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MEASUREMENT PROPERTIES AND CALIBRATION OF CEN-COMPLIANT GRIMM SMPS+C AND CPC

M. PESCH, G. STEINER, F. TETTICH AND D. BECKMANN

Grimm Aerosol Technik gmbh, Vordere Aue 4, 06774 Muldestausee, Germany

KEYWORDS: UFP, Particle Count, Particle Size Distribution, CEN-CPC, CEN-SMPS

INTRODUCTION

The latest air quality guideline published by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) clearly points out the danger of air pollution to human health and, in this context, also points out for the first time the danger posed by ultrafine particles (UFP, particles $< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$).

In the "Green Deal" of 2019, the European Commission committed itself to further improving air quality and aligning EU air quality standards more closely with the recommendations of the WHO. In a preliminary agreement on the revision of the European Air Quality Directives, the mandatory determination of the particle number and particle number size distribution of UFPs will therefore be introduced in addition to the established PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} measurements.

EUROPEAN DIRECTIVES

The European directives prEN 16976:2024 and CEN/TS 17434:2020 described how harmonized and traceable measurements of these two metrics can be carried out in outdoor air using the currently available measurement methods. The guidelines not only specify the performance characteristics of the measuring instruments to be used, but also describe in detail the calibration and testing methods to be used. It can be assumed that other regions in the world will follow the European requirements.

COUNTING EFFICIENCY

The directives envisaged that butanol-based condensation core counters (CPC) with a D₅₀ of 10 nm will be used to determine the particle number concentration. A typical counting efficiency of a GRIMM CPC with a D₅₀ of 10 nm is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Typical counting

CPC calibrated according to prEN 16976:2024 with a D₅₀ at 10 nm and a D₉₀ < 20 nm such measurements.

efficiency curve of a GRIMM

DETERMINATION OF THE PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION

To determine the particle size distribution, mobility particle size spectrometers (MPSS, SMPS+C) can be used, which in turn use CPCs as detectors and cover at least the size range from 10 – 800 nm. To check CEN conformity, CPC measurements can be carried out with silver aerosol in GRIMM's own calibration laboratory (see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 2. Typical linearity curve of a GRIMM CPC calibrated according to prEN 16976:2024 versus reference Faraday Cup electrometer. The slope of the regression line should be within $\pm 10\%$.

PERFORMANCE CHECK

A check of the performance data of the GRIMM CEN SMPS+C can be carried out by a direct comparison against a reference MPSS (e.g. TROPOS) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Comparison of the particle size distribution of a GRIMM CEN SMPS+C versus TROPOS reference MPSS

The figure also shows that the accepted uncertainty (grey range) is much higher for particles below 20 nm. The reason for that is that with smaller sizes the charging probability of the particles strongly decreases. Less ions produced by the neutralizer of the SMPS device are on the surface of the particle and the calculation of the total particle number is therefore more biased for smaller sizes.

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ADDRESSING DISCREPANCIES IN PARTICULATE MATTER MEASUREMENTS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OPTICAL PARTICLE COUNTERS AND GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ACCURACY IMPROVEMENT

A. BUWANIWAL¹, M. JOSHI², V. SHARMA¹, G. ARSHAD KHAN²
AND B. KAUR SAPRA²

¹ Department of Physics, Maharaja Ranjit Singh Punjab Technical University, Bathinda

²Radiological Physics and Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Ambient Air, Particulate Matter, Density, Refractive Index

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) concentration measurements play a vital role in air quality monitoring, but discrepancies between instruments challenge data reliability. Gravimetric techniques are widely regarded as the most accurate method for monitoring particulate matter (PM) mass concentration; however, they do not provide real-time analysis. To address this limitation, Optical Particle Counters (OPCs) are frequently employed in field and indoor campaigns. It measures number concentration by assuming a uniform refractive index across all size ranges. This is then converted to mass concentration using a correction factor (C Factor) and an assumption of uniform particle density. While these factors are validated for known aerosols in controlled environments, they remain untested for open, ambient conditions (Buwaniwal A et al.,2024). This study examines how variations in aerosol density and refractive index affect OPC accuracy. The study also includes the measurement of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ aerosol density and refractive index by different approaches.

METHODS

Size-segregated PM mass and number concentration measurements have been carried out using PM₁ Sampler, PM_{2.5} sampler, PM₁₀ sampler and Optical Particle Counter. PM Samplers are gravimetric technique-based instruments which filter desirable atmospheric particulates based on the impactor's cutoff size placed at its inlet. Optical Particle Counter (OPC) is used in this study to monitor mass and number concentration from 0.25 μ m to 32 μ m. Controlled experiments have been performed to analyse the impact of aerosol density on the discrepancies in the OPC estimated PM mass concentration using desired chemical solutions (e.g., 0.5% Sodium Chloride, Potassium Iodide, Lead Nitrate, and Ammonium Sulphate).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

This study compares OPC-estimated mass concentrations to gravimetrically measured values for PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀, using data from outdoor samples collected in Bathinda City, Punjab, India from January 2022 to November 2023. Results indicate significant discrepancies between the two methods, with gravimetric-to-OPC mass concentration ratios of 1.42 ± 0.77 for PM₁₀, 0.99 ± 0.51 for PM_{2.5}, and 1.17 ± 0.58 for PM₁, with more than half of the samples outside the 0.8-1.2 range as shown in Figure 1. Factors contributing to these discrepancies, such as variations in aerosol density, shape, and refractive index, are explored, revealing that the constant density value assumed by OPCs (1.6 g/cm³) does not accurately represent ambient conditions. The discrepancies have been verified using controlled experiments by examining the results for four know chemicals (Ammonium

Sulphate, Sodium Chloride, Potassium Iodide, and Lead Nitrate). The study also introduces two ways of measuring PM density- firstly using accurate PM mass and number concentration as shown in Figure 2 and secondly, using chemical composition. The mean densities of sampled data from April 2021 to November 2023 for PM1, PM2.5, and PM10 has been found to be $1.71 \pm 0.92 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $1.43 \pm 0.60 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and $1.51 \pm 0.86 \text{ g/cm}^3$, respectively. Further, the average densities calculated using atmospheric composition is found to be $1.7 \pm 0.30 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for PM10 and $1.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for PM2.5. Similarly, the refractive index calculated using the atmospheric composition for PM2.5 ranges from $1.68 \pm 1.36i$ to $1.00 \pm 0.42i$, while for PM10 it ranges from $1.53 \pm 2.42i$ to $0.40 \pm 0.60i$, indicating substantial day-to-day variation in the atmospheric density and refractive index. In the absence of clear guidelines and protocols, the study suggests ways to improve the accuracy via periodic measurement of the correction factor and/or incorporating calibration factors in

Figure 1: Frequency distribution plots of C factor, PM1-C, PM2.5-C and PM10-C ratios

Figure 2: Day wise variation in PM1, PM2.5, and PM10 real aerosol density in comparison to OPC density

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a comprehensive exploration of the inconsistencies found in the OPC

mass measurements. A significant role of aerosol density and refractive index in the deviation from accurate concentration has been determined using controlled experiments. The deviation has been found lowest for the lowest density aerosols which was observed to increase with the increase in density. The intercept observed between aerosol density and deviation indicates the influence of the refractive index as well. The methodologies included in this study to calculate accurate size segregated aerosol density and refractive index using chemical composition and using the accurate mass and number concentration data gave almost the same results. The study also suggests two ways of improving data accuracy, one is incorporating the calibration factor and another is modifying the periodic correction factor. In conclusion, this research emphasizes the critical need for other approaches to calculate real time measurement of mass concentration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Board of Research in Nuclear Science-Department of Atomic Energy (BRNS-DAE), GoI for providing financial assistance (Project Sanction No. 51/14/02/2020-BRNS/36091) and MRSPTU, Bathinda, Punjab for providing necessary facilities to carry out the research work.

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ENHANCING THE ACCURACY OF LOW-COST SENSORS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS TO ASSESS INDOOR AIR QUALITY EXPOSURE

Y. DAHIMA¹, A. VAISHYA^{1,2}

¹School of Arts and Sciences, Ahmedabad University, Ahmedabad – 380 009, India.

²Global Centre for Environment and Energy, Ahmedabad University, Ahmedabad – 380 009

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality, Low-Cost Sensors, Machine Learning, Particulate Matter Exposure.

INTRODUCTION

The “State of Global Air” report estimated that poor air quality caused 8.1 million deaths in 2021, with 58% linked to outdoor PM_{2.5} exposure and 38% to indoor pollution. Measuring indoor particle concentrations is crucial as people spend most of their time indoors. Conventional high-end instruments for continuous indoor monitoring are impractical due to their bulk (15-30 kg), high costs (₹5-30 lakhs), and maintenance needs (Castell et al., 2017). Thus, affordable and portable optical PM sensors offer a viable alternative though the accuracy of these low-cost sensors (LCS) may suffer when ambient RH exceeds 50%, causing PM_{2.5} overestimation due to hygroscopic particle growth (Zamora et al., 2019). Zimmerman (2022) recommends choosing simple and interpretable data correction methods; hence, we applied multiple linear regression (MLR) for correcting PM_{2.5}. While previous research on indoor air quality exposure primarily focuses on classrooms, commercial buildings, and homes (Kabirikopaeiet al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020), our research highlights the need for more research in higher education institutions, especially in indoor environments other than classrooms, which are underexplored in India.

METHODS

The Purple Air (PA) devices were employed in this study to measure PM_{2.5} concentration and meteorological parameters. Each device contains a PMS5003 optical sensor, based on light scattering, for PM measurements and a BME280 sensor for meteorological variables. Reference measurements for LCS data correction were obtained using a Met One - Beta Attenuation Monitor1020 (BAM) which determines PM_{2.5} mass through beta-ray attenuation on a filter tape. It is recognized as a “Federal Equivalent Method (FEM)” by the US EPA. PA devices were co-located with the BAM for approximately 10 weeks between November 2023 to January 2024. Both datasets underwent quality control checks, and PA data were averaged at 1-hour intervals for comparison. Comparison metrics included mean absolute bias (MAB), root mean squared error (RMSE), and Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r). The PM_{2.5} data from each sensor were corrected using the following equation (Nilson et al., 2022):

$$\text{corrected PM}_{2.5} = (\text{raw PM}_{2.5} \times a) + (\text{RH} \times b) + c \quad (i)$$

Constants a, b, and c were evaluated by linear regression (least squares method) using the machine learning library sci-kit-learn, minimizing RMSE between BAM and corrected LCS data. Sensors were deployed across various locations inside a university campus for one semester (winter 2024), representing different indoor microenvironments –with active emission sources (e.g., cafeteria, workshop) and without sources (e.g., library, classroom). We estimated time-weighted daily mean PM_{2.5} exposure for students under three scenarios based on different times spent in these spaces, hypothesizing that exposure varies by occupancy in different microenvironments. We assumed students spend most of their time in the library and lounge in Case 1; cafeteria, library, and laboratory in Case 2; and cafeteria, laboratory, and

fabrication workshop in Case 3 to estimate exposure variation based on their occupancy in different microenvironments.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Comparing uncorrected sensor data with reference data indicated that the sensors overestimate PM_{2.5} as RH rises. Hence, we applied RH-based correction, which improved the accuracy of sensor data: MAB decreased from 9.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 6.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, RMSE from 13.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 10.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and r² rose from 0.92 to 0.93.

Figure 1. Violin plots showing distribution of daily exposure (Left). Bar plots showing average contribution of various microenvironments of the university campus to daily exposure over a semester (Right).

Figure 1 shows students' PM_{2.5} exposure throughout the semester across different scenarios. Confined indoor environments without active emission sources showed better air quality, likely due to isolation from ambient air. However, areas with active emission sources showed elevated PM_{2.5} levels, raising health concerns. In the first two cases, daytime mean PM_{2.5} exposure peaked around 30-40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 90-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while in the last case, it was 30-40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 110-120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a bit higher than the previous two cases due to active emission sources present in those spaces. Semester-long average exposure ranged from 45-60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Spending extended time in microenvironments with active emission sources increases students' exposure to particulate pollution. Optimized combustion and improved ventilation could enhance air quality in such indoor spaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The RH-based correction significantly improved the accuracy of sensor PM_{2.5} data, reducing both MAB and RMSE. Our analysis further revealed that students' exposure to particulate matter heavily depends on the type of indoor microenvironment. Indoor environments without active emission sources showed better air quality, while those with emissions posed higher exposure risks. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions, such as efficient combustion and enhanced ventilation, to mitigate the adverse effects of indoor air pollution and protect occupant health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by Ahmedabad University via its Start-up grant (URBSASI20A1). Yash Dahima is supported as a PhD student by Ahmedabad University via University

Assistantship. The authors are grateful to the university administration for assistance during the deployment of sensors on the university campus.

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EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF PARTICLE COMPOSITION ON THE ACCURACY OF LOW-COST PM SENSORS

M. ZAID¹, V. SAHU¹, P. NAWALE AND M. SAHU^{1,2,3}

¹Aerosol and Nanoparticle Technology laboratory environmental Science and engineering department Indian Institute of Technology Bombay Mumbai 400076, India

²Interdisciplinary Program in Climate studies Indian Institute of Technology Bombay Mumbai

³Centre for Machine Intelligence and Data science IIT, BombayMumbai 400076, India

KEYWORDS: Low-Cost Particulate Matter Sensors, Purpleair PA-II, OPC_N3, Correlation, Particle Composition.

INTRODUCTION

The development of light-scattering-based low-cost particulate matter sensors (LCPMS) has opened new possibilities for understanding air pollution variations at high spatial and temporal resolutions. However, the data quality issues have limited the large-scale application of LCPMS (deSouza et al., 2022; Malyan et al., 2022). Therefore, to overcome the data quality issues, Previous studies largely relied on field calibration by comparing mass concentrations with standard instruments (BAM- Beta Attenuation Monitor) without considering the particle size, composition, and sensor type. The optical properties of particles, such as size and shape, play a crucial role in influencing both the intensity and angle of scattered light (Gramsch et al., 2021). Hence, there is a need to understand the performance of LCPMS with different particle compositions. This study evaluated the performance of two LCPMS - PurpleAir PA-II (nephelometry principle) and OPC-N3 (optical particle counter principle), alongside particle composition analysis.

METHODS

The LCPMS (PurpleAir PA-II and OPC-N3) collocated with the Scientific Carbonaceous Aerosol Speciation System (CASS), a combination of a Total Carbon Analyzer and an Aethalometer, alongside the X-ray Fluorescence (PX375) Spectrometer. The LCPMS recorded PM mass concentration at 2-minute intervals, while CASS recorded elemental carbon (EC), organic carbon (OC), and total carbon (TC) at hourly intervals. The PX375 measured the elemental composition of PM_{2.5} at hourly resolution. Data was collected from April to June 2024 at the IIT Bombay campus. The dataset was resampled to hourly averages, and pre-processing steps, including the removal of null values and outliers, were implemented to ensure data quality and reliability for the analysis. Correlation analysis (R) was conducted to evaluate the performance of both LCPMS (PA-II and OPC-N3) across different PM_{2.5} composition ranges.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Purple Air (R=0.56) and OPC-N3 (R=0.53) sensors showed moderate correlation with the BAM. It was found that the LCPMS overestimated PM concentration for the period when RH > 70%. Previous studies also reported that the LCPMS data was significantly affected at higher RH because of the hygroscopic growth (Kumar & Sahu, 2021). The elemental

composition of PM_{2.5} showed that Al-Aluminium had the highest contribution (42.46%), followed by Si-Silicon (19.33%) and other components like K-Potassium (14%) and S-Sulphur (10%) as shown in Figure 1. Al and Si were found to be the major source of natural dust (Gramsch et al., 2021). These results indicate that dust particles contributed significantly to the overall particulate matter. It was found that OPC-N3 outperformed Purple Air PA-II for aluminium concentrations above 100 ng/m³ (R=0.74 vs. R=0.11), similar trend was observed for silicon particles above 40 ng/m³ (R=0.61 vs. R=0.48). In contrast, Purple Air PA-II was found more sensitive at lower aluminium levels below 100 ng/m³ (R=0.71 vs. R=0.48) (Figure 2) and for silicon particles below 40 ng/m³ (R=0.76 vs. R=0.47). For Elemental Carbon (EC), Purple Air PA-II performed better at concentrations above 2 µg/m³ (R=0.61 vs. R=0.31), while OPC_N3 was more effective at lower EC concentrations (R=0.68 vs. R=0.14).

The findings suggested that OPC-N3 is more accurate for measuring coarse particles (dust) due to its ability to measure individual particles. Whereas the Purple Air PA-II measures a cloud of particles and is more sensitive to fine particles. Purple Air PA-II has limited efficiency for detecting coarser particles (dust) due to its blockage of the forward-scattered light and its limited ability to pass coarse particles into the device.

Figure 1. PM_{2.5} Elemental composition

Figure 2. LCS accuracy assessment with PM_{2.5} composition

CONCLUSIONS

Both the Purple Air PA-II and OPC_N3 sensors have valuable strengths in particulate matter monitoring, though their performance is affected by high relative humidity (RH) and varies based on pollutant concentration and composition. The finding of this study suggested that OPC_N3 is better suited for detecting coarser (dust) particles, whereas Purple Air PA-II is more sensitive to finer particles and combustion-related pollutants. Therefore, it is crucial to choose an appropriate sensor combination for covering the range of particles and their source. This study enhances the understanding of the capabilities and limitations of low-cost sensors for effective air quality monitoring.

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APPLICATION OF LIDAR IN ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH: CLOUD DETECTION IN FOOTHILLS OF HIMALAYA

C. PRAKASH, N. SINGH AND A. KUMAR

Aryabhata Research Institute of Observational Sciences (ARIES), Manora Peak Nainital

KEYWORDS: Lidar, Remote Sensing, Atmospheric Profiling, Cloud Detection, CALIPSO.

INTRODUCTION

LiDAR an acronym of Light Detection and Ranging, also known as LASER Radar plays a crucial role in atmospheric science research. LiDAR remote sensing is being widely used in atmospheric research due to its ability to provide precise, high-resolution measurements of various atmospheric properties. The application of LiDAR in atmospheric research has led to innovations in the design and development of devices, as well as improvements in the accuracy and scope of data collection. The High Energy Pulse LIDAR (HEPL) system has been installed at ARIES, Nainital for probing the atmosphere and to analyse the Mie scatterers. Aerosol and clouds have been detected in the foothills of central Himalayas using HEPL.

METHODS

The major applications of LiDAR in atmospheric science are i) Atmospheric profiling: to profile the atmosphere, measuring parameters such as temperature, pressure, humidity and aerosol content at different altitudes, ii) Cloud and aerosol detection: LiDAR is highly effective in detecting and characterizing clouds and aerosols (fine particulate matter suspended in the air). It allows researchers to study cloud formation, types, and their radiative properties, iii) Monitoring Greenhouse Gases and Pollutants: LiDAR has been instrumental in detecting and monitoring concentrations of Green House Gases (GHGs) like CO₂ and methane, as well as pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and sulphur dioxide (SO₂), iv) Weather Forecasting and Climate Modelling: LiDAR helps improve weather forecasting models by providing real-time data on wind profiles, cloud properties and aerosol distributions. ARIES is located in the foothills of central Himalayas, where the anthropogenic emission is minimal. This region is most suitable for the study of the troposphere and to study the vertical distribution of aerosol in the boundary layer. We have installed the High Energy Pulse LiDAR at ARIES Nainital to study the different atmospheric constituents and clouds in the boundary layer, troposphere and many more parameters in other layers of the atmosphere. The High Energy Pulse LIDAR (Fig. 1) has been operated at 532 nm wavelength at pulse widths (PW) of 200 ns, 1 μ s, and 2 μ s respectively. The LiDAR Observations have been taken starting from twilight hours to midnight to investigate the vertical structure and optical properties of the aerosol layers and clouds.

Data was collected from November 2020 - to December 2021 and showed the variations in the height coverage range of the measurement. The narrow laser beam i.e., 200 ns pulse provides the observations with high resolution and short dead zones but less height coverage (~ 2 km), while the observations with wide laser beam i.e. 1 μ s and 2 μ s pulse widths demonstrated height coverage up to 9 km. High-resolution observations provide important information on the aerosol masses and transport sources while low-resolution observation is suitable for boundary layer evolution and related mechanisms.

Figure 1 Block diagram of ARIES High Energy Pulse LIDAR

We have detected the presence of low, middle and high-level clouds. The atmospheric aerosol profile is observed up to about 3 km vertical resolutions as seen in the Fig. 2. The aerosol subtypes have been obtained using the CALIPSO satellite observations. These results verify the functionality and the response of the HEPL system to the required atmospheric conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The HEPL system mainly operated in Mie mode, using the Cassegrain type receiver telescope to conduct the intermittent nocturnal observations. Higher aerosol loading has been found in the lower troposphere (~ 3.5 km), indicating the vertical mixing through boundary layer processes and orographic influences. Observations recorded with different pulse widths demonstrated that a 200 ns pulse provides a clearer depiction of the above-ground mixing within the lower most regions up to about 2.5 km, while a 1µs pulse can offer reliable profiles up to ~ 5 km vertically. Vertical atmospheric profiling on different occasions revealed the presence of low, middle, and high-level clouds. The observed clouds are generally stationary or occasionally moving patches found in mostly clear sky conditions. Such observations could enhance cloud classification, supporting the data of satellites like CALIPSO, within the region. Overall, aerosols and cloud presence strongly affect astronomical observations conducted over this site, and these LIDAR observations can be utilized for both atmospheric and astronomical studies across the data void region of the central Himalayas.

Fig. 2: LIDAR Observation of Cirrus Cloud at an Altitude above 6 km over the Site. The lower panel displays feature flags and aerosol subtypes obtained from the CALIPSO satellite on 26th December.

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**THEME 7: AEROSOL, AIR QUALITY MODELLING AND ITS
IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH**

OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF SUMMERTIME PM_{2.5} OVER THE WESTERN HIMALAYAS

ADITI RANA¹, PREYAS PRABHAKARAN², SAYANTAN SARKAR¹

¹School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IIT, Mandi, Kamand, Himachal Pradesh

²School of Physical Sciences, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

KEYWORDS: DTT ASSAY; Hydroxyl Radical (\bullet OH); Surrogate Lung Fluid (SLF); Himalayas

INTRODUCTION

PM_{2.5} can have adverse impacts on human health due to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as H₂O₂, \bullet OH, and \bullet O₂⁻. An increase in ROS causes an imbalance in the – oxidant-antioxidant system and leads to inflammation and cell death (Liu et al., 2022). Various chemical assays are available for assessing the oxidative potential (OP) of atmospheric PM, and among them, the dithiothreitol (DTT) assay is closely linked to various health outcomes (Bates et al., 2019). However, limitations exist in the DTT assay since it only detects \bullet O₂⁻ generation (Xiong et al., 2017) and does not provide information on the generation of \bullet OH which can lead to an underestimation of oxidative stress. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate both oxidative potential (OP) and \bullet OH generation from PM due to their harmful effects on cellular components (Xiong et al., 2017). When evaluating oxidative stress, surrogate lung fluid (SLF) is more physiologically realistic (Wu et al., 2021; Charrier and Anastasio, 2011) than conventional techniques that employ methanol or aqueous extracts; however, very limited research has been done on the measurement of OP of ambient PM_{2.5} using SLF. This study therefore aims to evaluate oxidative stress generated by PM_{2.5} under realistic conditions using SLF, with a primary focus on OP and \bullet OH production during the summer season in the western Himalayas.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} samples were collected at Kamand (31.78° N, 76.99° E), a rural location situated in the western Himalayas. Samples were collected on pre-baked (550°C for 5 h) quartz filters (Whatman QMA, 20.32 cm × 25.4 cm) using high-volume PM_{2.5} samplers (Ecotech HiVol 3000, flow rate: 67.8 m³ h⁻¹) for a duration of 12 hours, i.e., daytime (7 AM to 7 PM) and nighttime (7 PM to 7 AM). A total of 30 samples were collected (day=15, night =15) for the summer season (March-May 2023). The antioxidant solution was freshly prepared daily for experiments, containing 200 μM L-ascorbic acid sodium salt, 300 μM citric acid, 100 μM reduced L-glutathione, and 100 μM uric acid (Charrier and Anastasio, 2015; Cross et al., 1994). Patches of 5 cm² from PM_{2.5}-loaded filters were ultrasonically extracted in 10 ml of SLF for 30 minutes and subsequently filtered through 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters for \bullet OH and DTT assays, with a parallel process conducted for blank filters. The procedure for DTT was as described by Sharma et al., (2024). The procedure for \bullet OH assay was as per Wei et al., (2019) and Wu et al., (2021), which were modified slightly without altering the ratios of the quantities of extracts and reagents.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The average OP_v and \bullet OH_v values for the summer season were 0.25 ± 0.13 nmol min⁻¹ m⁻³, and 0.0084 ± 0.002 nmol m⁻³ respectively. Similar values of \bullet OH_v were observed by Shen et al. (2022) in Los Angeles for the summer and winter seasons (0.0039 ± 0.0013 and $0.006 \pm$

0.22 nmol m⁻³, respectively). In contrast, higher OPv (3.94 ± 1.01 nmol min⁻¹ m⁻³) was observed by Wu et al. (2022) for the winter season in Shanghai. The summer average production of •OHv (1.006 ± 0.201 nmol m⁻³) for a 2-hour reaction time aligned with the findings of Rastogi et al. (2022) for Meghalaya. A minor difference was observed in the day-night values of OPv (0.23 ± 0.13 and 0.28 ± 0.12 nmol min⁻¹ m⁻³) and •OHv (0.009 ± 0.002 and 0.008 ± 0.001 nmol m⁻³), respectively, with no significant variability (t-test, $p > 0.05$). Sources contributing to oxidative stress might include biomass burning for cooking purposes, emissions from stationary sources, and mineral dust (Scott et al., 2019; Hara et al., 2023). The SO₄²⁻/NO₃⁻ ratio serves as an indicator of emission sources, distinguishing between stationary (>1) and mobile sources (<1) (Gao et al., 2018). At the study site, the SO₄²⁻/NO₃⁻ ratio during the summer season was 2.7, which signified a dominance of stationary source emissions, possibly transported over regional distances. Also, summertime intrusion of mineral dust from the west of the study location (Thar desert in India, and arid regions in Pakistan, Iran, Afghanistan, Iraq and Saudi Arabia) could have contributed to the observed oxidative potential. This is supported by a significant correlation of •OHv with Fe ($r = 0.51$, $p < 0.01$) and Mn ($r = 0.47$, $p < 0.01$). Both Fe and Mn, which are principally sourced from mineral dust, are known to exhibit redox-active characteristics (Vidrio et al., 2009; Li et al., 2019). Furthermore, the formation of ROS may be enhanced in the presence of Fe, with ascorbic acid acting as a pro-oxidant (Charrier and Anastasio, 2011).

A moderate correlation between PM mass and OPv ($r = 0.37$, $p < 0.05$) and OHv ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$) indicated that species contributing significantly to PM mass were also responsible for DTT depletion and •OH generation. A significant correlation ($r = 0.36$, $p < 0.05$) was observed between OPv and •OHv (Fig. 1a) similar species were responsible for the two oxidative endpoints. Biomass burning, both in the form of forest fires (4024 instances of forest fires in 2022-23 summer), and residential biomass fuel use (>90% of households utilizing ~1.46 kg capita⁻¹ day⁻¹ of fuelwood for daily activities; Kumar et al., 2015), could be responsible for ROS generation and the oxidative activity of PM at this site. The significant correlation of DTT depletion and •OHv generation with nss-K⁺, a tracer of biomass burning ($r = 0.53$, $p < 0.01$ and $r = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$), indicates as such (Fig. 1b, d) (Hudson et al., 2004).

Fig. 1. Correlation between (a) OPv and •OHv, (b) OPv and nss_K⁺, (c) •OHv and Fe and (d) •OHv and nss_K⁺

CONCLUSIONS

The study reported oxidative potential and •OH generation values at a western Himalayan site to be comparable to other rural/remote locations across the world. Based on the association of oxidative stress metrics with established tracers (nss-K⁺, Fe and Mn), biomass burning potentially from forest fires and residential fuel use and the summertime influx of transported mineral dust could have contributed to the oxidative capacity of PM at this location. Secondary evidence also indicated a potential role of transported emissions from stationary

sources in constraining OP levels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

IIT Mandi for funding, and the Advanced Materials Research Center for providing instrumentation facilities.

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UNLOCKING THE SECRETS OF VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS: SOURCE ATTRIBUTION & HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT AT SUBURBAN SITE OF TAJ CITY

N. BAGHEL¹, S. KIRTI¹, A. SATSANGI¹ AND K. M KUMARI¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh

KEYWORDS:Health Risk Assessment, Positive Matrix Factorization, Source Apportionment.

INTRODUCTION

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are essential precursors of O₃ formation in the atmosphere and are hazardous to human health and ecosystems (Li et al., 2022, Wang et al., 2024). VOCs are emitted from both natural (biogenic) and anthropogenic sources into the atmosphere. Plants are the primary sources of biogenic VOCs (BVOCs), which are considered the most significant source of VOCs globally and they have a significant impact on the formation of O₃ (Li et al., 2022). Numerous studies have demonstrated that the ratio of biogenic to anthropogenic VOC emissions is 9:1 (1000 Tg C year⁻¹: 110 Tg C year⁻¹) (Liu et al., 2024). The formation of O₃ and SOAs are strongly associated with the sources and the chemical reactivities of VOCs which are initiated by reaction with OH. radical (Zhan et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The sampling was carried out on the roof of the science faculty at a height of 12 meters at the campus of Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra (27.16° N, 78.08° E). Online sampling of VOCs was carried out using the Air-Server unit attached to the Gas Chromatograph- Mass Spectrometer. The VOCs were analysed using thermal desorption on a Thermal Desorption Unit (TDU) with UNITY-Xr and Air Server-XR (Markes International Limited) coupled with a Gas chromatograph (GC) (Agilent) equipped with a Mass selective detector MSD (Agilent 5977B GC-MSD/FID (Agilent Technologies, USA).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The concentrations of VOCs ranged from 20 to 310 µg/m³ with an average concentration of 152.0 ± 75.2 µg/m³. Toluene was the most abundant species with an average concentration of 32.5 ± 9.6 µg/m³ followed by benzene (24.0 ± 7.6 µg/m³) and least for acetaldehyde (2.8 ± 1.3 µg/m³). The most dominant compounds were aromatic hydrocarbons, which contributed 48.1% followed by alkanes 34.9%, alkenes 7.4%, aldehydes 4.9% and terpenes 4.7%. VOCs showed distinct Seasonal Variation with higher concentration during the winter season (218.2 ± 102.9 µg/m³) followed by post-monsoon (162.5 ± 69.1 µg/m³), summer (132.0 ± 39.2 µg/m³) and monsoon (95.7 ± 40.0 µg/m³). This pattern may be due to the changes in VOC sources, OH radicals and atmospheric mixed states. High concentrations of VOCs during the winter period may be associated with calm conditions and a stable atmosphere due to temperature inversion and low mixing heights which is not conducive to the dilution and diffusion of pollutants. The highest concentration of isoprene was observed in the summer season (5.0 ± 1.6 µg/m³). Isoprene and aldehyde showed a reverse pattern with high values in summer as compared to winter probably because of higher temperature causing greater emission of biogenic VOCs. Further, the higher availability of OH radicals along with high solar radiation facilitates a higher concentration of aldehyde in the summer season due to the

photo-oxidation of VOCs with OH radicals (Mishra et al., 2020).

PMF ANALYSIS

At this site, 4 factor solution was obtained. Factor 1 contributed 33.2% and had high loadings of BTEX which may have originated from vehicular emissions. Factor 2 had a 40.8% contribution of lower VOCs (ethylene, propane, n-butane, iso-butane, iso-pentane, n-pentane, n-hexane and cyclohexane). These species may have been emitted from gasoline evaporation and fossil fuel combustion. Factor 3 contributed 15.5% which constituted biogenic VOCs such as α -pinene, β -pinene and isoprene which may have originated from vegetation, shrubs and trees. This factor had the highest contribution (12.1%) of isoprene followed by β -pinene (9.5%) and α -pinene (9.0%). Factor 4 contributed 10.4%, mainly from formaldehyde and acetaldehyde. These species are mainly generated from photochemical reactions (Liu et al., 2023).

HEALTH RISK

The carcinogenic effect of VOCs for adults and children were calculated by Integrated Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) and non-carcinogenic effect by Hazard Quotient (HQ). ILCR values provide a meaningful indication of risk; a CR value of 10^{-6} indicates the potential cancer risk in terms of individual cases is one person per million people and according to WHO the safe range for cancer is between 1×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-6} . At the suburban site, ILCR values for adults were above the acceptable limit for benzene (1.5×10^{-5}) followed by formaldehyde (2.3×10^{-6}) and lower for the ethylbenzene (5.7×10^{-7}) and acetaldehyde (9.8×10^{-8}). HQ value was under the prescribed value (HQ=1).

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, real-time measurement of VOCs was carried out at suburban sites to determine the chemical composition. The concentrations of VOCs ranged from 20 to 310 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with an average concentration of $152.0 \pm 75.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The most dominant compounds were aromatic hydrocarbons which contributed 48.1% followed by alkanes, alkenes aldehydes and terpenes. Toluene was the most abundant species with an average concentration of $32.5 \pm 9.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. VOCs showed distinct seasonal variation with higher concentration during the winter season ($218.2 \pm 102.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) followed by post-monsoon ($162.5 \pm 69.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), summer ($132.0 \pm 39.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and monsoon ($95.7 \pm 40.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Gasoline evaporation was the main source of VOCs (40.8% followed by vehicular emissions (33.2%), biogenic sources (15.5%), and photochemical (10.4%). Benzene showed a higher ILCR value. The main sources at the present site were emissions from vehicles (diesel, petrol and CNG), biogenic and photochemical generation. These results may provide theoretical support to the local government for the development of VOC emission control strategies in suburban areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is financially supported by ISRO-GBP under ATCTM project and DST-FIST Programme (No. SR/FST/CS-II/2017/38 (C)). The authors are thankful to the Director, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra and the Head, Department of Chemistry, for the necessary help.

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TIME-SERIES MODELLING OF CERES-RETRIEVED UVA, UVB RADIATION & AOD USING SARIMA MODEL OVER THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

ANKITA MALL^{1,2}, ANJALI RANA^{1,2} AND SACHCHIDANAND SINGH^{1,2}

¹Environmental Sciences and Biomedical Metrology Division, CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi-110012, India.

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Headquarters CSIR-HRDC Campus, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh-201002, India

KEYWORDS: UVA, UVB, AOD, SARIMA, CERES

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) is considered a global hotspot, known for its dense population and severe pollution levels. This region is heavily impacted by atmospheric aerosols, which significantly influence the Earth's radiation budget and environmental cycles. This study presents a comprehensive time-series analysis of Ultraviolet A (UVA) and Ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation, as well as Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) using data retrieved from the Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) platform. In reference to the work of Box and Jenkins, the popular Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model was applied to simulate the monthly average CERES products (UVA, UVB and AOD) over the five sites of IGP. It is an extension to traditional ARIMA model by incorporating the two components (seasonal and non-seasonal) to address complex temporal patterns inherent in the data using the historic datasets for the UVA, UVB and AOD parameters from 2005 to 2020 (around 16 years). As a result, the forecast for a 2-year period from January 2021 to December 2022 was done and compared with the original datasets (from CERES, Ground- NPL, Delhi). The forecasted value showed the best modelled results by following the observed trends and structures over all the sites of study. The average values for the next two years (2021-2022) show that UVA flux ranges from 10 to 13 W/m², UVB flux ranges from 0.26 to 0.35 W/m², and AOD varies between 0.45 and 0.83 for all the sites. The actual and predicted values demonstrated a strong fit and exhibited high correlation coefficients for UVA, UVB fluxes, and AOD, with ranges of 0.91-0.97, 0.94-0.99, and 0.82-0.90, respectively. This study not only enhances the understanding of UV radiation variability in the presence of aerosols but also provides a reliable forecasting tool for environmental monitoring in the region. The time series forecasting of UV and AOD serves as a crucial analytical tool for projecting future UV radiation levels and aerosol loading over the IGP.

DATA & METHODOLOGY

For the present study we have used the satellite-retrieved datasets from Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) platform. CERES data products provide the surface derived daily-averaged all-sky UVA (0.32-0.40 μm), UVB (0.28-0.32 μm) and AOD (0.55 μm) with 1°X1° spatial resolution from January 2005 to December 2022 for all the sites. The five stations of Indo-Gangetic plain which have been considered for the present study are Delhi [28.50°, 77.50°], Kanpur [26.50°, 80.50°], Jaipur [26.50°, 75.50°], Lahore [74.50°, 31.50°] and Karachi [24.50°, 67.50°]. The ground measurements of UVA and UVB fluxes have been utilised from CSIR- National Physical Laboratory (NPL), Delhi measurements were used for comparison with modelled data and satellite observations. Statistical tools, including mean

square error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2), were employed to assess the model's adequacy for predicting UVA and UVB fluxes as well as aerosol optical depth (AOD). The SARIMA model is a seasonal univariate modelling approach which has been adapted to forecast UVA, UVB fluxes and AOD over the IGP region of India. Many studies has used the Box and Jenkins ARIMA model (Liu, 1988) the aerosol optical properties over northern India (Kumar et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2022). The SARIMA model has not yet been considered in the study, despite its ability to produce the lowest AIC and BIC values, along with high correlation coefficients and R^2 values. Among the models tested, SARIMA (1,1,1)(1,1,1)12 was identified as the most suitable for predicting UVA, UVB fluxes, and AOD, yielding the lowest mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) across all five sites.

RESULTS & CONCLUSIONS

Time series modelling of the past 16 years CERES retrieved UVA, UVB and AOD measured data from 2005 to 2020 has been used by the SARIMA model for the prediction of the next two years (2021-2022). The CERES-derived, ground-based (NPL, Delhi) and predicted values for UVA, UVB and AOD showed good agreement at all the study sites. The result indicates a high Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) at a 99% confidence interval (with $\alpha=0.01$ and $p < 0.001$) and r^2 values. The correlation coefficients for UVA, UVB fluxes, and AOD between the two datasets ranged approximately from 0.96-0.98, 0.98- 0.99, and 0.82-0.90, respectively, across all stations. Additionally, the R^2 values for UVA, UVB, and AOD ranged from 0.82-0.96, 0.86-0.98, and 0.67-0.83, respectively, for all five sites. The mean bias errors between the CERES-retrieved and predicted datasets for UVA, UVB fluxes, and AOD were found to be within the ranges of -0.3% to 1.3%, 0.6% to 2.7%, and -1.1% to 5.1%, respectively for all stations.

Figure 1. Comparison of CERES-derived, Predicted and Ground (NPL, Delhi) for UVA, UVB radiation and AOD parameters (left side) and regression analysis between the CERES-derived vs. predicted values and CERES-derived vs. ground values for the year 2021-2022 using the SARIMA model at Delhi with the R^2 values and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) for each plot (right side).

The analysis revealed the lowest mean absolute error (MAE) between the two datasets, with values ranging from 0.45-0.66 for UVA, 0.01-0.02 for UVB, and 0.07- 0.10 for AOD. Additionally, the study demonstrated the least root mean square error (RMSE) values, ranging from 0.57-0.85 for UVA, 0.01-0.02 for UVB, and 0.09-0.12 for AOD between the CERES-derived and predicted values across all stations. These results highlight the significance of the SARIMA model for forecasting UVA, UVB, and AOD measurements.

Table 1. The average and standard deviation of CERES-retrieved and predicted values at all five stations for the 2-year duration.

Stations	Measured Value (mean \pm std.)			Predicted Value (mean \pm std.)		
	UVA (W/m ²)	UVB (W/m ²)	AOD (550 nm)	UVA (W/m ²)	UVB (W/m ²)	AOD (550 nm)
Delhi	10.77 \pm 3.2 2 10.00 \pm 2.3 6 (grd.)	0.26 \pm 0. 10 0.24 \pm 0. 08 (grd.)	0.72 \pm 0.16 0.74 \pm 0.20 (grd.)	10.70 \pm 3.22	0.26 \pm 0.10	0.70 \pm 0.21
Kanpur	10.56 \pm 3.1 6	0.26 \pm 0. 10	0.83 \pm 0.15	10.59 \pm 3.09	0.26 \pm 0.10	0.79 \pm 0.18
Jaipur	12.26 \pm 3.0 6	0.31 \pm 0. 11	0.54 \pm 0.17	12.15 \pm 3.07	0.30 \pm 0.11	0.53 \pm 0.19
Lahore	11.01 \pm 3.4 0	0.26 \pm 0. 11	0.50 \pm 0.17	11.01 \pm 3.37	0.26 \pm 0.11	0.51 \pm 0.19
Karachi	13.62 \pm 2.6 6	0.35 \pm 0. 09	0.45 \pm 0.22	13.45 \pm 2.62	0.34 \pm 0.09	0.45 \pm 0.19

The SARIMA (1,1,1)(1,1,1)₁₂ model demonstrated the lowest normalized AIC and BIC values, along with favourable results from both the Ljung-Box and Jarque-Bera tests, indicating a superior fit and robustness in capturing the underlying patterns of the data. This underscores its effectiveness in accurately forecasting UVA, UVB, and AOD measurements. Consequently, APE between the CERES-derived and predicted data ranged from 3.5% to 6.9% for UVA flux, 4.7% to 6.9% for UVB flux, and 12.4% to 19.5% for AOD, highlighting the strong alignment and significance of both datasets.

Figure 2. Comparison of CERES-derived, Predicted and Ground (NPL, Delhi) for UVA, UVB radiation and AOD parameters and regression analysis between the CERES-derived vs. predicted values and CERES-derived vs. ground values for the year 2021-2022 using the SARIMA model at four sites Kanpur, Jaipur, Lahore and Karachi with the R² values and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) for each plot.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Author (AM) would like to acknowledge the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Research and development organisation in India for providing financial support as a CSIR

Fellow (18599).

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MORTALITY RISK ASSOCIATED WITH PARTICULATE MATTER OVER THE ENTIRE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN (IGP)

ADITYA PRAKASH¹, PRADHI RAJEEV¹

¹Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IIT, Patna Bihta, Patna -801106

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Mortality Risk, Exposure Assessment, Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP)

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution due to fine particulate matter (particulate matter less than 2.5 μm ; PM_{2.5}) is a major health concern worldwide, especially in India (Balakrishnan et al., 2019). In the post-monsoon and winter seasons, meteorological conditions favor the confinement of aerosols, leading to higher concentrations of PM_{2.5} in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) (Nair et al., 2007). Scientific research has associated PM_{2.5} exposure with various causes of premature mortality, including ischemic heart disease (IHD), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung cancer (LC) (Bowe et al., 2019). This study investigates transport of particulate matter and associated mortality risk over six states in the IGP to gain insights into their origin and transport, during the most polluted (post-monsoon and winter) seasons. A comparative analysis of PM levels and the mortality risk associated with the PM concentration over the six states (two sites in each state) in IGP has been reported in this study, which will help policymakers to make suitable remedial actions.

METHODS

PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations reported by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) at twelve (12) stations in six states of IGP for post-monsoon (Oct–Nov) and winter season (Dec–Feb) in the year 2022-23 have been utilized in this study. Further, air mass back trajectory analysis (AMBTs) was performed to visualize the trajectory patterns of aerosols at twelve (12) sites over the entire Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP). Across the 12 cities, the total mortality per million exposed population for each city in IGP due to six months of exposure to PM_{2.5} concentrations has been estimated. For estimating mortality, the Integrated Exposure Response (IER) function is used (Burnett et al., 2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The back trajectory analysis suggests that the majority of air masses are of Type 1 (Long-range air mass traversing from Middle-eastern countries) and Type 4 (local air masses) for all the states (as shown in Figure 1 for Punjab). Different patterns of air mass back trajectories are recorded for other states over the IGP.

Figure 1. Five-day air mass back trajectories of Punjab (Type 1: Long-range air mass traversing from Middle-eastern countries; Type 2: Long-range air mass coming from the south-west and traversing through the Arabian sea; Type 3: Long-range air mass traversing through the Bay of Bengal; and Type 4: local air masses).

Due to exposure to high PM_{2.5} concentrations,

premature mortality was calculated using the IER model from October 2022 - March 2023 for 6 polluted states over the IGP. The study was performed for three diseases namely IHD, COPD and LC. Anand Vihar, a site at Delhi documented the highest mortality 2380 for IHD, 1487 for COPD, and 557 for LC according to WHO's limit (Fig 2) followed by Dwarka and Patna. Using the Integrated Exposure-Response (IER) model, it has been found that PM_{2.5} exposure could result in more than 3000 total mortalities per million exposed population in each city per year, according to WHO limit.

Figure 2. Mortality per million exposed population for LC, COPD and IHD as per WHO's limit (10 µg/m³)

CONCLUSIONS

The back trajectory analysis suggests that the majority of air masses are long-range air masses traversing from Middle Eastern countries and the local air masses. The IER model projected more than 3000 premature deaths due to IHD, COPD, and LC for each city in IGP as per WHO's limit. Delhi faces the highest mortality risk (4425 total mortality per million) followed by Bihar > Uttar Pradesh > Haryana > Punjab > West Bengal. IHD (54.3 %) was the primary cause of premature mortality, followed by COPD (33.2 %), and LC (12.5 %). The following study suggests an immediate and collective need to implement mitigation strategies to reduce emissions and protect human health, particularly in most polluted cities of IGP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the support from IIT Patna in completing this study.

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A COMPREHENSIVE DEEP LEARNING APPROACH TO ESTIMATE PARTICULATE MATTER LEVELS FROM SATELLITE DATASETS

VERMA. SUNITA^{1*}, AJAY SHARMA¹, SWAGATA PAYRA² AND MANOJ MISHRA³

¹Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, BHU, Varanasi-221105, UP

²Department of Remote Sensing, Birla Institute of Technology Mesra, Jaipur Campus

³Space Applications Centre, Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), Ahmedabad

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, AOD, MODIS, INSAT-3D

INTRODUCTION

The present work proposes Particulate Matter (PM) estimation using satellite AOD and deep learning algorithm. Two different satellites, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), and INSAT-3D is used to retrieve AOD over a period of 7 years (2014 to 2020) over India. Ground datasets of AOD are taken from the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) for the validation of satellite retrieved AOD (Dey, S., & Di Girolamo, L. 2010).

METHODS

INSAT 3D AOD (Mishra, M. K.,2018). and MODIS AOD (Payra et al., 2015) is validated with ground-observed AERONET AOD at 550 nm. All the satellite and ground data are archived from the time period of 2014 to 2018. Two ground station Jaipur (26.906N, 75.806E) and Kanpur (26.513N, 80.232E). Prior to performing this estimation, a Power Law equation was utilized to harmonize the wavelength of both the satellite data and ground AOD.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Seasonal Spatial Distribution: INSAT-3d vs MODIS

The seasonal spatial distribution of aerosol optical depth (AOD) at a wavelength of 550 nm as observed by INSAT 3D and MODIS for the years 2014 to 2018 are analysed. During the winter season, high concentrations of aerosols are detected by INSAT 3D at the western (Gujrat and Rajasthan) and southern (Karnataka, Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, and Tamil Nadu) parts of India, with approximate values of 1.6, whereas MODIS AOD displays higher values (approx. 1.2) at the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region, encompassing Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. During the pre-monsoon season, both satellite data exhibit aerosol loading at IGP, with INSAT 3D and MODIS showing the highest values of 1.4 and 1.1, respectively. As India experiences widespread rainfall during the Southwest Monsoon season (June – September), the cloud masking algorithm of the satellite removes significant portions of the dataset, leading to a limited number of observations during this period.

CONCLUSIONS

After passing the data from the Machine learning algorithm, PM₁₀ is estimated all over India for the year 2020 shown in figure. We have found that both the satellite products are showing high value over Indo-Gangetic Plain. Similarly, MODIS is also showing high value in central parts of India. Further, the data sets are validated over various locations over India represented in the figure. After validation we have found that estimated PM₁₀ is highly correlating with the ground data provided by CPCB. MODIS shows correlation of 0.78 whereas INSAT 3D shows a correlation of 0.73. Our results are validated over various CPCB station data over India and found that both the satellite INSAT 3D and MODIS are highly

correlating.

Figure 7 Estimated PM10 Spatial distribution of all the satellites used

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The corresponding author would like to express thanks for funding support under the Indian Space Research Organization under the Respond program (ISRO/RES/3/806/19-20) for the financial support

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PREDICTION OF AIR POLLUTION NEAR CONSTRUCTION SITES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF POLLUTANT DISPERSION USING CFD AND AERMOD MODELS

PRASHANT NAWALE¹, AND MANORANJAN SAHU^{1,2,3}, *

¹Aerosol and Nanoparticle Technology Laboratory Environmental Science and Engineering Department Indian Institute of Technology Bombay Mumbai 400076, India.

²Interdisciplinary Program in Climate Studies Indian Institute of Technology Bombay

³Centre for Machine Intelligence and Data Science Indian Institute of Technology Bombay

KEYWORDS: Air Pollution, CFD Modelling, PM Dispersion, Near-Source Prediction

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a serious threat to public health, ecosystems, and the environment, especially in rapidly urbanizing areas. With the expansion of construction activities in urban centres, prediction for pollutant dispersion near construction sites and evaluation of particulate matter (PM) concentration levels is important for better management of air quality near construction sites. The traditional Gaussian dispersion model (AERMOD) is typically used for simple applications without obstacles or complexities. While the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model is used to capture detailed flow dynamics and pollutant dispersion under atmospheric conditions. Therefore, this study focuses on the prediction of PM dispersion from construction sites using both AERMOD and advanced prediction modelling techniques, i.e., CFD under various atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) conditions. The CFD model uses the steady-state Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) approach, incorporating the standard $k-\varepsilon$ (SKE) turbulence model to simulate the complex flow dynamics and pollutant dispersion patterns around construction sites. This approach allows for a more detailed analysis of the velocity field and pollutant dispersion under specified conditions, including the influence of local meteorology.

METHODS

This study uses the data from field sampling campaign conducted by Malyan et al., (2023) in May 2022 at a construction site in IIT Bombay campus. The emission factor for the construction site, with an intensity of $15.6 \mu\text{g/s}$, is based on the USEPA (AP-42) handbook. The average wind speed, wind direction, and atmospheric stability data from a Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Station (CAAQMS) situated within 500 meters of the construction site were also used for setting boundary conditions in the model. A neutrally stratified atmosphere was assumed for the simulation. The wind direction was aligned along the positive X-axis. A reference speed of 0.7 m/s at a 10-meter height. This was integrated into the CFD model using a power law wind profile with roughness parameters set at 0.23. The pollutant dispersion was modelled using the Gaussian dispersion model and RANS-based standard $k-\varepsilon$ (SKE) turbulence model approach. Sensitivity analyses were conducted to optimize the computational mesh, ensuring accurate and stable predictions. Model validation was performed using field measurements of PM concentrations, comparing the simulation results with experimental data.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

The simulation results showed that wind speed increased with height, indicating the typical

urban environment condition, influencing the vertical dispersion of pollutants. The comparison between AERMOD and CFD model predictions revealed a significant difference in pollutant concentration estimations. It was found that the AERMOD consistently overestimated the PM concentrations in the downwind direction, as shown in Figure 1. Whereas, the CFD model is well predicting experimental data, particularly near-construction activities. AERMOD model demonstrating a highly fitting power curve with the equation $y=81759x^{-1.634}$ shows near-construction concentration levels above $60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ within 100 m.

Figure 1. Models' prediction against experimental data near the construction site (CFD conditions: steady-state RANS model (SKE), power law wind profile, neutrally stratified atmosphere).

Results shows that AERMOD accurately predicts pollutant concentrations beyond 100m but overestimates within 100m compared to the CFD model. The CFD model demonstrated better alignment with the experimental data, particularly in capturing the spatial variation of PM concentrations near the construction site. The peak concentration predicted by the CFD model was $\sim 156 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at construction for the earthwork volume rate of $0.1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, aligning well with a source emission of $15.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{s}$. This suggests that the CFD model is more suitable for near-source predictions within 20% uncertainties. It is particularly effective in the downwind direction, where local effects such as construction activities play a major role.

CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive microclimate model was developed within a computational domain to predict particulate matter (PM) concentrations near a construction site. The study compared near-field experimental results with predictions from both AERMOD and CFD models to identify the most suitable approach for pollutant dispersion modelling in urban environments. The results demonstrate that AERMOD tends to predict overestimate pollutant concentrations near the source. Whereas, the CFD model, with its ability to incorporate detailed flow dynamics, provided more accurate and reliable predictions, closely matching experimental data. The findings offer valuable insights for developing better pollution control strategies for improving air quality from the sources. The state-of-the-art 3D digital pollution dispersion model offers significant potential for assessing spatial concentration levels and guiding effective air pollution mitigation measures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their gratitude to Dr. Y. S. Mayya, Chemical Engineering, for his technical support.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF REGULATORY ATMOSPHERIC DISPERSION MODELS FOR ESTIMATION OF ANNUAL AVERAGE CONCENTRATION

ANMOL BATRA, INDUMATHI S IYER, R SHRIVASTAVA AND R.B.OZA

Radiation Safety Systems Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai 400085, India

KEYWORDS: Air Quality, Pollutant Dispersion, GPM, ADMS, AERMOD

INTRODUCTION

Gaseous and particulate pollutants emitted from industrial sources are dispersed into the atmosphere by winds and turbulent eddies. To protect the people and environment from the deleterious effects of air pollutants, several countries and states have issued regulations on the maximum permissible air concentrations of pollutants. To ensure compliance with these limits, atmospheric dispersion models are important tools. This study compares the performance of three such widely used atmospheric dispersion models namely Gaussian Plume Model (GPM) (R.K. Hukkoet.al., 1988), American Meteorological Society-Environmental Protection Agency Regulatory Model (AERMOD) (A. J. Cimorelliet al., 2004) and Atmospheric Dispersion Modeling System (ADMS) (CERC,1998) in estimating annual average concentration for regulatory applications. Despite being Gaussian models, they differ in their requirements of meteorological input and turbulence characterisation.

METHOD

Annual dispersion calculations were carried out for a flat site using routinely collected hourly meteorological data using the three models. To harmonise the input, same basic parameters viz., wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation (SR) and cloud cover (CC) (atmospheric stability class estimated from SR and CC was fed into GPM) were fed as input to the models. ADMS and AERMOD also require air temperature as basic inputs in addition to the above parameters. ADMS and AERMOD models have met pre-processors which additionally consider site characteristics to model the boundary layer parameters that are not considered in GPM. Simulations were carried out with the three models for ground and elevated releases to generate annual average concentration. Surface roughness of the site is one of the mandatory parameters in advanced models which potentially affects the dispersion parameters, mixing height and thereby the pollutant concentration. Hence, the sensitivity of Ground Level Concentration (GLC) to surface roughness length (Z_0) was studied for different land use conditions. The Pasquill-Gifford dispersion parameters used in GPM are based on the Project Prairie Grass experiment (Sawford BL, 2001) where the minimum value of Z_0 was estimated to be 0.006 m. Considering this as the lower range of Z_0 , sensitivity analysis was carried out for flat terrain ($Z_0=0.006\text{m}$), forest region ($Z_0=1.3\text{m}$) and an inland site with average roughness ($Z_0=0.5\text{m}$). Variation of GLC with downwind distance, as estimated from the three models, are analysed and the results are discussed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure-1 is the annual wind rose for the year 2023 at the site which signifies that the site is affected predominantly by winds coming from South West (SSW) and North East (NNE). In order to compare the performance of the models, it was decided to compare the downwind variation of GLC for the plume sectors where GPM yielded the peak concentration in each case. The maximum annual average concentration estimated using GPM for ground and

elevated release was found in the plume sectors SSW and NNE respectively. Accordingly, GLC estimated from the three models are plotted only for these plume sectors for varying surface roughness, in Figures 2 (a) and (b). The difference in the magnitude and distance of peak concentration among the three models can be attributed to the difference in methodology of estimating atmospheric stability, percentage variation of each atmospheric stability category considered by the models, parameterization of horizontal and vertical plume spread parameters (σ_y and σ_z) and treatment of calm and missing hours within the models. It should be noted that in the case of GPM, atmospheric stability is a direct input to the model whereas, AERMOD and ADMS models compute these parameters based on input data and turbulence parameters. As for the effect of surface roughness, it is evident from the figure that GLCs are sensitive to surface roughness. Higher surface roughness causes enhanced turbulence, leading to increased dispersion and decreased GLC. Nevertheless, the effect is more pronounced for ground release as compared to elevated release. The results also suggest that the site studied here can be represented by an average Z_0 of 0.5m corresponding to a site with bushes and numerous obstacles.

Figure 1: Annual wind rose (Calms = 11.64 %)

Figure 2: Variation of maximum GLC for (a) ground and (b) elevated release estimated by GPM, ADMS and AERMOD.

CONCLUSIONS

Given the differences in model approach and results, annual average concentrations over flat terrain can be estimated using any one of the models used in the study. However, the advanced models, ADMS and AERMOD, should be used with utmost care considering their sensitivity to land use parameters and subjective estimation of boundary layer parameters. Meanwhile, GPM can be used with minimal input parameters and without any of the ambiguities of the advanced models.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Shri B. B. Ghorpade of RSSD, BARC for assistance in the measurements of meteorological data.

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A SIZE-SEGREGATED ASSESSMENT OF SUMMER AIRBORNE PARTICULATE MATTER AND ASSOCIATED HUMAN HEALTH EXPOSURE IN A SEMI-URBAN AREA

MUDIT YADAV*, HINDUSH PATNAM, AND SAILESH N. BEHERA

Air Quality Laboratory, Department of Civil Engineering, Shiv Nadar Institution of Eminence Deemed to be University, Delhi-NCR, Greater Noida, India 201314.

KEYWORDS: Gravimetric Method, Size-Segregated Pm, Moudi Impactor, Human Respiratory Tract, Deposition Fraction

INTRODUCTION

Ambient air pollution has become an increasingly serious concern attributed to accelerated urban advancement, economic growth, surging vehicular traffic, coal-operated power, and expanded industrial activities. These activities lead to the emission of various toxic pollutants: Particulate matter (PM) (Ultrafine (PM₁), fine (PM_{2.5}), Coarse (PM_{2.5-10}), and PM₁₀), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), as well as trace gases and heavy metals such as arsenic (As), manganese (Mn), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and nickel (Ni). The higher levels of ambient PM₁ and PM_{2.5} are attributed to several negative environmental consequences, including deteriorated air quality, reduced atmospheric visibility, and affecting the atmospheric radiation balance, which poses significant environmental and health risks (Mangal et al., 2021). Due to their smaller size, these particles can easily enter the deeper part of the human respiratory tract compared to the coarse particles and have a direct relationship with adverse effects on human health and the environment (Zhang et al., 2024). The aim of the present study was to investigate the concentration of size-segregated PM varying from 56 nm to 18 µm and the contribution to total PM, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, and PM deposition fraction in various regions of the human respiratory tract.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Shiv Nadar University, in Delhi-NCR, located at 28.47°N, 77.48°E, and 201, an elevation of 201 m above mean sea level (MSL). The study area exhibits pertinent seasonal variability. In winter, the temperature and relative humidity varied from 4°C - 26°C and 10% - 45%, and in summer, 20°C - 47°C and 30% - 99%. The study was conducted from 15th March to 15th April 2024 in the summer season. To obtain the size-segregated PM concentration, we have employed a Micro-orifice uniform deposit impactor (MOUDI, 110R, MSP Corp, USA) that collects particulates from 56 nm to 18 µm at 10 different sizes of 0.056-0.1, 0.1-0.18, 0.18-0.32, 0.32-0.56, 0.56-1, 1-1.8, 1.8-5.6, 5.6-10, 10-18 µm. We used a quartz filter of 47 mm diameter (Whatman QM-A grade). The Multiple Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) Model was employed to assess the PM fraction in the human respiratory tract; we have used the age-specific lobe-5 model (Madureira et al., 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AVERAGE SIZE-SEGREGATED PM CONCENTRATION

The average PM mass concentration in 11 – different-size bins is represented in Fig. 1a. We observed an unimodal distribution pattern of average PM mass concentration for all the sampling days, with the highest concentration peak in the size range of 1.8 - 3.2 µm, this range represents the particles attributed to settled road dust emissions and construction

activities in nearby places. The average overall PM concentration for all the sampling days is found to be 93.41 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For specific particle size fraction, concentrations of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ were 85.72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 50.29 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 37.56 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio of 0.59 suggests that the concentration of fine particulate is greater than the coarser fraction in PM₁₀, whereas the ratio of PM₁/PM₁₀ is 0.44, confirming that PM₁ constitutes a substantial fraction of the total mass. Ultrafine and fine particles are associated with adverse impacts to human health when inhaled and contribute to atmospheric visibility reduction (Zhang et al., 2024)

HUMAN HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT

Deposition fraction in the human respiratory tract (HRT)

The total deposition fraction in HRT was found to be highest for PM₁₀ (0.93) for inhaled PM, followed by PM_{2.5} (0.66), PM₁ (0.44), and PM_{0.18} (0.51). The regional deposition fraction in each region of the HRT (head (H), tracheobronchial (TB), and pulmonary (P)), the DFs of different sizes of inhaled particles (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, and PM_{0.18}) were simulated and given in Fig. 1b. The PM₁₀ DF through the nasal shows the highest deposition P (95%, highest of all the age groups), followed by TB (4.1%) head (1%) for 21-year old age group, for PM_{2.5} DF was highest found in H (54%), P (40%) and TB (6%) for 21-year old age group, for PM₁ DF were found highest in the H (51%), P (42%), and TB (7%) for 8-year old age group, for PM_{0.18} DF was found highest in the P (69%), head (13%), and TB (18%) for 21-year old age group. Most PM₁₀ was deposited in the top part of the respiratory tract (head), while the smallest fractions also entered deeper airways (TB). The DF varies in each region of HRT with respect to age group. It depends on humans' physiological parameters such as fractional residual capacity, Upper respiratory tract volume, and tidal volume (Madureira et al., 2020).

Fig. 1. (1a) Size-segregated PM mass distribution pattern, (1b). Deposition fraction of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, and PM_{0.18} in head airways, pulmonary and tracheobronchial regions for 03-Months Infants, 8-years children, 21-years adults.

CONCLUSION

The concentration for PM₁₀ (85.72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and PM_{2.5} (50.29 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was noted below the permissible limit of the NAAQS standard. The PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio of 0.59 indicated during the sampling days PM_{2.5} was observed to be higher than PM₁₀. PM_{0.18} and PM_{2.5} were highly deposited in the pulmonary region, followed by head airways, whereas PM₁ and PM₁₀ were highly deposited in head airways for 3 months, 8 years, and 21 years, respectively.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors sincerely thank Applied Research Associates Inc., Raleigh, NC, USA, for providing access to the Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model version 2.11 (<https://www.ara.com/mppd/>)

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MAPPING AIR QUALITY SPATIAL VARIATION OF AN ARID URBAN REGION

SAURABH¹ & D. BHATTU¹

¹Department of Civil and Infrastructure Engineering, IIT, Jodhpur, Rajasthan 342030, India

KEYWORDS: ARID, Mobile Measurement, Spatial Distribution.

INTRODUCTION

Urban air pollution, driven by industrialization, rapid urbanization, and anthropogenic activities, shows high spatiotemporal variability in the pollutant concentration due to non-uniformity in metrological parameters, complex flow patterns, and uneven emissions from local and regional sources. Over 80% of the urban population is exposed to pollutants that do not meet World Health Organization (WHO) air quality limits [1], resulting in 4.2 million premature deaths worldwide [2]. Various stationary experimental approaches like regulatory monitoring stations and near-roadway sampling provide high temporal variability of urban air pollutants with limited spatial variation. On the other hand, modelling approaches like Land use regression (LUR) and Chemical transport models (CTMs) provide exposure to fixed areas within cities by determining the source-specific components. In the last two decades, the mobile monitoring experimental approach has become popular because it can provide the pollutant concentrations at fine (~kilometre) length and spatial scales using different platforms, e.g., bicycles, pedestrians, and cars/vans, to better assess personal exposure, develop and validate air quality models [3]. In this research work, we are focusing on the identification of pollution hotspot areas within Jodhpur (an arid urban region) and evaluate the spatial representativeness of regulatory monitoring stations operated by the State Pollution Control Board. We will also investigate the source drivers responsible for high pollutant concentrations and estimate pollutant exposure in the city.

METHODS

A mobile monitoring campaign was done in the Jodhpur city, Rajasthan, for a period of three weeks in the summer season. The mobile van was equipped with a global positioning system (GPS), and real-time monitoring instruments like Aethalometer (Model AE33), carbon monoxide (CO) and ozone (O₃) gas analysers (Ecotech) and Aurora 3000 Integrating Nephelometer (Ecotech) to measure the black carbon (BC), CO, O₃ and the particle scattering coefficient at three different wavelengths (450nm, 525nm and 635nm). We used separate inlets for gas- and particle-phase instruments and to prevent sampling our own exhaust, the inlets were positioned 1m above the vehicle roof, with the sampling port facing the front part of the vehicle. Further, we selected the mobile monitoring zones depending on the population density and utilities such as residential, commercial, and industrial activities. A total of 26 runs were performed on the pre-selected routes in different zones of Jodhpur city.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The mean concentrations of CO, O₃ and BC over different mobile monitoring zones were 0.88ppm, 1.16ppm and 0.60 ppm; 22.06ppb, 19.54ppb and 18.21ppb; and 12.75µg/m³, 9.89µg/m³ and 8.18µg/m³ for residential, commercial, and industrial zone, respectively. CO was observed to be highest in the commercial zone CO with the maximum value of 10.78ppm near Jalori Circle (Chopasani Rd), where mixed traffic, hotels, snack shops and food carts, were present. This is due to the incomplete combustion of non-fossil (wood and other solid

fuel used in cooking) sources and the proximity of the sources to the travel routes.

Figure 1. Spatial variability of Ozone concentration level on one day of mobile monitoring campaign in different routes of (a) Residential Zone (b) Commercial Zone (c) Industrial Zone.

CO (Ppm)	Black Carbon($\mu\text{g}/\text{M}3$)	Ozone (Ppb)	Remarks
$\geq 11.09 \pm 16.04$	$\geq 1.19 \pm 0.75$	$\leq 16.23 \pm 2.64$	Primary Emission
$7 \pm 7.77 - 11.09 \pm 16.04$	$0.52 \pm 0.36 - 1.19 \pm 0.75$	$16.23 \pm 2.64 - 21.11 \pm 4.13$	Primary And Secondary Production
$\leq 7 \pm 7.77$	$\leq 0.52 \pm 0.36$	$\geq 21.11 \pm 4.13$	Secondary Production

Table 1. Pollutant emission concentration range in different zones of Jodhpur city.

On the other hand, O₃ (shown in Figure.1(a)) and BC were observed to be highest in the residential zone with a maximum value of 59 ppb and 470 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ near Paota C Road, an area with traffic and big commercial establishments such as marts, bazaars, showrooms, and juice shops. This is due to the presence of both fossil (traffic) and non-fossil (wood and solid fuel) fuel combustion leading to high VOC emissions and secondary O₃ production. Also, a sudden peak in BC concentration (470 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was recorded near Badwasia Road due to household waste incineration activities. Further, depending on the pollutant concentration range, we observed that higher concentrations of pollutants like BC and CO are primarily from direct emission and as concentrations increase, especially for O₃, secondary production becomes more significant. data analysis for hotspot identification and identification of pollutant source drivers is under process.

CONCLUSION

In this mobile measurement study, we have observed that day mean concentration value of BC, CO and O₃ is varying for different zones: 6.19 to 23.74 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 0.52 to 1.34ppm, 15.69 to 37.35ppb respectively in residential zone coming from pollution source like automobiles, waste incineration, big commercial establishments, households, manufacturing stores of marble statue and tiles; 7.01 to 12.87 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 0.72 to 1.54ppm, 14.87 to 20.10ppb respectively in commercial zone due to comixed traffic, commercial shops like big marts, malls, restaurants; 6.45 to 11.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 0.50 to 0.88ppm, 16.21 to 18.92ppb respectively in industrial zone coming from heavy and mixed traffic, animal husbandry, waste incineration, tyre burning, industrial processes like metal processing and tyre manufacturing.

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POLLUTION EPISODES OVER SOUTH EAST ARABIAN SEA DURING PRE-MONSOON SEASON- INVESTIGATION OF DYNAMICS & INDUCED ATMOSPHERIC HEATING

REETHU JAYAPRAKASH E¹ AND MARINA ALOYSIUS²

Assumption College Changanasserry, PG and Research Department of Physics, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam – 636901, Kerala, India.

KEYWORDS: AEROSOLS, AOD, Radiative Forcing.

INTRODUCTION

During the pre-monsoon season, the South Eastern Arabian Sea region, along the west coast of India, experiences a significantly high aerosol loading. The presence of such heavy loading of aerosols over the SEAS probably could affect the thermal structure, stability of the atmosphere and thereby the regional scale weather conditions over the region and near the southeast coastal regions of India.

METHODS

Collection-6 daily MODIS Level-3 Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) land and ocean mean data at 550 nm resolution at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ from the satellites TERRA (MOD08_D3_006) and AQUA (MYD08_D3_006) for the period 2015 to 2017 (March-April) - AEROSOL. Species-wise AOD (Sulphate, Black Carbon, Organic Carbon, Sea Salt, and Dust) and radiation parameters from MERRA2 - Reanalysis. High AOD days consisting of a few days are referred as Pollution Episodes and Clear days prior to episode are referred to as pre-episode days. Comparative analysis of all variables is carried out over the pollution days and clear days.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Aloysius et al., 2011 have highlighted the influence of wind convergence amplifying the accumulation of aerosols over the SEAS region by transporting them from surrounding land masses. The HYSPLIT back trajectory model shows that the higher altitude winds are arising from the north Indian region sweeping through parts of the Bay of Bengal and the peninsular states during the heavy pollution days. These air masses could probably be enriched with biomass-burning pollutants, industrial pollutants and polluted dust aerosols.

Fig.1 which quantitatively depicts the average of species-wise AOD distribution during the pre-episode and episode over the SEAS shows that AOD enhances to 1.6 - 3 times.

Fig.1. Species wise AOD distribution from Merra-2 Reanalysis for pre-episode (PE) and episodes (E1, E2, E3, E4, E5, E6) for the years 2015, 2016 and 2017 over the SEAS. SS_AOD, SU_AOD, DU_AOD, OC_AOD and BC_AOD represent the

species wise AODs for sea salt (SS), sulphates (SU), dust (DU), organic carbon (OC) and black carbon (BC).

The contribution of aerosol species over SEAS is in the order of SU, DU, OC, SS and BC. The higher values of SU, OC and BC could only be due to fossil fuel combustion from power plants, industries etc. and biomass burning activities which are very much prevalent over the SI region and the north Indian regions from where winds are blowing over to the study domain during this period. Although the contribution from BC is small, the percentage increase compared to pre-episode days is often higher.

In order to study the radiative effects due to this, aerosol radiative forcing is estimated using MERRA-2 for all the pre-episode and events for the years 2015, 2016 and 2017. It is observed that both surface and top of the atmosphere ARF has become more negative. The ARF_TOA which ranges between -5 to -10 Wm⁻² during the pre-episode, maximizes to ~ -16 Wm⁻², while the ARF_SUR which is within the values -10 to -15 Wm⁻² maximizes to ~-28 Wm⁻² during the event period. In all the event cases ARF_SUR is significantly high compared to the ARF_TOA and these values are found to be 2.8 and 1.4 times respectively compared to that of the corresponding pre-episode days. The ARF in the atmosphere has been observed to be always positive. The baseline values of ARF during the pre-episode period range from +4 Wm⁻² to +6 Wm⁻². However, during the episodes, the ARF increases to almost twice that of the pre-episode periods. This positive ARF is likely to be attributed to the increased concentration of absorbing aerosols even though sulphate AOD dominates. This heating is verified from the INSAT temperature profiles observed during the period. This warming can lead to changes in the weather patterns near the western coastal areas.

CONCLUSIONS

Pollution Episodes over the South Eastern Arabian Sea are very frequent in the Pre-monsoon season and are closely associated with the change in wind patterns in higher latitudes. During this time, winds are transported from the North-Central India region, via the Bay of Bengal and Southern India. Wind convergences and vertical winds strongly support elevated aerosol layers over the SEAS during this time. The Sulphate is the highest contributor of aerosol over the SEAS followed by Dust, Organic Carbon, Sea Salt and Black Carbon. Even when sulphate dominates the atmosphere, atmospheric heating is nearly twice as high as on pre-episode days. This is observed in the INSAT temperature profiles This atmospheric warming can lead to changes in the weather patterns near the western coastal areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Department of Science and Technology – for the fellowship: Women Scientist -A

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ASSOCIATION BETWEEN EXPOSURE TO MULTIPLE AIR POLLUTANTS AND ANAEMIA AMONG WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN INDIA

KHUSHBOO¹, EKTA CHAUDHARY², SAGNIK DEY¹, ALOK KUMAR¹, FAHAD IMAM¹, SANTU GHOSH³, NEHA SINGH¹, LUKE D. KNIBBS⁴ AND J. JASON WEST⁵

¹Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

²Department of Epidemiology, University of Michigan, USA

³St. John's Medical College, Bengaluru, India

⁴University of Sydney, New South Wales, Australia

⁵ University of California, USA

KEYWORDS: Anaemia, Air Pollution, WRA, Air Quality Index

INTRODUCTION

Air quality has been identified as the leading environmental health risk. The health burden attributable to air pollution in India is one of the highest globally. Recent epidemiological research on air pollution in India has produced local evidence linking ambient air pollution to various health outcomes, although they have exclusively utilized PM_{2.5} as the main air quality indicator.

METHODS

We established an air quality index (AQI) database for India at a 1-km × 1-km geographic resolution for 13 years (2005-2017) to indicate cumulative exposure to three primary air pollutants: PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃. We then integrated the AQI data with the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-2016 data to investigate potential associations with anaemia among women of reproductive age (WRA, 15-49 years) using the logistic regression model. A generalized additive model with penalized cubic splines was employed to investigate possible non-linear relationships. We also assessed the effect modification of AQI through multiplicative interaction factors involving SES, iron consumption, second-hand smoke, cooking fuel, type of residence, and educational attainment.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The country-averaged AQI rose by 22%, from 121.93 in 2005 to 148.84 in 2017, with the most significant spike noted in the Indo-Gangetic Plain and the western dry regions. In 2005, 40% of the Indian population was subjected to NO₂ levels, surpassing the World Health Organization (WHO) air quality guideline (AQG), with this proportion rising to 59% in 2017. The changes in the percentage of the population exposed to levels surpassing the WHO Air Quality Guidelines for PM_{2.5} and O₃ were 99% and 69% in 2005, increasing to 99% and 93% in 2017, respectively.

Utilizing a logistic regression model controlled for covariates, we determined that a 10-unit increase in long-term exposure to AQI correlates with a 6.1% increase in the odds of developing anaemia (95% UI: 5.8-6.3). The connection between the increase in the interquartile range of long-term exposure to pollutants was greater for NO₂ compared to

PM2.5 and O3. Individuals with an iron intake below 15 mg/day and of low socio-economic status were more adversely impacted by air pollution compared to those consuming iron supplements over 15 mg/day and other sub-groups.

The non-linear dose-response curve indicates that health risks are present even within the 'satisfactory' AQI group (51-100), and these risks escalate with more exposure within the same AQI category.

Figure 1. Spatial patterns of annual averaged AQI (2007-2016) in India.

CONCLUSIONS

Our findings indicate that mitigating air pollution might expedite India's efforts to alleviate the anaemia burden. Given that this is a cross-sectional study, we advocate for more cohort studies to comprehensively elucidate the biological mechanisms underlying the anticipated relationship related to inflammatory pathways as documented in the literature.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the funding from the Clean Air Fund through a research grant to IIT Delhi. The presenting author acknowledges the MHRD fellowship for M. Tech students. SD acknowledges support from IIT Delhi for the Chair Professor fellowship. The work is part of the M. Tech dissertation at the Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, IIT Delhi.

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EVALUATION OF HIGH RESOLUTION WRF-CHEM SIMULATIONS FOR CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT STUDIES

VAISHNAVI S¹, JYOTI BHATE¹, VIKAS SINGH², AMIT KESARKAR¹

¹National Atmospheric Research Laboratory, Gadanki -517112, India

²Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change, Delhi -110003, India

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, Ozone, Reanalysis Data, WRF.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change impacts on air pollution are essential to assess the adverse effects on the environment and human health. Studying the impacts of climate on air quality has a pivotal role in influencing air quality-related government policies aimed at providing a sustainable and safe future, therefore quantifying the future impacts of climate change is necessary. Climate change depends on the emission of GHGs which has a direct correlation to social and economic development. To study the impacts of climate change in the future, the 6th IPCC Assessment Report has introduced Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs). The impacts of climate change for different SSP scenarios can be studied by comparing a baseline “Present” scenario with the downscaled CMIP6 SSP scenarios in India. To achieve that, in this study a “Present” baseline air quality scenario is simulated for PM_{2.5} and Ozone for the Indian region using the WRF modelling system with 2022 EDGAR emissions and Data Assimilation for an accurate representation of real-world air quality conditions. This model needs to be evaluated spatio-temporally and has to be bias-corrected. Ground observation from CPCB does not allow for spatial evaluation as the instruments are scattered and not continuous. Therefore, reanalysis datasets MERRA-2, CAMS and satellite-derived particulate matter datasets are first evaluated against ground observations to determine the best reanalysis dataset which is used to estimate bias in the model.

METHODS

The baseline scenario is simulated at a high resolution of 3km X 3km to capture PM_{2.5} and Ozone concentrations by using data assimilation and EDGAR 2022 emissions for an accurate representation of the real atmosphere. For spatial inter-comparison of observations and reanalysis, CAMS and SDPM₂₅ data have been re-gridded at MERRA-2 grid resolution of 0.5° X 0.625°. The temporal comparison has been carried out by converting all datasets in monthly mean. The CAMS, MERRA-2 and SDPM₂₅ data have been compared at the CPCB observation locations and performance has been evaluated through statistics such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Absolute Bias (AB), Correlation Coefficient (r) and Relative Mean Bias (RMB). The best-performing reanalysis dataset is then used to estimate Bias in the model.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The box plot of performance indices, such as RMSE, AB, r and RMB, calculated at each observation site is shown in Fig. 1. CAMS shows high RMSE overall and it is highest over the IGP in the range of 100-150 µg/m³. MERRA-2 and SDPM₂₅ have lower RMSE. Correlation with surface observation is high and positive in general for all the datasets. In Fig.1, CAMS has high RMSE, AB, r and RMB compared to other datasets for all the regions. The variability of the statistics for CAMS is particularly high for the IGP and WEST region.

MERRA-2 and SDPM25 have similar statistics. MERRA-2 has a high correlation in the South region, whereas SDPM25 and CAMS have a higher correlation in other regions. Overall, CAMS significantly overestimates PM_{2.5} over most of the regions, in particular polluted regions such as IGP and desert areas. On the other hand, MERRA-2 has lower biases but has poor spatial correlation as compared to CAMS. Moreover, CAMS has a high spatial correlation as compared to MERRA-2. SDPM2.5 has a lower bias and high spatial correlation.

Figure 1. The box plot of performance indices (RMSE, AB, r and RMB) calculated for reanalysis data at each observation site in different regions

CONCLUSIONS

The Datasets were compared with ground-based observations by calculating different statistical parameters such as Correlation, RMSE and MAE. The datasets were evaluated across India. The comparison results reveal that both the MERRA-2 and SDPM25 follow spatial and temporal distribution similar to ground observations as compared to CAMS. Though MERRA-2 and SDPM25 both performed well, MERRA-2 has a higher temporal resolution. Hence MERRA-2 is used to estimate the bias in the baseline scenario.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank MERRA-2 reanalysis, CAMS reanalysis, Washington University (SDPM25), CAAQMS(CPCB) and NCAR for providing valuable data and software. We also thank NARL/DOS for providing the necessary support.

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MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES FOR AIR QUALITY INDEX PREDICTION: A COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE STUDY

PADMAVATI SHRIVASTAVA¹, MANU MEHTA², RISHIKESH DEOGHARIA¹,
DEEPENDRA PAINKRA¹, VIDHI MEHTA¹, RISHITA R. NAIR¹

¹ Rungta College of Engineering and Technology, Bhilai, India

² Indian Institute of Remote Sensing, ISRO, Dehradun, India.

KEYWORDS: Air Quality Index (AQI), Machine Learning, Prediction

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the most pressing environmental challenges of the modern era, affecting millions of people worldwide. The Air Quality Index (AQI) is a crucial metric used to measure and report air quality levels, providing a standardized way to inform the public about potential health risks associated with exposure to polluted air (Kumari and Jain (2018)). Accurate AQI prediction is vital for governments, health organizations, and individuals to mitigate the adverse effects of air pollution, plan timely interventions, and issue health advisories (IHME (2019)). In recent years, Machine Learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for predictive modelling in a wide range of fields, including environmental science (Liang et al. (2020)). Machine learning algorithms can learn patterns from large datasets, making them particularly well-suited for predicting AQI levels based on historical data and real-time environmental variables such as concentrations of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), gaseous pollutants (NO₂, CO, SO₂), and meteorological conditions (temperature, humidity, wind speed). This study explores various machine learning algorithms like Random Forests, XGBoost and CatBoost; and compares their performance in predicting AQI levels.

METHODS

In this study, an efficient model for AQI prediction is presented using the air quality dataset for Hyderabad provided by CPCB. Hourly data from various air quality monitoring stations across Hyderabad was collected and combined to create a comprehensive dataset. This dataset formed the foundation for subsequent pre-processing steps. To address the issue of missing values, records with less than 3 parameters present were dropped from the dataset. This ensured that only records with sufficient information were retained. Seven key parameters were selected for initial analysis: PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, NH₃, NO_x, CO, and Ozone. These parameters are crucial for understanding air quality and calculating the Air Quality Index (AQI). A separate, clean dataset was created, containing the selected 7 parameters along with their corresponding station information and timestamps. To ensure consistent performance, the dataset was normalised using z-score normalization. This step standardized the data, making it easier for the models to process and interpret. To handle the remaining missing data, KNN (K-Nearest Neighbors) imputation was performed. We utilized three machine learning models - Random Forest, CatBoost, and XGBoost - to predict air quality in Hyderabad. Each model was chosen for its unique strengths: Random Forest for handling non-linear relationships, CatBoost for managing categorical features, and XGBoost for its speed and performance with structured data. Each model was configured with specific parameters to balance complexity and generalization. For Random Forest and XGBoost, we used 10 estimators, while CatBoost was set with 100 iterations, a learning rate of 0.1, and a depth of 6. All models used a random state of 42 for reproducibility. Grid search with 5-fold cross-validation was used to fine-tune hyper-parameters. The data was split into 80% training

and 20% testing sets, with features normalized using z-score normalization. This comprehensive approach allowed us to compare the models' effectiveness in capturing the complexities of air quality prediction in Hyderabad.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The three ML models are evaluated in terms of mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and correlation coefficient (R2) (Table 1). The superior performance of the Random Forest model suggests it is well-suited for predicting air quality in Hyderabad, likely due to its ability to capture complex interactions between parameters (Figure 1). The study demonstrates the effectiveness of machine learning, with Random Forest outperforming CatBoost and XGBoost. Its high accuracy and precision underscore the value of this approach in air quality forecasting.

Model	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	R2
Random Forest	0.10	1.51	0.11%	1.00
CatBoost	3.04	6.29	4.05%	0.98
XGBoost	2.91	6.59	4.74%	0.98

Table 1. Comparison between model parameters

Figure 2. Model Performance (Actual vs Predicted Values)

CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to predict air quality in Hyderabad using machine learning models. Three models were evaluated: Random Forest, CatBoost, and XGBoost, using metrics like MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and R2 score. The Random Forest model stood out with exceptional performance, achieving near-perfect results across all metrics, indicating high accuracy and precision. Both CatBoost and XGBoost also performed well, showcasing good overall accuracy and strong predictive capabilities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors are thankful to Director, IIRS, Dehradun for the support and encouragement. Thanks, are also due to RCET, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh.

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RECENT CHANGES IN DISTRICT-LEVEL AIR QUALITY OF WEST BENGAL, INDIA – ROLE OF METEOROLOGY

¹SUDIPTA GHOSH#, ¹ATANU DE SARKAR#, ¹URMIMALA PAUL and ^{1,2}SAGNIK DEY*

¹Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, IIT Delhi, New Delhi, India

²Adjunct Faculty, Korea University, Seoul, South Korea #Equal contributions

KEYWORDS: NCAP, PM2.5, Meteorology.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the primary reasons contributing to negative health concerns in India (Balakrishnan et al., 2018). Due to topography, emission sources, and adverse meteorological conditions, exposure to PM_{2.5} has increased in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (Dey et al., 2020). The state of West Bengal is located at the receiving end of the Indo-Gangetic Plain outflow, which is a regional air pollution hotspot in South Asia. Additionally, West Bengal is also vulnerable to transboundary pollution due to North-westerly winds carrying polluted air from the Indo-Gangetic Plain to the Bay of Bengal (Dey and Di Girolamo, 2010; Purohit et al., 2019). According to the latest GBD report in 2021, India accounted for 2.1 million deaths due to air pollution alone. Therefore, given recent national efforts in India to mitigate air pollution, it is imperative to assess the progress of clean air in West Bengal as well.

METHODS

Here, we examined various data types to assess the air quality of West Bengal. However, it is crucial to note that more comprehensive data collection is needed. CPCB tracks ambient air quality through sparsely distributed manual and automated stations (CAAQMS). Manual stations collect data bi-weekly (excluded from validation) and automated records daily data but from 2019. Since the availability of daily data from 2015 is irregular and sparse, both data sources are unsuitable for this study. Therefore, gap-filled AOD data is used in the Random Forest machine learning technique to predict daily PM_{2.5} at 1 km resolution from 2015 to 2022. Katoch et al., (2023) showed that satellite-derived PM_{2.5} levels are over-estimated if daily satellite aerosol optical depth data are not gap-filled. A machine learning technique, XGBoost, was used to produce gap-filled AOD data. This study uses daily CAAQMS data from 2015-2022 across 15 stations in West Bengal to validate these satellite-integrated PM_{2.5} concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Additionally, the meteorological parameters – rainfall, planetary boundary height, and u and v components of wind have been taken from ERA5 reanalysis data. ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Government of India launched the National Clean Air Programme with a target of reducing ambient air pollution by ~20% - 30%. Since 2017 is the NCAP baseline year, 2015-2018 has been considered the pre-NCAP era in the current study, while 2019-2022 has been considered the post-NCAP era. Figure 1, represents the district-wise annual PM_{2.5} concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. It can be observed that the 2015-2018 period shows a high PM_{2.5} concentration for districts like Maldah, Coochbehar, Uttar and Dakshin Dinajpur. Their annual mean is greater than the NAAQS value of 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, from 2019, the ambient PM_{2.5} concentration has lowered across all the districts, improving air quality. Kalimpong

has shown the highest improvement of 26%. The 2020 COVID lockdown can be a probable reason for the observed decrease. However, for 2019, NCAP regulations and meteorological factors might have modulated the decrease. 2021 has shown an increased annual value than 2020, possibly due to the aggressive opening of activities after the lockdown, but overall, the values are way lower than the pre-NCAP era. In 2022, most districts have again shown a dip and values are comparable to those of 2019.

Figure

1: Annual distribution of mean PM2.5 concentration in ug/m3.

Meteorology plays an important role in ambient air quality distribution. This study considers rainfall and ventilation coefficient (VC henceforth) to understand the meteorological influence on air quality in West Bengal. The VC (m2/s) is derived from the product of wind speed and HPBL. Both rainfall and VC negatively correlate with air pollutants. Districts with high PM2.5 values, like Uttar and Dakshin Dinajpur, Malda, Coochbehar, Alipurduar and Jalpaiguri have lower VC values and vice-versa for South 24 Parganas, Howrah and Purba Medinipur. However, districts like Puruliya, Kolkata, Paschim Bardhaman, North 24 Parganas, and Hooghly have high VC along with high mean PM2.5 values. A probable reason for this observation can be regional emissions, either generated locally or transported. High rainfall over North Bengal districts is an important determining factor for their low PM concentrations. However, mean annual rainfall has decreased in 2022 compared to 2021 and 2020 over the rest of the districts. This can possibly explain the high annual PM2.5 concentrations in a few districts like Dakshin Dinajpur and Maldah.

CONCLUSIONS

District-wise variations in air quality can be observed during the post-NCAP era using satellite-derived PM2.5 concentrations. State-average annual PM2.5 concentration declined by ~18.7% from 70.1 ug m-3 in 2015-2018 to 57 ug m-3 in 2019-2022. This improvement is most likely a manifestation of the combined impact of meteorology and various measures. However, local and transboundary emissions can influence overall state pollution dynamics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is funded by the West Bengal Pollution Control Board through a research grant

operational at IIT Delhi. PM_{2.5} data from the ground monitors are freely available from the CPCB data portal and satellite-derived PM_{2.5} data is available from (Katoch et al., 2023). ERA-5 meteorological observations are freely available at <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5>.

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HEAVY METAL EXPOSURE THROUGH SETTLED ROAD DUST IN RISHIKESH: ANALYSING TOXICITY AND HEALTH RISKS ALONG NATIONAL HIGHWAY-58

V. GUPTA¹, AND L. BISHT²

¹Dr. Vidhu Gupta, Assistant Professor, H.N.B. Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal

²Dr. Lalita Bisht, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, UP, 201312, India

KEYWORDS: Road Dust, Heavy Metals, Pollution Index, Non-Carcinogenic Risk, Carcinogenic Risk

INTRODUCTION

Dust is one of the most common pollutants in urban areas that are ubiquitous, suspended in the atmosphere, and ultimately accumulates on different surfaces on Earth (Rajaram et al., 2014; Roy et al., 2019; Chelani and Gautam, 2021; Ambade et al., 2021). Road dust primarily accumulates on the roads and is an essential indicator of environmental contamination as it receives and stores multiple pollutants from various stationary and mobile sources that is why it can be used as a great tool for health risk assessment for different contaminants associated with it (Ryder et al. 2019). The prolonged presence of the metals in the urban environment, particularly in road dust, and their proximity to the human population significantly increase the exposure of the urban population to metals via inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact.

METHODS

This study examines the concentration, contamination, and health risks associated with heavy metals (HMs) present in settled road dust. Fifteen dust samples were collected from various commercial locations along National Highway 58 in Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, India. The heavy metals were analyzed using the aqua-regia acid digestion method, followed by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). To determine the contamination level, the research employed various indices including contamination factor, the degree of contamination, pollution load index, and geo-accumulation index. Additionally, to identify the sources of HMs in the road dust, statistical techniques such as Pearson's correlation analysis, principal component analysis, and hierarchical cluster analysis were utilized. For health risk assessment the study considered both carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks of studies HMs for two age groups namely Children and adults and calculated by the health risk assessment model developed by the United Nations Environmental Protection Agency, 2002.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average concentrations of nine potentially toxic metals—Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), and Arsenic (As)—were found to be 16742.23, 260.06, 667.78, 120.61, 138.99, 1.47, 29.46, 23.90, and 3.00 mg·kg⁻¹, respectively. Levels of Zn, Pb, Cu, Cd, and As exceeded background values (Indian natural soil and upper continental crust) (Kuhad et al., 1989; Gowd et al., 2010), while Fe, Mn, Cr, and Ni were below background levels.

Pollution assessment revealed that the road dust was highly contaminated with Cd, Pb, and Zn, and moderately contaminated with As, Cu, Ni, and Mn. Pearson's correlation analysis was employed to assess the relationships between HMs, and principal component analysis (PCA)

helped identify HM sources in road dust. PCA indicated that Pb, Cd, As, Cu, and Zn (PC1) were mainly attributed to vehicular pollution, such as tyre and brake pad wear and corrosion of metal parts. Ni and Cr were linked to fuel combustion and road paint abrasion (PC2), while Fe and Mn (PC3) originated from both anthropogenic and natural sources.

Health risk assessment showed that ingestion was the primary exposure route for all HMs studied, followed by dermal contact and inhalation, with children being more vulnerable to HM contamination than adults. The non-carcinogenic risk assessment indicated no risk for either children or adults, but the carcinogenic risk assessment revealed that Cd, Cr, Ni, and As exceeded the threshold (1×10^{-6}) for both age groups, suggesting a potential cancer risk. The order of lifetime cancer risk (LCR) for the four HMs was Cd > Ni > Cr > As, in both children and adults.

CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the concentration, contamination, and health risks of nine heavy metals (HMs) in road dust along NH-58, which passes through Rishikesh, Uttarakhand. The findings indicate that road dust in this area is highly polluted by HMs, mainly due to vehicular activity, with heavy traffic, jams, and encroachment contributing to the issue. While there is no non-carcinogenic risk from the HMs for any age group, children are more vulnerable to contamination. The increasing use of two-wheelers, along with the lack of protective gear like helmets and masks, may worsen health risks, potentially leading to future cancer concerns. In conclusion, urgent measures are needed to mitigate the heavy metal contamination in road dust along NH-58. It is recommended to improve traffic management, reduce vehicular emissions, and implement stricter regulations on encroachments near the highway. Regular monitoring of HM levels and public awareness campaigns should also be prioritized to safeguard the health of Rishikesh's residents and visitors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for the research facilities provided by the USIC (University Scientific Instrument Centre), and Department of Environmental Sciences, Hemwati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University (A Central University), Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India, and the Central Library, the Centre of Learning Resources.

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MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR LARGE-SCALE ESTIMATES OF BLACK CARBON OVER INDO-GANGETIC BASIN

VAISHNAV BARTARIA¹, ASHOK JANGID², AUROOPRATAN GANGULY³, RANJIT KUMARI*

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute (Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005 (India)

²Department of Physics & Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute (Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005 (India)

³Civil and Environmental Engineering, College of Engineering, Northeastern University

ABSTRACT

Black carbon (BC) has garnered increasing attention from researchers due to its detrimental health impacts. However, in-situ BC measurements are frequently overlooked in regulated air quality monitoring networks. While significant advancements have been made in estimating various aerosol components on a large scale, accurately estimating black carbon concentrations across extensive spatiotemporal scales remains a challenge. To address this issue, we developed a novel approach employing machine learning (ML) techniques to estimate BC concentrations on a large scale. Our method involved utilizing a comprehensive BC dataset along with auxiliary variables to train several ML models, with the Random Forest (RF) algorithm demonstrating the best performance. This model was utilized to estimate high-resolution BC concentrations across the Indo-Gangetic Basin. We applied extensive datasets to train various ML models and conducted variable importance and sensitivity analyses to understand the physical relevance of the variables in BC estimation. The RF algorithm outperformed other models, achieving robust predictive accuracy for both training and test datasets on a daily timescale, marking a significant improvement over previous modeling approach. Additionally, we examined seasonal variations in BC distribution, finding the highest model performance in spring and summer, followed by autumn and winter. Our analysis indicated that BC emission inventories and meteorological data were the most critical variables in estimating BC concentrations and enhancing model accuracy. This study illustrates that an emission-based ML model, bolstered by a comprehensive auxiliary database (including satellite and reanalysis data), can effectively estimate large-scale spatiotemporal BC concentrations. The encouraging results suggest that this methodology could also be applied to assess other primary pollutants in future research.

KEYWORDS: Machine Learning, Emission Inventories, Black Carbon, Remote Sensing, Spatial Distribution

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) aerosols, formed from the incomplete combustion of carbon-containing materials, are vital components of atmospheric aerosols. Although they account for only a small percentage of total aerosol mass (up to 10%), BC particles have significant environmental, climatic, and health effects. They absorb solar radiation across the entire wavelength range, playing a substantial role in global warming (Takemura et al., 2019; Yeganeh et al., 2021).

METHODS

Sampling of Black Carbon Measurement: The comprehensive seven-channel Aethalometer (Model AE33; Magee Scientific USA) will be used to assess the concentration of Black Carbon (BC). Prediction of Black Carbon Concentration: Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) used for predicting Black Carbon (BC) data due to their ability to handle complex, non-linear relationships and large datasets.

Figure 8 Supervised Machine Learning Model

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Model Performance: Training and cross-validation datasets were employed to develop several machine learning (ML) algorithms, including SGB, BT, XGBoost, and RF, using a repeated 10-fold cross-validation approach. The performance of these models in estimating ground-level BC concentrations is summarized in Figure 1. In contrast, algorithms like XGBoost, BT, and RF achieved higher performance. For example, the XGBoost model attained an R^2 of 0.64 and an RMSE of 1.79, highlighting its superior predictive capability.

Figure 9 Variations of the performance measures (R^2 , RMSE, and MAE) of our different predictive models

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the potential of using machine learning (ML) models to generate large-scale spatiotemporal estimates of black carbon (BC) concentrations. Various ML algorithms were utilized to develop BC estimation models, incorporating a range of input variables with physical relevance to BC levels. The models benefited from integrating BC emission inventories and ground-level BC monitoring data, achieving strong predictive

performance ($R^2 = 0.87$, RMSE = 1.17 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for the test dataset).

Analyses of variable importance and sensitivity highlighted the critical role of gridded BC emissions in enhancing estimation accuracy ($R^2 = 0.74$, RMSE = 1.69 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). This approach demonstrates the effectiveness of combining emission inventories with monitoring data to improve large-scale BC estimation models.

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FESEM ANALYSIS OF ATMOSPHERIC SOOT AND ORGANIC PARTICLE: MEASUREMENT, MODELLING, AND IMPACTS

VAISHNAV BARTARIA¹, ASHOK JANGID², AUROOPRATAN GANGULY³,
RANJIT KUMAR^{1*}

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational Institute
(Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005 (India)

²Department of Physics & Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Dayalbagh Educational
Institute (Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra-282 005 (India)

³Civil and Environmental Engineering, College of Engineering, Northeastern University,
Boston, MA 02115 (USA)

ABSTRACT

Soot and organic particles emitted from fossil fuel combustion and biomass burning significantly impact Earth's climate by interacting with solar radiation and modifying cloud properties. These particles can act as cloud condensation nuclei and ice-nucleating agents. Recent advancements in understanding their unique characteristics and microscopic composition have led to heightened interest in their microphysical properties. Morphological analyses of individual soot particles have been conducted using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) at various magnifications. To quantify soot morphology and ageing, the fractal dimension (Df) is commonly used as a quantitative measure, allowing for the characterization of soot aggregates and their changes in relation to ageing factors such as internal mixing state, core-shell structures, and composition heterogeneity. Models have been developed to integrate Df and diversity metrics of aged soot particles, enabling a quantitative evaluation of their optical absorption and radiative forcing effects. Their strong light-absorbing properties, presence of toxic organic compounds, and small size, primary carbonaceous particles like tar balls and soot require further investigation due to their potential impact on human health. Future research should focus on both atmospheric measurements and modelling strategies, particularly examining the changes in the mixing structures of soot and organic particle ensembles and their implications for climate dynamics and public health.

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Soot, Fesem-Edx, Aerosol Modelling, Environmental Impact.

INTRODUCTION

Soot emissions significantly affect the global climate through their interaction with solar radiation (Riemer et al., 2019). Studies have shown that soot is a major contributor to global warming, ranking just behind carbon dioxide emissions (Li et al., 2016). Additionally, soot particles can absorb hazardous compounds, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, resulting in the formation of ultra-fine particles that pose risks to the human circulatory system (Bond et al., 2013). The crystallite structure and fringe morphology of soot particles produced by combustion have gained increasing attention due to their strong correlation with primary particle formation and the oxidative reactivity of soot (Li et al., 2022). Soot models that incorporate morphological characteristics range from spherical particles to fractal-like

aggregates, each with distinct shape indicators. Monte Carlo algorithms have been utilized to predict not only bulk properties, like particle size distribution but also to simulate aggregate morphology and generate SEM-like images (Coppol et al., 2022). However, these complex models tend to be computationally intensive and often exhibit lower predictive accuracy for aggregated particles compared to primary particles (Wang et al., 2022). High-resolution analysis of the morphological evolution of flame-generated soot particles is crucial for refining soot models and enhancing predictions of their oxidative reactivity. Furthermore, the changes in soot morphology and flame temperature distribution are key factors that influence the properties of carbon nanomaterials synthesized through combustion.

METHODS

FESEM Analysis of Soot Particle: For the Morphological analysis of Aerosol and Black carbon samples by using the Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM) (JEOL JSM-IT800).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Soot and organic particles, play a pivotal role in exacerbating air quality issues and contribute substantially to the worldwide public health challenges. Soot particles, dominating within the size range of less than $1\mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 1).

Figure 10 Morphology of Soot Particle

CONCLUSION

This research highlights the use of FESEM analysis to characterize atmospheric soot and organic particles, providing detailed insights into their morphology and composition. By integrating measurement data with modelling approaches, the study enhances understanding of the sources, behavior, and environmental impacts of these particles, contributing to improved air quality management and policy development.

IMPLICATIONS

This study provides critical insights into the characterization and impacts of atmospheric soot and organic particles. By combining FESEM analysis with modeling, enhances source attribution, refines predictions of particle behaviour, and highlights their role in climate forcing and public health risks. The findings support the development of targeted mitigation

strategies, informed air quality policies, and advancements in analytical techniques for particulate matter research.

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THE IMPACT OF DISPERSED SOURCES PROGRAM ON LOCAL AIR QUALITY

AMARENDRA SINGH^A, SOFIA RAO^A AND SAGNIK DEY^A

^A Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi – 110016, India.

KEYWORDS: Portable Low-Cost Senosrs, Particulate Matter, Long Term Intervention, Air Pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Rising levels of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in the air pose significant environmental and health risks, particularly in developing countries (Chen et al., 2016). Portable low-cost sensors (PLCS) are transforming air quality monitoring by providing a cost-effective means to supplement conventional regulatory stations, which are often sparse and widely distributed (Liang and Daniels, 2022). Due to their affordability, PLCS offer a way to capture fine-scale spatial and temporal variations in PM_{2.5} levels. These sensors have been successfully deployed in a variety of applications, including environmental regulation, hotspot detection, traffic-related air pollution studies, and health risk assessments. The increased use of PLCS is driving a paradigm shift in environmental monitoring, particularly in regions where access to air quality data has traditionally been limited, hindering effective responses to pollution trends. In addition to being cost-effective, PLCS are easy to operate and foster community involvement through crowd-sourced data collection. This makes them ideal for expanding air quality monitoring networks and engaging local communities in pollution management. Furthermore, the integration of PLCS data with other sources, such as satellite-based remote sensing, enhances their utility across multiple disciplines and research areas. Despite their growing popularity in scientific, industrial, and civilian domains, air pollution remains heavily influenced by dispersed and often overlooked sources, such as unpaved roads, construction waste, garbage burning, and broken infrastructure. These sources significantly contribute to the pollution burden, especially in urban areas. This study assessed the program's effectiveness in reducing PM_{2.5} levels by using data from both the Government's Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Stations (CAAQMs) and portable low-cost sensors (PLCS). The central hypothesis was that if the program had a significant impact, measurable differences would be observed between the data from the PLCS and the nearest CAAQMS. To test this, a 'difference-in-difference' methodology was applied. The study was carried out in three clusters in Delhi, Jahangir Puri, Rohini, and Karol Bagh where 35 PLCS were deployed. Data collection spanned from July 2023 to March 2024, covering the entire study period.

METHOD

Collocation and Calibration of Low-Cost Sensors

Each low-cost sensor used in the study went through a rigorous collocation and calibration process where their collected data was referenced against a government grade Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Station (CAAQMS) placed in similar conditions. This process helped establish a robust correlation between low-cost sensor data and the established reference standard, strengthening the credibility of our findings. For this study, the sensors were collocated at US Embassy BAM by Airveda, During the collocation the Root Mean Square Value (RMSE) was 21.92 and R² was 0.91.

Differential Concentration Hypothesis

To evaluate the impact of resolution a ‘Projected Factor’ has been calculated for each instance of LT Issue resolution. This is the difference between the pre- and post-readings from the nearest CAAQMS. This difference is expressed using the following formula:

$$\text{Projected Factor} = \frac{\text{Final Concentration} - \text{Initial Concentration}}{\text{Initial Concentration}} * 100$$

Assuming that the increase or decrease in concentration observed in the CAAQMS data will also be reflected in nearby low-cost sensors, this factor is used to calculate the Projected Concentration for low-cost sensors: Projected Concentration (LCS) = PM2.5 levels 5 days Pre-Resolution (LCS)* Projected Factor

Finally, the Projected Concentration (LCS) is compared to the actual concentrations recorded by the low-cost sensor. The percentage reduction in PM2.5 levels is attributed to the local effects of the intervention, forming the basis of our hypothesis. Cluster-specific statistics were compiled and compared across the three regions to identify regional variations. Additionally, statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of different intervention types.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our study shows a significant reduction in PM2.5 levels at the hyperlocal level due to the dispersed sources program. As indicated above, data was studied for the resolution of 65 long term issues. The impact of each intervention is computed as the % difference between the projected and actual PM2.5 readings from LCS. It shows that resolving issues at a localized scale, can significantly help reduce PM2.5 concentration. In the study, PM2.5 was shown to reduce by 26.6% in Jahangirpuri, 15.7% in Rohini, and 15.3% in Karol Bagh.

Figure 1 Percentage reduction in three major hotspots of Delhi from (1st July 2023 - 31st March 2024) due to the resolution of long-term interventions.

CONCLUSION

This study also establishes the utility of a hybrid monitoring approach, particularly at a hyper-local scale, because the impact of interventions may or may not be captured by CAAQMS located at a distance. Since the magnitude of the impact depends on multiple factors, extending the study to other locations and even other cities within an airshed for a longer duration would provide an opportunity to understand the impact of resolving local dispersed

sources on regional air quality.

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SIMULTANEOUS BLACK CARBON AEROSOL MEASUREMENTS OVER URBAN AND RURAL LOCATIONS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY AND PREDICTION USING HYBRID MACHINE LEARNING

HAREEF BABA SHAEB. K, MALLIKARJUN.K AND ALOK TAORI

¹Atmospheric Sciences division, Earth and Climate Science Area, National Remote Sensing Centre Balanagar, Hyderabad – 500007, India.

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon; Absorption Coefficient; Meteorological Parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) is a primary aerosol emitted at the source from incomplete combustion of fossil fuel and biomass. BC strongly absorbs solar radiation which leads to positive radiative forcing (IPCC). Due to its fine size when it is inhaled, it has an impact on human respiratory health (Janssen et al. 2012). The present study focuses on the seasonal variation of BC during the period 2013-14 and investigates the role of source processes and prevailing meteorology, over two contrasting locations viz Hyderabad (urban site) and Shadnagar (rural site). Analysis of the spatiotemporal variability of BC over two different environments of the same region will be helpful in accessing the air quality of respective regions and also provide useful input to regional and global aerosol models when assessing regional radiative forcing and climate impacts. We use a Hybrid machine learning model (CNN-LSTM) to predict the BC concentration using MERRA-2 data

METHODS

Real-time measurements of atmospheric BC over Hyderabad and Shadnagar are carried out using seven channel Aethalometers (model AE31, Magee Scientific, USA) during the study period 2013-14. BC mass concentrations over both the sites are diurnally averaged after excluding the values with deviation more than 3σ from mean, by considering respective monthly diurnal data and is used for further analysis. Long-term BC datasets from 1980-2021 are used as a training dataset in a univariate CNN-LSTM model and predicted BC for the year 2022. For the model tuning, we have utilised the Time-Distributed Conv1D layer, epoch 25, batch size 256, sequence length 2, optimizer 'Adam' and activation function 'relu' and the model trained on 80-20 with a learning rate of 0.0003.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Seasonal variation of BC over Shadnagar and Hyderabad is shown in Figure 1. Both sites showed distinct seasonal variations, with more significant variation observed over Shadnagar. BC mean mass concentration during Pre-monsoon, Monsoon, Post-monsoon and Winter over Shadnagar is found to be 2.75 ± 0.35 , 1.33 ± 0.37 , 3.07 ± 0.78 , 3.28 ± 0.39 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively, while that over Hyderabad is found to be 7.14 ± 0.82 , 5.4 ± 0.38 , 5.06 ± 0.41 , and 6.5 ± 2.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during the respective seasons.

Figure 2 shows the frequency distribution of AAE over Shadnagar and Hyderabad during the study period most of the time, AAE values are found to be between 0.9 and 1.3 over both the sites, with ~89% of total occurrence over Hyderabad and ~70% over Shadnagar. About 20% of total AAE values observed over Shadnagar are less than 0.9 and 10% are more than 1.3. This can be due to localized biomass burning or cooking using wood, animal dung, coal-fired

electric utilities, brick kilns etc, which is a common practice in Indian rural villages

Figure 1. Seasonal diurnal variation of Black Carbon (BC) aerosols over Shadnagar and Hyderabad during the period 2013-14.

Figure 2. Frequency distribution (%) of Absorption Angstrom Exponent (AAE) over Shadnagar and Hyderabad.

Figure 3 shows the Actual BC Vs Predicted BC for the year 2022 using the CNN-LSTM model. The statistics obtained are R2 as 0.83 and RMSE as 1.03 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ indicating very good prediction using this model.

CONCLUSIONS

Annual BC mass concentration over Shadnagar (rural location) is found to be $2.46 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while over Hyderabad (urban location) it is about 3 times higher. The main source of BC is fossil fuel combustion over both locations; while over Shadnagar a small fraction of contribution from biomass burning is also inferred. The hybrid machine learning model (CNN-LSTM) is performing well in predicting the BC using long-term MERRA-2 data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Aerosol Radiative Forcing over India (ARFI) project under the ISRO Geosphere Biosphere Program (IGBP).

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SIMULATION OF PM_{2.5} OVER INDIA USING THE GEOS-CHEM MODEL FOR HEALTH IMPACT ASSESSMENTS

SUBHADEEP GHOSH AND SAJEEV PHILIP

Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi, 110016

KEYWORDS: Air Quality, PM_{2.5}, GEOS-CHEM, Model.

INTRODUCTION

Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is one of the most significant pollutants affecting public health and the environment. Urbanization, industrialization, and increased vehicular emissions have led to alarming levels of ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations in India. Assessment of changes in PM_{2.5} and factors leading to those changes requires in situ observational data and model simulations.

Chemical transport models (CTMs) are valuable tools for assessing PM_{2.5} pollution, spatiotemporal variability, emission source contributions, and human exposures over a region. There are limited studies focussed on the high-resolution simulations of PM_{2.5}, evaluation and comprehensive analysis, focusing on India (e.g., Bran et al., 2017; Kota et al., 2018). Here, we simulate PM_{2.5} concentrations over the India-domain (nested region) using the state-of-the-science CTM: GEOS-Chem at a high spatial resolution, for the first time. Our broad objective is to develop accurate annual mean PM_{2.5} data over India for multiple scientific problems, particularly for conducting health impact assessments. In this study, as a preliminary step, we perform simulations for a year, compare simulated PM_{2.5} with observations, and assess the PM_{2.5} seasonal and spatial variability.

METHODS

We conduct the GEOS-Chem global and regional Indian nested simulations for 2021. First, we conduct a global model simulation at a resolution of $2^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ latitude \times longitude. The boundary conditions from the global simulations are used to perform the nested Indian regional model simulations. The Indian nested model simulations have a spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.3125^\circ$ latitude \times longitude.

We use the NASA-GMAO GEOS-FP meteorological data to drive the model. The model is run with the CEDS anthropogenic emissions inventory version 2: CEDSv2, which includes species such as SO₂, NO_x, NH₃ from source sectors, Industry, Energy, Transport, and Agriculture. GEOS-Chem includes the simulations of carbonaceous aerosols, mineral dust and sea salt. The simulated PM_{2.5} concentrations at the lowest level of the GEOS-Chem model is referred to here as the surface-level PM_{2.5}. The seasons are defined here as winter (DJF), pre-monsoon (MAM), monsoon (JJAS), and post-monsoon (ON).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 shows the seasonal mean surface PM_{2.5} over India simulated with the GEOS-Chem CTM at a high spatial resolution for 2021. The enhanced PM_{2.5} concentrations throughout the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region are evident. The IGP region is a PM_{2.5} hotspot due to high population density, anthropogenic emissions, and unfavourable meteorology. We find that secondary inorganics (sulphate-nitrate-ammonium) is a significant component of total PM_{2.5} mass over the IGP region. The PM_{2.5} concentrations are high during the winter and

post-monsoon regions, with the lowest concentrations in monsoon season, primarily due to meteorological conditions and emissions. Our initial comparison of the simulated annual mean PM_{2.5} against Indian in situ observations shows a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.71$, and a slope of 1.01. To our understanding, this is the first simulation of PM_{2.5} over India using the GEOS-Chem model at a high spatial resolution.

Figure 1. The GEOS-Chem model simulated seasonal mean PM_{2.5} over India for the year 2021.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we simulate PM_{2.5} concentrations over India for 2021, using the state-of-the-science chemical transport model GEOS-Chem at a high spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.3125^\circ$ latitude \times longitude. We then assess the seasonal mean surface PM_{2.5} concentrations over India using the GEOS-Chem model simulations. We find IGP region as a PM_{2.5} hotspot with enhanced concentrations especially during winter and post-monsoon seasons. This simulation can be used to estimate population exposure to PM_{2.5} and to assess associated public health impacts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful for the computational resources made available by IIT Delhi's high-performance computing cluster. We thank the GEOS-Chem model support team and user community.

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COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF TRANSPORT AND DEPOSITION FOR NON-SPHERICAL PARTICLES IN HIGH REYNOLDS NUMBER REGIME

RIYA DEY^{1,2} AND S ANAND^{1,2}

¹Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai - 400085, India.

²Homi Bhabha National Institute, Anushaktinagar Mumbai - 400094, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Transport, Drift Velocity, Drag Force, CFPD.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol dynamics simulations rely on accurate computational fluid-particle dynamics (CFPD) models to predict particle behaviour under various fluid flow conditions. AeroSolved [Frederix et al., 2017; Lucci et al., 2022], an open-source software framework licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL), is used for studying the evolution of spherical particles in low Reynolds number regimes ($Re_d < 1$), where particle motion is governed by Stokes' law. In this study, we present modifications to the existing 'fullStokes' model in AeroSolved, extending its applicability to simulate the transport of non-spherical particles in higher Reynolds number regimes ($Re_d > 1$), thereby addressing the limitations of the default model.

METHODS

Governing equations for fluid flow and particle transport

The AeroSolved (v2.0) code, integrated into OpenFOAM (v1906), operates within a Eulerian-Eulerian framework, discretizing the particle size distribution and solving transport equations for particle number concentration while incorporating relevant source terms. Fluid flow is governed by the Navier-Stokes equations, describing key parameters such as velocity, pressure, density, and viscosity. Aerosol particles, modelled separately, account for forces such as drag, gravity, and electrostatic interactions. To model the inertial deposition of aerosols, the absolute velocity $\mathbf{v}(s)$ of the dispersed phase with mass s and diameter d is expressed in terms of particle drift velocity $\mathbf{V}(s)$ and the continuous phase velocity (\mathbf{u}) as:

$$\mathbf{v}(s) = \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{V}(s). \quad (1)$$

The partial differential equation governing the motion of the dispersed phase (particle) is:

$$s[\partial_t \mathbf{v}(s) + [\mathbf{v}(s) \cdot \nabla] \mathbf{v}(s)] = \mathbf{F}_D + \mathbf{F}_G \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{F}_D represents the drag force and $\mathbf{F}_G = (\rho_p - \rho_g)V_p \mathbf{g}$ is the gravitational force acting on the particle. Here, \mathbf{g} is gravitational acceleration, ρ_g is fluid density, and ρ_p and V_p are the particle density and volume, respectively. For spherical particles in a low Reynolds number regime ($Re_d < 1$), the drag force based on Stokes' law is given by:

$$\mathbf{F}_D = -\frac{1}{2} A_d \rho_g C_D |\mathbf{V}(s)| \mathbf{V}(s) \quad (3)$$

where A_d is the cross-sectional area of the particle and C_D is the drag coefficient, expressed as, $C_D = 24/Re_d$ for $Re_d < 1$. Here, $Re_d = (\rho_g |\mathbf{V}(s)| d)/\mu_g$ is the particle Reynolds number, and μ_g is the dynamic viscosity of the continuous phase (fluid). This formulation is implemented in the 'fullStokes' model in the current version of Aerosolved (Fig.1).

To simulate particle transport and deposition in the high Reynolds number regime ($Re_d > 1$), the drag force requires correction. The 'Schiller-Naumann' drag coefficient ($C_{D,SN}$) [Clift et

al., 1978] is used for $Re_d < 800$, given by: $C_{D,SN} = \frac{24}{Re_d} [1 + 0.15Re_d^{0.687}]$. Additionally, the drag force is adjusted by introducing the dynamic shape factor (χ) accounting for the effect of particle shape. The dynamic shape factor is defined as the ratio of the actual resistance force on a non-spherical particle to the resistance force on a spherical particle of the same volume and velocity [Hinds, 1999]. Hence, the modified drag force term is:

$$F_D = - \frac{(1+0.15Re_d^{0.687})}{\tau} s [\mathbf{v}(s) - \mathbf{u}] \chi, \quad (4)$$

where $\tau = \frac{\rho_p d^2}{18\mu_g}$ is the particle relaxation time. Based on the Eq. (4), a new module named 'snDrift' (Fig 2) has been integrated into Aerosolved to calculate the corrected drag force for non-spherical particles.

Library and Class Organisation in OpenFOAM & Aerosolved

Each working module (Fig. 1) consists of two files: (a) ApplicationName.C, which contains the source code of the application, and (b) Header_Files.H, which includes necessary header files to compile the application. The 'Make' directory contains: **files**: names all the source files (.C), it specifies the name of the new application and the location of the output file. **options**: specifies directories to search for include files and libraries to link the solver.

Figure 1. Structure of applications in OpenFOAM & Aerosolved

Figure 2. Modifications and introduction of new modules in Aerosolved

Debugging and testing

In addition to the functional changes, the 'snDrift' module includes a logging mechanism that records the shape factor values in a file named debug.log, facilitating tracking and troubleshooting during simulation to assess the impact of varying shape factors on results.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The modifications were implemented in AeroSolved v2.0 and tested against existing simulations of aerosol deposition in bent pipes and complex geometries. One test case involved respiratory deposition: for an inhalation flow rate of 7 L/min ($Re_d < 1$), both the default 'fullStokes' and the new 'snDrift' modules produced similar deposition results. However, at a flow rate of 15 L/min, where Re_d exceeded 1 in certain regions, the default 'fullStokes' module encountered instability, especially for particles larger than 10 μm . After implementing the 'snDrift' module, the simulation converged. For this test, the shape factor χ was set to 1 (spherical particles). The effect of different χ values on deposition along the bent pipe will be further discussed.

CONCLUSIONS

By incorporating the dynamic shape factor and modifying the drag coefficient, the ‘snDrift’ module expands AeroSolved's applicability to more complex scenarios involving non-spherical particles. This enhancement makes the code more versatile for various applications, where irregular particle shapes are frequently encountered.

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INTEGRATING TRACE GASES FOR ENHANCED PM_{2.5} ESTIMATION USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN AHMEDABAD

A. M. KURESHI¹, T. TURAKHIA², D. SHAH¹ AND M.R. PANDYA³,

¹Sir P.T Sarvajani College of Science, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat

²Department of Physics and Electronics, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad

³ Space Applications Centre, ISRO, Ahmedabad-380015, India.

KEYWORDS: Air Quality Modelling, Particulate Matter (Pm_{2.5}) Estimation, Machine Learning, Trace Gases,

INTRODUCTION

Monitoring and forecasting air pollution stands as the initial crucial measure for controlling air pollution, an essential aspect of achieving sustainable development. Accurately predicting the fluctuating and complex nature of air quality data necessitates extracting the spatial and temporal relationships within them and their connections to forecasting. The proposed study of estimating air pollution is conducted over Ahmedabad, Gujarat. The air quality data collected from GPCB (Gujarat Pollution Control Board) stations are highly dynamic, nonlinear, and hold intensely stochastic spatiotemporal correlations. Deep learning (DL) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms that are capable of extracting a higher level of abstraction in data can efficiently capture the spatiotemporal features in it. The observation shows that among the four - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Random Forest (RF) and XGBoost models implemented all of them show similar trends when trained over the provided data. However, RF is performing better compared to the other three models with a low RMSE of 19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and less overshooting.

METHODS

The process begins with collecting ground measurements of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and trace gases such as CO, SO₂, and NO_x from the GPCB station installed in Ahmedabad. Once collected, the data undergoes cleaning and exploration to remove any inconsistencies or outliers that could distort the analysis. This step prepares the data for modelling by identifying significant patterns and relationships, particularly correlations with PM_{2.5} levels. After processing, the data is split into a training set and a testing set, with the training set used to build the model and the testing set reserved for evaluating model performance on unseen data. The machine learning model is developed using the training data to predict PM_{2.5} levels based on identified relationships. The model's accuracy is then tested on the testing data, with metrics such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), MAE, and coefficient of determination (R²) providing insights into its performance and identifying potential areas for improvement. Finally, model selection occurs based on error analysis, with the goal of choosing a model that strikes the best balance between accuracy and complexity for the given data and task.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Air pollution has significant impacts on regional air quality, climate, and human activities, often leading to serious public health issues. PM_{2.5} is a key indicator of air pollution, commonly monitored via ground stations; however, the limited distribution of these stations restricts continuous, accurate information on PM_{2.5} concentrations. This study addresses these limitations by incorporating trace gas concentrations, known to correlate with PM_{2.5},

and applying machine learning models to estimate PM_{2.5} levels in Ahmedabad. Four models — ANN, LSTM, RF and XGBoost—were evaluated for predicting PM_{2.5} concentrations, revealing notable differences in their accuracy and predictive capabilities. Scatter plots compare actual vs. predicted PM_{2.5} values from each model, with a trend line indicating the ideal 1:1 relationship where predictions match observations. Key metrics, including sample size (N), R², and RMSE, assess the accuracy of each model's predictions, where higher R² values and lower RMSE signify better performance. These visualizations provide a comparative analysis of each machine learning model's effectiveness in estimating PM_{2.5}, highlighting their capacity to capture the relationship between observed and predicted values.

Figure 1 - Scatter plot showing the relationship between observed PM_{2.5} values (CPCB) vs. the predicted PM_{2.5} values estimated by the four models.

CONCLUSIONS

A comparison of four machine learning models— ANN, LSTM, RF and XGBoost —revealed that the Random Forest model provided the most accurate estimates of PM_{2.5} concentrations. The RF model achieved the lowest RMSE of 19 μg/m³ and demonstrated a superior capacity to capture variations in PM_{2.5} levels compared to actual ground measurements, indicating a strong ability to discern underlying patterns in the data. This makes RF a more reliable choice for predicting PM_{2.5} concentrations. The model's enhanced accuracy underscores its potential for real-time air quality monitoring, offering timely warnings to citizens and helping them take preventative health measures in response to pollution fluctuations. In the future, these models could also be adapted to predict the AQI, a key air quality indicator, positioning the RF model as a valuable tool for environmental monitoring and public health advisories, ultimately contributing to improved air quality management and healthier living conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am very much thankful to GPCB for providing us with the measurements of Particulate Matter and other gases over Ahmedabad.

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EFFECT OF DYNAMIC SHAPE FACTOR ON AEROSOL DYNAMICS USING COUPLED FLUID-PARTICLE DYNAMICS APPROACH

JAYANT KRISHAN^{1,2} AND S. ANAND^{1,2}

¹Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai – 400 094, India.

²Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Dynamic Shape Factor, Fluid Dynamics, Aerosol Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The distribution of aerosols released in a containment-like closed environment may not be uniform (Sapra et al., 2008). Generally used uniformly mixed models are not able to capture this heterogeneity in the aerosol distribution and hence, necessitate the development of a coupled fluid-particle dynamics (CFPD) approach as pointed out in the EPRI report (2018). This coupled approach can predict the aerosol behaviour in a closed environment even under complex or dynamic boundary conditions. An Open FOAM (Weller et al., 1998) library-based solver, Aerosolved (Lucci et al, 2022) combines the transport of aerosols with fluid flow to model the interplay between aerosols and the surrounding airflows. Also, the morphology of aerosol aggregates plays a vital role in determining its settling characteristics. The aerosol aggregates may be non-spherical in general and hence, dynamic shape factors are introduced in order to account for the non-spherical nature of these aerosol aggregates. Therefore, Aerosolved is modified by introducing the expressions for size-dependent dynamic shape factors and the new solver thus created is referred to as DyAerosolved. In order to demonstrate the importance of the implementation of these shape factors in the CFPD code, the evolution of aerosol concentration is studied in a 10.0 m³ chamber at a nuclear aerosol test facility (NATF). DyAerosolved solver can be used to study the spatial and temporal behaviour of aerosols released in reactor containment under accidental conditions, which will further improve the estimation of source terms during such accidental scenarios.

METHODS

The simulation involves the construction of geometry followed by meshing, the definition of boundary and input conditions. The chamber geometry used in the simulation consists of three ports including one inlet and two outlets. The generation of geometry and meshing is done using the student version of Ansys Workbench 2023 R2 (Ansys student) and the mesh file generated is converted to the Open Foam compatible format followed by the definition of boundary conditions. The aerosols with a CMD of 0.211 μm and GSD of 2.6 are injected in the chamber for 20 minutes with a velocity of 0.28 m/s. the initial aerosol concentration at the inlet is 3.22 g/m³. The chamber is assumed to be 1 atm pressure and a temperature of 293K. The velocity, dispersed and continuous phase mass fraction inputs are time dependent where the release phase continues for 20 mins and stops after that. After the release phase is over, aerosol concentration in the containment evolves due to coagulation, diffusion, gravitational settling and drift. For each of the volume elements, the equation of continuity, momentum, energy and species transport equation are solved. The governing aerosol dynamics equation is

solved using the sectional method where the size bin is divided into ‘ n ’ number of bins and the aerosols are distributed among these bins for a given value of CMD and GSD assuming the distribution of aerosols to be log-normal.

The governing equations for the drift and relaxation time are modified to account for the modification in the aerodynamic properties of the aerosols due to their non-spherical nature. The dynamic shape factor (χ) is introduced in the Brownian diffusivity term as given by,

$$D(d) = \frac{k_B T C_c}{3 \pi \mu d \chi} \quad (1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, C_c is the Cunningham slip correction factor, d is the diameter of the aerosol particle, μ is the fluid viscosity. The corresponding relaxation time (τ) for the droplets undergoing Stokes drag is modified to,

$$\tau = \frac{\rho_m d^2}{18 \mu \chi} \quad (2)$$

The dynamic shape correction terms added in the governing equations ensure that the governing equations are valid for the non-spherical aggregates as well which are generally encountered in the practical problems of interest. The results thus obtained by running the simulation using Aerosolved solver are discussed in the following section and will be compared with the results from DyAerosolved in future.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The evolution of aerosol mass concentration profile predicted by Aerosolved shows a similar trend as observed during experiments carried out by Sapra et al (2008) (Fig. 1). The mass concentration observed at the lower port is higher as compared to the upper port as the settling of aerosols leads to migration of these aerosols from higher height to a lower part in the spatial domain. However, there is a difference in the absolute values and the rate of reduction of aerosol mass concentration. This difference may be attributed to the uncertainties in the measurement of aerosol metrics near the release point and fact that the aerosols are assumed to be spherical in the present results. These aerosols are observed to be fractals during the measurements. To account for this, the correction has been incorporated and the case is being studied using the developed solver DyAerosolved.

Figure 1. Evolution of aerosol mass concentration in NATF chamber using CFPD code and comparison with experimental observations

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights the importance of a CFPD code and the necessity to incorporate corrections for the non-spherical nature of the aerosol aggregates for realistic estimates of aerosol concentration in a containment-like environment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge Dr D K Aswal, Director, HS&EG for his support, Dr Rudra and Dr Thaseem, IIT-Goa for useful technical discussions and suggestions.

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ASSESSING ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL POLLUTANTS SUSTAINABLE MITIGATION SCENARIOS TO MAXIMISE CLIMATE AND HEALTH CO-BENEFITS OVER THE INDIAN SUBCONTINENT: INTEGRATED MODELLING FRAMEWORK FOR SHORT-LIVED AEROSOL POLLUTANTS REGIONAL CLIMATIC IMPACTS ASSESSMENT AND SUSTAINABLE MITIGATION (IMPACTS)

SHUBHA VERMA¹, SHUBHAM PATEL¹ AND SRILEKHA VALASANI¹

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, West Bengal

Email: shubha@iitkgp.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Climate-Health Co-Benefits, Sustainable Mitigation, Combustion-Derived PM, Aerosol-Rainfall Interactions

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosol pollutants have a short atmospheric residence time in the troposphere varying only from a few days to a few weeks. Hence, in comparison to the greenhouse gases that are long-lived and therefore provide well-known global warming impacts being distributed rather uniformly across the globe; aerosols are largely concentrated near their emission sources and hence have the ability to exert a strong regional impact. Moreover, aerosols' climatic interactions are complex and highly uncertain, being classified with medium to low-level understanding in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Sixth Assessment Report. The complexity arises due to their ability to exert both the radiative cooling and heating of the atmosphere mainly governed by their large varying optical properties in space and time due to the variety of sources for different species, their short residence time, the large influence of prevailing meteorological conditions, and the various and complex aerosol dynamic processes. The short atmospheric residence time of aerosol pollutants prompts for regulation of their sustainable mitigation to achieve crucial climate and air quality co-benefits. Thereby demanding a proper scientific understanding of regional aerosol-climate response through fulfilling the technological requirements for efficiently reducing the adversity of regional climatic impacts and associated societal risks. An adequate technology is indeed required to meet challenges in the implementation of a judiciously designed sustainable mitigation of atmospheric pollutants taking into account potential trade-offs between management of air quality and climatic impacts over the Indian region. An efficient technological setup is nevertheless timelier required to assess the above-mentioned trade-offs for decision-making with the ongoing Government of India plans, such as Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY) for clean energy, or restricted open biomass burning, and coal combustion in industries. To address the research gaps and technological requirements, an Integrated Modelling framework for short-lived aerosol Pollutants regional Climatic impacts assessment and Sustainable mitigation (IMPACTS) is designed and assessed for aerosols-climate response and sustainable mitigation accounting for health benefits over the Indian subcontinent.

METHODS

The IMPACTS comprise an optimised aerosols-climate response module and aerosols-sustainability module. It is powered by various indigenously developed datasets and tools (with Aerosols air quality Climate Research Group supervised by S. Verma at IIT-Kharagpur,

(ACRG-IITKGP), <http://www.facweb.iitkgp.ac.in/~shubhaverma/graduates-shubhaverma-ACRG.html>) aiding to addressing sustainability perspectives of atmospheric pollution control over the Indian region. The novel and unique features of IMPACTS aerosol-climate response module include (i) configuration of the regional chemistry transport model, CTM (CHIMERE) coupled with a meteorological driver (Weather Research and Forecasting model., WRF) with the optimised schemes identified from aerosol chemistry transport modelling studies done and their implementation at IIT-Kharagpur. The IMPACT's capacity to adequately represent the spatially varying aerosol species burden and climatic response is boosted by coupling with a novel and an indigenously designed dynamic constrained emissions model to provide spatially and temporally resolved observation-constrained source-sector wide anthropogenic emissions of aerosol species over the Indian region. The aerosols-sustainability module of IMPACTS presently comprises inputs from the (i) aerosol-climate response module (discussed above); an indigenously developed (ii) aerosols-health-impact model; and (iii) prioritised clean air assessment tool (PCAT).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The health impacts attributable to ambient combustion-derived anthropogenic aerosols (e.g. black carbon aerosols, BC) are assessed in IMPACTS (Verma et al., 2022) in terms of population exposures to BC concentration and cardiovascular disease mortality (CVM) burden over the densely populated Indo-Gangetic plain (IGP). The spatial mapping of the relative risk (RR) factor implies that all populations living in the IGP, including those in rural areas, are at risk of BC-attributable health effects. Population exposure to BC is notable, with more than 60 million people identified as living in hotspots of BC concentration (wintertime mean $>20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The CVM burden can be reduced by a factor of 2 to 4 times more in most of the IGP or as large as 10 times or more in the northern IGP (including parts of Punjab/Haryana) by applying control of BC pollutants than that of targeting PM_{2.5} mass concentration. More than 400,000 lives can potentially be saved from CVM annually by implementing prioritized emission reduction from the combustion of domestic biofuel in the semi-urban area, diesel oil in transportation, and coal in thermal power plant and brick kiln industries in megacities. Furthermore, aerosol rainfall interactions using IMPACTS indicates aerosols drive monsoon rainfall spatial modulations (weakening and strengthening) over Indian region. A striking feature is a concordance of the spatial modulations (weakening and strengthening) in monsoon rainfall as modelled due to aerosols with the corresponding modulations from measurements. Our study shows the control of anthropogenic aerosols (see Figure 1) would aid in compensating the deficient rainfall or dry spell features by about 20% to 40% over the eastern coast. We also identify areas within the identified rainfall-excessive regions with augmented rainfall excessiveness driven by anthropogenic aerosol control (e.g. over Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Gujarat regions) including areas over the Arabian Sea.

CONCLUSIONS

Our study, therefore, suggests that atmospheric pollutants mitigation scenarios under various Govt. of India policies should be adequately assessed, accounting for the potential trade-off between air quality management and aerosol climate response. Thereby potential future challenges in action-response strategies for the policy-maker towards climate health co-benefits to the Indian population.

Figure 1: Anthropogenic aerosols control and associated water management

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WRF-CHEM SIMULATION OF TRANSPORT OF AEROSOLS AND TRACE GASES IN NORTHERN INDIA DURING SUMMER & WINTER SEASON

HIMANGI TRIPATHI¹, UJJWAL KUMAR² AND VIKAS SINGH²

¹Doon University, SENR, Dehradun – 248001, India.

²CAMQ, MOEFCC, Delhi, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, WRF-CHEM, PM10, Simulation

INTRODUCTION

The Weather Research and Forecasting model coupled with chemistry (WRF-CHEM) has been extensively used for analyzing the spatio-temporal distribution and forecasts of aerosols and trace gases (e.g., Tuccella et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2014). In India, the researchers have explored the application of WRF-CHEM in the Indian region, e.g., Sharma et al. (2016) highlighted the significant impact of aerosols on regional air quality in Northern India. Gupta et al. (2018) investigated the seasonal variability of aerosol properties in relation to meteorological conditions. Kumar et al. (2020) demonstrated the role of dust storms in influencing aerosol concentrations, emphasizing the need for a robust understanding of these phenomena. While previous research has provided valuable insights and improved our understanding of air pollutants distribution, the high-resolution WRF-CHEM simulation with desired accuracy of air pollutants spatial-temporal distribution is still a challenge, particularly, for the Indian region. This study aims to evaluate the WRF-CHEM simulation at 15x15 km for significant aerosols and trace gases in Northern India during both the summer and winter seasons.

METHODS

The WRF-CHEM model was used to simulate aerosol concentrations over Northern India in 2015. WRF-Chem integrates meteorology and chemistry for regional air quality simulations (Grell et al., 2005). Meteorological inputs were sourced from NCEP's FNL Operational Global Analysis at 6-hour intervals with a 1° resolution. Chemical boundary conditions were derived from CAM-Chem. The model domain covered India at 45x45 km, with a nested domain for Northern India at 15x15 km resolution. Anthropogenic emissions were obtained from EDGAR-HTAP while gas-phase chemistry was modelled using RADM2-GOCART (Stockwell et al., 1990). Biogenic emissions were included via the MEGAN model (Guenther et al., 2006), and fire emissions were from the FINN dataset (Wiedinmyer et al., 2011).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig 1 presents the WRF-CHEM simulated spatial and temporal variability of PM10 concentrations over the Indo-Gangetic Plains (IGP) in 2015 showing significant seasonal patterns. During winter, particularly in Oct, Nov and Dec, PM10 levels exceeded 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in southern IGP, driven by meteorological conditions trapping pollutants and emissions from various sources. During pre-monsoon from March to May, moderately high concentrations persisted in the northwestern part of IGP, largely due to dust storms and anthropogenic activities, with more widespread pollution. Monsoon season shows lower PM10 concentrations due to monsoon rains. Few areas represent significantly higher PM10 levels. This could indicate that there might be localized emissions from sources like biomass burning, industries, or traffic, which contribute to elevated PM10 levels in some regions. During post-monsoon the PM10 levels rose again, especially in northern IGP, due to crop

burning, industrial emissions, and poor atmospheric dispersion.

Fig1: Spatio temporal distributions of monthly mean concentrations of PM10 from January to December 2015.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates the spatio-temporal distribution of average PM10 for the year 2015. The significant pockets of high PM10 concentration have emerged during the study indicating the presence of various hotspots of air pollution in the region. Though the present study focuses on PM10, the simulation has also been carried out for most of the important air quality parameters such as O₃, NO₂, PM_{2.5}. Therefore, the study is useful for creating air quality scenario over Northern India. In future, we aim to establish a similar system for the operational air quality forecasting.

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ON SPATIAL HETEROGENEITY OF EFFECTIVE RADIATIVE FORCING OF AEROSOLS

RIDDHIMA BISWAS, SAKSHI & ANGSUMAN MODAK

Centre for Climate Studies, IIT Bombay, Mumbai – 400 076, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Climate Interactions, Effective Radiative Forcing, Spatial Pattern, Twomey and Albrecht Effects

INTRODUCTION

A change to Earth's atmospheric composition such as increased concentration of greenhouse gases and aerosols, acts as a perturbation to dislodge the planetary balance leading to climate change. Radiative forcing is a metric to quantify the strength of this perturbation: a positive radiative forcing causes climate warming while a negative induces cooling. Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF) is a recently accepted widely used metric to quantify radiative forcing. It is the net change in the energy budget at the top of the atmosphere (TOA) after allowing the land and the atmosphere to adjust but before the sea-surface temperature changes.

Aerosols can scatter as well as absorb the incoming solar radiation which would A) decrease the radiation reaching the surface and cause a cooling: direct effect, B) heat the atmospheric layers consequently altering the vertical stability: semi-direct effect, C) modulate precipitation through interactions with cloud: indirect effect, such as by acting as cloud condensation nuclei or as ice nucleating particles, they enhance the cloud albedo (Twomey, 1974) and the cloud lifetime through precipitation suppression (Albrecht, 1989). Unlike greenhouse gases, aerosols are not well-mixed in the atmosphere and have a spatially heterogeneous distribution. The spatial variability is driven by several factors: emission sources predominantly in the Northern Hemisphere, short atmospheric residence times, aerosol types, and the associated microphysical processes. Here, we investigate the spatial variability in the net TOA imbalance and ERF due to aerosols. We focus on studying the primary factors that govern their spatial distribution. Understanding what drives positive or negative trends in the magnitude of aerosol-induced TOA imbalance and ERF would unfold the cause for regional climate change and help design apt policies for sustainable development.

MODELS & METHODS

We apply a set of 9 Earth System Models (ESMs) that participated in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project version 6 (CMIP6). It is to be noted that although they are CMIP6 ESMs, some of them have prescribed aerosol modules while some have aerosol emission as the aerosol input type. We consider it to be an opportunity to differentiate the models based on the aerosol input type. We use “historical” (all anthropogenic forcing evolves over the historical period 1850-2014) and hist-piAer (same as “historical” but aerosols are fixed at pre-industrial levels) simulations to estimate the historical evolution of net TOA imbalance. We use piClim-control (prescribed-SST simulations with pre-industrial level forcing) and piClim-aer (same as piClim-control but aerosol forcing is set to 2014 levels) to estimate the ERF due to aerosols.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We find that the spatial distribution of the trend in the net TOA radiative flux change is

coherent among the models: a negative trend over South Asia while a positive trend in North American and European regions co-located with the emission source locations. Similarly, we find a negative trend over North Pacific while a positive in the north Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 1). We attribute the trends over the land regions to the direct and semi-direct effects as the clear-sky fluxes nicely capture the trends while the trends over the oceanic regions are captured by the cloud-sky fluxes (both not shown here).

Trend of Change in TOA imbalance for 1950-2014 due to aerosols(historical - hist-piAer) all_sky

Figure 1. The trend in the change in net radiative flux at TOA (Wm^{-2} per 30 years) because of the historical evolution of aerosols from 1950-2014. Stippling shows trends significant at 95% confidence interval.

On the other hand, we find negative global mean ERF due to aerosols ranging from -0.63 to $-1.47 Wm^{-2}$ across the models indicating a cooling of the climate system. The spatial distribution shows strong forcing where the emission sources are located but some models which have aerosol emission modules, simulate a negative forcing over north Pacific region. Here as well we segregated the ERF in terms of clear-sky and cloud-sky and found that remote forcing is associated with cloud-sky fluxes. We find this to be associated with aerosol indirect effects. A higher forcing at high latitude regions due to indirect effects points to its higher efficacy (Huusko et al. 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

This study indicates that the spatial variability in the ERF or the net TOA radiative flux change can be attributed to indirect effects, also known as the aerosol-cloud interaction. While the direct effect causes cooling in South-East Asia but causes a warming over the European and North American regions, the indirect effect results in a negative trend in North Pacific and positive in the North Atlantic Ocean. Similarly, a close look at the ERF distribution (not shown here) shows again the influence of indirect effects on the oceans. Our study necessitates delving deeper into separating the aerosol effect on the climate system.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

AM & RB acknowledges the funding support provided by the Science and Engineering Research Board Start-up Research Grant (SERB SRG), file no. SRG/2023/000886, which is now part of the Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF).

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CFD SIMULATION TO STUDY THE IMPACT OF VARIOUS VENTILATION PATTERNS ON AIR BORNE PATHOGENS IN AN INDOOR ENVIRONMENT

MARIAM¹, MANISH JOSHI¹, PS RAJAGOPAL², SHAKIL AHAMAD¹, ARSHAD KHAN¹, AND BK SAPRA¹

¹Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai
²ACRi Infotech Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore-560037, India

KEYWORDS: CFD, Bioaerosol, Ventilation, Indoor Environment

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 highlighted the need for research pertaining to the mitigation ways for airborne pathogens/bioaerosols. Airborne transmission of many diseases including COVID-19 has been supported by many scientific studies (Yang et al., 2011; Mariam et al., 2021). Aerosol particles depending on their sizes may remain suspended for a long time in an enclosed environment and hence pose a threat to people in that space. Complex interplay between fluid dynamics of indoor ventilation and expiration events from infected persons might affect the strategies to mitigate the transmission of the disease (Bourouiba 2020). The risk can be minimized by the use of proper ventilation inside the enclosed space. This study uses computation fluid dynamics (CFD) to simulate the dynamics of the particles emitted by the infected person to study the transmission of aerosols in an indoor environment for varying ventilation patterns and respiratory mechanisms.

METHODOLOGY

The simulation using CFD (ANSWER CFD) was done for a 4 m x 4m x 3m room with two occupants, one infected person and one susceptible person distanced by 2 m under 03 ventilation conditions viz., ceiling sidewall, ceiling and open ventilation (Figure 1) with the 4 ACH (air changes per hour). The respiratory droplets emitted by the infected person during the 04 events were considered viz., coughing, sneezing, normal talking and loud talking. For each combination of ventilation and respiratory event, an initial steady flow was obtained and then coupled with particle transport simulation. Input aerosol and respiratory events parameters were taken from the existing literature.

Fig 1. Arrangement of Human models and Inlet-Outlet configurations for 03 ventilation patterns: (a) Standing, Ceiling-Floor (b) Standing, Ceiling-Ceiling (c) Standing, Windows-Door

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Obtained results were segregated based on the respiratory events and the effect of the ventilation pattern was compared for all 04 events. Fig 2 shows the temporal evolution of the integral number concentration of aerosol particles reaching the second human (receiver) at 2 m. CFD analysis makes it possible to visualize the evolution of particles and their transportation to the receiver.

Fig 2. Temporal evolution of integral number concentration of aerosol particles reaching second human (receiver) for (a) Coughing (b) Sneezing (c) Normal talking (d) Loud talking

As can be seen from figure 2, open and ceiling side wall ventilation is effective for particle mitigation in case of sneezing. Whereas, for coughing and normal talking open ventilation poses a hazard for an initial 300-400 s. Amongst these 03-ventilation patterns, the ceiling sidewall provides the best protection for all respiratory events except loud talking. For loud talking, none of these ventilation patterns are sufficient to mitigate particles reaching the receiver. This might be attributed to the high ejection air flow rate during loud talking. Therefore, despite having proper ventilation in the room, there is a probability of transmission from an infected person which should be taken care of.

CONCLUSION

CFD simulations were performed to study the transmission of aerosols in an indoor environment representative of a typical small office room space, for varying inlet-outlet positions and respiratory mechanisms corresponding to standing positions. Input aerosol and

exit-air parameters were taken from the existing literature. The disappearance of number concentration at the receptor location and the features seen in evolution profiles could be interpreted based on the room airflow pattern and its interplay with the airflow changes induced due to the events

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MOS₂-DERIVED MXENE FOR ALCOHOL SENSING AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

KAVITA MISHRA ¹, SAURABH RAWAT ², HIMANI SHARMA ², CHARU DWIVEDI ^{1*}

¹ School of Physical Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Doon University, Dehradun

² School of Physical Sciences, Department of Physics, Doon University, Dehradun

KEYWORDS: Two Dimensional, Mxene, Nanocomposite, Sensor

INTRODUCTION

The development of sensors for detecting volatile organic compounds (VOCs) aerosols is essential for advancing environmental protection. In recent years, ethanol has been widely promoted as a vehicle fuel component for several reasons, including decreasing dependence on fossil fuels, lowering emissions that contribute to global warming, and reducing ambient levels of various air pollutants. The increased use of ethanol affects "criteria" pollutants, such as ozone, for which the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has established National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). Additionally, ethanol emissions impact air toxics-pollutants known to cause both cancerous and non-cancerous health effects. Gas-phase ethanol contributes to air pollution by forming ozone through acetaldehyde oxidation, producing peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN) in high NO_x areas, and affecting the atmosphere's oxidation capacity through its reactivity with hydroxyl radicals, making ethanol sensing imperative for air quality monitoring [1]. Two-dimensional materials have attracted extensive attention and research due to their large specific surface area and high carrier mobility [2]. Among many 2D materials, the MXene family has been extensively utilized to enhance and customize sensor designs, offering a large surface area, adjustable surface chemistry, excellent electrical conductivity, chemical stability, compatibility with flexible substrates, and potential for multifunctional applications. Moreover, MXenes can be synthesized in various forms, including films, layered structures, fibrous membranes, and gel-like configurations, which generate synergistic effects that significantly improve gas-sensing performance [3]. MoS₂, with its graphene-like structure, has gained significant attention due to its excellent electrical conductivity, large specific surface area, stability, strong adsorption capabilities, and high reactivity. However, MoS₂-based gas sensors face challenges such as low sensitivity and prolonged response times [4]. Incorporating other nanomaterials, such as semimetals/metals metal oxides other metal carbides (MCs), and conducting polymers into metal carbides (MCs) to create a heterostructure complex has proven to be an effective approach for enhancing sensing performance at room temperature. Recent studies indicate that Ti₃C₂ MXene and MXene-based nanohybrids exhibit strong performance as gas sensors for ethanol detection. For instance, Tripathi et al. synthesized MXene and fabricated a pure MXene sensor on an FTO electrode for ethanol detection, which demonstrated fast response and recovery times, high sensitivity, and long-term stability at room temperature [5]. In this work, a flexible sensing element was created by incorporating MoS₂ with a Ti₃C₂ MXene. The synergistic interaction between MoS₂ and Ti₃C₂ MXene enabled the sensor to demonstrate high sensitivity, selectivity, and environmental stability for ethanol detection at room temperature.

METHODS

In this study, a 2D MoS₂-MXene nanocomposite was successfully prepared by hydrothermal method. The prepared sample was analyzed by various characterization techniques such as FE-SEM, FTIR, XRD and Raman spectroscopy. Gas sensing elements were fabricated from 2D MoS₂-MXene and gas sensitivity tests were carried out to detect different concentrations of ethanol at room temperature.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

MXene-based gas sensor exhibits great capabilities in the field of gas sensing, especially for room-temperature gas detection. Figure 1 (a) shows the FE-SEM image of MXene and (b) shows the response plot of the MXene-MoS₂ toward 10 ppm ethanol at room temperature demonstrating its repeatable, fast gas response and recovery.

Figure 1. (a) FE-SEM image of multilayered MXene (b) Gas-sensing response of MXene-MoS₂ towards ethanol

CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results show that the gas sensor made from MoS₂-MXene holds great potential for detecting VOC gases, making it a promising candidate for efficient VOC gas sensing applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge DST for the INSPIRE fellowship [DST/INSPIRE Fellowship/2020/IF200420] and DST PURSE (Project no. SR/PURSE/2023/199) for providing the financial support.

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THEME 8 : AEROSOL-CLOUD RADIATION INTERACTIONS

THE IMPACT OF HYDRATED AEROSOLS AND FOG DROPLETS ON VISIBILITY DEGRADATION IN NEW DELHI, INDIA.

P. CHOUDHURY¹, S. WAGH² AND S.D GHUDE²

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, MH, India 411008

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Fog, Haze, Visibility, Mie Scattering.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) experiences prolonged and dense fog during winter which considerably impacts to air traffic and other economic aspects. The present study delves into the contributions of aerosols and fog droplets that result in low visibility (Vis). The study employed Mie theory to calculate light extinction due to hydrated aerosols and fog droplets at Indira Gandhi International Airport, New Delhi.

METHODS

Data was collected at IGI Airport from December 2017 - January 2018. A Fog Monitor (FM-120) was deployed to measure fog droplet sizes and concentration in 30 bins. SMPS particle counter that measured aerosol size distribution; and a visibility meter for atmospheric visibility measurements. Extinction coefficients for aerosols and fog droplets were established using the Mie scattering theory. Extinction coefficients for aerosols were measured at wavelengths of 450 nm, 532 nm, and 637 nm while fog droplets were measured at 532 nm.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Aerosol Contribution to Visibility Reduction

Aerosols, particularly below 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}), significantly obscure light through scattering and absorption of light. This phenomenon becomes pronounced when humidity is high, as aerosols begin to absorb water grow in size and scatter more light. In the present study aerosols alone accounted for 81.56% of total extinction during haze. Among all the 8 events, on the 2nd and 27th January 2018, noted the visibility reduction below 500m even without the presence of significant fog suggesting 100% of the attenuation is due to aerosols, whereas the remaining days a contribution above 50% even during the dense fog phase. Safai et al., 2017 and Tiwari et al., 2015 showed major inputs were black carbon and sulphate coming from anthropogenic sources because of their long-term presence in the atmosphere and high capacity for scattering and absorbing light.

Fog Droplet Contribution to Visibility Reduction

Despite the small number compared to aerosols, fog droplets had a profound impact on visibility in foggy regimes. During instances of dense fog (Vis < 200m) fog droplets contributed about 41.50% to total extinction. The longest fog duration observed on 4th January 2018, showed the highest droplet extinction coefficient up to 69.95%, whereas during other days, the coefficient percentage stayed remain below 50%. Nevertheless, during periods of thick fog events, the role of aerosol particles remained significant because these droplets require them to serve as condensation nuclei for accumulation and droplet growth.

Diurnal Variations

A clear tri-phase pattern is exhibited by the aerosol extinction coefficient, they rise during the day, peak in the late afternoon, and fall towards night-time. Solar radiation, heat activity, and

photochemical processes facilitate aerosol suspension and mixing during the day, influencing the trend. At night temperature inversions and nocturnal stability reduce extinction coefficients, while increases in photochemical reactions during the daytime contribute to mid-day peaks. The extinction that is started by the start of a day is furthered by the rise in aerosol concentration brought on by the morning warming.

Condition	3 rd Jan2018	4 th Jan2018	7 th Jan2018	19 th Jan2018	28 th Jan2018
Haze	-	6.00%±0.01	26.35%±0.15	20.89%±0.12	20.53%±0.98
SevereHaze	31.38%±0.81	10.28%±0.03	19.51%±0.16	25.93%±0.19	24.55%±1.43
ModerateFog	38.28%±0.32	19.77%±	21.19%±	21.01%±0.09	12.85%±0.56
Fog	30.34%±0.58	69.95%±	32.95%±0.25	32.17%±0.21	42.08%±2.81
	%	4.50%	%	%	%

Table 4: Ratio of attenuation of light due to droplet to that of aerosol in percentage.

Figure 1: Representative plot for (A) Droplet extinction coefficients (B) Aerosol extinction (C) Box plot for Aerosol extinction coefficient during different visibility regime (D) Droplet extinction coefficient, for the case of 4th January 2018.

CONCLUSIONS

To a large extent, the present study highlights aerosols' contribution to the decline in visibility in New Delhi when there are severe haze cases. Fog droplets make it worse but they do not have as much impact on this compared to aerosol components and fine particulate matter during intense haze events. Aerosols facilitate fog droplet creation; on the other hand, they can also support the dropping of visibility because of their ability to collect out different visible particles. In summary, we found that visibility reduction due to aerosols was dependent on more than just the concentration of aerosols, atmospheric states, mixing processes, and relative humidity also contributed. In contrast, fog droplet extinction coefficients exhibited a more pronounced contribution during dense fog.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my gratitude to the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES) and the Director of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology (IITM) for their very essential help and resources.

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RADIATIVE FORCING DUE TO AEROSOL INDIRECT EFFECT OVER THE NORTHERN INDIAN OCEAN

H. KUMAR^{1,2}, S. TIWARI^{*1,2}

¹Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

² Aerosol and Cloud Research Lab, Geological Oceanography Division, CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, India.

*Email: stiwari@nio.res.in

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud Interactions, Radiative Forcing, Cloud Radiative Effect, Indian Ocean.

INTRODUCTION

Despite numerous scientific endeavours made during the last five Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) assessment cycles, including in-situ field campaigns, satellite measurements and climate models, our understanding of aerosol and cloud effect on Earth's climate is still highly uncertain (Figure 1). A major source of this uncertainty arises from the extreme spatial and temporal variability in cloud cover and aerosol composition (Boucher et al., 2013). Global estimates of the radiative forcing associated with the Aerosol Indirect Effect (AIE) often averaged regional variations. However, in regions with pronounced seasonality in cloud cycles and aerosol compositions, the magnitude and sign of radiative forcing can differ significantly from the global mean estimate. With this consideration, we estimated the contribution of AIE to radiative forcing over the Northern Indian Ocean (NIO). The NIO, bordered by the densely populated South and Southeast Asian landmasses, experiences significant seasonality in both aerosol loading and composition (Kumar and Tiwari, 2023; 2024), making it an ideal region for studying AIE.

Figure 1: Global mean estimates (at 90% confidence level) of radiative forcing (in Wm⁻²) due to Aerosol Radiation Interactions (ARI) and Aerosol Cloud Interactions (ACI), from five successive IPCC assessment reports.

DATA AND METHODS

This study utilizes Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) SSF1deg Edition-4A daily top-of-atmosphere radiative fluxes (Doelling et al., 2016), while low-level liquid cloud fraction data is from MODIS C6.1 level-3 daily gridded product (Platnick et al., 2017). To estimate the radiative forcing due to AIE, we applied the approach of estimating the sensitivity of liquid cloud albedo and liquid cloud fraction with respect to the variation in aerosols following Christensen et al., (2016). The estimates of AIE decomposed into 'intrinsic forcing' (i.e., radiative forcing due to cloud albedo effect) and 'extrinsic forcing' (i.e., radiative forcing due to cloud fraction adjustment).

RESULTS

The annual mean intrinsic forcing is about 17% higher over the BoB than the AS, while extrinsic forcing is 3% higher over the AS (Table 1). Seasonally, intrinsic forcing dominates over the AS in winter and post-monsoon, but it is higher over the BoB during pre-monsoon and monsoon. Extrinsic forcing is greater over the BoB during winter and monsoon, whereas it is higher over the AS in pre- and post-monsoon. In comparison, radiative forcing from cloud adjustment is noted to dominate over the cloud albedo effect, particularly in winter and post-monsoon season.

Season	Arabian Sea (AS)		Bay of Bengal (BoB)	
	Intrinsic	Extrinsic	Intrinsic	Extrinsic
Annual	-0.41 ± 0.37	-0.66 ± 0.39	-0.48 ± 0.52	-0.64 ± 0.68
Winter	-1.06 ± 0.96	-3.91 ± 2.50	-1.01 ± 1.32	-4.08 ± 2.52
Pre-Monsoon	-0.33 ± 0.25	-0.37 ± 0.45	-0.50 ± 0.47	-0.25 ± 0.85
Monsoon	-0.07 ± 0.21	-0.38 ± 0.43	-0.22 ± 0.42	-1.04 ± 1.28
Post-Monsoon	-0.96 ± 1.07	-1.93 ± 1.61	-0.58 ± 0.82	-1.72 ± 2.19

Table 1. Domain averaged intrinsic forcing (cloud albedo effect) and extrinsic forcing (cloud fraction adjustment) components of AIE, in Wm^{-2} , for the period of 2003-2021.

CONCLUSIONS

In both annual and seasonal estimates, extrinsic forcing is noted as outweighing intrinsic forcing across the domain. Together, intrinsic (cloud albedo effect) and extrinsic (cloud adjustment effect) forcing components of AIE were found to exert negative shortwave forcing over the NIO during the study period.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, and the University Grant Commission. We acknowledge the CERES and MODIS science team for providing an open dataset used here.

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PM₁ AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS AND ITS ASSOCIATED DIRECT RADIATIVE FORCING AT AN URBAN STATION JAIPUR

A. GUPTA¹, A. K. SRIVASTAVA² AND C. JHAMARIA²

¹Department of Environmental Science, IIS (deemed to be University), Jaipur, India-302020

²Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, New Delhi, India-

KEYWORDS: Composite Aerosols, PM₁ And Direct Radiative Forcing

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols, including particulate matter (PM), play a significant role in the Earth's climate system and have direct implications for both air quality and human health (Boucher, 2015; Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). Among the different size fractions of particulate matter, PM₁ (particles smaller than 1 μm) is of particular interest due to its ability to penetrate deep into the respiratory system, causing severe health risks (Ramanathan & Carmichael, 2008). PM₁ also affects atmospheric processes, as these fine particles remain suspended in the air for longer periods, contributing to the scattering and absorption of solar radiation, which alters the Earth's energy balance (Schmale et al., 2014). This study focuses on PM₁ and black carbon (BC) concentrations in Jaipur, a rapidly growing city in Rajasthan, India, from October 2018 to June 2019. The research aims to understand the seasonal variability of PM₁ and BC, examining their physical, optical, and radiative impacts during different seasons. This investigation provides valuable insights into the role of these aerosols in local atmospheric conditions, radiative forcing, and potential effects on public health and regional climate patterns (Srivastava & Tripathi, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted over nine months, from October 2018 to June 2019, with daily measurements of PM₁ mass concentration collected using a high-volume air sampler. The concentration of water-soluble aerosols and the elemental and organic carbon content were analyzed (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 550 nm was measured using both ground-based and satellite instruments to assess the optical properties of the aerosols. Aerosol Radiative Forcing (ARF) was calculated using radiative transfer models at three levels: surface (ARFS), top of the atmosphere (ARFT), and within the atmosphere (ARFA). ARF values, particularly during pre- and post-monsoon seasons, were used to estimate the warming or cooling effects of aerosols. Additionally, the atmospheric heating rate was calculated from the ARF values to estimate the potential impact on local temperature (Srivastava & Tripathi, 2020).

RESULTS

The mass concentration of PM₁ aerosols ranged from 58.82 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 121.69 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a mean of 85.70 ± 15.56 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Concentrations were significantly higher during the post-monsoon season (43.35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) compared to the pre-monsoon season (23.47 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), likely due to increased fossil fuel combustion and reduced wet scavenging. AOD at 550 nm varied between 0.00 and 1.18, with a mean value of 0.27 ± 0.25 , indicating notable variation in aerosol loading. Surface ARF ranged from -6.50 W/m^2 to -69.90 W/m^2 , with an average of -28.68 ± 16.14 W/m^2 , reflecting surface cooling due to aerosol scattering. ARF at the top of the atmosphere ranged from 1.20 W/m^2 to -25.10 W/m^2 , with an average of -3.68 ± 5.23 W/m^2 . In contrast, ARF in the atmosphere ranged from +4.60 W/m^2 to +63.10 W/m^2 , with a mean of

+25.00 ± 13.27 W/m², indicating atmospheric warming. March recorded the highest atmospheric forcing (38.47 ± 21.38 W/m²) compared to April (13.60 ± 4.85 W/m²), with a corresponding heating rate of 1.08 K Day⁻¹.

DISCUSSION

The study highlights the seasonal variability in aerosol concentration and radiative forcing, with higher PM₁ levels observed post-monsoon, likely due to anthropogenic activities such as increased fossil fuel combustion (Schmale et al., 2014). The negative surface ARF suggests aerosols have a cooling effect by reducing solar radiation reaching the surface. However, the positive ARF in the atmosphere indicates net warming, as aerosols absorb solar radiation and re-emit it as heat, which may affect atmospheric stability and local weather patterns. The higher atmospheric forcing and heating rate in March suggest more intense atmospheric processes, potentially driven by boundary layer dynamics and aerosol load (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). These changes may influence local temperature profiles, contributing to shifts in weather systems such as cloud formation and convection (Ramanathan & Carmichael, 2008; Srivastava & Tripathi, 2020).

CONCLUSION

This study presents the first measurements of PM₁ and BC concentrations in Jaipur, providing key insights into their seasonal variation and radiative effects. The findings suggest that PM₁ and BC contribute significantly to surface cooling while causing warming in the atmospheric column. The seasonal differences in aerosol loading and radiative forcing highlight the impact of human activities on air quality and regional climate, emphasizing the need for effective pollution control measures to mitigate their health and environmental impacts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank our University Vice chancellor.

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EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE VARIABILITY ON RADIATIVE FORCING IN SURAT: INSIGHTS FROM COMPREHENSIVE SATELLITE OBSERVATION

A. M. KURESHI¹, T. TURAKHIA², D. SHAH¹ AND M.R. PANDYA³

¹Sir P.T Sarvajanic College of Science, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat

²Department of Physics and Electronics, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad

³Space Applications Centre, ISRO, Ahmedabad, 380 015, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Radiative Forcing, Surface – Atmosphere Interactions, Satellite Observations.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol radiative forcing is a critical component of the Earth's climate system, reflecting the impact of atmospheric aerosol particles on the planet's energy balance. These aerosols, which are solid or liquid particles suspended in the air, influence the Earth's atmospheric radiation budget by either backscattering or absorbing sunlight, thereby affecting the amount of energy that reaches the surface. The net effect of aerosols on radiative forcing can result in either cooling or warming, depending on their composition, size, and interactions with other atmospheric constituents. This process not only alters atmospheric temperature but also influences cloud formation and its properties, further affecting weather patterns and climate variability. In addition to their direct effects on radiative forcing, aerosols play significant indirect roles as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and ice nuclei (IN). Moreover, certain aerosols, such as dust, exhibit a semi-direct effect by absorbing solar radiation, which can lead to localized heating of the surrounding environment. This heating subsequently alters relative humidity and atmospheric stability, thereby influencing weather patterns and climate dynamics (H.S Joshi et al., 2021).

METHODS

The analysis begins with the collection of aerosol optical depth (AOD) data from the MODIS-Terra satellite (MOD08 v6.1) having a spatial resolution of 10 x 10, focusing on Surat City (21.1702E°,72.8311N°) from 2021 to 2024. This dataset is examined for yearly, monthly, and seasonal trends, allowing for a thorough understanding of the fluctuations in aerosol concentrations and their implications for radiative forcing over time. To simulate atmospheric radiative transfer, the SBDART model is employed. This model incorporates several key parameters related to aerosol properties and atmospheric conditions. Radiative forcing is calculated by analysing the differences in upwelling and downwelling irradiance, using the following formulas:

$$\Delta\text{TOA} = \text{TOA}(\downarrow) - \text{TOA}(\uparrow)$$

$$\Delta\text{SURF} = \text{SURF}(\downarrow) - \text{SURF}(\uparrow)$$

Where, TOA - Top of the Atmosphere, ↓ - downward, ↑ - upward and SURF - Surface

The aerosol radiative forcing at the surface and the top of the atmosphere is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta\text{FTOA}, \text{ SURF} = \text{flux}(\Delta\text{TOA}, \Delta\text{SURF}) \text{ with aerosols} - \text{flux}(\Delta\text{TOA}, \Delta\text{SURF}) \text{ without aerosols}$$

These calculations provide a robust framework for assessing the influence of aerosols on the Earth's radiation balance. By comparing scenarios with and without aerosols, the analysis quantifies the impact of aerosols on energy distribution at the surface, within the atmosphere,

and at the top of the atmosphere. This comprehensive approach enhances our understanding of aerosol interactions with solar radiation, contributing valuable insights for climate modelling and environmental policy.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 (a) - Monthly AOD trends from 2021 to 2024 (b) Comparison of Seasonal Radiative Forcing across atmospheric layers over Surat: 2021 to 2024.

The figure 1a illustrates significant patterns followed every year over a four-year period. On comparing the yearly variations, 2021 has moderate fluctuations whereas in 2022 AOD values are relatively stable values. AOD variability is more pronounced in 2023. The most significant change is seen in 2024, with a sharp rise in AOD during mid-year in the monsoon season. These trends suggest seasonal and year-specific variations in aerosol concentrations, possibly influenced by natural events or human activities. In figure 1b negative values indicate a cooling effect on the climate system while positive values indicate a warming effect. Here, where both radiative forcing values are negative, but the surface radiative forcing ($\Delta FSURF$) is more negative than the top-of-atmosphere radiative forcing ($\Delta FTOA$) - that is, $\Delta FSURF < \Delta FTOA$

CONCLUSIONS

This study examines the influence of AOD on radiative forcing in Surat over a four-year period. By utilizing satellite-derived AOD data, the study aims to deepen our understanding of how aerosol concentrations affect radiative forcing in the urban environment of Surat. The simulated results consistently show negative radiative forcing values at both the TOA and surface levels, indicating a net cooling effect on the climate system. Notably, the $\Delta FSURF < \Delta FTOA$, suggesting a stronger cooling effect at the surface. This pattern is likely linked to higher aerosol concentrations and interactions with cloud cover, particularly during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons. Over the four-year period, a clear trend emerges, with a notable intensification of cooling effects, particularly in 2024, which shows the most significant cooling due to increased aerosol concentrations. These findings offer critical insights into the relationship between aerosols and climate variability in urban settings, helping to understand how aerosol dynamics affect the Earth's radiative budget, highlighting regional implications for climate change and providing important information for climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are very much thankful to NASA GIOVANNI Platform for providing the MODIS TERRA AOD measurements over Surat city. Also grateful to the Space Application Centre

(SAC), ISRO, Ahmedabad for their support.

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HYGROSCOPICITY OF AEROSOL PARTICLES DURING THE WINTER FOG IN NEW DELHI: INSIGHTS FROM HTDMA MEASUREMENTS

C. SHINDE¹, S. WAGH¹ AND S. GHUDE¹

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Pune, India.

KEYWORDS: Hygroscopicity, Kappa, Critical Supersaturation, Fog Aerosol Mass Fraction.

INTRODUCTION

Delhi frequently experiences dense winter fog, impacting transportation and public health. Aerosol hygroscopic growth plays a key role in visibility reduction, as particles absorb water vapour, swell, and scatter light. This study explores how aerosol composition influences hygroscopic behaviour during winter fog events, offering insights into fog formation in New Delhi.

METHODS

Our research focuses on investigating the hygroscopic properties of aerosols using the Humidified Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer (HTDMA) at the India Meteorological Department (IMD) in Delhi. As part of the Winter Fog Experiment (WiFEX) conducted by IITM Pune, comprehensive field campaigns were carried out during the winter of 2024 at IMD Delhi. The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the hygroscopic property of the particles during fog events using HTDMA and correlate it with AMS data, which allows the determination of κ based on the chemical composition of aerosol particles.

The HTDMA operates in constant and varying humidity modes. The varying humidity mode is used in the present study. Aerosol particles with diameters ranging from 100 nm to 800 nm were exposed to varying RH conditions. The RH was varied from 30% to 90%. Using Köhler's theory and the HTDMA data, the hygroscopicity parameter κ was calculated following Equation (Petters & Kreidenweis, 2007). In addition, critical supersaturation was determined.

$$\kappa = (Gf^3 - 1) \left(\frac{\exp\left(\frac{A}{D_d Gf}\right)}{RH} - 1 \right)$$

Atmospheric visibility data were used to identify fog/haze/severe haze events during the campaign. For the corresponding period, aerosol chemical composition was analyzed using Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS) data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Size-Dependent Hygroscopicity

Hygroscopicity increases with the particle size (Figure B). A similar trend of hygroscopicity is also previously observed over Mahabaleshwar in India (Ray et. al. 2023). Required critical supersaturation (SS) decreases as hygroscopicity increases which can be found in Fig. A. SS_{crit} decreases from 100 nm to 800 nm, with fluctuations above 500 nm. We have seen there is little difference in the Fog and Non-Fog aerosols. We are trying to explain the chemical composition.

Impact of Aerosol Composition

Fog aerosols, enriched with organics, display lower κ , as seen in Plot D. Moderate fog events have higher organic concentrations, reducing κ , while shallow fog and haze events, dominated by ammonium and sulfate, maintain higher κ values, enhancing water uptake.

Temporal Variability

Day-to-day changes in κ are illustrated in Plot C, with significant variability, especially on 08-01-2024, which shows a wide range of values, likely due to pollution events or shifting meteorological conditions.

Fog Event Differences

Primary analysis has been shown in Figure D which reveals that different chemical compositions in fog events shallow fog and haze dominated by hygroscopic salts, while shallow fog has higher organic content.

Figure 1: Figure (A) relationship between critical supersaturation and dry particle diameter, Figure (B) variation of kappa with Dry Diameter for fog and non-fog events, Figure (C) variation of kappa over time. Figure (D) mass concentration of aerosol chemical components in different fog events.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates that aerosol size and composition significantly influence hygroscopicity and CCN activation during fog and non-fog conditions. Larger aerosols, particularly in non-fog events, are more efficient CCN due to higher inorganic content, while fog conditions show lower hygroscopicity due to organic aerosol dominance. This temporal and compositional variability in aerosols plays a critical role in fog formation and visibility reduction, with significant implications for air quality and atmospheric processes in wintertime urban environments like New Delhi.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to extend my sincere gratitude to the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES) and the Director of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology (IITM) for their invaluable support and resources.

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ABSORBING AEROSOLS AND ENTRAINMENT MIXING IN REVERSING THE FIRST AEROSOL INDIRECT EFFECT: WINTER INSIGHTS FROM THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

A. KUMAR¹, P. R. SINHA¹, V. KUMAR S. NAIR²

¹Department of Earth and Space Sciences, Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology Thiruvananthapuram– 695547, India.

²Space Physics Laboratory, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Thiruvananthapuram– 695022

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Modis, Aerosol Optical Depth, Entrainment Mixing

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI) is not well understood due to measurement limitations and complex aerosol-meteorology-cloud dynamics. High anthropogenic aerosol loading and shallow non-precipitating warm clouds over the Indo-Gangetic Plains (IGP) during winter provide an opportunity to study ACI. This study analysed multiple satellites and reanalysis data during the winter of 2003-2021 over the Eastern and Western IGP. Numerous evidences validate the occurrence of the reversal of the first aerosol indirect effect (reverse-Twomey effect) and the corresponding warming effect throughout the entire Indo-Gangetic Plains during winter.

METHODS

This study analysed quality-assured collocated Level-2 and Level-3 Moderate Resolution Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Terra and Aqua clouds and aerosols products during winter 2003-2021 over IGP. While minimizing the retrieval uncertainty the shallow non-precipitating warm clouds were screened based on the following screening criteria (i) $4 \mu\text{m} < \text{cloud effective radius (CER)} < 14 \mu\text{m}$, (ii) $4 < \text{cloud optical thickness (COT)} < 28$, (iii) cloud top pressure (CTP) $> 700\text{hPa}$, and (iv) cloud top temperature (CTT) $> 273 \text{ K}$, and the uncertainty in aerosol retrievals caused by fog, clouds etc. is minimized by criteria (i) $0.05 < \text{AOD} < 1.5$, (ii) $\text{AOD}(470\text{nm}) > \text{AOD}(550\text{nm}) > \text{AOD}(660\text{nm})$. To estimate ACI ($-\left[\frac{\partial(\ln\text{CER})}{\partial(\ln\text{AOD})}\right]_{\text{LWP}}$) for, weighted linear regression is applied to aerosol optical depth (AOD) and CER at a fixed liquid water path (LWP). The collocated CERES and MODIS products are utilized to estimate the intrinsic radiative forcing as follows:

$$\text{IRF}_{\text{aci}} = F^{\downarrow} \times \left\{ \frac{\partial\alpha_{\text{clr}}}{\partial(\ln\text{AOD})} - \frac{\partial\alpha_{\text{cld}}}{\partial(\ln\text{AOD})} \right\} \times \overline{CC}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The present study finds the prevalence of a significant reverse-Twomey effect for shallow non-precipitating warm clouds during winter over IGP. The study shows that increasing AOD reduces cloud albedo, particularly influenced by absorptive non-spherical aerosols like dust, supporting the reverse-Twomey effect and impacting regional cloud radiative forcing. The estimated IRF_{aci} values are 1.49 and 1.13 Wm⁻² over the EIGP and WIGP, respectively and attributing this warming effect to the observed reverse-Twomey effect. The analysis also identifies entrainment-driven evaporation as a key pathway contributing to the reversal of the Twomey effect over the IGP. These findings provide insights into aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI) processes at a regional scale, aiding their improved representation in global climate

models.

Figure. Aerosol-cloud

interaction (ACI) estimates for shallow non-precipitating warm clouds over the Eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (EIGP) (red bars) and Western Indo-Gangetic Plain (WIGP) (blue bars) for different quasi-constant liquid water path (LWP). Variation of cloud albedo (α_{cid}) with MISR-retrieved aerosol optical depth (AOD_{MISR}) for (b) small mode fraction (f_s) and (c) non-spherical fraction (f_{nsp}) over EIGP (red bars) and WIGP (blue colour bars). The red and blue curves in (b) represent AOD_{MISR} and (c) represent absorbing aerosol optical depth ($AAOD_{MISR}$) for EIGP and WIGP respectively during winter 2003-2021.

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AEROSOL RADIATIVE FORCING DURING FOG EPISODES OVER RANCHI, INDIA

D. PRAKASH^{1,2,*}, D. BHATTACHARJEE³, J. K. PRASAD⁴, S. K. DAS⁴ AND S.PAYRA³

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Poornima University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

²Office of Sustainability and Green Practices, Poornima University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

³Department of Remote Sensing, Birla Institute of Technology Mesra, Ranchi, 835215

⁴Department of Physical Sciences, Bose Institute, Kolkata, West Bengal, India *

Presenting Author

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, FOG, AOD, Radiative Forcing

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are generally defined as tiny, suspended particles dispersed in the atmosphere, ranging from 0.001 μm to 100 μm in diameter. The small size of these particles combined with other factors such as atmospheric conditions, their composition, etc. decides the residence time of these aerosols which in turn has an effect on the Earth's climate since aerosol particles are known to have a significant and complex role in the Earth's radiation budget (Poschl, 2005; Ramanathan et al., 2006; Pepper., et al, 2015). The effect of aerosols on radiative forcing is difficult to estimate because they exhibit significant differences in their chemical and physical properties due to the type of emission and their source of origin, which are dependent both on space and time (Satheesh et al., 2010). Aerosols can alter the radiation budget by scattering or absorbing the incoming solar radiation and indirectly by acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), modifying the radiative properties of clouds (Yu et al. 2006; Papadimas et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2010).

METHODS

Continuous measurement of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) was carried out from 13th December till 4th January using the MICROTOPS-II sun-photometer, at an interval of 15 minutes for every hour starting from 9:30 AM till 04:00 PM IST. Hourly measurements of Temperature, Pressure, Wind Speed, Wind Direction and Visibility along with 3-hour measurements of Relative Humidity were obtained for the study period from the India Meteorological Department (IMD). The data obtained from the sunphotometer were then diurnally averaged to identify the trend of aerosol optical depth and after comparing with the temporal variations in the meteorological parameters, the foggy and clear days were identified.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Atmospheric conditions such as low temperatures, high relative humidity, light and calm winds along lowered visibility favors the formation of fog in any given region. In this study, such parameters were obtained from the India Meteorological Department (IMD). The foggy periods were identified based on the hourly temporal variations of each parameter that fulfilled the above-mentioned conditions and were also validated with on-site observations. The hourly averaged temperature, relative humidity, visibility, wind speed and wind direction over Ranchi from 13th December 2022 to 4th January, 2023 is shown in Figure 2. In December 2022 six days were identified as foggy days i.e. 18th, 19th, 21st, 26th, 27th and 28th December. Whereas the densest fog events were observed from 1 - 4 January 2023. To distinguish the characteristics of aerosols during foggy and non-foggy days, 14th December

2022 is considered as non-foggy days while the 2nd January 2023 is considered as foggy days.

Table 1: Meteorological conditions during Foggy and Non-Foggy Days

DATE	Condition	Temp (°C)		RH (%)		Wind Speed (Knots)		Visibility (m)	
		Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min
12/14/2022	Non-Foggy Day	26.2	15.4	67	32	8.0	0.0	8000	2500
1/2/2023	Foggy Day	22.4	12.6	91	57	4.0	0.0	2500	800

On the non-foggy, the aerosol radiative forcing (ARF) values are significantly less, at TOA the forcing was -8.41 Wm^{-2} whereas ARF at BOA was -10.9 Wm^{-2} , resulting in the atmospheric forcing to be -2.5 Wm^{-2} . While, during the foggy day, aerosol radiative forcing at TOA was -44.1 Wm^{-2} significantly more than that on the non-foggy day. At the surface (BOA), the forcing value increased tremendously and was -91.5 Wm^{-2} and aerosol radiative forcing at ATM was therefore found to be 47.4 Wm^{-2} .

CONCLUSIONS

The radiative forcing within the atmosphere also surged from 2.50 Wm^{-2} during the non-foggy day to 47.4 Wm^{-2} in the foggy day, contributing to an overall warming (positive) effect on the climate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is partially supported by a grant from the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Govt. of India under the FIST Program 2022 (SR/FST/ES-1/2022/102).

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ACTIVATION PROPERTIES OF AEROSOLS AS CCN DURING FOGGY AND HAZY PERIODS IN POLLUTED URBAN ENVIRONMENT

B. KATRE^{1,*}, S. WAGH² AND S. GHUDE²

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pashan, Pune – 411008, India

* Presenting and Corresponding Author: bhagya.katre@tropmet.res.in

KEYWORDS: Cloud Condensation Nuclei, Activation, Supersaturation Levels, Aerosol Chemical Composition.

INTRODUCTION

Cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) are aerosol particles that facilitate condensation sites and aid in the formation of cloud/fog droplets at a certain level of supersaturation. The distribution and characteristics of CCN influence the microphysical properties of the cloud, cloud lifetime, precipitation, hydrological cycle, and, therefore, the climate. CCN activation at a given supersaturation depends on the particle size, chemical composition, and mixing state of the aerosol particles. Several studies have been carried out on the role of aerosols in clouds, but very few have focused on aerosols as fog condensation nuclei. Northern regions of India experience severe foggy conditions during the winter period (November–January). The present study focuses on the aerosol activation properties in fog and hazy periods and the chemical compositions of aerosol particles in New Delhi. Observations were carried out as part of the Winter Fog Experiment from January 1–15, 2024, at IMD, New Delhi. The aerosol chemical concentration and size distribution were also obtained simultaneously during the measurements, as well as the role of aerosol chemical composition, hygroscopic capacity on activation properties, and their influence under foggy and hazy conditions.

METHODS

The CCN counter was deployed to measure CCN Number concentration under different (SSw). In the current study, aerosol particles were exposed to SSw from 0.05–1 %. The activated droplets formed are counted using an optical particle counter in 20 bin sizes from 0.75–10 μm (Roberts and Nene's, 2005). Later, thirty minutes of average CCN data are used for the calculation. To understand aerosol particles' chemical composition and size distribution, an Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS) was used. The AMS provided detailed data on the mass spectra of aerosols, allowing for the identification and quantification of key chemical species, as well as the assessment of their size distribution across a broad range of particle sizes. The aerosol size distribution of aerosol particles based on their electrical mobility was measured using a Scanning Electrical Mobility Spectrometer (SEMS). The SEMS provides high-resolution data on particle size distribution by classifying particles according to their electrical mobility, offering insights into the size-resolved behaviour of aerosols in the atmosphere.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

CCN Analysis

The CCN size distribution shows the dominance of smaller droplet sizes, especially $< 3 \mu\text{m}$, and a distinctive concentration of droplets around 0.75 and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ shown in Fig. 1. It was also observed that during different fog phases, CCN spectra show variation as well a representative CCN spectra for 12th January shows that shallow fog episodes are accompanied with high CCN activity and droplets were grow up to $6\mu\text{m}$. on other hand CCN activity was decreased during dense fog and moderate fog episodes. Such a shift in the CCN activation is attributed to a chemical reaction that occurs during fog and Haze.

Figure 11 a) CCN activation time series during observation period, b) CCN droplet spectrum during different visibility conditions.

Further, CCN analysis for critical diameter (D_{crit}) reveals that D_{crit} varies with SSw, but interestingly, it never exceeds 200 nm . This implies that Aitken mode particles are active in fog droplet formation, which is against the conventional understanding that large particles participate in fog formation at lower SSw.

Aerosol Chemistry using Aerosol Mass Spectrometer.

The time series analysis of mass concentration obtained from AMS shows an increase in NO_3 during dense and shallow fog. Plenty of nitrate particles generated by the reaction of NO_3 with HC/ H_2O during the fog event mainly came from burning fossil fuels. Whereas in the case of haze, an increase in SO_4 was observed. The sulphate formation may be attributed to the aqueous oxidation of SO_2 by NO_2 , which is key to efficient sulphate formation in haze.

CONCLUSIONS

The primary conclusion highlighted that droplet formation observed at low SSw shows fine mode aerosol particles, too, contribute to fog droplet formation with large aerosols. Moreover, changes in the activation of CCN under different conditions (fog/haze) may be attributed to changes in the chemical composition of aerosols undergoing various reactions in the atmosphere.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Our sincere thanks to the Director of IITM, Pune, for supporting this work. We also thank IMD New Delhi for the logistic and administrative help.

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GLOBAL INSIGHTS ON OPTICAL AND RADIATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF AEROSOLS

K. ANSARI^{1,2}, S. RAMACHANDRAN¹

¹Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad – 380009, India.

²Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, Palaj, Gandhinagar – 382055, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Characteristics, Aerosol Radiative Forcing, AERONET, MERRA-2 Simulation

INTRODUCTION

Significant spatiotemporal variations in aerosol sources and their composition combined with their shorter lifetimes make aerosols the largest contributor to the uncertainty in the total radiative forcing (IPCC, 2021). It is found that uncertainty with aerosol radiative forcing (ARF) is higher in Asia (IPCC, 2021). Thus, the simulation of the radiative and climate impact of aerosols and the climate feedback of the changing aerosol trend over Asia is found to be uncertain because the current climate models, utilized in the latest IPCC assessment, do not accurately capture the observed recent aerosol trends over Asia (Ramachandran et al., 2022). In this context, for the first time, this study examines the regional variations of aerosol optical depth (AOD), single scattering albedo (SSA), absorbing AOD (AAOD), and aerosol radiative effects (ARF and heating rate (HR)) using high-quality Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) datasets during on seasonal and annual scales over Asia, and the rest of the globe. The seasonal and annual validation of Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications-2 (MERRA-2) simulations with AERONET datasets is performed to examine the model performance and provide observational constraints on a global scale.

METHODS

All points, level 2, version 3 cloud-screened, quality-assured, and calibrated AERONET direct Sun measurement of AOD, fine mode fraction (FMF), and inversion product of SSA, AAOD, and ARF (at the surface (SFC) and top of atmosphere (TOA)) are utilized (Holben et al., 2001). A total of 44 sites in Asia (Central: 3, South Asia: 11, Southeast: 8, East: 22), 86 sites in North America, 22 sites in South America, 57 sites in Europe, 13 sites in North Africa, 16 sites in South Africa, 16 sites in the Middle East, and 7 sites in Australia are included in the analysis, covering all four seasons with ≥ 9 months in at least a year. MERRA-2 (0.5°×0.625°) simulated 1-hourly AOD and net shortwave flux with and without aerosols under clear sky conditions are utilized for the collocated validation with AERONET observed AOD and ARF over the globe.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The regional mean AOD is relatively higher over South Asia in each season (>0.4) due to the influence of both fine anthropogenic aerosol emissions and coarse mode dust aerosols from seasonal transport with an annual regional average AOD of 0.61. SSA is lower in Central (0.86) and South Asia (0.90) than in East (0.93) and Southeast Asia (0.94) (Fig. 1). High AOD and low SSA lead to higher AAOD in South Asia, and it is relatively ~50% lower in Southeast and East Asia. This results in higher ARFSFC (~-70 Wm⁻²) and ARFATM (~-40 Wm⁻²), and a high aerosol-induced atmospheric HR (0.80 Kday⁻¹) over South Asia. In comparison, HR is ~50% lower in other Asian regions. On a global scale, AOD (<0.15) and AAOD (<0.02) are significantly lower with higher SSA (>0.90). The ARFSFC (>-20 Wm⁻²)

and ARFATM ($<10 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$) are significantly lower resulting in a low HR ($<0.15 \text{ Kday}^{-1}$) over North America, Europe and Australia. Further, the spatial and temporal variations in aerosol optical and radiative parameters are significantly less over these regions as well. Bias (underestimation) in MERRA-2 AOD increases with a lower Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) fraction for high AOD conditions over all regions, which are more pronounced over Asia (Ansari and Ramachandran, 2024). The underestimation in AOD during high AOD conditions (>0.4) leads to higher biases in ARFSFC, ARFTOA, and ARFATM and these biases are higher in Asia as conditions of high AOD are significantly more frequent.

CONCLUSIONS

The regional and seasonal scale analysis of aerosol columnar characteristics and radiative properties using AERONET datasets across the globe (from a total of 261 sites over 11 regions (Fig. 1)) reveals that AOD, AAOD, ARF, and atmospheric HR are significantly higher over South Asia and their values are $\sim 50\%$ lower

Figure 1: Regional variation of annual mean aerosol optical depth (AOD), fine mode fraction (FMF), single scattering albedo (SSA), absorbing AOD (AAOD), and aerosol-induced atmospheric heating rate (HR; K day^{-1}) over (a) North America, (b) South America, (c) Europe, (d) North Africa, (e) South Africa, (f) Middle East, (g) South Asia, (h) Central Asia, (i) East Asia, (j) Southeast Asia, and (k) Australia. The total number of observational sites in each region is given in brackets. AAOD values are multiplied by 10 to match the scale.

in other regions in Asia. North America, Europe, and Australia experienced low AOD, AAOD, ARF, and HR, and their spatial and temporal variations are also lower. Collocated validation of MERRA-2 simulations with AERONET showed that the biases in simulated AOD and ARF are higher for higher AOD and ARF conditions, and these biases are relatively higher over Asia compared to other regions as high AOD and high ARF conditions are more frequent. These results based on high-quality datasets with model validations on seasonal-, annual- and global scales provide observational constraints, hitherto not available, which are crucial to fine-tune and improving the models, and will be crucial for a more accurate

assessment of the radiative and climate impact of aerosols.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the principal investigators of each AERONET site for establishing and maintaining the AERONET sites. We acknowledge MERRA-2 for the production of simulated data and for maintaining the website.

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EVALUATION OF SIMULATED PRE-MONSOON AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH (AOD) WITH SATELLITE AND GROUND-BASED OBSERVATIONS: IMPLICATIONS OF DUST AND ANTHROPOGENIC AOD OVER INDIA

K. DUBEY¹, S. VERMA¹ AND R. RAY¹

¹Department of Civil Engineering, IIT Kharagpur, Kharagpur -721302, India.

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Optical Depth, India, Modia, MISR, Aeronet

INTRODUCTION

Recent investigations of aerosols from global aerosol multi-models show that forward model simulations are unable to reproduce the ground-based station-observed aerosol optical depth (AOD) and their spatial distribution over the Indian subcontinent. Assessment of aerosol optical properties is a complex process as they exhibit large variability in space and time due to their low atmospheric lifetime, and wide variety in their size and chemical composition (Dubey and Verma, 2024). In addition, the transport of aerosols and seasonal variations cause a change in the optical characteristics of aerosol species due to the variation of the mass extinction coefficient with particle size. During the pre-monsoon season, elevated levels of aerosols are often seen due to dust storms, biomass burning, and anthropogenic activities. Characterized by strong winds aerosol transport is prominent over long distances during the pre-monsoon season and the aerosol interactions specifically during this period can induce modulations in the summer monsoon. Ground-based and satellite observations can provide the aerosol properties with limitations of low spatial coverage and less frequency, respectively. However, chemical-transport models when evaluated against ground and satellite observations, can provide higher spatial and temporal scale information on pollutant emissions, air quality, aerosol radiative forcing, visibility, and global climate change.

METHODS

In the present study we performed high-resolution aerosol transport simulations in a state-of-the-art Eulerian chemistry-transport model, CHIMERE (version 2017). The CHIMERE model is forced externally by the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF-V3.7) model as a meteorological driver in offline mode. Simulations are carried out over the Indian domain (6° N to 38° N and 68° E to 99.25° E) at a horizontal resolution of 0.25° × 0.25°. These simulations are performed at a temporal resolution of 1 h for the pre-monsoon season (March-May, 2015). The optical properties are estimated with OPTical properties SIMulation (OPTSIM) using the 3-dimensional aerosol mass concentration simulated in CHIMERE. OPTSIM is a post-processing tool specially crafted for conducting comprehensive comparisons between aerosol distributions, as predicted by chemistry transport models (CTM), and passive as well as active remote-sensing observations. In OPTSIM, the aerosol optical properties are estimated based on mie theory, considering internal homogeneous mixing. The optical properties are estimated at six wavelengths (440, 500, 532, 550, 870, and 1064 nm) at the same horizontal and temporal resolution as of CHIMERE.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The spatial distribution of monthly mean AOD at 550 (AOD550) nm for the pre-monsoon months: March, April and May are compared with satellite (MODIS and MISR) observations for the year 2015 (Figure 1). A general increasing trend in AOD550 from March to May is

observed as also noticed from MODIS and MISR observations. The spatial pattern of pre-monsoon mean AOD550 showing high values in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP, 0.35-0.4) and eastern coast (0.4-0.5) is consistent with the features of observed AOD550 from satellite retrievals with an under-estimation of 30-40% (10-25%) as compared with MODIS (MISR). The IGP has a higher AOD than most parts of India attributed to high population density and greater emission sources (Verma et al., 2022). High pre-monsoon mean AOD550 values are also estimated over the Indian state of Telangana (0.4-0.5) which consistently matches with both MODIS and MISR retrievals. Assessment from the comparison of simulated AOD550 with the ground-based observations (AERONET and individual measurements) show that although the normalised mean bias (NMB: 21%) is low; the values are consistently underestimated over all the locations considered in the present study. Similar observations of high anthropogenic and dust AOD during May month as compared to March and April are noticed. The dust and anthropogenic contributions as estimated through the constrained simulations suggest the highest contribution of pre-monsoon mean dust AOD in the North-western region (0.3-0.4) followed by upper IGP (0.2-0.26). Simulated pre-monsoon mean anthropogenic AOD is greater than dust AOD over the IGP region. The highest anthropogenic AOD is obtained over central and eastern IGP followed by the east coast of India.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of pre-monsoon mean AOD at 550 nm from (a) constrained simulations, (b) Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), (c) Multi-angle Imaging Spectro-Radiometer (MISR) and their corresponding percentage bias (d,e)

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the tropospheric column AOD simulated by a high-resolution OPTSIM-CHIMERE was evaluated with satellite data and ground-based measurements over India for the pre-monsoon months of 2015. The model captured the general features of spatial variation of AOD at 550 nm with higher values over IGP than most of India as also seen in the satellite observations. The simulated AOD is in good agreement with the satellite observations with slight over-estimation over upper-IGP and southern states of Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. A good association (NME: 21%) is also achieved between simulated AOD and ground-based measurements. Assessment of anthropogenic and dust AOD showed a high influence of anthropogenic aerosols over the IGP region while that of dust over the north-western region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Computing resources and experimental work at the Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur were supported through grants received from the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (Reference No: 14/10/2014-CC (Vol. II)).

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SPATIO-TEMPORAL VARIABILITY OF AEROSOL DIRECT RADIATIVE FORCING OVER THE INDIAN SUBCONTINENT IN THE LAST TWO DECADES

S. SRIVASTAVA¹, S. DEY^{1,2,3}

¹Centre for Atmospheric Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

²Centre of Excellence for Research on Clean Air, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

³Adjunct Faculty, Korea University, Seoul, South Korea

KEYWORDS: Aerosol Radiative Forcing, Clear-Sky, All-Sky, CERES, Aerosol Speciation

INTRODUCTION

The direct perturbation of the Earth's radiation budget by aerosols, quantified through aerosol direct radiative forcing (ADRF), exhibits temporal and spatial variability influenced by changes in aerosol characteristics, atmospheric processes, and changing climate conditions (IPCC 2021). The Indian Subcontinent, recognized as a regional aerosol hotspot (Dey and Di Girolamo 2010), underscores the importance of understanding long-term trends in ADRF, particularly in the context of global initiatives aimed at reducing air pollution (Yang et al 2018). Ground-based ADRF estimates are often limited to specific sites, and the lack of widespread in-situ data makes it difficult to scale these findings to a regional level. The Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) aboard the EOS-Terra satellite has been measuring incoming and outgoing radiation fluxes with high accuracy since 2000, providing valuable data for understanding regional aerosol radiative effects (Rutan et al 2015).

METHODS

We process daily CERES data spanning 22 years (2000-2021), encompassing fluxes under various atmospheric conditions: clear sky (CS – aerosols present, no clouds), pristine (PR – no aerosols, no clouds), all-sky without aerosols (NAER – no aerosols, including clouds), and all-sky (AS – aerosols and clouds, representing actual atmospheric conditions), to calculate ADRF and analyze its spatiotemporal trends. CERES's Model for Atmospheric Transport and Chemistry (MATCH) assimilates AOD at a 550 nm wavelength using data from MODIS Collection 6.1 (Remer et al., 2005), available from Terra since March 2000, and both Terra and Aqua since May 2002. MATCH combines AOD data from the Dark Target (Levy et al 2013) and Deep Blue (Hsu et al 2013) algorithms. We explain the observed variability through changes in aerosol characteristics, utilizing aerosol composition information from MERRA-2 reanalysis data. Additionally, we estimate aerosol radiative forcing efficiency (ARFE) as ADRF per unit AOD.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The study offers a detailed analysis of the long-term spatiotemporal variability of ADRF across the Indian subcontinent, considering both local and regional emission sources, along with meteorological conditions. The mean ($\pm 1\sigma$) atmospheric ADRF over the Indian subcontinent is found to be 8.7 ± 7.7 , 12.6 ± 9.0 , 12.5 ± 9.5 , and 8.9 ± 6.8 W m⁻² for the winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon seasons, respectively, in all-sky conditions. We observe extremely high aerosol-induced atmospheric warming, exceeding 30 W m⁻², over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) under clear-sky conditions, which can be reduced by up to 8 W m⁻² in the presence of clouds. Over the last two decades, ADRF trends at the TOA, within the

atmosphere, and at the surface are observed as $-0.06 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, $0.03 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, and $-0.09 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, respectively over the study region, using 2000 as the baseline. MERRA-2 indicates regional increases in both black carbon and sulfate aerosols, with sulfate aerosols showing a tenfold higher rate of increase compared to black carbon. The distinct trends in ADRF and ARFE highlight the varying impacts of different aerosol types, signalling significant shifts in aerosol composition alongside the total aerosol burden. The increasing effect of scattering aerosols compared to absorbing aerosols results in enhanced TOA cooling efficiency but reduced atmospheric warming and surface dimming efficiency of aerosols.

Seasonal climatology of ADRF in the atmosphere in clear-sky (Top panel) and all-sky (Bottom panel) conditions for 22 years (2000-2021).

CONCLUSIONS

We observe an increasing trend in atmospheric warming, while the aerosols' warming efficiency decreases, likely due to enhanced scattering effects. The observed increase in atmospheric warming, combined with surface cooling, could lead to tropospheric stabilization, which may influence cloud formation. Aerosol-induced surface cooling can also alter weather patterns and atmospheric circulation. Additionally, the rise in scattering aerosols enhances cloud albedo, further intensifying cooling at TOA and the surface. This cooling effect may be masking the warming impact of greenhouse gases (GHGs), potentially creating a false sense of progress in mitigating global warming.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The first author acknowledges the support of the Prime Minister's Research Fellowship (PMRF) from the Government of India. We acknowledge the NASA science team for providing the open-source CERES-SYN1Deg data and MERRA-2 and MODIS aerosol data.

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AEROSOL CLOUD INTERACTION OVER DIFFERENT AEROSOL POLLUTION VULNERABLE ZONES: A LONG-TERM (2005-2019) STUDY IN INDIA

M. DUTTA AND A. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemical Sciences, Bose Institute, EN Block, Sector-V, Saltlake, Kolkata

KEYWORDS: Aerosol-Cloud-Interaction, Twomey Effect; Aerosol Pollution; Indo-Gangetic Plain

INTRODUCTION

The study of ACI poses a significant challenge and remains the most substantial source of uncertainty in assessing the anthropogenic contribution to climate change, as highlighted by the IPCC in 2021. There are ample studies (Leena et al., 2021; Tripathi et al., 2007) suggesting cloud effective radius (CER) tends to decrease with an increase in aerosol concentration however in recent two decades several studies (Khatri et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2018) indicated the opposite phenomena. In India where there is a wide heterogeneity among the aerosol source, and land use pattern, it is evident that the composition and nature of aerosol will vary which will impact the microphysical properties of the cloud. Therefore, the present study has been conducted in different pollution-loading regions of India and is the first-ever of its type where aerosol-cloud interaction was studied over different zones in terms of aerosol pollution in India.

METHODS

Long-term trend and mean were analyzed for CER, Cloud fraction (CF), cloud optical depth (COD) and liquid water path (LWP). In addition, region wise ACI were calculated for three consecutive time periods: 2005-2009, 2010-2014, and 2015-2019 using the equation below:

$$AIE = \frac{d \ln r_e}{d \ln T_a} \quad (1)$$

Depending on the aerosol loading Indian region was classified into four pollution regions: highly vulnerable, vulnerable, less vulnerable and safe zone and then ACI was calculated over these regions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variation of AEI in different LWP regimes and three different phases has been shown in Fig 1. In the highly vulnerable zone, AIE was found to be reduced from the first two phases (2005-2014) to the last phase (2015-2019) as the major sources of aerosol change. Notably, as LWP exceeded 100 g m⁻², the AIE approached zero during the initial two phases but displayed a negative trend in Phase 3. In extremely high LWP conditions (LWP > 170 g m⁻²), a consistent negative relationship, characteristic of the Twomey effect, was observed across all the phases. Over the vulnerable zones, where major sources of aerosols did not change over the years but the relative contributions changed, AIE showed different behaviours. Within a limited LWP range, only a fraction of aerosol particles participated in cloud droplet formation. However, in higher LWP conditions, the presence of negative AIE values indicated that a larger proportion of aerosols could contribute to cloud formation. Yet, in the third phase, the prevalence of absorbing aerosol particles had increased to such an extent that even in higher LWP conditions, aerosols resisted participate in cloud formation.

Fig 1: AIE computed from the slopes of CER versus AOD on the log-log scale stratified in four LWP regimes across three phases in (a) Highly vulnerable and (b) Vulnerable zone, black star shows significant slope

CONCLUSION

This study indicates that, even when the aerosol loading is similar, variations in the nature or types of aerosols (because of the variations in sources) lead to distinct changes in the microphysical properties of clouds.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India for supporting the study under the SPLICE-Climate Change Program (DST/CCP/Aerosol/84/2017/C). Fellowship of M. Dutta was funded by SPLICE-Climate Change Program, DST during the early stage of this study and subsequently by Bose Institute for pursuing the Ph.D.

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UNDERSTANDING THE ROLE OF NUCLEATION IN CCN FORMATION OVER DELHI USING WRF-CHEM MODELLING

BALA. MEDA^{1*}, C. SARANGI¹, B. ZHAO^{2,3}, J. SHEN³,
M. SHRIVASTAVA² AND S. K. SAHU⁴

¹Department of Civil Engineering, IIT Madras, Chennai, India

²Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, Richland, WA 99352, USA

³School of Environment, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

⁴Department of Environmental Science, Berhampur University, Berhampur, India

KEYWORDS: Nucleation, Aerosol Formation, PM₁, Cloud Condensation Nuclei

INTRODUCTION

New particle formation (NPF) is a significant source of atmospheric particles and cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), affecting climate and air quality. Understanding the mechanisms involved in urban aerosols is important to develop effective mitigation strategies (Dunne et al., 2016). In recent years, high new particle formation (NPF) rates have been observed over polluted boundary layers irrespective of very high condensation sink due to pre-existing aerosols (Kulmala et al., 2017). Sub-micron particles (PM₁) play a pivotal role in haze events experienced in Delhi. PM₁ contributes approximately 60 -70% of total PM_{2.5} mass. Modelling is needed to understand the aerosol formation and evolution.

METHODS

We have used WRF Chem, a complex chemical transport model to simulate PM₁ mass over Delhi. The domain of the simulation is centered over Delhi with a spatial resolution of 6 Km. Table 1 shows details of the model configurations. We have selected two different periods for simulations i.e., less polluted (LP) where the daily avg. PM₁ < 50 µg/ m³ and highly polluted (HP) where daily avg. PM₁ > 150 µg/m³. High-resolution local emissions over Delhi city from Sahu et al., (2015) are used for modelling.

Meteorological Input	ERA 5 Reanalysis data
Emissions	Edgar, MICS – Asia & FINN
Chemistry Module	SAPRC – 99 with MOSAIC
NPF scheme	Zhao et al., PNAS, 2020
SOA scheme	Shrivatsava et al., 2019

Table 1. Details of the model inputs and model configurations

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Simulated PM₁ and evaluated against the Gani et al., (2019) ACSM data during both LP (June 26 – July 3 2021) and HP). PM₁ is well simulated over both periods. Then, Sensitivity experiments are conducted without a nucleation scheme to understand the role of Nucleation in CCN formation. We have observed great proportions of CCN during the LP period is contributed through nucleation (~62.49%) while it is only ~14.5% during HP periods as shown in figure 1 even though nucleation rates are much higher during HP (J1.7 = 35) compared to LP (J 1.7 = 12.2). Very high nucleation rates observed over Delhi are mainly due

to the presence of high amounts of vapors over Delhi. Even though the nucleation rates are much higher, CCN contribution due to nucleation is significant as newly formed particles are scavenged through very high coagulation. To understand this, we have conducted another simulation with doubled SO₂ concentrations, due to which the nucleation rate is increased to ~134 which is three times the initial nucleation rate. Such an increase in nucleation rate results only in a 17.5% increase in CCN which explains the role of coagulation.

Fig 1. Spatial variation of CCN concentrations over Delhi region.

CONCLUSIONS

Nucleation plays an important role in CCN formation during LP, but not a very significant role during HP episodes which are mainly due to existing particles coagulating the newly formed particles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the use of TATTVA HPC of the Civil Engineering Department, IIT Madras for conducting WRF – Chem simulations.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CLOUD VERTICAL STRUCTURE AND ASSOCIATED RADIATIVE EFFECT OVER DELHI AND KOLKATA

S. SHARMA¹, A. K. MISHRA¹ AND S. SINGH^{2*}

¹School of Environmental Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi –110067, India.

²Environmental Science and Biomedical Metrology Division, National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi – 110012, India.

*Corresponding and presenting author Email: ssingh@nplindia.org

KEYWORDS: Clouds, Urbanization, Cloud Vertical Structure, Cloud Radiative Effect, Optical depth, Cloud Effective Radius.

INTRODUCTION

Clouds are a fundamental component of the Earth's climate system, intricately linked to the regulation of atmospheric energy through their interactions with solar and terrestrial radiation. The effective radiative forcing by clouds can vary significantly depending on their optical properties, cloud vertical structure (CVS), and the surrounding atmospheric conditions (Li et al., 2013; Kahn et al., 2014). The CVS significantly influences the climate system; for instance, low-level clouds often contribute to negative radiative forcing due to their high albedo, while high-altitude cirrus clouds can trap heat and induce warming (Feng et al., 2016). Understanding the complex feedback mechanisms between cloud types and their radiative processes is essential for improving climate models, as clouds remain one of the most significant sources of uncertainty in climate projections (Stephens et al., 2012; Koster et al., 2011). Urbanization significantly influences the radiative effects of clouds, with recent studies indicating that cities experience enhanced cloud cover and altered cloud properties, which can lead to increased cloud radiative forcing compared to surrounding rural areas (Yang et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2022). Given the importance of understanding cloud radiative effects in the context of urban climate change, this research focuses on the implications of cloud vertical structure and radiative effects in Delhi and Kolkata during the monsoon season. The monsoon period, characterized by heavy rainfall and cloud formation, presents an ideal context for analyzing how these urban environments interact with atmospheric processes. The study employs advanced satellite data, radiosonde datasets and radiative transfer modeling techniques to provide insights into the complexities of cloud formation, radiative transfer, and their subsequent impacts on local climate.

METHODS

Radiosonde observations obtained from the University of Wyoming have been used for CVS climatological analysis during 2000-2020 for the monsoon period from June-September over two major urban agglomerations of India viz., Delhi and Kolkata. CVS includes cloud base height and top height, and has been calculated using vertical profiles of relative humidity. We have used MODIS-Terra daily 1°×1° cloud products to derive macro- and micro-physical properties of clouds. Further, these clouds' properties and CVS climatology are used as input in a radiative transfer model, SBDART to compute the cloud radiative effect (CRE), with clouds categorized into single-layer and double-layer formations and further classified into warm or cold clouds based on their vertical temperature profiles.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the comparative statistics of mean cloud base height (CBH), cloud top Height (CTH), cloud optical thickness (COD) and cloud effective radius (CER) over Delhi and Kolkata for different cloud types during monsoon season for 2000-2020. The key inference from Table 1 is the variation in cloud thickness between Delhi and Kolkata. Over the years, Kolkata has consistently formed thicker clouds than Delhi during monsoon season, likely due to its proximity to the sea, while Delhi is over 1,000 km inland, surrounded by land. Further, the CRE results show that single-layer warm clouds predominantly contribute to cooling effects in the atmosphere due to the reflection of shortwave radiation. This cooling is more pronounced in Delhi (-24.18 W/m²) compared to Kolkata (-16 W/m²). In contrast, cold clouds create significant warming, particularly in Kolkata (102.11 W/m²), which is attributable to the thicker and higher clouds formed in this coastal region. Double-layer clouds exhibit varying radiative impacts. Double-layer warm clouds lead to moderate cooling in Delhi (-10.14 W/m²), while in Kolkata, they produce a slight warming effect (4.04 W/m²). The greatest warming effect is observed with double-layer cold clouds, with Kolkata showing higher warming (102.11 W/m²) compared to Delhi (64.02 W/m²). Additionally, double-layer warm-cold clouds contribute to cumulative warming, with Kolkata exhibiting higher values (66.86 W/m²) compared to Delhi (53.83 W/m²).

City	Cloud Types		CBH (km)	CTH (km)	COD	CER (μm)	
Delhi	Layer based	Phase based					
			Single	Warm	1.86	3.42	10.46
			Cold	8.82	9.97	14.88	30.28
	Double	Warm-Warm	upper	4.06	5.73	7.21	16.33
			lower	1.2	2.22	4.42	16.33
		Cold-Cold	upper	11.82	13.76	8.20	13.97
			lower	7.82	9.13	5.54	13.97
		Single	Warm	1.28	4.50	9.36	18.81
			Cold	9.47	12.68	14.59	30.66
	Kolkata	Double	Warm-Warm	upper	3.98	7.94	7.44
lower				0.62	1.78	2.17	19.06
Cold-Cold		upper	11.66	14.02	9.88	29.70	
		lower	7.62	8.94	5.49	29.70	

Table 1. Comparison between cloud base height (CBH), cloud top Height (CTH), cloud optical thickness (COD) and cloud effective radius (CER) over Delhi and Kolkata for different cloud types.

CONCLUSIONS

The results emphasize the crucial role of geographical and meteorological conditions in shaping cloud formation and their radiative effect. It highlights the need for region-specific cloud parameterization in climate models to improve predictions of cloud-climate interactions and future climatic changes in urban areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the School of Environmental Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

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AEROSOL-MOISTURE-CLOUD INTERACTION OVER EASTERN INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN DURING WINTER

K. V THEJAS.^{1,3}, V. S. NAIR² AND P. R. SINHA^{1*}

¹ Department of Earth and Space Sciences, Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Valiamala, Thiruvananthapuram, India

² Space Physics Laboratory, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Thiruvananthapuram, India

³ Centre for Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences, Indian Institute of Science, Bengaluru, India

Email: prs@iist.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Hygroscopic Growth, Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Twomey Effect, IGP, Winter

INTRODUCTION

Each year during winter, the Indo-Gangetic Plain in Northern India experiences increasingly prolonged and widespread occurrences of haze and fog, resulting in more days of poor visibility across the region. However, the underlying mechanisms driving winter haze in Northern India remain poorly understood. Here we employed a synergy of satellite and reanalysis data from 2006-2021 to evaluate the effect of relative humidity on aerosol growth known as hygroscopic growth in exacerbating winter haze and the associated impact of aerosol hygroscopic growth on cloud microphysics over the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (EIGP). This study suggests that more than half of the increasing trend in haze over the region arises due to aerosol-moisture interaction (hygroscopic growth). The aerosol hygroscopicity and size distribution alone cannot elucidate the reverse Twomey effect observed over the EIGP. Examination of free tropospheric humidity (FTH) at low LWP bins indicates a prevalence of drier cloud tops (FTH<40%), while moister cloud tops (FTH>40%) increase towards higher LWP bins. This suggests that evaporation-entrainment towards the cloud top likely explains the observed reverse Twomey effect, a hypothesis further substantiated by a decline in cloud LWP with increasing AI for dried cloud tops.

METHODS

Estimation of hygroscopic effect on AOD

Total AOD under dry conditions is given by the sum of the individual aerosol-type AODs corrected for hygroscopic growth as

$$\tau_{dry}^{MODIS} = \tau_{amb}^{MODIS} \times \left(\frac{\delta_{BC}}{f(RH)_{BC}} + \frac{\delta_{OC}}{f(RH)_{OC}} + \frac{\delta_{SS}}{f(RH)_{SS}} + \frac{\delta_{SU}}{f(RH)_{SU}} + \delta_{DU} \right), \quad (1)$$

where aerosol fraction, denoted as $\delta_{Aerosol}$ is computed as the ratio of the AOD contribution from the given aerosol type to the total AOD from MERRA-2 data (Gelaro et al., 2017).

Aerosol-cloud interaction

The ACI is estimated as the relative change in cloud properties due to a relative perturbation in aerosol properties used as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) proxy (Feingold et al. (2001) as

$$ACI_{CER-AOD} = - \left. \frac{d \ln(CER)}{d \ln(AOD)} \right|_{LWP}. \quad (2)$$

The ACI value is estimated as the slope derived from the linear fit of all LWP bins,

considering three CCN proxies: ambient (AOD_{amb}), dry (AOD_{dry}, extracted from AOD_{amb} after hygroscopic correction) and aerosol index ($AI = AOD_{amb} \times \text{\AA ngstr\AA om exponent}$).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The frequency of severe haze events ($AOD > 0.85$) increases by nearly 6-fold during ambient conditions compared to that in dry conditions indicating that extreme haze events over the EIGP are mainly influenced by the increase in atmospheric moisture content and associated aerosol hygroscopic growth. Despite the correction for this aerosol hygroscopicity, the reverse Twomey effect remains persistent for the three CCN proxies. The magnitude of estimated ACI values decreases in the order of AOD_{amb}, AOD_{dry}, and AI consistently at all LWP bins. This suggests that the observed reverse Twomey effect over the EIGP region during winter cannot be explained by aerosol size variability or humidification effects.

Figure1. Comparison of aerosol cloud interaction (ACI) estimates for three aerosol loading cases, namely AOD_{amb}, AOD_{dry} and aerosol index (AI) plotted on a double log scale for different quasi-constant LWP bins over the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plains (EIGP) during winter 2006-2021.

CONCLUSIONS

Winter haze over the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (EIGP) is intensified by the hygroscopic growth of anthropogenic fine-mode secondary aerosols and the enhancement of aerosol-radiative feedback. The aerosol hygroscopic growth estimated in this study is comparable to the values obtained from in situ measurements of aerosol chemical and optical properties at near the surface over the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (EIGP). The observed reverse Twomey effect at lower LWP bins during winter over the EIGP cannot be accounted for by the effects of hygroscopic growth and the dominance of aerosol size modes. The influence of the entrainment-mixing process on the observed reverse Twomey effect in the study area was examined using LTS and FTH values as indicators of entrainment-mixing conditions. Strong turbulent mixing in combination with low LTS, coupled with drier cloud-top air, was identified as leading to an evaporation-entrainment effect over the cloud-tops.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors sincerely acknowledge MODIS, MERRA-2, ERA5, and MERRA-2 to provide data used in this study.

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**THEME 9: AEROSOL EMISSION INVENTORIES, SOURCE
APPOINTMENT AND MITIGATION**

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PM_{2.5} AND GASEOUS EMISSION FACTORS FROM HOUSEHOLD SOLID FUELS

D. SAHU¹, S. PERVEZ^{1*} AND A. TAMRAKAR¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh

*Presenting Author, email: [dharinisahu3009@gmail.com](mailto:धारिनिसाहु3009@gmail.com),

** Corresponding Author, email: shamshpervez@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Solid Fuel Combustion, Flue Gases, Emission Factors, Air Quality Impact

INTRODUCTION

The growing global demand for biomass energy has heightened concerns about the environmental implications of solid fuel combustion. As a significant source of air pollution, solid fuel burning emits various pollutants, including PM_{2.5}, greenhouse gases and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which impact air quality and human health. This study investigates the emission factors of PM_{2.5}, CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO₂, and total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs) from the combustion of four solid fuels - rice straw (RS), coal balls (CB), dung cake (DC), and fuel wood (FW), mostly used in domestic heating activities in India. The findings of this study provide critical insights into pollutant emissions under real-world conditions.

METHODS

In this study, emissions from the combustion of four solid fuel types were analyzed at varying quantities within a controlled chamber environment to simulate real-world burning conditions. Emissions were characterized using advanced analytical techniques. Gaseous emissions, including CO, CO₂, NO_x, and SO₂, were quantified using a portable FTIR gas analyzer (Model-DX4040, Gaset), which provided real-time data on multiple gas species with high accuracy. Also, total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs) were measured using a photoionization detector based TVOCs monitors (Model-ppbRAE 3000, Honeywell), ensuring precise detection of VOC emissions. PM_{2.5} were sampled with Minivol PM10/PM2.5 samplers (Airmetrics, Springfield, OR, USA) operated at 5 L Min⁻¹ flow rate, employing quartz filters for gravimetric analysis to determine PM_{2.5} mass concentrations. The gaseous EFs were determined using the following equation (Watson et al., 2019):

$$EF_i = CMF_{\text{fuel}} \frac{C_i}{\left[C_{\text{CO}_2} \left(\frac{M_C}{M_{\text{CO}_2}} \right) + C_{\text{CO}} \left(\frac{M_C}{M_{\text{CO}}} \right) + C_{\text{CH}_4} \left(\frac{M_C}{M_{\text{CH}_4}} \right) + \sum_j C_{\text{others}_j} \left(\frac{n_j \times M_C}{M_{\text{others}_j}} \right) + PM_c \right]} \times 1000,$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM_{2.5} emissions

This study investigated PM_{2.5} emissions from various fuels, revealing significant variability. The mean PM_{2.5} emissions ranged from 8.98 ± 2.22 mg/m³ for FW to 18.48 ± 4.49 mg/m³ for AR. DC emissions were 12.83 ± 3.50 mg/m³, while CB emitted 17.83 ± 2.87 mg/m³. AR exhibited the highest PM_{2.5} emissions, followed closely by CB. Notably, DC emissions were

43% higher than FW.

Figure 1. Distribution of average PM_{2.5} emissions from different household solid fuels.

Gaseous emissions

The emissions observed for each fuel type, highlighting the differences in emission levels as the fuel typediffers. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions were highest for DC at 1,215-1,542 g/kg and lowest for AR at 1,344-1,654 g/kg. Also, release of carbon monoxide (CO) is observed with emission factors ranging in order of DC (20-50 g/kg) > FW (10-20 g/kg) > CB (10-30 g/kg) > AR (15-35 g/kg). Nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) emissions are also substantial, with ranges of 0.5-2.5 g/kg and 0.3-1.5 g/kg for DC, 0.5-3.5 g/kg and 0.3-2.5 g/kg for FW, 1-5 g/kg and 0.5-3 g/kg for CB, and 1-4 g/kg and 0.5-2 g/kg for AR. Sulfur dioxide (SO₂) emissions vary significantly, with DC and AR emitting 0.5-2 g/kg and 0.5-3 g/kg, respectively. FW emits 0.1-1 g/kg, while CB emits 2-10 g/kg, indicating higher sulfur content.

Total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs)

The emission factors for VOCs such as propene, benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene have been determined. Different fuels contribute to the release of different amounts of these compounds, with particular attention to their quantities and potential health impacts. Total Volatile organic compounds (TVOCs) emissions range from 230-350 g/kg for DC, 80-140 g/kg for FW, 10-55 g/kg for RS, and 5-10 g/kg for CB.

Figure 2. Emission Factor Distribution of CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO₂, and VOCs from Four Solid Fuels

CONCLUSIONS

The emission factors developed in this study reveal significant gaseous and volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions from various fuel samples, posing considerable risks to human health and environmental sustainability. The results indicate that differential fuel types and quantities exhibit distinct emission profiles. Specifically, DC combustion emits the highest concentrations of CO, CO₂, SO₂, and total VOCs (TVOCs), whereas combustion of FW is associated with higher NO_x emissions. PM_{2.5} emissions were observed highest for AR and CB, indicating a substantial air pollution potential from these fuels. These findings underscore the importance of considering fuel type and quantity as critical factors influencing gas emissions, highlighting the need for efficient strategies to mitigate environmental and health impacts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was primarily funded by the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), India, under project CRG/2022/003926, with additional support from the Department of Science and Technology (DST) Promotion of University Research and Scientific Excellence (PURSE) program (SR/PURSE/2022/145).

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SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF AMBIENT VOCs AND PM_{2.5} AT RAIPUR, CENTRAL INDIA

S. PERVEZ^{1*}, A. TAMRAKAR¹, J. C. CHOW^{2,3}, J. G. WATSON^{2,3}
Y. F. PERVEZ⁴ AND M. K. DEB¹

¹School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492010

²Division of Atmospheric Sciences, Desert Research Institute, Reno, NV, USA

³Institute of Earth and Environment, Chinese Academy of Science, Xian, China

⁴Government Dr. Waman Wasudev Patankar Girls PG College, Durg, Chhattisgarh, India

*Author for correspondence, email: shamshpervez@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Source Apportionment, Ambient Air, PMF 5.0, UNMIX 6.0

INTRODUCTION

Hazardous air pollutants, such as VOCs and PM_{2.5}, have been associated with adverse health impacts (WHO, 2021). Positive matrix factorization (PMF) was the most advanced source apportionment technique to apportion the sources of gaseous and particulate matter. These receptor models are well documented and widely applied in several ambient VOCs and PM_{2.5} source apportionment studies conducted earlier for different locations across the world (Liu et al., 2017). However, limited applications have been reported in India (Matawle et al., 2014; Sarkar et al., 2014). This research aims to apportion the anthropogenic and natural sources of ambient VOCs and PM_{2.5} using PMF5.0, and UNMIX6.0. To the best of our knowledge, the present study is one of the first detailed studies of VOCs source apportionment carried out in Central India.

METHODS

Ambient PM_{2.5} (n-164) and VOCs (n-120) sampling was carried out in the urban area of Raipur, the capital of Chhattisgarh during October 2015 to September 2016 and November 2021 to June 2022 periods, respectively. PM_{2.5} samples were analysed for twenty-one elements, nine water-soluble ions, OC and EC, and air samples, collected in Tenax adsorbent tubes, were analysed for twenty-one source marker VOCs. The analysis database was used to apportion the sources of PM_{2.5} and VOCs using air quality receptor models. The initial step involved the use of UNMIX6.0 to determine the optimal number of source factors. Subsequently, PMF5.0 was employed to obtain source factor profiles. PMF profiles and factor contributions were obtained by minimizing the object function (Q) using a matrix algorithm that considers the concentration and uncertainty of the data sets (Simayi et al., 2020).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

UNMIX 6.0 model extracted the four initial number of source factors that address > 90% of the receptor database. PMF5.0 was then executed using ambient receptor chemical profiles of PM_{2.5} and 21 VOCs by incorporating UNMIX6.0 extracted factor numbers. Further, an enhanced number of factors were also used to run PMF model till the extraction of two similar source-factor profiles. Both receptor matrices have shown a 4-factor solution.

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DEPENDENCE OF BROWN CARBON CHROMOPHORIC AND MOLECULAR COMPOSITION ON SOURCE REGIMES AND ATMOSPHERIC PROCESSING: A SYNTHESIS FROM THE EASTERN INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

S. SARKAR¹, S. DEY¹, AND A. RANA¹

¹School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IIT Mandi, Kamand, Himachal Pradesh

KEYWORDS: Humic-like substances (HULIS), Protein-like substances (PRLIS), Nitroaromatic compounds (NACs); Molecular composition; Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP)

INTRODUCTION

Brown carbon (BrC), a subset of aerosol organic carbon (OC), and its constituent humic-like substances (HULIS) and nitroaromatic compounds (NACs), strongly absorb in the UV and low-visible region of the spectrum, thereby perturbing the earth's radiative balance and affecting tropospheric photochemistry (Laskin et al., 2015). The molecular and chromophoric composition of BrC, and consequently its climate effects, are heavily constrained by source profiles and the nature/degree of atmospheric processing. Delineating these effects essentially requires a multipronged approach involving simultaneous optical-chemical characterization of BrC chromophores and an in-depth understanding of prevalent aerosol regimes. This work reports the synthesis of findings from a seasonally- and diurnally-resolved year-long campaign on BrC optical and chemical properties associated with the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) outflow.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} sampling was conducted at Mohanpur (22.96°N, 88.56°E), a rural receptor location in the eastern IGP, using low-volume PM_{2.5} samplers (APM550MFC, Envirotech) on pre-baked (550°C) 47 mm quartz filters (QMA, Whatman). Samples were collected on a 12-h (daytime and nighttime) basis with a total of 90 samples during 2019-2020 spread across the summer, post-monsoon and winter. Half of each filter was extracted in 20 ml ultrapure water, and ultrasonicated twice for 15 mins (total: 30 mins). The extracts were analyzed using UV-Vis absorption (250–700nm), and fluorescence excitation-emission (excitation range: 250-400 nm, emission range 290–500 nm), followed by parallel factor analysis (PARAFAC). Extraction of neutral and acidic fractions of HULIS (HULIS-n and HULIS-a) was conducted using a 3-step SPE method. Pooled filters were lyophilized, followed by analysis on FT-IR and NMR. Methanol extracts of the samples were analyzed for 9 NACs (nitrophenols (NPs), nitrocatechols (NCs), nitroguaiacols (NGs), and nitro salicylic acids (NSAs)) using GC-MS, and for molecular composition using HPLC-ESI-MS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The general aerosol phenomenology in the eastern IGP was governed by southwesterly marine air masses in the summer, and northwesterly air masses across the IGP in the post-monsoon and in the winter. BrC_{aq} and HULIS showed enhanced absorption (4-6 times) in the post-monsoon and winter as compared to the summer owing to the influence of chromophores released from biomass and biofuel combustion on a regional scale, which were characterized by highly humified, conjugated, and aromatic moieties. Correspondingly, the RRF contribution vis-à-vis EC in the 300-400 nm range increased by factors of 2-3 in the biomass

burning seasons (12%) over summer (4.5%). The role of summertime photooxidation was apparent from the large contributions of WSOCsec in this season (79%) while WSOCpri was significant (43-51%) in the biomass-burning-dominated post-monsoon and winter.

Two types of HULIS fluorophores, namely: degradation HULISfluoro_deg and condensation HULISfluoro_con, and protein-like substances (PRLIS) including tyrosine, tryptophan-type and hydroquinone-type compounds were identified in BrC_{aq} and HULIS fractions (Fig. 1a). HULIS fluorophores were dominant in the biomass burning seasons (62-66%) while PRLIS, possibly sourced from marine bioaerosols, showed large contributions during the summer (78%) (Dey and Sarkar, 2024). Functional group distribution demonstrated the substantial presence of C=O and C-OH moieties, especially in biomass-burning seasons, perhaps suggesting the formation of charge transfer complexes. The considerable presence of saturated oxygenated aliphatics across seasons (19-37%) from NMR measurements suggested consistent fossil fuel signatures along with season-specific influence of photodegradable cellulose from marine organisms in the summer and biomass burning in the post-monsoon and winter. The increased contribution of unsaturated oxygenated aliphatics towards post-monsoon and winter in BrC_{aq} and HULIS-a (24-25%) indicated the presence of highly oxidized compounds due to long-range transport over the IGP. Optical source apportionment using PMF revealed that BrC_{aq} absorption at 300, 365 and 420 nm wavelengths was mostly from biomass burning (60-75%), followed by combined marine and fossil fuel sources (24-31%), and secondary processes (up to 10%). Source-specific MAEs at 365 nm were, on the other hand, estimated to be the highest for the combined marine and fossil fuel source (1.34 m² g⁻¹) followed by biomass burning (0.78 m² g⁻¹) and secondary processing (0.13 m² g⁻¹) (Fig. 1b) (Dey et al., 2023).

In terms of BrC chromophores, NACs (annual average: 185±94 ng m⁻³) were dominated by NSAs, followed by NPs and NCs. The contribution of NACs to organic aerosol mass was only 0.42±0.23%, but their contribution to BrC absorption in the 300–450 nm range was higher by an order of magnitude (8±4%), with NCs and NSAs contributing almost equally in the low-visible (400-450 nm) range as at 365 nm (Rana and Sarkar, 2024). At a molecular level, -CHON was the most dominant group (42%), followed by -CHO (34%) and <10% contribution from organosulfates and nitroxy-organosulfates. Other compound classes such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), organonitrates, amides, amines, esters, alcohols, carboxylic acids, and ethers were identified as BrC constituents with varying day-night and seasonal profiles.

Figure 1: EEM-PARAFAC-derived HULIS and PRLIS components (left); PMF-derived source attribution of BrC_{aq} MAE (right).

Figure 2. Van Krevelen plot for H/C versus O/C for CHON+ and CHON- compounds, coded with aromaticity equivalent (X_c).

CONCLUSIONS

Humic- and protein-like components, derived predominantly from biomass burning and marine biological emissions, respectively, along with NACs from fossil fuel emissions constrain bulk absorption characteristics of BrC in the eastern IGP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

IISER Kolkata and IIT Mandi are acknowledged for funding.

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SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF VENTILATION COEFFICIENT ON FINE PARTICLE POLLUTION IN INDIA

V.^{1,3*}, V. Singh², J. BHATE¹ AND Vaishnavi^{1,3}

¹National Atmospheric Research Laboratory, Gadanki -517112

²Commission for Air Quality Management in National Capital Region & Adjoining Areas, Delhi - 110001

³Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Valiamala - 695547

Email: - *vikasrf@narl.gov.in

KEYWORDS: Air Quality, Local Emissions, Background Concentration, Long-Range Transport

INTRODUCTION

India faces a growing challenge of poor air quality resulting from a high density of anthropogenic emissions due to rapid urbanisation, vital construction projects, and economic expansion. The elevated pollution levels, particularly the fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), is a major environmental concern that has a detrimental effect on human health and regional climate. The particulate matter (PM) concentration over a region is influenced by emissions, ventilation coefficient, temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric stability, chemistry, long-range transport etc. These factors contribute to the spatio-temporal variation in particulate matter concentrations by influencing the conglomeration and dispersion of pollutants. One of the important factors that determines pollution dispersion is the Ventilation coefficient (VC). VC is a product of wind speed and planetary boundary layer height that is defined as the ability of the atmosphere to dilute and disperse pollutants over a region. VC plays a decisive role in the spatial distribution and seasonal variability of PM concentration.

DATA

This study aims to study the impact of the emissions, and meteorological factors on the spatial and temporal distribution of PM concentration over India. We use MERRA-2 (Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, version 2) reanalysis data for zonal wind speed (10m), meridional wind speed (10m), PBLH and PM_{2.5} concentration at the resolution of (0.5 x 0.625) degrees for the year 2022. The surface PM_{2.5} concentration was calculated using the following formula:

$$PM_{2.5} = [DUST_{2.5}] + [SS_{2.5}] + [BC] + (1.6) \times [OC] + (1.375) \times [SO_4] + 1.4 \times [SO_4]$$

We have obtained the monthly PM_{2.5} anthropogenic emission from the Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR v6.1). A global 1-km resolution land surface digital elevation model (DEM) derived from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) 30 arc-second SRTM30 gridded DEM data created from the NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) is used to assess the dispersion parameters. We conducted spatial and temporal correlation analysis to investigate the relationship between particulate pollution, emissions and meteorological parameters.

METHODS

Our analysis focused on Pearson's correlation coefficients, which gauge the linear

relationship between two sets of data, under the assumption of normal distribution of variables. The spatial and temporal correlations were calculated between the MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} concentration and meteorological variables, local anthropogenic emissions (primary PM_{2.5}), and background concentration. Background concentration was obtained by removing the local emission influence by keeping the lowest concentration value around the grid.

To assess the spatial and temporal effects of ventilation on PM_{2.5} levels across India, we calculated the correlation between surface PM_{2.5} concentration and the Ventilation Coefficient (VC). Since ventilation can disperse pollutants from regions of high emission to areas with lower emissions, potentially leading to higher concentrations in low-emission areas, it is crucial to consider local emissions alongside the ventilation coefficient. To address this, we introduced a metric termed "emissions over ventilation," represented by the ratio of local emissions (Q) to the ventilation coefficient (VC). This metric captures the combined effect of emission intensity and atmospheric ventilation on PM_{2.5} levels, with higher values indicating elevated local emissions relative to ventilation and vice versa.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The correlation between VC and PM_{2.5} concentration varies with season and location. The VC and PM_{2.5} exhibit a negative correlation during September to March and a positive correlation during pre-monsoon and monsoon months. Our analysis revealed a distinct seasonal pattern in the correlation between Q/VC and PM_{2.5} concentrations. Specifically, we observed a strong positive correlation during winter months, indicating that periods of reduced ventilation coupled with heightened local emissions contribute to elevated PM_{2.5} concentrations during this season. The absence of a significant correlation between emissions over ventilation (Q/VC) and PM_{2.5} concentrations during summer months suggests non-local dispersion of pollutants due to strong convection and horizontal transport. This results in the enhancement of the background concentration in the areas of low or zero anthropogenic emissions.

To account for the background pollution, the correlation between 'Q/VC+background' and PM_{2.5} concentrations was calculated. The consistently high positive correlation between 'Q/VC+background' and PM_{2.5} concentrations underscores the significant role of background pollution in shaping PM_{2.5} levels. This emphasizes the necessity of accounting for background pollution sources, including regional and long-range transport, alongside local emissions in PM_{2.5} assessments.

CONCLUSIONS

Ventilation Coefficient plays a pivotal role in influencing air quality, as it enables better ventilation and mixing of pollutants, leading to a decrease in PM levels. However, it also has a negative impact by transporting pollutants to regions with lower emissions, thereby exacerbating air quality issues in those areas. Ventilation is also associated with enhancing dust-related pollution.

The ventilation coefficient is not the only parameter that determines the air pollution potential of an area, the local emissions and background concentration need to be considered to determine the air pollution potential of an area of interest.

Figure 12: Spatial and temporal correlation between (a) PM_{2.5} and VC (b) PM_{2.5} and Q/VC (c) PM_{2.5} and Q/VC + Background

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ASSESSMENT OF VEHICULAR AMMONIA EMISSIONS IN THE MEGACITY OF DELHI: RESULTS FROM NEAR-ROAD AND ON-ROAD MOBILE MEASUREMENTS

A. ALI¹, A. PANDEY¹, S. PANNU¹, M. KUMAR² AND V. SINGH¹

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi Hauz Khas

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi Hauz Khas

Email: vs225@chemical.iitd.ac.in and inkmayank@mech.iitd.ac.in

KEYWORDS: On-road Ammonia, Vehicular Emissions, Mobile Monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

Ammonia is prevalent in Delhi's atmosphere and rapidly interacts with atmospheric acidic species such as nitric acid (HNO₃), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), and hydrochloric acid (HCl) to produce inorganic constituents of PM_{2.5}. Ammonia (NH₃) emissions from cars are becoming recognized as significant contributors to secondary aerosol production, consequently impacting regional air quality. Agriculture including livestock farming is the major ammonia source, contributing ~60% of global inventory. Recent studies around the world showed that vehicular ammonia could be the dominant source, especially in urban areas where vehicle density is relatively higher (Fenn et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2014). NH₃ could be emitted from Three-Way Catalytic Convertors (TWCs) in gasoline vehicles and use of SCR catalysts in diesel engines where NH₃ in the form of urea is explicitly used (Abualqumboz et al., 2022; Hopke & Querol, 2022; Sun et al., 2014). Ammonia emissions can exacerbate the development of photochemical smog, particularly in metropolitan regions with elevated levels of NO_x and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). The existence of ammonium salts in particulate matter complicates smog chemistry and can result in more severe air pollution events (Pinder et al., 2007). The most recent consideration for NH₃ emissions on the global scale is linked to climate change based on its ability to form PM_{2.5}, specifically ammonium particulates (Aneja et al., 2001). Hence, in this study, we investigated near-road and on-road ammonia concentration via a mobile monitoring approach to determine the Delhi region's on-road NH₃ and NH₃/CO₂ emission ratio. Precatalytic cars, emit ammonia at a low rate and contributed only approximately 3.3 tons per day to the 150 tons per day of NH₃ emissions in the South Coast Air Basin (SoCAB) that encompassed Los Angeles in 1974, before the introduction of catalyst-equipped passenger vehicles (Russell et al., 1983) The CO₂ emission inventories are relatively accurate so that total vehicular emissions can be estimated. Finally, the obtained results are compared with regional emission inventory estimates and those of other megacities worldwide.

METHODS

Clear Air Research Laboratory (CARLab) placed at IIT Delhi is a diesel-based research vehicle platform fitted with a comprehensive suite of measurements characterizing the range of particulate and gaseous species. For this, three gas analyzers are installed in CARLab measuring CO₂ (Licor), CO (Horiba), NO_x, and NH₃ (Ecophysics, Switzerland). First, self-sampling measurements were conducted to ascertain the contribution of our vehicle to the measurements obtained. Next, the background concentration was quantified and subtracted from the obtained time series. The first percentile within a certain temporal window is used to calculate background values (Pu et al., 2023). Then the on-road enhancements of

concentrations were calculated by obtaining point-to-point differences between the instant signal and background value. Finally, the on-road emission ratio was calculated to determine the emission factor.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Self-sampling sampling results showed that there is minimal increase in the enhancement due to our vehicle which is insignificant as compared to on-road concentrations. Near-road and on-road mobile sampling was conducted. On-road concentrations were significantly higher than fixed-site concentrations obtained from the CPCB site. After applying the background estimation technique, the on-road emission ratio was obtained to calculate vehicular emission estimates for the Delhi region. Trials using a BSIV scooter have produced a 0.46g/kg emission factor at the IIT Delhi campus. Using a carbon balancing approach, the NH3 EFs (Emission factor) are defined per kilogram of fuel consumed.

$$EF = \frac{\Delta[NH_3]}{\Delta[CO_2] + \Delta[CO]} \frac{MWNH_3}{MWC} W_c$$

Here MWNH3 and MWC are the molecular weights of NH3 and carbon. $W_c = 0.85$ is the mass fraction of carbon in gasoline. We neglect the W_c of diesel (0.87) because diesel vehicles have been reported to have very limited contributions to on-road NH3 emissions.

Figure 1. Distribution of on-road emission ratio from mobile monitoring in Delhi region.

CONCLUSIONS

The on-road emission ratio of NH3/CO2 (ppb/ppm) is obtained via mobile monitoring from the Delhi region. This study obtained vehicular emission estimates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the IRD Grand Challenge Project grant, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (Grant No. 428 IITD/IRD/MI01810G), under the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India, for the funding support to carry out this work.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL ASSAYS ON SOURCE-SPECIFIC PARTICLES

N. TABISH¹, A. KUMAR^{1a}, S. K. DEY² AND S. IZHAR^{1*}

¹ Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, IIT (Indian School of Mines) Dhanbad, Dhanbad, 826004, Jharkhand, India

^{1a} Desai Sethi School of Entrepreneurship, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, Mumbai, 400076, Maharashtra, India

² Department of Chemistry and Chemical Biology, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines) Dhanbad, Dhanbad, 826004, Jharkhand, India

*Corresponding Author Email: saifi@iitism.ac.in (Dr. Saifi Izhar)

KEYWORDS: PM, Oxidative Potential, DTT Assay, AA Assay.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) in ambient air has detrimental effects on the environment and human health. PM toxicity is a major cause of mortality and air quality degradation. One of the primary mechanisms responsible for PM toxicity is oxidative stress which arises when there is a surplus of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Oxidative potential (OP) is the ability of PM to cause oxidative stress in biological systems. This indicates the necessity of understanding the toxic characteristics of PM and its impact on the human body. Various chemical assays and analytical techniques are used to measure the OP. However, there is no consensus on a definitive measure to determine the OP. (Bates et al., 2019) Multiple assays co-exist to quantify the OP; the dithiothreitol (DTT) assay and the ascorbic acid (AA) assay are the two widely used assays. In the DTT Assay, DTT consumption rates in the PM samples are quantified, indicating their capacity to catalyze ROS formation. Similarly, the rate of oxidization of AA to form dehydroascorbic acid (DHA) is quantified in the AA Assay. Understanding the multifaceted relationship among particulate matter size, concentration, and oxidative potential is challenging. This study investigated the variation in the oxidative potential of particulate matter when assessed using two different chemical assays and when the PM was sampled from various emission sources in Dhanbad City, located in Jharkhand, India.

METHODS

PM sampling specific to traffic and combustion sources (Three sources, namely Urban traffic (UT), Mine Traffic (MT), and Diesel Concrete Mixer (DCM), were in the traffic group, while the other six sources (Garbage Burning (GB), Wood Burning (WB), Cow Dung Burning (CDB), Mixed Fuel 1 (MF1) comprised soft coke and wood, Mixed Fuel 2 (MF2) containing a mix of soft coke and cow dung, and Mixed Fuel 3 (MF3) containing a blend of raw coal and cow dung were in the combustion group) was conducted in Dhanbad. One-quarter of the quartz filter was used for extraction in Milli-Q water for water-soluble and methanol total fraction (water soluble+ water insoluble), respectively. The extraction process involved 5 mL of the solvent in an ultrasonicator for 60 minutes at 50°C and subsequently filtered from syringe filters of 0.45 µm. The filtered sample was incubated with 100 µM DTT+10 mM DTNB and 2mM AA solution at 37°C for the DTT and AA assay, respectively. Aliquots were collected at predetermined intervals of 0, 10, 20, and 30 minutes, and absorbance was monitored at 412 nm and 265 nm, respectively, by UV-vis spectrophotometer to estimate

oxidative potential associated with DTT and AA assays.(Clemente et al., 2023; Patel & Rastogi, 2018) Box plot analysis was done to observe the differences between the oxidative potential quantified through both chemical assays.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The box plot analysis revealed that the DTT assay consistently showed higher sensitivity, with more pronounced positive OP values, particularly for combustion sources, which exhibit greater variability and higher OP levels. The intrinsic OP (mass-normalized values: OPDTTm and OPAAm) demonstrates greater variation than the extrinsic OP (volume-normalized values: OPDTTv and OPAAv). Combustion sources generated higher OP, especially for smaller particles (PM_{2.5}), than traffic sources in both assays.

Figure 1. The box plot illustrates a comparative analysis of the oxidative potential of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, quantified using DTT Assay and AA Assay from the combustion and traffic sources.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings highlight the importance of assay selection in evaluating oxidative potential. The higher sensitivity of the DTT Assay suggests that the chemical species responsible for DTT oxidation may be more abundant or active in these particulate matter samples. The greater variability observed in intrinsic OP measurements highlights their sensitivity to compositional differences, making them valuable for detailed source analysis. However, the consistency of extrinsic OP measurements suggests they may be more reliable for assessing overall exposure levels. The study indicated a risk of elevated oxidative stress due to the PM emission from combustion-derived sources. These findings will be crucial in targeted mitigation strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB) of the Department of Science and Technology (DST) (SRG/2023/000186).

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GEOSPATIAL AND GROUND BASED MEASUREMENT OF AEROSOLS, LACK CARBON AND GASEOUS AIR POLLUTANTS IN INDIAN MALAYAN REGION: A STUDY OF SEMI-URBAN LOCATION IN HIMACHAL RADESH

I. THAKUR¹, R. LATA*¹, K. CHAND¹, AND J. C. UNIYAL*²

¹Govind Ballabh Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment, Himachal Regional

²Govind Ballabh Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment, Kosi-Katarmal Almora

Corresponding Author - renu15negi@yahoo.co.in

KEYWORDS: Air pollution, aerosols, black carbon HYSPLIT.

INTRODUCTION

Air Pollution is a complex mixture of gases, particles, aerosols, and water vapour which has originated due to human development and other natural/anthropogenic activities. Indian Himalayan region which is a fragile region is highly sensitive to air pollution. Understanding the seasonal variability of aerosols and gaseous air pollutants and their correlation with meteorological parameters, long-range transportation is important to understand the background values of pollutants in the region and suggest mitigating measures. The present study deals with the study of aerosol gaseous air pollutants such as SO₂, NO₂ and CO₂ to assess air quality, background value and long-range transport of these pollutants in a semi-urban location at Mohal Kullu Himachal Pradesh.

METHODS

The present study deals with the study of aerosols, black carbon and gaseous air pollutants such as SO₂, NO₂, and CO₂ both by ground and satellite monitoring these pollutants using multiwavelength radiometer, AE31 Aethalometer and thermo fisher gas analyzers for ground-level monitoring along with satellite data (MODIS, MEERA-2 and SENTINEL-5P) and meteorological parameters. The present study was carried out at Mohal Kullu which is a semi-urban location at Mohal Kullu Himachal Pradesh in the year 2023, further HYSPLIT model was used to compute back trajectories for long-range transportation of pollutants. Both ground level and satellite monitoring of pollutants along with the study of meteorological and long-range transportation of pollutants will be helpful in understanding background values of these pollutants in the region and to suggest mitigating measures.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that PM₁₀ showed an average value of $32.24 \pm 2.24 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, PM_{2.5} showed $36.5 \pm 3.70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The average value of AOD at 500 nm was 0.42. Seasonal AOD was also analyzed, AOD showed the highest value mean value in summer followed by in monsoon, in autumn and lowest in winter the year both in ground-based measurement and RS-GIS using MODIS data. Black Carbon which is one of the major pollutants for retreating glaciers showed the highest conc. in winter, similarly Sulphur Dioxide showed the highest average concentration of 3.13 ± 0.15 ppb in December 2023 and the lowest average concentration of 0.56 ± 0.19 ppb in August 2023. Oxides of Nitrogen (NO_x) showed the highest average concentration of 9.49 ± 0.91 ppb in January and the lowest average concentration of 2.09 ± 0.52 ppb in August 2023. Temperature inversion and stagnant conditions in the winter season with the availability of low OH radicals can lead to high concentrations of these

pollutants in winters(Kuttippurath et al.,2022).Nitrogen Dioxide also showed bimodal peaks during early morning and evening hours when there is heavy traffic. Nitrogen dioxide showed high average concentration of 6.65 ± 0.68 ppb in January 2023 while CO₂ showed a high concentration of 350.99 ± 12.34 ppm in August 2023. HYSPLIT model showed, that the air parcels followed a route originating from the north-western regions of Afghanistan and Pakistan, traversing Pathankot, India, and finally reaching the experimental site in summer months. Conversely, in winter and autumn, the air masses exhibited a westward movement from the experimental site.

Figure 1. Seasonal diurnal variation of SO₂

CONCLUSIONS

The present study assesses the seasonal variation and sources of gaseous air pollutants (SO₂, NO₂, CO₂, and black carbon aerosols) in a semi-urban area of the Indian Himalayas. The results showed that SO₂ and NO₂ concentrations peaked in winter due to biomass burning, vehicular emissions, and transported dust, while CO₂ was highest in the monsoon season. Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) revealed that transported dust, vehicles, and biomass burning were the dominant sources of pollution, with long-range transport from regions like Afghanistan and Pakistan contributing to higher pollution levels. The study emphasizes the need for targeted air quality management in the fragile Himalayan environment to address these seasonal and source-related variations effectively.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors sincerely thank the Director, G.B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment (NIHE), Kosi-Katarmal, Almora, Uttarakhand and G.B. Pant National Institute of Himalayan Environment (NIHE) Himachal Regional Center, for providing the essential facilities. The authors are thankful to ISRO, Bangalore for providing the necessary financial support to carry out the current work under two programs of ISRO-GBP. i.e. Atmospheric Chemistry Transport and Modelling (AT-CTM) and Aerosol Radiative Forces over India (ARFI). We would also like to thank the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) for their use of the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model and the Google Earth Engine for using SENTINEL-5P data.

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BLACK CARBON AEROSOLS OVER THE CENTRAL INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN: INFLUENCE OF METEOROLOGY AND LONG-RANGE TRANSPORT

P. SINGH¹, B. H. ABDULLAH¹, A. VAISHYA², P. PRASAD¹ AND S. RASTOGI¹

¹Department of Physics, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur

²School of Arts and Sciences, Ahmedabad University, Ahmedabad – 380009, India.

Corresponding Author: prayag_singh@hotmail.com

KEYWORDS: Black Carbon, Aethalometer, Central IGP

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) aerosols are linked with adverse health effects and contribute to climate change by absorbing solar radiation and affecting regional and global energy budgets (Bond et al. 2013). According to the Global Carbon Project (Friedlingstein et al. 2022) and various emission inventories (Klimont et al. 2017, Paliwal et al. 2016), India ranks second globally, following China, in terms of contributing to BC aerosol load. The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) exhibits both natural and anthropogenic aerosols that vary seasonally. As a result, air quality and aerosol loading are very complex and heterogeneous, making it a key region for studying aerosol-atmosphere interactions (Lawrence & Lelieveld 2010). This study presents the characteristics of black carbon (BC) and its association with various meteorological parameters, along with seasonal variability in BC source identification, at a semi-urban continental site in Gorakhpur (GKP), located in the central Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), based on five years of data (2014–2019).

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Continuous real-time BC measurements were carried out at GKP (26.75°N; 83.38°E; 85 m amsl) in the central IGP, by using Aethalometer (Model: AE 33) at seven wavelengths (370, 470, 520, 590, 660, 880 and 950 nm). The instrument is operated at a flow rate of 2 LPM and the data is logged with a time resolution of 1 minute. The other details related to instruments, data collection, analysis, correction and procedures are discussed in several earlier publications (Drinovec et al. 2015, Vaishya et al. 2017).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Scatter plot of daily averaged BC mass concentration with temperature (top panel), relative humidity (middle panel) and wind speed (bottom panel) during pre-monsoon (PM), monsoon (M), post-monsoon (PoM) and winter (W) season.

Figure 1 shows the correlations between BC mass concentration and various meteorological factors across different seasons. In the PoM season, there was a strong negative correlation between BC mass concentration and temperature (-0.56), while the PM season exhibited a moderate negative correlation (-0.41), and the W season showed a weaker negative correlation (-0.35). Notably, the M season displayed a positive correlation (0.58), potentially attributed to frequent rainfall events lowering both temperature and BC concentration through aerosol scavenging. Regarding relative humidity (RH), a negative correlation was observed in the PM (-0.38) and M (-0.28) seasons, with a weak negative correlation in the PoM season (-0.12). However, the W season displayed a positive correlation between relative humidity and BC concentration. Wind speed exhibited a negative correlation across all seasons, indicating that high BC concentration was associated with low to calm wind conditions, primarily from local emission sources.

Figure 2. WPSCF analysis of 5-day air mass back trajectories during different seasons.

To investigate the influence of possible BC source regions, weighted potential source contribution function (WPSCF) analysis using the HYSPLIT model is performed during different seasons at the receptor site based on 5-day isentropic air mass back trajectories and is shown in Figure 2. During PM season, a strong potential source of BC is in the North-West and West regions of GKP. Low BC concentration during M season mainly due to the washout by rainfall indicates most of the BC sources are transported from the North-West and South-East regions. During PoM and W seasons, local emission is dominant in the study region and a significant portion of BC is transported from the Western IGP.

CONCLUSIONS

The impact of seasonal meteorological conditions on the dispersion and concentration of BC aerosols over the central IGP, highlighting their varying effects. Additionally, the WPSCF analysis indicates that GKP is primarily influenced by local BC sources, with the most significant distant source region situated in the North-West region. These findings provide valuable insights into the interplay between meteorological factors and the behavior of BC aerosols, emphasizing their regional and seasonal significance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the ARFI project of ISRO – GBP under the grant SPL: GBP: ARFI:40. The author(s) also acknowledged the NASA team for providing the HYSPLIT data.

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INSIGHTS INTO THE MAJOR SOURCES OF NO_x AND FORMATION PATHWAYS OF PARTICULATE NO₃- USING DUAL ISOTOPE PROXY

C. SHAW^{a,b}, R. MANDAL^c, A. SINGH^d, P. SANYAL^c AND N. RASTOGI^{a,*}

^a Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad 380009, India

^b Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar, Gujarat 382355, India

^c Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Kolkata, Mohanpur 741246, India

^d Punjabi University, Patiala, 147002, India (presently at University of Delhi)

*Corresponding Email: nrastogi@prl.res.in

KEYWORDS: IGP, Dual Isotope, Nitrate Formation Pathways.

INTRODUCTION

Nitrate is an important component of particulate matter in the atmosphere. It has significant implications for air quality, climate, and human health, and rapid accumulation of which can increase PM load by aiding in secondary aerosol formations. Particulate nitrate also participates in haze formations, influences radiative forcing, and has a direct effect on ecosystems in the form of nutrients (Li et al., 2018). In the atmosphere, particulate nitrate is primarily formed through the transformation of NO_x via four distinct pathways: (P1) the oxidation of NO₂ by OH (NO₂ + OH) in the gas phase, (P2) the hydrolysis of N₂O₅ on existing aerosols (N₂O₅ + H₂O, and N₂O₅ + Cl⁻, a heterogeneous process), (P3) the reaction between NO₃ radicals and VOCs and (P4) reaction of NO₃ radical and ClO. The latter two mechanisms predominantly occur at night and are thus referred to as 'nocturnal chemistry'. However, studies on the sources and formation pathways of particulate nitrate from its precursor gas NO_x are limited pertaining to the globe as well as the Indian subcontinent. Dual isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of particulate nitrate are excellent tools for understanding the formation mechanism and sources of nitrate (thus NO_x) in the atmosphere. In this work, we have utilised the stable isotopic signature of nitrate in PM_{2.5} to understand its sources and formation pathways in the northwest Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) during a large-scale paddy-residue burning period. Furthermore, diurnal variations in formation pathways and sources of nitrate are also explored.

METHODS

Diurnal samples of PM_{2.5} were collected from 11 October to 16 November on the terrace of the Department of Physics at Punjabi University, Patiala. Samples were analysed water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC), total water-soluble nitrogen (WSTN), elemental carbon (EC), organic carbon (OC), and inorganic anions. Stable isotopic analysis ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of nitrate was done following Titanium Chloride one-step reduction method (Altabet et al., 2019). Estimation of different formation pathways were done following methods as described in Walter et al. (2015). Stable Isotope Mixing Model (MixSIAR) was utilised for source apportionment of NO_x thus nitrate over the study area.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NO₃⁻ of samples was 57.2 ± 8 ‰ was -1.9 ± 5 ‰. The major pathways contributing to the formation of NO₃⁻ was OH (~ 92%) followed by N₂O₅ (~ 5%), whereas, P3 and P4 contributed ~ 1.3 and ~ 1.5% only. NO₃⁻ formed via the OH pathway was

the dominant pathway during both day and night. This could be because the sampling duration (8-10 hours) is much less than the average life-time of particulate nitrate (few days). Further, the contribution of N₂O₅ pathway is significantly high ($p < 0.05$) during night. This is expected since during night in the absence of sunlight photochemically mediated processes (OH-pathway) cease and heterogenous hydrolysis becomes dominant. Source apportionment using MixSIAR shows no significant difference in source contribution between day and night. Furthermore, biomass burning and traffic exhaust were the major contributors of NO_x followed by combustion and soil emissions during the study period (Figure. 1).

Figure:1 Major sources of NO_x during day and night based on MixSIAR model.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study, the first of its kind over India, investigates the sources and formation pathways of particulate nitrate over northwest Indo-Gangetic Plain during a biomass-burning episode and found traffic emissions and biomass burning as the major sources followed by coal combustion and soil emissions. Further, particulate NO₃⁻ formed through the OH pathway is found to be a major fraction of total NO₃⁻ observed during day and night over the study region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Physical Research Laboratory, Department of Space, Govt. of India.

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STABLE CARBON AND NITROGEN ISOTOPE RATIO FOR SOURCE IDENTIFICATION OF PARTICULATE MATTER: A CASE STUDY AT TROMBAY, MUMBAI, INDIA

V. B. YADAV^{1*}, V. A. PULHANI^{1,2}

¹Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India - 400085.

²Homi Bhabha National Institute, Anushaktinagar, Maharashtra, India- 400094.

*Corresponding author: vbyadav@barc.gov.in

KEYWORDS: Particulate Matter, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM), a complex mixture of solid and liquid particles suspended in the air, has been a growing concern for its impact on human health (Kelly & Fussell, 2015), as well as climate and hydrological cycle (Ramanathan et al., 2001). PM is known to contain a variety of toxic substances such as heavy metals, organic compounds and microorganisms. Understanding the sources and transport of atmospheric dust is critical for predicting and mitigating its effects on environmental and human health. Among the various methods used, the stable isotope ratio of carbon and nitrogen ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) are useful tracers for understanding the sources and fate of particulate matter in the atmosphere (Sen et al., 2018). Many of the Indian cities have observed high level of the particulate matter and Mumbai is no exception to this, with high levels of PM₁₀ being recorded at various locations in the city (Joseph et al., 2003). In the present study, we have measured the stable isotope ratio of carbon and nitrogen ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) in particulate matter (PM₁₀) collected from Trombay area, a coastal site which is in the eastern suburbs of Mumbai. The measured parameters and correlations amongst the various parameters were used to understand the likely source of PM and the coastal effects on PM in the sampling area.

METHODS

PM₁₀ were collected at terrace of a building at a height of 20 meter above ground at Trombay, on pre-combusted glass fibre filter paper using high volume air samplers at flow rate of 1.0 m³.min⁻¹ during January 2022 to December 2022. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were measured using Elemental Analyser (EA; vario PYRO CUBE, Elementary Analysensysteme GmbH, Germany) connected in series with continuous flow Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (IRMS; IsoPrime100, IsoPrime U.K. Limited). The isotopic values are reported in δ (‰) which is calculated as a ratio of the less abundant or (heavier) atom with respect to naturally more abundant (lighter) atoms in a sample relative to a standard, by following equation:

$$\delta \text{ (‰)} = \left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}}} - 1 \right) \times 1000$$

Where R = ¹⁵N/¹⁴N and ¹³C/¹²C. The measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were calibrated and expressed relative to VPDB (Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite) scale and N₂-air scale, respectively

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values ranged from -26.2‰ to -22.4‰, while $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values ranged from -2.3‰ to

21.4‰ during the study period (Figure 1). The average values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ were $-24.9 \pm 0.9\text{‰}$ and $9.1 \pm 5.6\text{‰}$, respectively. The monthly average values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ have shown significant variation throughout the sampling period. The monthly average values for both the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ indicate that the PM10 gets depleted in terms of heavier isotopes (^{13}C and ^{15}N) in comparison to lighter isotopes (^{12}C and ^{14}N) during January to May. Similarly, PM10 gets enriched (^{13}C and ^{15}N) in comparison to lighter isotopes (^{12}C and ^{14}N) during the period from September to January. This variation may be attributed to different sources of carbon and nitrogen contributing to the particulate matter and photochemical ageing of atmospheric aerosols (Aggarwal et al., 2013). Higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in winter compared to that in summer may be associated with a higher contribution of aerosols from biofuels/biomass burning during winter, and photochemical aging of atmospheric aerosols due to longer lifetime of aerosols in the atmosphere during winter, as wet removal is lower in winter compared to summer since relative humidity during winter is lower than the relative humidity of summer. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values observed during the four different seasons at the study location have statistically significant differences at the 95% confidence level (p values < 0.05) (Figure 2). The major sources of the PM appear to be liquid fossil fuels and biomass based on the similarity of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ratios.

Fig. 13 Sample to sample variation of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ during the sampling period

Figure 14: : Range or mean (± 1 standard deviation) of stable carbon and nitrogen isotope ratios in PM at sampling location and its comparison with values in major sources.

CONCLUSIONS

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values observed indicate fossil fuels and biomass burning as dominant sources of the aerosol. The relative contribution of different sources (vehicular, biomass, coal, marine origin and continental dust) varies in different seasons.

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CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS AT AN URBAN MEGACITY DELHI: ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT

A. K. SRIVASTAVA*

Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, New Delhi, India

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: atul@tropmet.res.in

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosols, Absorption Coefficient, Emission Source, Urban Megacity

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols have been the focus of extensive studies in the last more than one decade due to its significant impacts on human health (Janssen et al., 2011) and climate change (Ramanathan and Carmichael, 2008). Carbonaceous aerosols constitute a major fraction of fine-mode aerosols (i.e., particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter $<2.5 \mu\text{m}$; PM_{2.5}), with organic carbon (OC; $\sim 10\text{--}15\%$ of PM_{2.5} mass), and minor black carbon (BC; $\sim 2\text{--}10\%$ of PM_{2.5} mass) being the key components. BC is conventionally assumed only to be the light-absorbing component of carbonaceous aerosol, whereas OC is often treated as purely scattering component (Bond et al., 2011). India, being one of the world's most climate-sensitive regions, faces challenges in understanding the implications of carbonaceous aerosols due to limited information. Recent studies have shown that certain types of OC are indeed able to absorb solar radiation efficiently at specific wavelengths (Laskin et al., 2015; Srivastava et al., 2020), which is usually termed as brown carbon (BrC). The present study investigates the contributions of BC and BrC to light absorption characteristics at an urban megacity Delhi in the western Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region.

METHODS

The study uses a dual spot 7-channel Aethalometer (Model AE33, Magee Scientific, USA) measurements at Delhi. The instrument measures BC mass concentration at seven discrete wavelengths ranging from 370 nm to 950 nm using associated aerosol absorption coefficient (babs) and default mass absorption cross-section (MAC) values at each wavelength. Further, the instrument also provides crucial information about the biomass burning fraction (BB%). A statistical approach was developed to study light absorption of BrC using year-long BC measurements at Delhi.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average BC mass concentration at Delhi was found to be $7.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during the entire study period from Nov 2019 to Oct 2020. A significant day-to-day variability in absorption coefficients of BC and BrC is shown in Fig. 1. The mean BC and BrC absorption coefficient were found to be 55 and 78 Mm^{-1} , respectively. The absorption coefficient due to BrC is found to be $\sim 26\%$ higher as compared to BC, which may differ seasonally. Fossil fuel (traffic) was identified as the primary source of BC during the winter (53.9%), pre-monsoon (76%), and monsoon (83.8%) seasons. However, Biomass burning (coal and biomass burning) dominates during the post-monsoon season (56.3%), indicating regional air transport due to limited combustion activities in Delhi. Over the study period, biomass-burning (BB)

absorption was found to be contributed ~43%, while fossil fuel (FF) absorption contributed ~57% to the total BC absorption as shown in the inset in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Day to day variability in BC and BrC absorption coefficient at Delhi. The monthly mean contribution of BB and FF absorption coefficient to the total BC absorption is shown in the inset.

CONCLUSIONS

The average BC mass concentration at Delhi was found to be $7.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during the period from Nov 2019 to Oct 2020. The absorption due to biomass burning (BB) was found to be contributed ~43%, and fossil fuel (FF) contributed ~57% to the total BC absorption. During the study period, the absorption coefficient due to BrC is found to be ~26% higher as compared to BC.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Director, IITM, Pune, for his encouragement and support throughout the study.

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SEASONAL VARIATIONS OF TRACE METALS IN PM_{2.5} IN THE INDUSTRIAL CITY DURGAPUR, WEST BENGAL, INDIA

KARIGOWDA¹, G. HABIB^{1*}

¹Department of Civil Engineering Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India

E-mail:cez238123@iitd.ac.in

KEYWORDS: PM_{2.5}, Trace Metals, ED-XRF.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid industrialization and urbanization in developing regions have caused a significant increase in air pollution. This is especially concerning for fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and its associated trace metals (Humairoh et al., 2020). Durgapur and Raniganj, located in West Bengal, India, is an industrial city with high densities of factories, power plants, and vehicles (Ghosh et al., 2018). Exposure to PM_{2.5} causes many health risks, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. In contrast, trace metals such as lead (Pb), arsenic (As), and cadmium (Cd) cause severe health risks, especially among children and other vulnerable groups (Force et al., 2022). These trace metals mainly originate from various sources, such as industrial processes, vehicular emissions, and resuspended dust. Although studies on air pollution -have been done in other Indian cities, no systematic research still focuses on the trace metals of Durgapur and Raniganj's PM_{2.5}, indicating a lack of knowledge about the pollutant's potential health risks. The main goal of the research is to understand the seasonal variation of PM_{2.5} and the season of these trace metals in Durgapur (Ghosh et al., 2018).

METHODS

The study was conducted in Durgapur, an industrial hub in West Bengal, India, covering residential, industrial, and commercial zones. PM_{2.5} samples were collected using a Speciation Air Sampling System (SASS) over four representative seasons from October 2022 to October 2023. Samples were collected on Teflon filters, conditioned in a controlled environment, and analysed gravimetrically to determine particulate matter concentrations. Chemical analysis of the samples focused on 17 trace metals, using Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (ED-XRF) to identify the composition of PM_{2.5}-bound metals. Finally, a comprehensive health risk assessment was conducted, evaluating both non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks from trace metal inhalation exposure for both children and adults (Duan et al., 2021).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the seasonal and annual concentrations of trace metals and PM_{2.5} in Durgapur and Raniganj. The concentrations are reported as the mean \pm standard deviation, showing significant seasonal variation. For instance, Mg, Al, and Si concentrations peak during the pre-monsoon, while lower concentrations are observed during the monsoon due to wet deposition. PM_{2.5} levels are highest in winter (201 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and lowest in the monsoon (67

$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), indicating the seasonal impact on air quality. The trace metals (TTMs) as a percentage of PM_{2.5} also vary, being highest in the pre-monsoon season.

Table 1: Annual and seasonal concentrations of trace metals ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}\text{m}^{-3}$) presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Elements	Post-Monsoon (Oct-Dec)	Winter (Jan-Feb)	Pre-Monsoon (Mar-May)	Monsoon (Jun-Sept)	Annual (2022-2023)
Mg	6.25 \pm 2.20	7.28 \pm 2.20	10.44 \pm 6.46	4.17 \pm 4.32	6.47 \pm 5.10
Al	1.99 \pm 0.64	2.28 \pm 0.63	3.15 \pm 1.97	1.80 \pm 1.34	2.25 \pm 1.42
Si	3.94 \pm 1.54	4.97 \pm 1.65	7.03 \pm 4.40	4.02 \pm 3.27	4.86 \pm 3.33
P	0.28 \pm 0.09	0.34 \pm 0.08	0.26 \pm 0.08	0.17 \pm 0.08	0.25 \pm 0.10
S	5.77 \pm 2.03	7.58 \pm 2.66	4.91 \pm 1.37	3.68 \pm 1.90	5.10 \pm 2.38
K	2.74 \pm 1.25	2.78 \pm 0.83	2.43 \pm 0.94	1.40 \pm 0.81	2.15 \pm 1.12
Ca	0.82 \pm 0.35	1.23 \pm 0.84	2.84 \pm 2.19	1.73 \pm 1.49	1.69 \pm 1.62
Ti	0.12 \pm 0.05	0.14 \pm 0.04	0.21 \pm 0.16	0.10 \pm 0.08	0.14 \pm 0.11
V	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.00
Cr	0.02 \pm 0.05	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.04 \pm 0.02	0.04 \pm 0.03	0.03 \pm 0.03
Mn	0.86 \pm 0.85	1.26 \pm 0.86	2.04 \pm 1.06	1.85 \pm 1.29	1.53 \pm 1.17
Fe	1.92 \pm 0.75	1.97 \pm 0.70	3.03 \pm 1.96	1.49 \pm 1.15	2.02 \pm 1.41
Ni	0.01 \pm 0.02	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.01
Cu	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.02 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01
Zn	0.97 \pm 0.90	1.53 \pm 0.86	1.82 \pm 1.50	1.42 \pm 1.23	1.41 \pm 1.21
Sn	0.05 \pm 0.02	0.06 \pm 0.03	0.03 \pm 0.02	0.04 \pm 0.03	0.04 \pm 0.03
Pb	0.15 \pm 0.10	0.19 \pm 0.08	0.15 \pm 0.08	0.11 \pm 0.07	0.14 \pm 0.08
TTMs	25.93 \pm 10.85	31.65 \pm 11.46	38.41 \pm 22.23	22.01 \pm 17.09	28.08 \pm 19.15
PM _{2.5}	176 \pm 66	201 \pm 64	124 \pm 44	67 \pm 33	133 \pm 70
TTMs/PM _{2.5}	15% \pm 16%	16% \pm 18%	31% \pm 51%	33% \pm 52%	21% \pm 27%

Figure 15: The figure presents seasonal variations in PM_{2.5} concentrations (Mean and Standard Deviation) and trace metals' contributions at the Durgapur Industrial monitoring site from 2022 to 2023.

Figure 16 depict the variations in PM_{2.5} concentration and the proportion of Trace Metals (TMs) at the Durgapur Industrial site. PM_{2.5} was highest during winter and post-monsoon and lowest during monsoon. TMs accounted for different percentages in PM_{2.5} concentrations in the squat season: high in post-monsoon and winter seasons and low in the monsoon season. Based on such trends, it is clear that several industrial processes and meteorological seasonal variations affect particulate pollution levels.

CONCLUSIONS

The study finds that PM_{2.5} levels and TMs express significant seasonality, particularly in the winter and post-monsoon, because of anthropogenic emission sources, biomass burning and meteorological conditions. Study reveals that monsoon seasons had low pollutant concentrations due to wet deposition. This has implications for suggesting that concentration strategies for PM_{2.5} and trace metals should be developed based on region to help reduce the possible health impacts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by the West Bengal Pollution Control Board.

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OPTICAL AND ISOTOPIC SOURCE PROFILE IN SIZE SEGREGATED TRAFFIC AND COMBUSTION SOURCES IN DHANBAD

K. G. MISHRA^{1*}, S. IZHAR¹, D. PAUL², A. M. QADRI³ AND T. GUPTA⁴

¹Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines), Dhanbad, Jharkhand, India

²Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

³Department of Civil Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi- 110025, India

⁴Department of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosol, Isotope, Absorption Angstrom Exponent, Mass Absorption Efficiencies.

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols (CA), including black carbon (BC) and brown carbon (BrC), are major contributors to air pollution and radiative forcing, significantly affecting climate systems. BC, predominantly emitted from traffic emissions, is known for its strong light absorption properties. At the same time, BrC is emitted from biomass burning and other low-temperature combustion and primarily absorbs light in the ultraviolet and visible spectrum. Absorption Angstrom exponent (AAE) and mass absorption efficiencies (MAE) of BC and BrC are crucial for quantifying CA's optical properties and climate impacts. Moreover, stable carbon isotope ratio ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) helps distinguish between different CA sources, offering insight into their emission profiles. However, the effect of source and size on these properties is poorly understood. This study investigates the optical and isotopic profiles of CA emitted from traffic and combustion emission sources and the effect of the size of particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) on these properties.

METHODS

A total of nine samples grouped as traffic and combustion sources were sampled on quartz filter as described in previous publication (Mishra et al., 2024). These were analysed in DRI Model 2015 multi-wavelength thermal and optical carbon analyser (Magee Scientific, Berkeley, CA, USA) for getting the attenuation values while the stable carbon isotope composition was determined using an elemental analyzer (Flash EA, 2000; Thermo Scientific, USA) coupled with a stable isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS; Thermo Scientific Delta V Plus, USA) in continuous flow mode at IIT Kanpur (Qadri et al., 2022; Izhar et al., 2020).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 summarises the variation of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and AAE in traffic and combustion sources. Less variability in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in traffic emissions was observed (-29‰ to -24‰) than in combustion sources (-31‰ to -22‰), and the effect of particle size was insignificant. Fossil fuels like petrol and diesel have distinct $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values between -30‰ and 25‰, sources hailing from the continental regions and C-3 plant biomass have a wider range of -32‰ to -22‰. While aerosols emitted from marine regions and burning C-4 plants like sugarcane have a higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value between -22‰ to -12‰. This consistent difference between traffic and combustion sources underscores the utility of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in tracing aerosol origins. AAE values were lower for traffic sources (0.9 to 1.3), indicating BC dominance. In contrast, combustion sources showed higher AAE values (1.5 to 3.0), reflecting significant BrC contributions.

Similarly, higher light absorption by BC in traffic and BrC in combustion sources is observed (Figure 2). These values are consistent with values reported for vehicular and combustion emissions in previous studies from the region. Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed significant differences in MAE between PM10 and PM2.5 for BC, whereas no significant differences were found for BrC. MAEBC for PM2.5 was found to be higher than MAEBC for PM10 for almost all emission sources, which can be largely attributed to BC particles dominantly present in finer size. MAEBC ranged from 26 to 38 m²g⁻¹ for PM2.5 and 14 to 20 m²g⁻¹ for PM10 in the traffic emission group, and from 11 to 33 m²g⁻¹ for PM2.5 and 9 to 28 m²g⁻¹ for PM10 in the combustion emission group at $\lambda = 405$ nm. In comparison to BrC, MAEBC at 405 nm is found to be 4 to 15 times and 2 to 20 times higher in the traffic and combustion emission groups, respectively.

Figure 1: Variation in AAE and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ for PM10 and PM2.5.

Figure 2: Variation in MAEBC and light absorption at 405 nm for BC & BrC in both sizes

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates significant variability in the optical and isotopic properties of carbonaceous aerosols from traffic and combustion emission sources in Dhanbad. Less variability in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in traffic emissions was observed (-29‰ to -24‰) than in combustion sources (-31‰ to -22‰). Distinct AAE values were seen for traffic (0.9 to 1.3) and combustion sources (1.5 to 3.0) with insignificant effect of size. Light absorption due to BC was higher in traffic emissions, while BrC was higher in combustion emissions. A significant effect of size on MAEBC is observed, with MAEBC PM2.5 being higher than MAEBC PM10. Also, MAEBC is 2 to 20 times higher than MAEBrC in all the sources and sizes. These findings underscore the importance of source-specific aerosol profiling for improving air quality assessments and refining climate models, especially in regions like South Asia, where traffic and biomass emissions contribute heavily to particulate pollution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study has been supported by the Science and Engineering Research Board, India (SRG/2023/000186) and IIT Dhanbad, India (FRS (172)/2022–2023/ESE).

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URBAN ROADSIDE AEROSOL MEASUREMENTS IN DELHI CITY: COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DIFFERENT EMISSIONS CONDITIONS

K. RAJAGOPAL¹, S. RAMACHANDRAN² AND R.K. MISHRA^{1*}

¹Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University, Delhi, India

²Space and Atmospheric Sciences Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad.

KEYWORDS: Urban Aerosols, Roadside Measurements, Transport Emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Urban regions are known for complex mixtures from different aerosol sources of aerosols (Rajagopal et al., 2024). Among the different sources, transport sources play a major role in the urban regions (Rajagopal et al., 2023). The engine exhaust of various vehicles emits particles in different size ranges based on the type of fuel used and ignition techniques (Mohan, et al., 2024 a). The emitted particles interact with different atmospheric conditions in roadside conditions, making it complex to mitigate (Mohan, et al., 2024 b). The aerosol concentration in the urban region is directly proportional to the intensity of the sources. In the present study, urban aerosols were measured during 2021 and 2023, considering different transport emission scenarios and analyzed to estimate the role of transportation sources in aerosol concentration in roadside conditions.

METHODS

TUDY AREA AND INSTRUMENTATION

The measurements of aerosol concentrations were performed in a busy urban street corridor adjacent to the Delhi Technological University campus, located in the north-west part of Delhi. The study region is a proper representation of the urban roadside microenvironment. The measurements were done using a scanning mobility particle size with an L-DMA having the capacity to measure particles from 10 nm to 1090 nm. The collected data was analyzed after classifying into five major seasons, i.e., winter, spring, summer, monsoon and autumn.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total particle number concentration (PNC) variations during the years 2021 and 2023 is based on the intensity of emission sources. Especially during summer 2021, when restrictions for the transportation sources were in place, PNC is less compared to the spring, whereas PNC in summer 2023 is higher than spring due to the increase in emissions from transportation sources (Fig. 1). The PNC is less during monsoon in both years. The PNC is higher during the winter season, followed by autumn.

Figure 1. Seasonal variation of N_{total} (10 to 1000 nm) particle number concentration during the years 2021 and 2023 over Delhi.

The percentage contribution of different-size particles to the total PNC during the years 2021 and 2023 reveals that the Aitken mode particles remain more or less the same (varying within $\pm 5\%$). The concentrations in the nucleation and accumulation modes change between the two years as the particles in this size range are more influenced by the surrounding environmental conditions in the atmosphere, thus, the seasonal changes in the contribution of different sizes are dominant in the smaller and larger size particles.

Figure 2. Percentage contribution of different size fractions of aerosols (nucleation (10 to 30 nm), Aitken (50 to 100 nm) and accumulation (100 to 1000 nm) to total PNC) during the years 2021 and 2023 over Delhi.

CONCLUSIONS

The concentration and behavior of urban aerosols in different seasons (winter, spring, summer, monsoon, and autumn) in mega city Delhi, are analyzed. The results suggest that urban aerosol measurement and mitigation are one of the major areas that need to be focused on reducing the exposure of urban residents. Stringent emission standards, better engines technology and fuel quality in transportation sectors can play a major role in reducing urban aerosol concentrations. Reducing emissions in urban regions will pave the way for a sustainable lifestyle, one of the major sustainable development goals (SDGs).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The measurements were conducted in the Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University.

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STUDY OF AEROSOL DEPOSITION CHARACTERISTICS IN A MECHANICALLY VENTILATED CHAMBER

S. SINGH, M. PAL, S. ANAND, A. KHAN AND S. KUMAR M. K.

¹ Health Physics Division,

² Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

Corresponding author: singhs@barc.gov.in

KEYWORDS: Deposition, Ventilation Rate, Aerosol Removal

INTRODUCTION

In nuclear facilities involved in the generation of nuclear energy, a high-quality energy source contributing to carbon neutrality, radioactive gases and aerosols are generated from various activities. Mechanical ventilation is an important engineering safety feature provided in each facility to remove airborne radioactivity. This helps minimize area contamination due to surface deposition, external exposure due to immersion, and personal internal contamination due to inhalation. Ventilation systems are designed based on the number of Air Changes Per Hour (ACPH) required in various workplace zones. Though this philosophy of ventilation design is suitable for workplaces with gaseous contaminants, it may not be an ideal choice when contaminants are particulate in nature, dispersed in air, and conventionally referred to as aerosols. Here, aerosol removal by ventilation is governed by complex processes such as flow field-induced turbulent diffusion, sedimentation, coagulation, and advective transport. Therefore, ventilation design based solely on ACPH may not be adequate. An optimization is needed between bulk removal through ventilation and deposition. Several studies in the literature have explored aerosol size-dependent deposition rates. Among the key findings are those from Corner and Pendlebury (1951), Crump and Seinfeld (1981), and Lai and Nazaroff (1999). It is felt that although these models account for various processes of flow and particle transport, they have not been rigorously tested for robustness through experimental observation. This study examines the particle size and flow-dependent deposition characteristics for aerosols ranging in size from 0.2 to 2 μm .

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Figure 1 represents a schematic diagram of the aerosol chamber used in this study, with dimensions of 2 m x 1.5 m x 1.5 m. The chamber had an air inlet at the top, fitted with a HEPA filter, and an outlet at the bottom connected to a blower equipped with a Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) for finer control of the ventilation rate. The ventilation rate was measured using a thermal mass flow meter. For aerosol sampling, the chamber was equipped with three ports located centrally at distances of 0.5 m, 1.0 m, and 1.5 m from the aerosol injection port inside the chamber. DOP (di-octyl phthalate) aerosols were generated and injected into the chamber. The number concentration of aerosols was measured using an Optical Particle Counter (OPC)-based aerosol spectrometer.

Figure 17: Schematic of aerosol chamber

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before the start of the experiments, the exhaust blower was operated at the desired flow rate, and the background particle concentration was brought to zero. Aerosols were then injected continuously while keeping the exhaust blower on. Once the particle concentration inside the chamber reached a steady state, an aerosol injection was stopped, with the ventilation remaining on. It was observed that the aerosol concentration began to decay exponentially over time. Typical data of aerosol decay concentration for particles sized 0.275 to 0.449 μm is shown in Figure 2. Similar data were generated for particle sizes up to 1.6 μm . The data were fitted to a first-order exponential decay, and the decay constant (effective removal rate, $\lambda = \lambda_v + \lambda_d$), which is the sum of the removal rate due to ventilation (λ_v) and the removal rate due to deposition (λ_d), was estimated.

Figure 18: Aerosol decay at a ventilation rate of 20CMH

The value of λ obtained for aerosol particles sized 0.44 to 1.6 μm showed that the effective removal rate was highest (5.7h^{-1}) for particles of size 0.449 μm . Afterwards, it decreased to a minimum value at 0.5 μm , and then remained constant for the particle size range of 0.5 to 1.6 μm . This experiment was repeated at various ventilation rates, with a constant aerosol injection rate, and the effective removal rate was estimated. From the effective removal rate, the particle removal rate due to deposition was estimated and presented in Figure 3.

It was observed that the deposition rate increased with ventilation rate. For smaller particles ($0.44 \mu\text{m}$), it increased from 1 h^{-1} to 5 h^{-1} as the ventilation rate increased from 20 CMH to 80 CMH, respectively. The deposition rate for particles between 0.5 to $1.6 \mu\text{m}$ remained constant up to a ventilation rate of 50 CMH, after which it increased to 1.5 h^{-1} at a ventilation rate of 80 CMH. The observed variation in the deposition rate was compared with the well-known V-shaped deposition rate curve proposed by Lai and Nazaroff (1999), and disagreement was found for smaller particle sizes.

Figure 19: Size-dependent deposition rate at different ventilation rates.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, optimizing ventilation rates in nuclear facilities is crucial to minimize aerosol deposition, particularly for particles in the 0.5 to $1.6 \mu\text{m}$ range. The study demonstrates that aerosol removal rates vary with particle size, with the highest rate observed for $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ particles. Higher ventilation rates enhance deposition, especially for smaller particles, but this effect levels off at larger sizes. Additionally, the V-shaped deposition model requires further verification for smaller particles under varying conditions. Future work should focus on refining these models and conducting experiments with different aerosol types and environmental settings to improve their applicability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author expresses their gratitude to Shri S Wadhwa Dy. Plant Superintendent, WIP and Smt Jyoti Diwan, Superintendent EE&I, WIP for their support related to mechanical; electrical & instrumentation for conducting the experiments.

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THEME 10 : NUCLEAR AND RADIOACTIVE AEROSOLS

CHARACTERIZATION OF INDOOR AEROSOLS (PM_{2.5}) DURING SUMMER SEASON AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISK IN GANGTOK, SIKKIM

T. TAYE¹, Y. SAPKOTA^{1#}, A. ROY¹, A. GUPTA^{1,2}, R. RAJAK^{1,2}, B. BARUAH^{1,2}
AND R. K. RANJAN^{1,2*}

¹Department of Geology, Sikkim University, Gangtok, Sikkim, 737102

²DST's Centre of Excellence, Department of Geology, Sikkim University, Sikkim, 737102

#Presenting author: yooglesaps@gmail.com

*Corresponding author: rkranjan@cus.ac.in

KEYWORDS: Indoor, Aerosols, PM_{2.5}, Heavy Metals, Black Carbon, Heath Risk, Sikkim

INTRODUCTION

Indoor air pollution, particularly fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), has emerged as a significant public health concern, especially in urban areas. It is a global concern that disproportionately impacts all living beings and poses a variety of wellness, ecological and societal problems in today's world. In regions like Gangtok, and Sikkim, where high altitudes and unique urban topography contribute to distinct climatic and air quality conditions, understanding indoor air quality is crucial. This study focuses on the characterization of indoor aerosols, particularly PM_{2.5} levels in indoor environments, and the associated health risks to provide effective mitigation strategies to improve indoor air quality and public health in high-altitude urban settings.

METHODS

The present work has been carried out in the capital city of Gangtok, Sikkim. Aerosol samples were collected during the summer season from June 2023 to October 2023, with a focus on PM_{2.5} particles. The study involved the collection of aerosol samples using high-volume aerosol samplers, followed by chemical analyses to determine the concentration of heavy metals and black carbon. In addition to characterizing the indoor pollutants, this study also included a comprehensive health risk assessment. Using the hazard quotient (HQ) method, the study evaluated the risk posed by PM_{2.5}-bound metals to three different demographic groups: infants, children, and adults. Health risk assessment focused on 3 groups of people, according to their ages, including infant children (<1-5), children (6-17) and adults (>18) (Kaewrat et. al., 2021). The health risk model for infant children, children and adults was defined through the following equation: -

$$HQ = \frac{ADD}{RfD}$$
 where,

HQ (Hazard Quotient) - Exposure to PM, ADD (AverageDailyDose) - Exposure to pollutants by respiratory inhalation (mg/kg.day), and RfD (ReferenceDose) - Level of daily intake

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study shows that iron (Fe) had the highest concentration among the analyzed heavy metals, with the highest levels recorded in June 2023 (4.37 µg/m³) during the night. Arsenic (As) was found to be the second-highest metal, with a concentration of 1.62 µg/m³ during the

same month. Seasonal variations revealed that summer recorded the highest concentrations of these metals, emphasizing the influence of atmospheric conditions and human activities on indoor air quality. The monthly median concentration of selected metal during the study period has been presented in Table 1. It is also found that infants are particularly vulnerable, with HQ values exceeding the safety threshold, suggesting moderate health risks due to exposure to indoor air pollutants. The HQ for children and adults, though lower, also pointed to potential health risks.

Month	Li	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	As	Se	Rb	Sr	Cd	Hg	Pb	U
Jun-2023	0.0 40	0.2 40	0.1 00	4.3 70	0.0 04	0.1 30	0.0 70	1.6 20	0.0 10	0.1 10	0.7 60	0.0 10	0.0 01	0.1 70	0.00 4
Jul-2023	0.0 07	0.3 10	0.0 80	3.4 30	0.0 03	0.3 00	0.0 40	1.2 20	0.0 04	0.0 08	0.0 70	0.0 02	0.0 06	0.1 60	0.00 5
Aug-2023	0.0 07	0.1 10	0.1 30	1.8 50	0.0 06	0.2 20	0.0 60	1.2 80	0.0 02	0.0 06	0.0 50	0.0 02	0.0 03	0.1 50	0.00 7
Sep-2023	0.0 05	0.1 00	0.2 00	1.6 90	0.0 05	0.1 20	0.0 30	1.1 90	0.0 01	0.0 04	0.0 50	0.0 01	0.0 02	0.1 10	0.00 6
Oct-2023	0.0 07	0.1 50	0.1 20	1.7 20	0.0 08	0.1 10	0.0 40	1.0 90	0.0 02	0.0 04	0.0 40	0.0 01	0.0 01	0.0 60	0.00 5

Table 1: Monthly median concentration of selected metal during the study period

CONCLUSIONS

This study estimates the concentration of indoor pollutants in Sikkim. Despite its reputation as a green state, with less population as compared to other states of India, Sikkim faces significant challenges related to pollution. This study has shed light on indoor pollution affecting the region which threatens both environmental sustainability and public health. The findings recommend critical insights into the public health implications of indoor pollution in Sikkim and emphasize the importance of regulatory measures to mitigate exposure to harmful aerosols and heavy metals.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors dully acknowledge DST's Centre of Excellence (CoE), at the Department of Geology, Sikkim University, for providing instrument facilities for sample analysis.

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ESTIMATION OF AMBIENT PARTICULATE MATTERS IN HUMAN RESPIRATORY TRACT IN AN URBAN ATMOSPHERE

S. DEY¹, S. DAS² AND S. MONDAL³

¹Department of Environmental Studies, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Kolkata

²Department of Computer Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai

³Department of Mathematics, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong- 793022

Corresponding author: sharadiadey1985@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, MPPD Model, Deposition Fraction

INTRODUCTION

Ambient particulate matter is a major air pollutant in the urban areas. Toxicological and epidemiological studies have shown that exposure to ambient particulate matters (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) is associated with a variety of adverse health effects. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} get deposited in different parts of the respiratory tract thereby causing a detrimental impact on respiratory health. Kolkata, the capital of West Bengal has been identified as one of the non-attainment cities by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), India where annual ambient PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels exceeded the national ambient air quality standard (NCAP, 2019). Kolkata has been found to have one of the highest PM levels in the country. The estimation of the deposition of particulate matters in different parts of the human respiratory system is vital for understanding the health impact of PM exposure on human beings. MPPD (Multipath Particle Dosimetry) model is a deterministic, multipath model which can predict the deposition of PM in different parts of the human respiratory system (Asgharian et al., 2001). The present work focuses on the seasonal variation of PM concentration in the ambient atmosphere of the study area and estimates the deposition of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in the respiratory tract of males and females over Kolkata during 2019 by using Multiple Path Particle Dosimetry model

METHODS

The data of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and meteorological parameters have been collected from CPCB station (22° 32' 42" North, 88° 20' 33") in Kolkata, West Bengal during 2019. The data has been classified into different seasons as per the classification of the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD). The deposition of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the human respiratory tract (both males and females) have been estimated using ARA's (Applied Research Associates) Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model, Version 3.04. Regional and lobar deposition of particulate matters have been estimated. The human respiratory tract has been divided into three parts – head (from nose to larynx regions), tracheobronchial or TB (between the trachea and terminal bronchioles) and alveolar region (pulmonary region). In the Stochastic Lung Model of MPPD, the seasonal average of PM₁₀ & PM_{2.5} has been applied for constant exposure. The particulate matters are assumed to be entering the human respiratory system through the nose (nasal) and in an upright position. The key input parameters in the parameters for the calculation of deposition fraction and deposition dose in males and females are Functional Residual Capacity (ml), Upper Respiratory Tract (ml), breathing frequency (min⁻¹), tidal volume (ml), inspiratory fraction and density (g/cm³).

The Deposition dose of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was calculated using the formula given below (Passi et al., 2021), Deposition Dose (μg) = DF * AM * TV * f * t

where, DF = deposition fraction (unitless),

AM = aerosol mass concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$),
TV = tidal volume (m^3 /breath),
f = breathing frequency (breath/min),
t = exposure duration (min).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was highest in winter followed by post-monsoon, pre monsoon and monsoon over the study area. The deposition dose of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the head, trachea bronchial (TB) and pulmonary region was calculated for 1 hour. The total PM_{2.5} depositions has been found to be higher in males than in females but the pulmonary region of the females received higher PM_{2.5} dose than males. It is observed that the lobar deposition fraction of both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are also higher in females than in males. The right middle (RM) lobe of the lungs of both males and females is found to have the highest deposition fraction of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. The highest deposition dose of PM₁₀ was received by both males and females in winter followed by post monsoon, pre monsoon and monsoon. The lobar deposition fraction of both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are found to be higher in females than in males. The deposition fraction of PM₁₀ in females was RL (0.005) > LL (0.0049) > RU (0.0047) > LU (0.0024) > RM (0.0017) and in males was RL (0.0048) > LL ~ RU (0.0043) > LU (0.0021) > RM (0.0016). Deposition fractions of PM₁₀ corresponding lobes of females are found to be slightly higher than those of males. The ambient concentration ambient PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} is maximum during the winter season and minimum during the monsoon and meteorology has been found to play a vital role in ambient particulate matter concentration. Low temperature, less boundary layer mixing height and stagnant weather condition leads to accumulation of the aerosol particles near the earth's surface during the winter season. Depositions of particulate matters in different regions of the respiratory tract are influenced by the mechanisms of inertial impaction, diffusion and sedimentation. Higher lung volume and higher breathing rate of males than females led to higher deposition dose in males than females. Longer removal time results in a high deposition dose in the pulmonary region (Sturm and Hofmann, 2009). The lowest PM_{2.5} deposition dose in the TB region can be attributed to a faster clearance rate by mucociliary activity (Manojkumar and Srimuruganandam, 2022).

CONCLUSION

This work attempts to study the variation of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ over Kolkata during different seasons and the deposition dose of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in different parts of the human respiratory tract in males and females. This study shows the difference in the deposition dose in different regions and lobes of the respiratory system in males and females. Gender-specific health surveys over the chosen area may further help in identifying the impacts of higher deposition of fine particulate matters in different parts of the respiratory tract. Personal exposure data and local clinical data on lung parameters may further help in understanding the adverse impacts of PM deposition on the respiratory health of males and females.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support provided by St. Xaviers College (Autonomous), Kolkata for this research work.

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UNDERSTANDING INDOOR AIR POLLUTION AND ITS IMPACT ON HEALTH IMPLICATIONS IN COLD REGIONS OF INDIA

H, BANOO¹, DR. V. SHARMA

¹Lovely Professional University Punjab – 144411, India.

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Pollution, Source Identification, Cold Region, Health Consequences

ABSTRACT

Indoor air pollution is one of the world's most important environmental challenges, particularly among the poorest people, who typically do not have access to clean cooking fuel. According to the Global Burden of Disease study, indoor pollution caused 2,313,992 deaths in 2022 (Our World Data 2022). India suffers the most from this crisis, experiencing the highest annual mortality rate related to indoor air pollution (IAP) among developing nations, responsible for 28% of global deaths. This comprehensive study explores the intricate web of indoor air pollution, emphasizing its profound health consequences and socioeconomic disparities, with a particular focus on cold regions. Delving into the often-neglected realm of indoor environments, the research underscores the prevalence of pollutants emanating from building materials, combustion sources, and household products. They may spend hours a day near the stove, exposing them to high levels of household air pollution (HAP), which could harm their respiratory and contribute to COPD. We conducted a scoping review to identify the existing knowledge about Indoor air-pollution-related health outcomes in a cold region of India. While there is a significant study on indoor air pollution in India, most of it focuses on urban areas or general environmental conditions, with less focus on cold, high-altitude regions like the Himalayas, J&K, and Ladakh. These regions have distinct characteristics such as closed spaces due to extreme cold, which limits ventilation and increases the concentration in indoor air pollutants. The health implications span from acute respiratory infections and pulmonary diseases to building-associated illnesses. Additionally, the study unveils the due to use of biomass fuel exacerbating indoor air pollution risks, calling for targeted interventions and a heightened awareness of environmental health equity. This thorough analysis emphasizes the significant result regarding indoor air pollution on public health in cold locations, focusing on cardiovascular and respiratory hazards. Socioeconomic gaps increase exposure, particularly in locations where data on indoor air pollution is scarce. Cold temperatures increase pollution from heating practices, adding to health risks. The research sheds light on the importance of contaminants including carbon monoxide CO and volatile organic compounds. It demonstrates a compelling need for study on this nexus via rigorous literature analysis. It highlights a critical need for comprehensive policies addressing indoor air quality to safeguard public health in diverse global contexts.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) each year, indoor and outdoor air pollution is responsible for nearly 7 million deaths around the globe. Ninety-nine percent of human beings currently breathe air that exceeds the WHO's guideline limits for pollutants, with those living in low- and middle-income countries suffering the most. Long-term exposure to air pollution is consistently linked to an increased incidence of cardiovascular and respiratory ailments, birth abnormalities, and neurological disorders. Short-term exposure to ambient air pollution may aggravate asthma and lead to hospital admissions. Understanding

how air pollution affects people differently depending on their socioeconomic level is critical for achieving environmental health equality, as it assures that no community faces an unequal burden of environmental risks or is denied the advantages of clean, natural resources (Li et al., 2021). When we talk about environmental health equity, we mean making sure that vulnerable communities aren't unfairly subjected to environmental externalities or lacking access to natural amenities.

Environmental dangers, such as air pollution, noise, and extreme events, are not uniformly dispersed among European populations, according to a new study published by the European Environment Agency (EEA) (Shrubsole et al., 2019). People at the bottom of the social hierarchy, who have fewer resources and less ability to adjust to changing conditions, are frequently the worst hit by environmental risks. People of lower socioeconomic status are more likely to be exposed to outdoor air pollution, noise, and overheating, which may have especially negative impacts on the health of children, the elderly, and those with chronic conditions. These inequalities in risk arise from two sources: (1) unequal exposure to environmental dangers within a community, and (2) unequal susceptibility to the negative health consequences of exposure owing to preexisting diseases (Milojevic et al., 2017).

METHODS

Methodology: A systematic review was conducted using keywords related to indoor air pollution, cold climates, health effects, and socioeconomic factors. Studies in English, focused on cold regions and peer-reviewed sources, were included, while studies on warm climates or non-peer-reviewed sources were excluded.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Results and Discussion: Indoor air pollution (IAP) is linked to serious health conditions, including respiratory illnesses (e.g., asthma, acute respiratory infections, COPD) and lung cancer, with increased risks in children and individuals exposed to solid fuel combustion. Poor indoor air quality in cold climates exacerbates these risks, impacting vulnerable populations and contributing to high morbidity and mortality.

CONCLUSIONS

Indoor air pollution (IAP) in cold climates poses significant respiratory and cardiovascular risks, with socioeconomic disparities intensifying exposure in high-altitude regions like Ladakh and the Himalayas. Pollutants from solid fuels, building materials, and household products are trapped indoors due to limited ventilation, and worsening health impacts. Vulnerable populations, especially women and children, face heightened risks from cooking smoke and poor IAQ. Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions, improved ventilation, cleaner fuels, and policies to reduce IAP, thereby mitigating health inequities and protecting public health.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the National Fellowship for the ST category

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THREE DECADES OF RADIOACTIVITY MONITORING OF AIR PARTICULATES AT NAPS NARORA SITE

Y P. Gautam¹, A. K. SHARMA¹, V. KUMAR¹, D. Kumar¹, S. KUMAR¹, J. KUMAR¹, B. SINGH¹, V. KUMAR¹, I. V. Saradhi², AND A.V. Kumar²

¹ Environmental Survey Laboratory, EMAD, Narora Atomic Power Station, Narora 203389

²EMAD, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai 400 085

INTRODUCTION

Natural radionuclides (cosmogenic, ²³⁸U and progenies, ²³²Th and progenies, and ⁴⁰K) are omnipresent in the atmospheric dust and their monitoring is one of the important aspects of environmental impact assessment carried out around any NPP. Apart from the natural radioactivity, anthropogenic sources, such as nuclear/radiological accidents, nuclear weapon tests, or the production and application of phosphorus fertilizers (Bossey, P 2017) also contribute to radioactivity in the air. Monitoring of long-lived gross alpha, gross beta activity and other source related radionuclides such as ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr is mandatory around NPP sites for detecting radioactivity released to the atmosphere (EPA2020). Continuous measurement of gross alpha and gross beta activity is usually used as a control indicator of the radioactivity levels in air. The long-term monitoring of gross alpha and beta activity concentrations enables us to study the temporal variability of environmental radioactivity (Tositti, L). This paper describes the gross alpha, gross beta, ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr concentrations at NAPS Narora site during last thirty-five-year period (1988–2023), to study the impact of the operation of the nuclear power plant on air particulate activity.

METHOD

The study was carried out at the Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) site (28.1968°N and 78.3814°E) situated in Uttar Pradesh, India. Air particulate matter was collected on 50 mm (dia.) Whatman GFA filter mounted at 2.5m height using a high-volume air sampler with a flow rate of 100-120 lpm on a weekly basis. Long lived beta activity was defined as gross beta activity after four days counting when short lived ²²²Rn progeny decayed into ²¹⁰Pb. Filters were counted on GM tube-based gross beta and ZnS (Ag) based gross alpha counter. ¹³⁷Cs activity was measured using a 50% HPGe gamma spectrometry system and ⁹⁰Sr was estimated by radiochemical analysis followed by counting in low beta counting system

Table 1 Summary of gross alpha and gross beta activity in air particulate samples at NAPS Narora during 1988-2023

Description	Gross alpha (mBq m ⁻³)	Gross beta (mBq m ⁻³)	¹³⁷ Cs (mBq m ⁻³)	⁹⁰ Sr (mBq m ⁻³)
No. of samples	1043	1043	104	104
No. of BDL	55	330	104	104
MDL	0.01	0.18	0.02	0.01
Range	< 0.007 - 0.98	< 0.35 - 2.5	0.02	0.01
AM	0.14	1.23	0.02	0.01
G.M.	0.06	0.78	0.02	0.01

Preoperational (Range)	values	0.14- 0.85	0.7-3.4	≤0.05	≤0.04
Preoperational (GM)	values	0.23	1.65	0.05	0.04

Figure 1: Gross alpha and gross beta activity in air samples during 1988-2023 at NAPS Narora

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the summary of long-lived gross alpha, gross beta, ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr activity in air measured at NAPS, Narora. It is observed that gross alpha activity ranged from < 0.03 – 0.98 mBq m⁻³ with a geometric mean of 0.06 mBq m⁻³ while gross beta activity ranged from < 0.30 to 2.46 mBq m⁻³ with a geometric mean of 0.78 mBq m⁻³ during the study period. The data is comparable with preoperational data and it can be seen that mean gross beta and gross alpha activity in air particulate samples during the operation of the nuclear power plant at Narora are comparable with the values during the preoperational period (Sharma et al. 1989) indicating there is no impact of releases of particulate activity from NAPS to the atmosphere around Narora region. From Figure 1, it can be seen that the mean values are at the global fallout level. Both ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr activities were found to be less than the detection limit of 0.02 mBq m⁻³ in all the quarterly cumulative air filter samples collected during the years 1988-2023 as shown in Table 1.

CONCLUSIONS

The study of gross alpha and gross beta at Narora Atomic Power Station reveals that the value observed during the operational period is comparable with the values during the preoperational period. Thus, there is no impact of release of air particulate activity from NAPS.

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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A NUMERICAL CODE FOR THE TRANSPORT OF AEROSOLS THROUGH A NARROW CAPILLARY

S. SIVAKUMAR, A.J. SUDHA AND A.J ARUL

Radiation Shielding and Aerosol Transport Studies Division, Reactor Design Group, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam, 603102

KEYWORDS: Nuclear Aerosols, Aerosol Transport, Severe Accident, Plugging

INTRODUCTION

During a hypothetical Core Disruptive Accident (CDA) in a Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor (SFR), it is envisaged that about 350kg of sodium may get released into the Reactor Containment Building (RCB) through the leak paths in the top shield of the reactor main vessel. This may lead to a sodium fire, and the containment gets slightly pressurised due to sodium aerosols generated by combustion. A small fraction of the nuclear fuel/fission product aerosol is also generated by condensation of their vapours that reach RCB along with liquid sodium. The quantity of these mixed aerosols that may leak through the cracks developed in the RCB concrete walls due to their pressurisation is one of the crucial factors for evaluating the Environmental Source Term (EST) of radioactivity. It depends on the dynamics of aerosols within the RCB and the characteristics of the cracks formed. The present work aims to develop a code named AEROCAP for solving the transport equation of aerosols to predict the quantity of aerosol deposited inside a leak path, which will be modelled as a capillary for simplicity. The code is developed following the mathematical formulation derived by Mitrakos et al. (2008) to predict the transport and plugging of aerosols in a capillary. The code can predict quantities such as the plugging time, aerosol mass leaked through the capillary, gas leaked and plugged mass. The reliability of the code is ensured by comparing it with an analytical solution, and the agreement is very good. The code will be used to predict the plugging of leak paths in the containment in future.

METHODOLOGY

The model is based on the numerical solution of the one-dimensional aerosol transport equation and uses an approach based on calculating the total deposited mass to determine the evolution of the crack cross-section as a function of time. The methodology assumes that aerosol deposits uniformly around the capillary's inner perimeter, reducing the inner radius and finally leading to plugging. Various deposition mechanisms are considered, including gravitational settling, Brownian diffusion, turbulent diffusion, and eddy impaction. No assumptions are made on the profile of the aerosol plug along the leak path. A highly idealised geometrical description of the leak path is employed as a single straight capillary. The one-dimensional aerosol transport equation for a capillary is given by

$$\left(\frac{\partial C(z,t)}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial (u C(z,t))}{\partial z} - \frac{v_d \chi}{A} C(z,t)\right) \quad (1)$$

The numerical solution marches in time by first calculating the fluid velocity in each time step, and then Eq. (1) is solved using an implicit finite difference scheme where an upwind scheme is used to discretise the convection term.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The AEROCAP code is developed in Octave to study the transport and deposition of aerosols

through a narrow capillary. The developed code is validated with the analytical solution derived by Williams (1994) for the input conditions as listed in Table 1.

Parameter	Values
Length of the Capillary	10 cm
Radius of the Capillary	254 μm
Pressure Difference	5 kPa -20 kPa
Concentration	3 g/m ³ -3.6 g/m ³
Particle Diameter	1.4 μm
Temperature	300 K
Density of Aerosol Particle	2130 kg/m ³

Table 1. Input values for the code.

The analytical solution is derived based on the assumption of turbulent flow and considers eddy impaction as the only deposition mechanism. The results obtained are given in Table 2 and Figure 1.

Quantity	Analytical Solution	Predicted (AEROCAP)	Error %
Plugging Time (s)	217	197.7	9%
Leaked mass of aerosol(mg)	2.4	1.7	29%
Plugged mass of aerosol(mg)	11.1	11.4	2%
Quantity of gas leaked (l)	5.2	5.4	3%

Table 2. Comparison between theoretical predictions and analytical solution.

Figure 1 (a) Plugged Mass in the capillary with time (b) Change in capillary radius along its length.

CONCLUSIONS

Aerosol retention in the leak paths of the containment building during a severe accident is an important phenomenon that can reduce conservatism in the estimation of EST. A code named AEROCAP is developed to evaluate the transport of aerosols through a narrow capillary, a simplified and conservative geometry for modelling cracks. The methodology is based on the assumption of uniform aerosol deposition along the capillary's perimeter, which leads to the capillary plugging. Different deposition mechanisms are considered, such as gravitational settling, Brownian and turbulent diffusion and eddy impaction. The code can predict the change in the internal geometry, time required to plug the capillary, mass leaked out, and gas leaked out. The code is validated with the available analytical solution. The results predicted by the code agree with the analytical solution. It is planned to validate the code with experimental results. Further, parametric studies on influencing parameters will be carried out using the code.

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PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF PLUTONIUM AEROSOL DURING HEAT EXCHANGER REPLACEMENT WORK AT SPENT FUEL REPROCESSING PLANT

D. K PANDEY, N. PARASHAR, A. CHAKRABORTY, P. KUMAR, U. V. DEOKAR AND
J. P. N. PANDEY

Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai – 400 085, India.

KEYWORDS: PHWR, Reprocessing Plant, Aerosol, Particle Size, AMAD

INTRODUCTION

At a PHWR spent nuclear fuel facility, various process cells are designed to house the equipment handling different cycles of the PUREX process. For example, Process Cell-1 consist of HA cycles (Co-decontamination cum partitioning cycle), HAW evaporators and Rework cycle equipment. Thermosyphon Evaporators are used to concentrate HA cycle raffinate (HAW) having activity concentration in the range of 4000-7000 TBq/m³ ($\beta\gamma$). During the course of operations, the heat exchangers (HX) of these evaporators have shown a minor breach in their containment and hence it was replaced with new ones inside Process Cell-1. Replacing a failed HX involves cutting the old HX, edge preparation by grinding, and welding a new HX into the circuit, a process typically taking six months with multiple entries into the active cell. In spite of cell ventilation and arrangement of local exhaust, there is a likelihood of long-lived plutonium (Pu) air activity that can be released to the working personnel and increase the chances of inhalation. There is a likelihood of variation in particle size of airborne Pu during each stage of maintenance due to the different nature of processes involved. The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) has considered default particle size as 5- μ m activity median aerodynamic diameter (AMAD) and geometric standard deviation (GSD) of 2.5 for working out dose coefficients for different radionuclides. Determination of committed effective doses following inhalation intake requires site-specific knowledge about aerosol AMAD. A study was thus carried out for the characterisation of Plutonium aerosols during replacement of failed heat exchanger work at a typical PHWR spent fuel reprocessing plant. This study will help in the assessment of dose estimates due to intake for occupation workers in similar kind of operation.

METHODS

Particle Aerodynamic Size Separator (PASS) was used for sampling of aerosols during different maintenance operations like cutting, grinding and welding of HX made of SS-304L inside process Cell-1. The PASS operates at a flow rate of 45 lpm and segregates particles in size ranges of 0.53-8.95 μ m in seven class intervals (Singh, 2005). A backup filter gives an absolute collection of submicron particles. Glass fibre filter papers (2.95" diameter) were loaded onto all seven collection stages and the backup filter to capture particulate activity, with a 24-hour sampling period optimized to ensure sufficient collection of long-lived activity. The filter papers were measured for activity after 4 days to allow for decay of radon and thoron progenies. A large number of samples were collected however only ten such samples showed measurable activity which were considered for evaluation of AMAD. Alpha activity measurements at each stage of impactor samples were carried out using a wide area (100 cm²) silver activated zinc sulphide [ZnS (Ag)] scintillation detector. The background counts were noted each day before the sample counting. The alpha counter was calibrated using an electroplated plate source ²⁴¹Am of known activity. The average efficiency was

observed to be 25 %. The minimum detectable activity for sampling time of 24 h and counting time of 500 s is 1.65 mBq/m³.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Plutonium activity collected at each stage was worked out for all the samples collected from PASS. The percentage of total activity for different cut-off diameter of PASS during HX replacement work is displayed in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the average Pu activity percentage distribution for each stage of the impactor. The cumulative percentage of plutonium activity at each stage was calculated after measuring the activity. Cumulative percentage less than the stated size was plotted versus the Effective Cut off diameter (ECD) of that stage on log probability scale. The scatter plot for 10 samples is shown in Figure 2. For each sample, the linear regression line was evaluated ($y = a + bx$), where y is the “cumulative percentage less than stated size” and x is the ECD. AMAD for each sample was calculated by evaluating x at $y=50$. GSD for each sample is calculated by using the ratio of x at $y=50$ to x at $y=16$.

Figure-1. Percentage of Pu activity for each particle size distribution

Figur-2. Pu Aerosol AMAD Estimation (Sample 1 to 10)

The AMAD of Pu aerosol in during HX replacement work is found in the range 3.59 µm to 11.2 µm and the average AMAD representative for the work is 5.31 ± 0.72 µm with a GSD of 3.96 ± 0.30 . Aerosol activity is widely distributed with respect to aerodynamic diameter. Higher values of GSD (and hence, variation in particle size) were due to the different nature of the process (e.g., cutting, grinding, welding etc.) involved during HX replacement work.

CONCLUSIONS

Studies on the particle size distribution and characterization of Pu aerosols generated during Heat exchanger replacement work at the reprocessing plant were carried out. Since AMAD is the most relevant parameter of aerosol distribution which will assist in intake estimates, the study was aimed at determining aerosol size distribution using a cascade impactor. Particle size distribution during HX replacement work showed mean AMAD of $5.31 \pm 0.72 \mu\text{m}$ with GSD 3.96 ± 0.30 . Based on these AMAD and GSD values, the dose coefficient and ALI values can be derived for use in such operations which will help for an accurate estimate of the intake in case of any internal exposure to radiation workers.

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COMPREHENSIVE ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF FINE AND COARSE ATMOSPHERIC PARTICULATE MATTER UTILIZING SECONDARY TARGET-BASED EXCITATION X-RAY FLUORESCENCE EXCITATION TECHNIQUES

M. TIWARI^{*1,2}, S. K. SAHU^{1,2}, J. SUDHAKAR¹, P PADMA SAVITRI¹, V. PULHANI^{1,2}
AND A. VINOD KUMAR^{1,2}

¹Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre,
Mumbai- 400 085 India

²Homi Bhabha National Institute, Anushakti Nagar Mumbai– 400 094, India

*Corresponding Author Email: mtiwari@barc.gov.in

KEYWORDS: Atmospheric Particulate Matter, Air Quality, Edxrf, Elemental Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Analysing the elemental composition of atmospheric aerosols is essential for evaluating air quality, safeguarding human health, comprehending climate behaviour, and mitigating environmental effects. This analysis supports informed decision-making, the development of policies, and the implementation of strategies to tackle the issues arising from aerosol particles in the atmosphere. Particulate matter (PM) is categorized based on aerodynamic diameter into PM_{2.5} (fine), PM₁₀ (coarse), and TSP (total suspended particles) (Kim et al., 2010). Chemically characterizing particulate matter (PM) is crucial for epidemiological research and source apportionment studies, as it helps quantify the radiative forcing linked to PM in climate research. PM consists of a complex mixture that includes anions, cations, mineral dust, trace elements, organic carbon, elemental carbon, and water (Police et al., 2018). Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) is an effective technique for analysing atmospheric aerosols due to its ability to simultaneously detect and quantify a wide range of elements with high sensitivity and precision. In this study, we have optimized secondary target-based EDXRF methods for the multielement analysis of atmospheric particulate matter collected in a nucleopore filter paper. Thin films of each target element were used for qualitative and quantitative calibration of methods; subsequently, calibration was verified using a NIST SRM. These secondary targets based EDXRF methods were also applied for the analysis of aerosol samples collected from a DAE site at BARC, Vizag.

METHODS

Elemental analysis of the particles was performed using an Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) spectrometer (Xenometrix EX-6600), equipped with a Rhodium anode as the X-ray source, operating at 60 kV and 6 mA (400 W). The system was fitted with a silicon drift detector (SDD) with a resolution of 130 eV at 5.9 keV Mn X-ray and employed various secondary targets. Table 1 shows the optimized XRF parameters for selected target elements.

Table 1: XRF parameters and secondary targets/ filter used to analyse the different elements in air particulate matter samples.

Target elements	Secondary Target / Filter	Current (μA)	Voltage (kV)	Pre-set time (Second)	Atmosphere
Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Cu, Zn	Ge - target	2000	40	400	Air
Al, S, K, Ca	Ti- target	1000	27	500	Vacuum
Pb, Ba	W- filter	1000	55	500	Air

The instrument was calibrated using individual pure element or salt thin films (Micromatter Standards), and the analyte concentrations in the samples were subsequently determined based on these calibrations. The EDXRF measurement technique was validated with the NIST SRM 2783 reference material (air particulate on filter media, NIST, USA). The measured concentrations were found to be in good agreement with the certified values for NIST SRM 2783. Both fine (PM_{2.5}) and coarse (PM_{2.5-10}) particulate matter samples were collected using a Gent dichotomous sampler at BARC Vizag, which employed a stacked filter unit consisting of two 47 mm Nuclepore polycarbonate filters. These samples were analyzed for elemental concentration using the optimized EDXRF method

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A total of 14 elements were identified and quantified in the samples, and their mean concentrations are reported in Fig. 1. The order of abundance of target elements in air particulate matter is as follows: Al > Fe > Ca > K > Mn > S > Ti > Zn > Ba > Cu > Pb > Cr > V > Co. Crustal elements such as Al, Fe, and Ca are more abundant in the coarse fraction compared to the fine fraction of atmospheric particulate matter, indicating windblown dust as a contributor to the coarse fraction. Elements such as K, Mn, S, Zn, and Ba were found to be more concentrated in the fine fraction compared to the coarse fraction (Fig. 1), suggesting that fine particulate matter originates from combustion or anthropogenic sources. Malm et al. (1994) proposed that a K to Fe ratio of 0.6 ± 0.2 suggests the presence of potassium from soil dust. In our study, the K to Fe ratio was found to be 0.63 in PM₁₀, indicating a substantial contribution of soil dust to the particulate matter.

Fig 1. Elemental concentration (ng/m³) in (PM_{2.5}) and coarse (PM_{2.5-10}) particulate matter samples collected from BARC Vizag.

Among the analyzed elements, Pb is one of the criteria pollutants in PM, as listed in the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) by the CPCB, with annual limits of 1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The Pb concentration was found to be well below the annual limits during the monitoring period. This non-destructive method requires minimal sample preparation and can analyse various sample types, making it ideal for rapid, routine monitoring for regulatory purposes and for source apportionment studies of APM.

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CARBONATION OF SODIUM AEROSOL GENERATED BY SODIUM COMBUSTION WITH AMBIENT AND ZERO AIR

U. PUJALA^{1,2}, R. ANANTHANARAYANAN^{3,2}, V. SUBRAMANIAN², A. KUMAR^{4,2}, A. JASMIN SUDHA^{4,2}, and M. S. KRISHNA³

¹Health and Industrial Safety Division,

³Security and Innovative Sensors Division,

⁴Radiation Shielding and Aerosol Transport Studies Division, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research (IGCAR), Kalpakkam-603102, India.

²HBNI, Training School Complex, Anushaktinagar, Mumbai- 400094, India.

KEYWORDS: Sodium Aerosol, Combustion, Relative Humidity, Speciation.

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of hazard associated with NaOH species of sodium compound aerosol during accidental sodium fire is critical towards fast reactor safety. In a confined environment, the aerosol species are progressively converted from hydroxides to carbonates and bicarbonates with time for an initial concentration of 2 to 4 g/m³ (Ananthanarayanan et al., 2015). Open atmospheric sodium aerosol dispersion experiments observed that the aerosol samples at all downwind distances contained only bicarbonate. This may be due to the low particle concentrations (mg/m³) in the dispersed plume (or) conversion during aerosol sampling from the atmospheric air with abundant CO₂ and moisture (Subramanian et al., 2019). This study investigates the threshold aerosol concentration for instantaneous carbonation through closed-chamber experiments.

METHODS

The estimated threshold sodium aerosol concentration derived from chemical kinetic equations for 410 ppm of ambient CO₂ level is 1.5 g/m³ for instantaneous carbonate conversion, and 0.75 g/m³ if parallel bicarbonate species formation is considered. With this basis, experiments are conducted inside a leak-tight 1 m³ aerosol test chamber (Figure 1). The aerosols generated in the combustion cell are simultaneously allowed to flow into the aerosol chamber soon after the liquid sodium ignition. The time-varying speciation is studied for two combustion conditions separately, using ambient air (with moisture 75±3% RH and 410 ppm CO₂) and zero air (moisture and CO₂ free), and in each, for 3 different initial RH conditions of the aerosol chamber about 23%, 47%, and 78%. In ambient air combustion, carbonation occurs considerably inside the combustion cell, and these species reach the test chamber. Only oxides are formed in zero air combustion, and the carbonation starts once the aerosol reaches the test chamber conditioned with ambient air. Filter paper (FP) sampling is used to collect the aerosol samples from the test chamber at different instants up to 1300 s to analyse the chemical speciation. Each FP sample is immersed in a separate deionized demineralised water matrix immediately after the sampling and analysed for the speciation of NaOH, Na₂CO₃ and NaHCO₃ within 4 hours after sampling using a high-resolution pulsating conductometric titration technique (Ananthanarayanan et al., 2015). A gas analyser & Air velocity meter are used to monitor the aerosol chamber's CO₂, RH, and temperature levels (Figure 1).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The list of experimental conditions is given in Table 1. The variation of sodium aerosol speciation with time is presented in Figure 2 for ambient and zero conditions at 23% RH only. The speciation during generation (-ve time) is the combination of carbonate and bicarbonate, with bicarbonate dominant. After the generation of specified total concentration, the speciation is the combination of carbonate and bicarbonate, with carbonate being dominant. Overall, the carbonate is converted to bicarbonates in all three RH cases in both combustion conditions. Except at 23% RH, ambient combustion condition with 1.1 g/m³, the aerosol species are a combination of carbonates and bicarbonates all the time, and NaOH species are entirely absent (Figure 2). The aerosol species does not have NaOH in zero air combustion conditions at 23% RH, with 0.75 g/m³.

Figure 1. Schematic of test facility

Figure 2. Chemical speciation at 23% RH in ambient (left) and zero air combustion conditions (right).

The CO₂ and moisture consumptions are faster with an increase in RH condition for the given aerosol concentration, due to the rapid diffusion of CO₂ and moisture into the liquid state of particles, and faster conversion to carbonate and bicarbonate (Palntamp et al., 2016). The estimated cumulative CO₂ consumed within total time from the chemical analysis is compared with measured CO₂ from the analyser, presented in Table 1). The measured and estimated CO₂ consumption levels agree and support the measured speciation within 5 to 15%, except at 23% RH with ambient air combustion. At 23% RH, 1.1 g/m³, the large deviation is due to additional uncertainty in un-identifying small quantities of NaOH, which may present in FP samples but could convert when transferred to DI water in the presence of dissolved CO₂.

RH (%)	Concentration (g/m ³)	Time of last sampling (s)	Estimated CO ₂ (ppm)	Measured CO ₂ (ppm)	% deviation
Ambient air combustion					
78±2	1.1±0.2	1220	320	360±18	13.5
47±2	1.1±0.2	1215	327	284±14	15.1
23±2	1.1±0.2	1340	316	187±9	63.0
Zero air combustion					
78±2	1.5±0.2	1200	361	333±17	8.5
47±2	0.81±0.1	1250	305	323±16	5.6
23±2	0.75±0.1	1200	172	187±9	8.0

Table 1. Measured and estimated total CO₂ consumption by sodium aerosol inside the aerosol chamber.

CONCLUSIONS

At 78% RH, the carbonation is instantaneous, bicarbonate formation is faster, and the threshold conc. is of 1-1.5 g/m³. At 47% RH, the carbonation is instantaneous, but bicarbonate formation is comparatively slower, and the threshold conc. is of 1 g/m³. At 23% RH, the carbonation and bicarbonate formations are much slower, and the threshold conc. is of 0.75 g/m³. The aerosol concentration below this threshold gets rapidly converted to NaHCO₃ due to abundant CO₂ and moisture levels as observed in open atmosphere.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors sincerely thank former Director IGCAR, Director EIG, Director RDG, AD SQRMG, AD EPG, Head HISD, Head HPS for supporting the work; team of SISD, in the chemical analysis of the samples.

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EFFECT OF DYNAMIC SHAPE FACTOR ON AEROSOL DYNAMICS USING COUPLED FLUID-PARTICLE DYNAMICS APPROACH

J. KRISHAN^{1,2}, S. ANAND^{1,2}

¹Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai – 400 094, India.

²Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Aerosols, Dynamic Shape Factor, Fluid Dynamics, Aerosol Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The distribution of aerosols released in a containment-like closed environment may not be uniform (Sapra et al., 2008). Generally, used uniformly mixed models are not able to capture this heterogeneity in the aerosol distribution and hence, necessitates the development of a coupled fluid-particle dynamics (CFPD) approach as pointed out in the EPRI report (2018). This coupled approach can predict the aerosol behaviour in a closed environment even under complex or dynamic boundary conditions. An OpenFOAM (Weller et al., 1998) library-based solver, Aerosolved (Lucci et al, 2022) combines the transport of aerosols with fluid flow to model the interplay between aerosols and the surrounding airflows. Also, morphology of aerosol aggregates plays a vital role in determining its settling characteristics. The aerosol aggregates may be non-spherical in general and hence, dynamic shape factors are introduced to account for the non-spherical nature of these aerosol aggregates. Therefore, Aerosolved is modified by introducing the expressions for size-dependent dynamic shape factors and the new solver thus created is referred to as DyAerosolved. In order to demonstrate the importance of implementation of these shape factors in the CFPD code, the evolution of aerosol concentration is studied in a 10.0 m³ chamber at a nuclear aerosol test facility (NATF). DyAerosolved solver can be used to study the spatial and temporal behaviour of aerosols released in reactor containment under accidental conditions, which will further improve the estimation of source terms during such accidental scenario.

METHODS

The simulation involves the construction of geometry followed by meshing, definition of boundary and input conditions. The chamber geometry used in the simulation consists of three ports including one inlet and two outlets. The generation of geometry and meshing is done using the student version of Ansys Workbench 2023 R2 (Ansys student) and the mesh file generated is converted to the OpenFoam compatible format followed by the definition of boundary conditions. The aerosols with a CMD of 0.21 μm and GSD of 2.6 are injected in the chamber for 20 minutes with a velocity of 0.28 m/s. the initial aerosol concentration at the inlet is 3.22 g/m³. The chamber is assumed to be 1 atm pressure and a temperature of 293K. The velocity, dispersed and continuous phase mass fraction inputs are time dependent where the release phase continues for 20 mins and stops after that. After the release phase is over, aerosol concentration in the containment evolves due to coagulation, diffusion, gravitational settling and drift. For each of the volume elements, the equation of continuity, momentum, energy and species transport equation are solved. The governing aerosol dynamics equation is solved using a sectional method where the size bin is divided into 'n' number of bins and the aerosols are distributed among these bins for a given value of CMD and GSD assuming the distribution of aerosols to be log-normal. The governing equations for the drift and relaxation time are modified to account for the modification in the aerodynamic properties of the aerosols due to non-spherical nature. The dynamic shape factor (χ) is introduced in the

Brownian diffusivity term as given by,

$$D(d)=(k_B T C_c)/(3 \pi \mu d \chi) \quad (1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, C_c is the Cunningham slip correction factor, d is the diameter of the aerosol particle, μ is the fluid viscosity. The corresponding relaxation time (τ) for the droplets undergoing Stokes drag is modified to,

$$\tau=(\rho_m d^2)/(18 \mu \chi) \quad (2)$$

The dynamic shape correction terms added in the governing equations ensure that the governing equations are valid for the non-spherical aggregates as well which are generally encountered in the practical problems of interest. The results thus obtained by running the simulation using Aerosolved solver are discussed in the following section and will be compared with the results from DyAerosolved in future.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The evolution of aerosol mass concentration profile predicted by Aerosolved shows a similar trend as observed during experiments carried out by Sapra et al (2008) (Fig. 1). The mass concentration observed at the lower port is higher as compared to the upper port as the settling of aerosols leads to migration of these aerosols from higher height to a lower part in the spatial domain. However, there is a difference in the absolute values and the rate of reduction of aerosol mass concentration. This difference may be attributed to the uncertainties in the measurement of aerosol metrics near the release point and the fact that the aerosols are assumed to be spherical in the present results. These aerosols are observed to be fractals during the measurements. To account for this, the correction has been incorporated and the case is being studied using the developed solver DyAerosolved.

Figure 1. Evolution of aerosol mass concentration in NATF chamber using CFPD code and comparison with experimental observations

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights the importance of a CFPD code and the necessity to incorporate corrections for the non-spherical nature of the aerosol aggregates for realistic estimates of aerosol concentration in a containment-like environment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge Dr D K Aswal, Director, HS&EG for his support, Dr Rudra and Dr Thaseem, IIT-Goa for useful technical discussions and suggestions.

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ESTIMATION OF ELECTROSPRAYED DROPLET DIAMETER

R. PARVEEN¹, H. RAWATE¹, A. KHAN², M. JOSHI²,
Y S MAYYA¹ ANDROCHISH AND M. THAKAR¹

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai

²Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai

KEYWORDS: Electrospray Atomization, Air Cleaning, Particle Capture, Aerosol Instrument

INTRODUCTION

Electrosprays are devices which generate fine droplet sprays ejected from electrified nozzles (Jaworek and Sobczyk (2008)). A major challenge in electrospray diagnostics is to estimate the droplet sizes. Broadly speaking, the droplets would occur in two size groups: namely large primary droplets and smaller satellite droplets which are formed due to the Rayleigh break-up of primary droplets and are sub-nanometric in size. Because of the high velocity of these droplets due to their motion in a strong electric field, it is difficult to sample them into sizing instruments for performing size analysis. Singh et al. (2013) measured the sizes of electrospray droplets using SMPS by pre-neutralizing the droplets using a radioactive source. However, it was possible to estimate the size distribution of only the satellite droplets in the size range of less than 100nm. The larger primary droplet sizes were measured by investigators in the past using phase-doppler-anemometry (Gañán-Calvo et al. (1997), Tang, K., and Gomez, A. (1994)). This instrument is somewhat expensive and not readily available. One can still obtain an estimate of the sizes of primary droplets by using the information on the operating data of the electrospray combined with theoretical reasoning. One such approach is based on the current measurements. In this paper we present the theoretical basis of this technique and validate it against the electrospray system set up in IIT Bombay as well as against known previous studies.

METHODS

The IITB electrospray studies were conducted using a concoction of water-ethanol mixture (50% ethanol) as the working fluid. The system is made up with a chamfered shape stainless steel needle (ID: 0.25 mm, OD: 0.3 mm) held above a grounded plate at a distance of 3 cm. The fluid is driven by a syringe pump at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/h to 0.5 mL/h. A potential of 4-5kV is applied to form a stable electrospray in the cone-jet mode. The current is measured as a function of varying potential until corona discharge is found to occur (shown in Figure 1(a)). This exercise is carried out at different flow rates.

Theory: It is possible to obtain an estimate of the sizes of droplets ejected from the nozzle using the following argument. If the current measured at the stage of formation of a stable electrospray is denoted by (I) for a liquid flow rate (Q_f), then the volumetric charge density (ρ_c) in the fluid is defined as, $\rho_c = I/Q_f$. We now assume that this charge density is uniform across all droplet sizes. In that case, the total charge (Q_d) is carried by a typical droplet of size d , as $Q_d = \rho_c \left[\frac{\pi}{6} d^3 \right] = \frac{\pi}{6} I/Q_f d^3$, it would be true for all the droplet sizes. However, due to the presence of electric charge, the droplets will develop Rayleigh instability if the charge contained in the droplet exceeds its Rayleigh limit, given by, $Q_R = (8 \pi^2 \epsilon_0 \gamma d^3)^{1/2}$. Where, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space and γ is the surface tension of the liquid. The current value for the stable cone-jet mode (Figure 1(a)) was used to estimate the charge density at different sizes. The plot in Figure 1 (b), shows a comparison of the acquired

charge (Q_d) and the Rayleigh limit (Q_R) for the water-ethanol mixture as a function of droplet size. As may be seen, for larger droplets the acquired charge dominates and for smaller droplets Rayleigh charge is higher. Since droplets cannot exist with charges higher than the Rayleigh charge, the crossover point is the diameter at or below which the droplets will exist. Since Rayleigh break-up process involves expelling a large charge (40%) with very little (~1-4%) loss of mass (Gawande et al. 2017), the size of the primary droplets will alter very little in the initial stages. This is essentially an upper limit since evaporation and break-up events will eventually create a broad droplet spectrum as they traverse in the electrospray.

Figure 1: (a) Current measurement plot for different flow rate, (b) Crossover point of Rayleigh charge and estimated volumetric charge

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

By comparing the Rayleigh charge with the acquired charge at the cross-over point, we

determined the maximum droplet diameter, as
$$d_{max} \approx \left(\frac{\sqrt{8\epsilon_0\gamma}}{\rho_c} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$$
.

For the present case for the water-ethanol mixture, it yields $d_{max} = 3.3 \mu\text{m}$ (same as the cross-overpoint in Fig. (2b)), thereby indicating that the droplets in the spray are at or below $3.3 \mu\text{m}$. This assessment (without direct measurements) has helped optimize the system for applications. In order to test the validity of the value of d_{max} , we make use of the experimental data of Gañán-Calvo et al. (1997), who employed phase-doppler anemometry to measure droplet sizes. They reported a mean droplet diameter of about $34.6 \mu\text{m}$ for heptane having a conductivity of $4.3 \mu\text{S/m}$, flow rate of $1.53 * 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and a current of $4.5 * 10^{-8} \text{ A}$. The cross-over point occurs for $d_{max} = 39 \mu\text{m}$, which is quite close to their directly measured diameter. This agreement lends strong support for our approach to estimating droplet diameter.

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical approach derived here offers a simple way to estimate primary droplet sizes. It is essentially an upper bound rather than the mean size and is useful for assuring that one does not have to include droplets larger than this size in developing theoretical models. The sizes of satellite droplets however cannot be obtained this way and need to be estimated with more detailed modelling of the evaporative shrinkage, Rayleigh break up processes and validated by instrumental technique.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Board of Research in Nuclear Sciences through sanction number 59/14/11/2022-BRNS/34062

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COMPARATIVE RADIATIVE FORCING OF METHANOL-SOLUBLE VS. WATER-SOLUBLE CARBON IN ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS

T.D. RATHOD^{1,2}, S. K. SAHU*^{1,2}, M. TIWARI^{1,2}, R.C. BHANGARE¹ AND P.Y. AJMAL¹

¹Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai- 400 085 India

²homi Bhabha National Institute, Anushakti Nagar Mumbai– 400 094, India

*Corresponding Author Email: Sksahu@Barc.Gov.In

KEYWORDS: Carbonaceous Aerosols; Organic Carbon; Absorption Coefficients; Absorption Angstrom Exponent

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols, which significantly impact the Earth's climate system are categorized as organic carbon (OC) and black carbon (BC), with BC being a powerful light absorber (Bond et al., 2013). Some OC, known as brown carbon (BrC), also absorbs light, and understanding its absorption is vital for climate analysis. Various methods exist to measure BrC, including molecular analysis, particle characterization, and optical techniques. A commonly used method for optical measurement of BrC is achieved through water or organic solvent extraction followed by BrC absorption measurement in the extracts using UV-visible spectroscopy (Chen and Bond, 2010). This method allows for the assessment of BrC absorbance without interference from BC. Typically, water along with methanol solvent has been extensively used to report BrC optical absorption properties. Measurements of these optical characteristics of MSOC and WSOC extracts can be used to estimate its radiative forcing potential. The present study focuses on Mumbai, examining the light-absorbing capabilities of WSOC and MSOC, and estimating their relative radiative forcing in the urban area of Mumbai.

METHODS

In this study, particulate matter with a diameter less than 2.5 μm (PM2.5) was collected in an urban area of Mumbai (19.01° N, 72.92° E), India, known for its dense population and industrial activity. Sampling was conducted twice a week for 24 hours each, from September 2017 to May 2018, totalling 62 samples. The collected PM2.5 samples were analysed for WSOC and MSOC extracts. Their optical properties like absorption coefficients, mass absorption coefficients, and absorption angstrom exponent were estimated using UV-visible spectroscopy analysis (Liu et al., 2013). These optical properties were used to estimate the relative radiative forcing using equation 1.

$$f_{MSOC} = \frac{\int I(\lambda) \left\{ 1 - e^{-\left(MAC_{365,MSOC} \left(\frac{365}{\lambda} \right)^{AA_{MSOC}} \cdot C_{MSOC} \cdot h_{ABL} \right)} \right\} d\lambda}{\int I(\lambda) \left\{ 1 - e^{-\left(MAC_{550,BC} \left(\frac{550}{\lambda} \right)^{AA_{BC}} \cdot C_{BC} \cdot h_{ABL} \right)} \right\} d\lambda} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

Here, f_{MSOC} is the relative radiative forcing due to MSOC. $MAC_{365,MSOC}$ is the mass absorption efficiency or cross-section of MSOC at 365 nm. C_{MSOC} is the concentration of MSOC, h_{ABL} is the atmospheric boundary layer, C_{BC} is the BC concentration, $MAC_{550,BC}$

BC is the mass absorption efficiency or cross-section of BC at 550 nm, taken as $7.5 \pm 1.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (Bond and Bergstrom, 2006). The information regarding the atmospheric boundary layer height (hABL) was retrieved from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF, ERA-5) reanalysis data archive. The relative radiative forcing was estimated for UV (300 nm -400 nm), visible (400 nm – 800 nm) and infrared wavelengths (800 nm – 2500 nm), respectively. Similar calculations were repeated for estimating the relative radiative forcing due to WSOC.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

It was found that the contribution of MSOC to relative radiative forcing was significantly higher than the contribution of WSOC across all wavelength ranges considered. In the case of MSOC as well as WSOC, UV absorption contributed to a large proportion of the relative radiative forcing. There was a 15.3 % contribution from MSOC to the UV wavelength region in contrast to a 12 % contribution from WSOC in the same wavelength region. With the inclusion of visible and infrared wavelengths into the calculations, the contribution to the relative radiative forcing decreased systematically. This is expected as the major absorption region of MSOC and WSOC is at UV and near UV-visible wavelengths. The substantial light absorption due to OC in UV wavelengths could have a significant impact on atmospheric chemical reactions by influencing the formation of ozone and other radicals like OH and HO₂. The calculated fractional contribution in the UV-visible region for MSOC and WSOC, respectively, was $10.1 \pm 5.2 \%$ (range: 2.6 - 25 %) and $6.3 \pm 3.8 \%$ (range: 2 – 14.2 %).

Figure 1. Relative radiative forcing calculated at different wavelength regimes for the Mumbai location for (a) MSOC and (b) WSOC

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the significant role of MSOC in contributing to relative radiative forcing, particularly in the UV wavelength region, compared to WSOC in the urban atmosphere of Mumbai. MSOC as a surrogate for BrC can provide better estimates of its radiative forcing potential compared to WSOC.

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EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL COMPARISON OF SODIUM AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS AND THERMAL HYDRAULICS IN COVER GAS SPACE

A. KUMAR^{1,3}, P. R. PATEL^{2,3}, S. KRISHNAKUMAR⁴, J.A. SUDHA^{1,3}, S.M. ALI², S. CHANDRAMOULI⁴, D.K. MOHAPATRA² AND A.J. ARUL^{1,3}

¹Engineering Physics Group, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam

²Safety Research Institute, Atomic Energy Regulatory Board, Kalpakkam – 603 102, India.

³Homi Bhabha National Institute, Training School Complex, Anushaktinagar Mumbai

⁴Fast Reactor Technology Group, Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam

KEYWORDS: Cover Gas, Sodium Aerosol, SFR, OPENFOAM.

INTRODUCTION

Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors (SFR) require an inert cover gas space to isolate the highly reactive liquid sodium. Within this space, due to the temperature gradient between the sodium pool and top shield, several phenomena co-occur, viz., sodium evaporation, vapour nucleation and condensation, convective flow, heat and mass transfer, aerosols coagulation and deposition. The behaviour of sodium aerosols is crucial for reactor engineering safety, as they can impact thermal hydraulics and radiological consequences during severe accidents. Understanding and predicting the impact of sodium aerosols on thermal hydraulics on the top shield structure and cooling requirement is of significant interest. The deposition of aerosols on the top shield structure across the cover gas space may hinder the movement of reactor components through the top shield penetrations. Also, the aerosol characteristics influence the coolant leakage detection system, cover gas purification system and assessment of radiological consequences during severe accident scenarios (Huang et al., 2019). A multi-physics model coupled with a CFD model is necessary to comprehensively understand the cover gas region thermal hydraulics and aerosol dynamics and their verification with simulated experiments. This study employs a detailed 3D CFD model to investigate the sodium aerosol characteristics and thermal hydraulics parameters within the cover gas space. The model is validated against the results of the Test Pot (TP-1) of the SILVERINA loop. The results will contribute to a deeper understanding of sodium aerosol behaviour and provide valuable insights into the thermal hydraulics and engineering safety of SFRs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For SFRs, the sodium vapour pressure would be sufficiently high during reactor operation to promote sodium evaporation from the pool, leading to nucleation and condensation of the sodium vapour, which generates the aerosol. The generated sodium aerosol would be transported under the influence of the temperature difference between the sodium pool and the top shield surface. This necessitates the study of aerosol behaviour and thermal hydraulics in the cover gas space under reactor operating conditions. For the current study, a mixture-based Eulerian model is used, which is validated against in-house experiments at the SILVERINA loop and governing equations are solved in the modified Aerosolved, written in the OpenFOAM framework (Parth et al., 2023). During reactor operation, the cover gas experiences a higher temperature difference between the pool and the top shield (~410 K). Aerosol behaviour in cover gas under 823 K sodium pool and 413 K roof temperatures is studied. The geometrical parameters of the TP-1 vessel are as follows: the vessel height is ~ 2235 mm, the inner diameter is 760 mm, and the cover gas height is ~ 820 mm (Kumar et al., 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1 shows the sodium aerosol concentration near the sodium pool surface (715 mm), the middle region (415 mm) and near the top surface (215 mm). The measured count median diameter (CMD) of sodium aerosol near the sodium pool, middle region and the top region are $7.7\mu\text{m}$, $3.9\mu\text{m}$ and $3.8\mu\text{m}$, respectively. The total sodium aerosol concentration is higher near the pool surface than in the middle region and near the top surface. Further, the larger diameter aerosols are found to be nearer to the pool surface due to the influence of gravitational force. However, the smaller diameter aerosol is closer to the top surface because smaller particles can only be transported to the top region. In the central part of the cover region, a uniform distribution of $1 - 20\mu\text{m}$ aerosol exists. From the simulation, it is found that the smaller aerosol exists in the whole cover gas region. In contrast, the larger ones do not exist near the top surface because the larger ones are heavier and difficult to carry by the mixed gas convection. These aerosol phenomena are also estimated and given in Fig. 2. The heavier particles $\sim 23\mu\text{m}$ are mainly concentrated near the sodium pool only. This is also seen in the experimental observation, where, in the bottom-most elevation, particles $> 5\mu\text{m}$ are dominant. Further, due to high condensation rates near the pool surface, $< 1\mu\text{m}$ aerosols are not seen. The temperature variation across the vertical direction ranges from 393 to 823 K. Though temperature varies widely, the average temperature in the cover gas is ~ 600 K. The average convective velocity in cover space is 0.4 m/s; however, the peak convective velocity is near the wall surface (~ 0.8 m/s).

Fig. 1 The aerosol size-dependent number concentration for three locations in the cover gas space (left), the total aerosol number density and CMD (centre) as a function of cover gas height and aerosol size-dependent mass concentration for three locations in the cover gas space (right).

Fig. 2 The aerosols distribution of diameter $23\mu\text{m}$ (left), the temperature contour inside the cover gas space (centre) and convective velocity inside the cover gas space (right).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A detailed 3D CFD model was employed to simulate the aerosol characteristics and thermal

hydraulics parameters within the cover gas space at the reactor operating temperature. The results of the CFD model are compared with experimental observations. The experimental observation found that the CMD is higher near the pool than in the middle and near the top region of the cover gas space. However, the total aerosol concentration is higher near the pool than in the middle and near the top area. The larger diameter aerosol is nearer to the pool surface, and the smaller aerosol is closer to the top surface. This was also observed in the CFD simulations, where the heavier particles $\sim 23 \mu m$ were mainly concentrated near the sodium pool surface. The CFD model predicted an average count median diameter (CMD) of $\sim 7 \mu m$, consistent with experimental findings. Additionally, the numerically estimated average cover gas temperature of ~ 600 K and peak convective velocity of ~ 0.8 m/s near wall surfaces. The numerical estimates agree with the experimental observations. In the future, these validated CFD models can be used to estimate aerosol deposition in annular penetrations of the top shield.

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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON PARTICULATE MATTER AT THE KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR SITE

P. JAYASUDHA¹, B. VIJAYAKUMAR¹ AND I. V. SARADHI²

¹Environmental Survey Laboratory, Kudankulam Nuclear Power Project, Tirunelveli

²Environmental Monitoring & Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai 400 085

Communicating author: vijaykumarb@barc.gov.in

KEYWORDS: PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, Meteorological, Relative Humidity

INTRODUCTION

A primary atmospheric component of air pollution, i.e., particulate matter (PM), has become a major source of concern all around the world due to its impacts on air quality, human health, and the earth's ecosystem. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} refer to airborne particulate matter having aerodynamic diameters of $\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, respectively (Spandana et al., 2021). PM_{2.5} is significantly more harmful than PM₁₀ due to their complexity and smaller size (Miri et al., 2017). Industry, power plants, vehicular use and other combustion activities are all responsible for the production of PM, which comes from both primary emission and chemical alteration of precursor gases, which results in secondary particles. According to their size, fine PM can reach the deeper regions of the lungs, whereas coarse PM may be deposited in upper regions like the thoracic path (Mehta et al, 2008). In general, the availability of air pollutants, to a great extent, is influenced by climatic factors such as relative humidity, wind speed, among others. In this paper, the dispersion of particulate matter PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the dry season and wet season and the influence of meteorological parameters viz. relative humidity, temperature and wind speed on particulate pollution is discussed.

METHODS

Airborne particulate samples were collected for 24 hours at ground level for the period 2019-2023 (56 samples) at Kudankulam nuclear power project construction site, where 2 units are under operation and 4 units are under construction. PM₁₀ was collected using a Respirable Dust Sampler (Envirotech) with a cone separator on a glass fibre filter paper of area 382 sq.cm (22.2 cm X 17.2cm) and for PM_{2.5}teflon filter paper of 30 mm diameter is used for collection using PM_{2.5} samplers. PM_{2.5}& PM₁₀ data obtained in the study and the meteorological data collected at the site are used for analysis using the Pearson Correlation method.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The statistical analysis of particulate matter and meteorological parameters during the period 2019-2023 is given in Table 1. During the study period, the PM₁₀ values ranged from 27.1 to 65.1 with a mean value of 53.7 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ whereas the PM_{2.5} values ranged from 13.6 to 32.7 with a mean value of 24.6 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$. The levels of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} observed are well within the limits of the National Ambient Air Quality Standards stipulated by the Central Pollution Control Board. Figure 1 presents the variation of mean concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} during dry season (March – September) and wet season (October - February). As shown in the figure, the average PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} levels during dry season are 55.1 and 25.2 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$

respectively while during the wet season, the mean concentrations are 24.0 and 20.0 $\mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ for PM10 and PM2.5 respectively which is about half compared to the dry season. Pearson correlation analysis was used to study the influence of meteorological parameters on PM2.5 and PM10. For PM2.5, temperature has a positive influence ($r=0.3$, $p < 0.05$) while a negative correlation was observed for relative humidity ($r= - 0.25$, $p < 0.05$) and wind speed ($r= - 0.14$, $p < 0.28$). A similar pattern was also observed for PM10, having a positive correlation with temperature ($r=0.52$, $p < 0.05$), and a negative correlation with relative humidity ($r= - 0.36$, $p < 0.05$) while there was a non-significant correlation with wind speed ($r= - 0.09$, $p < 0.23$). The wind speed at the site ranged between 1.20-10.8 m.s^{-1} with a mean of 3.8 m.s^{-1} and 4.70-5.10 m.s^{-1} dominated the wind speed frequency. The insignificant Pearson Correlation coefficients for PM2.5 and PM10 with wind speed indicate that this parameter is not a reliable predictor for PM2.5 and PM10 concentration at this site. However, a reasonably good positive correlation was observed with temperature with Pearson Correction coefficients of 0.52 and 0.30 with PM10 and PM2.5 respectively. Kudankulam, being a coastal site, the temperature varied from 20 to 39.8°C with a mean value of 29.3 °C during the study period.

Table1. Descriptive Statistics of PM & climatic indices

Parameters	PM10	PM2.5	Wind speed (m/s)	RH (%)	Temp (°C)
Mean	53.7	24.6	3.78	78	29.3
SD	7.9	3.1	0.11	0.89	1.8
Max	65.1	32.7	10.8	100	39.8
Min	27.1	13.6	1.2	30	20

Figure 1. Variation of mass concentration of PM10, PM2.5 level in dry and wet seasons (2019-2023)

CONCLUSION

The particulate matter levels have been measured at Kudankulam nuclear power plant site during the period 2019-2023 and statistical analysis has been carried out to determine the influence of meteorological parameters like temperature, relative humidity and wind speed. Both PM10 and PM2.5 have shown a marginally positive correlation with temperature whereas the influence of wind speed is insignificant. Statistically significant differences in PM2.5 & PM10 concentration levels are observed in different months of the year. The study indicates that apart from local meteorological parameters, other factors such as long-range transport of pollutants, and other sources may also influence the particulate matter concentrations at Kudankulam site.

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EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL COMPARISON OF SODIUM AEROSOL RADIOLOGICAL DOSE ASSESSMENT FROM ATTACHED AND UNATTACHED RADON-THORON PROGENY FRACTIONS IN INDOOR ENVIRONMENT

O. P. NAUTIYAL¹, A. RAWAT¹, M. JOSHI², P. SINGH¹, T. AHAMAD¹

¹Uttarakhand Science Education and Research Centre, Dehradun, India-248001

²Radiological Physics and Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India-400094

*Corresponding Address: Prakhar Singh, theoreticalps@gmail.com

KEYWORDS: Indoor Measurements; Activity Concentrations; Radon-Thoron Progeny; Aerosols; Attachment Fraction; Attachment Rate; Dose.

INTRODUCTION

This study aimed to evaluate the radiological dose due to inhalation of attached (to aerosols) and unattached ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn progeny in indoor environments across 80 locations in the eastern Kumaun Himalayan region, India. Direct Progeny Sensors (DTPS/DRPS) and LR-115 type-II detectors were employed to measure the total progeny concentrations (including both attached and unattached fractions) of ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn, while wire-mesh-capped sensors were used to assess the attached fractions. The attachment of progeny to aerosol particles was also examined, as it influences deposition rates in the human respiratory system. Unattached progeny is typically more readily deposited in the deeper lung regions, whereas attached progeny is carried by aerosols and deposited in the upper respiratory tract. Using the Human Respiratory Tract Model, inhalation doses for nasal and oral breathing were calculated. The average unattached fraction for ²²²Rn progeny (0.22) was 2.2 times higher than the UNSCEAR recommended value (0.1), and for ²²⁰Rn progeny (0.33), it significantly exceeded the recommended level (0.02). Total progeny concentrations, as well as the attached/unattached fractions of ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn, were higher in mud houses compared to cemented structures. Dose Conversion Factors (DCF) for nasal and oral breathing were calculated using the Porstendörfer approach, accounting for aerosol size and attachment dynamics (Porstendörfer, 1994). The calculated total annual effective dose (AED) remained within the ICRP reference limits, though the inhalation dose (ID) for oral breathing was found to be 2.5 times greater than for nasal breathing (Clement et al., 2010).

METHODS

This study comprises of seasonal (Winter, Summer, and Rainy) passive measurement for 120 straight days for each season of indoor accumulation of radioactive isotopes of radon (²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn) which are commonly known as radon and thoron and their short-lived progenies (²¹⁸Po, ²¹⁶Pb, ²¹⁴Po, and ²¹²Pb). To conduct this study solid state nuclear track detectors (SSNTDs) were deployed in single-entry pinhole dosimeters (for gas concentrations), direct progeny sensors (DPS) for progeny concentrations, wire-meshed direct progeny sensors to segregate the attached and unattached progenies in an indoor environment. The following models are used to calculate the dose to humans via exposure to these radionuclides (Kumar et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2009).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average activity concentrations of radon (EERC, Bq/m³) and thoron (EETC, Bq/m³) along with Attached-Unattached (EERCU+A) and Attached (EERCA, Bq/m³) progeny concentrations, and Attached Fraction (F'Rn) and Unattached fraction (FRn) are given in the table below. Figure 1 depicts the frequency distribution of annual effective dose (mSv/y) due to exposure to radon and thoron in an indoor environment to the inhabitants.

Table 1: Activity Concentrations of Radon and Thoron's Progenies in terms of Equivalent Equilibrium Concentrations and Attached-Unattached fractions.

Activity Concentration (in Bq/m ³)	Average Seasonal Variation (AM ± SD)		
	Rainy	Winter	Summer
EERCU+A	22.67 ±10.51	23.34 ±10.54	22.81 ±10.40
EERCA	19.79 ±10.39	8.88 ±8.38	5.96 ±1.64
EERCU	2.88 ±2.18	14.46 ±6.37	16.85 ±9.52
F'Rn	0.85 ± 0.12	0.36 ± 0.16	0.30 ± 0.11
FRn	0.15 ± 0.12	0.64 ± 0.16	0.70 ± 0.11
EETCU+A	3.54 ± 1.47	3.85 ± 1.50	3.67 ± 1.51
EETCA	2.20 ± 0.58	2.36 ± 0.60	2.25 ±0.62
EETCU	1.34 ± 1.06	1.49 ± 1.08	1.42 ± 1.09
F'Th	0.68 ± 0.17	0.66 ± 0.17	0.66 ± 0.17
FTh	0.32 ± 0.17	0.34 ± 0.17	0.34 ± 0.17

Abbreviation: AM=Arithmetic Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

CONCLUSIONS

1. The unattached fraction of ²²²Rn progeny was found to be 0.22, which is 2.2 times higher than the UNSCEAR recommended value of 0.1. For ²²⁰Rn progeny, the average unattached fraction was 0.33, significantly higher than the recommended value of 0.02.
2. Significant variations were observed in the attached and unattached radon and thoron progeny due to seasonal changes and different types of dwellings, showing normal distribution of data.
3. The equilibrium equivalent concentration for radon-attached progeny ranged from 2.67 to 37.04 Bq/m³, while for thoron-attached progeny, it ranged from 0.56 to 3.30 Bq/m³. The study also observed that the average total progeny concentration (attached + unattached) was higher in mud houses.

4. The calculated total annual effective dose (AED) was within the ICRP reference level, yet the study underscores the importance of including both attached and unattached fractions in dose assessments for more accurate health risk evaluations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Department of Atomic Energy (DAE), Board of Research in Nuclear Science (BRNS), Mumbai, India, for extending their laboratory facilities and funding for the research work (Project Ref. 36(4)/14/46/2016-BRNS). The authors also acknowledge the Uttarakhand Science Education and Research Centre (USERC), Dehradun for providing laboratory and basic facilities for conducting the above experimental work.

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INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF AEROSOL DENSITY AND CHARGE ON DEPOSITION DYNAMICS IN THE CONTEXT OF NUCLEAR REACTOR ACCIDENT

A. KHAN, MARIAM, M. JOSHI, A. NAKHWA, S. AHAMAD AND B.K. SAPRA

Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre,
Mumbai 400085, India

KEYWORDS: NATF, Nuclear Aerosols, ELPI, SMPS

INTRODUCTION

Radioactive aerosol particles (fission products, actinides, structural materials) are released into RCS (Reactor coolant system) and containment following a severe nuclear reaction accident. Deposition and interaction mechanisms acting on aerosols decide their fate and life in containment, which is governed by their size, number concentration, charge and shape. Aerosol number concentration can vary in a wide range depending on the severe accident scenario, accident progression and the location. Therefore, it is important to understand the aerosol dynamics through experimental and theoretical studies for accurate source term estimation and nuclear safety. Such studies in the past have been extensively carried out worldwide especially for the light water reactors in the context of probabilistic safety assessment. However, limited studies exist for Pressurized Heavy Water Reactor (PHWR). Therefore, experiments have been carried out in Nuclear Aerosol Test Facility (NATF), simulating aerosol phenomenon in the context of the Indian PHWR reactors (Mayya et al., 2005; Sapra et al. 2008). In these experiments, aerosols were characterized in the containment atmosphere for their number and charge size distribution, density and shape.

METHODOLOGY

NATF facility comprises a 10 m³ test vessel, plasma torch aerosol generator (PTAG) and aerosol instrumentation. The vessel is equipped with a fan for homogenization and multiple ports. Zn metallic powder was aerosolized using PTAG and fed into the vessel and measurements were made at inlet ports as well as vessels (Fig 1). The number size distribution and charge size distribution were estimated using SMPS (scanning mobility particle sizer) and ELPI (electrical-low pressure impactor) respectively. The aerosol collected on a gross sampler were analyzed for their shape using SEM (scanning electron microscope).

Fig 1. Schematic of experimental set-up (P1 -P5: sampling ports on chamber)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The PTAG was operated for half an hour (10:45 to 11:15) and the generated aerosols were continuously measured using SMPS and ELPI even after the generation was stopped. Figure 2 shows the measured number concentration, geometric mean (GM) and charge/particle at different times. As can be seen from fig 2(a) particles coagulated from ~ 40 nm to ~ 300 nm as they travelled from the inlet side to the chamber. The number concentration at the inlet reached up to 108 particles/cc. When the plasma torch was ON, the charge per particle reached up to +35 for particles of $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ size, then decreased. After 1 hour, the charge per particle for $0.12 \mu\text{m}$ aerosols turned negative, stayed negative for the next hour, and then returned to neutral. Figure 3 shows the porous structure of evolved aerosol particles collected from the chamber.

Fig 2. Evolution with of (a) Total number concentration and Geometric mean (GM) (b) Charge/particle of PTAG generated particles

The density of the aerosol particle was theoretically estimated from the mobility diameter and aerodynamic diameter given by SMPS and ELPI respectively. The aerosol particles after around 3 hours were found to have a density of around 0.5 g/cc , suggesting the porous nature of the evolved particle.

CONCLUSION

Experiments were carried out in NATF to simulate the aerosol dynamics in containment after the severe nuclear accident conditions. Aerosols were generated using PTAG and measured using SMPS and ELPI. Experimental data of ELPI and SMPS was analyzed for the charge, number, size and density information of the particle inside the chamber. The number concentration at the inlet reached up to 108 particles/cc and GM changed from from ~ 40 nm

to ~300 nm as they travelled from the inlet side to the chamber due to coagulation. When the plasma torch was ON, the charge per particle reached up to +35 for particles of 1.2 μm size, then decreased. After 1 hour, the charge per particle for 0.12 μm aerosols turned negative, stayed negative for the next hour, and then returned to neutral.

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A RECENT STUDY OF ATMOSPHERIC CONCENTRATION, FLUXES AND DRY DEPOSITION VELOCITY OF FALL OUT ²¹⁰Pb AEROSOLS AT A COASTAL SITE OF MUMBAI HARBOUR BAY

A. KUMAR¹, D.G. MISHRA²

¹Board of Research in Nuclear Sciences (BRNS) Secretariat, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai – 400085

²Environmental Monitoring and Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai – 400085

(Corresponding Author: E mail: ajaykls@barc.gov.in)

INTRODUCTION

Radionuclides introduced into the atmosphere undergo mixing and dispersing with the suspended particulate matter by various physicochemical processes. After a considerable period of time, the suspended particles (depending on particle size) settle down on the ground by wet and dry deposition processes. These deposition processes are very much influenced by many factors such as climatic conditions, wind speed, particle size distribution, surface structure, time since deposition etc (Fukuyama and Fujiwara, 2008) and play a determinant role in the mobility and bioavailability in soil systems through sorption processes. Hence, the present study is aimed at determining the radioactivity levels of ²¹⁰Pb in the atmospheric aerosols and evaluating their fluxes and deposition velocities to understand atmospheric transport processes and scavenging, using soil profile distribution method (indirect). ²¹⁰Pb (T_{1/2} = 22.3 years), a naturally occurring radioisotope, is a member of the ²³⁸U decay series and is continuously introduced into the environment by deposition from the atmosphere. Radioactive disequilibrium between ²¹⁰Pb and its precursor ²²⁶Ra arises through the mobility of the intermediate gaseous radionuclide ²²²Rn. A proportion of the ²²²Rn formed by ²²⁶Ra decay in continental soils diffuses into the atmosphere where it decays to ²¹⁰Pb (Appleby and Oldfield, 1992). This radionuclide is readily attached to airborne particulates and removed from the atmosphere both by wet and dry deposition.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

An extensive sampling of suspended particulate matter was carried out at a height of 20 m above the ground at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Mumbai, using high volume air sampler (HVS, Envirotech model, APM 460) with a Whatman glass fiber filter paper during the period of November, 2022 to February, 2022. The mean wind velocity was 7.2 km/h and the average relative humidity was 60 % during the periods. The collected weighed dust particles on glass fibre filter paper were broken into small pieces and transferred in a cylindrical acrylic container, sealed and kept for 30 days to allow for the in-growth of radon gas to achieve secular equilibrium between ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁴Pb and ²¹⁴Bi in the ²³⁸U decay chain. The activity levels of ²¹⁰Pb of aerosols were estimated directly by gamma transitions lines of energy 47.4 keV using N- type co-axial Gamma-ray spectrometry system (50% RE). The efficiency calibration was carried out using multi gamma-ray energy of uranium ore (U₃O₈) standard. The widely used method of determining the atmospherically derived ²¹⁰Pb is given by;

$$\Phi = \lambda(^{210}\text{Pb}) \times I \quad (1)$$

where Φ is the total flux (in Bqm-2.y-1) of the radionuclide to the earth's surface, λ is the ^{210}Pb decay constant (0.0311 y-1) and I is the ^{210}Pb inventory in soil, measured in Bqm-2.

The well-known equation for the deposition velocity (V_d in cms-1) is usually described

$$V_d = \frac{\Phi}{C_{air}} \quad (2)$$

where C_{air} is the atmospheric concentration of a radionuclide at the sampling site.

The total activity of ^{210}Pb in soil will include both the atmospherically derived unsupported ^{210}Pb and the supported ^{210}Pb derived from the in-situ decay of the parent ^{226}Ra under the assumption of secular equilibrium. The atmospherically derived unsupported ^{210}Pb is determined by subtracting the ^{226}Ra activity from the total ^{210}Pb activity.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The mass concentration of aerosols over the four months ranged from 278 to 409 μgm^{-3} with a mean value of $342 \pm 63 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ (CV: 18%). The mean activity concentration of ^{210}Pb in aerosols of study area worked out to be $1.28 \pm 0.162 \text{mBqm}^{-3}$ respectively. The average total deposited ^{210}Pb for the studied area was 5.17 kBqm-2 and correspondingly the mean atmospheric flux & the dry deposition velocity of ^{210}Pb were obtained to be 161 Bqm-2y-1 and 0.4 cms-1 respectively. Earlier studies have estimated the atmospheric flux of ^{210}Pb , in the range of 190 - 570 Bqm-2y-1, derived from the sediment cores of Mumbai Harbor Bay (Kumar et al. 2015). The mean global atmospheric flux and inventory of ^{210}Pb fallout was about 165 Bq m-2y-1 and 5.3 kBq m-2, respectively (Krishnaswami and Lal 1978). Appleby and Oldfield 1992, reported that the global average atmospheric flux value of 185 Bqm-2y-1.

CONCLUSIONS

The estimated values of atmospheric concentration, fluxes and dry deposition velocity of fallout ^{210}Pb aerosols are well within the reported values in the literature. These can be used as inputs in existing conceptual and numerical models and subsequently can be demonstrated for long-term transport processes in accidental releases of nuclear accidents. Furthermore, such data can be one of the key parameters, necessary for calculation of the inhalation dose to humans and the resuspension factor.

Table 1. Atmospheric Concentration, flux and dry deposition velocity of ^{210}Pb Aerosols

Month	Mass concentration of aerosols (μgm^{-3})	^{210}Pb (mBqm^{-3})	I (upto soil depth of 15 cm) (kBqm^{-2})	Φ ($\text{kBqm}^{-2}\text{y}^{-1}$)	V_d (cms^{-1})
November (10)	300 ± 36	1.31 ± 0.34 (0.98 - 1.72)	6.5 ± 0.35	206 ± 11	0.5
December (6)	278 ± 45	1.12 ± 0.48 (0.62 - 1.35)	1.1 ± 0.27	35 ± 8	0.1
January (8)	381 ± 28	1.50 ± 0.48 (1.25 - 1.85)	2.7 ± 0.34	95 ± 11	0.2

February (7)	409 ± 52	1.22 ± 0.35 (1.12 – 1.34)	10.4 ± 0.58	307 ± 14	0.8
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PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL STUDY OF CONDENSATIONAL BEHAVIOR OF IODINE ON AEROSOL PARTICLES

S. AHAMAD, MARIAM, M. JOSHI, A. NAKHWA, A. KHAN AND B.K. SAPRA

Radiological Physics & Advisory Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre,
Mumbai 400085, India

KEYWORDS: IODINE, Nuclear Accident, AEROSOL, Condensation.

INTRODUCTION

Radioiodine released to the environment after Fukushima accident and Chernobyl accidents were 408 PBq and 1760 PBq respectively (IRSN report, 2012). The removal rates for iodine depend on whether it is in an aerosol or in vapour form (Funke et al., 2012). The Presence of aerosols significantly affects the removal of radioactive iodine as the latter condenses on suspended aerosol particles and the subsequent transport, deposition and distribution will depend on the host aerosol's behaviour and ultimately affect the source term. The effect of existing aerosols on the behaviour of iodine vapours has been indicated in the state-of-the-art report on nuclear aerosols ((NEA/CSNI/R 2009). There is a need for sufficient vapor-aerosol interaction data. Therefore, this study was performed to carry out condensation of iodine on aerosol particles in lab scale set-up, including development of the required methodology for characterisation (Physical and chemical).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Preliminary experiments were done to develop a methodology for the generation and measurement of iodine. Chemical characterization was done using UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Iodine was generated using chemical reaction (Dushman reaction) and sublimation process. For quantitative estimation of iodine using spectrophotometer, calibration curve was generated using iodide - iodine reaction. Main experiments were carried out in 0.5 m³ chamber equipped with a fan for homogenization. Aerosols generated by nebulization of 1% (w/v) NaCl were fed into the chamber and their number size distribution and number concentrations were monitored using a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS) (Fig 1). Once the steady state is achieved, SMPS was disconnected and iodine was inserted into the chamber. The sampling after the insertion was done using the filter paper gross sampler and bubbling system (1% Na₂CO₃) with 15 lpm and 3 lpm respectively. A methodology was established to analyze both the systems using spectrophotometer giving iodine condensed on aerosol and in gaseous form. The samples were digested to extract iodine

in aqueous solution as iodide. Since the calibration curves were generated for iodine, extracted aqueous iodide was converted to iodine using reaction mixture of KNO₂ and HCl.

Fig 1: Experimental set-up

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two sets of experiments were performed with an average mass concentration, number concentration and geometric mean as ~ 5 mg/m³, 5 * 10⁵ number/cc and 80 nm respectively. Fig 2 shows the calibration curve and

scanning plot for iodide-iodine reaction.

Fig 2 (a) scanning plot. (b) standard curve using UV-Vis spectrophotometer

The analysis showed iodine concentration on filter paper was around 2.5 ppb. Since filter paper only collects aerosol and is transparent to gases, the collected iodine has to be attached to aerosol which confirms the iodine condensation on aerosol. We estimated iodine concentration condensed on aerosol is the order of ~ 2.2 ppb and concentration estimated from bubbler is the order of ~ 3000 ppb (Fig 3)

Fig 3: Iodine concentration measured in aerosol form and aerosol + gas form

CONCLUSION

Iodine generation by sublimation and chemical reaction (Dushman reaction) was standardized. Calibration curve using iodide-iodine reaction for the estimation of iodine using spectrophotometer were generated. A methodology was established to analyze measured samples using spectrophotometer giving iodine condensed on aerosol and in gaseous form. Iodine concentration on filter paper was found to be ≈ 2.5 ppb, confirming condensation of iodine on aerosols. The understanding of iodine condensation plays a pivotal role in predicting source terms, which in turn influences emergency response. It can also contribute to the Engineering Safety Features (ESF) design in nuclear reactors.

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We provide you with an innovative and customizable analyzer for environmental monitoring needs such as **MARGA** (Monitor for AeRosols and Gases in Ambient air) and **MARS** (Metrohm AeRosol Sampler). Metrohm MARS in combination with IC or VA enables semi-continuous air monitoring at a high temporal resolution. The 2060 MARGA uses ion chromatography to monitor air quality by measuring the concentration of water-soluble gases and aerosols in air containing different sizes of particulate matter.

CORPORATE OFFICE:
Metrohm India Private Limited
"Metrohm-SIRI" Towers, 3&4, Fourrts Avenue, Annai Indira Nagar
Okkiyam, Thoraipakkam, Chennai - 600096, India
Phone: 044 40440440 | Email: info@metrohm.in

 Metrohm
India Private Ltd.

NEW PRODUCT FROM ENVIROTECH BIO AEROSOL SAMPLER

Six Stage Bio Aerosol Sampler

Glass fibre Filters
90 mm dia

Borosil Glass Petri
dishes 94 mm dia

Pump Assembly

- Ideal for collection of viable & non-viable aerosols
- Multi orifice cascade impactor allows measure of particle concentration and size distribution
- Particle collection on filter papers & viable bio-aerosols on Petri dishes filled with culture medium
- Supplied with complete sampling assembly

DESIGNED & DEVELOPED BY CSIR-NPL
MANUFACTURED INDIGENOUSLY BY ENVIROTECH

FOR PRICES AND ORDERING, PLEASE CONTACT
Envirotech Instruments Pvt. Ltd.

Pioneers & Leaders in Appropriate Indigenous instruments for monitoring Air Pollution & Air Quality
A-271, Okhla Industrial Area, Phase - I, New Delhi - 110 020, India.
Phone : +91-11-26814139, 26813887, 41026749, 26811833
Mobile : +91-98100 38803

E-mail : sales@envirotechindia.com ; sales.envirotech@gmail.com
Website : www.envirotechindia.com

	<p>POLLUTION EQUIPMENT & CONTROLS</p>	<p>A-3/4, Local Shopping Centre, Sanjeev Tower, Janakpuri, New Delhi – 110 058 Tel No : 011 – 44446860 - 69 Website : www.pecindia.com e-mail : pec@pecindia.com</p>
<p>Doppler Weather Radar Weather Station, Hydrology, Meteorology, Noise, Remote Sensing, Atmospheric Instruments.</p>		

We introduce ourselves as leading company engaged in the field various Environmental, Atmospheric Process Instrumentation, Air and Noise. Doppler Weather Radar , Lightning Detection Network and various other turnkey projects for over 40 years and following are our current range of products:--

AUTOMATIC WEATHER STATION :

Weather Station for general Meteorology, Agriculture, Marine, Airport, wind energy etc.

Sensors: Wind speed, Wind Direction, Barometric Pressure, Relative Humidity, Air Temperature, Pyranometer, Net/Albedo, Rainfall, Surface Wetness, Soil Temperature, Soil Moisture, with Data Logger, solar power panel with battery for unattended operation with varied communication options available. Suitable Mast with mounting sensors accessories.

SOLID STATE ANEMOMETER : Solid State Automatic Weather Station and Wind Speed and Director System with No Moving Parts For NBC , Military Vehicles , other applications.

POCKET WEATHER TRACKER:

Pocket Weather Tracker, with Tripod, wind Vane, USB interface.

LIDAR SYSTEM :

Backscatter Lidar. Raman Lidar, DIAL Ozone Aerosol Measurement. Customized Lidar are the speciality,

Micro pulse Lidar

DOPPLER WEATHER RADAR SYSTEMS : Doppler Weather Radar of 'X, C and S Band Solid State Technology, Klystron and Magnetron Transmission for Fixed and portable, application, customization solution can also be facilitated.

MICROWAVE RADIOMETER : Temperature, Humidity and vapour, PR series Radiometer for Soil with skycast solution, and for Thermodynamic profiling.

WIND PROFILER : RAPTOR Radiometrics designs and manufactures a full line of Radar Wind Profilers (RWPs). Most RAPTOR systems can be customized for user requirements. Some of the standard configuration is Boundary Layer, XBS-T Troposphere, FBS-ST Troposphere/Stratosphere, height Resolution from 3 km to 20km depending on frequency and application.

UPPER AIR SOUNDING SYSTEM GPS BASED FOR MOVING PLATFORM AND FIXED LOCATIONS:

The DFM Radiosondes System, Ozone Sondes with complete Systems, Antenna, and Ground Station, in house developed Software, with Balloon Filling Unit for Land and Marine applications.

SODAR : Sodar's (Acoustic Wind Profilers) software resulting in the Minimized hardware and thus amazing reliability, Very light instruments allowing easy transportation, Very low power consumption, No post filtering needed which is a unique feature of our instruments, High data accuracy.

HYDROGEN GENERATOR : For filling Met Balloons, No Liquid Electrolyte Necessary, Zero maintenance with minimal spares required to maintain, needs only electricity and water.

METEOROLOGICAL BALLOONS : Meteorological Balloons of different variants.

SOUND LEVEL METER :

Integrating Sound Level Meter with Data logging, OLED Display , Class 1 and 2 range of Sound Level Meter with due approval from PTB, . LNE OPLUS ,ISO Certified, with full Octave Band confirming to latest IEC standards. Dose Badge and Intrinsically Safe Dose Badge with latest development of Octave Band integrated with dose badge. Airport Noise Monitoring Equipment. On site Print out facility , Also available the Calibration Facility for Noise Level Meter and Calibrators. Sound Level Meter also available with built in GPS facility.

LIGHTNING DETECTION SYSTEM :

Most Accurate Forecast for Weather Observation Measurement, Total Lightning Measurement, Alerting, forecasting, Visualization, Dangerous Thunderstorm Alert, Pol & Rad, Spheric Map etc.

SUN PHOTOMETER/ SKY RADIOMETER : Automatic Sun/Lunar Tracking Photometer has been designed and realized to be a very accurate sun photometer.

AUTOMATIC FOG SAMPLER : Fog water is collected with a sampler operating on the impactor principle. The air is sucked at a rate of rd. 125 m³/h through a twin nozzle behind.

AUTOMATIC PRECIPITATION CHEMISTRY SAMPLER : The precipitation sampler is used for the purpose of collecting the precipitation, depending of its configuration, in a large sample bottle.

Sky Imager : Day & Night Measurement of the Sky's features.

Drone System : for Meteorological Purpose

For More details on the other products and services please visit our web page www.pecindia.com

Thanking you.

Yours faithfully,

For **POLLUTION EQUIPMENT & CONTROLS**

AMAR JYOTI
9810092198

Company Overview

Aurasure is transforming environmental monitoring with cutting-edge AI and IoT solutions, tackling critical challenges with precision and innovation. Our mission is to empower individuals, policymakers, industries, institutions, and communities with accurate, real-time data to protect health, mitigate risks, and foster sustainable development.

From air quality monitoring and hyperlocal climate insights to early flood detection and advanced forecasting, Aurasure offers comprehensive solutions to address diverse environmental issues. By turning complex data into actionable insights, we aim to support proactive decision-making and drive impactful environmental management.

Our Products

Aurasure Infra
Environmental Monitoring Solution

Aurasure Trust
Real Time Flood Monitoring System

Aurasure Care
Indoor Air Quality Monitoring Device

Sensing

Air Flood Climate Heatwave Noise

Unlock real-time insights and precise data with IoT enabled sensors, delivering actionable intelligence for your operational needs.

Data Insights

Hotspot Mapping Forecast Data Data Scenarios Risk Models Early Warning

Access comprehensive analytics and customizable reports, empowering you with accurate, actionable data for strategic growth.

Clients & Partners

Honeywell

Google

Key Metrics

Total Number of Cities **150+**

Total Number of Devices **1K+**

Total Number of Data in Bn **2.5+**

Airshed Planning Professionals Private Limited.

Airshed ensures **exceptional quality** in every service provided.

Our team comprises **highly skilled and experienced professionals**.

Airshed is dedicated to providing **excellent customer support**.

Contact Details

- www.airshed.in | hr@airshed.in
- Plot 16, Mukherjee Vihar, Kalyanpur, Kanpur 208026
- +91 0512 298 555, +91 9044471242

About Us

Incorporated in October 2017, the objective of team AIRSHED is to provide expert advice on air pollution, impact assessment, and air quality management to industry, scientific institutions, local authorities, regulatory authorities, and policymakers. We, at AIRSHED, are drawn with a proven track record in the field of air pollution, research, and practice. Experienced in air quality the solutions are appropriate, reliable, and cost-effective. Airshed works exclusively to provide air-related environmental services which include source apportionment, air pollutant emission inventory, GHG emission inventory, ambient air quality monitoring, source monitoring, consulting/permitting, air pollution dispersion modeling, and air toxics risk assessment. Airshed provides monitoring solutions for Ambient Air Quality Monitoring, Source Monitoring, and Indoor Air Quality Monitoring.

Services

- Air Quality Assessment and Management Plan
- Air Pollutant Emission Inventory
- PM Speciation
- Source Apportionment Studies
- GHGs Emission Inventory
- Carbon Neutrality as per PAS 2060
- Air Dispersion Modeling
- Receptor Modeling
- Inhalation And Air Toxic Health Risk Assessment
- GIS-Based Pollutant Mapping
- Indoor Air Quality

IASTA National Aerosol Conference 2024

December 17-20, 2024

Doon University, Dehradun

Conference : Proceedings of IASTA - 2024